

Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of **basis operations** along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, S-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers, etc.** This paper brings **selfie numbers** with **triangular numbers** in reverse order of digits. The previous work of author [21] is up to 4-digits numbers. This work extends to 5-digits numbers. The work on digit's order in 5-digits numbers can be seen in author's work [32].

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1 Selfie Numbers

During past years, the author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. In past, these type of numbers were called **wild narcissistic numbers**. These can be obtained by use of **basis operations** along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, S-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers**, etc. This paper brings **selfie numbers** with **triangular numbers** in digit's order. The previous work of author [21] is up to 4-digits numbers. This work extends to 5-digits numbers. The work on reverse order is given in a separate paper. Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** in different situations.

1.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13825} &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{14641} &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{15552} &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{16377} &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 \mathbf{23328} &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 \mathbf{116565} &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 \mathbf{131072} &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 \mathbf{147419} &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{147429} &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{147491} &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{156252} &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

1.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1463} &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & \mathbf{361469} &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{10077} &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & \mathbf{364292} &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 \mathbf{40585} &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & \mathbf{397584} &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 \mathbf{80518} &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & \mathbf{398173} &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 \mathbf{317489} &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & \mathbf{408937} &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 \mathbf{352797} &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & \mathbf{715799} &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357592} &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & \mathbf{720599} &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357941} &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \end{aligned}$$

1.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9} / 6 &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\ 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\ 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7. \end{aligned}$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer [14, 15].

1.4 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence values are well know in the literature. The general formula to write **Fibonacci sequence** [10] is given by

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1. \tag{1}$$

In particular,

$$F(1) = 1, F(2) = 1, F(3) = 2, F(4) = 3, F(5) = 5, F(6) = 8, \text{ etc.}$$

The examples given in subsections, 3.3 and 3.4 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. While the subsection 3.2 brings values just with basic operations. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} 235 &:= 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\ 256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\ 4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 &:= F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\ 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 &:= 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [22]. In [22], the author included the results with **factorial** too.

1.5 Triangle Numbers

According to equation (1) the triangular numbers are give by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$$

$$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$$

$$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$$

$$4999 := 49 + T(99)$$

$$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$$

$$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$$

$$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$$

$$0105 := 50 + T(10)$$

$$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$$

$$1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$$

$$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$$

$$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [20]. For **simultaneous selfie numbers** with **Fibonacci** and **Triangular numbers** see the author's work [25].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal values**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

1. Selfie numbers with **Basic Operations**: [14, 15, 16, 30];
2. Selfie numbers with **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. Selfie numbers with **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. Selfie numbers with **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**: [23];
6. Selfie numbers with **Triangular numbers**: [21, 31]; This work extends to 5-digits numbers in reverse order of digits.
7. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci and Triangular numbers**: [24];
8. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
9. Selfie numbers with **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
10. Selfie numbers with **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
11. Selfie numbers with **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
12. Selfie numbers with **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
13. Selfie numbers with **Cubic numbers**: [29];
14. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients and Fibonacci sequence**: [31];

The last Section 3 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with proper references.

The work on **triangular-type selfie numbers** given above in subsection 1.5 [21] is only up to 4-digits numbers. This work extend the same up to 5-digits numbers. Since there are lot of values, the work is divided in two parts. One in **digit's order** and another in **reverse order of digits**. The work in digit's order for 5-digits numbers is given in [31]. This work is up to 5-digit's numbers in reverse order of digits.

2 Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **triangular-type selfie numbers** in reverse order of digits up to 5-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsection. The first one give **symmetric** and **consecutive**, the second subsection give **symmetric** and **non-consecutive**. The third subsection give general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$120 := 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$121 := 1 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$122 := 2 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$123 := 3 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$124 := 4 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$125 := 5 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$126 := 6 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$127 := 8 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$128 := 9 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$129 := 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$210 := 0 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$211 := 1 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$212 := 2 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$213 := 3 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$214 := 4 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$215 := 5 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$216 := 6 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$217 := 7 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$218 := 8 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$219 := 9 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$990 := 0 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$991 := 1 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$992 := 2 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$993 := 3 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$994 := 4 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$995 := 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$996 := 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$997 := 7 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$998 := 8 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$999 := 9 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$0150 := 0 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0151 := 1 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0152 := 2 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0153 := 3 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0154 := 4 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0155 := 5 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0156 := 6 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0157 := 7 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0158 := 8 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0159 := 9 + T(5) \times 10$$

$$0190 := 0 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0191 := 1 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0192 := 2 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0193 := 3 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0194 := 4 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0195 := 5 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0196 := 6 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0197 := 7 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0198 := 8 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0199 := 9 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0210 := 0 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0211 := 1 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0212 := 2 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0213 := 3 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0214 := 4 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0215 := 5 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0216 := 6 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0217 := 7 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0218 := 8 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$0219 := 9 + 1 \times T(20)$$

$$1260 := 0 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1)$$

$$1261 := 1 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}1262 &:= 2 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1263 &:= 3 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1264 &:= 4 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1265 &:= 5 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1266 &:= 6 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1267 &:= 7 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1268 &:= 8 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\1269 &:= 9 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2))) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1540 &:= 0 + T(4 + 51) \\1541 &:= 1 + T(4 + 51) \\1542 &:= 2 + T(4 + 51) \\1543 &:= 3 + T(4 + 51) \\1544 &:= 4 + T(4 + 51) \\1545 &:= 5 + T(4 + 51) \\1546 &:= 6 + T(4 + 51) \\1547 &:= 7 + T(4 + 51) \\1548 &:= 8 + T(4 + 51) \\1549 &:= 9 + T(4 + 51)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1660 &:= 0 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1661 &:= 1 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1662 &:= 2 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1663 &:= 3 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1664 &:= 4 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1665 &:= 5 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1666 &:= 6 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1667 &:= 7 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1668 &:= 8 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\1669 &:= 9 - T(T(6)) + T(61)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1680 &:= 0 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1681 &:= 1 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1682 &:= 2 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1683 &:= 3 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1684 &:= 4 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1685 &:= 5 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1686 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1687 &:= 7 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\1688 &:= 8 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$1689 := 9 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}1740 &:= 0 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1741 &:= 1 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1742 &:= 2 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1743 &:= 3 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1744 &:= 4 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1745 &:= 5 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1746 &:= 6 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1747 &:= 7 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1748 &:= 8 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1) \\1749 &:= 9 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1770 &:= 0 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1771 &:= 1 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1772 &:= 2 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1773 &:= 3 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1774 &:= 4 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1775 &:= 5 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1776 &:= 6 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1777 &:= 7 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1778 &:= 8 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1) \\1779 &:= 9 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1830 &:= 0 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1831 &:= 1 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1832 &:= 2 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1833 &:= 3 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1834 &:= 4 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1835 &:= 5 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1836 &:= 6 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1837 &:= 7 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1838 &:= 8 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81) \\1839 &:= 9 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1980 &:= 0 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1981 &:= 1 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1982 &:= 2 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1983 &:= 3 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1984 &:= 4 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1985 &:= 5 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1986 &:= 6 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1987 &:= 7 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1988 &:= 8 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\1989 &:= 9 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2080 &:= 0 + T(8^{02}) \\2081 &:= 1 + T(8^{02}) \\2082 &:= 2 + T(8^{02}) \\2083 &:= 3 + T(8^{02}) \\2084 &:= 4 + T(8^{02}) \\2085 &:= 5 + T(8^{02}) \\2086 &:= 6 + T(8^{02}) \\2087 &:= 7 + T(8^{02}) \\2088 &:= 8 + T(8^{02}) \\2089 &:= 9 + T(8^{02})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2210 &:= 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2211 &:= 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2212 &:= 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2213 &:= 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2214 &:= 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2215 &:= 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2216 &:= 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2217 &:= 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2218 &:= 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\2219 &:= 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2310 &:= 0 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2311 &:= 1 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2312 &:= 2 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2313 &:= 3 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2314 &:= 4 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2315 &:= 5 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2316 &:= 6 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2317 &:= 7 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2318 &:= 8 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\2319 &:= 9 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2340 &:= 0 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2341 &:= 1 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2342 &:= 2 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2343 &:= 3 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2344 &:= 4 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2345 &:= 5 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2346 &:= 6 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2347 &:= 7 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2348 &:= 8 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\2349 &:= 9 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2520 &:= 0 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2521 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2522 &:= 2 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2523 &:= 3 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2524 &:= 4 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2525 &:= 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2526 &:= 6 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2527 &:= 7 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2528 &:= 8 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\2529 &:= 9 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2850 &:= 0 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2851 &:= 1 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2852 &:= 2 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2853 &:= 3 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2854 &:= 4 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2855 &:= 5 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2856 &:= 6 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2857 &:= 7 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2858 &:= 8 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\2859 &:= 9 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2940 &:= 0 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2941 &:= 1 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2942 &:= 2 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2943 &:= 3 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2944 &:= 4 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2945 &:= 5 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2946 &:= 6 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2947 &:= 7 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\2948 &:= 8 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2)\end{aligned}$$

$$2949 := 9 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2)$$

$$3150 := 0 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3151 := 1 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3152 := 2 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3153 := 3 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3154 := 4 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3155 := 5 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3156 := 6 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3157 := 7 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3158 := 8 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3159 := 9 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3240 := 0 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3241 := 1 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3242 := 2 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3243 := 3 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3244 := 4 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3245 := 5 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3246 := 6 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3247 := 7 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3248 := 8 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3249 := 9 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$3450 := 0 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3451 := 1 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3452 := 2 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3453 := 3 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3454 := 4 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3455 := 5 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3456 := 6 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3457 := 7 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3458 := 8 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3459 := 9 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$3570 := 0 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3571 := 1 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3572 := 2 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3573 := 3 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3574 := 4 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3575 := 5 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3576 := 6 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3577 := 7 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3578 := 8 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3579 := 9 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3))$$

$$3780 := 0 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3781 := 1 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3782 := 2 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3783 := 3 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3784 := 4 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3785 := 5 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3786 := 6 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3787 := 7 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3788 := 8 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$3789 := 9 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3)))$$

$$4140 := 0 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4141 := 1 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4142 := 2 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4143 := 3 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4144 := 4 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4145 := 5 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4146 := 6 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4147 := 7 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4148 := 8 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4149 := 9 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4)))$$

$$4190 := 0 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4191 := 1 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4192 := 2 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4193 := 3 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4194 := 4 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4195 := 5 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4196 := 6 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4197 := 7 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4198 := 8 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4199 := 9 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4270 := 0 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4271 &:= 1 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4272 &:= 2 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4273 &:= 3 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4274 &:= 4 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4275 &:= 5 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4276 &:= 6 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4277 &:= 7 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4278 &:= 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4279 &:= 9 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4290 &:= 0 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4291 &:= 1 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4292 &:= 2 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4293 &:= 3 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4294 &:= 4 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4295 &:= 5 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4296 &:= 6 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4297 &:= 7 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4298 &:= 8 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4299 &:= 9 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4560 &:= 0 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4561 &:= 1 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4562 &:= 2 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4563 &:= 3 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4564 &:= 4 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4565 &:= 5 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4566 &:= 6 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4567 &:= 7 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4568 &:= 8 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4569 &:= 9 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4620 &:= 0 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4621 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4622 &:= 2 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4623 &:= 3 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4624 &:= 4 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4625 &:= 5 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4626 &:= 6 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4627 &:= 7 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4628 &:= 8 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4629 &:= 9 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4650 &:= 0 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4651 &:= 1 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4652 &:= 2 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4653 &:= 3 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4654 &:= 4 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4655 &:= 5 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4656 &:= 6 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4657 &:= 7 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4658 &:= 8 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\ 4659 &:= 9 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4950 &:= 0 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4951 &:= 1 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4952 &:= 2 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4953 &:= 3 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4954 &:= 4 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4955 &:= 5 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4956 &:= 6 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4957 &:= 7 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4958 &:= 8 + T(5 + 94) \\ 4959 &:= 9 + T(5 + 94) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6930 &:= 0 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6931 &:= 1 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6932 &:= 2 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6933 &:= 3 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6934 &:= 4 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6935 &:= 5 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6936 &:= 6 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6937 &:= 7 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6938 &:= 8 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6939 &:= 9 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8280 &:= 0 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8281 &:= 1 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8282 &:= 2 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8283 &:= 3 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8284 &:= 4 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\8285 &:= 5 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\8286 &:= 6 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\8287 &:= 7 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\8288 &:= 8 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\8289 &:= 9 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8460 &:= 0 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8461 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8462 &:= 2 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8463 &:= 3 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8464 &:= 4 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8465 &:= 5 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8466 &:= 6 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8467 &:= 7 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8468 &:= 8 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\8469 &:= 9 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9240 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9241 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9242 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9243 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9244 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9245 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9246 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9247 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9248 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\9249 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9450 &:= 0 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9451 &:= 1 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9452 &:= 2 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9453 &:= 3 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9454 &:= 4 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9455 &:= 5 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9456 &:= 6 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9457 &:= 7 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9458 &:= 8 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\9459 &:= 9 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9)\end{aligned}$$

$$01090 := 0 + T(T(9)) + T(010)$$

$$\begin{aligned}01091 &:= 1 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01092 &:= 2 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01093 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01094 &:= 4 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01095 &:= 5 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01096 &:= 6 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01097 &:= 7 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01098 &:= 8 + T(T(9)) + T(010) \\01099 &:= 9 + T(T(9)) + T(010)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01250 &:= 0 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01251 &:= 1 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01252 &:= 2 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01253 &:= 3 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01254 &:= 4 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01255 &:= 5 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01256 &:= 6 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01257 &:= 7 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01258 &:= 8 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10 \\01259 &:= 9 + 5^{T(2)} \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01470 &:= 0 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01471 &:= 1 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01472 &:= 2 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01473 &:= 3 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01474 &:= 4 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01475 &:= 5 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01476 &:= 6 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01477 &:= 7 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01478 &:= 8 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10)) \\01479 &:= 9 - 7 \times T(4) + T(T(10))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01540 &:= 0 + T(45 + 10) \\01541 &:= 1 + T(45 + 10) \\01542 &:= 2 + T(45 + 10) \\01543 &:= 3 + T(45 + 10) \\01544 &:= 4 + T(45 + 10) \\01545 &:= 5 + T(45 + 10) \\01546 &:= 6 + T(45 + 10) \\01547 &:= 7 + T(45 + 10)\end{aligned}$$

$$01548 := 8 + T(45 + 10)$$

$$01549 := 9 + T(45 + 10)$$

$$01550 := 0 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01551 := 1 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01552 := 2 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01553 := 3 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01554 := 4 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01555 := 5 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01556 := 6 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01557 := 7 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01558 := 8 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01559 := 9 + T(55) + 10$$

$$01580 := 0 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01581 := 1 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01582 := 2 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01583 := 3 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01584 := 4 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01585 := 5 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01586 := 6 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01587 := 7 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01588 := 8 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01589 := 9 + 8 \times 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01590 := 0 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01591 := 1 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01592 := 2 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01593 := 3 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01594 := 4 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01595 := 5 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01596 := 6 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01597 := 7 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01598 := 8 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01599 := 9 + T(9) + 5 + T(T(10))$$

$$01650 := 0 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01651 := 1 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01652 := 2 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01653 := 3 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01654 := 4 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01655 := 5 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01656 := 6 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01657 := 7 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01658 := 8 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01659 := 9 + 5 \times 6 \times T(10)$$

$$01680 := 0 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01681 := 1 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01682 := 2 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01683 := 3 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01684 := 4 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01685 := 5 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01686 := 6 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01687 := 7 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01688 := 8 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01689 := 9 + 8 \times T(6) \times 10$$

$$01770 := 0 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01771 := 1 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01772 := 2 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01773 := 3 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01774 := 4 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01775 := 5 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01776 := 6 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01777 := 7 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01778 := 8 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01779 := 9 + T(7 \times 7 + 10)$$

$$01830 := 0 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01831 := 1 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01832 := 2 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01833 := 3 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01834 := 4 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01835 := 5 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01836 := 6 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01837 := 7 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01838 := 8 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$01839 := 9 + T(-3 + 8 + T(10))$$

$$02730 := 0 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02731 := 1 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02732 := 2 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02733 := 3 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02734 := 4 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02735 := 5 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02736 := 6 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02737 := 7 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02738 := 8 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$02739 := 9 + (T(3) + 7) \times T(20)$$

$$03150 := 0 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03151 := 1 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03152 := 2 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03153 := 3 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03154 := 4 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03155 := 5 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03156 := 6 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03157 := 7 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03158 := 8 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$03159 := 9 + T(T(5) - 1) \times 30$$

$$04920 := 0 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04921 := 1 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04922 := 2 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04923 := 3 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04924 := 4 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04925 := 5 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04926 := 6 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04927 := 7 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04928 := 8 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04929 := 9 + (-T(2) + 9) \times T(40)$$

$$04950 := 0 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04951 := 1 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04952 := 2 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04953 := 3 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04954 := 4 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04955 := 5 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04956 := 6 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04957 := 7 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04958 := 8 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04959 := 9 + T(59 + 40)$$

$$04990 := 0 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04991 := 1 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04992 := 2 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04993 := 3 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04994 := 4 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04995 := 5 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04996 := 6 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04997 := 7 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04998 := 8 + T(99) + 40$$

$$04999 := 9 + T(99) + 40$$

$$05970 := 0 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05971 := 1 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05972 := 2 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05973 := 3 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05974 := 4 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05975 := 5 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05976 := 6 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05977 := 7 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05978 := 8 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$05979 := 9 + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(50)$$

$$06540 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06541 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06542 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06543 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06544 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06545 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06546 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06547 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06548 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$06549 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 60$$

$$07350 := 0 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70$$

$$07351 := 1 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70$$

$$07352 := 2 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{07353} &:= 3 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07354} &:= 4 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07355} &:= 5 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07356} &:= 6 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07357} &:= 7 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07358} &:= 8 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \\ \mathbf{07359} &:= 9 + 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10620} &:= 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10621} &:= 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10622} &:= 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10623} &:= 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10624} &:= 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10625} &:= 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10626} &:= 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10627} &:= 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10628} &:= 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \\ \mathbf{10629} &:= 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(60 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12480} &:= 0 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12481} &:= 1 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12482} &:= 2 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12483} &:= 3 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12484} &:= 4 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12485} &:= 5 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12486} &:= 6 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12487} &:= 7 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12488} &:= 8 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{12489} &:= 9 + 8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12640} &:= 0 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12641} &:= 1 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12642} &:= 2 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12643} &:= 3 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12644} &:= 4 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12645} &:= 5 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12646} &:= 6 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12647} &:= 7 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12648} &:= 8 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \\ \mathbf{12649} &:= 9 + 4 \times T(T(6 \times 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13280} &:= 0 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13281} &:= 1 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13282} &:= 2 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13283} &:= 3 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13284} &:= 4 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13285} &:= 5 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13286} &:= 6 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13287} &:= 7 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13288} &:= 8 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13289} &:= 9 + (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13320} &:= 0 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13321} &:= 1 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13322} &:= 2 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13323} &:= 3 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13324} &:= 4 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13325} &:= 5 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13326} &:= 6 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13327} &:= 7 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13328} &:= 8 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13329} &:= 9 + T(T(2^3)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13340} &:= 0 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13341} &:= 1 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13342} &:= 2 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13343} &:= 3 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13344} &:= 4 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13345} &:= 5 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13346} &:= 6 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13347} &:= 7 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13348} &:= 8 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13349} &:= 9 + (T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13380} &:= 0 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13381} &:= 1 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13382} &:= 2 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13383} &:= 3 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13384} &:= 4 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13385} &:= 5 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \\ \mathbf{13386} &:= 6 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$13387 := 7 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)$$

$$13388 := 8 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)$$

$$13389 := 9 + (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)$$

$$13530 := 0 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13531 := 1 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13532 := 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13533 := 3 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13534 := 4 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13535 := 5 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13536 := 6 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13537 := 7 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13538 := 8 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13539 := 9 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$13860 := 0 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13861 := 1 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13862 := 2 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13863 := 3 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13864 := 4 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13865 := 5 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13866 := 6 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13867 := 7 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13868 := 8 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$13869 := 9 + (-6 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$$

$$14250 := 0 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14251 := 1 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14252 := 2 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14253 := 3 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14254 := 4 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14255 := 5 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14256 := 6 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14257 := 7 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14258 := 8 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14259 := 9 + 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14490 := 0 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14491 := 1 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14492 := 2 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14493 := 3 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14494 := 4 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14495 := 5 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14496 := 6 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14497 := 7 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14498 := 8 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14499 := 9 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$14590 := 0 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14591 := 1 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14592 := 2 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14593 := 3 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14594 := 4 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14595 := 5 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14596 := 6 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14597 := 7 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14598 := 8 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14599 := 9 - T(T(9)) + 5^{T(4-1)}$$

$$14640 := 0 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14641 := 1 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14642 := 2 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14643 := 3 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14644 := 4 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14645 := 5 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14646 := 6 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14647 := 7 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14648 := 8 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14649 := 9 + (-T(4) + T(6))^4 - 1$$

$$14850 := 0 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14851 := 1 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14852 := 2 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14853 := 3 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14854 := 4 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14855 := 5 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14856 := 6 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14857 := 7 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14858 := 8 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14859 := 9 + T(5) \times T(T(T(8)/4) - 1)$$

$$14940 := 0 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14941 := 1 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14942 := 2 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14943 := 3 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14944 := 4 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14945 := 5 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14946 := 6 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14947 := 7 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14948 := 8 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$14949 := 9 + T(4) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1))$$

$$15340 := 0 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15341 := 1 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15342 := 2 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15343 := 3 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15344 := 4 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15345 := 5 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15346 := 6 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15347 := 7 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15348 := 8 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15349 := 9 + (T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15400 := 0 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15401 := 1 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15402 := 2 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15403 := 3 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15404 := 4 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15405 := 5 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15406 := 6 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15407 := 7 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15408 := 8 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15409 := 9 + T(04) \times T(T(T(5 - 1)))$$

$$15410 := 0 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15411 := 1 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15412 := 2 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15413 := 3 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15414 := 4 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15415 := 5 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15416 := 6 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15417 := 7 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15418 := 8 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15419 := 9 + (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15420 := 0 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15421 := 1 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15422 := 2 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15423 := 3 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15424 := 4 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15425 := 5 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15426 := 6 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15427 := 7 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15428 := 8 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15429 := 9 + (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15430 := 0 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15431 := 1 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15432 := 2 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15433 := 3 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15434 := 4 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15435 := 5 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15436 := 6 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15437 := 7 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15438 := 8 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15439 := 9 + (3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15440 := 0 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15441 := 1 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15442 := 2 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15443 := 3 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15444 := 4 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15445 := 5 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15446 := 6 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15447 := 7 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15448 := 8 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15449 := 9 + (4 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15450 := 0 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15451 := 1 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15452 := 2 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15453 := 3 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15454 := 4 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15455 := 5 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15456 := 6 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15457 := 7 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15458 := 8 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15459 := 9 + (5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15460 := 0 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15461 := 1 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15462 := 2 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15463 := 3 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15464 := 4 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15465 := 5 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15466 := 6 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15467 := 7 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15468 := 8 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15469 := 9 + (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15470 := 0 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15471 := 1 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15472 := 2 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15473 := 3 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15474 := 4 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15475 := 5 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15476 := 6 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15477 := 7 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15478 := 8 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15479 := 9 + (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15480 := 0 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15481 := 1 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15482 := 2 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15483 := 3 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15484 := 4 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15485 := 5 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15486 := 6 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15487 := 7 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15488 := 8 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15489 := 9 + (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15490 := 0 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15491 := 1 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15492 := 2 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15493 := 3 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15494 := 4 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15495 := 5 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15496 := 6 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15497 := 7 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15498 := 8 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$15499 := 9 + (9 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5 - 1)$$

$$16380 := 0 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16381 := 1 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16382 := 2 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16383 := 3 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16384 := 4 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16385 := 5 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16386 := 6 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16387 := 7 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16388 := 8 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16389 := 9 + T(T(8) + 3) \times T(6 \times 1)$$

$$16740 := 0 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16741 := 1 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16742 := 2 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16743 := 3 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16744 := 4 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16745 := 5 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16746 := 6 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16747 := 7 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16748 := 8 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16749 := 9 + 4 \times (T(T(7 + 6)) - 1)$$

$$16790 := 0 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1)$$

$$16791 := 1 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1)$$

$$16792 := 2 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1)$$

$$16793 := 3 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}16794 &:= 4 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1) \\16795 &:= 5 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1) \\16796 &:= 6 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1) \\16797 &:= 7 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1) \\16798 &:= 8 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1) \\16799 &:= 9 + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16920 &:= 0 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16921 &:= 1 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16922 &:= 2 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16923 &:= 3 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16924 &:= 4 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16925 &:= 5 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16926 &:= 6 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16927 &:= 7 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16928 &:= 8 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1) \\16929 &:= 9 + T(2 + T(9)) \times T(6 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16940 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16941 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16942 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16943 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16944 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16945 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16946 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16947 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16948 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1) \\16949 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-9 + T(6) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17820 &:= 0 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17821 &:= 1 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17822 &:= 2 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17823 &:= 3 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17824 &:= 4 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17825 &:= 5 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17826 &:= 6 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17827 &:= 7 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17828 &:= 8 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1) \\17829 &:= 9 + (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18270 &:= 0 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18271 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18272 &:= 2 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18273 &:= 3 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18274 &:= 4 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18275 &:= 5 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18276 &:= 6 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18277 &:= 7 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18278 &:= 8 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1) \\18279 &:= 9 + T(T(7)) \times T(2 + 8 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18480 &:= 0 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18481 &:= 1 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18482 &:= 2 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18483 &:= 3 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18484 &:= 4 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18485 &:= 5 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18486 &:= 6 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18487 &:= 7 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18488 &:= 8 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1) \\18489 &:= 9 + T(8 \times 4) \times (T(8) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18630 &:= 0 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18631 &:= 1 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18632 &:= 2 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18633 &:= 3 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18634 &:= 4 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18635 &:= 5 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18636 &:= 6 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18637 &:= 7 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18638 &:= 8 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1)) \\18639 &:= 9 + 3 \times 6 \times T(T(8 + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20250 &:= 0 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20251 &:= 1 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20252 &:= 2 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20253 &:= 3 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20254 &:= 4 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20255 &:= 5 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02)) \\20256 &:= 6 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02))\end{aligned}$$

$$20257 := 7 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02))$$

$$20258 := 8 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02))$$

$$20259 := 9 + T(5)^{T(2)} \times T(T(02))$$

$$21390 := 0 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21391 := 1 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21392 := 2 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21393 := 3 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21394 := 4 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21395 := 5 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21396 := 6 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21397 := 7 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21398 := 8 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21399 := 9 + 93 \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))$$

$$21420 := 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21421 := 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21422 := 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21423 := 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21424 := 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21425 := 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21426 := 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21427 := 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21428 := 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21429 := 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(4 \times T(T(1+2)))$$

$$21450 := 0 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21451 := 1 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21452 := 2 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21453 := 3 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21454 := 4 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21455 := 5 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21456 := 6 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21457 := 7 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21458 := 8 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$21459 := 9 + 5 \times T(T(4)) \times T(12)$$

$$22050 := 0 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22051 := 1 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22052 := 2 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22053 := 3 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22054 := 4 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22055 := 5 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22056 := 6 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22057 := 7 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22058 := 8 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22059 := 9 + 50 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$22080 := 0 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22081 := 1 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22082 := 2 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22083 := 3 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22084 := 4 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22085 := 5 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22086 := 6 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22087 := 7 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22088 := 8 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22089 := 9 + 80 \times T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$22110 := 0 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22111 := 1 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22112 := 2 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22113 := 3 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22114 := 4 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22115 := 5 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22116 := 6 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22117 := 7 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22118 := 8 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22119 := 9 + T(T(11)) \times T(2+2)$$

$$22440 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22441 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22442 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22443 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22444 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22445 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22446 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22447 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22448 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$22449 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(4^2) \times T(2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22450 &:= 0 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22451 &:= 1 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22452 &:= 2 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22453 &:= 3 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22454 &:= 4 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22455 &:= 5 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22456 &:= 6 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22457 &:= 7 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22458 &:= 8 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \\ 22459 &:= 9 + T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22680 &:= 0 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22681 &:= 1 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22682 &:= 2 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22683 &:= 3 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22684 &:= 4 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22685 &:= 5 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22686 &:= 6 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22687 &:= 7 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22688 &:= 8 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \\ 22689 &:= 9 + T(8+6) \times T(T(2))^{T(2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22880 &:= 0 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22881 &:= 1 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22882 &:= 2 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22883 &:= 3 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22884 &:= 4 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22885 &:= 5 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22886 &:= 6 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22887 &:= 7 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22888 &:= 8 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 22889 &:= 9 + T(8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22890 &:= 0 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22891 &:= 1 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22892 &:= 2 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22893 &:= 3 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22894 &:= 4 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22895 &:= 5 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22896 &:= 6 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22897 &:= 7 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22898 &:= 8 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 22899 &:= 9 + (T(T(9)) + T(8+2)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23410 &:= 0 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23411 &:= 1 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23412 &:= 2 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23413 &:= 3 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23414 &:= 4 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23415 &:= 5 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23416 &:= 6 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23417 &:= 7 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23418 &:= 8 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \\ 23419 &:= 9 + 1 + T(-4 + T(T(3)))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23730 &:= 0 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23731 &:= 1 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23732 &:= 2 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23733 &:= 3 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23734 &:= 4 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23735 &:= 5 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23736 &:= 6 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23737 &:= 7 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23738 &:= 8 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23739 &:= 9 + (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7+T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23940 &:= 0 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23941 &:= 1 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23942 &:= 2 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23943 &:= 3 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23944 &:= 4 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23945 &:= 5 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23946 &:= 6 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23947 &:= 7 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23948 &:= 8 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23949 &:= 9 + T(T(4)+9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24250 &:= 0 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24251 &:= 1 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24252 &:= 2 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24253 &:= 3 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24254 &:= 4 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24255 &:= 5 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24256 &:= 6 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24257 &:= 7 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24258 &:= 8 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24259 &:= 9 - 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24360 &:= 0 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24361 &:= 1 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24362 &:= 2 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24363 &:= 3 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24364 &:= 4 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24365 &:= 5 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24366 &:= 6 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24367 &:= 7 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24368 &:= 8 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24369 &:= 9 + T(T(T(6)/3)) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24480 &:= 0 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24481 &:= 1 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24482 &:= 2 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24483 &:= 3 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24484 &:= 4 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24485 &:= 5 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24486 &:= 6 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24487 &:= 7 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24488 &:= 8 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 24489 &:= 9 + 8 \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24570 &:= 0 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24571 &:= 1 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24572 &:= 2 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24573 &:= 3 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24574 &:= 4 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24575 &:= 5 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24576 &:= 6 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24577 &:= 7 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24578 &:= 8 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$24579 := 9 + T(7 \times 5 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24720 &:= 0 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24721 &:= 1 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24722 &:= 2 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24723 &:= 3 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24724 &:= 4 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24725 &:= 5 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24726 &:= 6 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24727 &:= 7 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24728 &:= 8 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \\ 24729 &:= 9 + (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24960 &:= 0 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24961 &:= 1 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24962 &:= 2 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24963 &:= 3 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24964 &:= 4 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24965 &:= 5 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24966 &:= 6 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24967 &:= 7 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24968 &:= 8 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \\ 24969 &:= 9 + (T(6) - 9) \times T(4^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25290 &:= 0 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25291 &:= 1 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25292 &:= 2 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25293 &:= 3 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25294 &:= 4 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25295 &:= 5 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25296 &:= 6 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25297 &:= 7 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25298 &:= 8 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25299 &:= 9 + (T(T(9) \times 2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25350 &:= 0 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25351 &:= 1 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25352 &:= 2 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25353 &:= 3 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25354 &:= 4 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25355 &:= 5 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25356 &:= 6 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25357 &:= 7 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25358 &:= 8 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \\ 25359 &:= 9 + T(T(5) - 3) \times T(5^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25410 &:= 0 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25411 &:= 1 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25412 &:= 2 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25413 &:= 3 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25414 &:= 4 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25415 &:= 5 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25416 &:= 6 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25417 &:= 7 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25418 &:= 8 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25419 &:= 9 + (T(14) + 5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25420 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25421 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25422 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25423 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25424 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25425 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25426 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25427 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25428 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25429 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25620 &:= 0 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25621 &:= 1 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25622 &:= 2 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25623 &:= 3 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25624 &:= 4 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25625 &:= 5 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25626 &:= 6 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25627 &:= 7 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25628 &:= 8 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 25629 &:= 9 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25650 &:= 0 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25651 &:= 1 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25652 &:= 2 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25653 &:= 3 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25654 &:= 4 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25655 &:= 5 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25656 &:= 6 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25657 &:= 7 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25658 &:= 8 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \\ 25659 &:= 9 + (T(T(5)) - 6) \times T(5)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25740 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25741 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25742 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25743 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25744 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25745 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25746 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25747 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25748 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25749 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(7+5) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25840 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25841 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25842 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25843 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25844 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25845 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25846 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25847 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25848 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25849 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25880 &:= 0 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25881 &:= 1 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25882 &:= 2 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25883 &:= 3 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25884 &:= 4 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25885 &:= 5 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25886 &:= 6 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$25887 := 7 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25888 := 8 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25889 := 9 + 8 - (8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25950 := 0 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25951 := 1 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25952 := 2 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25953 := 3 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25954 := 4 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25955 := 5 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25956 := 6 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25957 := 7 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25958 := 8 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25959 := 9 - T(59) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25990 := 0 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25991 := 1 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25992 := 2 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25993 := 3 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25994 := 4 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25995 := 5 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25996 := 6 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25997 := 7 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25998 := 8 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$25999 := 9 + T(T(9))/9 \times (-5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26250 := 0 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26251 := 1 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26252 := 2 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26253 := 3 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26254 := 4 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26255 := 5 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26256 := 6 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26257 := 7 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26258 := 8 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26259 := 9 + 5^{T(2)} \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$26280 := 0 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26281 := 1 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26282 := 2 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26283 := 3 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26284 := 4 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26285 := 5 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26286 := 6 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26287 := 7 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26288 := 8 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26289 := 9 + T(T(8) \times 2) \times T(6 - 2)$$

$$26460 := 0 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26461 := 1 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26462 := 2 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26463 := 3 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26464 := 4 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26465 := 5 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26466 := 6 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26467 := 7 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26468 := 8 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26469 := 9 + 6 \times T(4) \times T(6)^2$$

$$26540 := 0 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26541 := 1 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26542 := 2 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26543 := 3 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26544 := 4 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26545 := 5 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26546 := 6 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26547 := 7 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26548 := 8 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26549 := 9 - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2))$$

$$26550 := 0 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26551 := 1 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26552 := 2 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26553 := 3 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26554 := 4 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26555 := 5 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26556 := 6 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26557 := 7 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26558 := 8 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$26559 := 9 + T(5) \times T(56 + T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26670 &:= 0 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26671 &:= 1 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26672 &:= 2 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26673 &:= 3 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26674 &:= 4 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26675 &:= 5 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26676 &:= 6 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26677 &:= 7 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26678 &:= 8 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26679 &:= 9 + (-T(T(7)) + T(6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26790 &:= 0 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26791 &:= 1 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26792 &:= 2 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26793 &:= 3 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26794 &:= 4 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26795 &:= 5 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26796 &:= 6 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26797 &:= 7 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26798 &:= 8 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 26799 &:= 9 + T(T(9) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27280 &:= 0 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27281 &:= 1 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27282 &:= 2 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27283 &:= 3 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27284 &:= 4 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27285 &:= 5 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27286 &:= 6 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27287 &:= 7 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27288 &:= 8 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 27289 &:= 9 + T(8+2) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27360 &:= 0 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27361 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27362 &:= 2 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27363 &:= 3 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27364 &:= 4 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27365 &:= 5 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27366 &:= 6 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27367 &:= 7 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27368 &:= 8 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27369 &:= 9 + (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(7-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27450 &:= 0 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27451 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27452 &:= 2 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27453 &:= 3 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27454 &:= 4 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27455 &:= 5 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27456 &:= 6 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27457 &:= 7 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27458 &:= 8 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \\ 27459 &:= 9 + T(5) \times T(4 \times T(7-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27720 &:= 0 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27721 &:= 1 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27722 &:= 2 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27723 &:= 3 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27724 &:= 4 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27725 &:= 5 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27726 &:= 6 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27727 &:= 7 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27728 &:= 8 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \\ 27729 &:= 9 + T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28050 &:= 0 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28051 &:= 1 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28052 &:= 2 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28053 &:= 3 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28054 &:= 4 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28055 &:= 5 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28056 &:= 6 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28057 &:= 7 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28058 &:= 8 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \\ 28059 &:= 9 + 50 \times T(T(8) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28080 &:= 0 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28081 &:= 1 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28082 &:= 2 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28083 &:= 3 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28084 &:= 4 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28085 &:= 5 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28086 &:= 6 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28087 &:= 7 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28088 &:= 8 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \\ 28089 &:= 9 + T(8) \times T(T(08) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28290 &:= 0 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28291 &:= 1 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28292 &:= 2 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28293 &:= 3 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28294 &:= 4 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28295 &:= 5 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28296 &:= 6 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28297 &:= 7 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28298 &:= 8 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \\ 28299 &:= 9 + T(T(9))/T(2) \times 82 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28710 &:= 0 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28711 &:= 1 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28712 &:= 2 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28713 &:= 3 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28714 &:= 4 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28715 &:= 5 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28716 &:= 6 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28717 &:= 7 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28718 &:= 8 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \\ 28719 &:= 9 + T(1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28890 &:= 0 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28891 &:= 1 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28892 &:= 2 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28893 &:= 3 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28894 &:= 4 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28895 &:= 5 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28896 &:= 6 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28897 &:= 7 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28898 &:= 8 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$28899 := 9 + (T(98) - T(8)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29250 &:= 0 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29251 &:= 1 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29252 &:= 2 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29253 &:= 3 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29254 &:= 4 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29255 &:= 5 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29256 &:= 6 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29257 &:= 7 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29258 &:= 8 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \\ 29259 &:= 9 + T(5^2) \times T(9) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29520 &:= 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29521 &:= 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29522 &:= 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29523 &:= 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29524 &:= 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29525 &:= 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29526 &:= 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29527 &:= 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29528 &:= 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29529 &:= 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29770 &:= 0 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29771 &:= 1 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29772 &:= 2 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29773 &:= 3 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29774 &:= 4 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29775 &:= 5 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29776 &:= 6 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29777 &:= 7 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29778 &:= 8 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \\ 29779 &:= 9 + T(7) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31250 &:= 0 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31251 &:= 1 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31252 &:= 2 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31253 &:= 3 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31254 &:= 4 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31255 &:= 5 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31256 &:= 6 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31257 &:= 7 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31258 &:= 8 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31259 &:= 9 + 5^{T(T(2))} \times (-1 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31280 &:= 0 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31281 &:= 1 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31282 &:= 2 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31283 &:= 3 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31284 &:= 4 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31285 &:= 5 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31286 &:= 6 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31287 &:= 7 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31288 &:= 8 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 31289 &:= 9 + T(8 \times 2) \times (-1 + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32340 &:= 0 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32341 &:= 1 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32342 &:= 2 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32343 &:= 3 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32344 &:= 4 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32345 &:= 5 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32346 &:= 6 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32347 &:= 7 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32348 &:= 8 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32349 &:= 9 + T(T(4 \times 3 - 2)) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32460 &:= 0 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32461 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32462 &:= 2 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32463 &:= 3 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32464 &:= 4 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32465 &:= 5 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32466 &:= 6 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32467 &:= 7 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32468 &:= 8 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \\ 32469 &:= 9 + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T((2 + 3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32480 &:= 0 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32481 &:= 1 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32482 &:= 2 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32483 &:= 3 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32484 &:= 4 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32485 &:= 5 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32486 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32487 &:= 7 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32488 &:= 8 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 32489 &:= 9 + 8 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32490 &:= 0 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32491 &:= 1 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32492 &:= 2 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32493 &:= 3 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32494 &:= 4 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32495 &:= 5 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32496 &:= 6 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32497 &:= 7 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32498 &:= 8 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32499 &:= 9 + T(9 + T(4)) \times T(T(2) \times T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32640 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32641 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32642 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32643 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32644 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32645 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32646 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32647 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32648 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32649 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(6) + T(T(2) + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33150 &:= 0 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33151 &:= 1 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33152 &:= 2 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33153 &:= 3 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33154 &:= 4 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33155 &:= 5 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33156 &:= 6 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33157 &:= 7 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33158 &:= 8 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33159 &:= 9 + T(5) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33540 &:= 0 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33541 &:= 1 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33542 &:= 2 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33543 &:= 3 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33544 &:= 4 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33545 &:= 5 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33546 &:= 6 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33547 &:= 7 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33548 &:= 8 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \\ 33549 &:= 9 + T(4) \times (T(5)^3 - T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34320 &:= 0 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34321 &:= 1 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34322 &:= 2 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34323 &:= 3 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34324 &:= 4 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34325 &:= 5 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34326 &:= 6 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34327 &:= 7 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34328 &:= 8 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34329 &:= 9 + T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34420 &:= 0 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34421 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34422 &:= 2 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34423 &:= 3 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34424 &:= 4 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34425 &:= 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34426 &:= 6 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34427 &:= 7 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34428 &:= 8 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \\ 34429 &:= 9 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34440 &:= 0 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34441 &:= 1 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34442 &:= 2 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34443 &:= 3 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34444 &:= 4 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34445 &:= 5 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34446 &:= 6 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34447 &:= 7 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34448 &:= 8 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34449 &:= 9 + (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34450 &:= 0 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34451 &:= 1 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34452 &:= 2 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34453 &:= 3 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34454 &:= 4 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34455 &:= 5 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34456 &:= 6 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34457 &:= 7 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34458 &:= 8 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34459 &:= 9 + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34540 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34541 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34542 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34543 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34544 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34545 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34546 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34547 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34548 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \\ 34549 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times (5^4 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34840 &:= 0 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34841 &:= 1 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34842 &:= 2 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34843 &:= 3 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34844 &:= 4 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34845 &:= 5 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34846 &:= 6 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34847 &:= 7 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \\ 34848 &:= 8 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$34849 := 9 + (4 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)$$

$$34860 := 0 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34861 := 1 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34862 := 2 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34863 := 3 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34864 := 4 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34865 := 5 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34866 := 6 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34867 := 7 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34868 := 8 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$34869 := 9 + (T(-T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35190 := 0 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35191 := 1 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35192 := 2 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35193 := 3 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35194 := 4 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35195 := 5 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35196 := 6 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35197 := 7 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35198 := 8 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35199 := 9 + T(T(9)) \times (T(T(-1 + 5)) - T(T(3)))$$

$$35280 := 0 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35281 := 1 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35282 := 2 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35283 := 3 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35284 := 4 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35285 := 5 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35286 := 6 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35287 := 7 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35288 := 8 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35289 := 9 + (8 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$35340 := 0 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35341 := 1 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35342 := 2 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35343 := 3 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35344 := 4 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35345 := 5 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35346 := 6 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35347 := 7 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35348 := 8 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35349 := 9 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 \times T(3))$$

$$35640 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35641 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35642 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35643 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35644 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35645 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35646 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35647 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35648 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35649 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 3$$

$$35750 := 0 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35751 := 1 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35752 := 2 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35753 := 3 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35754 := 4 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35755 := 5 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35756 := 6 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35757 := 7 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35758 := 8 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$35759 := 9 + (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5^3$$

$$36270 := 0 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36271 := 1 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36272 := 2 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36273 := 3 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36274 := 4 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36275 := 5 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36276 := 6 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36277 := 7 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36278 := 8 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36279 := 9 + T(T(7) + 2) \times T(6 + T(3))$$

$$36480 := 0 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4)) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36481 &:= 1 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36482 &:= 2 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36483 &:= 3 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36484 &:= 4 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36485 &:= 5 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36486 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36487 &:= 7 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36488 &:= 8 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36489 &:= 9 + 8 \times T(-T(T(4) + 6) + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36750 &:= 0 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36751 &:= 1 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36752 &:= 2 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36753 &:= 3 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36754 &:= 4 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36755 &:= 5 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36756 &:= 6 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36757 &:= 7 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36758 &:= 8 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ 36759 &:= 9 + 5 \times T(T(7) + T(6)) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36840 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36841 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36842 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36843 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36844 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36845 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36846 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36847 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36848 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 36849 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36990 &:= 0 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36991 &:= 1 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36992 &:= 2 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36993 &:= 3 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36994 &:= 4 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36995 &:= 5 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36996 &:= 6 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36997 &:= 7 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36998 &:= 8 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 36999 &:= 9 + (-T(9) + T(T(9)) \times 6) \times T(3) \\ 37260 &:= 0 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37261 &:= 1 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37262 &:= 2 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37263 &:= 3 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37264 &:= 4 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37265 &:= 5 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37266 &:= 6 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37267 &:= 7 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37268 &:= 8 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \\ 37269 &:= 9 + 6 \times T(T(2 + 7)) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38430 &:= 0 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38431 &:= 1 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38432 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38433 &:= 3 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38434 &:= 4 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38435 &:= 5 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38436 &:= 6 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38437 &:= 7 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38438 &:= 8 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \\ 38439 &:= 9 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times T(8 - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= 0 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38761 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38762 &:= 2 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38763 &:= 3 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38764 &:= 4 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38765 &:= 5 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38766 &:= 6 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38767 &:= 7 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38768 &:= 8 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 38769 &:= 9 + (T(T(6)) \times T(7) - 8) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38880 &:= 0 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3)) \\ 38881 &:= 1 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3)) \\ 38882 &:= 2 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3)) \\ 38883 &:= 3 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$38884 := 4 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38885 := 5 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38886 := 6 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38887 := 7 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38888 := 8 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38889 := 9 + T(8) \times T(8) \times (T(8) - T(3))$$

$$38910 := 0 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38911 := 1 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38912 := 2 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38913 := 3 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38914 := 4 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38915 := 5 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38916 := 6 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38917 := 7 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38918 := 8 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38919 := 9 + T(1 + T(9)) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$38940 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38941 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38942 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38943 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38944 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38945 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38946 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38947 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38948 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$38949 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)) - 3)$$

$$39270 := 0 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39271 := 1 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39272 := 2 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39273 := 3 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39274 := 4 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39275 := 5 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39276 := 6 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39277 := 7 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39278 := 8 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39279 := 9 + T(T(7) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(3)))$$

$$39330 := 0 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39331 := 1 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39332 := 2 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39333 := 3 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39334 := 4 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39335 := 5 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39336 := 6 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39337 := 7 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39338 := 8 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39339 := 9 + (T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(9)) / T(3)$$

$$39690 := 0 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39691 := 1 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39692 := 2 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39693 := 3 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39694 := 4 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39695 := 5 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39696 := 6 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39697 := 7 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39698 := 8 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39699 := 9 + T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - 3)$$

$$39840 := 0 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39841 := 1 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39842 := 2 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39843 := 3 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39844 := 4 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39845 := 5 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39846 := 6 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39847 := 7 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39848 := 8 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$39849 := 9 + T(4) \times (T(89) - T(T(3)))$$

$$40920 := 0 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40921 := 1 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40922 := 2 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40923 := 3 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40924 := 4 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40925 := 5 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40926 := 6 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40927 := 7 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40928 := 8 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40929 := 9 + (-T(2) + T(90)) \times T(4)$$

$$40940 := 0 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40941 := 1 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40942 := 2 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40943 := 3 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40944 := 4 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40945 := 5 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40946 := 6 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40947 := 7 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40948 := 8 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$40949 := 9 + T(4) \times T(90) - T(4)$$

$$41580 := 0 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41581 := 1 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41582 := 2 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41583 := 3 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41584 := 4 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41585 := 5 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41586 := 6 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41587 := 7 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41588 := 8 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41589 := 9 + T(8) \times T(5 + 1) \times T(T(4))$$

$$41850 := 0 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41851 := 1 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41852 := 2 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41853 := 3 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41854 := 4 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41855 := 5 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41856 := 6 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41857 := 7 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41858 := 8 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41859 := 9 + (T(T(5 + 8)) - 1) \times T(4)$$

$$41860 := 0 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41861 := 1 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41862 := 2 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41863 := 3 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41864 := 4 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41865 := 5 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41866 := 6 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41867 := 7 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41868 := 8 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41869 := 9 + T(T(6 + 8 - 1)) \times T(4)$$

$$41920 := 0 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41921 := 1 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41922 := 2 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41923 := 3 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41924 := 4 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41925 := 5 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41926 := 6 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41927 := 7 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41928 := 8 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$41929 := 9 + (T(T(2)) + T(91)) \times T(4)$$

$$42180 := 0 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42181 := 1 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42182 := 2 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42183 := 3 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42184 := 4 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42185 := 5 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42186 := 6 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42187 := 7 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42188 := 8 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42189 := 9 + T(T(8) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \times T(4)$$

$$42240 := 0 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42241 := 1 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42242 := 2 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42243 := 3 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42244 := 4 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42245 := 5 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42246 := 6 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42247 := 7 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42248 := 8 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$42249 := 9 + (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42750 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42751 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42752 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42753 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42754 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42755 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42756 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42757 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42758 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42759 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42770 &:= 0 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42771 &:= 1 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42772 &:= 2 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42773 &:= 3 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42774 &:= 4 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42775 &:= 5 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42776 &:= 6 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42777 &:= 7 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42778 &:= 8 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42779 &:= 9 - T(T(7)) + T(7) \times (2 + T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42780 &:= 0 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42781 &:= 1 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42782 &:= 2 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42783 &:= 3 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42784 &:= 4 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42785 &:= 5 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42786 &:= 6 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42787 &:= 7 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42788 &:= 8 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\ 42789 &:= 9 + T(8 + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42840 &:= 0 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42841 &:= 1 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42842 &:= 2 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42843 &:= 3 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42844 &:= 4 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42845 &:= 5 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42846 &:= 6 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42847 &:= 7 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42848 &:= 8 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \\ 42849 &:= 9 + (4 + 8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42900 &:= 0 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42901 &:= 1 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42902 &:= 2 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42903 &:= 3 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42904 &:= 4 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42905 &:= 5 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42906 &:= 6 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42907 &:= 7 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42908 &:= 8 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \\ 42909 &:= 9 + T(T(09) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42930 &:= 0 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42931 &:= 1 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42932 &:= 2 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42933 &:= 3 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42934 &:= 4 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42935 &:= 5 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42936 &:= 6 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42937 &:= 7 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42938 &:= 8 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \\ 42939 &:= 9 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(-2 + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43120 &:= 0 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43121 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43122 &:= 2 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43123 &:= 3 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43124 &:= 4 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43125 &:= 5 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43126 &:= 6 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43127 &:= 7 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43128 &:= 8 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\ 43129 &:= 9 + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(3) + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43540 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43541 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43542 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43543 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43544 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43545 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43546 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43547 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43548 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \\ 43549 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(3 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43920 &:= 0 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43921 &:= 1 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43922 &:= 2 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43923 &:= 3 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43924 &:= 4 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43925 &:= 5 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43926 &:= 6 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43927 &:= 7 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43928 &:= 8 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \\ 43929 &:= 9 + (-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3) \times T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44170 &:= 0 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44171 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44172 &:= 2 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44173 &:= 3 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44174 &:= 4 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44175 &:= 5 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44176 &:= 6 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44177 &:= 7 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44178 &:= 8 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 44179 &:= 9 + T(T(7)) \times T(14) + T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44220 &:= 0 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44221 &:= 1 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44222 &:= 2 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44223 &:= 3 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44224 &:= 4 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44225 &:= 5 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44226 &:= 6 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44227 &:= 7 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44228 &:= 8 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \\ 44229 &:= 9 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44250 &:= 0 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44251 &:= 1 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44252 &:= 2 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44253 &:= 3 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44254 &:= 4 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44255 &:= 5 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44256 &:= 6 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44257 &:= 7 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44258 &:= 8 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \\ 44259 &:= 9 + 5^2 \times T(4 + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44550 &:= 0 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44551 &:= 1 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44552 &:= 2 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44553 &:= 3 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44554 &:= 4 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44555 &:= 5 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44556 &:= 6 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44557 &:= 7 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44558 &:= 8 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \\ 44559 &:= 9 + T(T(5)) \times T(54)/4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44650 &:= 0 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44651 &:= 1 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44652 &:= 2 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44653 &:= 3 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44654 &:= 4 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44655 &:= 5 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44656 &:= 6 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44657 &:= 7 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44658 &:= 8 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \\ 44659 &:= 9 + (T(T(5) \times 6 + 4)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45360 &:= 0 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45361 &:= 1 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45362 &:= 2 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45363 &:= 3 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45364 &:= 4 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45365 &:= 5 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45366 &:= 6 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45367 &:= 7 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45368 &:= 8 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \\ 45369 &:= 9 + 6^3 \times T(5 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45430 &:= 0 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45431 &:= 1 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45432 &:= 2 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45433 &:= 3 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45434 &:= 4 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45435 &:= 5 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45436 &:= 6 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45437 &:= 7 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45438 &:= 8 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45439 &:= 9 + (T(3) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45930 &:= 0 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45931 &:= 1 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45932 &:= 2 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45933 &:= 3 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45934 &:= 4 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45935 &:= 5 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45936 &:= 6 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45937 &:= 7 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45938 &:= 8 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45939 &:= 9 + T(3) \times (-T(9) + 5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46380 &:= 0 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46381 &:= 1 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46382 &:= 2 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46383 &:= 3 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46384 &:= 4 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46385 &:= 5 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46386 &:= 6 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46387 &:= 7 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46388 &:= 8 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46389 &:= 9 + (T(8) - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$46530 := 0 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46531 &:= 1 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46532 &:= 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46533 &:= 3 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46534 &:= 4 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46535 &:= 5 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46536 &:= 6 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46537 &:= 7 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46538 &:= 8 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \\ 46539 &:= 9 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46560 &:= 0 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46561 &:= 1 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46562 &:= 2 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46563 &:= 3 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46564 &:= 4 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46565 &:= 5 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46566 &:= 6 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46567 &:= 7 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46568 &:= 8 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \\ 46569 &:= 9 + T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) \times (T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46640 &:= 0 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46641 &:= 1 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46642 &:= 2 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46643 &:= 3 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46644 &:= 4 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46645 &:= 5 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46646 &:= 6 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46647 &:= 7 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46648 &:= 8 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46649 &:= 9 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46830 &:= 0 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46831 &:= 1 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46832 &:= 2 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46833 &:= 3 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46834 &:= 4 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46835 &:= 5 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46836 &:= 6 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\ 46837 &:= 7 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$46838 := 8 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4)$$

$$46839 := 9 - T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4)$$

$$46980 := 0 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46981 := 1 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46982 := 2 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46983 := 3 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46984 := 4 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46985 := 5 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46986 := 6 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46987 := 7 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46988 := 8 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$46989 := 9 + T(8) \times (9 + 6^4)$$

$$47040 := 0 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47041 := 1 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47042 := 2 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47043 := 3 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47044 := 4 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47045 := 5 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47046 := 6 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47047 := 7 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47048 := 8 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47049 := 9 + 40 \times T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$47250 := 0 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47251 := 1 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47252 := 2 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47253 := 3 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47254 := 4 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47255 := 5 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47256 := 6 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47257 := 7 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47258 := 8 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47259 := 9 + 5^{T(2)} \times T(-T(7) + T(T(4)))$$

$$47520 := 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47521 := 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47522 := 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47523 := 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47524 := 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47525 := 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47526 := 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47527 := 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47528 := 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47529 := 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times T(7 + 4)$$

$$47530 := 0 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47531 := 1 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47532 := 2 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47533 := 3 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47534 := 4 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47535 := 5 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47536 := 6 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47537 := 7 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47538 := 8 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47539 := 9 + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 7) \times T(4)$$

$$47740 := 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47741 := 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47742 := 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47743 := 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47744 := 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47745 := 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47746 := 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47747 := 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47748 := 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47749 := 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (7 + T(7) - 4)$$

$$47880 := 0 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47881 := 1 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47882 := 2 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47883 := 3 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47884 := 4 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47885 := 5 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47886 := 6 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47887 := 7 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47888 := 8 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$47889 := 9 + T(8) \times (-T(-8 + T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48450 &:= 0 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48451 &:= 1 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48452 &:= 2 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48453 &:= 3 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48454 &:= 4 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48455 &:= 5 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48456 &:= 6 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48457 &:= 7 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48458 &:= 8 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 48459 &:= 9 + T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \\
 \\
 48520 &:= 0 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48521 &:= 1 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48522 &:= 2 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48523 &:= 3 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48524 &:= 4 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48525 &:= 5 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48526 &:= 6 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48527 &:= 7 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48528 &:= 8 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 48529 &:= 9 + (T(T(-2 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 48720 &:= 0 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48721 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48722 &:= 2 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48723 &:= 3 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48724 &:= 4 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48725 &:= 5 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48726 &:= 6 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48727 &:= 7 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48728 &:= 8 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 48729 &:= 9 + T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + 4) \\
 \\
 48840 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48841 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48842 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48843 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48844 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48845 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48846 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48847 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48848 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 48849 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))/T(T(T(8/4))) \\
 \\
 49280 &:= 0 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49281 &:= 1 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49282 &:= 2 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49283 &:= 3 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49284 &:= 4 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49285 &:= 5 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49286 &:= 6 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49287 &:= 7 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49288 &:= 8 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 49289 &:= 9 + T(T(8))^2/9 - 4 \\
 \\
 49570 &:= 0 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49571 &:= 1 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49572 &:= 2 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49573 &:= 3 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49574 &:= 4 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49575 &:= 5 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49576 &:= 6 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49577 &:= 7 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49578 &:= 8 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 49579 &:= 9 + T(7) \times T(59) + T(4) \\
 \\
 49780 &:= 0 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49781 &:= 1 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49782 &:= 2 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49783 &:= 3 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49784 &:= 4 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49785 &:= 5 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49786 &:= 6 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49787 &:= 7 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49788 &:= 8 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 49789 &:= 9 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 \\
 49830 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)) + 9) \times T(T(4)) \\
 49831 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)) + 9) \times T(T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49832 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49833 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49834 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49835 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49836 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49837 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49838 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49839 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8) + 9) \times T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49920 &:= 0 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49921 &:= 1 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49922 &:= 2 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49923 &:= 3 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49924 &:= 4 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49925 &:= 5 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49926 &:= 6 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49927 &:= 7 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49928 &:= 8 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49929 &:= 9 - (T(T(T(2))) - T(9) \times T(9 + T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49950 &:= 0 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49951 &:= 1 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49952 &:= 2 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49953 &:= 3 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49954 &:= 4 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49955 &:= 5 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49956 &:= 6 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49957 &:= 7 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49958 &:= 8 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \\ 49959 &:= 9 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(9 \times 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51840 &:= 0 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51841 &:= 1 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51842 &:= 2 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51843 &:= 3 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51844 &:= 4 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51845 &:= 5 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51846 &:= 6 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51847 &:= 7 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \\ 51848 &:= 8 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$51849 := 9 + T(T(4) \times 8) \times (1 + T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52290 &:= 0 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52291 &:= 1 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52292 &:= 2 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52293 &:= 3 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52294 &:= 4 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52295 &:= 5 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52296 &:= 6 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52297 &:= 7 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52298 &:= 8 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \\ 52299 &:= 9 + T(9^2 + 2) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52380 &:= 0 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52381 &:= 1 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52382 &:= 2 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52383 &:= 3 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52384 &:= 4 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52385 &:= 5 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52386 &:= 6 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52387 &:= 7 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52388 &:= 8 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 52389 &:= 9 + (T(83) + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52650 &:= 0 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52651 &:= 1 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52652 &:= 2 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52653 &:= 3 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52654 &:= 4 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52655 &:= 5 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52656 &:= 6 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52657 &:= 7 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52658 &:= 8 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 52659 &:= 9 + T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52680 &:= 0 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52681 &:= 1 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52682 &:= 2 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52683 &:= 3 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52684 &:= 4 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52685 &:= 5 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52686 &:= 6 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52687 &:= 7 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52688 &:= 8 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \\ 52689 &:= 9 - T(T(8)) + T(T(6))^2 - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52920 &:= 0 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52921 &:= 1 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52922 &:= 2 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52923 &:= 3 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52924 &:= 4 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52925 &:= 5 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52926 &:= 6 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52927 &:= 7 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52928 &:= 8 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 52929 &:= 9 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(2) \times T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53130 &:= 0 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53131 &:= 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53132 &:= 2 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53133 &:= 3 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53134 &:= 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53135 &:= 5 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53136 &:= 6 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53137 &:= 7 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53138 &:= 8 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53139 &:= 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times (-1 + T(T(3) + T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53220 &:= 0 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53221 &:= 1 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53222 &:= 2 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53223 &:= 3 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53224 &:= 4 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53225 &:= 5 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53226 &:= 6 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53227 &:= 7 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53228 &:= 8 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \\ 53229 &:= 9 + T(T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3)) - T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53280 &:= 0 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53281 &:= 1 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53282 &:= 2 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53283 &:= 3 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53284 &:= 4 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53285 &:= 5 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53286 &:= 6 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53287 &:= 7 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53288 &:= 8 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \\ 53289 &:= 9 + T(T(8)) \times 2/3 \times T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53340 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53341 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53342 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53343 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53344 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53345 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53346 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53347 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53348 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 53349 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(4))) + T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53460 &:= 0 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53461 &:= 1 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53462 &:= 2 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53463 &:= 3 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53464 &:= 4 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53465 &:= 5 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53466 &:= 6 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53467 &:= 7 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53468 &:= 8 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53469 &:= 9 + (T(T(6) \times 4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53550 &:= 0 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \\ 53551 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \\ 53552 &:= 2 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \\ 53553 &:= 3 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \\ 53554 &:= 4 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \\ 53555 &:= 5 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5))) - T(3 + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53556 &:= 6 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(3 + 5)) \\ 53557 &:= 7 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(3 + 5)) \\ 53558 &:= 8 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(3 + 5)) \\ 53559 &:= 9 + T(5) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(3 + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53640 &:= 0 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53641 &:= 1 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53642 &:= 2 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53643 &:= 3 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53644 &:= 4 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53645 &:= 5 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53646 &:= 6 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53647 &:= 7 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53648 &:= 8 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\ 53649 &:= 9 + (T(4 \times T(6)) + T(3)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53760 &:= 0 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53761 &:= 1 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53762 &:= 2 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53763 &:= 3 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53764 &:= 4 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53765 &:= 5 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53766 &:= 6 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53767 &:= 7 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53768 &:= 8 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 53769 &:= 9 + (T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54340 &:= 0 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54341 &:= 1 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54342 &:= 2 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54343 &:= 3 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54344 &:= 4 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54345 &:= 5 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54346 &:= 6 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54347 &:= 7 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54348 &:= 8 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \\ 54349 &:= 9 + (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54450 &:= 0 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54451 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54452 &:= 2 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54453 &:= 3 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54454 &:= 4 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54455 &:= 5 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54456 &:= 6 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54457 &:= 7 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54458 &:= 8 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54459 &:= 9 + T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54670 &:= 0 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54671 &:= 1 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54672 &:= 2 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54673 &:= 3 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54674 &:= 4 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54675 &:= 5 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54676 &:= 6 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54677 &:= 7 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54678 &:= 8 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54679 &:= 9 + (T(7) - 6) \times T(T(T(4)) + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55320 &:= 0 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55321 &:= 1 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55322 &:= 2 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55323 &:= 3 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55324 &:= 4 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55325 &:= 5 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55326 &:= 6 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55327 &:= 7 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55328 &:= 8 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \\ 55329 &:= 9 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55350 &:= 0 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55351 &:= 1 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55352 &:= 2 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55353 &:= 3 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55354 &:= 4 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55355 &:= 5 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55356 &:= 6 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55357 &:= 7 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \\ 55358 &:= 8 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$55359 := 9 + (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(5))$$

$$55440 := 0 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55441 := 1 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55442 := 2 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55443 := 3 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55444 := 4 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55445 := 5 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55446 := 6 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55447 := 7 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55448 := 8 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55449 := 9 + T(4 + 4) \times T(55)$$

$$55560 := 0 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55561 := 1 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55562 := 2 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55563 := 3 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55564 := 4 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55565 := 5 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55566 := 6 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55567 := 7 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55568 := 8 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55569 := 9 + T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))$$

$$55680 := 0 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55681 := 1 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55682 := 2 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55683 := 3 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55684 := 4 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55685 := 5 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55686 := 6 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55687 := 7 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55688 := 8 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55689 := 9 + T(T(8) - 6) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(5))$$

$$55920 := 0 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55921 := 1 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55922 := 2 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55923 := 3 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55924 := 4 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55925 := 5 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55926 := 6 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55927 := 7 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55928 := 8 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55929 := 9 + T(T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$55980 := 0 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55981 := 1 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55982 := 2 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55983 := 3 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55984 := 4 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55985 := 5 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55986 := 6 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55987 := 7 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55988 := 8 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$55989 := 9 + T(8) \times (T(T(T(9 - 5))) + T(5))$$

$$56520 := 0 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56521 := 1 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56522 := 2 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56523 := 3 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56524 := 4 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56525 := 5 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56526 := 6 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56527 := 7 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56528 := 8 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56529 := 9 + (2 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56640 := 0 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56641 := 1 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56642 := 2 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56643 := 3 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56644 := 4 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56645 := 5 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56646 := 6 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56647 := 7 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56648 := 8 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56649 := 9 + (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$56880 := 0 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56881 := 1 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56882 := 2 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56883 := 3 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56884 := 4 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56885 := 5 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56886 := 6 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56887 := 7 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56888 := 8 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$56889 := 9 + 8 \times (-T(T(8)) + 6^5)$$

$$57330 := 0 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57331 := 1 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57332 := 2 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57333 := 3 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57334 := 4 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57335 := 5 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57336 := 6 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57337 := 7 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57338 := 8 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57339 := 9 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(5)$$

$$57420 := 0 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57421 := 1 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57422 := 2 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57423 := 3 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57424 := 4 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57425 := 5 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57426 := 6 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57427 := 7 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57428 := 8 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57429 := 9 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(4+7)) \times T(5)$$

$$57960 := 0 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57961 := 1 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57962 := 2 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57963 := 3 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57964 := 4 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57965 := 5 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57966 := 6 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57967 := 7 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57968 := 8 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$57969 := 9 + 69 \times 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$58240 := 0 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58241 := 1 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58242 := 2 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58243 := 3 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58244 := 4 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58245 := 5 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58246 := 6 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58247 := 7 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58248 := 8 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58249 := 9 + T(4^{T(2)}) \times T(-8 + T(5))$$

$$58320 := 0 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58321 := 1 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58322 := 2 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58323 := 3 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58324 := 4 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58325 := 5 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58326 := 6 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58327 := 7 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58328 := 8 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58329 := 9 + (T(T(T(2))) + T(-T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))$$

$$58650 := 0 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58651 := 1 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58652 := 2 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58653 := 3 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58654 := 4 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58655 := 5 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58656 := 6 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58657 := 7 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58658 := 8 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58659 := 9 + 5 \times T(68) \times 5$$

$$58740 := 0 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5)$$

$$58741 := 1 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5)$$

$$58742 := 2 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5)$$

$$58743 := 3 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58744 &:= 4 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \\ 58745 &:= 5 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \\ 58746 &:= 6 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \\ 58747 &:= 7 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \\ 58748 &:= 8 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \\ 58749 &:= 9 + T((4+7) \times 8) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58830 &:= 0 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58831 &:= 1 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58832 &:= 2 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58833 &:= 3 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58834 &:= 4 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58835 &:= 5 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58836 &:= 6 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58837 &:= 7 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58838 &:= 8 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 58839 &:= 9 + (T(3) + T(88)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58950 &:= 0 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58951 &:= 1 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58952 &:= 2 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58953 &:= 3 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58954 &:= 4 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58955 &:= 5 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58956 &:= 6 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58957 &:= 7 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58958 &:= 8 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58959 &:= 9 + (T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59220 &:= 0 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59221 &:= 1 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59222 &:= 2 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59223 &:= 3 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59224 &:= 4 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59225 &:= 5 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59226 &:= 6 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59227 &:= 7 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59228 &:= 8 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \\ 59229 &:= 9 + T(T(2) \times T(T(2))) + 9^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59280 &:= 0 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59281 &:= 1 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59282 &:= 2 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59283 &:= 3 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59284 &:= 4 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59285 &:= 5 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59286 &:= 6 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59287 &:= 7 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59288 &:= 8 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \\ 59289 &:= 9 + T(T(8-2)) + 9^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59400 &:= 0 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59401 &:= 1 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59402 &:= 2 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59403 &:= 3 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59404 &:= 4 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59405 &:= 5 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59406 &:= 6 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59407 &:= 7 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59408 &:= 8 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \\ 59409 &:= 9 + T(T(04)) \times 9 \times T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59440 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59441 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59442 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59443 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59444 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59445 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59446 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59447 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59448 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \\ 59449 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59520 &:= 0 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59521 &:= 1 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59522 &:= 2 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59523 &:= 3 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59524 &:= 4 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59525 &:= 5 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59526 &:= 6 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5+9)) \times T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59527 &:= 7 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5 + 9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59528 &:= 8 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5 + 9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ 59529 &:= 9 + T(T(T(T(2))) + T(-5 + 9)) \times T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59790 &:= 0 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59791 &:= 1 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59792 &:= 2 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59793 &:= 3 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59794 &:= 4 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59795 &:= 5 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59796 &:= 6 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59797 &:= 7 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59798 &:= 8 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \\ 59799 &:= 9 + T(T(9) - 7) + 9^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59820 &:= 0 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59821 &:= 1 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59822 &:= 2 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59823 &:= 3 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59824 &:= 4 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59825 &:= 5 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59826 &:= 6 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59827 &:= 7 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59828 &:= 8 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 59829 &:= 9 + 2 \times T(T(8)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59840 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59841 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59842 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59843 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59844 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59845 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59846 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59847 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59848 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \\ 59849 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9 \times T(T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59850 &:= 0 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59851 &:= 1 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59852 &:= 2 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59853 &:= 3 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59854 &:= 4 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59855 &:= 5 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59856 &:= 6 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59857 &:= 7 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59858 &:= 8 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \\ 59859 &:= 9 + (-T(5) + T(89)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61620 &:= 0 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61621 &:= 1 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61622 &:= 2 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61623 &:= 3 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61624 &:= 4 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61625 &:= 5 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61626 &:= 6 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61627 &:= 7 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61628 &:= 8 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61629 &:= 9 + T(T(2 \times 6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62490 &:= 0 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62491 &:= 1 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62492 &:= 2 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62493 &:= 3 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62494 &:= 4 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62495 &:= 5 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62496 &:= 6 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62497 &:= 7 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62498 &:= 8 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \\ 62499 &:= 9 - T(T(9)) + T(T(4))^2 \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63140 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63141 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63142 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63143 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63144 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63145 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63146 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63147 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63148 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 63149 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 + T(T(3)) + T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63750 &:= 0 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63751 &:= 1 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63752 &:= 2 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63753 &:= 3 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63754 &:= 4 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63755 &:= 5 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63756 &:= 6 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63757 &:= 7 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63758 &:= 8 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \\ 63759 &:= 9 + T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64260 &:= 0 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64261 &:= 1 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64262 &:= 2 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64263 &:= 3 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64264 &:= 4 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64265 &:= 5 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64266 &:= 6 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64267 &:= 7 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64268 &:= 8 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \\ 64269 &:= 9 + 6 \times T(2) \times T(4 \times T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64680 &:= 0 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64681 &:= 1 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64682 &:= 2 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64683 &:= 3 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64684 &:= 4 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64685 &:= 5 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64686 &:= 6 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64687 &:= 7 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64688 &:= 8 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 64689 &:= 9 + T(8 \times 6) \times T(4 + 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64740 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64741 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64742 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64743 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64744 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64745 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64746 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64747 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64748 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 64749 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64890 &:= 0 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64891 &:= 1 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64892 &:= 2 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64893 &:= 3 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64894 &:= 4 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64895 &:= 5 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64896 &:= 6 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64897 &:= 7 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64898 &:= 8 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \\ 64899 &:= 9 + (9 + T(T(8 + 4))) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65520 &:= 0 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65521 &:= 1 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65522 &:= 2 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65523 &:= 3 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65524 &:= 4 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65525 &:= 5 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65526 &:= 6 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65527 &:= 7 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65528 &:= 8 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \\ 65529 &:= 9 + T(-2 + T(5)) \times T(T(5)) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66150 &:= 0 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66151 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66152 &:= 2 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66153 &:= 3 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66154 &:= 4 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66155 &:= 5 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66156 &:= 6 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66157 &:= 7 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66158 &:= 8 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \\ 66159 &:= 9 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(6)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68040 &:= 0 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68041 &:= 1 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68042 &:= 2 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68043 &:= 3 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68044 &:= 4 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68045 &:= 5 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68046 &:= 6 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68047 &:= 7 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68048 &:= 8 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \\ 68049 &:= 9 + T(T(4) \times 08) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69300 &:= 0 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69301 &:= 1 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69302 &:= 2 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69303 &:= 3 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69304 &:= 4 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69305 &:= 5 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69306 &:= 6 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69307 &:= 7 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69308 &:= 8 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 69309 &:= 9 + T(T(T(03))) \times T(T(9) - T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69390 &:= 0 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69391 &:= 1 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69392 &:= 2 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69393 &:= 3 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69394 &:= 4 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69395 &:= 5 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69396 &:= 6 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69397 &:= 7 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69398 &:= 8 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \\ 69399 &:= 9 + T(9)^3 - T(T(9)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 70560 &:= 0 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70561 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70562 &:= 2 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70563 &:= 3 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70564 &:= 4 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70565 &:= 5 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70566 &:= 6 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70567 &:= 7 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \\ 70568 &:= 8 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07) \end{aligned}$$

$$70569 := 9 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \times T(07)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72450 &:= 0 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72451 &:= 1 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72452 &:= 2 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72453 &:= 3 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72454 &:= 4 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72455 &:= 5 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72456 &:= 6 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72457 &:= 7 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72458 &:= 8 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\ 72459 &:= 9 + (T(5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72870 &:= 0 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72871 &:= 1 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72872 &:= 2 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72873 &:= 3 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72874 &:= 4 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72875 &:= 5 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72876 &:= 6 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72877 &:= 7 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72878 &:= 8 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \\ 72879 &:= 9 + (T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(2 \times 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72930 &:= 0 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72931 &:= 1 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72932 &:= 2 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72933 &:= 3 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72934 &:= 4 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72935 &:= 5 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72936 &:= 6 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72937 &:= 7 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72938 &:= 8 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \\ 72939 &:= 9 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(2) + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 73920 &:= 0 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7)) \\ 73921 &:= 1 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7)) \\ 73922 &:= 2 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7)) \\ 73923 &:= 3 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7)) \\ 73924 &:= 4 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$73925 := 5 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7))$$

$$73926 := 6 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7))$$

$$73927 := 7 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7))$$

$$73928 := 8 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7))$$

$$73929 := 9 + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(T(3 + 7))$$

$$74480 := 0 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74481 := 1 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74482 := 2 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74483 := 3 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74484 := 4 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74485 := 5 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74486 := 6 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74487 := 7 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74488 := 8 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74489 := 9 + (T(T(8)) \times 4 - 4) \times T(7)$$

$$74550 := 0 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74551 := 1 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74552 := 2 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74553 := 3 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74554 := 4 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74555 := 5 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74556 := 6 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74557 := 7 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74558 := 8 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74559 := 9 + (T(5) + T(5)) \times T(T(4) \times 7)$$

$$74880 := 0 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74881 := 1 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74882 := 2 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74883 := 3 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74884 := 4 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74885 := 5 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74886 := 6 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74887 := 7 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74888 := 8 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$74889 := 9 + T(8) \times T(T(8) + 4 \times 7)$$

$$75440 := 0 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75441 := 1 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75442 := 2 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75443 := 3 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75444 := 4 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75445 := 5 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75446 := 6 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75447 := 7 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75448 := 8 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$75449 := 9 + T(T(4) \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$76230 := 0 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76231 := 1 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76232 := 2 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76233 := 3 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76234 := 4 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76235 := 5 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76236 := 6 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76237 := 7 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76238 := 8 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$76239 := 9 - T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6))/7))$$

$$77140 := 0 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77141 := 1 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77142 := 2 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77143 := 3 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77144 := 4 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77145 := 5 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77146 := 6 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77147 := 7 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77148 := 8 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$77149 := 9 + T(-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$78540 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78541 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78542 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78543 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78544 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78545 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78546 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78547 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78548 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$78549 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$79540 := 0 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79541 := 1 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79542 := 2 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79543 := 3 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79544 := 4 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79545 := 5 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79546 := 6 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79547 := 7 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79548 := 8 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$79549 := 9 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times 97$$

$$82890 := 0 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82891 := 1 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82892 := 2 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82893 := 3 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82894 := 4 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82895 := 5 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82896 := 6 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82897 := 7 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82898 := 8 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$82899 := 9 + T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8))$$

$$83160 := 0 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83161 := 1 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83162 := 2 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83163 := 3 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83164 := 4 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83165 := 5 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83166 := 6 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83167 := 7 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83168 := 8 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83169 := 9 + T(T(6)) \times T(1+3) \times T(8)$$

$$83250 := 0 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83251 := 1 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83252 := 2 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83253 := 3 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83254 := 4 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83255 := 5 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83256 := 6 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83257 := 7 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83258 := 8 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$83259 := 9 + (T(5)/T(2))^3 \times T(T(8))$$

$$84260 := 0 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84261 := 1 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84262 := 2 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84263 := 3 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84264 := 4 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84265 := 5 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84266 := 6 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84267 := 7 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84268 := 8 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84269 := 9 + T(T(6-2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)$$

$$84960 := 0 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84961 := 1 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84962 := 2 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84963 := 3 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84964 := 4 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84965 := 5 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84966 := 6 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84967 := 7 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84968 := 8 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$84969 := 9 + (T(69) - T(T(4))) \times T(8)$$

$$85140 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85141 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85142 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85143 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85144 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85145 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85146 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85147 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85148 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$85149 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(-1+5))) + 8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 85260 &:= 0 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85261 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85262 &:= 2 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85263 &:= 3 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85264 &:= 4 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85265 &:= 5 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85266 &:= 6 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85267 &:= 7 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85268 &:= 8 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 85269 &:= 9 + (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 85280 &:= 0 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85281 &:= 1 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85282 &:= 2 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85283 &:= 3 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85284 &:= 4 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85285 &:= 5 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85286 &:= 6 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85287 &:= 7 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85288 &:= 8 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \\ 85289 &:= 9 + T(8^2) \times (5 + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 85920 &:= 0 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85921 &:= 1 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85922 &:= 2 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85923 &:= 3 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85924 &:= 4 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85925 &:= 5 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85926 &:= 6 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85927 &:= 7 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85928 &:= 8 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \\ 85929 &:= 9 + T(T(2)) + (9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86240 &:= 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86241 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86242 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86243 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86244 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86245 &:= 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86246 &:= 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86247 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86248 &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \\ 86249 &:= 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (2^6 - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87360 &:= 0 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87361 &:= 1 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87362 &:= 2 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87363 &:= 3 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87364 &:= 4 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87365 &:= 5 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87366 &:= 6 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87367 &:= 7 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87368 &:= 8 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \\ 87369 &:= 9 + (T(6) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87660 &:= 0 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87661 &:= 1 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87662 &:= 2 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87663 &:= 3 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87664 &:= 4 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87665 &:= 5 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87666 &:= 6 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87667 &:= 7 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87668 &:= 8 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \\ 87669 &:= 9 + 6 \times (-6 + T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88290 &:= 0 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88291 &:= 1 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88292 &:= 2 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88293 &:= 3 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88294 &:= 4 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88295 &:= 5 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88296 &:= 6 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88297 &:= 7 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88298 &:= 8 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 88299 &:= 9 + T(9) \times (T(2) \times T(T(8)) - T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89460 &:= 0 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89461 &:= 1 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89462 &:= 2 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89463 &:= 3 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89464 &:= 4 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89465 &:= 5 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89466 &:= 6 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89467 &:= 7 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89468 &:= 8 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \\ 89469 &:= 9 + T(T(6) + 49) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 91350 &:= 0 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91351 &:= 1 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91352 &:= 2 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91353 &:= 3 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91354 &:= 4 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91355 &:= 5 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91356 &:= 6 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91357 &:= 7 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91358 &:= 8 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \\ 91359 &:= 9 + 5 \times T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92430 &:= 0 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92431 &:= 1 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92432 &:= 2 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92433 &:= 3 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92434 &:= 4 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92435 &:= 5 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92436 &:= 6 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92437 &:= 7 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92438 &:= 8 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \\ 92439 &:= 9 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92730 &:= 0 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92731 &:= 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92732 &:= 2 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92733 &:= 3 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92734 &:= 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92735 &:= 5 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92736 &:= 6 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92737 &:= 7 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \\ 92738 &:= 8 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$92739 := 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93150 &:= 0 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93151 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93152 &:= 2 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93153 &:= 3 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93154 &:= 4 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93155 &:= 5 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93156 &:= 6 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93157 &:= 7 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93158 &:= 8 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 93159 &:= 9 + T(5) \times T(1 \times 3) \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93690 &:= 0 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93691 &:= 1 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93692 &:= 2 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93693 &:= 3 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93694 &:= 4 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93695 &:= 5 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93696 &:= 6 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93697 &:= 7 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93698 &:= 8 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \\ 93699 &:= 9 + (9 \times T(T(6)) + 3) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93870 &:= 0 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93871 &:= 1 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93872 &:= 2 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93873 &:= 3 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93874 &:= 4 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93875 &:= 5 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93876 &:= 6 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93877 &:= 7 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93878 &:= 8 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\ 93879 &:= 9 + (T(T(7) + T(8)) + T(3)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94240 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 94241 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 94242 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 94243 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 94244 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}94245 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\94246 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\94247 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\94248 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) \\94249 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}95220 &:= 0 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95221 &:= 1 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95222 &:= 2 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95223 &:= 3 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95224 &:= 4 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95225 &:= 5 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95226 &:= 6 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95227 &:= 7 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95228 &:= 8 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9)) \\95229 &:= 9 + (2 + T(T(2)) \times (T(5))) \times T(T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}95490 &:= 0 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95491 &:= 1 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95492 &:= 2 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95493 &:= 3 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95494 &:= 4 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95495 &:= 5 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95496 &:= 6 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95497 &:= 7 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95498 &:= 8 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9)) \\95499 &:= 9 + T(9) \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}95760 &:= 0 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95761 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95762 &:= 2 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95763 &:= 3 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95764 &:= 4 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95765 &:= 5 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95766 &:= 6 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95767 &:= 7 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95768 &:= 8 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9)) \\95769 &:= 9 + T(6) \times T(T(7) \times 5 - T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$96720 := 0 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}96721 &:= 1 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96722 &:= 2 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96723 &:= 3 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96724 &:= 4 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96725 &:= 5 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96726 &:= 6 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96727 &:= 7 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96728 &:= 8 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9) \\96729 &:= 9 + (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}97280 &:= 0 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97281 &:= 1 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97282 &:= 2 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97283 &:= 3 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97284 &:= 4 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97285 &:= 5 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97286 &:= 6 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97287 &:= 7 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97288 &:= 8 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9) \\97289 &:= 9 + 8^{T(2)} \times T(T(7) - 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}97290 &:= 0 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97291 &:= 1 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97292 &:= 2 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97293 &:= 3 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97294 &:= 4 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97295 &:= 5 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97296 &:= 6 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97297 &:= 7 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97298 &:= 8 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) \\97299 &:= 9 + (T(9 + 2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}99360 &:= 0 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99361 &:= 1 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99362 &:= 2 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99363 &:= 3 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99364 &:= 4 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99365 &:= 5 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99366 &:= 6 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9)) \\99367 &:= 7 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$99368 := 8 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9))$$

$$99369 := 9 + (T(T(6)) - 3 \times T(9)) \times T(T(9))$$

$$99450 := 0 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99451 := 1 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99452 := 2 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99453 := 3 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99454 := 4 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99455 := 5 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99456 := 6 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99457 := 7 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99458 := 8 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99459 := 9 + (T(T(T(5) - 4)) \times T(9) - T(9))$$

$$99540 := 0 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99541 := 1 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99542 := 2 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99543 := 3 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99544 := 4 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99545 := 5 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99546 := 6 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99547 := 7 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99548 := 8 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99549 := 9 + T(T(-4 + T(5))) \times T(9) + T(9)$$

$$99630 := 0 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99631 := 1 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99634 := 4 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99635 := 5 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99636 := 6 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99637 := 7 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99638 := 8 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99639 := 9 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

2.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive

$$0105 := 50 + T(10)$$

$$0127 := 72 + T(10)$$

$$0138 := 83 + T(10)$$

$$0369 := -96 + T(30)$$

$$0378 := -87 + T(30)$$

$$0387 := -78 + T(30)$$

$$0396 := -69 + T(30)$$

$$00123 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 100$$

$$00223 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 200$$

$$00323 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 300$$

$$00423 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 400$$

$$00523 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 500$$

$$00623 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 600$$

$$00723 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 700$$

$$00823 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 800$$

$$00923 := T(T(3)) + 2 + 900$$

$$00134 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 100$$

$$00234 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 200$$

$$00334 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 300$$

$$00434 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 400$$

$$00534 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 500$$

$$00634 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 600$$

$$00734 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 700$$

$$00834 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 800$$

$$00934 := T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) + 900$$

$$00149 := T(9) + 4 + 100$$

$$00249 := T(9) + 4 + 200$$

$$00349 := T(9) + 4 + 300$$

$$00449 := T(9) + 4 + 400$$

$$00549 := T(9) + 4 + 500$$

$$00649 := T(9) + 4 + 600$$

$$00749 := T(9) + 4 + 700$$

$$00849 := T(9) + 4 + 800$$

$$00949 := T(9) + 4 + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00139} := T(9) - T(3) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00239} := T(9) - T(3) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00339} := T(9) - T(3) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00439} := T(9) - T(3) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00539} := T(9) - T(3) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00639} := T(9) - T(3) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00739} := T(9) - T(3) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00839} := T(9) - T(3) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00939} := T(9) - T(3) + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00145} := T(5 + 4) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00245} := T(5 + 4) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00345} := T(5 + 4) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00445} := T(5 + 4) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00545} := T(5 + 4) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00645} := T(5 + 4) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00745} := T(5 + 4) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00845} := T(5 + 4) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00945} := T(5 + 4) + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00136} := 6 \times T(3) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00236} := 6 \times T(3) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00336} := 6 \times T(3) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00436} := 6 \times T(3) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00536} := 6 \times T(3) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00636} := 6 \times T(3) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00736} := 6 \times T(3) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00836} := 6 \times T(3) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00936} := 6 \times T(3) + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00163} := 3 \times T(6) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00263} := 3 \times T(6) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00363} := 3 \times T(6) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00463} := 3 \times T(6) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00563} := 3 \times T(6) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00663} := 3 \times T(6) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00763} := 3 \times T(6) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00863} := 3 \times T(6) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00963} := 3 \times T(6) + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00124} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00224} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00324} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00424} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00524} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00624} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00724} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00824} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00924} := 4 \times T(T(2)) + 900$$

$$\mathbf{00115} := T(5) + 1 \times 100$$

$$\mathbf{00215} := T(5) + 1 \times 200$$

$$\mathbf{00315} := T(5) + 1 \times 300$$

$$\mathbf{00415} := T(5) + 1 \times 400$$

$$\mathbf{00515} := T(5) + 1 \times 500$$

$$\mathbf{00615} := T(5) + 1 \times 600$$

$$\mathbf{00715} := T(5) + 1 \times 700$$

$$\mathbf{00815} := T(5) + 1 \times 800$$

$$\mathbf{00915} := T(5) + 1 \times 900$$

$$\mathbf{00121} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 100$$

$$\mathbf{00221} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 200$$

$$\mathbf{00321} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 300$$

$$\mathbf{00421} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 400$$

$$\mathbf{00521} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 500$$

$$\mathbf{00621} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 600$$

$$\mathbf{00721} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 700$$

$$\mathbf{00821} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 800$$

$$\mathbf{00921} := T(T(1 + 2)) + 900$$

2.3 General Representations: Up To Four Digits Numbers

$$\mathbf{15} := T(5) \times 1$$

$$\mathbf{21} := T(T(1 + 2))$$

$$\mathbf{23} := T(T(3)) + 2$$

$$\mathbf{24} := 4 \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) & 244 &:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 36 &:= 6 \times T(3) & 245 &:= 5 \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \\ 39 &:= T(9) - T(3) & 246 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(4)/2) \\ 45 &:= T(5+4) & 247 &:= T(T(7) + T(4))/T(2) \\ 49 &:= T(9) + 4 & 248 &:= 8 \times (T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 55 &:= T(5+5) & 252 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2 \\ 63 &:= 3 \times T(6) & 253 &:= T(-3 + 5^2) \\ 66 &:= T(T(T(6)))/T(6) & 254 &:= T(T(4)) \times 5 - T(T(T(2))) \\ & & 255 &:= T(5) \times (T(5) + 2) \\ 105 &:= T(T(5) - 01) & 256 &:= (T(6) - 5)^2 \\ 132 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + 1) & 264 &:= 4 \times T(T(T(6)))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 135 &:= T(T(5)) + T((T(3) - 1)) & 268 &:= -8 + T(T(6) + 2) \\ 136 &:= T(6 + T(3 + 1)) & 273 &:= T(T(3) + 7) \times T(2) \\ 147 &:= 7 \times T(T(4 - 1)) & 274 &:= T(4) \times T(7) - T(T(2)) \\ 152 &:= T(2 + T(5)) - 1 & 275 &:= 5 \times T(7 + T(2)) \\ 154 &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(5 - 1) & 276 &:= T(T(6)) + T(7 + 2) \\ 167 &:= T(7) \times 6 - 1 & 279 &:= 9 \times (T(7) + T(2)) \\ 168 &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) & 285 &:= -T(5) + T(8 \times T(2)) \\ 171 &:= T(17 + 1) & 286 &:= T(T(6)) + T(8 + 2) \\ 176 &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + 1 & 287 &:= 7 \times 8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 185 &:= 5 \times (T(8) + 1) & 294 &:= 49 \times T(T(2)) \\ 186 &:= T(T(6)) - T(8 + 1) & 295 &:= T(59)/T(T(2)) \\ 191 &:= T(19) + 1 & 315 &:= T(5) \times T(T(1 \times 3)) \\ 221 &:= -T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) & 324 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2)) - T(3) \\ 222 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) & 325 &:= T(5 \times (2 + 3)) \\ 223 &:= T(T(T(3))) - 2^{T(2)} & 336 &:= T(63)/T(3) \\ 224 &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) & 337 &:= 7^3 - T(3) \\ 225 &:= (5 \times T(2))^2 & 339 &:= T(T(9))/3 - T(3) \\ 226 &:= T(T(6)) - 2 - T(2) & 342 &:= (2 + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \\ 227 &:= -7 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) & 345 &:= T(T(5 + 4))/3 \\ 228 &:= (T(8) + 2) \times T(T(2)) & 346 &:= T(T(6) + 4) + T(T(3)) \\ 229 &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) - 2 & 348 &:= T(T(8) - T(4)) - 3 \\ 231 &:= T(T(1 \times 3 \times 2)) & 351 &:= T(1 \times 5 + T(T(3))) \\ 232 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2) & 355 &:= (5 + T(T(5))) \times 3 \\ 233 &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + 2 & 356 &:= T(T(6)) + 5^3 \\ 234 &:= T(4 \times 3) \times T(2) & 364 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(6)) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 236 &:= T(T(6)) + 3 + 2 & 369 &:= T(T(9)) - T(6 \times T(3)) \\ 237 &:= T(7 \times 3) + T(T(2)) & 372 &:= T(27) - T(3) \\ 241 &:= T(1 \times 4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) & 375 &:= T(5) \times (T(7) - 3) \\ 242 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2))) & 385 &:= (T(T(T(5) - 8)) - T(T(3))) \\ 243 &:= 3^4 \times T(2) & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 392 &:= T(T(2) + T(9))/3 \\ 396 &:= (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(3) \\ 399 &:= 9 \times T(9) - T(3) \\ 416 &:= T(T(6 + 1)) + T(4) \\ 417 &:= T(T(7)) + 1 + T(4) \\ 427 &:= T(T(7)) + T(2 + 4) \\ 433 &:= T(3^3) + T(T(4)) \\ 435 &:= T(-5 + 34) \\ 437 &:= -T(7) + T(3 \times T(4)) \\ 455 &:= T(T(5) + T(5)) - T(4) \\ 456 &:= (-6 + T(T(5))) \times 4 \\ 461 &:= T(T(1 + 6)) + T(T(4)) \\ 462 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(6 - 4)))) \\ 465 &:= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \\ 466 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + 4 \\ 467 &:= T(T(7)) + 6 + T(T(4)) \\ 469 &:= T(9 + T(6)) + 4 \\ 475 &:= T(5) \times T(7) + T(T(4)) \\ 485 &:= T(5) \times T(8) - T(T(4)) \\ 492 &:= -T(2) + 9 \times T(T(4)) \\ 496 &:= T(T(6) - T(9) + T(T(4))) \\ 497 &:= T(T(7)) + T(9 + 4) \\ 522 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(2^5) \\ 523 &:= T(32) + 5 \\ 524 &:= -4 + T(2^5) \\ 525 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5 \\ 526 &:= T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + T(T(5)) \\ 528 &:= T((8 - T(T(2)))^5) \\ 556 &:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times 5) \\ 561 &:= T(T(1 + 6) + 5) \\ 564 &:= 4 \times (T(6) + T(T(5))) \\ 572 &:= 2 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(5))) \\ 573 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(7) - T(5) \\ 576 &:= T((T(T(6))/7)) + T(5) \\ 637 &:= T(7 + T(T(3))) + T(T(6)) \\ 647 &:= T(T(7)) + T(4) + T(T(6)) \\ 658 &:= -8 + T(T(5) + T(6)) \\ 663 &:= -3 + T(6 \times 6) \\ 666 &:= T(-6 + T(6) + T(6)) \\ 672 &:= T(2) \times (-7 + T(T(6))) \\ 687 &:= T(T(7) + 8) + T(6) \\ 693 &:= (-T(3) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 696 &:= T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6)) \\ 697 &:= T(T(7) + 9) - 6 \\ 703 &:= T(30 + 7) \\ 722 &:= T(2)^{T(T(2))} - 7 \\ 728 &:= 8 \times T(T(T(2))) + 7 \\ 729 &:= 9^{T(T(T(2)))/7} \\ 735 &:= 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 7 \\ 741 &:= T(T(1 \times 4) + T(7)) \\ 756 &:= T(6) \times T(T(5) - 7) \\ 758 &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) - T(7) \\ 759 &:= T(T(9)) - T(-5 + T(7)) \\ 774 &:= -T(4) + T(7) \times T(7) \\ 777 &:= T(7) \times T(7) - 7 \\ 812 &:= 2 \times T(T(-1 + 8)) \\ 825 &:= T(5) \times T(2 + 8) \\ 826 &:= T(T(6)) + T(-2 + T(8)) \\ 842 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(8)) \\ 861 &:= T(-1 + 6 + T(8)) \\ 864 &:= 4 \times 6 \times T(8) \\ 867 &:= T(7 \times 6) - T(8) \\ 874 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(8)) \\ 882 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(8)) \\ 897 &:= T(T(T(T(-7 + 9)))) + T(T(8)) \\ 903 &:= T(-3 + T(09)) \\ 915 &:= -T(T(5)) \times 1 + T(T(9)) \\ 924 &:= 4 \times T(T(-T(2) + 9)) \\ 946 &:= T(-6 + 49) \\ 957 &:= -T(7 + 5) + T(T(9)) \\ 966 &:= T(6) + T(6) \times T(9) \\ 969 &:= T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9) \\ 972 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-7 + T(9)) \\ 977 &:= -T(T(7))/7 + T(T(9)) \\ 0122 &:= 2 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(10))) \\ 0124 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(2))) + 10) \\ 0128 &:= 8 \times (T(T(2)) + 10) \\ 0133 &:= -3 + T(T(3) + 10) \\ 0136 &:= T(6) \times T(3) + 10 \\ 0137 &:= -T(7) + 3 \times T(10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0143 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 4) - 10 \\ 0144 &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(4) - 10 \\ 0146 &:= T(6 + T(4)) + 10 \\ 0149 &:= 94 + T(10) \\ 0165 &:= T(5) \times (T(6) - 10) \\ 0182 &:= 2 \times (T(8) + T(10)) \\ 0184 &:= 4 \times (T(8) + 10) \\ 0189 &:= 9 \times T(T(T(-8 + 10))) \\ 0205 &:= -5 + T(020) \\ 0231 &:= T(1^3 + 20) \\ 0234 &:= 4 \times T(3) + T(20) \\ 0251 &:= T(T(1 + 5)) + 20 \\ 0253 &:= T(-3 + 5 + 20) \\ 0273 &:= 3 \times T(-7 + 20) \\ 0276 &:= T(T(6)/7 + 20) \\ 0288 &:= 8 \times T(8) + 2 \times 0 \\ 0296 &:= T(T(6)) + T(9) + 20 \\ 0297 &:= -T(7) + T(T(9) - 20) \\ 0351 &:= T(1 - 5 + 30) \\ 0355 &:= T(5 \times 5) + 30 \\ 0376 &:= T(T(6) + 7) - 30 \\ 0397 &:= T(T(7)) - 9 + 3 \times 0 \\ 0422 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 40 \\ 0425 &:= T(T(5) \times 2) - 40 \\ 0462 &:= 2 \times T(T(6 + 4 \times 0)) \\ 0465 &:= T(5 \times 6) + 4 \times 0 \\ 0467 &:= T(T(7)) + T(6) + 40 \\ 0493 &:= -3 + T(-9 + 40) \\ 0528 &:= T(82 - 50) \\ 0546 &:= T(T(6) + T(4)) + 50 \\ 0562 &:= 2 \times (T(T(6)) + 50) \\ 0568 &:= 8 \times (T(6) + 50) \\ 0579 &:= T(T(9)) - T(T(7)) - 50 \\ 0633 &:= 3 \times T(T(T(3))) - 60 \\ 0637 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3))) + 6 \times 0 \\ 0729 &:= 9^{T(2)} + 7 \times 0 \\ 0736 &:= T(6 \times T(3)) + 70 \\ 0763 &:= 3 \times T(T(6)) + 70 \\ 0823 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 2) - 80 \\ 0924 &:= 4 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9 \times 0 \\ 0945 &:= T(T(5 + 4)) - 90 \\ 0963 &:= 3 \times (T(T(6)) + 90) \\ 1024 &:= 4^{T(T(2))-01} \\ 1029 &:= T(T(9)) - T(2 + 01) \\ 1035 &:= T(T(5 + 3 + 01)) \\ 1036 &:= T(T(6 + 3)) + 01 \\ 1039 &:= T(T(9)) + 3 + 01 \\ 1081 &:= T(1 + T(8 + 01)) \\ 1122 &:= 2 \times T(T(2) \times 11) \\ 1125 &:= T(5)^{T(2)}/T(1 + 1) \\ 1128 &:= T(8 \times T(2 + 1) - 1) \\ 1129 &:= T(T(9) + 2) + 1 \times 1 \\ 1134 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3) + 1 \times 1)) \\ 1144 &:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))))) \\ 1147 &:= T(7) \times 41 - 1 \\ 1152 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 - T(1 + 1) \\ 1153 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 5 - 1 - 1 \\ 1154 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(5 + 1) - 1 \\ 1155 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5) \times T(1 + 1)) \\ 1156 &:= T(T(6)) \times 5 + 1 \times 1 \\ 1165 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) + 1 + 1) \\ 1174 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 7) - 1 - 1 \\ 1176 &:= T((6 \times ((7 + 1) \times 1))) \\ 1177 &:= T(7 \times 7 - 1) + 1 \\ 1182 &:= T(T(2)) + T(8 \times T(T(1 + 1))) \\ 1188 &:= T(8) \times (T(8) - T(1 + 1)) \\ 1197 &:= 7 \times T(9 \times (1 + 1)) \\ 1217 &:= T(T(7)) \times (1 + 2) - 1 \\ 1218 &:= T(T(8 - 1)) \times (2 + 1) \\ 1222 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \\ 1224 &:= T((T(4) - T(2))^2) - 1 \\ 1225 &:= T((5 + 2)^2 \times 1) \\ 1226 &:= T((T(6)/T(2))^2) + 1 \\ 1227 &:= T(7^2) + 2 \times 1 \\ 1235 &:= 5 \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \\ 1237 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(3))) \times T(2) + 1 \\ 1239 &:= T(T(9)) - T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1243 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\ 1245 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)) + 1)) \\ 1246 &:= T(6) + T(T(T(4)) - T(2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 1247** := $(T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times T(2) - 1$
1248 := $T(-8 + T(T(4))) + T(T((T(T(2)) - 1)))$
1249 := $T(T(9)) + 4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1$
1254 := $T(T(4) \times 5) - 21$
1259 := $T(9) \times T(5 + 2) - 1$
1272 := $-T(2) + T(7^2 + 1)$
1273 := $3 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2) + 1))$
1274 := $T(T(4) \times (7 - 2)) - 1$
1275 := $T(5 \times (7 + 2 + 1))$
1276 := $T(-6 + T(7) \times 2) + 1$
1288 := $-8 + T(8)^2 \times 1$
1291 := $T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1$
1295 := $T(T(5)) + T(T(9) + T(2)) - 1$
1296 := $6^{9/T(2)+1}$
1297 := $(-T(7) + T(T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 1$
1322 := $T(T(T(2))) \times T(2) \times T(T(3)) - 1$
1323 := $T(T(3)) \times (2^{T(3)} - 1)$
1324 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))^3 \times 1$
1325 := $T(T(5) + T(2^3)) - 1$
1326 := $T(6 + T(2^3 + 1))$
1327 := $T(T(7) + 23) + 1$
1328 := $(T(T(8)) - 2) \times (3 - 1)$
1329 := $T(T(9) + T(T(2))) + 3 \times 1$
1332 := $2 \times T(T(3 \times 3 - 1))$
1334 := $T(T(4) \times T(3)) - T(31)$
1337 := $T(7) - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3 + 1)))$
1338 := $(T(T(8)) + 3) \times (3 - 1)$
1342 := $(T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1)$
1343 := $T(T(3)) \times 4^3 - 1$
1345 := $T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(3 \times 1)$
1349 := $T(9) \times T(4) \times 3 - 1$
1356 := $(T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(3 \times 1)$
1359 := $9 \times (T(T(5)) + 31)$
1362 := $T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) - 3 - 1)$
1364 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(3 + 1))$
1365 := $T(5) \times T(6 + T(3) + 1)$
1366 := $6 \times T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) + 1$
1368 := $8 \times T(6 \times 3 \times 1)$
1369 := $-9 + T(T(6) + 31)$
1372 := $(T(T(T(2))) + T(7)) \times T(T(3) + 1)$
1374 := $T(T(4)) \times (T(7) - 3) - 1$
1377 := $T(7 \times 7 + 3) - 1$
1378 := $T(8 \times 7 - 3 - 1)$
1379 := $T(T(9)) + 7^3 + 1$
1384 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(8) - T(T(T(3) - 1))$
1385 := $T(-5 + 8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1$
1386 := $T(6) \times T(8 + 3 \times 1)$
1389 := $T(9) \times T(8) - T(T(T(3 \times 1)))$
1392 := $-T(2) + T(9) \times 31$
1396 := $T(T(6) + 9) \times 3 + 1$
1421 := $-T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$
1422 := $-T(T(T(2))) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1423 := $-T(T(T(3))) + T(2 + T(T(4))) + 1$
1424 := $-T(T(4)) - T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1425 := $-T(T(5) + T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$
1426 := $-6 + T(-2 + T(T(4))) + 1$
1427 := $-T(7)^2 + T(T(T(4) + 1))$
1428 := $-8 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$
1429 := $T(9 \times T(T(2))) - T(T(4)) - 1$
1431 := $T(13 \times 4 + 1)$
1432 := $T(-2 + T(T(3) + 4)) + 1$
1434 := $T(T(T(4)) - 3) + T(T(4)) + 1$
1435 := $T(53) + 4 \times 1$
1442 := $T(-2 + T(T(4))) + T(4) + 1$
1443 := $-T(T(T(3)) - 4) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$
1444 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 41$
1445 := $T(5) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1446 := $(T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(4 - 1)$
1447 := $-T(7) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1448 := $-T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 1$
1449 := $-T(9 + 4) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$
1452 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(54 - 1)$
1455 := $-T(5) - T(5) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1456 := $T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1)$
1457 := $T(7) + T(54 \times 1)$
1462 := $-T(2 \times 6) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$
1463 := $-T(T(3) + 6) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$
1464 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4 \times 1))$
1465 := $-T(T(5))/6 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1472 := $-T(T(2)) - 7 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$

- 1474** := $T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(4) + 1)$
1479 := $-T(T(9 - 7)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1482 := $T(T(2)) + T(8) \times 41$
1483 := $-T(T(3)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$
1484 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) - 1$
1485 := $T(5 + 8 + 41)$
1486 := $T(6 \times T(8)/4) + 1$
1487 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(8) + T(4 \times 1))$
1492 := $-2 + 9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1493 := $-3 - T(9) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$
1494 := $T(T(T(4))) + 9 - T(T(4 \times 1))$
1495 := $T(-5 + 9) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1496 := $T(6 \times 9) + T(4) + 1$
1497 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(4)) + 1$
1512 := $-T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1519 := $T(T(9 + 1)) - T(5 + 1)$
1522 := $-T(T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1524 := $T(T(T(4))) - 2^{5-1}$
1525 := $-T(5) + T(T(2 \times 5 \times 1))$
1526 := $T(T(T(6 - 2))) - T(5) + 1$
1527 := $-7 - T(T(2)) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1528 := $-T(8)/T(2) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1529 := $-9 - 2 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1532 := $-2^3 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1533 := $-T(T(3))/3 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1534 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(-3 + 5 + 1)$
1535 := $-5 + T(T(T(3) + 5 - 1))$
1536 := $T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) + T(51)$
1538 := $-8 + T(3) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1539 := $9 \times T(3 \times (5 + 1))$
1552 := $-T(2) + T(5) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1555 := $T(5) + T(55 \times 1)$
1556 := $T(6) - 5 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1557 := $T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) + T(51)$
1561 := $T(1 \times 6) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1563 := $T(3) + T(T(6)) + T(51)$
1564 := $T(T(T(4))) + 6 \times (5 - 1)$
1573 := $(T(3) + 7) \times (T(T(5)) + 1)$
1574 := $T(T(T(4))) + 7 \times 5 - 1$
1575 := $T(5) \times 7 \times T(5 \times 1)$
1576 := $T(6) \times 75 + 1$
1578 := $T(8) \times 7 + T(51)$
1579 := $-T(9) + T(T(7)) \times (5 - 1)$
1582 := $2^8 + T(51)$
1591 := $T(T(1 + 9)) + 51$
1593 := $-3 + T(T(T(9 - 5)) + 1)$
1594 := $T(T(T(4))) + 9 \times (5 + 1)$
1595 := $T(T(-5 + 9)) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1596 := $6 \times T(9) + T(51)$
1601 := $T(T(10)) + 61$
1616 := $T(T(6)) \times (1 + 6) - 1$
1617 := $7 \times T(T(1 \times 6 \times 1))$
1618 := $(8 - 1) \times T(T(6)) + 1$
1623 := $T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + 1)$
1624 := $4 \times T(T(2 + 6 - 1))$
1625 := $5 \times T(26 - 1)$
1637 := $7 \times (3 + T(T(6))) - 1$
1638 := $T(T(8)/3) \times T(6 \times 1)$
1639 := $T(9 + 3) \times T(6) + 1$
1645 := $5 \times (T(T(4)) \times 6 - 1)$
1647 := $(-T(7) + T(T(4))) \times 61$
1648 := $8 \times (-4 + T(T(6) - 1))$
1652 := $T(T(T(2) + 5) + T(6)) - 1$
1653 := $T(T(3 + 5) + T(6 \times 1))$
1654 := $T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) - 6 \times 1$
1656 := $6 \times T(-5 + T(6 + 1))$
1657 := $T(T(7) - 5) \times 6 + 1$
1675 := $T(57) + T(6) + 1$
1711 := $T(T(11) - 7 - 1)$
1712 := $T(2 \times (1 + T(7))) + 1$
1722 := $2 \times T(T(T(2)) \times 7 - 1)$
1724 := $T(T(T(4)) + 2) + 71$
1728 := $T(8)^{T(2)}/(T(7) - 1)$
1739 := $T(T(9)) + T(37) + 1$
1755 := $5 \times T(5 + T(7 - 1))$
1759 := $T(T(9) + T(5)) - 71$
1763 := $3 \times T(6) \times T(7) - 1$
1764 := $4 \times T(6) \times T(7 - 1)$
1769 := $T(T(9) + T(6) - 7) - 1$
1782 := $T(T(2) + 8) \times (T(7) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 1785 &:= T(5) \times (T(8+7) - 1) \\ 1823 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - T(2)) \times 8 - 1 \\ 1825 &:= -5 + T(-T(T(T(2)))) + 81 \\ 1826 &:= -T(6) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8 - 1 \\ 1827 &:= T(T(7))/2 \times (8+1) \\ 1829 &:= T(T(9) + T(-T(2) + 8)) - 1 \\ 1844 &:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(8-1))) \\ 1846 &:= T(6 + T(T(4))) - T(8+1) \\ 1847 &:= T(T(T(7-4))) \times 8 - 1 \\ 1848 &:= 8 \times T(T(T(-4+8-1))) \\ 1853 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(8)) - 1 \\ 1864 &:= 4 \times (T(-6 + T(8)) + 1) \\ 1875 &:= T(T(5)) \times 7 + T(T(8+1)) \\ 1876 &:= 67 \times T(8-1) \\ 1883 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 8 + T(8) - 1 \\ 1895 &:= 5 \times (T(-9 + T(8)) + 1) \\ 1896 &:= T(T(6)) + T(9) \times (T(8) + 1) \\ 1911 &:= T(T(T(1+1))) \times 91 \\ 1922 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) - T(T(9) + 1) \\ 1925 &:= T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9+1)) \\ 1928 &:= 8 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9 + 1) \\ 1932 &:= 2 \times T(T(3)) \times (T(9) + 1) \\ 1934 &:= 43 \times T(9) - 1 \\ 1937 &:= T(7 \times T(3)) + T(T(9)) - 1 \\ 1938 &:= T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(T(9 \times 1)) \\ 1939 &:= T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9)) + 1 \\ 1944 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(9) + 1) \\ 1946 &:= T(6 + T(T(4))) + T(9+1) \\ 1947 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(4) + T(9)) + 1 \\ 1952 &:= T(T(2) + 59) - 1 \\ 1953 &:= T(3 + 59 \times 1) \\ 1967 &:= T(T(7)) + T(6) + T(T(9+1)) \\ 1975 &:= 5 \times T(T(7)) - T(9+1) \\ 1978 &:= (T(8) + 7) \times (T(9) + 1) \\ 1992 &:= T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) + T(T(9-1)) \\ 1995 &:= T(5) + T(9) \times (T(9) - 1) \\ 1997 &:= -T(7) + T(9) \times T(9 \times 1) \\ 1998 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(9/9+1) \\ 2016 &:= T(61+02) \\ 2018 &:= T(8 + T(10)) + 2 \\ 2022 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(02)))) \\ 2025 &:= (T(5) \times T(2))^{02} \\ 2061 &:= T(1 \times 60) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2063 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(60) + 2 \\ 2075 &:= -5 + T(70 - T(T(2))) \\ 2077 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(70) - 2 \\ 2078 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) - 02 \\ 2079 &:= 9 \times T(7 \times T(02)) \\ 2122 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)) + T(T(1 + T(2)))) \\ 2124 &:= T(4^{T(2)} + 1) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 2133 &:= T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) - T(12) \\ 2135 &:= 5 \times (T(T(T(3) + 1)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2136 &:= T(63) + T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \\ 2139 &:= T(93 - 1)/2 \\ 2142 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4)) + T(1 + T(2))) \\ 2143 &:= T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) - 1) - 2 \\ 2144 &:= T(T(4) + T(T(4))) - 1^2 \\ 2145 &:= T(5 \times (T(4) \times 1 + T(2))) \\ 2147 &:= T(T(7+4) - 1) + 2 \\ 2148 &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) - T(2) \\ 2156 &:= T(T(6+5)) - T(T(1 + T(2))) \\ 2162 &:= T(T(T(2) + 6) + 1) \times 2 \\ 2164 &:= (T(46) + 1) \times 2 \\ 2166 &:= T(66 - 1) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 2169 &:= 9 \times (T(T(6)) + T(1 + T(2))) \\ 2172 &:= T(2)^7 - T(-1 + T(T(2))) \\ 2174 &:= -T(4) + T(7) \times T(12) \\ 2175 &:= 5 \times T(T(7) + 1^2) \\ 2177 &:= -7 + T(7) \times T(12) \\ 2178 &:= T(T(8)) - T(7) + T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) \\ 2183 &:= T(T(3+8)) - T(1 + T(T(2))) \\ 2184 &:= T(4+8) \times T(1 + T(T(2))) \\ 2196 &:= T(T(6) + T(9)) - T(-1 + T(T(2))) \\ 2198 &:= T(8) + T(T(9) + 1) \times 2 \\ 2201 &:= (-10 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 2205 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(02))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 2208 &:= T(T(8 + T(02))) - T(2) \\ 2209 &:= (T(9) + 02)^2 \\ 2211 &:= T(T(1 + 12 - 2)) \\ 2214 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 1) + T(2)^{T(T(2))} \end{aligned}$$

- 2217** := $T(T(7 + 1 + T(2))) + T(T(2))$
2221 := $T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))$
2222 := $(T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))$
2223 := $T(T(3)^2 + 2) \times T(2)$
2224 := $T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(2)$
2226 := $T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))$
2227 := $7 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(2^{T(T(2))})$
2229 := $T(T(9 + 2)) + T(2) \times T(T(2))$
2231 := $-1 + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2232 := $(T(T(2)^3) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(2))$
2233 := $3 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2 + 2)))$
2234 := $T(T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))) + 2 + T(T(T(2)))$
2235 := $5 \times (T(T(3))^2 + T(T(2)))$
2237 := $T(7) + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) - 2$
2238 := $T(T(8 + 3)) + T(2)^{T(2)}$
2239 := $T(T(9) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2))$
2242 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(4) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
2243 := $T(T(T(3))) - 4 + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2))))$
2244 := $4 \times (T(T(4) \times T(2) + T(2)))$
2245 := $-5 + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))))$
2246 := $T(T(6)) \times T(4) - 2^{T(T(2))}$
2247 := $T(T(7 + 4)) + T(2)^{T(2)}$
2248 := $T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2252 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2))))$
2253 := $T(T(T(3) + (5))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2254 := $T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(2))$
2256 := $T(T(6)) + (T(5) \times T(2))^2$
2257 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5))/2) + T(T(T(2)))$
2259 := $T(95)/2 - T(T(T(2)))$
2262 := $-T(T(2)) + 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)})$
2264 := $-4 + 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)})$
2265 := $T(T(5)) + T(62 + T(2))$
2266 := $T(66) + T(T(2 + 2))$
2268 := $T(8)/6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)})$
2269 := $9 \times T(6) + T(2^{T(T(2))})$
2271 := $T(-1 + T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(2)$
2274 := $(T(T(4)) \times 7 - T(T(2))) \times T(T(2))$
2275 := $T(-5 + 72) - T(2)$
2276 := $T(67) - T(T(2))/T(2)$
2277 := $7 \times T(T(7) - T(2)) + 2$
2278 := $T(-8 + 72 + T(2))$
2279 := $9 \times T(T(7) - T(T(2))) + 2$
2281 := $T(1 + T(8 + T(2))) + T(2)$
2283 := $-T(T(3)) + (8 \times T(T(2)))^2$
2284 := $T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) + 2) + T(2)$
2286 := $(T(6) + T(T(8) + 2)) \times T(2)$
2288 := $8 \times (T(8 + 2) + T(T(T(2))))$
2289 := $(T(9) + 8^2) \times T(T(T(2)))$
2292 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2))))$
2294 := $-T(4) + (T(9) + T(2))^2$
2295 := $T(5) \times T(T(9)/T(2) + 2)$
2297 := $-7 + (T(9) + T(2))^2$
2299 := $T(T(9)) + T(T(9)) - 2 + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2304 := $T(4) \times T(T(T(03))) - T(T(2))$
2311 := $T((1 + 1)^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2313 := $T(T(T(3))) \times T((1 + 3)) + T(2)$
2314 := $T(4) \times (1 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
2316 := $T(T(6)) \times T((1 + 3)) + T(T(2))$
2317 := $T(T(7)) + T(13) \times T(T(T(2)))$
2324 := $(T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2)^3)) \times 2$
2325 := $5 \times T(-2 + 32)$
2328 := $T(T(8))/T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) - T(2)$
2331 := $T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2332 := $T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2334 := $T(4) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(2)$
2338 := $T(T(8) + 3) \times 3 - 2$
2352 := $2 \times T(T(5) \times 3 + T(2))$
2354 := $T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))/3) - T(T(2))$
2355 := $5 \times (T(5 \times T(3)) + T(T(2)))$
2358 := $(T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times T(3)/2$
2364 := $T(4) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(3))) - T(T(2))$
2365 := $-T(T(5)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(3)))/T(2))$
2373 := $T(T(3)) \times (-7 + T(T(3 + 2)))$
2374 := $(-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(3) - 2$
2375 := $(T(T(5)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) + 2$
2376 := $6 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3) - 2))$
2377 := $T(T(T(7))/7) + T(T(3)^2)$
2378 := $(-T(8) + T(T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times 2$
2379 := $(-9 + T(T(7))) \times T(3) - T(2)$

- 2382** := $T(T(T(2) + 8)) + T(T(3) \times T(2))$
2384 := $T(4) \times (8 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
2385 := $(T(5) + T(T(8) + 3)) \times T(2)$
2387 := $-T(7) + T(T(8 + 3) + T(2))$
2388 := $T(8) + T(8 \times T(3)) \times 2$
2394 := $(T(4) + 9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))$
2396 := $T(69) - T(T(3)) + 2$
2397 := $(T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times T(3) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2398 := $8 \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) - 2$
2407 := $T(70) - T(T(4) + 2)$
2412 := $-T(2) + T(T(1 + T(4)) + T(2))$
2413 := $T(3 + T(1 + T(4))) - 2$
2415 := $T(5 + 1 \times 4^{T(2)})$
2418 := $T(81) - T(42)$
2421 := $T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))$
2422 := $(T(T(T(2)))/T(2))^4 + T(T(T(2)))$
2425 := $T(T(T(5))/2) + T(T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))$
2428 := $-8 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4) - T(2)))$
2432 := $T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(3))) - T(4) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2433 := $T(3) \times T(T(3 + 4)) - T(2)$
2435 := $-T(5) + (T(-T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times 2$
2436 := $6 \times T(3 \times T(4) - 2)$
2437 := $T(T(7)) \times T(3) + 4 - T(2)$
2438 := $T(T(8 + 3)) - 4 + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2439 := $T(T(9)) \times 3 - T(T(4 \times 2))$
2442 := $(-T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2)$
2443 := $T(T(T(3) + 4)) + T(42)$
2444 := $4 \times (-T(T(4)) + T(T(4 \times 2)))$
2445 := $(-5 + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2)$
2446 := $T(T(6)) \times T(4) + T(4^2)$
2448 := $(8 + T(4)) \times T(4^2)$
2452 := $T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(4) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2454 := $T(T(4)) \times T(5 + 4) - T(T(T(2)))$
2455 := $(-5 + T(-T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times T(2)$
2456 := $T(6) \times T(T(5)) - 4^{T(2)}$
2457 := $-T(7) + T(T(5 \times 4)/T(2))$
2462 := $2 \times (T(T(6)) + T(4)^{T(2)})$
2463 := $T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2464 := $T(T(T(4))) + T(6) + T(42)$
2465 := $T(5) \times T(T(6)) - T(4)^{T(2)}$
2467 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(4) \times T(T(2)))$
2469 := $T(9) \times T(6 + 4) - T(T(2))$
2472 := $(T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times (4 + 2)$
2473 := $-T(3) + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(T(2))$
2474 := $T(4) + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))$
2475 := $T(5) + (T(T(7)) + 4) \times T(T(2))$
2476 := $-6 + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(2)$
2478 := $-8 + T(T(7)) + T(4^{T(2)})$
2479 := $T(T(9)) + (T(7) + T(4))^2$
2481 := $T(1 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(2))$
2482 := $-T(2) + T(-8 + T(T(4) + 2))$
2483 := $T(T(3 + 8) + 4) - 2$
2485 := $T(5 \times (8 + 4 + 2))$
2487 := $T(7 \times T(8 - 4)) + 2$
2488 := $T(-8 + T(8 + 4)) + T(2)$
2492 := $(T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9) + 4)) \times 2$
2493 := $T(T(3)) + T(9) \times T(T(4)) - T(2)$
2495 := $5 \times (-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))$
2496 := $(-6 + T(9)) \times 4^{T(2)}$
2497 := $T(7) + T(9) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(2))$
2499 := $(T(T(9))/9 + 4) \times T(T(T(2)))$
2505 := $(-T(5) + T(T(05))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
2513 := $(-T(3) - 1 + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
2514 := $-T(41) + T(5)^{T(2)}$
2515 := $-5 + T(15) \times T(T(T(2)))$
2517 := $T(7 - 1) \times T(T(5)) - T(2)$
2523 := $T(T(3)) \times T(T(2) \times 5) + T(2)$
2524 := $(T(4) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2))$
2525 := $T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(5)/T(2)$
2526 := $T(6) \times T(T(2) \times 5) + T(T(2))$
2527 := $T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(5) - 2)$
2532 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(2))$
2534 := $-T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)) + T(T(5) \times T(T(2)))$
2535 := $T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \times T(2)$
2536 := $T(T(T(T(6)))/T(T(3))) + T(5^2)$
2538 := $(T(T(8)) - 3^5) \times T(T(2))$
2541 := $(1 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5 - 2)))$
2543 := $T(T(T(3))) \times (-4 + T(5)) + 2$
2544 := $T(T(T(4)) + 4 + T(5)) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
2545 := $-5 + T(T(4) \times 5) \times 2$

$$\begin{aligned} 2546 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(4) + 5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2547 &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5) \times T(2)) \\ 2548 &:= (T(8) + T(T(4))) \times T(5 + 2) \\ 2549 &:= T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) - 5 - T(T(T(2))) \\ 2552 &:= (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2) \\ 2553 &:= T(T(T(3) + 5) + 5) - T(2) \\ 2554 &:= T(-4 + 5 \times T(5)) - 2 \\ 2555 &:= -T(55) + T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) \\ 2556 &:= T(T(6) + 5 \times 5 \times 2) \\ 2561 &:= -1 + T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 2562 &:= T(T(2) \times 6) \times T(5) - T(2) \\ 2563 &:= T(3 \times 6) \times T(5) - 2 \\ 2565 &:= T(5) \times T(6 \times (5 - 2)) \\ 2568 &:= 8 \times (T(6) \times T(5) + T(T(2))) \\ 2569 &:= T(T(9)) - 6 + T(T(5 \times 2)) \\ 2572 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) + T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2574 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(7 + T(5))) \times 2 \\ 2577 &:= T(-7 + T(7 + 5)) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 2579 &:= T(T(9) + T(7)) - T(T(5)) - 2 \\ 2583 &:= 3 \times T(T(8) + T(5)/T(2)) \\ 2584 &:= 4 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))/T(T(2))) \\ 2585 &:= -T(5) + 8 \times T(5^2) \\ 2586 &:= T(68) + T(T(5)) \times 2 \\ 2588 &:= T(T(8) + T(8)) - T(T(5))/T(2) \\ 2589 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(5 + T(T(2)))) \\ 2592 &:= T(T(2))^{9-5} \times 2 \\ 2595 &:= T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(5 \times 2) \\ 2596 &:= T(6) + T(T(9)) + T(T(5 \times 2)) \\ 2597 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(-T(9) + T(T(5)) + 2) \\ 2598 &:= T(8 \times 9) - T(5) \times 2 \\ 2617 &:= T(T(7)) + T((1 + T(6)) \times T(2)) \\ 2618 &:= T(T(8)) - 1 + T(62) \\ 2619 &:= T(T(9 - 1)) + T(62) \\ 2622 &:= T(2 \times T(2 + 6)) - T(T(2)) \\ 2624 &:= -4 + T(2 \times 6^2) \\ 2625 &:= 5^{T(2)} \times T(T(6/2)) \\ 2626 &:= T(6 \times 2 \times 6) - 2 \\ 2627 &:= T(72) - 6/T(T(2)) \\ 2628 &:= T(8 + 2 + 62) \\ 2634 &:= T(4 \times 3 \times 6) + T(T(2)) \\ 2638 &:= -8 + T(3) \times T(6)^2 \\ 2643 &:= -T(T(3)) + 4 \times T(6^2) \\ 2644 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 4 \times T((T(6) + 2)) \\ 2646 &:= T(T(6 - 4)) \times T(6)^2 \\ 2648 &:= (T(T(8)) - 4) \times (6 - 2) \\ 2652 &:= 2 \times T(T(5) + 6^2) \\ 2662 &:= 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)} \\ 2664 &:= (T(4) - 6) \times T(6^2) \\ 2667 &:= 7 \times (T(T(6) + 6) + T(2)) \\ 2672 &:= -T(2) - T(T(7)) + T(T(6 \times 2)) \\ 2673 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(2)) \\ 2674 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2675 &:= T(T(5 + 7)) - T(T(T(6)/T(2))) \\ 2681 &:= -1 + T(T(8)) + T(T(6) \times T(2)) \\ 2682 &:= (T(T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2685 &:= (T(T(5)) + 8) \times T(6) - T(2) \\ 2688 &:= 8 \times 8 \times T(6) \times 2 \\ 2691 &:= (T(T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(2) \\ 2694 &:= T(4) \times T(9) \times 6 - T(T(2)) \\ 2695 &:= -5 + 9 \times T(T(6) + T(2)) \\ 2697 &:= T(T(7) + T(9)) - 6 + 2 \\ 2698 &:= T(T(T(8))/9) - T(T(6))/T(2) \\ 2701 &:= T(1 + 072) \\ 2708 &:= 80 + T(72) \\ 2712 &:= T(2) \times (1 + T(7 \times T(T(2)))) \\ 2719 &:= 91 + T(72) \\ 2722 &:= T(T(T(2)^2) + T(7)) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 2723 &:= -T(T(3)) + (2 \times 7)^{T(2)} \\ 2728 &:= 8 \times (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \\ 2734 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(3)) - 7)^{T(2)} \\ 2736 &:= (T(T(6) + 3) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 2737 &:= -7 + (T(T(3)) - 7)^{T(2)} \\ 2738 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(37)) \times 2 \\ 2742 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(T(4))) - 7) \times 2 \\ 2744 &:= (-4 - T(4) + T(7))^{T(2)} \\ 2745 &:= -T(5) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times T(2)) \\ 2747 &:= -T(7) + T(-T(4) + T(7) \times T(2)) \\ 2748 &:= T(T(8)) \times 4 + T(7) \times T(2) \\ 2749 &:= -9 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) \times T(2) \\ 2754 &:= T(4) \times T(-5 + T(7)) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

- 2755** := $5 \times T(57)/T(2)$
2756 := $T(T(-6 + T(5)) + 7) \times 2$
2758 := $T(-T(8) + T(T(5))) - T(T(7)) \times 2$
2759 := $T(-T(9) + T(T(5))) - T(7 + T(T(2)))$
2764 := $T(T(4)) + T(6 \times 7) \times T(2)$
2765 := $5 \times (-T(T(6)) + T(7)^2)$
2768 := $8 \times (T(6) + T(T(7) - T(2)))$
2771 := $-1 + T(77) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
2772 := $-T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$
2773 := $T(-3 + 77) - 2$
2774 := $(-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 7 + 2$
2775 := $T(-5 + 7 + 72)$
2778 := $(T(T(8) - 7) + T(7)) \times T(T(2))$
2779 := $(-9 + T(T(7))) \times (T(7) - T(T(T(2))))$
2782 := $T(2) \times T(T(8)) + T(7)^2$
2783 := $(3 + 8) \times T(T(7) - T(T(2)))$
2784 := $4 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7 - 2))$
2786 := $T(6) \times (-8 + T(T(7)))/T(2)$
2787 := $T(78 - 7) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2789 := $T(9) + 8 \times 7^{T(2)}$
2793 := $T(T(3)) \times (T(9 + 7) - T(2))$
2794 := $(T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times T(7) - T(T(2))$
2795 := $T(T(T(5)) - T(9)) - T(7 + T(2))$
2796 := $T(6) + T((9 + T(7)) \times 2)$
2797 := $T(T(7)) - T(9) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))$
2799 := $T(9 + 9) + T(72)$
2805 := $5 \times T(T(08) - T(2))$
2808 := $T(8) \times T(T(08)/T(2))$
2809 := $(T(9) + 08)^2$
2812 := $2 \times T(1 + T(8)) \times 2$
2814 := $4 \times T(1 + T(8)) + 2$
2823 := $T(T(T(3))) + 2 \times T(8)^2$
2826 := $(T(T(6) + 2) + T(T(8))) \times T(2)$
2828 := $(T(8^2) - T(T(8))) \times 2$
2829 := $T(9 + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(T(2)))$
2832 := $T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) - T(T(8)/2)$
2835 := $-T(5) + T(3 + T(8)) \times 2$
2837 := $T(73) + T(8 \times 2)$
2838 := $(T(T(8) - T(3)) + 8) \times T(T(2))$
2842 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(8)^2$
2845 := $-5 + T(T(4 + 8) - T(2))$
2846 := $-T(T(6)) - 4 + T(T(T(8)/T(2)))$
2847 := $T(74) + T(8) \times 2$
2862 := $T(T(2)) + T(6) \times T(8 \times 2)$
2865 := $T(5) - T(T(6)) + T(T(T(8)/T(2)))$
2868 := $(8 + T(T(6))) \times T(8)/T(2)$
2872 := $T(T(T(2) + 7)) + T(T(8)) \times 2$
2874 := $T(T(4 + 7)) + T(T(8)) - T(2)$
2877 := $7 \times (T(T(7)) + 8 - T(2))$
2883 := $T(T(3 + 8)) + T(T(8)) + T(T(2))$
2884 := $(T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8/2$
2886 := $(T(6) - 8) \times T(T(8))/T(2)$
2887 := $T(7) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2889 := $(T(T(9)) - T(8) - T(8)) \times T(2)$
2891 := $-T(19) + T(T(T(8)/T(2)))$
2892 := $-T(T(T(2))) \times 9 + T(T(T(8)/T(2)))$
2894 := $T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(2)))$
2895 := $-T(5) + T(9) \times 8^2$
2898 := $T(8) + T(T(9) + 8) \times 2$
2918 := $(-8 + T(T(1 + 9) + T(T(T(2))))$
2922 := $T(T(2)) + (T(T(2)) \times 9)^2$
2923 := $-3 + T(-2 + T(9 + T(2)))$
2924 := $4 \times (2 + 9^{T(2)})$
2925 := $(-T(T(5))/2 + T(T(9))) \times T(2)$
2926 := $T(T(6 - 2) + T(9 + 2))$
2927 := $T(T(7) - T(2)) \times 9 + 2$
2928 := $T(T(8) + T(T(2))) + T(9)^2$
2932 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(3 + 9) - 2)$
2937 := $-T(7) \times T(3) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$
2952 := $-T(2 + T(5)) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$
2955 := $T(T(5)) + T(5) \times 9 \times T(T(T(2)))$
2957 := $-T(7) - T(T(5)) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$
2961 := $-T(T(-1 + 6)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))$
2962 := $T(T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(9) - 2)$
2964 := $T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 9 - T(T(2))$
2965 := $-5 + T(6 \times 9) \times 2$
2973 := $T(T(3) \times 7) + T(T(9)) \times 2$
2975 := $5 \times T(T(7) + 9 - T(2))$
2976 := $6 \times T(T(7) + 9)/T(2)$
2977 := $T(T(7)) \times 7 + T(9) \times T(2)$

- 2978** := $8 \times T(T(7)) - T(9) \times T(T(2))$
2982 := $T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))$
2985 := $T(T(5)) \times 8 + T(9)^2$
2988 := $T(8) \times (T(8) + T(9) + 2)$
2994 := $499 \times T(T(2))$
2997 := $(T(7) + 9) \times 9^2$
3003 := $T(T(T(T(3))))/003$
3024 := $T(T(T(T(4))))/20 + T(T(3))$
3075 := $T(T(5 + 7)) - T(03)$
3078 := $T(8 + 70) - 3$
3081 := $T(1 + 80 - 3)$
3084 := $T(T(4 + 8)) + 03$
3087 := $T(78) + T(03)$
3122 := $2 \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(1 + 3))))$
3123 := $T(T(T(T(3))))/T(2) + (T(T(-1 + T(3))))$
3135 := $T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(T(3)))$
3136 := $T(T(6 + T(3))) + T(T(1 + 3))$
3139 := $T(T(9 + 3) + 1) - T(T(3))$
3145 := $T(T(5)) + T(T(4))^{-1+3}$
3163 := $T(T(T(3) + 6)) + 1 + 3$
3164 := $T(4 \times T(6)) - T(T(1 + T(3)))$
3165 := $T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + 1 - T(T(3)))$
3166 := $T(T(6 + 6) + 1) + T(3)$
3174 := $(T(4 + T(7)) + 1) \times T(3)$
3178 := $-T(8) \times T(7) + T(T(13))$
3179 := $-T(T(9)) + T(7) + T(T(13))$
3185 := $5 \times (T(T(8 - 1)) + T(T(T(3))))$
3189 := $((T(T(9)) + T((8 - 1))) \times 3)$
3213 := $T(T(3)) \times T(-1 + T(2) \times T(3))$
3224 := $-T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3)$
3225 := $(-T(5) + T(2 + T(2 \times T(3))))$
3227 := $T(T(7)) \times 2^{T(2)} - T(T(3))$
3228 := $(T(8) + T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3))$
3232 := $(-2 + T(T(T(T(3))))/T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))$
3234 := $T(T(4 \times 3) + 2) - (T(3))$
3235 := $5 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(2^{T(3)})$
3236 := $T(T(T(6))/3) + 2 + T(T(T(3)))$
3237 := $7 \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 3$
3252 := $T(T(2) + T(5)) + T(T(2 \times T(3)))$
3255 := $T(T(5) + T(5))/T(2) \times T(T(3))$
3258 := $(T(8) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3)$
3264 := $T(46) \times T(2) + T(T(3))$
3272 := $(T(2) + T(T(7))) \times 2^3$
3276 := $T(6 + 7) \times T(2^3)$
3277 := $T(7) \times 7 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))$
3278 := $8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(2)) + T(3)$
3279 := $T(9) + 7 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))$
3283 := $T(T(T(T(3)) - 8)) - T(2 \times T(T(3)))$
3285 := $5 \times T(T(8)) - T(T(2) \times 3)$
3288 := $(T(8) + 8^{T(2)}) \times T(3)$
3294 := $T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)/T(T(T(2))) - T(3)$
3295 := $-5 + T(9^2) - T(T(3))$
3297 := $(T(7 + 9) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3))$
3298 := $T(T(8) + T(9)) - 23$
3312 := $T(21) + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$
3313 := $T(T(T(3))) + 1 + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$
3315 := $T(5) \times (-T(1 + 3) + T(T(T(3))))$
3318 := $T(81) + 3 - T(3)$
3321 := $T((1 + 2)^3 \times 3)$
3324 := $T(T(4) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(3))) + 3$
3327 := $T(T(7) \times T(2) - 3) + T(3)$
3333 := $T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$
3336 := $T(T(6)) + 3 \times T(T(3 \times 3))$
3339 := $(T(T(9)) + T(T(3) + T(3))) \times 3$
3342 := $T(T(2)) \times (-4 + T(33))$
3345 := $-T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)) \times 3$
3348 := $T(8) \times (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times 3$
3352 := $-2 + T(5)^3 - T(T(3))$
3354 := $(T(4) + 5)^3 - T(T(3))$
3355 := $5 \times (5 + T(T(3) \times T(3)))$
3357 := $T(7) \times T(5 \times 3) - 3$
3358 := $T(T(8)) \times 5 + T(T(T(3)))/3$
3363 := $-3 + 6 \times T(33)$
3366 := $6 \times T(6 + 3^3)$
3367 := $T(76) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(3))$
3369 := $(9 + 6)^3 - T(3)$
3372 := $T(-2 + 7)^3 - 3$
3384 := $T(T(T(4)) - 8) \times (-3 + T(3))$
3385 := $5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))$
3388 := $(8 + T(8)) \times T(T(T(3)))/3$

$$\begin{aligned} 3391 &:= T(1 + T(9 + 3)) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3396 &:= -6 + 9 \times T(3^3) \\ 3397 &:= T(79 + 3) - T(3) \\ 3398 &:= T(T(8) + T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))/3 \\ 3399 &:= 9 \times T(9 \times 3) - 3 \\ 3403 &:= T(T(3) + T(T(04)) + T(T(3))) \\ 3405 &:= T(5) \times (-04 + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 3421 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 3422 &:= 2 \times T(-2 + T(4) \times T(3)) \\ 3423 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-2 + T(T(4)) \times 3) \\ 3424 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(2 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3427 &:= 7^{T(2)} \times T(4) - 3 \\ 3428 &:= T(82) + 4 + T(T(3)) \\ 3429 &:= T(T(9))/T(2) \times T(4) - T(T(3)) \\ 3431 &:= T(T(T(1 + 3))) + T(T(T(4)) + (T(3))) \\ 3432 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \\ 3434 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 3 + T(T(T(4)) + T(3)) \\ 3435 &:= T(5)^3 + T(4) \times T(3) \\ 3436 &:= T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) \\ 3437 &:= -T(7) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3 \\ 3438 &:= 8^3 + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \\ 3442 &:= 2 \times (T(4) + T(T(T(4)) + 3)) \\ 3444 &:= 4 \times T(44 - 3) \\ 3462 &:= T(2) \times T(6) \times T(T(4)) - 3 \\ 3465 &:= T(5) \times T(6 \times 4 - 3) \\ 3466 &:= 6 \times T(T(6)) + T(4^3) \\ 3471 &:= T((1 + 7) \times T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3472 &:= T(T(2) + T(7)) \times (4 + 3) \\ 3474 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) - 4 \times 3 \\ 3475 &:= -5 + T(T(7) + T(T(4))) - T(3) \\ 3478 &:= -8 + T(T(7) + T(4 + T(3))) \\ 3483 &:= -3 + T(8 \times T(4) + 3) \\ 3484 &:= 4 \times (-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3 \\ 3485 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4) + T(T(3))) \\ 3486 &:= T(6 + 8 \times T(4) - 3) \\ 3487 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T((8 - 4) \times 3)) \\ 3489 &:= T(9) \times T(8 + 4) - T(T(3)) \\ 3492 &:= T(2) \times (9 + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 3495 &:= -T(5) + T(9) \times T(4 \times 3) \\ 3497 &:= -T(7) - T(9) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3498 &:= (8 + T(9)) \times T(-T(4) + T(T(3))) \\ 3515 &:= 5 \times T(1 + T(5 + 3)) \\ 3518 &:= T(T(8) + 1) \times 5 + 3 \\ 3522 &:= T(T(T(2)))^2 + T(T(T(5) - 3)) \\ 3525 &:= 5^2 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \\ 3528 &:= T(82) + 5^3 \\ 3534 &:= (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(3)) \\ 3542 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5) + T(3))) \\ 3543 &:= T(3 \times 4) + T(5) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 3546 &:= (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(5) + T(T(3)) \\ 3549 &:= (T(9) + 4 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3552 &:= T(T(T(2)) + 5 \times T(5)) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3555 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) - 3) \\ 3557 &:= -T(7) + T(T(5)) + T(5) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 3558 &:= T(-T(8) + T(T(5))) - T(5) + 3 \\ 3564 &:= T(4 \times T(6)) - T(T(5 - 3)) \\ 3565 &:= -5 + T(6 \times T(5) - T(3)) \\ 3567 &:= (7 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) - 3 \\ 3568 &:= (8 - T(T(6))) \times (5 - T(T(3))) \\ 3582 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(8)) \times 5 + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3584 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 5 - T(T(3)) \\ 3585 &:= T(5) \times (8 + T(T(5) + T(3))) \\ 3587 &:= T(7) \times (8 + T(T(5))) + 3 \\ 3589 &:= -T(9) + T(85) - T(T(3)) \\ 3591 &:= T(-T(-1 + 9) + T(T(5))) + T(T(3)) \\ 3612 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (1 + T(6 \times 3)) \\ 3619 &:= (T(T(9)) - 1) \times T(6)/T(3) \\ 3624 &:= 4 \times (T(2 \times T(6)) + 3) \\ 3627 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(2)) \times (6 + 3) \\ 3628 &:= T(82) + T(T(6)) - T(3) \\ 3634 &:= T(4^3 + T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ 3642 &:= T(-2 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) \\ 3645 &:= 5 \times T(-4 + 6)^{T(3)} \\ 3647 &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4)) - 6) \times 3 \\ 3648 &:= T(84) + T(6 + T(3)) \\ 3649 &:= T(T(9 + 4) - 6) - T(3) \\ 3652 &:= T(T(-2 + T(5)) - 6) - 3 \\ 3654 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times T(6) - T(T(3)) \\ 3655 &:= T(-5 + 5 \times 6 \times 3) \\ 3657 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(5) - 6) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3658 &:= T(85) + 6 - 3 \\ 3672 &:= (2 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 3) \\ 3675 &:= T(T(5) + T(7) + 6) \times 3 \\ 3676 &:= T(6) + T(T(7 + 6) - T(3)) \\ 3688 &:= ((T(88) - T(T(6))) + 3) \\ 3696 &:= T(T(6)) \times 96 / T(3) \\ 3699 &:= T(9 \times 9) + T(T(6) + T(3)) \\ 3724 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(2)^7 - 3 \\ 3725 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(7) + T(T(3))) \\ 3727 &:= T(T(7)) + T(27 \times 3) \\ 3728 &:= T(82) + T(T(7) - 3) \\ 3729 &:= 9 \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(3)) \\ 3732 &:= (T(T(2))^3 + T(T(7))) \times T(3) \\ 3735 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(3) - T(7)) - T(3) \\ 3736 &:= T(T(6 + 3)) + T(73) \\ 3738 &:= 8 \times T(T(3)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\ 3739 &:= T(T(9)) + 3 + T(73) \\ 3741 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4)) + T(7) + 3) \\ 3745 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\ 3746 &:= T(T(6)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\ 3751 &:= (1 + T(T(5))) \times (T(7) + 3) \\ 3752 &:= T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - 7^3 \\ 3759 &:= (T(T(9)) / 5 - T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3762 &:= T(T(2) \times 6) \times (T(7) - T(3)) \\ 3767 &:= T(7) \times T(T(6)) - T(73) \\ 3773 &:= T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\ 3774 &:= T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(T(7))) - T(3) \\ 3775 &:= -5 + T(T(7) + 7) \times T(3) \\ 3779 &:= T(T(9)) + (7 + 7)^3 \\ 3792 &:= (T(2) + T(T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(3) \\ 3795 &:= (T(5) + T(9) \times T(7)) \times 3 \\ 3797 &:= T(79) + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3798 &:= -T(T(8)) + 9 \times T((T(7) + 3)) \\ 3816 &:= (6 + T(-1 + T(8))) \times T(3) \\ 3822 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(3))) \\ 3824 &:= -4 + T(T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(3))) \\ 3825 &:= T(5 \times (2 + 8)) \times 3 \\ 3828 &:= T(8 / 2 + 83) \\ 3834 &:= T(-4 + T(T(T(3)) - 8)) + T(3) \\ 3835 &:= -T(T(5)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-8 + T(T(3)))) \\ 3837 &:= T(T(7) \times 3) + T(8) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3843 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(8) + T(3)) \\ 3846 &:= (-T(6) - 4 + T(T(8))) \times T(3) \\ 3849 &:= T(9 + T(4 + 8)) + T(T(3)) \\ 3855 &:= 5 \times (T(5) + T(8) \times T(T(3))) \\ 3856 &:= T(6 \times T(5)) - 8 - T(T(T(3))) \\ 3858 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(5) - 8) \times T(3) \\ 3864 &:= -(T(T(4)) - T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3865 &:= -5 + (-T(6) + T(T(8))) \times T(3) \\ 3882 &:= T(2) \times T(8) \times T(8) - T(3) \\ 3884 &:= -4 + T(8) \times T(8) \times 3 \\ 3885 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)) / T(3)) \\ 3886 &:= T(T(6)) + T(88 - 3) \\ 3888 &:= T(8) \times T(8) \times T(8 - T(3)) \\ 3892 &:= T(T(-2 + 9)) + T(83) \\ 3906 &:= (T(T(6)) - T(09)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3909 &:= T(90) + T(9) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 3916 &:= T(61 + 9 \times 3) \\ 3922 &:= T(-2 + 2 \times T(9)) + T(3) \\ 3925 &:= T(T(T(5)) / T(2)) + T(T(9)) \times 3 \\ 3927 &:= 7 \times T((2 + 9) \times 3) \\ 3928 &:= 8 \times (2^9 - T(T(3))) \\ 3942 &:= (T(T(2 \times 4)) - 9) \times T(3) \\ 3944 &:= 4 \times (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) - T(3) \\ 3948 &:= T(84) + T(9 \times 3) \\ 3963 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(6) \times 9 - T(3) \\ 3964 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(6)) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\ 3966 &:= T(6) \times T(6) \times 9 - 3 \\ 3967 &:= T(76) + T(T(9)) + T(3) \\ 3968 &:= 8 \times T((T(T(6)) - T(9)) / T(3)) \\ 3969 &:= 9 \times T(6) \times T(9 - 3) \\ 3972 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-7 + 93) \\ 3975 &:= -T(5) + T(T(7) - 9) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3978 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(-7 + 9)) \times T(3) \\ 3982 &:= -2 + T(89) - T(T(3)) \\ 3984 &:= T(T(4 + 8)) + T(T(9) - 3) \\ 3988 &:= -8 + T(T(8)) \times (9 - 3) \\ 3993 &:= -T(3 \times 9) + T(93) \\ 3996 &:= 6 \times T(9 + 9 \times 3) \\ 3997 &:= T(T(7)) + T(9 + 9) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

- 4045** := $5 \times T(40) - T(T(4))$
4075 := $T(5) + T(T(7)) \times T(04)$
4091 := $T(1 \times 90) - 4$
4092 := $-T(2) + T(9 \times T(04))$
4093 := $-T(3) + T(90) + 4$
4099 := $T(T(9) + T(9)) + 04$
4109 := $T(90) + 14$
4125 := $T(5) \times (T(T(2)) - 1) \times T(T(4))$
4131 := $T(T(13)) - T(T(1 \times 4))$
4134 := $T(T(T(4)) - 3) \times (-1 + 4)$
4136 := $(T(T(6 + 3)) - 1) \times 4$
4164 := $4 \times (6 + T(T(-1 + T(4))))$
4172 := $T(T(T(T(2)) + 7)) - 14$
4175 := $T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) - 1 - T(4)$
4176 := $T(T(6 + 7)) - T(1 \times 4)$
4178 := $-8 + T(T(T(7) - T(1 + 4)))$
4182 := $T(T(T(T(2)) + 8 - 1)) - 4$
4183 := $-3 + T(T(8 + 1 + 4))$
4185 := $T(T(5 + 8)) - 1^4$
4186 := $T(6 + 81 + 4)$
4204 := $(T(40) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 4$
4215 := $T(T(5)) + T(-1 + T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4218 := $T(T(8) + 1) \times (2 + 4)$
4222 := $T(2^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4223 := $T(T(T(T(3)) + 2) / T(2)) - T(T(4))$
4224 := $T(42) + T(T(2)^4)$
4225 := $T(5^2) \times (T(2) + T(4))$
4228 := $T(8) + T(T(2)) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4229 := $T(92) + T(T(2)) - T(T(4))$
4232 := $-T(2) + T(T(T(3))) / T(2) \times T(T(4))$
4235 := $T(T(5) + T(3)) / T(2) \times T(T(4))$
4236 := $T(T(6 + T(3))) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))$
4238 := $T(T(-8 + T(T(3)))) - T(2) + T(T(4))$
4239 := $9 \times (T(3) + T(T(2) \times T(4)))$
4241 := $T(T(1 \times 4)) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4243 := $T(T(3 + T(4))) + 2 + T(T(4))$
4246 := $6 \times T(4) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4252 := $T(T(T(2)) + 5) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$
4257 := $T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) - T(2 + 4)$
4258 := $T(8) \times (T(T(5)) - 2) + T(4)$
4263 := $T(T(3)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2) + 4))$
4265 := $T(T(5)) \times 6^2 - T(T(4))$
4267 := $T(T(7 + 6)) + T(2)^4$
4268 := $T(86 + T(T(2))) - T(4)$
4269 := $-9 + T((T(6) + 2) \times 4)$
4273 := $T(37) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(4))$
4275 := $T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) - T(-2 + 4)$
4278 := $T(T(8) + 7 \times 2 \times 4)$
4282 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(4))$
4285 := $-5 + T(T(8) / T(2)) \times T(T(4))$
4289 := $T(T(9) + 8) \times T(2) - 4$
4323 := $3 \times (T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))$
4324 := $4 \times T(T(2^3)) + T(4)$
4326 := $T(T(6)) + T(T(2) \times 3 \times T(4))$
4327 := $T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(3) + T(T(4)))$
4334 := $T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))$
4335 := $T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 3 + T(T(4)))$
4345 := $(T(5) + 4^3) \times T(T(4))$
4348 := $(T(T(8) + T(4)) + T(3)) \times 4$
4352 := $2^5 \times T(T(3) + T(4))$
4355 := $T(5 + T(5)) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(4))$
4356 := $T(6 + 5)^{T(3)-4}$
4362 := $T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(4)))$
4365 := $T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(3) \times T(4))$
4367 := $-T(T(7) - 6) + 3 \times T(T(T(4)))$
4368 := $8 \times 6 \times T(3 + T(4))$
4371 := $T(-1 + T(7) \times 3 + T(4))$
4378 := $(-8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(4))$
4379 := $(-9 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4)$
4385 := $5 \times (-T(T(8)) + 3 + T(T(T(4))))$
4389 := $-T(98) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))$
4392 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(9 + T(T(3)) \times 4)$
4395 := $-5 \times T(9) + 3 \times T(T(T(4)))$
4396 := $T(6) + T(93) + 4$
4398 := $-T(T(8)) + (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4$
4412 := $2 \times T(T(1 + T(4))) - T(4)$
4422 := $2 \times T(T(T(2) + 4 + 4))$
4425 := $T(5) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4) + T(4))$
4427 := $-T(7) + T(2)^4 \times T(T(4))$
4432 := $2 \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) + T(4)$

$$\begin{aligned} 4437 &:= -T(7) + T(-T(3) + T(4) \times T(4)) \\ 4442 &:= T(T(T(2) + T(4))) + 4^4 \\ 4443 &:= 3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \\ 4445 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4446 &:= 6 \times T(T(T(T(4)))) / T(T(4)) + T(4) \\ 4449 &:= T(94) - 4 \times 4 \\ 4455 &:= (T(5)/5)^4 \times T(T(4)) \\ 4462 &:= -T(2) + T(T(6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\ 4463 &:= -3 + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4465 &:= T((T(5) + 6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\ 4466 &:= T(T(6) + T(6 + 4)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4469 &:= T(T(9) - 6 + T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 4473 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-7 + 4 \times T(T(4))) \\ 4482 &:= T(2) \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(4) \\ 4484 &:= (T(48) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 4485 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(-4 + T(4)))) \\ 4486 &:= T(6) + T(84 + T(4)) \\ 4488 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4) + 4)) \\ 4495 &:= -5 + (T(9) \times T(4)) \times T(4) \\ 4496 &:= T(6) + T(94) + T(4) \\ 4497 &:= T(7) + T(94) + 4 \\ 4524 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(2)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(4)) \\ 4526 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5) + T(4)) \\ 4532 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3) + 5)) + T(T(4))) \\ 4536 &:= T(6) \times (T(3) + T(5 \times 4)) \\ 4542 &:= T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))/T(4)) \\ 4543 &:= T((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) / T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4545 &:= -T(5) + T(T(4) \times T(5) - T(T(4))) \\ 4555 &:= -5 + T(5 \times (T(5) + 4)) \\ 4556 &:= T(6 \times T(5) + 5) - 4 \\ 4559 &:= T(95) - 5 + 4 \\ 4575 &:= T(5) + T(7 \times T(5) - T(4)) \\ 4584 &:= 4 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) \times 4) \\ 4585 &:= T(T(5)) + T(-T(8) + T(T(5)) + T(4)) \\ 4589 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4593 &:= 3 \times (-T(9)/5 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4595 &:= 5 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)) + 4) \\ 4596 &:= (-6 + T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times 4 \\ 4602 &:= T(2) \times (-06 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4615 &:= 5 \times (-1 + T(T(6)) \times 4) \\ 4616 &:= T(T(6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) - 4 \\ 4632 &:= 2 \times (T(3) + T(T(6)) \times T(4)) \\ 4634 &:= -4 + 3 \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4635 &:= T(5) + 3 \times T(T(6 + 4)) \\ 4638 &:= T(8 - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4639 &:= T(T(9)) \times 3 - 6 + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4641 &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(4)) \\ 4642 &:= T(T(2 + T(4))) + T(6) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4644 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4646 &:= T((6 + T(4)) \times 6) - T(4) \\ 4648 &:= -8 + T(4 \times 6 \times 4) \\ 4662 &:= T(T(2)) + T(6 \times (6 + T(4))) \\ 4675 &:= (T(-T(5) + T(7)) - 6) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4678 &:= T(T(8)) \times 7 + 6 + T(4) \\ 4682 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) + T(T(6) + T(4)) \\ 4683 &:= T(T(3)) \times (8 \times T(6) + T(T(4))) \\ 4687 &:= 7 \times T(T(8)) + T(6) + 4 \\ 4692 &:= 2 \times T(T(-9 + T(6)) - T(4)) \\ 4694 &:= (4 + T(T(9))) \times 6 - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4696 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(9) - 6 + T(T(4))) \\ 4697 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4698 &:= T(T(8)) \times 9 - 6^4 \\ 4704 &:= 4 \times T(-07 + T(T(4))) \\ 4717 &:= 7 \times T(T(1 + 7)) + T(T(4)) \\ 4722 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4725 &:= T(5)^2 \times T(T(7 - 4)) \\ 4726 &:= T(6^2) + T(T(7)) \times T(4) \\ 4728 &:= T(T(8)) + 2 + T(T(7)) \times T(4) \\ 4729 &:= T(9) \times T(2 \times 7) + 4 \\ 4732 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(3) \times 7 + T(T(4))) \\ 4733 &:= T(3 \times T(3)) \times T(7) - T(T(4)) \\ 4738 &:= (T(T(8)) + 3) \times 7 + T(T(4)) \\ 4743 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(7 + T(4)) \\ 4744 &:= (T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 7)) \times 4 \\ 4746 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \\ 4749 &:= T(9 \times T(4) + 7) - 4 \\ 4752 &:= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)) \\ 4753 &:= T(T(3) \times T(5) + T(7)/4) \\ 4759 &:= T(T(9)) \times 5 - T(T(7)) - T(4) \\ 4762 &:= 2 \times (6 \times T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4763 &:= T(T(3) + T(6 + 7)) + T(4) \\ 4779 &:= -9 + T(7) \times T(T(7) - T(4)) \\ 4782 &:= -T(2) + 87 \times T(T(4)) \\ 4784 &:= (T(T(4) + 8) \times T(7)) - 4 \\ 4785 &:= 5 \times T(87)/4 \\ 4788 &:= (-8 + T(8)) \times T(T(7) - T(4)) \\ 4789 &:= T(98) - 7 - T(T(4)) \\ 4792 &:= T(2 \times 9) \times T(7) + 4 \\ 4795 &:= (T(-T(5) + T(9)) \times 7 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4796 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(9 - 7))) - T(T(4)) \\ 4799 &:= -9 + T(97) + T(T(4)) \\ 4832 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) - T(T(4)) \\ 4833 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)) - 8 - T(4) \\ 4837 &:= 7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) + 4) \\ 4842 &:= T(T(T(2) + T(4))) + T(T(8)) - T(4) \\ 4845 &:= T(5 \times T(4)) + T(84) \\ 4847 &:= T(7 + T(T(4)) + T(8)) - 4 \\ 4848 &:= (T(8) + T(48)) \times 4 \\ 4851 &:= T(-1 + T(5) + 84) \\ 4852 &:= T(T(T(2) + 5)) + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) \\ 4855 &:= T(T(5)) \times 5 \times 8 + T(T(4)) \\ 4859 &:= 9 \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(4)) \\ 4863 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) + 8 + 4 \\ 4866 &:= 6 \times (T(6) \times T(8) + T(T(4))) \\ 4871 &:= -1 + T(T(7)) \times (8 + 4) \\ 4872 &:= T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (8 - 4) \\ 4875 &:= T(5) \times T(-7 + 8 \times 4) \\ 4882 &:= -T(T(2)) + 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \\ 4884 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4 \\ 4888 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(8 - 4))) \\ 4889 &:= T(T(9) - 8) + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) \\ 4892 &:= (-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) \times 8 - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4895 &:= T(T(5) \times 9 - T(8)) - T(T(4)) \\ 4896 &:= T(6 + T(9)) + T(84) \\ 4898 &:= -8 + T(98) + T(T(4)) \\ 4914 &:= (T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(9 + 4) \\ 4921 &:= (1 + T(2)^9)/4 \\ 4924 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(9))) \times 4 \\ 4926 &:= (T(6) + T(2)^9)/4 \\ 4927 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(2) + 9) + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4935 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \\ 4937 &:= T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) + 9 - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4942 &:= 2 \times (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \\ 4943 &:= T(T(3 + T(4)) - 9) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 4945 &:= T(T(5)) \times 4 + T(94) \\ 4946 &:= T((T(6) - T(4)) \times 9) - 4 \\ 4962 &:= 2 \times (6 + T(9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 4965 &:= -T(56) + 9^4 \\ 4968 &:= 8 \times 6 \times T(T(9))/T(4) \\ 4972 &:= 2 \times (T(T(7)) + T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 4973 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) + T(9) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4985 &:= (T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(9) - T(T(4)) \\ 4987 &:= 7 \times (T(T(8)) + T(9)) + T(4) \\ 4992 &:= (T(T(2) + 9) \times (9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 4995 &:= 5 \times T(T(9)) - T(9) \times 4 \\ 4999 &:= T(9) + T(99) + 4 \\ 5112 &:= 2 \times T(T(11) + 5) \\ 5133 &:= 3 \times T(3 + T(T(-1 + 5))) \\ 5147 &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 5 \\ 5159 &:= T(T(9)) \times 5 - 1 - T(5) \\ 5166 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(6)) \times 1 + T(5)) \\ 5175 &:= 5 \times T(T(-7 + 1 + T(5))) \\ 5195 &:= (5 + T(T(9)) - 1) \times 5 \\ 5196 &:= T(6) + T(T(9)) \times 1 \times 5 \\ 5226 &:= T(T(6) + 2) + T(-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5))) \\ 5235 &:= (T(5 + T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(5) \\ 5244 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4)) - 2) - T(T(5))) \\ 5248 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times (T(2) + 5) \\ 5256 &:= -T(6) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(2))^5 \\ 5259 &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)) \\ 5265 &:= T(5) \times T(-6 + 2^5) \\ 5272 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(7)) \times (-2 + T(5)) \\ 5274 &:= -4 - T(T(7)) \times (2 - T(5)) \\ 5287 &:= 7 \times T(8) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 \\ 5292 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(2 + T(5))) \\ 5295 &:= T(59) \times T(2) - T(5) \\ 5297 &:= T(7) \times 9 \times T(T(T(2))) + 5 \\ 5313 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(1 + T(3) + T(5)) \\ 5328 &:= 8 \times T(T(2 \times 3) + T(5)) \\ 5368 &:= 8 \times (T(6 \times T(3)) + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5372 &:= 2 \times (T(73) - T(5)) & 5793 &:= -3 + T(T(9)) \times T(7)/5 \\ 5376 &:= T(T(6)) + 7^3 \times T(5) & 5794 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(9)) \times T(7))/5 \\ 5382 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3) + T(5))) & 5795 &:= (-5 + T(T(9)) \times T(7))/5 \\ 5385 &:= (T(T(5)) + 8 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) & 5796 &:= T(6) \times T(T(9) - 7 - T(5)) \\ 5395 &:= -5 + T(9) \times T(3 \times 5) & 5824 &:= 4^{T(2)} \times T(8 + 5) \\ 5405 &:= T(50 - 4) \times 5 & 5832 &:= (T(2) \times T(3))^{8-5} \\ 5415 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-1 + T(4)) + T(5) & 5845 &:= -T(5) + T(T(T(4))) + T(8) \times T(T(5)) \\ 5432 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) & 5848 &:= -8 \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \\ 5433 &:= 3 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(5)) & 5852 &:= 2 \times T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \\ 5434 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(5)) & 5859 &:= T(9)/5 \times (T(T(8)) - T(5)) \\ 5445 &:= T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5) & 5865 &:= 5 \times T(6 \times 8) - T(5) \\ 5448 &:= 8 \times T(T((4 + 4))) + T(T(5)) & 5866 &:= T(66) + T(85) \\ 5475 &:= (T(5) \times T(7) - T(T(4))) \times T(5) & 5868 &:= T(8) \times (T(6) \times 8 - 5) \\ 5487 &:= (7 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(4)) \times T(5) & 5894 &:= -T(T(4)) + 9 \times (T(T(8)) - 5) \\ 5488 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) + 4 \times 5) & 5895 &:= T(5) + T(-9 + T(8)) \times T(5) \\ 5497 &:= T(7 + T(9)) \times 4 - T(5) & 5922 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(T(5))) \\ 5523 &:= (-T(T(3)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))/5) & 5925 &:= T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(9) + T(5)) \\ 5525 &:= (T(5) + 2) \times T(5 \times 5) & 5928 &:= 8 \times T(-2 + T(9) - 5) \\ 5534 &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))/5 & 5949 &:= 9 \times (T(4 \times 9) - 5) \\ 5535 &:= T(5) \times (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5)) \times 5) & 5955 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(5)) \times T(9) - T(T(5)) \\ 5537 &:= -7 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))/5 & 5976 &:= T(6) + (T(T(7)) - 9) \times T(5) \\ 5544 &:= T(T(-4 + T(4))) \times T(T(5))/5 & 5982 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 9 + T(5) \\ 5568 &:= 8 \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5) + T(5))) & 5983 &:= -T(3) + T(T(8)) \times 9 - 5 \\ 5597 &:= -T(7) + T(9) \times (5 + T(T(5))) & 5984 &:= -T(4) + T(T(8)) \times T(9)/5 \\ 5625 &:= 5^{T(2)} \times T(-6 + T(5)) & 5985 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(8)) + T(T(T(9))/T(5)) \\ 5655 &:= 5 \times 5 \times T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) & 5987 &:= -7 + T(T(8)) \times T(9)/5 \\ 5658 &:= (8 + T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5)) & 5994 &:= T(4 \times 9) \times T(9)/5 \\ 5664 &:= 4 \times 6 \times T(T(6)) + T(T(5)) & 5995 &:= 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5) \\ 5665 &:= T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5 & 5998 &:= T(T(8)) \times 9 + 9 - 5 \\ 5673 &:= 3 \times T(76 - T(5)) & 5999 &:= 9 \times T(T(9) - 9) + 5 \\ 5676 &:= 6 \times T(7 + T(6) + T(5)) & 6027 &:= 7 \times T(20 + T(6)) \\ 5688 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(-6 + T(5))) & 6125 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(T(2))) + T(1 + 6)) \\ 5724 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 2 + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) & 6135 &:= T(5) \times (3 + T(T(1 + 6))) \\ 5725 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \times 7 - T(5) & 6154 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (5 - 1) - 6 \\ 5726 &:= T(T(T(6 - 2))) + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) & 6162 &:= 2 \times T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \\ 5733 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \times (T(7) - T(5)) & 6192 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(9))) \times 1 \times 6 \\ 5735 &:= T(T(T(5))/3) \times 7 - 5 & 6194 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(9)) - 1) \times 6 \\ 5745 &:= -T(5) + (T(T(4)) - 7) \times T(T(5)) & 6195 &:= -T(5) + T(T(9)) \times 1 \times 6 \\ 5747 &:= -T(7) + T(T(4)) \times 7 \times T(5) & 6197 &:= -7 + (T(T(9)) - 1) \times 6 \\ 5775 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 5 & 6216 &:= 6 \times (1 + T(T(T(2) + 6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6222 &:= T(2) \times (-T(T(2)) + T(2^6)) \\ 6225 &:= -T(5) + T(2) \times T(2^6) \\ 6227 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(2) \times T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6)) \\ 6228 &:= T(8) \times (2 + T(T(2) \times 6)) \\ 6229 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)) - 2 + T(6) \\ 6234 &:= T(4^3) \times T(2) - 6 \\ 6235 &:= -5 + 3 \times T(2^6) \\ 6237 &:= (T(7) - 3 + 2) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6244 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(-T(2) + 6))) \\ 6246 &:= T(64) \times T(2) + 6 \\ 6249 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times T(T(2)) - T(6) \\ 6258 &:= (8 + T(T(5) \times T(2))) \times 6 \\ 6272 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(7)^{T(2)}/T(6) \\ 6278 &:= 8 \times T(7)^2 + 6 \\ 6279 &:= T(9 \times 7) \times T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ 6285 &:= (-T(5) + T(8 \times T(2))) \times T(6) \\ 6288 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8) + T(2))) + 6 \\ 6295 &:= -5 + T(T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6) \\ 6318 &:= 81 \times T(T(3) + 6) \\ 6321 &:= (1 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)) + T(6)) \\ 6327 &:= 7 \times T(2 \times T(T(3))) + 6 \\ 6336 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6 \\ 6342 &:= (2 + T(4 \times T(3))) \times T(6) \\ 6363 &:= (3 + T(T(6) + 3)) \times T(6) \\ 6374 &:= -T(4) + T(7) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) \\ 6375 &:= 5 \times T(-T(7) + T(T(3) + 6)) \\ 6377 &:= -7 + T(7) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) \\ 6384 &:= (4 + T(8 \times 3)) \times T(6) \\ 6391 &:= T(T(1 + 9)) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6399 &:= 9 \times (T(9) + T(36)) \\ 6426 &:= (6 + T(24)) \times T(6) \\ 6435 &:= (T(T(5)) - 3) \times T(4 + 6) \\ 6437 &:= T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) - T(6) \\ 6438 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + T(T(4)))/6 \\ 6447 &:= T(7) \times T(T(-4 + T(4))) - T(6) \\ 6453 &:= 3 \times (T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + 6) \\ 6456 &:= 6 \times (-5 + T(46)) \\ 6468 &:= (8 + T(6 \times 4)) \times T(6) \\ 6472 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7) + T(4) - 6 \\ 6474 &:= (-T(T(4)) - T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 6 \\ 6483 &:= -3 + (T(T(8) + T(4))) \times 6 \\ 6484 &:= T(4) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) - T(T(6)) \\ 6486 &:= 6 \times T(T(8) + 4 + 6) \\ 6489 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4 + 6)) \\ 6492 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(-9 + T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 6496 &:= 6 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(6)) \\ 6517 &:= T(T(7)) \times (1 + T(5)) + T(6) \\ 6524 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 - T(6) \\ 6525 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(2) + 5 + T(6))) \\ 6528 &:= 8 \times T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(6)) \\ 6534 &:= T(T(4)) \times (3 + T(T(5))) - T(T(6)) \\ 6545 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(4))) - 5 \times T(T(6)) \\ 6549 &:= -T(9) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 6 \\ 6552 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(5))) \times 56 \\ 6567 &:= T(7) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(5)) - T(6) \\ 6573 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) + 5 \times T(6) \\ 6574 &:= 4 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5)) - T(6)) \\ 6579 &:= T(T(9)) \times 7 - T(T(5) + T(6)) \\ 6582 &:= T(2)^8 + T(5) + 6 \\ 6594 &:= (T(4) + T(9)) \times T(T(5)) - 6 \\ 6615 &:= T(5) \times T(1 \times 6) \times T(6) \\ 6624 &:= 4 \times T(2 + T(6)) \times 6 \\ 6633 &:= (-3 + T(3)) \times T(66) \\ 6636 &:= T(T(6)/3) \times (6 + T(T(6))) \\ 6642 &:= 2 \times T(T(4) \times 6 + T(6)) \\ 6645 &:= -T(5) + T(4) \times T(6 \times 6) \\ 6648 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(4) - 6 - 6 \\ 6654 &:= T(4) \times T(T(5) + T(6)) - 6 \\ 6657 &:= 7 \times (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(T(6))) \\ 6678 &:= (87 + T(T(6))) \times T(6) \\ 6696 &:= (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 6 \times 6 \\ 6699 &:= (T(T(9))/T(9) + 6) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6721 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6727 &:= T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6732 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(3)))/7) \times 6 \\ 6742 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times T(7) - 6 \\ 6744 &:= (-4 + T(47)) \times 6 \\ 6754 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) + 7) - T(T(6)) \\ 6756 &:= (6 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 6 \\ 6762 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(7 + 6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6822 &:= T(T(2 \times T(T(2)))) + T(86) & 7296 &:= 6 \times (-9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7)) \\ 6825 &:= T(5^2) \times T(T(8)/6) & 7298 &:= T(T(8)) \times (9 + 2) - T(7) \\ 6828 &:= T(8) + T(2)^8 + T(T(6)) & 7299 &:= -9 + 9 \times 2 \times T(T(7)) \\ 6843 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(8) + T(6)) & 7308 &:= T(8) \times (T(T(T(03))) - (T(7))) \\ 6844 &:= 4 \times T(T(4) + 8 \times 6) & 7326 &:= 6 \times (T(2) + 3 \times T(T(7))) \\ 6855 &:= T(5) + T(T(5)) \times (T(8) + T(6)) & 7329 &:= (T(T(9)) + 2 \times T(3)) \times 7 \\ 6864 &:= T(4) \times (T(6) + T(T(8))) - 6 & 7332 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-3 + T(T(T(3)) + T(7))) \\ 6873 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(8) + T(6)) & 7335 &:= -T(5) + T(3) \times T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) \\ 6888 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(8) + T(T(6))) & 7343 &:= T(3) \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) - 7 \\ 6891 &:= (1 + 9) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) & 7353 &:= 3 \times (T(5) + T(3) \times T(T(7))) \\ 6894 &:= T(-4 + T(9)) \times 8 + 6 & 7356 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(5))/3) + T(T(7))) \\ 6924 &:= T(T(T(4)))/2 \times 9 - 6 & 7362 &:= T(2) \times 6 \times (3 + T(T(7))) \\ 6925 &:= -5 + (T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(6)) & 7365 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(6 + 3)) \times 7 \\ 6948 &:= T(8) \times (4 + 9 \times T(6)) & 7391 &:= -1 + (T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) \times 7 \\ 6954 &:= (4 + T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 6 & 7392 &:= (T(T(2)) \times T(9) - T(3)) \times T(7) \\ 6966 &:= (6 \times T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 6 & 7394 &:= T(4) \times T(T(9) - T(3)) - T(T(7)) \\ 6972 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7 \times (T(T(9)) - 6) & 7395 &:= T(5) \times (T(9 + T(T(3))) + T(7)) \\ 6978 &:= -T(8) + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(T(6)) & 7425 &:= 5 \times T(T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\ 6987 &:= -7 \times (T(8) - T(T(9))) - 6 & 7427 &:= -T(7) + T(2) \times T(T(4) \times 7) \\ 6993 &:= (T(3 \times 9) - T(9)) \times T(6) & 7428 &:= T(8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4 - T(7)) \\ 7112 &:= (T(T(T(T(2))) + 1) + 1) \times T(7) & 7435 &:= T(5)^3 + T(4) \times T(T(7)) \\ 7129 &:= T(9) + T(T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T(7) & 7443 &:= 3 \times (-4 + T(T(4) \times 7)) \\ 7133 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 31 - T(7) & 7452 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T(T(4)) - T(7) \\ 7157 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(5)) \times 17 & 7455 &:= T(5)/5 \times T(T(4) \times 7) \\ 7182 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(8) + T(-1 + T(7))) & 7482 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) \\ 7189 &:= (T(T(9)) - 8) \times 1 \times 7 & 7483 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + (-T(8) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) \\ 7196 &:= (-6 + T(T(9)) - 1) \times 7 & 7484 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + 8 \times T(47) \\ 7223 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 2) \times (T(2) + T(7)) & 7485 &:= 5 \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - 7) \\ 7224 &:= 4 \times 2 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 7 & 7514 &:= T(T(4) + 1) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(7)) \\ 7245 &:= T(T(5) \times T(4 - 2)) \times 7 & 7532 &:= T(2) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) - T(7) \\ 7248 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(4) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(7) & 7548 &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) \times 5 + T(7) \\ 7252 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5 + 2)) \times T(7) & 7568 &:= 8 \times (T(T(6) + T(5) + 7)) \\ 7259 &:= (T(9 \times 5) + 2) \times 7 & 7595 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 5) \times 7 \\ 7266 &:= T(6) \times (T(6) + T(-T(2) + T(7))) & 7596 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(-5 + 7)) \\ 7273 &:= T(T(3)) + (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7) & 7599 &:= T(9 \times 9) + T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) \\ 7279 &:= T(T(9)) \times 7 + T(T(2)) + T(7) & 7623 &:= T(T(3 \times 2)) \times T(T(6))/7 \\ 7288 &:= 8 \times (8 + T(T(T(2)) \times 7)) & 7626 &:= (T(T(6))^2 + T(6))/7 \\ 7289 &:= T(9) \times T(T(8)/2) - T(T(7)) & 7627 &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))/7 \\ 7293 &:= 3 \times (T(9)^2 + T(T(7))) & 7672 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7) - 6)) \times T(7) \\ 7294 &:= (T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(2)) \times 7 & 7714 &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7728 &:= T(8 \times 2 + 7) \times T(7) \\ 7735 &:= 5 \times (T(T(3 + 7)) + 7) \\ 7749 &:= 9 \times T(T(T(4)) - 7 - 7) \\ 7776 &:= 6^{(T(7)+7)/7} \\ 7784 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times (7 + 7) \\ 7819 &:= (T(T(9) + 1) + T(8)) \times 7 \\ 7826 &:= T(T(6)) \times (-2 + T(8)) - T(7) \\ 7833 &:= T(T(3)) \times (3 - T(8) + T(T(7))) \\ 7839 &:= 9 \times (T(-T(3) + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \\ 7845 &:= 5 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8) - 7) \\ 7847 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4)) - 8)) \times 7 \\ 7848 &:= T(8) \times (T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) + T(7)) \\ 7867 &:= T(T(7)) \times T(6) - T(T(8)) + 7 \\ 7893 &:= 3 \times (T(T(9)) + T(8 \times 7)) \\ 7896 &:= T(-6 + T(9) + 8) \times 7 \\ 7918 &:= T(T(8)) + (1 + T(T(9))) \times 7 \\ 7924 &:= (4 + T(2 + T(9))) \times 7 \\ 7963 &:= T(3) \times T(6 + T(9)) + 7 \\ 7965 &:= T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(T(9)) \times 7 \\ 7982 &:= 2 \times T(89) - T(7) \\ 8028 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(08) \\ 8127 &:= T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times (1 + 8) \\ 8136 &:= (T(T(6)) - T(3) + 1) \times T(8) \\ 8223 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) \times 2 \times T(T(8)) \\ 8225 &:= -T(T(5) - 2) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8228 &:= T(8) + 2^{T(T(T(2)))-8} \\ 8232 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(3^2))) \times 8 \\ 8234 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(8) \\ 8235 &:= -T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(2) + T(8))) \\ 8237 &:= -7 + (T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(8) \\ 8238 &:= -T(T(8)/3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8244 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) - 2) \times T(8) \\ 8245 &:= 5 \times (-4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \\ 8256 &:= (T(T(-6 + T(5))) - T(2)) \times 8 \\ 8265 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(6/2)) + T(8)) \\ 8267 &:= -T(7) - T(6) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8268 &:= T(8) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(2)) \times 8 \\ 8273 &:= (T(T(3) + 7))^2 - 8 \\ 8275 &:= -5 + T(T(7 + 2)) \times 8 \\ 8279 &:= -9 - T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8292 &:= T(T(T(2))) - T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8293 &:= 3 + (T(T(9)) + 2) \times 8 \\ 8294 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 8 \\ 8295 &:= -T(T(5) - 9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8297 &:= -7 + (T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 8 \\ 8308 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(03))) - 8 \\ 8312 &:= -T(2) - 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8313 &:= -3 + 1 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8316 &:= T((6 + 1) \times 3) \times T(8) \\ 8321 &:= -1 + T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8322 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(2 \times 3)) \times T(8) \\ 8323 &:= T(T(3))/T(2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8324 &:= T(4 \times 2) \times T(T(T(3))) + 8 \\ 8325 &:= -T(5) \times (T(T(2)) - T(-3 + T(8))) \\ 8326 &:= T(6 - 2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8328 &:= T(8)/T(2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8331 &:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8337 &:= 7 \times 3 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8343 &:= T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(8)) \\ 8344 &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8345 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) \\ 8348 &:= 8 \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8352 &:= (T(T(2)) - 5 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8) \\ 8364 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6) + T(T(3))) - T(T(8)) \\ 8372 &:= 2 \times T(T(7 \times 3 - 8)) \\ 8379 &:= 9 \times (T(7) + T(T(3) + T(8))) \\ 8382 &:= T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\ 8385 &:= (5 + 8) \times (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \\ 8388 &:= T(8) + T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) \\ 8415 &:= T(5) \times T(1 + 4 \times 8) \\ 8423 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 2^{T(4)} \times 8 \\ 8424 &:= 4 \times T(T(2)) \times T(-T(4) + T(8)) \\ 8452 &:= T(T(2))^5 + T(4) + T(T(8)) \\ 8458 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(5) - T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 8496 &:= (T(T(6)) + 9 - 4) \times T(8) \\ 8523 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8)) \\ 8525 &:= 5 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(58)) \\ 8526 &:= T(6) \times T(T(T(2) \times 5 - 8)) \\ 8532 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) + T(5))) \times T(8) \\ 8544 &:= 4 \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8552 &:= -T(2) + 5 \times T(58) & 9233 &:= T(T(3))^3 - T(-2 + 9) \\ 8567 &:= T(T(7)) \times T(6) + 5 + T(8) & 9234 &:= T(T(4 \times 3)) \times T(2) - 9 \\ 8568 &:= 8 \times T(6) \times (T(5) + T(8)) & 9252 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(5))^{T(2)} - 9 \\ 8572 &:= 2 \times (T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) + 8) & 9261 &:= T(1 \times 6)^{-T(T(2))+9} \\ 8574 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(7 - 5)) - (T(T(8))) & 9264 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times 6 - T(T(T(2))) + T(9) \\ 8576 &:= 67 \times (T(T(5)) + 8) & 9265 &:= -5 + T(6)^{T(2)} + 9 \\ 8592 &:= (-T(T(2)) + 9 \times T(T(5))) \times 8 & 9276 &:= -6 + 7 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(9) \\ 8624 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 2 \times T(T(6))) \times 8 & 9279 &:= (T(T(9)) - 7 + T(2)) \times 9 \\ 8642 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(46) \times 8 & 9282 &:= T(T(2)) \times (8^{T(2)} + T(T(9))) \\ 8644 &:= -4 + T(46) \times 8 & 9285 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - 2 - T(9)) \\ 8646 &:= 6 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(6)) \times T(8) & 9288 &:= T(8) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) \\ 8648 &:= 8 \times T(4 + 6 + T(8)) & 9294 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 9) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 8658 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(5) + 6 - 8) & 9297 &:= T(7) \times T(T(9)) - T(2)^9 \\ 8673 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(8))) & 9306 &:= T(6)^{03} + T(9) \\ 8674 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) & 9312 &:= T(2) \times (-1 + 3 \times T(T(9))) \\ 8679 &:= (9 + T(T(7))) \times T(6) - T(8) & 9315 &:= (5 + 1 + 3) \times T(T(9)) \\ 8739 &:= T(9) + T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + 8) & 9324 &:= 42 \times (T(T(T(3))) - 9) \\ 8742 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(7)) - T(T(8)) & 9333 &:= 3 \times (T(3) + 3 \times T(T(9))) \\ 8745 &:= T(5) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(7) + T(T(8))) & 9336 &:= T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3)) \times 9 \\ 8749 &:= (9 + 4) \times (7 + T(T(8))) & 9339 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9)) \\ 8764 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(6 \times 7) \times 8 & 9355 &:= (-5 + T(T(5)) \times T(3 + 9)) \\ 8784 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(8) - T(T(7))) \times 8 & 9369 &:= ((T(T(9)) + T((6 - 3))) \times 9) \\ 8824 &:= 4 \times (T(T(2 + 8)) + T(T(8))) & 9387 &:= -T(7) \times T(8) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(9) \\ 8827 &:= 7 \times (T(-2 + T(8)) + T(T(8))) & 9396 &:= (6 + T(T(9)) + 3) \times 9 \\ 8834 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(3) - T(-8 + T(8)) & 9397 &:= T(7) + (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9 \\ 8844 &:= 4 \times T(T(4 \times 8)/8) & 9424 &:= T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(4) + 9) \\ 8848 &:= (8 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 & 9426 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(9) \\ 8856 &:= 6 \times (5 + T(8)) \times T(8) & 9435 &:= -T(5) + T(T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(9) \\ 8895 &:= -T(5) + 9 \times T(8 + T(8)) & 9444 &:= 4 \times (T(-4 + T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) \\ 8925 &:= T(5) \times T(2 \times (9 + 8)) & 9445 &:= -5 + T(T(4) + T(4)) \times T(9) \\ 8928 &:= (8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9) \times T(8) & 9462 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + 6 \times T(T(T(4))) - 9 \\ 8968 &:= (86 + T(T(9))) \times 8 & 9465 &:= T(5) + T(6) \times T(4) \times T(9) \\ 8991 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (T(T(9)) - T(8)) & 9471 &:= T(T(-1 + 7)) \times (-4 + T(9)) \\ 9129 &:= -T(T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1 + T(9)) & 9485 &:= T(5) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9)) \\ 9195 &:= -T(T(5)) + 9 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) & 9495 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(9) + T(T(4) \times 9) \\ 9216 &:= T(6)^{1+2} - T(9) & 9546 &:= T(T(6)) + T(45) \times 9 \\ 9222 &:= T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) - T(9) & 9567 &:= (T(7) + T(T(-6 + T(5)))) \times 9 \\ 9225 &:= T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) \times 2 + T(T(9)) & 9576 &:= T(6) \times T(T(7)) + T(5) + T(T(9)) \\ 9231 &:= T(T(T(1 + 3))) \times T(T(2)) - 9 & 9585 &:= T(5) \times (-T(8) + T(5) \times T(9)) \\ 9232 &:= T(T(T(2)))^3 - 29 & 9586 &:= T(T(T(6) - 8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9594 &:= (T(T(T(4)) - 9) - T(5)) \times 9 & 9765 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(6) + 7 \times T(T(9)) \\
 9624 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6) - 9)) & 9795 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(7)) + T(T(9)) \\
 9639 &:= (T(9) + T(3)) \times T(6) \times 9 & 9825 &:= T(5) \times (-2 + T(T(8)) - 9) \\
 9644 &:= 4 \times (-4 + T(69)) & 9837 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 9 \\
 9645 &:= -T(5) + 4 \times T(69) & 9852 &:= -T(2) + T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - 9) \\
 9648 &:= (8 + 4) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) & 9882 &:= T(2)^8 + T(T(8) + T(9)) \\
 9667 &:= T(T(7)) + T(6)^{-6+9} & 9884 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 8 \times (8 + T(T(9))) \\
 9672 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(6) + T(9)) & 9927 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(2) \times 9) - T(T(9)) \\
 9693 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(9)) + T(6)) \times 9 & 9936 &:= 6 \times T(3) \times T(T(T(9)) / T(9)) \\
 9724 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 7 - T(T(9)) & 9945 &:= ((T(5) \times T((4 \times 9))) - T(9)) \\
 9728 &:= 8^{T(2)} \times (T(7) - 9) & 9963 &:= (-3 + 6) \times T(9 \times 9) \\
 9729 &:= T(9 \times 2 + T(7)) \times 9 & 9981 &:= T(T(1 \times 8)) + T(T(9)) \times 9 \\
 9742 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4))) \times 7 - T(T(9)) & 9985 &:= T(5) \times T(T(8)) - T(9) / 9 \\
 9747 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1. From now onwards the results are with unnecessary extra brackets, such as, "(...)". After simplifications, these can be removed easily.

2.4 General Representations: Five Digits Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 00265 &:= T(5 \times 6) - 200 & 01138 &:= (T(((8 \times T(3)) - 1)) + 10) \\
 00397 &:= T(T(7)) - 9 + 3 \times 00 & 01139 &:= (T(T(9)) - ((T(3) - 110))) \\
 00462 &:= 2 \times T(T(6 + 4 \times 00)) & 01144 &:= (4 \times (T(T(T((4 - 1)))) + (T(10)))) \\
 00465 &:= T(5 \times 6) + 4 \times 00 & 01145 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(4)) - T((1 \times 10))) \\
 00529 &:= T(T(9)) - T(T(2)) - 500 & 01146 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(4))) + ((1 - 10))) \\
 00637 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3))) + 6 \times 00 & 01149 &:= (T(T(9)) + (4 + 110)) \\
 00729 &:= 9^{T(2)} + 7 \times 00 & 01152 &:= -((T(2) - (T((5 + 1)) \times T(10)))) \\
 01025 &:= (T((T(5) \times T(2))) - 010) & 01155 &:= ((T(5) + (5 + 1)) \times T(10)) \\
 01028 &:= (-((8^{T(2)})) + T(T(010))) & 01156 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 5) + (1^{10})) \\
 01035 &:= T(((5 + 30) + 10)) & 01162 &:= (-((T((26 + 1))) + T(T(10)))) \\
 01045 &:= ((T(5) + (4)) \times T(010)) & 01163 &:= ((3 \times T(T((6 + 1)))) - (T(10))) \\
 01056 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(5) \times T(010))) & 01164 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(6)) - ((1 - 10))) \\
 01069 &:= (T(T(9)) - ((T(6) - T(010)))) & 01165 &:= ((5 \times T(T(6))) + (1 \times 10)) \\
 01088 &:= (T((T(8) + T(8))) - T(T(010))) & 01168 &:= (-8) + (T(6) \times (1 + T(10))) \\
 01122 &:= (2 \times T((T(2) \times (1 + 10)))) & 01173 &:= (-3) + T((-7) + T((1 \times 10))) \\
 01124 &:= (-4) + T((2 + T(-(1 - 10)))) & 01175 &:= ((-T(5)) - T(T(7))) + T((1 + T(10))) \\
 01127 &:= -((T(7) - (21 \times T(10)))) & 01179 &:= ((T(9) - T(T(7))) + T(T((1 \times 10)))) \\
 01128 &:= T((-8) + T(((2 - 1) \times 10))) & 01182 &:= (T(T(2)) + T((-((8 - 1)) + T(10))) \\
 01129 &:= (T((T(9) + 2)) + (1^{10})) & 01183 &:= (T(((T(3) \times 8) - 1)) + (T(10))) \\
 01132 &:= (-2) - (T(T(3)) \times (1 - T(10))) & 01184 &:= (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) + (1 + T(10))) \\
 01133 &:= -((T(T(T(T(3)) / 3)) - (-1) + T(T(10)))) & 01186 &:= (T((6 \times 8)) + (1 \times 10)) \\
 01134 &:= ((T(T((4 + 3))) \times (-1)) + T(T(10))) & 01189 &:= -((T((-9) + T(8)) - 1) - T(T(10))) \\
 01136 &:= (T((T((6 + 3)) + 1)) + (T(10))) & 01191 &:= (T((1 + T(9))) + (110)) \\
 01137 &:= (((T(T(7)) - 3) \times (-1)) + T(T(10))) & 01197 &:= (7 \times T(((9 - 1) + 10)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 01205** := $(50 + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(10)))$
01222 := $(-(T(2)) + T(((T(2) \times (-2)) + T(10))))$
01223 := $(-(T(3)/T(2)) + T(-(T(T(2)) - (T(10))))))$
01228 := $(-(T(T(8)) - T(2)) + T((T(T(2)) + (T(10))))))$
01229 := $(T((T(9) + T(2))) + (-2) + T(10))$
01231 := $(T((1 \times 3)) + T(-(T(T(2)) - (T(10))))))$
01232 := $(((-2) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) - T(T(10))$
01233 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(10))))$
01234 := $((T(4) \times T(T(3))) + (2^{10}))$
01235 := $((-5) - T((T(T(3)) + T(2)))) + T(T(10))$
01236 := $(6 \times ((T(3))^{T(2)} - 10))$
01238 := $(-(T((8 \times 3)) + 2)) + T(T(10))$
01239 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(3) - (210))))$
01241 := $((1 - T((4 \times T(T(2)))))) + T(T(10))$
01242 := $(-(T(24) - 2)) + T(T(10))$
01243 := $((T(3)^4 + 2) - T(10))$
01244 := $((4 \times T(T(4))) + (2^{10}))$
01245 := $(T(T((5 + 4))) + (210))$
01246 := $(T(6) + T(-(4 + 2)) + T(10))$
01247 := $(-T(7) + T(((T(4)/2) \times 10)))$
01248 := $(T((8 + 4)) \times (T(T(2)) + 10))$
01249 := $(T(T(9)) + (4 + 210))$
01271 := $(T((17 \times T(2))) - (T(10)))$
01272 := $(-(T(2) - T(((7 - 2) \times 10)))$
01273 := $((T(3) \times T(T(7)))/2) + (T(10))$
01276 := $((-6) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(10))$
01277 := $((T((7 \times 7)) - T(2)) + T(10))$
01278 := $(-(((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) + 2) - T(T(10))))$
01281 := $((-T(-(1 - 8))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(10))$
01282 := $(-((2^8) + 2)) + T(T(10))$
01283 := $(-3) + ((T(8)^2) - 10)$
01284 := $(-(4 \times (8^2))) + T(T(10))$
01285 := $((T(5) \times 82) + T(10))$
01287 := $(-(T((T(7) - (8 - 2))) - T(T(10))))$
01288 := $((T(8) \times T(8)) + ((2 - 10)))$
01291 := $(T((1 + T(9))) + (210))$
01292 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - (T(10)))$
01294 := $((4 - T(9)) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(10))$
01295 := $((T(5) \times T(9)) \times 2) - T(10)$
01297 := $((T(T(7)) + T((T(9) - 2))) - (T(10)))$
01298 := $(T((-8) + T(9)) + T(-(T(T(T(2))) - (T(10))))))$
01299 := $(-T((9 \times 9)) + (T(2) \times T(T(10))))$
01303 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(T(03)))) + T(T(10))$
01305 := $(T(50) + (3 \times 10))$
01309 := $(-(T(T(9 - 03))) - T(T(10)))$
01321 := $(1 - ((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(10))))$
01322 := $((2 \times T(T((2^3)))) - 10)$
01323 := $(-(((3^{T(2)}) \times (T(3) - T(10))))$
01324 := $(4 \times (T(23) + T(10)))$
01325 := $((5 \times T(23)) - T(10))$
01326 := $(6 \times (T(23) - T(10)))$
01329 := $(9 - ((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(10))))$
01333 := $(-T((3^3)) + T((3 + T(10))))$
01335 := $(T(5) + ((3 + T(T(3))) \times T(10)))$
01336 := $((-T(6)) - T(T(3))) + T((-3) + T(10))$
01337 := $((T(7) - T(T((3 + 3)))) + T(T(10)))$
01339 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(3) - 310)))$
01341 := $((1 + T(4))^3 + 10)$
01342 := $(-T((2 \times 4)) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01344 := $((-4) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) + T(T(10))$
01345 := $(T(T((5 + 4))) + 310)$
01347 := $(-T(7) - ((4 + T(T(3))) \times (-T(10))))$
01348 := $((-(8 \times 4)) \times T(3)) + T(T(10))$
01352 := $(2 \times (T(T((5 + 3))) + 10))$
01353 := $((3 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(3)) - 10))$
01354 := $((4^5) + (T(3) \times T(10)))$
01355 := $(5 \times ((-T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(10)))$
01357 := $(-((T(T(T((7 - 5)))) - (T((-3) + T(10))))))$
01358 := $((8 \times T((T(5) + 3))) - 10)$
01361 := $(T(16) + T(-(T(3) - T(10))))$
01363 := $((T(3) - T(6)) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01365 := $(T(5) \times T(((6 - 3) + 10)))$
01366 := $(-((6 + 6)) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01371 := $(-1) - (T(7) \times (T(3) - T(10)))$
01372 := $(-T(2) - ((T(7) - 3) \times T(10)))$
01373 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 7) \times T(3)) - (T(10))$
01374 := $(-4) + T((7 \times T(3)) + 10))$
01375 := $((T(5) + (7 + 3)) \times T(10))$
01376 := $((6 \times T((7 \times 3))) - 10)$
01381 := $(T((T(1 + 8)) + T(3))) + (T(10))$
01383 := $(-((3 - 8)) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01384 := $(4 \times (T(8) + 310))$
01385 := $((T(5) - 8) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01387 := $(-((T(-(7 - (8 \times 3)))) - T(T(10))))$
01391 := $(T((1 + T(9))) + 310)$
01393 := $((T(3) + 9) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01394 := $((4 - T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(10))))$
01396 := $((6 \times T(T((9 - 3)))) + 10)$
01397 := $((T(7) - 9) + T((-3) + T(10)))$
01398 := $((89 - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(10))$
01399 := $((T(T(9)) - T((T(9) + 3))) + T(T(10)))$
01404 := $(-T((4 \times 04))) + T(T(10))$
01421 := $(T(-(1 \times 2)) + T(T(4))) - 10$

- 01424** := -((((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) - T(T(10))))
01425 := (-(((5^{T(2)}) - T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01426 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(2))) + (4 × 10))
01427 := (((7^{T(2)}) × 4) + T(10))
01428 := (-(((T(8) × T(2)) + (4))) + T(T(10)))
01432 := (((T(2)³) × (-4)) + T(T(10)))
01433 := (T((-3) + T((T(3) + (4)))) + T(T(10)))
01434 := (T(T(T(4))) - (T(3) - (T(4) × (-10))))
01436 := ((6 × T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) - T(T(10)))
01437 := (((T(T(7)) + T(3)))/(-4)) + T(T(10)))
01438 := ((8 × T(T(T(3)))) - (410))
01439 := (T(T(9)) - ((T(3) - 410)))
01442 := ((2 - (T(4) × T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01443 := ((3 - (T(4) × T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01444 := ((4 - (T(4) × T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01445 := ((5⁴) + T((4 × 10)))
01447 := ((7 - (T(4) × T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01448 := ((8 - (T(4) × T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01449 := (T(T(9)) + (4 + 410))
01452 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) + T((-4) + T(10)))
01453 := -((((T(T(3)) + T((T(5) - 4)))) - T(T(10))))
01455 := (((-5) × T(5)) - T(4)) + T(T(10)))
01458 := (-((T((8 × 5))/T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01459 := (-((9 × (5 + 4))) + T(T(10)))
01462 := (-T(((2 + 6) + 4)) + T(T(10)))
01464 := (-((T(4)) - T((T(6) - T(4)))) + T(T(10)))
01465 := (((T(T(5)) + T(6)) × T(4)) + T(T(10)))
01466 := (-((T((6 + 6)) - 4)) + T(T(10)))
01467 := (-((7) - T((T(6) - T(4)))) + T(T(10)))
01468 := (-((8 + 64)) + T(T(10)))
01483 := (-((3) + T(T(8))) + T((4 × 10)))
01484 := (-(((T(4) + T(8)) + T(4))) + T(T(10)))
01485 := T((((5 × 8) + 4) + 10))
01486 := (T((T(6) + (8 × 4))) + T(T(10)))
01489 := (-((T(9)) - T(T((8/4)))) + T(T(10)))
01491 := (T((1 + T(9))) + 410)
01492 := (((T(2) + 9) × (-4)) + T(T(10)))
01493 := (-(((T(3) + T(9)) - 4)) + T(T(10)))
01494 := (-((4 × 9) - T(4)) + T(T(10)))
01495 := ((T(5) × T(9)) + T((4 × 10)))
01499 := (T((9 + T(9))) + (4 + 10))
01504 := (-T((40/5)) + T(T(10)))
01505 := (-((50) + T(5)) + T(T(10)))
01506 := (T(T(6)) - (0 - T((5 × 10))))
01507 := (-((T(7) - (0 - 5))) + T(T(10)))
01521 := (((-1) - T(2)) - T(5)) + T(T(10)))
01522 := (-((T(2) + (T(2) × 5))) + T(T(10)))
01523 := ((-32) + T(5)) + T(T(10)))
01524 := (((-4) + T(2)) - T(5)) + T(T(10)))
01525 := (-5) - (T(2) × (-510))
01526 := ((T(T((6 × 2))) - T(5)) - T(T(10)))
01527 := (-((T(7) - (T(2) × 5))) + T(T(10)))
01528 := ((T(8)/(2 - 5)) + T(T(10)))
01529 := ((9 × T((T(2) + T(5)))) - 10)
01561 := ((16 + 5) + T(T(10)))
01562 := ((2 × (6 + 5)) + T(T(10)))
01564 := ((4 × (T(6) - T(5))) + T(T(10)))
01565 := (((T(5) × T(6)) × 5) - 10)
01566 := (((T(T(6))/T(6)) + T(5)) + T(T(10)))
01567 := ((7 × T(T(6))) - (5 × 10))
01568 := (T(((8 - 6) + 5)) + T(T(10)))
01569 := ((9 × T(T(6))) - (510))
01571 := ((T((1 + 7)) - 5) + T(T(10)))
01572 := ((27 + 5) + T(T(10)))
01573 := (((-3) + T((-7) + T(5))) + T(T(10)))
01574 := ((4 × T(T(7))) - (5 × 10))
01575 := (T(5) × (7 × (5 + 10)))
01579 := ((T(9) - T(T((7 - 5)))) + T(T(10)))
01603 := ((3 × T(06)) + T(T(10)))
01605 := (T(50) - (-6) × T(10))
01606 := ((60 + 6) + T(T(10)))
01607 := ((7 × T(T(06))) - 10)
01609 := ((90 - T(6)) + T(T(10)))
01622 := (2 × (-((T(2)⁶)) + T(T(10))))
01624 := (4 × (T(26) + T(10)))
01627 := ((T(T(7)))/(-2)) + T((6 × 10))
01628 := ((82 + 6) + T(T(10)))
01629 := (9 × (T((T(2) × 6)) + 10))
01631 := (T(((1 + T(3)) + 6)) + T(T(10)))
01632 := ((2 × T(3)) × T((6 + 10)))
01634 := (T((4 + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(10))))
01635 := (-5) × (3 + (-6) × T(10))
01636 := ((T(63)/T(6)) + T(T(10)))
01637 := ((T(T(7)) + T(3)) + T((-6) + T(10)))
01642 := (((T(2)⁴) + T(6)) + T(T(10)))
01643 := (T((T((3 × 4)) - T(6))) - 10)
01644 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) - 6) + T(T(10)))
01645 := (T(T((5 + 4))) + (610))
01648 := ((T((8 + 4)) × T(6)) + 10)
01649 := (T(T(9)) + (4 + 610))
01671 := (-1) - ((-7) × T(T(6))) - T(T(10))
01672 := (T((2 × T(7))) + ((T(6) + T(10))))
01673 := -((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) × (-10))))
01676 := (T(((6) + T(7)) - 6)) + T(T(10))

$$\begin{aligned} 01677 &:= (T((T(T(7))/7)) + ((T(6) - T(10)))) \\ 01691 &:= (T((1 + T(9))) + (610)) \\ 01693 &:= ((T((3 + 9)) \times T(6)) + T(10)) \\ 01695 &:= ((T(5) \times (-9)) + T((6 \times 10))) \\ 01697 &:= ((T((7 + 9)) + T(6)) + T(T(10))) \\ 01708 &:= ((8 \times T(T(07))) - T(T(10))) \\ 01721 &:= ((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((7 + T(10)))) \\ 01722 &:= (2 \times T(((T(2) + T(7)) + 10)) \\ 01723 &:= (T((T(T(3)) - 2) - (7 - T(T(10)))) \\ 01725 &:= (T(5) \times (T((2 \times 7) + 10)) \\ 01726 &:= ((62 \times T(7)) - 10) \\ 01728 &:= ((T(8)/T(2))^{-7+10}) \\ 01729 &:= ((9 \times T(2)) \times 7) + T(T(10)) \\ 01732 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(((T(T(3))/7) + (T(10)))) \\ 01735 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(3) + (7))) + T(T(10))) \\ 01736 &:= (T(63) - (T(7) \times 10)) \\ 01743 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((4 \times 7) + T(10))) \\ 01745 &:= -((T(5) - ((4 + T(7)) \times T(10))) \\ 01748 &:= ((T(8) + T(4)) \times (T(7) + 10)) \\ 01749 &:= (T(T(9)) + (4 + 710)) \\ 01752 &:= ((2 \times T(T(5))) - T(7)) + T(T(10)) \\ 01756 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(5) - (T(7) \times T(10)))) \\ 01761 &:= ((T((1 + T(6))) \times 7) - 10) \\ 01762 &:= (((-2) + T(T(6))) - (7)) + T(T(10)) \\ 01765 &:= (-5) + T(((T(6) + T(7)) + 10)) \\ 01768 &:= (8 \times (T(T(T((T(6)/7)))) - 10) \\ 01769 &:= (((-9) + T(T(6))) + (7)) + T(T(10)) \\ 01784 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(8) - (T(7) \times 10)))) \\ 01785 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(8) + T(7)) + T(10))) \\ 01786 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 8) - (7 + T(10))) \\ 01791 &:= (T((1 + T(9))) + 710) \\ 01792 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(9 - 7)))) + T(T(10))) \\ 01793 &:= (T((T(3) + (9 + 7))) + T(T(10))) \\ 01794 &:= (((-4) \times (-T(9) - T(T(7)))) - 10) \\ 01795 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(9) - T(7))) + T(T(10))) \\ 01822 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2) \times 8) - 10) \\ 01824 &:= (T((T(T(4)) + 2)) + T((8 + 10))) \\ 01825 &:= (-5) + T(-((2 - 8) \times 10)) \\ 01826 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + (8 \times T(10))) \\ 01843 &:= (((-3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(8)))) + 10) \\ 01844 &:= -((T((4 \times 4)) - (T(8) \times T(10))) \\ 01845 &:= (T(54) - (T(8) \times (-10))) \\ 01848 &:= (8 \times T(T(((4 - 8) + 10))) \\ 01849 &:= (T(T(9)) + (4 + 810)) \\ 01852 &:= ((2 \times (T(T(5)) + T(8))) + T(T(10))) \\ 01855 &:= (((T(5) \times T(5)) \times 8) + T(10)) \\ 01856 &:= ((T(6) \times T((5 + 8))) - T(10)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 01858 &:= ((T((T(8) - T(5))) \times 8) + 10) \\ 01862 &:= (((-T(2)) - T(T(6))) \times (-8)) - 10) \\ 01865 &:= (T((5^{-6+8})) + T(T(10))) \\ 01866 &:= (6 \times (T(T(6)) + ((8 \times 10)))) \\ 01872 &:= (2 \times (T((7 + T(8))) - 10)) \\ 01873 &:= ((T((-3) + T(7)) + 8) + T(T(10))) \\ 01874 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 7)) - T(T(8))) + (T(10))) \\ 01875 &:= ((T(5) \times (-7)) + (T(8) \times T(10))) \\ 01891 &:= T(-((1 - ((9 \times 8) - 10))) \\ 01892 &:= (2 \times T((T(9) + ((8 - 10)))) \\ 01893 &:= (3 \times ((-T(9) + T(T(8))) + 10)) \\ 01895 &:= (-5) \times ((-9) \times T(8) - T(10)) \\ 01898 &:= (((8 + T(9)) \times T(8)) - 10) \\ 01899 &:= (-((9 \times 9)) + (T(8) \times T(10))) \\ 01905 &:= (T(50) + T((T(9) - 10))) \\ 01924 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) \times (9 + T(10)))) \\ 01925 &:= (-((5 \times (2 - 9))) \times T(10)) \\ 01926 &:= (T((T(6) \times T(2))) - ((9 \times 10))) \\ 01928 &:= (T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) + (T(T(9)) - 10)) \\ 01936 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(3))) - T(9)) + T(T(10))) \\ 01939 &:= (T(T(9)) - ((T(3) - 910))) \\ 01943 &:= (3 \times T((4 \times 9)) - T(10)) \\ 01944 &:= (-T((4 \times 4)) + T((9 + T(10)))) \\ 01945 &:= ((T((5 \times 4)) \times 9) + T(10)) \\ 01946 &:= (T(6) - ((T(4) - T(9)) \times T(10))) \\ 01947 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (T(4) - 9)) + T(T(10))) \\ 01949 &:= (T(T(9)) + (4 + 910)) \\ 01953 &:= T(((3 + 5) \times 9) - 10) \\ 01955 &:= ((-5) - T(T(5))) + T((9 + T(10))) \\ 01961 &:= (T(((1 + 6) \times 9)) - T(10)) \\ 01963 &:= ((T((T(3) + T(6))) + T(9)) + T(T(10))) \\ 01965 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(6)) - ((T(9) + T(10)))) \\ 01975 &:= ((T(5) \times (-7)) + T((9 + T(10)))) \\ 01976 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(7))) + 9) + T(T(10))) \\ 01993 &:= ((T((-3) + T(9))) + T(T(9))) + (T(10)) \\ 01995 &:= (T((5 + 9)) \times (9 + 10)) \\ 01996 &:= ((T((T(6) + 9)) - 9) + T(T(10))) \\ 01997 &:= (T((7 \times 9)) - (9 + 10)) \\ 01999 &:= (-((9 \times 9)) + T((9 + T(10)))) \\ 02036 &:= (T(63) - (0 - 20)) \\ 02136 &:= (T(63) + (120)) \\ 02142 &:= (2 \times (T(41) + T(20))) \\ 02144 &:= (T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - (1^2 0)) \\ 02145 &:= T((5 + ((4 - 1) \times 20))) \\ 02163 &:= (T(((3 \times T(6)) - 1)) + (T(20))) \\ 02165 &:= (T((T((5 + 6)) - 1)) + (20)) \\ 02168 &:= (8 \times (61 + T(20))) \end{aligned}$$

- 02175** := $(5 \times T((T(7) + (1^2 0))))$
02184 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) - (120)))$
02191 := $(T(T(((1 + 9) + 1))) - (20))$
02192 := $(T(T((2 + 9))) + ((1 - 20)))$
02208 := $(8 \times T((T(02) + (20))))$
02231 := $(T(T((13 - 2))) + (20))$
02234 := $(T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (T(2) + (20)))$
02235 := $(((T(5) \times 3)^2) + T(20))$
02236 := $(T(63) + (220))$
02242 := $(T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(2)) + (20))))$
02244 := $(4 \times T(((T(4) + T(2)) + (20))))$
02252 := $(T(T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) + (T(T(T(2))) + (20)))$
02255 := $(55 \times (T(T(T(2))) + (20)))$
02268 := $((T(8) \times T(6)) \times T((2 + (2 \times 0))))$
02272 := $-((T(T(2)) - T((7 + (T(2) \times 20))))$
02274 := $(-4) + T((7 + (T(2) \times 20)))$
02275 := $(T(((5 \times 7) \times 2)) - T(20))$
02276 := $(T(67) - (2 + (2 \times 0)))$
02278 := $T(((T(8) + T(7)) + T((2 + (2 \times 0))))$
02283 := $(3 \times (T((T(8) + 2)) + (20)))$
02285 := $((-5) + T((8^2))) + T(20)$
02286 := $(T(68) - (T(2) \times 20))$
02287 := $(T((T(7) + T(8))) - (T(2) - T(20)))$
02288 := $((T((8 \times 8)) - 2) + T(20))$
02289 := $((9 \times T(T((8 - 2)))) + (T(20)))$
02292 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times 2) + (T(20))$
02295 := $((T(5) \times (-9)) \times (T(2) - (20)))$
02315 := $(5 \times (T((1 + T(T(3)))) + (T(20)))$
02336 := $(T(63) + 320)$
02343 := $(-3) + T(-((4 \times (3 - 20))))$
02345 := $((5 \times T((T(4) \times 3))) + (20))$
02355 := $(T(5) \times (-53) + T(20))$
02356 := $((T(65) + T(T(T(3)))) - (20))$
02358 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times (3 + (2 \times 0)))$
02373 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-7 - (T(3) \times (-20))))$
02376 := $((6 \times T(T(7))) - (3 \times 20))$
02392 := $(2 \times (T((T(9) + 3)) + (20)))$
02395 := $(T((T(5) + (9 \times T(3)))) - (20))$
02411 := $(T(T(11)) + (T(4) \times 20))$
02435 := $(T((-T(5)) - (T(T(3)) \times (-4)))) + (20)$
02436 := $(T(63) + 420)$
02457 := $(-T(7)) + T(((5 \times T(4)) + (20)))$
02477 := $((-T(7)) + T((7 \times T(4)))) + (20)$
02492 := $(-T(2)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(4))) + (20))$
02493 := $(3 \times (-9) + (4 \times T(20)))$
02495 := $((5 \times 9) \times T(T(4))) + (20)$
02497 := $(T(T(7)) + (-9) + (T(4) \times T(20)))$
02505 := $(T((-50) + T(T(5)))) + (20)$
02511 := $(T(T(11)) + (T(5) \times 20))$
02535 := $(T(5) + ((-3) + T(5)) \times T(20))$
02536 := $(T(63) + 520)$
02544 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((4^5) - 20))$
02568 := $(8 \times (T(6) + (T(5) \times 20)))$
02576 := $((6 \times T(T(7))) + T(T(5))) + (20)$
02583 := $(3 \times T((T(8) + (5 + (2 \times 0))))$
02584 := $((4 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(5)))) - (20))$
02585 := $-((T(5) - (8 \times T((5 + 20))))$
02636 := $(T(63) + (620))$
02637 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) + (20))$
02646 := $(T(6) \times ((-4) \times T(6)) + T(20))$
02648 := $(T(((8 + 4) \times 6)) + (20))$
02652 := $((-2) + T(5)) \times (-6) + T(20))$
02655 := $(-T(T(5)) + T(-((T((-5) + T(6))) - (T(20))))$
02664 := $(4 \times T(((6 \times 6) + (2 \times 0))))$
02666 := $((T(6) \times T(6)) \times 6) + (20)$
02667 := $((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(6) + T(20)))$
02674 := $(T((T(4) \times 7)) - ((T(6) - T(20))))$
02692 := $(2 \times (T((T(9) + (6))) + (20)))$
02715 := $(T(5) \times ((-1) - T(7)) + T(20))$
02746 := $((6 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7)))) - (20))$
02747 := $(T(74) - T((7 + (2 \times 0))))$
02752 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(7))) - (20)$
02757 := $((T(T(7)) - (T(5))) \times 7) + (20)$
02758 := $((T((8 + 5)) \times T(7)) + T(20))$
02759 := $(T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))) - T(-((7 - 20)))$
02765 := $((5 \times T((6 + T(7)))) - (T(20)))$
02766 := $(T((T((6 + 6)) - (7))) + (T(20)))$
02775 := $T((5 + ((7 \times 7) + 20)))$
02779 := $((-9) + T(T(7))) \times (7 + (2 \times 0))$
02808 := $(T(8) \times T(((0 - 8) + 20)))$
02834 := $((T(4) + 3) \times (8 + T(20)))$
02836 := $(T(63) + 820)$
02842 := $((T(2) + (4)) \times T((8 + 20)))$
02846 := $(-((T(T(6)) + (4))) + T(T(-((8 - 20))))$
02863 := $(T(T((T(3) + (6)))) - (8 + T(20)))$
02865 := $((T(5) - T(T(6))) + T(T(-((8 - 20))))$
02868 := $((8 + T(T(6))) \times (-8 - 20))$
02871 := $(T((1 \times 78)) - T(20))$
02873 := $((3^7) + T(T(8))) + (20)$
02874 := $((4 \times T((T(7) + 8))) + (T(20)))$
02878 := $(T(8) + (7 \times T((8 + 20))))$
02891 := $(-T(19)) + T(T(-((8 - 20))))$
02892 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-9)) + T(T(-((8 - 20))))$
02895 := $(T(5) \times (-9 + 8)) + T(20))$

- 02936** := $(T(63) + 920)$
02945 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + (20)$
02946 := $(T(((T(6) + T(4)) + T(9))) + (20))$
02955 := $(T(5) + ((5 + 9) \times T(20)))$
02982 := $(2 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) - (T(20))))$
02983 := $(T((3 - (T(T(8)) / (-9)))) - (20))$
02986 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(T(8)) / 9))) - (20))$
03111 := $(T(T((1 + 11))) + (30))$
03142 := $(2 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (1 + 30)))$
03184 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) + 130))$
03185 := $(5 \times (T(T(8)) + ((1 - 30))))$
03189 := $((9 \times T(T((8 - 1)))) - (T(30)))$
03192 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - ((1 - 30))))$
03197 := $(T((T(7) + T(9))) + (T((1 + 30))))$
03208 := $(T(80) - (2 + 30))$
03218 := $((8 \times T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) - (30))$
03227 := $(-7) \times ((2 + 2) - T(30))$
03243 := $(3 \times T(((4^2) + 30))$
03248 := $(8 \times T(-((4 - 2) - 30)))$
03252 := $-((T(2) + (-((5 + 2) \times T(30))))$
03255 := $((5 + 5) - T(2)) \times T(30)$
03272 := $(T(2) - (-7) \times (2 + T(30)))$
03273 := $(-3) + (7 \times (T(2) + T(30)))$
03279 := $(T(9) - (7 \times (T(2) - T(30))))$
03282 := $(T(T(2)) \times (82 + T(30)))$
03289 := $(T((T(9) + T(8))) - (2 + 30))$
03291 := $(T(((1 \times 9)^2)) - (30))$
03297 := $(-7) \times ((-9) + T(2)) - T(30))$
03315 := $(T((T(5) \times (-1) + T(3))) + (T(30)))$
03318 := $(T(81) - (3 + (3 \times 0)))$
03342 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-4) + T((3 + 30)))$
03345 := $((5 + T(4))^3 - (30))$
03355 := $(-5) \times (-5 - T((T(3) + (30))))$
03363 := $(-3) - (-6) \times T((3 + 30))$
03366 := $(6 \times T(((6 - 3) + 30))$
03382 := $-((T(T(T(2))) - T(-((8 - (3 \times 30))))$
03384 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(3) \times 30)))$
03391 := $(T((T((1 + 9)) + T(T(3)))) + (T(30)))$
03403 := $T(((3) + T(T(04))) + (30))$
03414 := $((T(41) \times 4) - (30))$
03423 := $((3 \times (T(T(2))^4)) - (T(30)))$
03424 := $(-T(T((4 + 2))) + T((T(T(4)) + (30))))$
03425 := $(-T(T(5)) - ((-2) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(30)))$
03426 := $(-((T(T(6)) - 2)) + T((T(T(4)) + (30))))$
03445 := $(-T((5 \times 4)) + T((T(T(4)) + (30))))$
03446 := $(T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(30))))$
03469 := $((T(9) - T(T(6))) + T((T(T(4)) + (30))))$
03475 := $-((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(4))) + (T(30))))$
03478 := $(-8) + T((T(7) + T(T((4 + (3 \times 0))))))$
03482 := $(2 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(30)))$
03484 := $((4 \times T(T(8))) + T((T(4) + (30))))$
03486 := $T((T(6) + ((8 \times 4) + 30)))$
03516 := $(-6) \times ((-1) - T(T(5))) - (T(30))$
03522 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((2 + T(T(5))) + (T(30))))$
03523 := $((T(T(T(3))) / (-T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03524 := $((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)) \times 30)$
03525 := $((T(5)^{T(2)}) + (5 \times 30))$
03542 := $((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times 30)$
03557 := $(-((T(7) + T(5))) + (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03582 := $(2 \times (T((T(8) + T(5))) + (T(30))))$
03585 := $-((T(5) + ((-8) \times T(5)) \times 30))$
03586 := $(-((6 + 8)) + (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03591 := $(-((1 \times 9)) + (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03597 := $-((T(-((7 - 9))) - (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03599 := $(-((9/9)) + (T(T(5)) \times 30))$
03609 := $(T(90) - T(6)) - T(30)$
03615 := $((T(5) \times T((-1) + T(6))) + (T(30)))$
03625 := $(T((T(5) + (2^6))) + (T(30)))$
03645 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) \times T(6)) - (30)$
03655 := $T(((5 \times (5 + 6)) + 30))$
03672 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((7 \times T(6)) + T(30)))$
03675 := $((-T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(6) \times T(30)))$
03684 := $(T((T(4) \times 8)) - ((T(6) - T(30))))$
03685 := $(T((T((5 + 8)) - (6))) + (30))$
03693 := $(T((-3) + T(9)) - (-6) \times T(30))$
03699 := $(9 \times (-((9 \times 6)) + T(30)))$
03715 := $(-5) + ((1 + 7) \times T(30))$
03721 := $(T(T(-((1 - (2 \times 7)))) - (T(30)))$
03749 := $(T(T((9 + 4))) + ((T(7) - T(30))))$
03754 := $((4 \times T((T(5) + T(7)))) - (30))$
03755 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) - (T(30)))$
03765 := $((T(5) \times T((-6) + T(7))) - (30))$
03768 := $(8 \times (T((T(6) / 7)) + (T(30))))$
03784 := $(4 \times T((T(8) + (7 + (3 \times 0))))$
03789 := $((-9) + T(87)) - (30)$
03816 := $(6 \times (T(18) + T(30)))$
03822 := $(T(T(2)) + (T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8)) - (30))))$
03845 := $((-5) \times (-T(4)) - T(T(8))) + (T(30))$
03849 := $(94 \times T(8)) + T(30)$
03852 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(8))) + (T(30)))$
03855 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(5) + (8 \times T(30))))$
03856 := $(T((T(6) - 5)) + (8 \times T(30)))$
03858 := $(T(((T(8) + T(5)) + T(8))) + (30))$
03867 := $((7 \times T(6)) + (8 \times T(30)))$

- 03876** := $(6 \times (T(T(7)) + (8 \times 30)))$
03885 := $(5 \times (T(8) + T((8 + 30))))$
03894 := $((T((T(4) \times 9)) - T(T(8))) + (T(30)))$
03945 := $-((T(T(5)) - T((T(4) \times 9))) + (30))$
03954 := $-((T(T(T(T((T(4)/5)))) - (9 \times T(30))))$
03964 := $((T(4) - T(T(6))) - ((-9) \times T(30)))$
03972 := $(2 \times (T((7 \times 9)) - (30)))$
03975 := $((T((5 + 7)) \times T(9)) + T(30))$
03978 := $((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (9 + (3 \times 0)))$
04092 := $-((T(2) - T((90 + (4 \times 0))))$
04105 := $(-5) \times ((0 - 1) - T(40))$
04115 := $(5 \times (T((1 + 1)) + T(40)))$
04125 := $(5 \times (T(T(2)) + (-1) + T(40)))$
04135 := $(5 \times ((T(3) + 1) + T(40)))$
04185 := $(T(T((5 + 8))) - (1^4 0))$
04205 := $(5 \times (T(T(T(02))) + (T(40))))$
04212 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1) + T(-((T(2) - 40))))$
04226 := $(T(T((T((6 - 2)) + T(2)))) + 40)$
04235 := $(5 \times ((3^{T(2)}) + T(40)))$
04236 := $(6 \times (T((T(3)^2)) + 40))$
04255 := $((5 - T(T(5))) \times (T(2) - 40))$
04262 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(40))))$
04269 := $(T(T(9)) - (6 - T(2 \times 40)))$
04272 := $(-T(T(2))) + T(-((T(7) - (T(2) \times 40))))$
04274 := $(-4) + T(-((T(7) - (T(2) \times 40))))$
04275 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(7) - T(2))) - 40))$
04285 := $((T(5) \times T(T((8 - 2)))) + (T(40)))$
04295 := $(-5) \times ((-T(9)) + T(T(2))) - (T(40)))$
04296 := $((T(6) + T(T(9))) + T((2 \times 40)))$
04324 := $(4 \times T((2 \times 3) + 40))$
04325 := $(5 \times (T((T(2) \times 3)) + (T(40))))$
04329 := $(9 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + 40))$
04332 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3)) - 40))$
04335 := $(T((T(5) \times T(3))) - (T(3) \times (-40)))$
04358 := $(T(85) + T(-((3 - 40))))$
04371 := $T(((1 - T(7)) + ((3 \times 40))))$
04375 := $(5 \times (T((7 + 3)) + T(40)))$
04376 := $(T(T((6 + 7))) + T(-((T(T(3)) - 40))))$
04382 := $((2 \times T(T((8 + 3)))) - 40)$
04385 := $(-5) \times ((-T(8)) - T(T(3))) - (T(40)))$
04392 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (T((93 + (4 \times 0))))$
04411 := $(T(T(11)) + (T(T(4)) \times 40))$
04424 := $(-T((4^2))) + T((T(T(4)) + 40))$
04425 := $(T(((T(5) \times T(T(2))) + (4))) - 40)$
04428 := $(T(8) \times (T(2) + T((T(T(4)) - 40))))$
04432 := $((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(40)))$
04435 := $((5 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(40)))$
04439 := $((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))) + (T(40)))$
04452 := $(-T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) - (T(40)))$
04465 := $T(((T(5) \times 6) + (4 + (4 \times 0))))$
04475 := $(-5) + (T(7) \times (4 \times 40))$
04476 := $(-6) \times (74 - T(40))$
04516 := $((T(T(6)) \times (1 + T(5))) + (T(40)))$
04522 := $(2 \times (T(T(-((T(2) - T(5)))) - (T(40))))$
04527 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (5 \times T(40)))$
04555 := $(-5) + T((55 + 40))$
04565 := $(T((5 \times 6)) + (5 \times T(40)))$
04576 := $-(((T(T(6)) - 7) - (T(T(5)) \times 40)))$
04587 := $((7 \times (T(T(8)) - 5)) - 40)$
04593 := $(3 \times (-9) + T((T(5) + 40)))$
04595 := $((-5) + T(95)) + 40$
04615 := $((T(5) \times T((1 + T(6)))) + (T(40)))$
04616 := $(T((6 \times 16)) - 40)$
04624 := $(T((4^2)) \times (-6 - 40))$
04634 := $((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) - ((-6) \times T(40))$
04653 := $(-3) + T((56 + 40))$
04667 := $-((T((T(7) - 6)) - (6 \times T(40))))$
04683 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-8) + T(T((6 + (4 \times 0))))$
04685 := $(5 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) + 40))$
04688 := $((8 \times T(T(8))) - 640)$
04693 := $((-3) + T(96)) + 40$
04695 := $((-5) \times T(9)) + (6 \times T(40))$
04696 := $(T(T(6)) + T((9 \times 6) + 40))$
04728 := $(T(8) + (2 \times T((T(7) + 40))))$
04752 := $(T(-((2 - 5))) \times (-T(7) - T(40)))$
04753 := $T(((T(3) \times T(5)) + (7 + (4 \times 0))))$
04758 := $((8 + 5) \times (T(T(7)) - 40))$
04768 := $(-8) \times (T(T(6)) - (7 + T(40)))$
04812 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-18) + T(40))$
04815 := $(T(5) \times (1 + (8 \times 40)))$
04816 := $((6 \times T(T((1 \times 8)))) + (T(40)))$
04822 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) + (T(40))))$
04825 := $(T(((5^{T(2)}) - T(8))) + (T(40)))$
04836 := $(-6) \times ((T(3) + 8) - T(40))$
04851 := $T(((1 \times 58) + 40))$
04852 := $(T(T((-2) + T(5))) + (T(T((8 + (4 \times 0))))$
04856 := $((T((T(6) - 5)) \times T(8)) - 40)$
04864 := $(4 \times (T((6 \times 8)) + 40))$
04866 := $(-6) + (-6) \times (8 - T(40))$
04872 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(7) - T(8)) + T(40)))$
04875 := $(T(5) \times T(-((7 + 8) - 40)))$
04891 := $(T((1 \times 98)) + 40)$
04915 := $(T((T((5 - 1)) \times 9)) + (T(40)))$
04935 := $(T(5) + (-((3 - 9)) \times T(40)))$

- 04936** := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(9) + 40)))$
04938 := $-((T(8) - (T(3) \times (9 + T(40))))$
04964 := $-((T(4) - ((-6) \times (-9) - T(40))))$
04967 := $(-7) + (-6) \times (-9) - T(40))$
04974 := $(T(-(4 - 7)) \times (9 + T(40)))$
04983 := $(3 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) - 40))$
05104 := $(-4) \times ((0 - 1) - T(50))$
05124 := $(4 \times (T(2 + 1) + T(50)))$
05132 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1)) + 50)$
05144 := $(4 \times ((T(4) + 1) + T(50)))$
05149 := $(T(9) - (-4) \times (1 + T(50)))$
05215 := $(5 \times ((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(50)))$
05224 := $((4^{T(T(2))}) + T(-((T(2) - 50))))$
05229 := $(-T(T(9))) - (T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(50)))$
05235 := $(-T(5)) - (T(T(3)) \times (-250))$
05244 := $(4 \times (T((4 \times 2) + T(50)))$
05245 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(2) \times T(50))$
05263 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(6) + 2)) - 50)$
05265 := $(T(5) - (T(6) \times (-250)))$
05268 := $((T(T(8)) \times 6) - ((T(2) - T(50))))$
05271 := $((T(T((1 + 7))) \times T(T(2))) + T(50))$
05279 := $((T(9) + T(7))^2 - 50)$
05283 := $((3^8 - T(2)) - T(50))$
05322 := $(2 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(50)))$
05325 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - T(50))$
05328 := $(T(8) \times (-2 - (3 \times 50)))$
05343 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-4) \times (3 + T(50)))$
05344 := $(4 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(3) + T(50))))$
05347 := $((7 \times T(43)) - T(50))$
05349 := $((T((9 \times T(4))) - T(T(3))) + T(50))$
05364 := $(4 \times (T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) + T(50)))$
05368 := $((T((T(8) + 6))) \times T(3)) - 50)$
05382 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(-(3 - 50))))$
05385 := $-((T(5) + (T(8) \times (-3 \times 50))))$
05394 := $((4 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(3))) + T(50)$
05405 := $(5 \times T(((0 - 4) + 50)))$
05419 := $((T(T(9)) + 1) \times 4) + T(50)$
05424 := $(4 \times ((T(2)^4) + T(50)))$
05425 := $(T(5^2)) + (4 \times T(50))$
05435 := $(-5) \times (-T(3)) - T(-((4 - 50)))$
05439 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(3)) \times 4) + T(50))$
05463 := $(3 \times ((T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 50))$
05475 := $((T(5) \times T(7)) \times T(4)) + T(50)$
05482 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) + T(50))$
05486 := $((6 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 50)$
05497 := $(T(T(7)) + (-9) + (4 \times T(50)))$
05514 := $-((T(41) + (-5) \times T(50)))$
05535 := $((T(T(5)) + 3) \times (-5 - 50))$
05565 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times (-50)))$
05566 := $(T(T((6 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - 50)))$
05573 := $-(((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-50))))$
05585 := $(-T(5)) + ((8 - T(T(5))) \times (-50))$
05589 := $(9 \times (T(T(8)) + ((5 - 50))))$
05642 := $(2 \times ((4^6) - T(50)))$
05644 := $(4 \times (T((T(4) + 6))) + T(50))$
05682 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) + 50))$
05739 := $(9 \times T((3 + T(7)))) + T(50)$
05741 := $((1 + T(4)) \times T(T(7))) + T(50)$
05822 := $(2 \times (T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) - T(50)))$
05823 := $((T(3)/2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(50)))$
05835 := $(-5) \times ((3 \times T(8)) - T(50))$
05867 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T((6 - 8)))) + T(50))$
05889 := $(9 \times T(T(8))) - T(-((T(8) - 50)))$
05899 := $(-T(9)) - ((-9) \times T(T(8))) + 50)$
05916 := $(-6) \times ((-1) - T(T(9))) + 50)$
05922 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((2 + T(T(9))) - 50))$
05925 := $(-5) \times ((2 \times T(9)) - T(50))$
05935 := $(T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(9)) - 50)))$
05936 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) + 50)$
05944 := $((T(T((4 + 4))) \times 9) - 50)$
05984 := $(-T(4)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-9 + (5 \times 0)))$
05987 := $(-7) - (T(T(8)) \times (-9 + (5 \times 0)))$
05989 := $(9 \times T(T(8))) + ((T(9) - 50))$
05994 := $(T((4 \times 9)) \times (9 + (5 \times 0)))$
06132 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (1 + 60)))$
06195 := $(T((5 + 9)) \times (-1 - 60))$
06227 := $(-T(T(7))) - (-T(2)) \times T((T(T(2)) + 60))$
06244 := $(4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T((2 + (6 \times 0))))))$
06245 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 60))$
06252 := $((2 \times T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) + T(60))$
06255 := $(5 \times (T(T((T(5) - T(2)))) - T(60))$
06276 := $(-6) \times ((T(7)^2) - T(60))$
06282 := $(2 \times (T(T((T(8)/T(2)))) + 60))$
06288 := $(T((T(8) + T(8))) - (-2) \times T(60))$
06294 := $((4 + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2))) + 60)$
06375 := $(5 \times T(-((7 + 3) - 60))$
06393 := $(T((-3) + T(9))) - (-3) \times T(60))$
06396 := $((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times T(3)) + 60)$
06424 := $(4 \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 60))$
06425 := $(5 \times (T(-((T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) + 60))$
06432 := $((T(2) \times (-T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(60))$
06445 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) + 60)))$
06472 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) + (4 + (6 \times 0)))$
06473 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(7)) - ((T(T(4)) - 60)))$

- 06482** := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)) + (-4 - T(60)))$
06573 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((7 + T(5))) + (60)))$
06576 := $((T(6) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) - T(60)$
06583 := $(T((T(3) + T((8 + 5)))) + T(60))$
06633 := $((-3) + T(3)) \times T((6 + 60))$
06652 := $(2 \times (5 + T((T(6) + (60)))))$
06654 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - (6 - 60))$
06655 := $(-5) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) \times (-60))$
06675 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) - (60))))$
06693 := $((3 \times T((T(9) + T(6)))) + (60))$
06738 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 7)) - T(60))$
06748 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(4)) + ((T(7) + (60))))$
06752 := $(T(-((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))))) - (T(7) - T(60)))$
06753 := $(3 \times ((T(5) + T(T(7))) + T(60)))$
06779 := $((T(T(9)) \times 7) - T(T(7))) - (60)$
06846 := $((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(8)) - T(60)$
07125 := $-((T(T(5)) + (-T(2)) \times T(-((1 - 70)))))$
07222 := $((-2) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(2) \times T(70))))$
07224 := $-((T(T((4 + 2))) - (T(2) \times T(70))))$
07226 := $-((T(T(6)) + (-2) - (T(2) \times T(70))))$
07233 := $-((T(T(T(3))) + (-3) \times (T(2) + T(70))))$
07234 := $((T(4) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(2) \times T(70))))$
07238 := $(T((T((-8) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(2)))) + (T(70))$
07245 := $-((T((5 \times 4)) - (T(2) \times T(70))))$
07266 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(6) + 2)) + 70))$
07269 := $((T(9) - T(T(6))) + (T(2) \times T(70)))$
07284 := $(-4) \times (T(T(8)) - (2 + T(70)))$
07293 := $(3 \times ((-9) \times T(T(2))) + (T(70)))$
07328 := $(-8) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(70)))$
07333 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) - (3 - T(70)))$
07335 := $-((T((5 \times 3)) - (3 \times T(70)))$
07336 := $((T(6) \times T(T(3 + 3))) + (T(70)))$
07345 := $-((T(T(5)) - ((T(4) + (3 \times T(70))))))$
07365 := $((T(5) \times (-6)) + (3 \times T(70)))$
07383 := $(3 \times (-((8 \times 3)) + T(70)))$
07392 := $-((T(2) \times (T((9 - 3)) - T(70)))$
07395 := $-(((T(5) + T(9)) - (3 \times T(70))))$
07398 := $((8 + 9)^3 + T(70))$
07413 := $(3 \times (-14) + T(70))$
07422 := $-((T(2) + (T(2) \times (T(4) - T(70))))$
07425 := $(-((5 - 2)) \times (T(4) - T(70)))$
07428 := $((T(82) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(70)))$
07435 := $((T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(70))$
07443 := $(T((T(3) - 4)) \times (-4) + T(70))$
07452 := $(T(2) \times (-((5 - 4)) + T(70)))$
07455 := $(-(((5/5) - 4)) \times T(70))$
07482 := $(T(2) \times ((T(8)/4) + T(70)))$
07485 := $(-((5 - 8)) \times (T(4) + T(70)))$
07495 := $((T(5) \times 9) \times T(T(4))) + 70$
07497 := $((7 \times T((-9) + T(T(4)))) - 70$
07533 := $(3 \times (T(T(3)) + (5 + T(70))))$
07563 := $(3 \times ((T(6) + T(5)) + T(70)))$
07564 := $(4 \times T(((6 - T(5)) + 70)))$
07596 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(5)) \times 70))$
07653 := $(3 \times (T((5 + 6)) + T(70)))$
07665 := $(T(5) \times ((T(6) \times T(6)) + 70))$
07686 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T((8 - 6)) \times T(70))))$
07749 := $(9 \times ((-4) \times T(T(7))) + (T(70)))$
07784 := $((T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times T(T(7))) + 70$
07812 := $((T(2) + 1) \times T(-((8 - 70)))$
07824 := $(-4) \times (-T(2) - T(-((8 - 70))))$
07837 := $(T(T(7)) - (3 \times (8 - T(70))))$
07848 := $(T(8) - (-4) \times T(-((8 - 70))))$
07854 := $(T(T(T(T((4)/5)))) \times (-T(8) - 70))$
07855 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(5)) - 8) \times (-70)))$
07864 := $(T(4) - (T(T(6)) \times (T(8) - 70)))$
07925 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(70))))$
07928 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(2))) + (970)))$
07945 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + 70$
07984 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-9)) + (T(70))$
07987 := $(-7) \times ((-T(8) - T(T(9))) - 70)$
08236 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(3)^2)) - (80))$
08238 := $((T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((2 - 80)))$
08256 := $((6^5) - (T(T(2)) \times (-80)))$
08262 := $(T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(-((T(T(2)) - (80))))))$
08265 := $(5 \times T(-((T(6) + (2 - 80))))$
08272 := $((2^{7+T(T(2))}) + (80))$
08278 := $((-8) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(2))) - (80)$
08279 := $-(((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) - ((T(2) \times T(80))))$
08335 := $((T(5) \times T(33)) - (80))$
08342 := $-((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + (-3) \times T(80))$
08424 := $((4 \times (T(T(2))^4)) + (T(80)))$
08446 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) - (80))$
08472 := $(-T(2)) \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(4) - T(80))))$
08519 := $-((T((T(9) + 1)) + (T(T(5)) \times (-80))))$
08524 := $(4 \times (T(T(T(T(2)) + 5))) - (80))$
08526 := $(T(6) \times T(T(((2 + 5) + (8 \times 0))))$
08535 := $(-T(5)) + (3 \times T(-((5 - 80))))$
08565 := $-((T(T(T(5) - 6))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-80)))$
08578 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(5))) - (80))$
08627 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(6) + (80)))$
08642 := $(2 \times (T(46) + T(80)))$
08645 := $((5 \times T(46)) + T(80))$
08648 := $(8 \times T((46 + (8 \times 0))))$

- 08673** := $(T(T(3)) \times (-7) \times (T(6) - (80)))$
08732 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(3) + T(T(7)))) + (80))$
08733 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (-3) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(80))))$
08736 := $(T(6) \times (T((3 + T(7))) - (80)))$
08738 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + (7))) + (80))$
08748 := $((T(8) \times T((T(4) + (7)))) + (T(80)))$
08755 := $(-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (-7 - 80))$
08832 := $(2 \times (T((T(3) \times 8)) + (T(80))))$
08835 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-3) - T(T(8))) + (80))$
08924 := $((4 \times T(T((2 + 9)))) + (80))$
08973 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 9) + (T(80))$
09225 := $(T((T(5) \times T(2))) - (-2) \times T(90))$
09242 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (2 + (9 \times 0)))$
09243 := $(3 \times T(((4) \times T(2)) + (90)))$
09246 := $((6 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((2 + (9 \times 0))))$
09261 := $(T((1 \times 6))^{T(2+9 \times 0)})$
09288 := $(T(8) \times ((8 \times T(T(T(2)))) + (90)))$
09312 := $(2 \times T((T((1 \times 3)) + (90))))$
09324 := $((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + (90)))$
09342 := $((2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(3) + (90))$
09345 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(3)) + (90)))$
09351 := $((T((1 + 5))^3) + (90))$
09387 := $((7 \times T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(90))$
09522 := $(2 \times (T(T((T(2) + (5)))) + (T(90))))$
09735 := $(5 \times (-T(3)) + T(-(T(7) - (90))))$
09745 := $(5 \times (-4) + T(-(T(7) - (90))))$
09765 := $(T(5) \times (T(6) + ((7 \times 90)))$
09828 := $(T((T(8)/T(2))) \times (T(8) + (90)))$
09855 := $(T(5) + (T(T(5)) \times (-8 - 90)))$
09883 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - (8 + T(90)))$
10125 := $((T(5)^{T(2)}) \times T((1 + 01)))$
10128 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T((10 - 1))))))$
10139 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times 10) - 1$
10164 := $((4 \times T(T(6))) \times (10 + 1))$
10349 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(4)) - ((3 \times 0) + 1))$
10374 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - T(T((T(3) + 01))))$
10392 := $(-T(2)) + (T(9) \times T(T((3 \times 01))))$
10393 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(9)) - (3 - 01))$
10394 := $((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(3))) - 01$
10395 := $((5 \times 9) \times T(T(T(3 \times 01))))$
10396 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(9)) + ((3 \times 0) + 1))$
10437 := $(7 \times (T(3) + T((T(T(4)) - 01))))$
10449 := $((T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times T(4)) - 01$
10455 := $(5 \times (-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(4) + 01))))$
10521 := $(T(T((1 + 2))) \times 501)$
10536 := $((T(6)^3) + T((50 \times 1)))$
10635 := $(T(5) + (T(3) \times T((60 - 1))))$
10725 := $(5 \times T(-(T(T(2)) - ((70 + 1))))))$
10745 := $((5 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (7 \times (0 - 1)))$
10774 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - (7 - 01))$
10879 := $((T((9 + 7)) \times 80) - 1)$
10927 := $(7 \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T((9 + 01))))))$
11025 := $(-5) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(011)))$
11052 := $(-T(2)) + (5 \times T(T(011)))$
11055 := $(5 \times T(T(((5 \times 0) + 11))))$
11137 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((T(3) + 1))) - T(T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11165 := $(-5) \times (-((T(6) + 1)) - T(T(11)))$
11172 := $(T((2 \times T(7))) \times (1 + T(T((1 + 1))))$
11199 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(9) - 1) \times T(T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11235 := $(-5) \times (-((T(3)^2)) - T(T(11)))$
11242 := $((2^{T(4)}) - 2) \times 11$
11245 := $((T(T(5)) - (4)^2) - T(T(11)))$
11253 := $(3 \times (T(T((5 \times 2))) + T(T(11))))$
11255 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(5))/(-T(2))) - T(T(11)))$
11256 := $(T(T(6)) + (-5) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(11))))$
11264 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (2 - T(11)))$
11265 := $(-5) \times ((T(6) \times (-2)) - T(T(11)))$
11277 := $((T(7) \times T(T(7))) - (T(2 + 11)))$
11283 := $(-3) + (T((T(8)/2)) \times T(11))$
11286 := $((T(6) + T(8)) \times T(2) \times T(11))$
11289 := $((T(9) \times T((8 \times T(2)))) - T(T(11)))$
11292 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(9 \times 2)) \times T(11)))$
11294 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(92) \times T((1 + 1))))))$
11295 := $(-5) \times (-((T(9) + T(2))) - T(T(11)))$
11319 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-1)) + (T(3))) \times (-11)$
11322 := $(T(T((2^{T(2)}))) \times (T(3) + 11))$
11329 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3)))) - 11)$
11339 := $((9 \times T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) - 1)) - 1)$
11341 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 1)) + 1)$
11343 := $((T(3) \times T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) - T((1 + 1)))$
11345 := $(5 \times ((T(T(4)) + 3) + T(T(11))))$
11346 := $(6 \times T(((T(4) \times T(3)) + (1 \times 1))))$
11347 := $((T(7) \times T(T((4 + 3)))) - T(T(T((1 + 1))))$
11352 := $(T(2) - T((T(5) \times 3))) \times (-11)$
11357 := $(-T(7)) + (T((T(5) \times 3)) \times 11)$
11364 := $((T((T(T(4)) + (6))) + 3) \times T(T((1 + 1))))$
11367 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((T(6)/3))) - (1 \times 1))$
11372 := $(T(2) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(3) + 1))) + 1))$
11373 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(3) + 1))) - 1))$
11374 := $(47 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 11))$
11377 := $((T(7) \times T(T(7))) + (3^{1+1}))$
11379 := $((T(9) \times T((T(7) - T(3)))) - T(T((1 + 1))))$
11385 := $((T(5) + 8) \times (T(31) - 1))$
11392 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(9) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))) + 1))$

- 11394** := $(T(4) + ((T(9) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))) - 1))$
11395 := $(5 \times (T(((T(9) + T(T(3))) + 1) + 1))$
11396 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(9)))/T(T(3))) + 11$
11424 := $((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T((4^{1+1}))$
11429 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 11$
11433 := $((T(3) \times (-3) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(11))))$
11435 := $(5 \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(11))))$
11439 := $(-T(T(9)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(4)) - 1) \times (-1))))$
11445 := $((-5) + (T(4) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T((1 + 1))))$
11448 := $(8 \times T((T(T(4)) - ((4 - 1) - 1)))$
11451 := $((1 + 5) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(11)))$
11452 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (1 + 1))$
11466 := $((T(6) \times 6) \times T((T(4) + T((1 + 1))))$
11472 := $((T(T(T(2)))^{7-4}) + (T(T(11))))$
11473 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (7 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(11))))$
11477 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(7)) + (4))) - T((1 + 1)))$
11484 := $(T((T(T(4)) + (8 \times 4))) \times T((1 + 1)))$
11488 := $(8 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(4)))/(1 + 1)))$
11492 := $(-T(2) + ((T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times 11))$
11494 := $((T(4) + T(T(9))) \times (T(4) + 1) - 1)$
11495 := $((T((5 \times 9)) + T(4)) \times 11)$
11525 := $((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 51) - 1$
11529 := $(9 \times (T(T(2)) + T((51 - 1))))$
11535 := $(-T(5) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (51 - 1)))$
11544 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((4 \times 5))) - T(T((1 + 1))))$
11545 := $(-5) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T((5 + 1) - 1))))$
11549 := $((-T(9)) \times T(T(T(4))))/(-5 + 1) - 1$
11557 := $((7 + T(T(5))) \times T((T(5) - (1 + 1))))$
11564 := $((T(T(4)) - (6)) \times (5 + T(T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11565 := $(T(5) + (T(T(6)) \times (51 - 1)))$
11572 := $(2 \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times 11))$
11583 := $((-3) + T(8)) \times T((T(5) + 11))$
11594 := $((-4) - T(T(9))) - (T(5)) \times (-11)$
11595 := $(T(T(5)) - (-9) \times T((51 - 1)))$
11616 := $((T(6) + 1) \times T((T(6) + 11)))$
11627 := $(-7) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(61) + 1)))$
11647 := $((T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times T((6 + 1)) - 1)$
11648 := $(8 \times (T((T(T(4)) - (6))) + T(T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11649 := $((T(T(9)) + (4 \times 6)) \times 11)$
11655 := $(5 \times (T(T(5)) + T((6 \times 11))))$
11658 := $((-T(85)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T((1 + 1)))$
11664 := $((-4) \times (-6 - T(6)))^{1+1}$
11674 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 6) - (1 + 1)$
11676 := $(-6) \times (7 - T((61 + 1)))$
11684 := $((T(4) + T(8)) \times (T((T(6) + 1)) + 1))$
11685 := $(5 \times (-T(T(8))) + T((T(T(6))/T((1 + 1))))$
11715 := $(-T(5)) \times (-1) - T((T(7) + 11))$
11725 := $(5 \times (T(-(T(2) - 71))) - 1)$
11735 := $(5 \times (T(-(3 - 71))) + 1)$
11736 := $(-((T(T(6)) - (3^7)) \times T(T((1 + 1))))$
11739 := $(T((T(9) - 3)) \times (7 + T(T((1 + 1))))$
11742 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) + 11))))$
11748 := $(T((8 \times (4 + 7))) \times T((1 + 1)))$
11749 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - (T(11))))$
11755 := $(-5) + (T(5) \times (T(7)^{1+1}))$
11757 := $((T(7) \times T(5)) \times T(7)) - T((1 + 1))$
11767 := $((T(T(7)) + (6)) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11768 := $((8 + T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T((1 + 1)))$
11771 := $((1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) - T((1 + 1))$
11772 := $(-2) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + (1 \times 1)))$
11773 := $((T((T(T(3)) + (7))) \times (T(7) + 1)) - 1)$
11774 := $(T((4 \times 7)) \times (T(7) + (1 \times 1)))$
11775 := $(T(5) \times ((T(7) \times T(7)) + (1 \times 1)))$
11777 := $((T(7) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) + T((1 + 1))$
11781 := $((1 - T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \times (-11)$
11782 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) - (-7 + T(T(11))))$
11786 := $(-6) + ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times 11)$
11814 := $((T((T(T(4)) - 1) \times 8) - (T(11)))$
11823 := $(T(T(3)) \times (2 + T((T(8) - T((1 + 1))))))$
11824 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(8)) - 1)) - 1)$
11832 := $(-T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (-8 + T(T(11))))$
11855 := $(-5) \times (5 - (T(8) \times T(11)))$
11856 := $((T(6) - 5) \times T((T(8) + (1 + 1))))$
11862 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(6)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T((1 + 1))))$
11869 := $((T((9 \times 6)) \times 8) - 11)$
11885 := $(5 \times (T(T(8)) + T((-8) + T(11))))$
11889 := $(9 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) - 11))$
11891 := $(T((1 + T(9))) \times (8 + T((1 + 1))))$
11894 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times 8) - (T(11))$
11895 := $(-((T(T(5)) - T(T(9)))) \times (-8 + T(T(T((1 + 1))))))$
11912 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T((1 + T(9))) \times (-11)))$
11924 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(9))) \times 11$
11925 := $((T(T(5)) - T((2 \times T(9)))) \times (-T((1 + 1))))$
11928 := $(8 \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(9) + 1) - 1)))$
11934 := $(T((-4) + T(T(3))) \times T((9 + T((1 + 1))))$
11946 := $((T((6 + T(4))) + T(9)) \times T(11))$
11949 := $(-T(T(9)) + (-4) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(11))))$
11957 := $((-7) - (T(T(5)) \times 9)) \times (-11)$
11964 := $(4 \times (T(6) + (T(9) \times T(11))))$
11968 := $(8 \times (T((6 \times 9)) + 11))$
11973 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times 11))$
11977 := $(T(T(7)) + (7 \times T((-9) + T(11))))$
11982 := $(T(2) \times (T(89) - 11))$
11984 := $(-4) + (T(T(8)) \times (9 \times (1 + 1)))$

- 11985** := $(5 \times (T((8 \times 9) - T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))))$
11987 := $-((T(7) - (T(89) \times T((1 + 1))))$
11988 := $(T(T(8)) \times (((8 + 9) \times 1) + 1))$
11989 := $((9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(9 - 1)))) + 1)$
12012 := $-(((T(2) - T(10)) \times T(21)))$
12013 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(10) - T(2))) + 1)$
12074 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(70))) \times T(2) - 1)$
12075 := $(5 \times T(((70 - 2) + 1)))$
12096 := $(6 \times T((9 \times (T(T(02)) + 1))))$
12097 := $((T((7 \times 9)) \times T(T(02))) + 1)$
12144 := $(44 \times T(((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)))$
12149 := $((T(9) \times T((T(4) - 1))) \times T(T(2))) - 1)$
12154 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(51)) / T(T(2))) - 1)$
12165 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(T((6 + 1))) \times (-2)) + 1)$
12167 := $((T(7) - (6 - 1))^{2+1})$
12168 := $((8 + T((6 - 1)))^{T(2)} + 1)$
12169 := $((T(T(9)) - (T(6))) \times 12) + 1)$
12175 := $((5 \times T(T(7))) - 1) \times T(T(2)) + 1)$
12177 := $((T(7) \times T((T(7) + 1))) - (2 + 1))$
12184 := $(-4) \times ((T(8) - T(T(12))) - 1)$
12185 := $(5 \times ((T(T((8 - 1))) \times T(T(2))) + 1))$
12189 := $((T(9) + 8) \times (-1 + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 1)$
12192 := $((T(2) + T(9)) \times (1 + T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))))$
12222 := $((2 + T(T(T(2))))^{T(2)} + T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12223 := $((T(T(T(3)) \times T(2)) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(2))) + 1)$
12224 := $((-((4^{T(T(2))})) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(2))) - 1)$
12225 := $(T(5) \times (T(2) + (2 \times T(T((T(2) + 1))))))$
12241 := $(-1) + (((T(T(4)) - 2) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))$
12242 := $((-2) + T(T(4))) \times T(T((2 \times T(2)))) - 1)$
12243 := $((T((T(3) + 4)) - 2) \times T(21))$
12244 := $((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) - T((2 + 1)))$
12245 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times 2) - 1)$
12246 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(4)) - 2)) + (2 + 1))$
12248 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(2)^2 \times 1)))$
12249 := $((T((T(9) + 4))) \times T((2 + 2))) - 1)$
12254 := $((-T(4) + T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(2)) - 1)$
12255 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) - T(((2^{T(T(2))}) + 1)))$
12257 := $(-T(7) + (T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times (2 + 1)))$
12258 := $((T(T(8)) + (T(5))) \times (T(2) \times T((2 + 1))))$
12259 := $((-9) + T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(2)) + 1)$
12264 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) - (2^{T(2)}))) - 1)$
12265 := $((-5) + T(T(6))) - T(2)) \times T(T((T(2) + 1)))$
12275 := $(5 \times (((T(T(7)) + T(2)) \times T(T(2))) + 1))$
12276 := $((T(T(T(6)) / 7) - T(2)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 1))$
12282 := $(T(2) \times (T((T(8 - T(2))) \times T(T(2)))) - 1)$
12283 := $(-T(T(3))) + (8 \times (-2) + T(T(T(T(2) + 1))))$
12284 := $(-4) \times ((-((8^{T(2)})) \times T(T(2))) + 1)$
12285 := $(T(5) \times ((T(8) + T(2)) \times 21))$
12286 := $((T((-6) + T(8)) \times T(2)) \times T(2) + 1)$
12287 := $((T(7) + T(8))^2 \times T(2) - 1)$
12292 := $((2 + T((T(9) \times 2))) \times T(2) + 1)$
12293 := $((3 + T((T(9) \times 2))) \times T(2) - 1)$
12294 := $((T((T(4) \times 9)) + T(2)) \times (2 + 1))$
12296 := $((6 + T(9)) + 2) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
12297 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(9) + 2) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))))$
12298 := $((8 + T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12315 := $(T(5) \times (T((-1) + T(T(3))) \times 2) + 1)$
12318 := $(8 \times T(T(T(1 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)$
12319 := $((T(T(9 + 1))) \times (T(3) + 2)) - 1)$
12321 := $((T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) \times (T(3) + 2)) + 1)$
12322 := $((T(T(2^{T(2)})) / T(3))^2 + 1)$
12323 := $((T(3) - 2) \times T(T((T(3) \times 2)))) - 1)$
12324 := $(4 \times T(T(((2 \times 3) \times 2) \times 1)))$
12325 := $((T(T(T(5) - T(2))) \times (T(3) - 2)) + 1)$
12326 := $(T(T(6)) - ((-T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) + 1)$
12327 := $((T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3))) - 21)$
12328 := $(8 \times (T(T((2^3) + 2))) + 1)$
12329 := $(T(9) \times (T(23) - 2)) - 1)$
12332 := $(2 + T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) \times (T(2) + 1))$
12333 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-T(3)) \times (T((T(3)) \times T(2))) + 1)$
12334 := $(4 \times T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) + T((T(2) + 1)))$
12336 := $((T(T((6 + T(3)))) + 3) \times (T(2) + 1))$
12339 := $(9 \times (T(3) \times T(T(3))) - T((T(T(2)) - 1)))$
12342 := $(T(T((2 + T(4)))) + (T(T(3))^{2+1}))$
12343 := $(T(T((3 \times 4))) + ((T(T(3))^{T(2)} + 1))$
12344 := $(T(T(4)) + ((4^{T(3)}) \times T(2)) + 1)$
12345 := $((T((-T(5)) + T(T(4))) + 3) \times T((T(T(2)) - 1)))$
12346 := $(T(6) + ((4 \times T(T((T(3) \times 2)))) + 1))$
12347 := $(-T(7)) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(3) - T(21)))$
12348 := $(T(8) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))$
12349 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T((4 \times 3))) \times T(2)) + 1)$
12355 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(5)) / 3))) + T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12358 := $(T(8) + (((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3))))^2 + 1))$
12359 := $((T(T(9)) - 5) \times (T(3) \times 2) - 1)$
12364 := $((T(4) + T(T((6 + T(3)))) \times (T(2) + 1))$
12366 := $(6 \times (T(T(6)) + T((T(3)) \times T((T(2) + 1))))$
12368 := $(8 \times (6 + T(T(((3^2) + 1))))$
12369 := $(T(9) - (T(T((6 + T(3)))) \times (-T(2) + 1)))$
12373 := $(-3) - (-T(7)) \times ((T(T(3))^2 + 1))$
12374 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((7 \times 3) - T(T(2)))) - 1)$
12375 := $(-T(5)) \times (((T(T(7)) + (T(3))) \times (-2)) - 1)$
12376 := $(T((6 + 7)) \times T(T((3 + 2)) + 1))$

- 12377** := $((T(7) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3)^2))) + 1)$
12383 := $(((-3) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12384 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 8) \times ((3^2) - 1))$
12385 := $(T(T(5)) - ((8 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12389 := $(T(9) + (8 \times (3 + T(T(T((T(2) + 1))))))$
12392 := $((2 \times T(T(9))) \times T(3)) - T((T(T(2)) + 1))$
12393 := $((T(3) + T(9)) \times (3^{T(T(2))-1}))$
12396 := $((6 - (T(T(9)) \times 3)) \times (-T(2) + 1))$
12397 := $((T(7) + T((9 - 3))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))$
12398 := $((T(8) \times T(T(9)))/3 - T(T(T(2)))) - 1$
12399 := $((T(T(9)) \times (9 + 3)) - (21))$
12415 := $(-5) - ((1 - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))$
12419 := $((T(T(9)) \times (14 - 2)) - 1)$
12422 := $((T(2) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))$
12424 := $-((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(4^{T(2)})) - 1))$
12425 := $(5 \times T((2 \times (T((4 \times 2)) - 1)))$
12426 := $((T((T(6) \times T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times T((2 + 1))$
12428 := $((8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (2 + 1))$
12429 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(2))) + (4) \times 2) + 1$
12432 := $((T(2) - T(34)) \times (-21))$
12433 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(34) - T(2))) + 1)$
12435 := $((-5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4)) + (T(T(2)) - 1)$
12438 := $(-T(8)) - (-T(3)) \times (T(4^{T(2)} - 1))$
12439 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) + T(4)) \times 2 - 1$
12442 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(4) - T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))$
12445 := $((T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + 4) \times (T(T(2)) - 1))$
12446 := $((T(6) \times T(T((4 + 4))) - T(T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12447 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (T((T(4) - T(2)) - 1))$
12448 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (4^2 \times 1)))$
12449 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-4)) - T(4)) \times (-T(2)) - 1$
12452 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) + 1)$
12453 := $-((T(T(3)) - (54 \times T(21))))$
12455 := $(5 \times (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + T((2 + 1)))$
12456 := $(-6) \times ((5 - T(4^{T(2)})) - 1)$
12458 := $(-T(T(8))) - (-5^4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 1$
12462 := $-((T(2) - T(64)) \times T((2 + 1)))$
12463 := $((T(3) \times (T(64) - T(2))) + 1)$
12464 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) - (T(4) + T(21)))$
12465 := $-((T(5) - (6 \times T(4^{2+1}))))$
12467 := $(T((7 + 6)) \times (T(4^2) + 1))$
12468 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2))) + 1$
12472 := $(2 \times (((-T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))$
12473 := $-((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(4)^{T(2)}))) + 1)$
12474 := $(T(-((4 - 7))) \times (T(4^{T(2)} - 1))$
12475 := $(5 \times (T((7 \times T(4))) + T((T(2) + 1)))$
12479 := $((T(T((9 - 7))) \times T(4^{T(2)})) - 1)$
12492 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times (4 \times (2 + 1)))$
12493 := $((T(3) + T(T(9))) \times (T(4) + 2) + 1)$
12495 := $(T(((T(5) + 9) + T(4))) \times 21)$
12496 := $((T(6) \times T(((9 \times 4) - 2))) + 1)$
12497 := $(-T(-((T(7) - T(9)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1)))$
12516 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(T(-((1 - 5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) + 1))$
12524 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) + (5^{T(T(2))-1}))$
12525 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) - 1)$
12527 := $(-T(7)) + (T(2) \times (T(T((T(5) - 2))) - 1))$
12528 := $-((T(8) \times (T(2) - T((5 + 21))))$
12534 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(5) + (2 + 1))))$
12536 := $(-T(6)) + ((3 \times T(T((T(5) - 2)))) - 1)$
12537 := $(7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(((T(T(5))/2) - 1)))$
12542 := $(2 \times ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))) + 1))$
12543 := $-((T(T((3 \times 4))) - (5^{T(T(2)} - 1)))$
12544 := $((-(4 + 4) + T(T(5)))^2 \times 1)$
12545 := $((-T(T(5)) + T(T((-4) + T(5)))) \times T(T(2)) - 1)$
12546 := $((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times T((2 + 1))$
12547 := $((T(T((7 + 4))) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))) + 1$
12549 := $(9 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)))) - (T(21)))$
12552 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((-T(T(5)) + T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) + 1))$
12555 := $(T((T(5) + T(5))) \times (T((5 + 2)) - 1))$
12557 := $((-7) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(5))) + T(T(2)))) - 1$
12558 := $(T(T((8 + 5))) \times ((5 - 2) \times 1))$
12559 := $((T(9)/T(5)) \times T(T((T(5) - 2))) + 1)$
12564 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5))) - (21)$
12565 := $(-5) \times (((-T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(2))) + 1$
12572 := $((T((2 \times 7)) \times T(T(5))) - T((T(T(2)) + 1))$
12573 := $((T(T((T(3) + 7))) + 5) \times (2 + 1))$
12576 := $((6 + T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (2 + 1))$
12578 := $(-8) - (T(T(7)) \times ((T(5) \times (-2)) - 1))$
12579 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(5)))/T(T(2)) - 1$
12582 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T((52 + 1))))$
12583 := $(3 \times (8 + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + 1)$
12585 := $((-5) + T(8)) \times T(T((5 + 2))) - 1$
12586 := $((T((-6) + T(8)))/T(5)) \times T(T((T(2)) + 1))$
12587 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(8) - 5)) + (2 - 1))$
12589 := $(T(9) - (((-8) + T(T(5)))^2) \times (-1))$
12594 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T((-9) + T(5)))) - 2) - 1)$
12595 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((9 + 5))) - T(T(2))) + 1$
12597 := $(T((-7) + T(9))) \times (T(5) + (2 \times 1))$
12599 := $-((T(9) \times (T(9) - T(5^2))) + 1)$
12617 := $((T(T(7)) + 1) \times (T(6) + T((T(2) + 1))))$
12628 := $((8 + T(T(2))) \times (T((T(6) \times 2)) - 1))$
12635 := $((T(5)^3) + ((T(6)^{T(2)} - 1))$
12636 := $((T(T(6)) + 3) \times (T(T((6 - 2))) - 1))$
12639 := $((-T(9)) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T((T(2) + 1))))$

- 12653** := ((T(T((3+5))) × (T(6) - 2)) - 1)
12654 := ((4 + T(5)) × T(((6²) × 1)))
12655 := ((T(T(5)) × (5 × T(6))) + T(T((T(2) + 1))))
12656 := ((T(T(6)) - (5)) × (T(T((6 - 2))) + 1))
12657 := ((T(7) × ((-5) + T(T(6))) × 2) + 1)
12658 := (((T(8) × T(5 + T(6)))) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)
12663 := (-((T(T(3)) + T(6))) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((T(2) + 1))))))
12664 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(6))) - ((T(6) × 2) - 1))
12668 := (-T(8)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T((6 - 2)))) - 1))
12672 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-7)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((T(2) + 1))))))
12677 := ((T(T((T(7)/7))) × T(T(6))) - T((T(T(2) + 1))))
12682 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) × T(2) + 1)
12683 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T(8)) - 62)) - 1)
12684 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T((T(8)/6)))) - 21)
12693 := (3 × (T(9) + T(T((6 × 2) + 1))))
12695 := ((T(T(-(5 - 9))) × T(T(6))) - T((T(2) + 1)))
12696 := ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) × (T((6 + T(2))) + 1))
12698 := ((T(T((T(8)/9))) × T(T(6))) - (T(T(2) + 1))
12699 := (T(T(9)) + (9 × (6^{T(2)+1})))
12704 := ((T(T(4)) × T((07 × T(2)))) - 1)
12705 := (T(T(T(T(-(5 - 07)))))) × T(T((T(2) + 1)))
12706 := ((T(T(6)) × T((07 + T(2)))) + 1)
12723 := (3 × (T(T((T(T(2)) + 7))) + T(T((T(2) + 1))))))
12724 := (((-T(T(4)) - T(T((T(T(2)) + 7)))) × (-T(2))) + 1)
12725 := (-T(5) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7))) × (T(T(T(2)) - 1))))
12726 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(2) + 7))) + 21)
12728 := (8 × ((T((2 × T(7))) - T(T(2))) + 1))
12733 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(3 + 7)) + T((T(T(2) + 1))))
12734 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7) + (2 - 1)))
12735 := (-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7))) × (T(T(T(2)) - 1)))
12738 := ((T(8) - 3) × ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 1))
12742 := (2 × ((T(4) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 1))
12743 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(4))) + (T(7) + T((T(2) + 1))))
12744 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (4 × (T((T(7) × T(2))) + 1))))
12745 := (-5) + (T(4) × T(((7²) + 1)))
12746 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) + ((7 × T(T(2))) - 1))
12747 := ((T(T(7)) × (-T(4))) + (7^{T(T(2))-1}))
12748 := (((8 × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)
12749 := (T(9) + ((T(T(4)) × T((7 × T(2)))) - 1))
12752 := (2 × (-T(T(5)) + (T(7) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1))))
12755 := (-5) × (5 - T((72 - 1)))
12759 := (-9) + (((T(T(5)) - (7)²) - 1))
12761 := (((1 + T(T(6))) × T((7 + T(2)))) + 1)
12767 := (((76 × T(7)) × T(T(2))) - 1)
12768 := (8 × T((6 + (7²) + 1)))
12769 := ((T((9 + 6)) - (7))² × 1)
12772 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) × (T(7) + (2 + 1)))
12773 := (((T(3) + T(T(7))) × (T(7) + T(2))) + 1)
12775 := (5 × (T((77 - T(T(2)))) - 1))
12778 := ((8 × T((T(7) + T(7)))) + T((T(2) + 1)))
12782 := (T(T(2)) - (-8 × (T((T(7) × 2)) + 1)))
12784 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 8) + (T((T(7) + 2)) - 1))
12785 := (5 × (T((T(T(8)) - T((T(7) + T(T(2)))))) + 1))
12788 := (((8 × T((8 × 7))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 1)
12789 := (-T(T(9))) + (T(8) × ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(2)))) - 1))
12795 := ((T((T(5) + T(9))) × 7) - T((T(T(2)) - 1)))
12796 := ((T(T(6)) × T(9)) + ((7^{T(2)+1})))
12797 := ((T(7) × ((T(9) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2)))) + 1)
12798 := ((T(T(8)) + T(9)) × (T(7) - T((T(2) + 1))))
12817 := (7 × (T((-T(18)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 1))
12824 := -(((T(T(T(4))) + (-T(2)) × T(T(8))) × T((T(T(2) + 1))))))
12825 := ((5²) × ((8^{T(2)}) + 1))
12826 := (((T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) × (T(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) + 1)
12827 := (-7) + (T(2) × T((T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) + 1))
12831 := ((T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(8))) × (-21))
12832 := -(((T(T((-2) + T(3))) - T(T(8))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 1))
12834 := (T(((4 × T(T(3))) + 8) × (2 + 1))
12842 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T((8 × 2) + 1))
12844 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(4)) - T(((T(8) × 2) - 1)))
12845 := (T(5) + ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 1))
12846 := (-6) × (4 - T(((8²) + 1)))
12848 := (8 × (T(4) + T((T(8) + 2) + 1)))
12851 := (((1 - T(T(5))) × (-T(8) × T(2))) - 1)
12852 := (((2 + T(5)) × T(8)) × 21)
12853 := (((T(-T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(8))) × T(2) + 1)
12854 := ((T(4) × T((T(5) + T(8)))) - T(T((T(T(2) + 1))))))
12855 := (-5) × (-T(5) - T(((T(8) × 2) - 1)))
12857 := ((T(7) + T(5)) × (T((8 × T(2)) - 1))
12865 := (-5) + (6 × T(((8²) + 1)))
12869 := ((T(9) × (T(T(6)) + T((8 + 2)))) - 1)
12871 := ((T(((1 + T(7)) + T(8))) × T(T(2))) + 1)
12872 := (-T(2) + (((T(T(7)) × T(T(8)))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1))
12873 := (-3) - ((T(T(7)) × T(T(8)))/(-21))
12874 := (-T(T(4)) - (7 × ((-8) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 1))
12875 := (-5) + ((7 × 8) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))
12876 := ((T((T(6) + 7)) × T(T(8)))/21)
12877 := (((T(T(7))/7) × T(T(8)))/T(2)) + 1)
12878 := ((-T(8) - T(T(7))) - (-T(T(8)) × (T(T(T(2)) - 1)))
12879 := (9 × T(((7 × 8) - 2) - 1))
12884 := (((T(T(4)) - T(8)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1)
12886 := ((6 × T((8 × 8))) + T(T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
12887 := (T(T(7)) - ((-T((8 × 8))) × T(T(2))) - 1))
12888 := ((8 × T(T(8))) - (-T(8)) × T((T(T(T(2)) - 1)))

- 12899** := (((9 × T((T(9) + 8))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 1)
12903 := ((T(3) + T(09)) × T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)))
12914 := (((T(41) × T(9))/T(2)) - 1)
12915 := (T(5) × T((-1) + T(9)) - (2 + 1)))
12924 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 1)))
12925 := ((5 + T(T(2))) × (T((T(9) + T(2))) - 1))
12928 := (8 × ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (9 - 2)) - 1))
12934 := ((T(T(4)) + 3) × ((-9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1))
12935 := (((5 + T(3)) × T((T(9) + T(2)))) - 1)
12936 := (T(T(6)) × ((T(3) × 9) + (2 × 1)))
12937 := (((-T(7)) × T(T(-(3 - 9)))) × (-2)) + 1)
12942 := -(T(T(2)) × ((T(T(4)) - T(T(9 + 2)))) - 1))
12943 := ((T(T(T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + 9))) × (-T(T(2)) + 1))
12944 := (-4) × (4 - T((9²) - 1))
12945 := -(T(5) - (4 × T((9²) - 1)))
12946 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) + 9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1)
12947 := ((7 + 4) × (T((T(9) + T(2))) + 1))
12957 := (7 × (T((T(5) + T(9))) + (21)))
12959 := (((9 × T(T(5))) × (9 + T(2))) - 1)
12964 := (4 × (T((T(6) - 9) + 2) + 1))
12968 := (8 × ((6 × T(9)) × T(T(2))) + 1))
12969 := (9 × ((T(T(6)) + 9) × T(T(2))) + 1))
12972 := (T(2) × (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T(2)) + 1))
12979 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) × 9) + T((T(2) + 1)))
12985 := ((T((5 × 8)) + T(T(9))) × (T(T(2)) + 1))
12986 := ((T(6) × (T(T(8)) - T(9))) - T(T((T(2) + 1))))
12988 := (((8 × T(8)) × T(9)) + T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
12992 := ((2^{T(9)/9}) × T(T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
12993 := -(T(T(T(3))) - (((T(T(9))/9)²) - 1))
12995 := ((T(5) + 99)² - 1)
12996 := ((69 + T(9))² × 1)
12997 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × 9) + T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
13034 := ((-T(T(4))) × (-T(3) - T(T(T(03)))) - 1)
13035 := (T(5) + (T(30) × T((T(3) + 1))))
13084 := (4 × (T(80) + (31)))
13113 := (3 × T((T((1 + 1)) × 31)))
13122 := (2 × (T(2)^{1+T(3)+1}))
13123 := ((T(3) × (T(2)^{1+T(3)})) + 1)
13125 := ((5^{T(2)}) × T((13 + 1)))
13145 := (((5⁴) + 1) × T(T(3))) - 1)
13146 := (T(T(6)) + (T(41) × T((T(3) - 1))))
13167 := (7 × (T(61) - T((3 + 1))))
13168 := (((T(8) + T(6)) × T(T(T((1 × 3)))) + 1)
13194 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 9) - T(T((1 + T(3)) + 1)))
13201 := ((T(10) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(31)))
13211 := ((T(T(11)) × T(T(2))) - T(T((3 + 1))))
13216 := ((T(61) - T(2)) × (T(3) + 1))
13224 := ((T(T(4)) + 2) × (T(T((2 × 3))) + 1))
13225 := ((T(T(5)) - (2 + T(2)))³⁻¹)
13229 := ((T((T(9) - T((2 + 2)))) × T(T(3))) - 1)
13231 := ((T((-1) + (T(3)²))) × T(T(3))) + 1)
13232 := (2 + (T(T(3)) × T((T((2³)) - 1))))
13233 := (3 + (T(T(3)) × T((T((2³)) - 1))))
13234 := (4 + (T(T(3)) × T((T((2³)) - 1))))
13235 := (-5) × (((T(T(3))²) × (-T(3))) - 1)
13236 := (6 + (T(T(3)) × T((T((2³)) - 1))))
13237 := (7 × T((-3) + (2^{T(3×1)})))
13238 := ((T(T(8 + 3))) × T(T(2))) - T((T(3) + 1)))
13239 := (9 + (T(T(3)) × T((T((2³)) - 1))))
13242 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T((2³))) + 1)))
13243 := (T(3) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) × (T(3) + 1)))
13244 := (-4) × (T(4) - T((T(2)³⁺¹)))
13245 := (-T(5)) × ((-42) × T(T(3))) - 1)
13246 := ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) × T(T(2))) - (T(T(3)) - 1))
13247 := (((-7) + T(T(4))) × T(23)) - 1)
13248 := (T(8) × (-T(4) + T((T(2)³ × 1))))
13252 := ((T(2) × (T(T((T(5) - 2))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1)
13253 := (((T(T((T(3) + 5)))) - 2) × T(3)) - 1)
13254 := ((T(T((-4) + T(5))) - 2) × T(3 × 1))
13255 := (((5 + 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(3 + 1)))
13256 := ((T(T((6 + 5))) × T(T(2))) - T(3 + 1))
13258 := -(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) - 2)³⁻¹))
13261 := (((-1) + T(T((T(6))/T(T(2)))))) × T(3)) + 1)
13262 := ((T(T(2)) × T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(2)))))) - (3 + 1))
13263 := (-3) - ((-6) × T(T((2 × T(3)) - 1)))
13264 := ((T(T(-(T(4) - T(6)))) × T(T(2))) - (3 - 1))
13265 := ((T(T((5 + 6))) × (2 × 3)) - 1)
13266 := (6 × T((62 + 3) + 1))
13267 := ((T(T(((7 + 6) - 2))) × T(3)) + 1)
13268 := (8 + (6 × (T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(T(3)))) - 1)))
13269 := ((T((T(9) + T(6))) × T(T(2))) + (3 × 1))
13272 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(((7 × 2) - 3))) + 1))
13278 := -(T(T(8)) + (T(7) × (-2) - T(31)))
13279 := (T(97) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(T((T(3) + 1))))
13292 := ((2 + T((9²))) × (3 + 1))
13293 := (((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))/2) × T(T((3 × 1))))
13294 := ((4 × T((9²))) + T((3 + 1)))
13295 := (((5 + T(T(9 + 2))) × T(3)) - 1)
13296 := (6 × (T(T((9 + 2))) + (T(3) - 1)))
13318 := ((T(T(8)) × (-1) + T(T(3))) - (3 - 1))
13335 := ((-5) × T(T(3))) × ((-T(3)) × T(T(3))) - 1)
13338 := (T((T(8)/3)) × T((3 × T(3 × 1))))

- 13339** := $((T((9+3)) \times T((3 \times T(3)))) + 1)$
13354 := $(- (T(T(4))) + (53 \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))))$
13355 := $((T(5) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times T(3)) - 1)$
13356 := $(T((6 \times T(5))) + (T(T(3)))^3 \times 1)$
13357 := $((T(7) \times T(53))/3 + 1)$
13359 := $(T(T(9)) + (T(T((T(5) - 3))) \times (3 + 1)))$
13364 := $((T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(3)) - T(31))$
13365 := $((T(5) + T(T(6))) - 3) \times T(T(3 + 1))$
13367 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))) - T(3 + 1))$
13371 := $(T(T((1 + 7))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3 + 1))))$
13372 := $(- (T(T(2))) + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) + 1))$
13373 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(3))) - (3 + 1)$
13374 := $(- (4) + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) + 1))$
13375 := $(- (5) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3 \times (3 + 1))))$
13376 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T((3 + 3))) - 1$
13377 := $((T(T(7)) + T((7 \times 3))) \times T(T(3 \times 1)))$
13378 := $((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) + 1$
13391 := $(- (1) - (- (9 \times 3)) \times T(31))$
13392 := $((T(2)^{9/3}) \times T(31))$
13393 := $((T(T(3)) + T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) \times T(3)) + 1)$
13394 := $((T((T((4 + 9)) + 3)) \times 3) - 1)$
13395 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(9) - 3)) - T(3 + 1)))$
13397 := $((T(T(7)) \times ((9 \times 3) + T(3))) - 1)$
13398 := $((T(8) - (9/3)) \times T(T((3 + 1))))$
13419 := $(9 \times (T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + T(3 \times 1))$
13423 := $((T((3^{T(2)})) + T(T(4))) \times 31)$
13425 := $(T(T((T(5) - 2))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(3)) - 1))$
13426 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(2) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(3) + 1)))$
13427 := $(T(7) + (((T(2) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 1))$
13428 := $((- (T(8)) - T((T(2)^4))) \times (- (3 + 1)))$
13429 := $((T(T(9)) - 2) \times ((4 \times 3) + 1))$
13432 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(31))))$
13433 := $((3^{T(3)}) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 1))$
13439 := $((T(9) + T(34)) \times T(T(3))) - 1$
13442 := $((T(T((2 \times 4))) - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1))$
13446 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(4) + T((T(3) + 1))))$
13447 := $(T((T(7) + T(4))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 1))$
13452 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T((T(5) - 4)))) + 31)$
13453 := $(- (3) + ((T(T(5)) - 4)^{3-1}))$
13454 := $((T(45) \times (T(4) + 3)) - 1)$
13455 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(43) - 1))$
13456 := $((6 + T(T(5))) - T(4))^{3-1}$
13464 := $((4 \times T((T(6) - 4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1))$
13465 := $((T(5) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(4)^{3+1}))$
13467 := $((T(7) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)) - 1$
13469 := $((T(9) \times T((6 \times 4))) - (31))$
13474 := $((4 + 7) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) - 1)$
13475 := $((- ((5 \times 7)) \times T(T(4))) \times (- (T(3) + 1)))$
13476 := $((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times (- (T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + 1)$
13479 := $((T(9) \times T((T(7) - 4))) - T(T(3 \times 1)))$
13482 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(T((4 \times 3) - 1))))$
13483 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) - (4 \times T(3)))) + 1)$
13485 := $((- (5) + T(8)) \times T((T((4 + 3)) + 1)))$
13486 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) + (- (4) - T(31)))$
13492 := $((T(T(T(2)) + T(9))) \times T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1$
13493 := $((- (3) - T(T(9))) \times (- (T(4) + 3))) - 1$
13495 := $(5 \times ((T(9) \times T(4)) \times T(3)) - 1)$
13497 := $((T(T(7)) - 9) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) - 1$
13499 := $(T(9) - ((T(T(9)) \times (- (T(4) + 3))) + 1))$
13504 := $(4 \times ((T(05)^3) + 1))$
13523 := $((T((T(T(3)) \times 2)) \times T(5)) - (T(T(3)) + 1))$
13524 := $((T(42) \times T(5)) - T(T(3 \times 1)))$
13525 := $(- (5) + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(5)) \times T(T(3 + 1))))$
13528 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(2) + T(5))) + T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13544 := $(4 \times (T(4) + ((T(5)^3) + 1)))$
13545 := $(T(5) \times T((45 - 3) \times 1))$
13546 := $((T(64) - ((5^{T(3)}) + 1))$
13549 := $(T(9) - (- (4) \times ((T(5)^3) + 1)))$
13552 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((- (T(T(5))) \times (- (T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) - 1))$
13555 := $(- (5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(3) + 1))))$
13557 := $((- (7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - (3 \times 1)$
13559 := $((T(9) + T(5)) \times (- (5) + T(T(T(3)))) - 1)$
13564 := $(4 \times (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5) - 3)) + 1)))$
13566 := $(T(6) \times (T(6) + ((5^{3+1})))$
13567 := $((T((7 \times 6)) \times T(5)) + T(T(3)) + 1)$
13572 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1)$
13573 := $((T((T(3) \times 7)) \times T(5)) + T((T(3) + 1)))$
13575 := $((T(T(5)) - 7) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(3) - 1))$
13576 := $((T((6 \times 7)) \times T(5)) + (31))$
13584 := $(- (4) \times (- (T(8)) - (T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) + 1))))$
13587 := $(7 \times (T(T(8)) + T((5 \times T((3 + 1))))$
13592 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((9 + T(5))^3) - 1))$
13593 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((9 + T(5))^3)) \times (- 1))$
13596 := $(T(T(6)) - (- (9) \times T((53 + 1))))$
13597 := $((T(7) - T(95)) \times (- 3) + 1)$
13599 := $((T(9) \times T(9)) - ((5^{T(3)}) - 1))$
13608 := $((T(80) \times T(6)) / (T(3) - 1))$
13623 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(2)) + (T(6))) \times (- (T(31))))$
13624 := $((T(T(4)) - T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + 31))$
13628 := $((T(8) \times T((T(T(2)) + (T(6)))) + (T(T(3)) - 1))$
13629 := $((9 \times T(T(T(- (2 - 6)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (- 1)))$
13632 := $(T(T(2)) \times (- (T(3)) + T((T(T(T(6))) / T(T(3)))) + 1))$

- 13635** := $(-(T(5)) \times (-(T(3)) - T((T(6) \times (3 - 1))))$
13636 := $((T(63) \times 6) + T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13644 := $((4 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(3) - 1))$
13649 := $((9 \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(3))) + 1))$
13653 := $((3 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T((T(3) - 1))))$
13657 := $((T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6)))) / (-3 - 1))$
13658 := $(T(T(8)) + (56 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 1)))$
13662 := $((T(2) + (6) \times 6) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1)))$
13664 := $((T(T(4)) + (6)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(3) + 1)))$
13665 := $(T(T(5)) + (T((T(6) + T(6))) \times T((T(3) - 1))))$
13668 := $((T(8)/6) \times T((T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) + 1))$
13671 := $((1 \times 7) \times T(63 - 1))$
13672 := $((T(2) + T(7)) \times T(6)) \times T(T(3)) + 1$
13679 := $((T(-T(9 + 7)) + T(T(6))) \times 3) - 1$
13684 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((8 \times 6) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))))$
13685 := $((T(5) + 8) \times T((-T(6)) + T(T(3 + 1))))$
13686 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - (T(6 \times (3 + 1))))$
13688 := $(8 \times T((8 + T(6)) \times (3 - 1)))$
13689 := $((9 \times (-8 + T(6)))^{3-1})$
13692 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (9 \times (-T(6) + T(T(T(3 + 1))))))$
13694 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(9) \times 6) - T(T(3)))) - 1$
13695 := $((T(5) \times T(T(9))) - T(6 \times T(3 + 1)))$
13698 := $(T(8) + ((9 \times 6) \times T((T(3)) + 1)))$
13716 := $(T(T(6)) - (T((1 + T(7))) \times (-31)))$
13718 := $-((T(T(8)) - ((1 + T(7)) \times T(31))))$
13724 := $((T(T(4))^2 + T(T(7))) \times (3 + 1))$
13726 := $((T(62) \times 7) + T(T(3 + 1)))$
13728 := $((T(8) - T(2)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(3 + 1)))$
13729 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (7 + T(3))) + 1$
13739 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(7 + 3)) - 1))$
13749 := $-((T(T(9)) - (T(4 + T(7))) \times T((T(3) + 1))))$
13752 := $-((T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) - ((T(7) \times T(31))))$
13755 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-T(5) - T(T(7))) - (T(31)))$
13756 := $((T(6) \times T(T(T(5) - 7))) - T(T(T(3))) + 1)$
13759 := $((-9) - T(T(5))) + (T(7) \times T(31))$
13762 := $((T(T(2)) \times (-T(6))) + (T(7) \times T(31)))$
13768 := $(8 \times (T((T(6) + T(7))) + T(31)))$
13771 := $((1 - T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) + T(3))) + 1$
13773 := $((T(3) + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) - 31$
13775 := $-((T(T(5)) + (-7) - (T(7) \times T(31))))$
13776 := $((T(T(6 + 7))) + T(T(7))) \times (3 \times 1)$
13777 := $(-T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(7) + T(3))) - 1)$
13779 := $((T((T(9) + 7))) \times (7 + 3)) - 1$
13782 := $(((-2) + T(8)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(3)) - 1$
13783 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(7))/3 - 1))$
13784 := $((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(8)) - 7) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-1))$
13785 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7) - T(3))) \times (-1))$
13788 := $(T(8) \times (((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(3)) - 1))$
13789 := $((9 \times (-8 + T(T(7 + 3)))) + 1)$
13794 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 9) - T((7 + 3) + 1))$
13795 := $(T(5) - (T((T(9) + 7))) \times (-T(3 + 1)))$
13796 := $((T(6) \times (9 \times 73)) - 1)$
13797 := $((T(7) + T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$
13798 := $((T(T(8)) - 9) \times (7 \times 3) + 1)$
13816 := $((T(6) - 1) \times T(T(8))) + (T(31))$
13817 := $((T(7) + T((-1) + T(8))) \times T(T(3))) - 1$
13818 := $((-8) + T(T(1 \times 8))) \times T(T(3 \times 1))$
13819 := $((-T(9) + T(1 + T(8))) \times T(T(3))) + 1$
13822 := $(-2) - (((T(2) \times 8)^3) \times (-1))$
13826 := $(62 \times ((T(T(8))/3) + 1))$
13829 := $((9 \times T(T(2 + 8))) - 31)$
13832 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(3) + T(T(8)))) - T((T(3) + 1)))$
13833 := $(-T(3)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(3) + 1)))$
13834 := $(T(4) + ((3 \times 8)^3) \times 1)$
13835 := $-((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - 31)))$
13839 := $(T(9 - 3)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(3) + 1))$
13842 := $((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(8)/(3 + 1))$
13843 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-4 \times T(83 - 1)))$
13845 := $(-T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(8) \times (T(3) + 1)))$
13848 := $(T(8 \times 4) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)))$
13849 := $((9 \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((8 + 3) \times 1))$
13851 := $-((T(1 + T(5)) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + 1)))$
13852 := $((T(2)^5) \times (T(8) + T(T(3)))) + 1$
13853 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-5) + T(T(8))) - T((T(3) + 1)))$
13856 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - 8) / (3 - 1)$
13857 := $((T(T(7)) + (5 + T(8))) \times 31)$
13858 := $((-8) - T(T(5))) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-1))$
13859 := $((9 \times T(58 - 3)) - 1)$
13872 := $((2 + T(T(7))) \times (T(8) - (3 - 1)))$
13874 := $((-4) \times T(7)) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-1))$
13875 := $(5 \times T((78 - 3) - 1))$
13878 := $((T(T(8)) \times 7) - T(8)) \times (3 \times 1)$
13879 := $(-9) - (-T(7)) \times T(((T(8) - T(3)) + 1))$
13882 := $((T(2) + T(T(8))) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 1$
13884 := $(-4) - ((8 - T(8)) \times T(31))$
13887 := $((T(7) \times T((8 - (8 - 3)))) - 1)$
13888 := $(T((8 - (8/8))) \times T(31))$
13889 := $(-98) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + 1)$
13893 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((-T(9) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1)))$
13894 := $(-T((4 + 9))) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - 1)$
13898 := $(-89) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + 1)$
13912 := $(-T(2)) - (-T(1 + 9)) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))$
13914 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(19 + 3)) - 1)$
13915 := $(T(T(5 - 1))) \times T(-(9 - 31))$

- 13923** := $(T(T(3)) \times (-T(2) - T((9 \times (3 + 1)))))$
13924 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 9) + T((T(T(3)) + 1))$
13925 := $((5 + T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) - 1)$
13926 := $((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3 \times 1)))))$
13934 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) \times 9) + (T(T(3)) - 1)$
13937 := $((7 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) - T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13938 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(9) + (3 \times 1)))$
13941 := $((-1) + T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13942 := $((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \times 9) + T(T(T(3 + 1)))$
13944 := $(4 \times T(((4 + T(9 + 3)) + 1)))$
13945 := $(-5) - ((T(4) \times T(9)) \times (-31))$
13949 := $((T(9) \times (T(4) + T((T(9) - T(T(3)))))) - 1)$
13952 := $(2 \times ((T(5) \times T(9 + T(T(3)))) + 1))$
13954 := $-((T(T(T(4)))) + ((-T(5)) \times T(T(9)) + 31))$
13955 := $((-T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(3))) - 1$
13956 := $(6 \times (T((T(5) + T(9))) + T(31)))$
13957 := $((-T(7)) - (-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3 + 1)))$
13958 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((T(5) - 9))) - T((T(3) + 1)))$
13959 := $(9 \times (T(T(5)) + T(((9 \times T(3)) - 1)))$
13964 := $(T((4 \times T(6))) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 1))$
13965 := $((T(5) \times T(6)) \times T(9)) - T((T(T(3)) - 1))$
13967 := $((T((T(-7) + T(6))) - 9) \times 3) - 1$
13968 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) - (9 \times (3 - 1)))$
13969 := $((T(96) \times (9/3)) + 1)$
13975 := $((T(5) + T(7)) \times T(((T(9) - T(T(3))) + 1)))$
13981 := $((T(T(-1 - 8))) + T(9)) \times 31$
13982 := $(-T(2)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T((9 - 3))) - 1)$
13983 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - ((9/3) \times 1))$
13984 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times ((9 + T(3)) + 1))$
13985 := $((T(5) \times T((T(8) + 9))) - T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13986 := $(T(6) \times T((8 + ((9 \times 3) + 1))))$
13987 := $((T((T(7) + 8)) \times T((9 - 3))) + 1)$
13992 := $(T(T(2)) + (T((T(9) - 9)) \times T(T(3 \times 1))))$
13993 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + (T(3) + 1))$
13994 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 9) + ((T(9) \times 3) - 1))$
13995 := $((T(5) \times 9) - (-9) \times T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
13996 := $((T(6) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + T(3 + 1))$
14028 := $((T(T(8)) + 2) \times T(T((04 - 1)))$
14049 := $(9 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T((04 - 1))))$
14079 := $((T(T(9)) + T(70)) \times 4) - 1$
14092 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((-9) \times T(T(T(04)))) - 1)$
14112 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(11)) - T(T(T(4)))) + 1))$
14124 := $((4 + T((T(T(T(2))) - 1))) \times T((T(4) + 1)))$
14134 := $((4 + T((T(T(3)) + 1))) \times T(T(4))) - 1$
14139 := $(9 \times (31 + T(T(T(4 \times 1))))$
14144 := $(T((4 \times 4)) \times (T(14) - 1))$
14146 := $(T(T(6)) - (-T(T(4))) \times T((1 + T(T((4 - 1))))))$
14162 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T((T(6) + 1)) \times (T(T(4)) + 1))))$
14164 := $(-4) + (T((T(6) + 1)) \times (T(T(4)) + 1))$
14167 := $((T((T(7) - 6))) \times (1 + T(T(4)))) - 1$
14168 := $(8 \times (T(61) - T(T((4 + 1))))$
14174 := $((4^7) + 1) - T(T((T(4) + 1)))$
14175 := $((T(5) \times T((7 - 1))) \times T((T(4) - 1)))$
14184 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) \times (-1) + T((4 \times 1)))$
14196 := $(T(6) \times ((T(9) \times T((1 + 4))) + 1))$
14211 := $((T(11) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T((T(4) - 1))))$
14215 := $((T(T(5)) - 1)^2) + T(T(4)) - 1$
14217 := $((T(T((7 + 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T((4 - 1))))$
14224 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T((4 \times 1))))$
14225 := $((T(T(5))^2) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) + 1))$
14226 := $(6 \times (((-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(4))) + 1))$
14227 := $((T(72) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 1$
14228 := $((T((T(8) \times 2)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T((4 \times 1))))$
14229 := $(9 \times (T(T(T(2 + 2)))) + 41)$
14235 := $(T(5) \times (3 + T((2 + 41))))$
14238 := $((T(T(8)) + (T(3) \times 2)) \times T(T((4 - 1)))$
14239 := $(9 \times ((T(T(3)) \times 2) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1)$
14242 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(2) - T(T(T((4 \times 1))))$
14243 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - 2) + T(T(T((4 \times 1))))$
14244 := $((4^4) + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) - 1$
14245 := $((T(5) - 4) \times ((T(T(2))^4) - 1))$
14246 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(4) - T(2)))) \times T(T(4)) + 1)$
14248 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + 241))$
14262 := $(T(T(2)) - ((6^{T(2)})) \times T((T(4) + 1)))$
14265 := $((T(5) \times T(6)) + 2) \times T((T(4) - 1))$
14266 := $((T(T(6)) \times 62) - T(T(4))) - 1$
14267 := $(T(T(7)) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) \times (-T(4))) - 1)$
14272 := $((-2) + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times (4 \times 1)$
14273 := $((T((3 \times T(7))) - 2) \times 4) + 1$
14274 := $((T(4) - T((T(7) \times 2))) \times (-T(4) - 1))$
14275 := $(-5) - (T((T(7) \times T(2))) \times (-4 \times 1))$
14279 := $((T(((9 \times T(7))/T(2))) \times 4) - 1)$
14281 := $((T((T(-1 - 8)) \times T(2))) \times 4) + 1$
14283 := $((T(3) \times T((T(8) \times 2))) - T(T(T(4) - 1)))$
14284 := $(4 \times (T((T((8 - 2)) \times 4)) + 1))$
14286 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - (T(24) \times (-1)))$
14287 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(4))) - 1))$
14289 := $((T((T(9) + 8)) - 2) \times T(4)) - 1$
14292 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T((9 \times 2)) + T(T(T(4) + 1))))$
14295 := $(T(5) \times (92 + T(41)))$
14301 := $((T(10) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1)))$
14319 := $(9 \times ((1 - T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))))$
14321 := $(-1) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + 41))$
14322 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (2 \times 341))$

$$\begin{aligned} 14323 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + 1) \\ 14325 &:= (((T(T(5))^2) - T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) + 1) \\ 14326 &:= ((62 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 \times 1)) \\ 14328 &:= (T(8) \times (2 - (-T(3)) \times T((T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14334 &:= (((-4) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(3)) - T(T(4))) - 1) \\ 14343 &:= (-T(T(3))) \times (T(4) - (3 \times T(T(T(4 - 1))))) \\ 14344 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(4)) - T(T(3))) - T(T((T(4) - 1)))) \\ 14345 &:= ((T(T(5))^{-4+T(3)} - T(T((4 \times 1)))) \\ 14349 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(4) + T(3))) - T(T((T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14354 &:= (-T(4) + ((T(5) - T(3)) \times T((T(T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14355 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) - T(3 \times (4 - 1))) \\ 14356 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + 1) \\ 14357 &:= (-7) + ((T(5) - T(3)) \times T((T(T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14359 &:= (-((T(T(9)) - (5^{T(3)})) - T(T(T(4 - 1)))) \\ 14362 &:= (-2) + ((6 + 3) \times T((T(T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14363 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (T((6 \times 3) \times 4)) - 1) \\ 14364 &:= ((4 \times T(6)) \times T(3 \times T((4 - 1)))) \\ 14375 &:= (((T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1) \\ 14379 &:= ((T(97) \times 3) + T(T((4 + 1)))) \\ 14382 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + (T(3) \times T((T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14383 &:= (((T(T(3)) + 8) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) - 1) \\ 14385 &:= ((T(T(5))^{8-T(3)} - T((4 + 1))) \\ 14386 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) - 41) \\ 14387 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - (4 + 1))) \\ 14388 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (8 \times 3)) - T((T(T(4) + 1))) \\ 14391 &:= (T(-((1 - (9 \times 3)))) \times 41) \\ 14393 &:= (-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(9) \times T((T(T(3)) + (4)))) - 1))) \\ 14395 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((9 + T(3)))) - (4 + 1)) \\ 14399 &:= (((T(9) - T(9 \times T(3)))) \times (-T(4))) - 1) \\ 14406 &:= (6 \times (T(T(T(04))) + (T(41)))) \\ 14412 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((1 + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(41)))) \\ 14415 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T((1 + 4)))) + T((4 + 1))) \\ 14418 &:= ((-T(8)) - T(T(T(-((1 - 4)))))) \times (-T(T(4) - 1))) \\ 14419 &:= ((9 \times T((1 + T(T(4)))) + T(T((4 \times 1)))) \\ 14425 &:= ((T(T(5))^2) + (T(4) + T((4 + 1)))) \\ 14426 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T((4 + 4)))) - 1) \\ 14427 &:= (7 \times (T((T(T(2)) \times T(4))) + T(T(T(4 - 1))))) \\ 14428 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((-4) + T(4))) + 1) \\ 14429 &:= (((-9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(4) + T(T(4))) - 1) \\ 14432 &:= (((T(2) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(4) + 1) \\ 14433 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(4) - 1)))) \\ 14443 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 4) \times (-T(4) + 1)) \\ 14444 &:= (-((T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) + (-T(4)) \times T((T(T(4) - 1))))) \\ 14445 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(4)) - 4) \times T((T(4) - 1))) \\ 14448 &:= (8 \times (T((T(4) + T(4))) + T((T(T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14449 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(4) + (4))) - 41) \\ 14454 &:= (T((-4) + T(5)) \times ((4 \times T(T(4))) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14455 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + T((4 + T((4 - 1)))) \\ 14458 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((5 \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - 1)) \\ 14464 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(T(6)) + (4)) \times T(T(4))) - 1)) \\ 14465 &:= (((5 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))) \\ 14466 &:= (-6) \times (((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times (-T(4))) - 1) \\ 14472 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((7^4) + T(4) + 1)) \\ 14475 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(74))) \times (4 + 1)) \\ 14476 &:= ((-((T(T(6)) - 7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(4) + 1)) \\ 14477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + (4))) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))) \\ 14478 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(T(7)) - (4))) + T((4 - 1))) \\ 14482 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + T(-((T(4) - 41)))) \\ 14483 &:= ((T(3) \times ((-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 1) \\ 14484 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(4))) \times T((4 - 1))) \\ 14489 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times ((8 - 4) + T(4))) - 1) \\ 14515 &:= (((T(T(5)) + 1) \times T(T(5))) - (4 + 1)) \\ 14524 &:= (4 \times ((T((T(T(2)) + 5)) \times T(T(4))) + 1)) \\ 14525 &:= ((T(T(5))^2) + (5^{4-1})) \\ 14526 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T((4 + 1)))) \\ 14527 &:= ((T(7)^{T(2)} + (-5) \times T((T(T(4)) - 1))) \\ 14534 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T((T(5) \times 4)) - 1)) \\ 14535 &:= (-T(5) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T((5 + 4)) - 1))) \\ 14544 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(4)) - (-5) + T(41)) \\ 14552 &:= ((2 + T(5)) \times (-5) + T(41)) \\ 14553 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(5)) + T((T(5) - (4 - 1)))) \\ 14559 &:= ((T(T(9)) / (-T(5))) \times (-T((5 \times 4) + 1))) \\ 14562 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(5)) + T(T((T(4) + 1)))) \\ 14564 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + T(6))) \times 5) - T((T(4) + 1))) \\ 14567 &:= (7 \times (T(((T(6) - 5) \times 4) + 1)) \\ 14568 &:= (T((T(8) + T(6))) + (T(5) \times T(41))) \\ 14569 &:= (-((T(T(9)) + (T(6) - (5^{T(4-1)}))) \\ 14573 &:= (-((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)))) + ((T(5) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 1)) \\ 14574 &:= (((T(4) \times T(7)) - T(5)) \times T(T(4)) - 1) \\ 14575 &:= (5 \times (-T(T(7)) + T((T(5) + T((T(4) + 1))))) \\ 14576 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(4)) + 1) \\ 14583 &:= (-3) - (T((T(8) + T(5))) \times (-T(4) + 1)) \\ 14584 &:= (4 \times ((T(85) - T(4)) + 1)) \\ 14585 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(8))) \times (T(5) - (4))) - 1) \\ 14586 &:= (((6 \times T(8)) + 5) \times T((T(4) + 1))) \\ 14587 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) - ((T(T(5))/4) - 1)) \\ 14588 &:= ((-8) + T(85)) \times (4 \times 1) \\ 14589 &:= (9 \times ((T(8) \times T((5 + 4))) + 1)) \\ 14616 &:= (T(T((6 + 1))) \times (T(6) + T((4 + 1)))) \\ 14619 &:= ((T((91 - 6)) \times 4) - 1) \\ 14622 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(26) \times 41)) \\ 14624 &:= (4 \times (T((T(T(T(2))) + 64)) + 1)) \\ 14625 &:= ((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(((6 \times 4) + 1))) \\ 14626 &:= ((T((6 + T(2))) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 14627** := ((T(T(7)) × T((2+6))) + (T(4)+1))
14631 := (((-1)+T(3)) × T((T(6)+T(T(4)))) + 1)
14632 := ((2³) × (T((6 × T(4))) - 1))
14635 := (5 × (T((T(T(3)) + T((6+4)))) + 1))
14636 := ((-T(6)) × ((-3) × T(T(6))) - (4)) - 1)
14637 := ((-((7-3)) + T(6)) × T(41))
14639 := (((T((9 × T(3))) - (T(6))) × T(4)) - 1)
14652 := (((T(2)⁵) - T(6)) × T((T(4)+1)))
14655 := (T(5) + (((5+6)⁴) - 1))
14656 := (T(6) + (5 × (T((T(6)+T(T(4)))) + 1)))
14657 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(5)+T(6))) + 41)
14662 := (T(T(T(2))) - (((T(T(6))/T(6))⁴) × (-1)))
14663 := (T(T(3)) + (((T(T(6))/T(6))⁴) + 1))
14665 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(6)) × 64) + 1)))
14672 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(7))) × 6) + T(T(4))) + 1)
14675 := (5 × ((T(76) + T(4)) - 1))
14676 := (-6) × ((T(T(7)) × (-6)) - T((4 × 1)))
14678 := ((T(8) × T(T(7))) + (T(6)+41))
14679 := (9 × (T(T(7)) + T((-6) + T(T((4 × 1))))))
14682 := (-2) - (((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(4))) + 1)
14683 := (-3) - (((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(4))) - 1)
14684 := ((T(T(4)) × T(8)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) - 1))
14685 := (-5) × ((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) × (T(4)+1))
14686 := (((T(T(6)) + T(8)) × T((6+4))) + 1)
14688 := (((T(T(8)) + T(8)) × T(6)) - T(T(4))) + 1)
14697 := ((T((T(7)+9)) × T(6)) - T((T(4)+1)))
14718 := ((T(8) × (1 + T(T(7)))) + T((T(4)+1)))
14724 := (-4) × ((T(2) + T(T(7))) × (-T(4)-1))
14725 := ((T(T(5))²) + T((T(7) - (4-1))))
14727 := ((T(7) × (-2) + T((T(7) + (4)))) - 1)
14728 := (((T(T(8)) + T(2)) - T(T(7))) × (T(T(4)) + 1))
14736 := (((6 × T(3)) × T(T(7))) + T(T((4+1))))
14739 := (((9 + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7))) × T(T(4))) - 1)
14742 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(4)) + ((7⁴) + 1)))
14743 := (((3 + T(4)) × (-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1)
14749 := ((T(9) + (4)) × (T((T(7) - (4)) + 1)))
14752 := ((2⁵) × (T(T(7)) + T(T((4 × 1))))))
14756 := ((T((6 × T(5))) - T(T(7))) × (4 × 1))
14759 := ((T((T(9) - 5)) × (T(7) - T(4))) - 1)
14762 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(((T(T(6))/7) + (4)))) - 1)
14763 := (T(T(3)) × T(((6 × 7) - 4) - 1))
14764 := (T(T(T(4))) + (6 × (-7) + T(T((T(4)+1))))))
14766 := (-6) × ((-6) × (T(T(7)) + (4)) - 1)
14774 := ((T((4 + T(7))) × T(7)) - T((4 × 1)))
14777 := (-7) - ((-T(7)) × T((T(7) + (4 × 1))))
14778 := (T(T(8)) - (-7) × T((7 × (T(4) - 1))))
14782 := (-2) - ((-8) × T(7)) × T((T(4)+1)))
14783 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T(4)))) - 1)
14784 := (T((4 × 8)) × ((7 × 4) × 1))
14785 := ((T((T(5) - 8)) × T((T(7) + (4)))) + 1)
14787 := ((T(T(7)) × T(8)) + T((T(7) - (4 × 1))))
14788 := (-8) - ((-T(8)) × (T(T(7)) + (4 + 1)))
14795 := (((T(5) × T(9)) - T(T(7))) × T(T((4 × 1))))
14796 := (((T(T(6)) + (T(9) - 7)) × T(T(4))) + 1)
14797 := ((7 × ((9 × T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 1)
14812 := (T((T(T(2)) + 1)) × (T((8 × 4) + 1))
14821 := ((T(12) × T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) + 1)
14822 := (2 × ((T((2 + T(8))) × T(4)) + 1))
14823 := ((-T(3)) + T((T(T(T(2))) + T(8))) × (T(4) - 1))
14825 := (-5) × ((T((2 + T(8))) × (-4) - 1))
14826 := (-T(6)) + (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(8)) + 41))
14827 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) × T(8)) - (4 + 1))
14829 := (T(9) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × ((8 + T(T(4))) + 1))
14835 := (T(5) × (T(((3+8) × 4) - 1))
14837 := (((T(T(7)) + (T(3))) × T(8)) + (4 + 1))
14838 := (((-8) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-8)) + (T(T(4)) - 1))
14842 := ((2 + (T(4) × T(8))) × 41)
14844 := ((T(T(T(4))) - ((4⁸)/4)) × (-1))
14845 := (-5) + (T(4) × T((T(T((8-4)) - 1))))
14847 := ((T(T(7-4)) × T(T(8))) + (T(41)))
14849 := (((T(9) × T(T(4))) × T(T((8/4)))) - 1)
14861 := (((-1) + T(6)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4))) + 1)
14865 := (T(5) × (T(((6 × 8) - 4) + 1))
14868 := ((T(T(8)) - (-6) - T(8)) × T(T((4-1))))
14872 := ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) × ((T(T(8)) + T(4)) × (-1)))
14873 := (((T(3) + T(T(7))) × T(8)) + 41)
14874 := ((4 - T(T(7))) × (8 - T((T(4) - 1))))
14875 := (-5) × (T(7) - T((T(8) + 41)))
14877 := (T(((7 × 7) + 8)) × (T(4) - 1))
14878 := ((87 × T((8 + T(4)))) + 1)
14883 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(8))) + ((T(8) + T(41))))
14894 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 9) + T(T((T(8)/4)))) - 1)
14895 := (T(5) × (T(T(9)) - (T(8) + T((4-1))))
14896 := ((-T(6)) × T(T(9))) + ((T(T(8)) × T(T(4))) + 1))
14916 := ((T(T(6)) × T((1+9))) + T(T((T(4)+1))))
14922 := (T(T(2)) × ((T((-2) + T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1))
14924 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(2) + T(9)))) × 41)
14925 := (((T(T(5))/T(2)) - T(T(9))) × (-T((4+1))))
14928 := (8 × (T(T(T(2))) - (T(9) × (-41))))
14934 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((-3) × T(94)) + 1))
14937 := ((-T(7)) × T(T(3))) - (T(T(9)) × (-T((4+1))))
14939 := (((-9) - T((T(3) × 9))) × (-T(4))) - 1)
14951 := ((T(-(1-5))) × (-T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1)

- 14952** := $(2 \times ((5 \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1))$
14964 := $(4 \times T((-6) + T((9 + 4)) + 1))$
14972 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(7) + 9)) + T(4)) - 1)$
14973 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + 9)) + T((4 \times 1)))$
14977 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + 9)) - T((T(4) - 1)))$
14982 := $(-T(2) - ((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times T((4 + 1))))$
14984 := $((T(T(4) \times T(T(8))) \times 9) / 4 - 1)$
14985 := $-((T(5) \times (T(8) - T(9 \times (4 + 1)))))$
14986 := $((T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + T(9))) + T(T((4 \times 1)))$
14994 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-9 + 4)) + 1))$
15015 := $((T(T(5)) - T(10)) \times T(T((5 + 1)))$
15016 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-T(10)) + T(T(5))) + 1)$
15096 := $((T(6) + 90) \times T((T(5) + 1)))$
15124 := $((T(T(4))^2 \times (1 \times 5)) - 1)$
15125 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times (T(15) + 1))$
15126 := $(-6) \times ((-21) \times T(T(5))) - 1)$
15128 := $(8 \times T(((T(2) + 1) \times T(5)) + 1))$
15136 := $(T(((T(6) + T(T(3))) + 1) \times (T(5) + 1)))$
15148 := $((T((T(8) + T(4)) + 1) \times (T(5) - 1))$
15168 := $(8 \times (T(61) + (5 \times 1)))$
15177 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(7)) + T((1 + T(5)))) + 1)$
15195 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(9)) - (1 + T((5 + 1))))$
15196 := $((((-T(6)) + T(T(9))) - 1) \times T(5) + 1)$
15209 := $(((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(02)))) \times (-T(5)) - 1)$
15217 := $((T(71) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(5))) + 1)$
15224 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) - 1))$
15225 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(5) - 1)))$
15226 := $(-T(6) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(2) + (5)))) + 1))$
15228 := $((T(8) \times T(2)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-1))))$
15232 := $((2^{T(3)} \times 2) \times (T(T(5)) - 1))$
15236 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(T(3)) / T(T(T(2)))))) - T((5 - 1)))$
15238 := $(-8) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) + 1))$
15239 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) + 2) \times T(5) - 1)$
15241 := $((T((1 + T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (5 \times 1))$
15242 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) - (5 - 1))$
15243 := $(-3) + (T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((5 + 1))))$
15244 := $((T(4) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 2)) - T((T(5) + 1)))$
15245 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(4))^2 \times (5 \times 1)))$
15246 := $(T(T(6)) \times T(((4 - 2) \times 5) + 1))$
15247 := $((T((7 + 4)) \times T((T(T(2)) + (T(5)))) + 1)$
15248 := $((8 \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-1)))$
15249 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(4) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) / (T(5) \times (-1)))$
15252 := $((-T(2)) - T(T(5))) \times ((-T(2)) - T(T(5))) - 1)$
15255 := $((-T(5)) - T(T(5))) \times ((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) + 1)$
15256 := $((T(6) \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))) + T((T(5) + 1))$
15262 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(6)) / T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(5) + 1))$
15264 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((6 - 2))) - T((T(5) + 1)))$
15265 := $((5^6) - (T(2) \times T(T((5 \times 1))))$
15266 := $(T(6) + ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) - 1))$
15274 := $((47 \times T(25)) - 1)$
15276 := $(-67) \times (T(2) - T(T((5 + 1))))$
15282 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + ((T(T(2))^{5-1}))$
15283 := $((T(T(3)) + 8) \times (T((2^5) - 1))$
15285 := $(-T(5) - (T((8 \times T(2))) \times (-51)))$
15287 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(8)) - T((T(2) \times 5)))) - 1)$
15288 := $((8 \times T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((5 + 1)))$
15293 := $((T(T(3)) \times (9^{T(2)})) - (T(5) + 1))$
15294 := $-(((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) - (2^{T(5)-1}))$
15295 := $((T(5) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(T(2)) + (T(5)))) + 1)$
15299 := $((9 - T(T(9))) + T(T(2))) \times (-T(5)) - 1)$
15309 := $((9^{03}) \times T((5 + 1)))$
15312 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times T((T(3) + (5 \times 1)))$
15313 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times T((T(3) + (5)))) + 1)$
15318 := $(T(T(8)) \times (-((1 - 3) + T((5 + 1))))$
15322 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((2 \times (T(3)^5) + 1)))$
15323 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(2)^{T(3)})) + (T(5) - 1))$
15325 := $((5^{T(T(2))}) - T((3 + T((5 + 1))))$
15328 := $((T(T(8)) \times 23) + T((5 - 1)))$
15335 := $(5 \times (T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) - (T(5) - 1)))$
15336 := $(6 \times T(((T(3) \times (-3) + T(5))) - 1))$
15337 := $(T(7) + ((3^{T(3)}) \times T((5 + 1)))$
15352 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(T(5)) + (T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + 1))$
15354 := $(((-T(4) + T(T((T(5) - 3)))) \times 5) - 1)$
15355 := $(5 \times (T(T((T(5) - 3))) - T((5 - 1))))$
15356 := $(T(T(6)) + ((5^3) \times (T(T(5)) + 1)))$
15357 := $((7 \times T(T((5 + T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-1)))$
15358 := $((-T(8) - (5^{T(3)})) - T(T((5 + 1))))$
15359 := $((T(T(9)) - (5 + T(3))) \times T(5) - 1)$
15364 := $(T(T(4)) + (T(6) \times (3^{5+1})))$
15365 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(3) + (5)))) - 1))$
15366 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-1)))$
15367 := $((7 + T((T(6) - T(3)))) \times (T(T(5)) + 1))$
15368 := $((T(8) - (T(T(6)) / (-3))) \times T((T(5) + 1)))$
15372 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (5 + 1)))$
15373 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times T((3 + 5))) + 1)$
15375 := $(T(5) \times (((7 - 3)^5) + 1))$
15378 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(3)))) + (5 + 1))$
15382 := $((T((T(2) + 8)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(5) + 1)))$
15383 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T((T(8)/3))) \times 5) - 1))$
15384 := $(((-4) + T(T((T(8)/3)))) \times 5) - 1)$
15385 := $(5 \times (T(T((T(8)/3))) - (5 - 1)))$
15389 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((8 - 3))) - T((T(5) + 1)))$
15392 := $(2 \times ((T(9) \times T((3 + T(5)))) + 1))$

- 15393** := $(T(T(3)) \times ((9^3) + 5) - 1)$
15394 := $((((4-9))^{T(3)} - T(T((5+1))))$
15395 := $((5 \times T(T((9+3)))) - T((5-1)))$
15396 := $(-6) \times (-T(9) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(5))) + 1))$
15397 := $(-7) + ((T(T((9+3))) \times 5) - 1)$
15398 := $(-8) - ((T(T((9+3))) \times (-5)) - 1)$
15399 := $(9 \times T(((T(9) + 3) + T((5-1))))$
15505 := $-((T(T(5)) + (0 - (5^{5+1})))$
15509 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(05)) - (T(5) + 1))$
15518 := $-((T(T(8)) + ((1 - T(T(5))) \times T((T(5) + 1))))$
15519 := $((T(T(9)) \times 15) - (5 + 1))$
15522 := $(2 \times ((T(T(2))^{5}) - T((5 \times 1)))$
15523 := $(-3) - ((T((T(2) \times T(5))) \times (-T(5))) - 1)$
15524 := $((T((T((4-2)) \times T(5))) \times T(5)) - 1)$
15525 := $(T(5) \times T(-((2-5)) \times T((5 \times 1))))$
15526 := $((T(T((6 \times 2))) \times 5) + T(T(5))) + 1)$
15527 := $(T(T(7)) + (((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))) + 1))$
15528 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(5) + 1))))$
15529 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(2) \times 5)) + (5 - 1))$
15532 := $(2 \times ((T(3)^5) - T((5-1)))$
15534 := $(T(4) - ((T((3 \times T(5))) \times (-T(5))) + 1))$
15535 := $((5^{T(3)}) - (T(5) \times (5 + 1)))$
15539 := $((T(T(9)) \times (3 \times 5)) + (T(5) - 1))$
15541 := $((1 + T(45)) \times T(5)) + 1)$
15544 := $-((T(T(4)) - (((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - 1)))$
15545 := $((T(T(5)) + T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T((5-1)))$
15546 := $(T(6) - ((T(45) \times T(5)) \times (-1)))$
15547 := $(-7) \times (-T(4) - T(T((5+5) + 1)))$
15548 := $((T(T(8)) + T(4)) \times ((T(T(5))/5) - 1))$
15552 := $((T(T(2))^{5}) \times ((5/5) + 1))$
15555 := $(-5) \times (T(5) - ((5^5) + 1))$
15556 := $((T(T(6)) \times 5) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + 1))$
15564 := $-((T(T(4)) + (6 - (5^{5+1})))$
15565 := $((5^6) - (T(5) \times (5 - 1)))$
15567 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + (T((5 \times 5)))) - 1)$
15568 := $-(((T(8) + T(6)) - ((5^{5+1}))))$
15569 := $((T(9) \times (T(6) + T((5 \times 5)))) - 1)$
15576 := $-(((T(6) + T(7)) - ((5^{5+1}))))$
15579 := $((T(T(9)) + 7) \times T(5)) - 51)$
15582 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(8)) + ((5 \times T(5)) + 1)))$
15583 := $-(((T(3) + T(8)) - ((5^{5+1}))))$
15591 := $((1 + T(T(9))) \times T(5)) + 51)$
15593 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(9)) + 5) \times (-T(5))) + 1)$
15594 := $(T(T(4)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))) - (T(5) - 1)))$
15595 := $((T(5) - T(9)) + ((5^{5+1})))$
15598 := $-((T(8) - ((9 + (5^{5+1}))))$
15599 := $((((T(T(9))/9) + (T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - 1)$
15614 := $((T(T((T(4) - 1))) + 6) \times T(5)) - 1)$
15615 := $((5 \times 1)^6) - T((5-1))$
15621 := $(((-1) + T(T(2)))^6) - (5 - 1)$
15623 := $((T(T(3)) \times ((T(2)^6) + T(5))) - 1)$
15624 := $((T(4)/2)^{T(6)-T(5)} - 1)$
15627 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/6) - (5 - 1))$
15629 := $((-T(9) - T(T((2 \times 6)))) \times (-5)) - 1)$
15631 := $((-1) + T(3))^6 + (5 + 1)$
15635 := $((5^{T(3)}) + ((6 + 5) - 1))$
15636 := $(T(T(6)) - (T(T((T(3) + 6)))) \times (-5 \times 1))$
15637 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))))/6) + (5 + 1)$
15641 := $((1 + 4)^6) + T(5) + 1)$
15642 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) \times (6 + T(T((5 + 1))))$
15645 := $(-T(5)) \times (((-4) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5))) + 1)$
15652 := $(T(T(2)) - ((5^6) - T((5 + 1))))$
15656 := $(T(6) + (5^6)) + T((5 - 1))$
15657 := $(T(7) + (((5^6) + 5) - 1))$
15659 := $((T(9) \times T((5 + T(6)))) - T((T(5) + 1)))$
15664 := $(4 \times T((T((6 + 6)) + T((5 - 1))))$
15674 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(6)) + T(T((5 - 1))))$
15682 := $((T((2 + T(8))) \times T(6)) + T(T(5))) + 1)$
15687 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + (T(6) \times 51))$
15688 := $((T(88) + 6) \times (5 - 1))$
15697 := $((T((-7) + T(9))) \times T(6)) + T((T(5) + 1))$
15707 := $(T(7) \times T((T(07) + 5))) - 1)$
15725 := $((5^2) \times (T((7 \times 5)) - 1))$
15726 := $((T(6) \times 2) \times T(T(7))) - T(51)$
15729 := $((T(9) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) - T((T(5) - 1))$
15731 := $((T(T((1 + 3))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(5)))) + 1)$
15732 := $((T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T((5 \times 1))))$
15733 := $((T((3 \times T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(5))) + 1)$
15736 := $(T((T(6)/3)) \times (T((T(7) + 5))) + 1)$
15745 := $((5^{T(-4+7)}) + T(T((5 \times 1))))$
15747 := $-(((T(T(7)) - (4^7)) + T(T((5 + 1))))$
15749 := $((T(9) \times T(4)) \times (7 \times 5)) - 1)$
15755 := $(-5) \times ((-5) \times T((7 \times 5))) - 1)$
15756 := $(T(T(6)) - (-T(5)) \times T(T(((-7) + T(5)) + 1))))$
15762 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T((67 + 5)) - 1))$
15765 := $((5^6) + (T(7) \times (5 \times 1)))$
15771 := $(T(-((1 - 7))) \times 751)$
15772 := $((T(T((2 + 7))) - (7^5)) \times (-1))$
15779 := $((T(T(9)) - ((7 + (7^5)))) \times (-1))$
15783 := $((3 + T(8)) \times T(T(7))) - 51)$
15785 := $((5 + T(8)) \times 7) \times T(T((5 - 1)))$

- 15792** := $(T((2 + T(9))) \times (-7) + T((5 + 1)))$
15793 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) + ((7^5) \times 1))$
15794 := $((((T(4) - T(T(9))) - T(7)) \times (-T(5))) - 1)$
15795 := $((T(5) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7))) - T((T(5) + 1))$
15823 := $((T(3) \times T((2 \times T(8)))) + T(T((5 - 1)))$
15824 := $(-4) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T((8 + 5))) + 1))$
15825 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(T(2)) \times 8)) - ((T(T(5)) + 1)))$
15827 := $((T(7) + T((T(T(2)) + 8))) \times (T(T(5)) - 1)$
15834 := $(T(T((4 + 3))) \times ((8 \times 5) - 1))$
15835 := $((5^{T(3)}) + T(((T(8) - T(5)) - 1)))$
15839 := $((T(T(9)) - T((T(3) + T(8)))) \times T(T(5)) - 1)$
15842 := $(2 \times ((T((4 \times 8)) \times T(5)) + 1))$
15843 := $(3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T((85 + 1))))$
15846 := $(-6) \times ((T((4 \times 8)) \times (-5)) - 1)$
15855 := $((T(T(5)) + (-5) + T(8)) \times T((T(5) - 1))$
15856 := $(T(T(6)) - (5^{T(8-5)}) \times (-1))$
15862 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(6) \times T(8))) - (T(5) - 1)$
15863 := $((((3 + T(6)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) - 1)$
15864 := $((4 \times 6) \times T(T(8))) - T(T((5 \times 1)))$
15866 := $((T(6) \times T(6)) \times T(8)) - T((5 - 1))$
15868 := $(-8) + ((T(6) \times T(8)) \times T((5 + 1)))$
15872 := $(T((T(2) + T(7))) \times (8 \times (5 - 1)))$
15876 := $(T(6) \times ((T(7) + 8) \times T((5 + 1)))$
15879 := $(((-9) + T(T(7))) \times (8 \times 5)) - 1)$
15884 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(88))) \times (5 - 1))$
15897 := $((T((7 \times 9)) \times 8) - T(T((5 + 1)))$
15912 := $((2 + 1) + 9) \times T(51)$
15917 := $(T(T(7)) - (((-1) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(5))) - 1)$
15924 := $(((-T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-9)) - T((5 \times 1)))$
15925 := $(T(5^2)) \times (T(9) + (5 - 1))$
15927 := $((T(T(7)) - T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))) + 1))$
15929 := $((((-9) \times T(2)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(5))) - 1)$
15931 := $(T(T((1 + T(3)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times (-1))))$
15932 := $(-T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(9))/T(5))) - 1)$
15933 := $(T(T(3)) - ((3 + 9) \times T(51)))$
15934 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9) - (5 \times 1)$
15935 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(9))/T(5))) + 1)$
15937 := $((T(T(7)) + T(3)) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times (-1))))$
15938 := $((T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) \times (T(T(9))/T(5))) - 1)$
15939 := $((-9) + T((3 + 9))) \times T(T((5 + 1)))$
15943 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 9) + (5 - 1)$
15944 := $((T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times 9) + (T(5) - 1))$
15945 := $(-T(5)) + (T(4) \times T((T(T(9 - 5))) + 1))$
15948 := $(T(8) \times ((-4) \times (9 - T(T(5)))) - 1)$
15966 := $((T(6) \times T(6)) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times (-1))))$
15967 := $(T(7) - ((69) \times T(T((5 + 1))))$
15968 := $(8 \times ((T(6) \times 95) + 1))$
15972 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(5) + 1)))$
15974 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 9) - T(T(T((5 - 1))))$
15982 := $(-2) - (T(T(8)) \times (-9) - T((5 \times 1)))$
15983 := $((T(3) \times T(T(8))) \times (9 - 5)) - 1)$
15984 := $((-4) \times T(T(8))) \times (9 - T((5 \times 1)))$
15987 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + ((T(9) + T(51))))$
15988 := $((8 - T(89)) \times (-5 - 1))$
16128 := $(8 \times T(((2 \times 1) + 61)))$
16152 := $((2^{T(5)-1}) - T(T(6))) - 1)$
16153 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((5 - 1)^{6+1})))$
16169 := $((9 + 61) \times T(T(6))) - 1)$
16171 := $((-(1 - 71)) \times T(T(6))) + 1)$
16174 := $(4^7) - T((-1) + T((6 \times 1)))$
16195 := $((T(5) \times T((T(9) + 1))) - (T(6) - 1))$
16199 := $((T(T(9)) + T(9)) \times T(-((1 - 6)))) - 1)$
16207 := $((T((70 + T(2))) \times 6) + 1)$
16214 := $((T(T((T(4) + 1)))/T(2)) \times (T(6) + 1))$
16215 := $(T(5) \times T((1 + T((2 + 6) + 1))))$
16224 := $((T(T(4)) - T(2))^2) \times (6 \times 1)$
16228 := $(T(8) + ((2^{T(T(2))}) \times T((T(6) + 1))))$
16234 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(3))/2) \times T(6) + 1)$
16235 := $((T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) - 1)$
16236 := $((6 \times 3) \times (T((2 \times T(6))) - 1))$
16253 := $((3 + T(5)) \times T((2 \times T(6)))) - 1)$
16255 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(5)))/(-T(2))) \times T(T((6 + 1))))$
16264 := $((4^{T(6)/T(2)}) - T(T((6 - 1))))$
16275 := $((5 \times 7) \times T((2 \times T((6 - 1))))$
16282 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((6 + 1)))$
16287 := $((T(7) + 8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 61)$
16296 := $(T(6) \times ((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) - T((T(6) + 1))))$
16297 := $((((-T(7)) + T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6)) + 1)$
16318 := $((T(8) + 1) \times T(T(3))) \times T(6) + 1)$
16324 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T((6 \times 1))))$
16334 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-3) + T((3 + T(6)))) - 1)$
16338 := $((8 \times T((3 \times T(T(3)))) + (T((T(6) - 1))))$
16345 := $(5 \times (T((T(T(4)) - 3)) + (T(61))))$
16348 := $(-((T(8) - ((T(4) - T(3))^{6+1})))$
16349 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(3) - T(6))) - 1)$
16364 := $((4^{T(6)/3}) - (T(6) - 1))$
16365 := $(-T(5)) + (T((6 + T(3))) \times T((T(6) - 1)))$
16368 := $((T(T(8)) + T((6 + T(3)))) \times (T(6) + 1))$
16379 := $(T(9) \times ((7^3) + T(6))) - 1)$
16395 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(9)) - ((3 - 61))))$
16412 := $(2^{14}) + T((6 + 1))$
16422 := $(T(((2^{T(T(2))}) + 4)) \times (6 + 1))$
16425 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-((T(4) - 61))))$

- 16426** := $((T(6) \times 2) + (4^{6+1}))$
16428 := $((T(T(8))^2)/(T(T(4)) - T((6+1))))$
16429 := $((T(T(92) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 6) + 1)$
16434 := $(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times (-4) + T((T(6) + 1)))$
16435 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(6) + 1))))$
16439 := $((T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - 61)$
16442 := $((T(2) + T(T(4))) + (4^{6+1}))$
16444 := $-((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(4)) \times T((4 \times 6))) - 1)))$
16445 := $((T((5 + T(4))) - T(T(4))) \times T((T(6) + 1)))$
16454 := $(T(T(4)) + (T(5) + (4^{6+1})))$
16455 := $(T(5) \times ((T(5) + T(46)) + 1))$
16459 := $((-T(9)) + T(T(5))) + (4^{6+1})$
16462 := $(T((2 \times 6)) + (4^{6+1}))$
16463 := $((((3^6) + T(T(4))) \times T(6)) - 1)$
16464 := $(4 \times (T(6) + ((4^6) - 1)))$
16465 := $((5^6) + (4 \times T((T(6) - 1))))$
16469 := $((9 \times T(((6+4) \times 6))) - 1)$
16472 := $((-T(2) - 74) \times (T(T(6)) + 1))$
16475 := $(T(-((T(5) - T(7)))) + (4^{6+1}))$
16478 := $((8 + T((T(7) + T(4)))) \times (T(6) + 1))$
16479 := $(9 \times (T((T(7+4)) - (6))) + 1)$
16492 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((-9) \times T((T(4) \times 6))) - 1)$
16493 := $((T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) \times T(T(4))) - (6 + 1))$
16495 := $(T(T(5)) - ((9 - (4^{6+1}))))$
16497 := $(T(7) + ((9 \times T((T(4) \times 6))) - 1))$
16499 := $((T(T(9)/9) + (4^{6+1}))$
16527 := $(T((7 \times T(T(2)))) + ((5^6) - 1))$
16528 := $(T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) + ((5^6) \times 1))$
16529 := $(T((T(9) - T(2))) + ((5^6) + 1))$
16534 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(3) + 5)) - T(T((6+1))))$
16539 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) - 5)) - T((6 \times 1)))$
16544 := $((4 \times 4) \times (T(T((T(5) - 6)))) - 1)$
16545 := $(T(5) + (T(4) \times T((56+1))))$
16551 := $((T((1 + T(5))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T((6 \times 1))))$
16552 := $(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((-5) + T(6))) + 1))$
16559 := $((T((9 \times 5)) \times (-5) + T(6)) - 1)$
16561 := $((16 \times T(T((T(5) - 6)))) + 1)$
16565 := $(T(T(5)) + (65 \times T((T(6) + 1))))$
16569 := $((T(9) \times T(6)) + ((5^6) - 1))$
16572 := $((-((T(2) - (7^5))) - T(T(6))) - 1)$
16573 := $((-(3 - (7^5))) - T(T((6 \times 1))))$
16574 := $((4^7) + T(((T(T(5))/6) - 1)))$
16576 := $((-((T(6) - (7^5))) - T((T(6) - 1)))$
16584 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) - (-T(5)) \times (T(T(6) + 1))))$
16585 := $((T(T(5)) \times 8) + ((5^6) \times 1))$
16587 := $((T(7) - T(T(8))) \times (-5) - T(6)) - 1)$
16592 := $((2 + T(T(9))) \times (-5) + T((6 \times 1)))$
16598 := $((T((T(8) + T(9))) \times 5) - (6 + 1))$
16599 := $((T((9 \times 9)) \times 5) - (6 \times 1))$
16614 := $((4^{1+6}) + T(T(6))) - 1)$
16625 := $((5^2) \times (T((6 \times 6)) - 1))$
16626 := $((-6) \times (((-2) \times T(T(6))) \times 6) + 1)$
16627 := $((72 \times T(T(6))) - (6 - 1))$
16632 := $((T((2^3)) \times T(6)) \times (T(6) + 1))$
16633 := $((T(T(3) + T(3)) \times 6) \times T(T(6))) + 1)$
16638 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(6)))) + (6 \times 1))$
16645 := $((-T(5)) - (T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) \times (-T((6+1))))$
16648 := $(8 \times (T((-((4-6)^6)) + 1))$
16654 := $((4^5) - T(T(6))) \times T(6) + 1)$
16655 := $((-5) \times ((-5) \times T((6 \times 6))) - 1)$
16668 := $(T(8) \times ((T(6) \times T(6)) + T(6)) + 1)$
16675 := $(T(5) + (T(7) \times T((6 + T((6+1))))))$
16684 := $(4 \times (T(T((-8) + T(6)))) - T((6-1)))$
16688 := $(8 \times ((-T(8)) + T(T(6))) + (T(61)))$
16692 := $((T(T(2)) - ((T(9) + T(6)) \times T((T(6) + 1))))$
16694 := $((-4) + ((T(9) + T(6)) \times T((T(6) + 1))))$
16695 := $((T(5) + T((T(9) - 6))) \times T((6 \times 1)))$
16698 := $((8 \times 9) - 6) \times T((T(6) + 1))$
16724 := $((-4) \times ((T(T(2)) - T(T((7+6)))) - 1))$
16728 := $(82 \times ((-T(7)) + T(T(6))) + 1)$
16729 := $((T((9 + T(2))) - ((7^{6-1})))$
16735 := $((T(5)^3) - T(7)) \times (6 - 1)$
16752 := $((T((2 \times 5)) - (7^{6-1}))$
16757 := $((7^5) - T(7)) - T(6) - 1)$
16762 := $((T((T(2) + 6)) - ((7^{6-1})))$
16764 := $((4 \times T(T((6+7)))) + (T(6) - 1))$
16771 := $((T((1+7)) - (7^{6-1}))$
16773 := $((T(3) + T(7)) - (7^{6-1}))$
16775 := $((5 \times T(T((T(7)/7))) \times 61)$
16778 := $((T(8) - ((7 + (7^{6-1}))))$
16779 := $((T(9) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (-1)))$
16786 := $((T(6) \times T(8)) + 7) \times (T(6) + 1)$
16787 := $((T(7) - (8 + (7^{6-1})))$
16813 := $(T(3) + (-((1-8)^{6-1}))$
16822 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(2) + T(8))) + (T(6)))) + 1)$
16824 := $(4 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) + T((T(6) - 1))))$
16825 := $((5^2) \times (T(T(8)) + (6 + 1)))$
16827 := $((7^{-T(2)+8}) + (T(6) - 1))$
16835 := $((T(5)^3) - 8) \times (6 - 1)$
16836 := $((T((T(6) - T(3)) + 8)) \times 61)$

- 16842** := $((T(2^4) + T(T(8))) \times T((6 \times 1)))$
16843 := $((T((T(3) + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 1)$
16845 := $((-5) + T((T(4) - 8))) \times T((6 - 1))$
16847 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times (8 \times 6) - 1)$
16848 := $((T(8) \times T((4 + 8))) \times (6 \times 1))$
16862 := $((((-2) \times T(T(6))) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(6))) - 1$
16863 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times ((68 + 6) - 1))$
16864 := $((T(T(4)) - T(6)) \times T((T(8) - (6 - 1))))$
16877 := $-((T(7) - (7 \times T((8 + 61))))$
16878 := $(-87) \times ((T(8) - T(T(6))) + 1)$
16884 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) + 8) \times (-T((6 + 1)))$
16896 := $((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times ((T(8) - T(6)) + 1))$
16936 := $((T((T(6)/3)) + T(9)) \times (T(T(6)) + 1))$
16953 := $-((T((T(3) + 5)) - (9 \times T(61))))$
16954 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) + (9 \times T(61)))$
16959 := $-((T(9) + T(5)) - (9 \times T(61)))$
16964 := $-((T((4 + 6)) - (9 \times T(61))))$
16965 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) \times (T(6) - 1))))$
16967 := $((T(7) + T((-6) + T(9))) \times T(6) - 1)$
16968 := $(8 \times (T(T(6)) - (-9 \times T((T(6) - 1))))$
16986 := $((T(6) + T(8)) \times (T(9) + T((T(6) + 1)))$
16989 := $((T(9) \times T((T(8) - 9))) - T((6 \times 1))$
16992 := $((2 \times 9) \times ((T(9) \times T(6)) - 1))$
16994 := $((T(T(4)) \times (9 + T((T(9) - T(6)))) - 1)$
16995 := $(T(5) \times ((9 + T(9)) \times T(6) - 1))$
17015 := $(5 \times T(((T(10) + T(7)) - 1)))$
17019 := $(9 \times T(-(10 - 71)))$
17073 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(07))) + 1))$
17079 := $((T(9) - T(70)) \times (-7) - 1)$
17136 := $((T(6) \times T(3)) \times T((17 - 1)))$
17138 := $(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times (-71)))$
17157 := $(-7) \times (T((T(5) - 1)) - T(71))$
17172 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) - 1)) \times (T(7) - 1))$
17196 := $(T(T(6)) + (T(9) \times (-1) + T((T(7) - 1))))$
17198 := $((T(T(8)) + (-((T(9) - 1) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-1))$
17199 := $((9 \times 91) \times T((7 - 1)))$
17224 := $((T(T(4)) - 2) \times T(-(T(2) - T(7)))) - 1$
17226 := $((T(6) + T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)) + 1)))$
17238 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times (27 - 1))$
17239 := $((T((T(9) + T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) + (7))) + 1)$
17247 := $((T(T(7)) + T((T(4) \times 2))) \times T(7) - 1)$
17248 := $((T((T(8) + 4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((7 \times 1)))$
17253 := $((3^{T(5)/T(2)}) \times 71)$
17254 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (71)$
17255 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(5)) - T((T(2) \times T(7)))) - 1)$
17256 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) + T((7 + 1)))$
17262 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) - 1))$
17276 := $(T(T(6)) + (7 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - 1)))$
17279 := $((T(9) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) - T(7))) - 1)$
17282 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((-T(8)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + 1)$
17283 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (((-T(8)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T((7 \times 1))))$
17284 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) + T(((T(2) \times T(7)) + 1))))$
17287 := $(-T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-2) + T(7)) - 1)$
17291 := $((T(19) \times T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) + 1)$
17295 := $(T(5) \times ((9 \times 2^7) + 1))$
17297 := $(-T(7)) - (T(9) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T((7 \times 1))))$
17298 := $((8 \times 9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((7 + 1)))$
17316 := $((T(6) - 1) + T(3)) \times T(T((7 + 1)))$
17322 := $(T(2) \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-3) + T(7))) - 1)$
17324 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) \times 3))) \times 7) - 1$
17325 := $((T(5)^2) \times (T(3) + 71))$
17326 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(2) \times (-3) + T(7))) + 1)$
17328 := $((T(8) + 2) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(7) + 1))))$
17329 := $((T(9) - 2) \times (-3) + T(T((7 \times 1))))$
17342 := $((T(2) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \times (T(7) + 1))$
17343 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T((T(T(3)) + (71))))$
17346 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \times T((7 - 1)))$
17352 := $((T(-(T(2) - T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((7 + 1)))$
17354 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(7) + 1)$
17355 := $(-5) \times (T(5) - T((3 \times T(7)) - 1))$
17357 := $((-((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3))))/(-7)) - 1)$
17372 := $((-2) + T(T(7))) \times ((T(3) \times 7) + 1)$
17374 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - 3) \times (7 \times 1))$
17375 := $(T(T(5)) + (T((T(7) + T(3))) \times (T(7) + 1)))$
17387 := $((T(T(7)) + 8) \times (T(3) \times 7) - 1)$
17388 := $(T(8) \times (((8^3) - T(7)) - 1))$
17389 := $((-T(9)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(3)) + (7)) + 1)$
17391 := $(T((-1) + T(9))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times 71)$
17394 := $((T((T(T(4)) + (9 + T(3)))) \times 7) - 1)$
17395 := $((5 + 9) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 71$
17415 := $(T(5) \times ((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T((T(7) - 1))))$
17418 := $(T(T((8 + 1))) + (((4^7) - 1)))$
17419 := $(T(T(9)) + (((1 \times 4)^7) \times 1))$
17424 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(4) \times T((T(7) + 1))))$
17425 := $(5 \times ((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(7)) - 1)))$
17431 := $((-1) + T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) + 1)$
17435 := $(-5) \times ((T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(T(7))) \times (-1))$
17437 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (7 \times 1)$
17439 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) + (((4^7) - 1)))$
17445 := $(5 \times ((4 + T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) - 1))$
17446 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(4) - 71))$
17448 := $((T(8) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) \times (7 + 1))$
17452 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((-5) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) - 1)$
17455 := $(5 \times (5 + T((T(T(4)) + T((7 \times 1))))$

- 17456 := (T(6) - (-5) × (T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) + 1))
17457 := (((T(7) + T(5)) × T((4 × 7))) - 1)
17459 := (((9 + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) × 7) + 1)
17464 := (T(46) + ((4⁷) - 1))
17465 := (5 × ((6 + T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) + 1))
17469 := (9 × ((-6) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) + 1))
17472 := (2 × ((T(T(7)) + T(4)) × T((7 - 1)))
17473 := ((-T(3)) × ((T(T(7)) + T(4)) × (-7)) + 1)
17478 := -((T(T(8)) - ((-7) + T(T(4))) × T((T(7) - 1))))
17484 := (4 × T((T(8 × 4) - T((T(7) + 1))))
17488 := (8 × ((T((8/4))⁷) - 1))
17492 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(4) + (7))) - 1)
17493 := ((-T(3)) + T(T(9))) × (-4) + T((7 - 1))
17495 := ((5 × T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (7 + 1))
17499 := (((T(9)/9)⁴) × T(7)) - 1)
17516 := (T(61) + (5⁷⁻¹))
17532 := (-T(2)) × (T(T(T(3))) + (-T(5)) × (T(T(7)) - 1))
17535 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(3))) - (T(5))) × (7 × 1))
17538 := ((T(T(8)))/(-3)) × (-T((5 + 7)) + 1))
17542 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) × (7 × 1))
17543 := (((T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) × 7) + 1)
17544 := (4 × (T((4 × T(5))) + (T(71)))
17549 := (((T(9 × T(4))) × T(T(5)))/T(7)) - 1)
17556 := ((T(6) - T(5)) × T((5 + 71)))
17562 := (T(T(2)) + (6 × T((5 + 71))))
17564 := -((T(T(4)) - (-T(6)) × ((T(T(5)) × (-7)) + 1)))
17568 := (8 × (T(6) + (5 × T((T(7) + 1))))
17583 := (T(3) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) × (T(7) - 1))
17592 := (-2) + ((T(9) × (-T(5) + T(T(7)))) - 1)
17593 := (-3) + ((T(9) × (-T(5) + T(T(7)))) + 1)
17595 := ((5 × 9) × (-T(5) + T(T((7 × 1))))
17622 := (T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(6)) + T((7 + 1)))
17625 := (T(5) × (((2 × T(6)) × T(7)) - 1))
17635 := (5 × (((T(3) × T(6)) × T(7)) - 1))
17639 := (((9 + T(T(3))) × (T(6) × T(7))) - 1)
17641 := (((T(14) × 6) × T(7)) + 1)
17643 := (3 × (((T(4) × T(6)) × T(7)) + 1))
17644 := ((T(T(4)) × T((4 + T(6)))) - T(T((7 - 1))))
17646 := ((T(T(6)) × T(4)) - (-6) × T(71))
17647 := (7 × (T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) - ((T(T(7)) - 1)))
17648 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T((4 + 6)))) × (7 + 1))
17649 := (-9) × (T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) - (T(71)))
17655 := (T(5) + (T(5) × T((6 × (7 + 1))))
17664 := (-4) × ((-T(6)) × T(T(6))) + T((T(7) + 1)))
17667 := (((T(T(7)) - 6) + T(T(6))) × T(7)) - 1)
17682 := -((T(T(2)) - (8 × T((67 - 1))))
17684 := (-4) - (-8) × T((67 - 1))
17685 := (((-5) + T(T(8))) - 6) × (T(7) - 1))
17688 := (8 × T(((T(8) - 6) + T((7 + 1))))
17697 := ((79 × (T(T(6)) - 7)) + 1)
17724 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)) × T((7 + 1))))
17728 := (8 × (((T(2)⁷) + T(7)) + 1))
17729 := ((T(9) × (-T(2)) + T(T(7))) - T(T((7 × 1))))
17732 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(-((T(3) - T(7)))) × (-71)))
17736 := (-6) × ((T(3) - T(T(7))) - (T(71)))
17739 := ((T(9) × (3 + T(T(7)))) - T(T((7 + 1))))
17745 := (T(5) × (T((T(T(4)) - 7)) + (7 × 1))
17748 := (T(8) × (-4 - (7 × 71)))
17749 := ((T(9) × (-T(4)) + T(T(7))) - 71))
17756 := -((T((T(6) - 5)) + (-7) × T(71)))
17766 := ((-6) × T(6)) - (-7) × T(71))
17769 := ((T(9) × (-6) + T(T(7))) - T(T((7 - 1))))
17772 := -((T(T(-(2 - 7))) + (-7) × T(71)))
17784 := (T((T(4) + 8)) × (T((7 + 7)) - 1))
17786 := ((T(T(T(T(-(6 - 8)))) × 77) - 1)
17787 := (-7) × ((8 + 7) - T(71))
17793 := (3 × 9) × (-7) + T(T((7 + 1)))
17794 := ((-4) + T(9)) × (T(7) + T(T((7 × 1))))
17832 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-3) × T(T(8))) × (7 + 1))
17835 := (((T(5)/3) + T(8)) × T((T(7) + 1))
17836 := ((T(6)/3) × (-8) + T(71))
17837 := (((7 × T((T(T(3)) - 8))) × T(7)) + 1)
17845 := (5 × (T(((4 + 8) × 7) - 1))
17846 := -((T((6 + T(4))) - (T(T(8)) × (T(7) - 1)))
17849 := (((-9) × T(T(4))) × (-T(8))) + (T(7) + 1))
17853 := (-3) + (T((-5) + T(8))) × T((7 + 1))
17855 := (5 × (T((-5 - 8) × T(7)) + 1))
17856 := ((6 × T((-5) + T(8))) × (7 - 1))
17857 := (-7) × (5 + (T(8) × (-71)))
17862 := (26 × (T(T(8)) + T((7 - 1)))
17863 := (((36 + 8) × T(T(7))) - 1)
17864 := (-((4 - (6 × 8))) × T(T((7 × 1))))
17865 := (((T(5) + T(6)) + 8) × T(T(7))) + 1)
17869 := -((T((T(9) - 6)) - ((T(T(8)) × T(7)) + 1)))
17874 := ((-4) + T((T(7) + 8))) × (T(7) - 1))
17877 := (-T((7 + 7)) + (T(T(8)) × (T(7) - 1)))
17885 := ((T((-5) + T(8))) × T(8)) + (T(7) + 1))
17886 := (T(6) + (((8 + T(8)) × T(T(7))) + 1))
17891 := ((T(-((1 - 9 × 8))) × 7) - 1)
17892 := (((-2) + T(9)) - T(8)) × T(71))
17893 := (((-3 × 9) + T(T(8))) × T(7)) + 1)
17895 := (-T(5)) + (T(9) × (-8) + T(T((7 × 1))))
17927 := ((7 + T(T(2))) × (T((T(9) + 7)) + 1))
17928 := (T(8) + (-((2 - 9) × T(71)))

- 17934** := $((4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(9) \times T((T(7) - 1))))$
17939 := $((T(T(9))/(-3)) \times (-T(9) + (7))) - 1$
17945 := $((T((T(5) + T(4))) + (-T(9) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-1))$
17946 := $-((T((T(6) + (4))) + ((-T(9) \times T(T(7))) - 1)))$
17952 := $((2 + T(5)) \times (T(T(9)) + T((7 - 1))))$
17955 := $(5 \times (T((5 \times 9)) + T(7)))$
17956 := $((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + T(9) \times 7) + 1$
17964 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (-6 - T(T(9)))) \times T((7 + 1)))$
17968 := $(8 \times (T(T(6)) + (T((9 \times 7) - 1))))$
17969 := $-((T((T(9) - T(6))) + ((-T(9) \times T(T(7))) + 1)))$
17972 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(9))) - T((7 \times 1))$
17973 := $((-T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T(9)) - (T(7) - 1)$
17975 := $((T((T(5) + T(7))) \times (-9) + T(7)) + 1)$
17976 := $(T(6) - (-7 \times (9 + T(7))))$
17981 := $(-1) + (T(T(8)) \times (-9) + T((7 + 1)))$
17982 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) - T((7 + 1)))$
17983 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-9))/(-7) + 1$
17986 := $-(((T(T(6)) + 8) + (-T(9) \times (T(T(7)) - 1))))$
17988 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(8) - 9)) + (7 - 1))$
17993 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (-T(9) - ((-T(9) \times T(T(7))) + 1)))$
17997 := $(7 \times (T((T(9)/9)) + T(7)))$
18144 := $(-4) \times ((T(T(4)) + 1) \times (-81))$
18189 := $((T(9) \times T(T(8 - 1))) - 81)$
18195 := $-((T(T(5)) - (T(9) \times (1 + T(T(8 - 1))))))$
18197 := $(-T(7)) + (T(9) \times (-1) + T(T(8 - 1)))$
18216 := $(T((T(6) + 1)) \times (2 \times T((8 \times 1))))$
18222 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times (-81))$
18223 := $((T((3 + (2^{T(T(2))}))) \times 8) - 1)$
18224 := $(T((4^{T(2)} + T(2))) \times (8 \times 1))$
18225 := $((5 \times T(2))^2 \times 81)$
18227 := $((-T(7)) \times (T((2 + T(2))) - T(T(8)))) - 1$
18228 := $((T(T(8)) - T((2 + T(2)))) \times T((8 - 1)))$
18233 := $((T(3) \times (T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) + T(8))) - 1$
18234 := $((T(4) + T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \times (8 + 1))$
18244 := $((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) - T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18245 := $(5 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(2) \times T((T(8) + 1))))$
18248 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((2 + T((8 \times 1))))))$
18252 := $((T((2^5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((8 \times 1)))$
18255 := $(-T(5)) + (T(T((5 + 2))) \times T((8 + 1)))$
18256 := $(652 \times T((8 - 1)))$
18265 := $(-5) + (T((6 + T(2))) \times T(T((8 - 1))))$
18269 := $((T(9) \times T((6^2) - 8)) - 1)$
18284 := $((-T(4) + T(T(8))) - T(2)) \times T((8 - 1))$
18285 := $(T(5) - ((8 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((T(8) - 1))))$
18288 := $(8 \times (8 + T((T(T(2) + 8)) + 1)))$
18292 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((T(9) \times T(28)) + 1))$
18296 := $((T(6) \times T((T(9) - T(2)))) - T(T(8))) - 1$
18297 := $(T(7) + ((T(9) \times T(28)) - 1))$
18326 := $((T(T(6))/T(2)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (8 - 1)))$
18333 := $((-T(T(3))) - T((3 \times T(T(3)))) \times (-8 + 1))$
18345 := $(-T(5)) \times (((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(8))) + 1)$
18346 := $(-6) - (T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(8) + 1))$
18352 := $(T((25 + T(3))) \times (T(8) + 1))$
18356 := $((T(6) + 5) \times (3 + T((T(8) + 1))))$
18359 := $((T(9) + T((5 \times T(3)))) \times T(8)) - 1$
18369 := $-((T(T(9)) - (T(T(6)) \times (3 + 81))))$
18372 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((-T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(81)))$
18373 := $(T(T(3)) + (T((T(7) + 3)) \times (T(8) + 1)))$
18375 := $(T(5) \times T(((7^3)/(8 - 1))))$
18376 := $((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(-(3 - 8))) + 1)$
18377 := $(-T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) + 3) \times T((8 + 1)))$
18378 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) - ((T(3) \times T((8 + 1))))$
18379 := $(T(9) \times T(T(7))) + ((3 \times T(8)) + 1)$
18384 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 8) \times ((3 + 8) + 1))$
18387 := $((T(7) \times 8) + 3) \times 81$
18393 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(3))) - (T(81))$
18396 := $(T((69 + 3)) \times (8 - 1))$
18397 := $(T(T(7)) + (9 \times ((3 \times T(T(8))) + 1)))$
18417 := $(7 \times (T((1 + T(T(4)))) + T(T((8 + 1))))$
18424 := $(-T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(4) \times (-8))) + 1)$
18426 := $(6 \times ((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (8 + 1)))$
18432 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - (8 + 1)))$
18433 := $((-T(3)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(4))) \times 8) + 1$
18435 := $((T(5) - 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((8 + 1))$
18438 := $((T(8) + T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) \times 8) - 1))$
18443 := $((3 \times 4) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(8) + 1)$
18445 := $((T(T(5))/T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(8) - 1)$
18449 := $((T(T(9)) - T(4)) \times (T(4) + 8)) - 1$
18452 := $((-T(2) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((8 - 1))$
18456 := $(-6) \times (5 - T(T((4 + 8) \times 1)))$
18459 := $((T(T(9)) \times 5) - (-4 \times T(81)))$
18462 := $(2 \times ((6 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (8 + 1)))$
18463 := $((3 + T((T(6) + T(4)))) \times (T(8) + 1))$
18465 := $(T(5) \times (6 + T((48 + 1))))$
18466 := $(-T(6)) + ((6 \times T(T((4 + 8)))) + 1)$
18468 := $(T(8) \times ((64 \times 8) + 1))$
18469 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(6)) + T(T(4))) - (T(81))$
18472 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(8))) - 1$
18473 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times T(((4 + 8) + 1)))$
18475 := $(-5) \times ((-7) \times T((4 \times 8))) + 1$
18478 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) - T((T(4) + 8))) + 1$
18479 := $((T(T(T(T(9 - 7)))) \times (T(4) \times 8)) - 1)$
18492 := $((-T(2) - 9) \times (T(T((4 + 8)))) + 1)$
18495 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T((T(9) + 4)) + 8) \times (-1))$

- 18496** := $((T(6) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(4) \times 8))) + 1$
18497 := $((T((7+9))^{T(4)-8}) + 1$
18507 := $((T(7) \times ((0-5) + T(T(8)))) - 1$
18508 := $((T(T(8)) - 05) \times T((8-1)))$
18522 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(((5+8)-1))))$
18523 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T((5+T(8)))))) + 1$
18525 := $(T((5^2)) \times (58-1))$
18527 := $((T(T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(5))) \times 8) - 1$
18533 := $((T(3) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5)))) + 8) - 1$
18536 := $(T((T(6)/3)) \times ((-5) + T(T(8))) + 1)$
18537 := $((T((T(7)+3)) + (5)) \times (T(8)+1))$
18539 := $((T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T((5-8)))) - 1$
18546 := $(-6) \times (-T(4) - T(T(((5+8)-1))))$
18564 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(6))) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(8))) \times (-1)))$
18567 := $((T(7) \times T((T(6) + T(5)))) - (81))$
18583 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(8) - (5))) \times (T(8) + 1)))$
18585 := $((-T(5) + T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) \times (T(8) - 1)$
18595 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(9) - T(5))) \times (-8) + 1)$
18613 := $((T(31) + T(6)) \times T(8) + 1)$
18615 := $(-T(5) + ((1 - T(T(6))) \times (-81)))$
18624 := $(4 \times T(((2 \times 6) \times 8) \times 1))$
18625 := $(-5) + ((T(2) \times 6) \times T(T((8+1))))$
18627 := $(-((T(7) \times T(2))) + (T(T(6)) \times 81))$
18629 := $((T(T(9)) \times (26-8)) - 1)$
18642 := $(T((2+T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) + (8 \times 1)))$
18643 := $((T((3 \times 4)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8)) + 1)$
18645 := $(-((T(T(5) - (4))) - (T(T(6)) \times 81)))$
18647 := $((T(T(7)/4) + T(6)) \times T(T(8))) - 1$
18648 := $((84 \times 6) \times (T(8) + 1))$
18649 := $((T((9+4) - 6)) \times T(T(8))) + 1$
18657 := $((T(7) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))) + (8+1))$
18666 := $(-6) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(6) + T(81)))$
18673 := $(-3) + ((7+T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) + 1))$
18675 := $((T(5) + T(T(7))) - (6)) \times T((8+1))$
18676 := $((67 - T(6)) \times T(T((8-1))))$
18677 := $(T(7) + ((7+T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + 1)$
18678 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (-6) + T((8 \times 1)))$
18682 := $(-((T(T(T(2))) + (8 - (T(T(6)) \times 81))))$
18684 := $((T((4+8)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18685 := $((T(5) \times T(8)) - T(6)) \times T(8) + 1$
18687 := $((T(7) \times T(T(8))) + (-6) + T((8+1)))$
18696 := $(-((6+9)) + (T(T(6)) \times 81))$
18697 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(9)) + (T(6))) + T(T((8-1)))$
18704 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(07) \times T(T(8))) + 1))$
18711 := $(T((T((1+1)) \times 7)) \times 81)$
18714 := $(T((T(4) + 1)) + (T(7) \times T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18719 := $((9 \times T(((1+7) \times 8))) - 1)$
18722 := $(T(22) \times (-7-81))$
18723 := $(3 \times ((T(2) \times T((T(7) + T(8)))) + 1))$
18724 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) \times T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18725 := $((T((T(5) - T(2))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(8))) - 1))$
18726 := $((T((6 \times 2)) + (T(7) \times T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18728 := $((T(8) \times T(2)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) - 1)))$
18729 := $(9 \times ((2 + T((T(7) + T(8)))) - 1))$
18731 := $(T(T((1+3))) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)))$
18732 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (T((3 \times 7)) \times 81))$
18734 := $((T(T(4)) + 3) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)))$
18735 := $(T((5 \times T(3))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T((8+1))))$
18738 := $(T((-8) + T(T(3))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(8))) - 1))$
18739 := $((-T(9)) \times T(T(3))) - (-T(7) \times T((T(8) + 1)))$
18742 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)))$
18749 := $((T(9) + T(T(4))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(8))) + 1))$
18752 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times 5) + ((T(7) \times T(T(8))) - 1))$
18753 := $((T(T(3)) \times 5) + (T(7) \times T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18755 := $((T(T(5)) - (5)) + T(T(7))) \times T(8) - 1$
18756 := $(6 \times (T(T((5+7))) + T((8+1))))$
18759 := $((-9) + T(T(5))) + (T(7) \times T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18765 := $((5+6) + T(T(7))) \times T((8+1))$
18767 := $((7 \times T(6)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) - 1)))$
18768 := $(8 \times T(-((6+7) - 81)))$
18769 := $((T((96 - T(7))) \times 8) + 1)$
18774 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(7)) + (-T(7)) \times T((T(8) - 1))))$
18775 := $(-5) \times ((-T(7) - T(T(7))) - (T(81)))$
18784 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (81)))$
18786 := $(-6) \times ((-87) \times T(8) + 1)$
18792 := $((T(2) \times 9) \times (-7) + T((T(8) + 1)))$
18795 := $(T(5) \times ((T(9) \times T(7)) - (8-1)))$
18796 := $(T((6+9)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)))$
18816 := $((6 + T(T((1 \times 8)))) \times T((8-1)))$
18822 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times T((8-1))))$
18823 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((-2) + T(T(8))) \times T((8-1)))$
18824 := $((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T((8-1))))$
18836 := $((T(6) \times (T(T(T(T(-((T(3) - 8)))))) + (T(T(8)))) - 1)$
18837 := $((T(T((7+T(3)))) \times T(8)) / (8 \times 1))$
18838 := $((8^3) \times T(8) + T(T((8-1))))$
18844 := $((T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + (8-1)))$
18845 := $((T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times 8) - T(T((8+1))))$
18847 := $((T(7) \times (T(4) + T(T(8)))) - (81))$
18855 := $((T(5) \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) - T(T((8+1))))$
18871 := $((T((1 \times 7)) \times (8 + T(T(8)))) - 1)$
18872 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 7) \times (8 + T(T((8 \times 1))))$
18873 := $((T(T(3)) + (7)) \times (8 + T(T(8)))) + 1$
18879 := $(T(T(T(T((9-7)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T((8-1))))$
18885 := $(T(5) \times ((T(8) \times T(8)) - T(8) - 1))$

- 18895** := $(-5) + ((9 + T(T(8))) \times T((8 - 1)))$
18907 := $(7 \times T(((09 \times 8) + 1)))$
18915 := $(T(5) \times (1 + (T(9) \times T((8 - 1))))$
18923 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((2^9) \times (T(8) + 1)))$
18924 := $((T(T(4)) + 2) \times (T(T(9)) - T((T(8) + 1))))$
18926 := $((T(6) \times T(-(T(2) - T(9)))) - (T(8) + 1))$
18936 := $(T((6 \times T(3))) - (-T(9)) \times T(T((8 - 1))))$
18937 := $((T(T(7)) + T((T(3) + 9))) \times T(8)) + 1$
18942 := $(T(T((2 + 4))) \times ((T(9) + T(8)) + 1))$
18943 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4) + (9 \times 8))) + 1)$
18959 := $((T((T(T(9))/T(5))) - T(9)) \times 8) - 1$
18962 := $((-2) + T(6)) \times T(T(9)) - T((T(8) + 1))$
18963 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((T(6) \times ((9 - 8) + 1)))$
18973 := $(T(37) - (-T(9)) \times T(T((8 - 1))))$
18981 := $(T((1 + T(8))) \times (-9) + T((8 \times 1)))$
19125 := $(T(5) \times T(((T(2) + 1) + T(9)) + 1))$
19152 := $(-(T(2) - T(5))) \times T((1 + T((9 + 1))))$
19172 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(7) + T((1 + 9)))) - 1)$
19173 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (-((7 + 1) - 91)))$
19176 := $(-6) \times ((-71) \times T(9)) - 1$
19216 := $((T(T((6 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) + 1$
19222 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-2)) + (((T(2)^9) + 1))$
19224 := $(4 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((9 \times 1)))$
19225 := $((T(T(5)) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times 9) + 1$
19228 := $((T(T(8)) - T(2)) \times 29) + 1$
19236 := $(-T(6)) \times ((T(T(3 + 2))) - T(T(9)) - 1)$
19243 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-4) \times T((T(T(2)) + (91))))$
19245 := $((-5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(9) - 1)))$
19256 := $((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) - 2) - T(T(9))) - 1)$
19259 := $((9 \times T(5))^2 + T(T(9)) - 1)$
19269 := $(9 \times (-T(6)) + (2 \times T((T(9) + 1))))$
19272 := $-(((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) - ((T(2)^9) + 1)))$
19273 := $((-3) - T(T(7))) + ((T(2)^9) - 1)$
19274 := $((-4) - T(T(7))) + ((T(2)^9) + 1)$
19276 := $-((T((T(6) + (7))) - ((T(2)^9) - 1)))$
19277 := $(-T(7)) + (T((T(7) - 2)) \times T((9 + 1)))$
19279 := $((9 \times ((7 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 9)) + 1)$
19287 := $(-T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times 29) + 1)$
19295 := $((-((T(5) + 9)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))) - 1)$
19296 := $((T(69) - T(2)) \times (9 - 1))$
19305 := $((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(03)))) \times (-T((9 + 1)))$
19322 := $((T(2) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(3) \times T(T(9)))) - 1)$
19323 := $(3 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(3) \times T(T((9 \times 1))))$
19328 := $(8 \times (T(((T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(9))) + 1)$
19329 := $((T(9) + T(T(2))) \times (T((3 \times 9)) + 1))$
19332 := $-((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + (-3) \times T((T(9) + 1))))$
19339 := $((T(T(9)))/(-3)) + ((3^9) + 1)$
19343 := $((T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) \times 39) - 1)$
19355 := $(-5) \times ((T(5) \times T(T(3))) - (T(91)))$
19356 := $(T(T(6)) + (T(5) \times T(((T(3) + T(9)) - 1)))$
19358 := $((-T(8) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(9) + 1)$
19364 := $(4 \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) - (9 + 1))$
19365 := $(T(5) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(T(3))) + T((T(9) + 1)))$
19368 := $(8 \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(3)) + T(T((9 \times 1))))$
19377 := $((T(7) \times (-((7^3) + T(T(9)))) + 1)$
19382 := $-((T((T(2) \times 8)) - ((3^9) - 1))$
19383 := $((T(3) \times T(8)) - 3) \times 91$
19384 := $(4 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(3) - T(91))))$
19397 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(9) + 3)) - (91))$
19422 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(2)) + T((T(4) \times (9 - 1))))$
19425 := $(-T(5)) + (T(T(2)) \times T((T(4) \times (9 - 1))))$
19426 := $((-T(6)) \times ((2 \times T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) + 1)$
19432 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(91)))$
19434 := $((T(4) + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) - 1)$
19435 := $(-5) + (T(3) \times T((T(4) \times (9 - 1))))$
19444 := $(4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(-((T(4) - (91))))$
19446 := $(-T(6)) \times (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) - 1)$
19448 := $((T(8) + T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) \times (T(9) - 1))$
19453 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(5) + 4)) \times (T(T(9) + 1)))$
19458 := $((T(8) \times 5)/T(4)) \times T((T(9) + 1))$
19475 := $(T(5) - ((-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (9 + 1))$
19476 := $(-6) \times ((T(T((7 + 4))) + T(T(9))) \times (-1))$
19479 := $(-9) + (T(T(7)) \times (49 - 1))$
19485 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((8 + T(4)))) - T(T((9 \times 1)))$
19486 := $((6 \times T((8 \times T(4)))) + (T(9) + 1))$
19487 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T((8/4) + T(9))) - 1)$
19488 := $(T((-8) + T(8))) \times (49 - 1)$
19492 := $((T(2)^9 - T((T(4) + 9))) - 1)$
19493 := $((3^9) - T((T(4) + (9 \times 1))))$
19494 := $((T(4) + 9) \times ((-T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 1))$
19522 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(-(T(2) - T(5)))) + (T(T(9)) + 1))$
19525 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(2)) - 5) \times T((9 + 1))$
19529 := $((T(9) - T(2)) \times T(-(T(5) - T(9)))) - 1$
19532 := $(2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(-(T(5) - T(9)))) + 1))$
19536 := $((-T(6)) + T((T(3) \times 5))) \times (T(9) - 1)$
19537 := $(7 \times ((T(3) \times T(-(T(5) - T(9)))) + 1))$
19545 := $((T(T(5)) + ((-4) - T(5)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-1))$
19548 := $((T((8 \times 4)) + T(5)) \times T((9 - 1))$
19565 := $((T((T(T(5))/6)) + 5) \times 91)$
19572 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7)) + (T(T(5)) \times (9 - 1)))$
19574 := $((T((-4) + T(7)) + 5)) \times T(9) - 1$
19575 := $((T(5) \times T(7)) + T(5)) \times T((9 \times 1))$
19576 := $((T(-(6 - (7 \times 5))) \times T(9)) + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 19579 &:= ((T(97) \times 5) - T(91)) \\ 19584 &:= ((4 \times T(8)) \times ((T(5) \times 9) + 1)) \\ 19588 &:= ((T(88) \times 5) + (9 - 1)) \\ 19592 &:= ((T(2)^9) - T((5 + 9) - 1)) \\ 19596 &:= (T(6) - (-T(9)) \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)) + 1))) \\ 19619 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-1) + T(6)) - T((T(9) + 1))) \\ 19624 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) + T((9 + 1)))) \\ 19628 &:= (-T(8)) + (((-2) + T(6)) \times T(T(9)) - 1) \\ 19629 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(2))) \times T(6)) + T(T((9 - 1)))) \\ 19632 &:= (-T(2)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (6 - 91)) \\ 19634 &:= (-T((4^3))) - (-T(6)) \times (T(T(9)) - 1) \\ 19635 &:= (T((T(5) + T(3))) \times (-6 - 91)) \\ 19637 &:= (-73) \times ((-6) \times T(9)) + 1) \\ 19639 &:= -((T(9) - ((-3 - 6)^9) + 1)) \\ 19642 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) + 91)) \\ 19643 &:= -((T((-3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(6)) \times 91)) \\ 19645 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6)))) + (9 + 1)) \\ 19646 &:= ((T(6) + ((4 - 6))) \times (T(T(9)) - 1)) \\ 19647 &:= ((-T(7)) + T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) \times (9 \times 1) \\ 19648 &:= (-T(8)) + ((T(-((4 - 6))^9) + 1)) \\ 19653 &:= (-3) + ((-T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 91) \\ 19655 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (-5) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(91)))))) \\ 19656 &:= ((T(6) + T(5)) \times (6 \times 91)) \\ 19664 &:= (((-4) + (T(6) \times T(6))) \times T(9)) - 1) \\ 19665 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 6)/6) \times T(T(9 \times 1))) \\ 19668 &:= (((T(8) \times 6) + T(T(6))) \times (T(9) - 1)) \\ 19678 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) - 6) + T(T(9))) + 1) \\ 19681 &:= (-1) + ((T((8 - 6)^9) - 1)) \\ 19682 &:= (((T(2)^8) \times (-6 - 9)) - 1) \\ 19684 &:= ((T(((4 - 8) + 6)^9) + 1) \\ 19693 &:= ((3^9) + T(-((6 - 9) - 1))) \\ 19694 &:= (T(4) + (((9 - 6)^9) + 1)) \\ 19695 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(9) \times T((T(6) + (9 - 1)))))) \\ 19712 &:= (T((T(T(2)) + 1) \times (T((T(7) + 9)) + 1)) \\ 19725 &:= (T(5) \times (T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) + (T((T(9) - 1)))))) \\ 19729 &:= (T(9) - (((T(2)^7) \times (-9)) - 1)) \\ 19734 &:= (T((4 \times 3)) \times ((T(7) \times 9) + 1)) \\ 19748 &:= (((-8) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((9 - 1))) \\ 19759 &:= (((T(T(9)) + 5) \times (T(7) - 9)) - 1) \\ 19764 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T(67) \times (-9 - 1))) \\ 19768 &:= (-8) \times ((T(T(6)) - T((T(7) + T(9)))) - 1) \\ 19775 &:= (-5) \times (T((-7) + T(7)) - (T(91))) \\ 19776 &:= ((6 + T(T(7))) \times (-7) + T((9 + 1))) \\ 19779 &:= ((-9) + T(7)) \times ((7 + T(T(9))) - 1) \\ 19784 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(9) + 1)))) \\ 19785 &:= (-T(5)) + ((-8) + T(7)) \times T((T(9) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19795 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((9 + 1)))) \\ 19797 &:= (((7 + T(T(9))) \times (T(7) - 9)) - 1) \\ 19799 &:= (-T(9)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(9) - 1) \\ 19801 &:= (((T(10) \times 8) \times T(9)) + 1) \\ 19823 &:= ((-T(T(3))) \times (T((T(T(T(2))) - 8)) - T(T(9)))) - 1) \\ 19824 &:= (4 \times (T(T(2)) + T((8 + 91)))) \\ 19826 &:= (((T(T(T(T(6)))/T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \times 9) - 1) \\ 19828 &:= (((-8) + T(T((T(2) + 8)))) \times 9) + 1) \\ 19837 &:= (((-7) + T(T((3 + 8)))) \times 9) + 1) \\ 19842 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(8))) - (T(9) + 1))) \\ 19844 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(4) \times T(8))) + (T(9) - 1)) \\ 19845 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(((8 + T(9)) - 1))) \\ 19846 &:= (((T(6)^{T(4)-8}) \times T(9)) + 1) \\ 19847 &:= (-7) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (-9 \times 1)) \\ 19854 &:= ((4 + 5) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T((9 + 1)))))) \\ 19855 &:= ((T((5 \times 5)) + T(8)) \times T((9 + 1))) \\ 19866 &:= (T(6) \times ((T((6 + 8)) \times 9) + 1)) \\ 19872 &:= ((-T(2)) + T((-7) + T(8))) \times (T(9) + 1) \\ 19875 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(8)) \times T((9 \times 1))) \\ 19876 &:= ((T(6) \times T((7 + T(8)))) + (9 + 1)) \\ 19886 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (88 - T(T(9)))) - 1) \\ 19888 &:= (8 \times (T(((T(8) - T(T(8)))/(-9)) + 1)) \\ 19893 &:= (-T(3)) + (9 \times T(T((T(8)/9) + 1))) \\ 19894 &:= (49 \times T((-8) + T((9 - 1)))) \\ 19896 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(8) - T((9 + 1)))))) \\ 19898 &:= ((T(((T(T(8))/9) - 8) \times 9) - 1) \\ 19899 &:= (9 \times T(T(((9 - 8) + 9) + 1))) \\ 19921 &:= (1 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19922 &:= (2 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19923 &:= (3 \times ((2 \times T((9 \times 9))) - 1)) \\ 19924 &:= (4 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19925 &:= ((T((5 - 2)) \times T((9 \times 9))) - 1) \\ 19926 &:= (T((6/2)) \times T(((9 \times 9) \times 1))) \\ 19927 &:= ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + ((T(9) \times T(9)) \times (-1))) \\ 19928 &:= (8 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19929 &:= (9 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19931 &:= (-1) + (T(3) \times (T((9 \times 9)) + 1)) \\ 19932 &:= ((2 \times 3) \times (T((9 \times 9)) + 1)) \\ 19933 &:= (T(3) + ((T(3) \times T((9 \times 9))) + 1)) \\ 19934 &:= (((4 + T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) \times 9) - 1) \\ 19935 &:= (T(5) + (T(3) \times (T((9 \times 9)) - 1))) \\ 19936 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(3))) \times T(9)) + 91) \\ 19943 &:= ((T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) \times 9) + (T(9) - 1)) \\ 19945 &:= ((T(T(T(5) - 4))) \times 9) + (T(9) + 1) \\ 19954 &:= ((T(T((-4) + T(5))) \times 9) + T((9 + 1))) \\ 19956 &:= (-6) \times (-5 - T((9 \times 9) \times 1)) \\ 19957 &:= (-7) \times (-T(59)) - T((T(9) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 19962** := $(T(T(2)) \times (6 + T(((9 \times 9) \times 1))))$
19963 := $((T(3) \times (6 + T((9 \times 9)))) + 1)$
19964 := $((T(4) \times T(69)) - T(91))$
19965 := $(-T(5) - ((T(6) + 9) \times T((9 - 1))))$
19968 := $(8 \times (T(6) + (T(9) \times T((9 + 1))))$
19975 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times T((9 + 1))))$
19982 := $(2 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T((T(9)/9))) + 1))$
19985 := $(5 \times (T(89) - (9 - 1)))$
19986 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (T(9)/(-9))) - 1)$
19988 := $((8 \times T((8 \times 9))) - T(T(9))) - 1$
19989 := $(-((T(T(9)) - (8 \times T((9 \times (9 - 1))))))$
19992 := $(T((T(2) + T(9))) \times ((9 + 9) - 1))$
20139 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) - (T(10))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
20162 := $((T((T(2) \times T(6))) \times 10) + 2)$
20163 := $((T((3 \times T(6))) \times 10) + T(2))$
20192 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))) - (T(T(10)) + T(2)))$
20193 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(10))) - 2$
20244 := $(4 \times ((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(02))))$
20286 := $((T((6 \times 8)) - T(20)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
20289 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(20)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
20297 := $(-((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(9)) \times 20) + T(2))))$
20328 := $((-8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3)))/(0 - T(T(T(2))))$
20346 := $((T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(30))) \times T(T(2)))$
20349 := $((T(T(9)) - T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(02))))$
20355 := $(-((T(T(5)) + (-5) \times T((30 \times T(2))))$
20379 := $((T(9) \times (-7) + T(30)) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
20385 := $(-((T(5) \times (T(8) - (T(30) \times T(2))))$
20425 := $((5^2) \times (T(40) - T(2)))$
20439 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) \times T(T(T(02))))$
20448 := $(8 \times T((T(T(4)) + (4^{02})))$
20455 := $(-5) \times (5 - (4^{T(T(02))}))$
20475 := $(T(5) \times ((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(T(02))))$
20476 := $(-6) - (-7) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(02))))$
20478 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(4) \times T(T(02))))$
20482 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(8) + 40)))/T(2))$
20497 := $((T(T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-40)))/(-2))$
20522 := $((T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + 02)$
20523 := $((T((T(3) \times T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + T(02))$
20526 := $((T((T(6) - T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(02)))$
20531 := $((T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times 50) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
20568 := $(8 \times (T(6) + (T(50) \times 2)))$
20628 := $((T(T(8)) + (T(T(2)) \times (-T(60)))) \times (-2))$
20646 := $((T(6) + T(4)) \times T((6^{02})))$
20648 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(4) + T(6))) + 02)$
20664 := $((4 \times T(T(6))) + (60)) \times T(T(T(2)))$
20693 := $((T(T(3)) - (T(T(9)) \times 60)))/(-T(2))$
20695 := $(-5) - (T(T(9)) \times (-60)/T(2))$
20727 := $((T(7)^{T(2)}) - T((7^{02})))$
20736 := $((6 + T(3))^{7-T(02)})$
20745 := $(-T(5) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times (0 - T(2))))$
20754 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5)) - (T((70 - 2))))$
20769 := $((T((T(9) - T(6))) \times 70) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
20797 := $(7 \times (T(9) + T((70 + T(T(2))))$
20823 := $(-3) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(80))) \times (-T(T(2))))$
20825 := $(5 \times (-T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((-8) + T(T(T(02))))$
20826 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + (T(80) \times T(T(2))))$
20832 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(80))) \times (-T(T(2))))$
20835 := $(-T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(80)/2))$
20845 := $(5 \times ((T(T(4)) \times 80) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
20852 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 5) \times 802)$
20855 := $(5 \times (-T(5) + T(T((-8) + T(T(T(02))))$
20856 := $((T(T(6)) + (5 + T(80))) \times T(T(2)))$
20862 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) + (T(80))) \times T(T(2)))$
20895 := $((T(5) + 980) \times T(T(T(2))))$
20897 := $(-T(7) + (T(9) \times T((T(8) - T(T(02))))$
20915 := $(5 \times (T((1 + 90)) - T(2)))$
20916 := $(T(-((6 + 1) - 90)) \times T(T(2)))$
20925 := $((T(5)^2) \times (90 + T(2)))$
20927 := $((T((T(7) + 2)) \times T(9)) + 02)$
20928 := $((T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) + T(02))$
20931 := $((-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(02))))$
20937 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(3) + T(9))) + T(T(T(T(02))))$
20943 := $(T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (-90) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
20944 := $((T(T(T(4)))/T(4)) - (-90) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
20945 := $(5 \times (T(T((4 + 9))) + T(02)))$
20982 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(9)))) + T(02))$
21021 := $(T((12 + 01)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
21077 := $(-7) \times (70 - T(T(12)))$
21112 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times T((1 + 12)))$
21114 := $((T(4) - 1) \times T((T(11) + 2)))$
21147 := $((-T(7) + T(T((T(4) - 1)))) \times T(T((1 + 2)))$
21154 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(5) - 1)) - T(T((1 + T(T(2))))$
21159 := $(9 \times (5 + T((T(11) + 2))))$
21168 := $((T(8) \times T(6)) \times T((1 + T((1 + 2))))$
21175 := $(5 \times ((T(T(7)) \times 11) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
21184 := $((-4) + T(T(8))) \times (11 + T(T(T(2))))$
21186 := $(6 \times (T(81) + T((-1) + T(T(T(2))))$
21195 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(9)) + T((T((1 + 1))^{T(2)})))$
21196 := $((T(6) \times T((T(9) - 1))) + T(T((1 + T(T(2))))$
21223 := $(-((3^{T(T(2))})) + (T((T(T(2)) + 1))^{T(2)}))$
21228 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(2)) + T(T(T((T(2) + 1)))) \times T(T(2)))$
21229 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (2 \times T((1 + T(T(T(2))))$
21231 := $((T(13) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((-1) + T(T(T(2))))$
21239 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T((1 + T(2))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 21245 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T((1 + T(2)))))) \\ 21246 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T((T(4) + T(2))) + 1) - T(T(2))) \\ 21251 &:= (-1) - (-((T((T(5) - 2)) + 1) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21252 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(5)) + 2) \times T(T(T(1 + 2)))) \\ 21253 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) - 2))) + 1) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21255 &:= (T(5) \times (-((T(T(5)) + T(2))) + T(T(T(1 + T(2)))))) \\ 21257 &:= (((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-1) + T(T(2))) \\ 21258 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))) + T(T(2))) \\ 21264 &:= (4 \times ((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))) + T(2))) \\ 21273 &:= (-((T(T(3)) - T(T((7 + 2)))) + 1) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21274 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) \times (-T(12)))) \\ 21276 &:= (6 \times (T((T(7) + 2)) + T(T(12)))) \\ 21279 &:= ((9 + (T(7) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))) \times T(2)) \\ 21283 &:= ((-3) - T(T(8))) + (T((T(T(2)) + 1))^{T(2)}) \\ 21284 &:= (4 \times (8 - (-T(T(T(2)))) \times T((1 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21285 &:= (5 \times (T((8 \times T(T(2)))) + T(T(12)))) \\ 21288 &:= (((-8) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) \times (-1 - T(2)) \\ 21292 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) - 21)) - 2) \\ 21293 &:= (((-T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (1^2)) \\ 21294 &:= ((T((4 + 9)) \times T(2)) \times T(12)) \\ 21296 &:= (((T(6) - T(T(9))) \times (-21)) + 2) \\ 21297 &:= (((7 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times T(2)) \\ 21299 &:= (-T(9)) - (92 \times (-1 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21315 &:= ((T((T(5) - 1)) \times T(T((T(3) + 1))))/2) \\ 21316 &:= (((T(6) \times (1 + T(3))) - 1^2) \\ 21318 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (1 + 31)) + T(T(2))) \\ 21324 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 12) \\ 21328 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) \times T(31))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21329 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(31 - T(2)))) \\ 21334 &:= ((43 \times T(31)) + T(T(2))) \\ 21336 &:= -((T(T(6)) + ((T(T(3)))/(-3)) \times T(T(12)))) \\ 21337 &:= (((7 \times T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) + 1) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21342 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((4 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(12))) \\ 21343 &:= (((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(3) + 1)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21345 &:= (((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 3) \times T((-1) + T(T(2))) \\ 21348 &:= (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 12) \\ 21357 &:= (-7) \times ((5 \times T(3)) - T(T(12))) \\ 21369 &:= (-((T(9) \times (T(6) - T(31)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21372 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(7) - T(3)))) \times T(12)) \\ 21375 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) - 3) \times (-1) + T(T(2))) \\ 21378 &:= (((-8) + T((T(7) \times 3))) + 1) \times T(T(2)) \\ 21379 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(7)) \times T(T(3))) + 1) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21384 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (-8) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 21385 &:= (T((5 + 8)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (1 + T(2)))) \\ 21414 &:= ((T((T(T(4 - 1))) \times 4) - 1) \times T(T(2))) \\ 21432 &:= ((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T((41 + T(T(2)))) \\ 21434 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(3) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(1 + T(T(2)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21435 &:= (-5) \times (3 - (T(T(4)) \times T(12))) \\ 21439 &:= ((9 \times T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(T(T((1 + T(2)))))) \\ 21441 &:= ((-14) + T(T((T(4) - 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21444 &:= (((T(4) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(T(2)) \\ 21445 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - (-1) + T(T(2))) \\ 21448 &:= ((8 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-((T(4) + 1) + T(2))) \\ 21462 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T((T(6) \times 4))) + 1) \times T(T(2))) \\ 21465 &:= (T(5) \times T((T((6 + 4)) - (1 \times 2)))) \\ 21468 &:= ((-8) - T((T(6) \times 4))) \times (-T((1 + 2))) \\ 21469 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(6)) - (T((T(T(4)) + 1))/T(T(2)))) \\ 21472 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((7 + T(T(4)))) - 1))/(-T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21475 &:= -((T(T(5)) + (-7) \times (4 + T(T(12)))) \\ 21476 &:= (-T(6)) - (-7) \times (-T(4) + T(T(12))) \\ 21482 &:= (((T(T(2)) + 8) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(12))) \\ 21483 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times (((8 \times 4) - 1) \times T(2))) \\ 21488 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(8)) \times 4) + 1) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21492 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(2))) \\ 21493 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - (T(4) + 1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21494 &:= (-T(4)) - (-((T(T(9)) - (T(4) + 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21495 &:= (-5) \times (-9) - (T(T(4)) \times T(12)) \\ 21497 &:= (-7) \times ((-T(9)) + T(T(4)) - T(T(12))) \\ 21504 &:= (4^{05}) \times T(T((1 + 2))) \\ 21505 &:= ((T(50)/T(5)) \times T((1 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21518 &:= (T(T((8 - 1))) \times (51 + 2)) \\ 21524 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times (T(5) - 1)) + T(T(2))) \\ 21525 &:= ((T((T(5) \times T(2))) - T((5 - 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21528 &:= (T((T(8)/T(2))) \times T((T((5 + 1)) + 2))) \\ 21532 &:= ((T(T(T(2)))/3) \times (-5) + T(T(12))) \\ 21539 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))) - ((T(5) - 1)^2)) \\ 21542 &:= (T(2) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5) - 1)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21544 &:= (-T(4)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5) - 1)) + T(T(2))) \\ 21545 &:= (-T(5)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5) - (1^2))) \\ 21546 &:= (T(6) \times (((4^5) \times 1) + 2)) \\ 21547 &:= (-7) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5) - 1)) + T(T(2))) \\ 21549 &:= (T(9) - (-((4^5) \times T(T((1 + 2)))))) \\ 21552 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (T(51) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21554 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5)) - T(T(T((5 - 1)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21555 &:= (T(5) \times (-((T(T(5)) - T(51))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21558 &:= ((T(8) \times ((T(T(5)) \times 5) - 1) - T(T(2))) \\ 21562 &:= ((T(T(T(-((2 - 6)))) \times (T(5) - 1)) + 2) \\ 21567 &:= (7 \times T(T(((6 - 5) \times 12))) \\ 21571 &:= ((1 + T(T(7))) \times (51 + 2)) \\ 21572 &:= (2 \times ((7 \times T(T(T((5 - 1)))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 21573 &:= (T(3) - (-7) \times T(T(((5 + 1) \times 2)))) \\ 21575 &:= (T(5) - ((7 \times T(T(T((5 - 1)))) \times (-2))) \\ 21577 &:= ((7 \times T(T((7 + 5)))) + T((1 + T(2)))) \\ 21578 &:= (((-T(8)) - (T(7) \times T(T(T((5 - 1)))))))/(-2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21582 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + (8 \times T(T(5)))) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21585 &:= (T(5) \times (8 + T((51 + 2)))) \\ 21592 &:= ((2 + (-T(9)) \times T(T(5)))) \times (-1 - T(2)) \\ 21593 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(5) + 1))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21594 &:= (((4 \times T(9)) \times T(T(5))) - T((1 + 2))) \\ 21595 &:= (-5) - ((-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) \times (1 + T(2)) \\ 21596 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(5) + 1))) - T(2)) \\ 21598 &:= (((-T(8)) \times T((9 + T(5)))) + 1) \times (-2) \\ 21609 &:= ((T(T(9)) - 06) \times T(T((1 + 2)))) \\ 21624 &:= ((T(T(4)) - 2) \times (T(T((6 + 1))) + 2)) \\ 21627 &:= ((T(7)^{T(2)} - T((6 - 1)^2)) \\ 21629 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) \times T(6)) - 1) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 21636 &:= (6 \times (T(T(T(3))) + ((T((6 - 1))^{T(2)}))) \\ 21637 &:= (T(7) + ((T(T(3)) \times (6 + 1))^2)) \\ 21644 &:= ((T(4) + 4) \times (6 + T(T(T(1 + T(2)))))) \\ 21645 &:= ((5 \times ((T(4)^6 - 1)) / T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 21648 &:= ((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times (T(6) + 12)) \\ 21649 &:= (((T(T(9)) - 4) \times T(6)) - (1 \times 2)) \\ 21658 &:= (T((8 + 5)) \times ((T(T(6)) + 1) + T(T(2)))) \\ 21664 &:= (T(T(4)) + (((T(6) \times (6 + 1))^2)) \\ 21669 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(6)) - ((T(6) + 1) \times T(2))) \\ 21672 &:= ((-2) \times T((7 \times 6))) \times (-12) \\ 21673 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) - (((7 \times T(6)) + 1)^2)) \\ 21678 &:= (-T(8)) - (-7) \times (T(6) + T(T(12)))) \\ 21684 &:= (((T(T(4)) - 8) + T(T(6))) \times T(12)) \\ 21692 &:= (((-2) + T(T(9))) \times T(6)) - (1^2) \\ 21693 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T((9 \times (6 - 1))) - 2)) \\ 21695 &:= ((T(5) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(6)))) - T(T((1 + T(2)))) \\ 21697 &:= (-T(7)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))) + T((1 + T(2)))) \\ 21698 &:= (-T(8)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))) + (1^2)) \\ 21708 &:= ((T(80) + T((T(7) - 1))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 21714 &:= ((T((T(4) + 1) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(1 + 2)))) \\ 21721 &:= -((T(T(T(1 + 2)))) - ((T(7)^{1+2})) \\ 21723 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T((2 + 7)))) - 12) \\ 21724 &:= (T(4) - (-((T(T((2 + 7))) - 1)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21725 &:= (((-5) - T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T((1 + T(2)))) \\ 21727 &:= (((T(7)^{T(2)} - T(T((7 - 1)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 21728 &:= ((-T(8)) + (2 \times T(T(7)))) \times T((1 + T(T(2)))) \\ 21729 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(2) \times 7)) - T((1 + 2))) \\ 21732 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(((7 \times 1) + 2)))) \\ 21733 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(((3 + 7) - 1)))) - 2) \\ 21735 &:= ((T(5) - T(3)) \times T((71 - 2))) \\ 21736 &:= (-((6^3)) + (T(7)^{1+2})) \\ 21739 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))) + ((7 + 1)/2)) \\ 21741 &:= ((T(T((-1) + T(4))) \times T((7 - 1))) + T(T(2))) \\ 21742 &:= -((T((2 \times T(4))) - ((T(7)^{1+2}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21743 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) + (-7) \times T(T(12)))) \\ 21749 &:= (T((9 + 4)) \times ((7 + 1) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21755 &:= (((5^5) \times 7) - T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \\ 21756 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(7))) \times (-1 - T(T(2)))) \\ 21758 &:= ((8 + T(5)) \times T((T(7) + T((-1) + T(T(2)))))) \\ 21762 &:= -((T((-2) + T(6))) - ((T(7)^{1+2})) \\ 21763 &:= ((T(T((T(3) + 6)))) + (T(7))) \times (1 + T(T(2))) \\ 21768 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(6))) / 7) - T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21769 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(6)) + (T(7) + T((1 + 2)))) \\ 21777 &:= (T(T(7)) - (-7) \times (-T(7) + T(T(12)))) \\ 21781 &:= -((T(18) - (T(7)^{1+2})) \\ 21783 &:= ((T(3) \times T(8)) - (-7) \times T(T(12))) \\ 21784 &:= (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(12)))) \\ 21792 &:= (((T(2) + T(T(9))) \times T((7 - 1))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21793 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) + ((T(7) + 1) \times 2)) \\ 21795 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) + 12)) \\ 21798 &:= (((-8) + T(T(9))) \times T((7 - 1))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21813 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) + T(12)) \\ 21824 &:= (((T(4)^{T(2)} - 8) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21825 &:= (-T(5)) - (-T((T(2) + T(8))) \times T((1 + T(T(2)))) \\ 21826 &:= ((-T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + (T((8 - 1))^{T(2)}) \\ 21832 &:= -((T(T(2 + 3))) - (T((8 - 1))^{T(2)})) \\ 21835 &:= ((5^{T(3)} + (T(T((8 + 1))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 21837 &:= ((T(7) \times T((38 + 1))) - T(2)) \\ 21838 &:= ((T((T(8) + 3)) \times T((8 - 1))) - 2) \\ 21842 &:= -((T(2) - (((4^8) - 1) / T(2))) \\ 21843 &:= -(((T(3) - (((4^8) - 1))) / T(2))) \\ 21845 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(4)) - (-T(T((8 + 1)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21846 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (4 - T(T(8)))) / (-1 - T(T(2)))) \\ 21847 &:= (-7) \times ((-4) - T(8)) - T(T(12)) \\ 21852 &:= ((-T(2) + T(T(5))) - (-T(T((8 + 1)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21853 &:= ((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) + (T((8 - 1))^{T(2)})) \\ 21855 &:= (5 \times T(((5) + T(8)) \times (1 + 2))) \\ 21859 &:= (-T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) + T((8 - 1)))^2) \\ 21861 &:= (T((1 \times 6)) \times (T(T((8 + 1))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 21863 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (6 + T(T((8 + 1)))) + 2) \\ 21864 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 6)) - 8) \times 12) \\ 21874 &:= (T(T(4)) - (-7) \times (T(8) + T(T(12)))) \\ 21875 &:= (-T(5)) - (-((T(T(7)) - 8) \times T(T((1 + T(2)))))) \\ 21876 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (-7 - T(T((8 + 1)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21879 &:= -(((T(9) + T(7)) - (T((8 - 1))^{T(2)})) \\ 21882 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (8 + T(T((8 + 1)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 21884 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-8) + T(T((8 - 1)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 21885 &:= (-5) \times (-((T(8) \times T(8)) - T(T(12)))) \\ 21888 &:= (-((8 \times 8)) + (T((8 - 1))^{T(2)})) \\ 21889 &:= ((T(9) + 8) \times (T(T(8)) - T((1 + T(T(2)))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 21893** := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T(9)) + 8) – T((1 + T(2))))
21894 := ((4 + (T(9) × 81)) × T(T(2)))
21896 := ((T(6) × (T(T(9)) + 8) – (1 + T(T(2))))
21897 := ((7 × T(T(9))) – (–(T(T(8))) × (1 + T(T(T(2))))))
21912 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) × (T((T(9) – 1) + T(T(2))))
21918 := (((T(T(8 – 1))) × 9) – 1) × T(T(2))
21922 := (–(2) – ((T(T(2)) × (–9)) × T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))))
21923 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9)))) – T((1 + T(T(T(2))))))
21924 := ((T(T(4)) + T(2)) × T((9 × (1 + 2))))
21925 := (–(5) – (–(T(T(2))) × T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21927 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(2))) × 9) + (1 + 2))
21931 := (1 – (–(T(3)) × T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21932 := ((T(T(2)) × T(–((T(3) – (91)))))) + 2
21933 := ((T(3) × T(–((T(3) – (91)))))) + T(2)
21934 := (((T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) × 91) + T(2))
21935 := (5 – (–(T(3)) × T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21936 := ((6 × T(–((T(3) – (91)))))) + T(T(2))
21937 := ((T(7)³) – T((9 + 1)/2))
21938 := (8 – (–(T(3)) × T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21939 := (9 – (–(T(3)) × T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21942 := (–(T(2)) – ((–(T(4)) – T(T(9))) × T(T((1 + 2))))))
21943 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(4) + T(T(9)))) – (1 × 2))
21945 := (T((5 × 4)) + (T(T(9)) × T(T((1 + 2))))
21946 := ((–(T(6)) × (–(T(4)) – T(T(9)))) + (1²))
21948 := (–((T((8 × 4)) – T(91))) × T(T(2)))
21951 := (–(1) + (T((T(5) – (9 – 1)))^{T(2)}))
21954 := (((–(4) × (T(T(5)) – T(T(9)))) – 1) × T(T(2)))
21955 := (–(5) – (T((T(5) + T(9))) × (–12)))
21957 := (((T(7) + (5)) × T(T((9 – 1)))) – T(T(T(2))))
21959 := ((T(T(9)) – (–(5) × T(91))) – T(T(2)))
21962 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – ((–(T(6)) × T(T(9))) + (1 + T(2))))
21963 := ((–(3) + T(T(6))) + (T(T(9)) × T(T((1 + 2))))))
21965 := (((T(5) + (6)) × T(T(9))) – 1) + T(T(T(T(2))))
21966 := (((T(T(6))/T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(T((1 + 2))))
21967 := ((T(7)^{–6+9}) + T(–(1) + T(T(2))))
21969 := (9 × ((T((T(6) + T(9))) – 1) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
21972 := (T(T(2)) × (7 + T((91 – T(T(2))))))
21973 := (T(T(3)) + ((T(7)^{9/(1+2)}))
21975 := (((5 + T(7)) × T(T((9 – 1)))) – T(2))
21976 := (((T(T(6))/7) × T(T((9 – 1)))) – 2)
21978 := (T(T(8)) × (T(7) + ((9 + 1)/2)))
21984 := ((4 × 8) × (T(T((9 – 1))) + T(T(T(2))))))
21987 := ((7 × T(8)) + (T(T(9)) × T(T((1 + 2))))
21988 := (T(8) + ((–(8) + T((9 – 1)))^{T(2)}))
21993 := ((3⁹) – (–((9 + 1) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
21996 := ((6 + T((T(T(9))/T(9)))) × T(12))
21998 := (–(T(–(8) + T(9)))) + (T((T(9) + 1)) × T(T(T(2))))
22029 := (((T(T(9)) + (20)) – T(T(2))) × T(T(T(2))))
22048 := ((8 × T((T(T(4)) – T(02)))) × 2)
22068 := (T(8) × ((T(60)/T(2)) + T(2)))
22075 := (T(T(5)) + (((T(7)^{T(02)}) + T(2)))
22092 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (–((T(T(9)) + T(T(02)))) × T(T(T(2))))))
22123 := (T((T(3) × T(2))) + (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22125 := (T(5) – (–(T((T(2) + 1))) × T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))))
22127 := ((T(T(7)) – T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22128 := (8 × (((T(T(T(T(2)))) – 1) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(2))))
22135 := (((T(T(5)) + T((T(3) + 1)))²) + T(T(T(T(2))))
22139 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(3))) + T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) – 2)
22147 := (T(T(7)) + ((T(T((T(4) – 1))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2))))
22154 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(5)) – T(((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))))))
22155 := (–(T(T(5))) – (–(T(5)) × T(–(1) + T(T((2 + 2))))))
22159 := ((T(T(9))/5) + (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22162 := (–(((T(T(T(2))) – T(T(6))) – (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22165 := ((5 + 6) × (–(1) + T((T(2) × T(T(T(2))))))
22168 := ((T(8) × 6) + (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22174 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(7))) – (T(12) × 2))
22176 := (T(T(6)) × (((T(7) + 1) + T(2)) × T(2)))
22178 := ((–((T(8) × T(7))) × (–(1) – T(T(T(2)))) + 2)
22179 := (((T(T(9)) + T((7 – 1))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(2))
22182 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T((8 + 1)))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2)))
22183 := (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(((8 + 1) – 2))^{T(2)}))
22185 := (T(5) × (–(T(T(8))) + T((1 + 2^{T(T(2))}))))
22186 := (T(T(6)) + (((T((8 – 1))^{T(2)}) + T(2)))
22192 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (–(9) – (T((1 + T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))
22194 := (((T(T(T(4))) – T(9)) × T(–(1) + T(T(2)))) – T(T(T(T(2))))
22195 := (5 × (T(91) + T(22)))
22196 := (((T(6) × T(T(9))) – 1) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
22197 := (((T(7) + T(T(9))) – T(1 + 2)) × T(T(T(2))))
22214 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) – 2)) – T(T(2)))
22218 := (((T(T((8 + 1))) + 2) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
22224 := (((4 × T(T(T(T(2)))) + 2) × (T(2) + T(T(T(2))))
22225 := (5 × ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(2)))) – T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2))))))
22239 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) + T(2)) × T((2 × T(2))))
22242 := ((T(T(T(2))) – T(4)) × (T(T(2)) + T((T(2) × T(T(T(2))))))
22243 := ((3 + T(4)) × T((T(2) + T(T((2 + 2))))))
22245 := ((T(54) – 2) × T((2 + T(2))))
22246 := ((T(T(6)) – (4)) × ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) + (T(T(T(2))))))
22247 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(T(4)) – 2)) + (T(2)^{T(T(2))}))
22248 := ((T(8) × ((T(4)²) + T(2))) × T(T(2)))
22249 := ((T(T(9)) + (T((4²)))) × (T(T(T(2))) – 2))
22252 := ((T((2 + 5))^{T(2)}) + T((T(2) + T(T(T(2))))))

$$\begin{aligned} 22253 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(5) + 2)^2)) / T(2)) \\ 22254 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(5) \times (T(2)^{T(2)})) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22267 &:= (7 \times (T(((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) / T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22269 &:= ((T((9 \times 6)) \times T((2 + T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22272 &:= ((-T(2)) + T((T(7) - 2))) \times (2^{T(T(2))}) \\ 22273 &:= ((T(T(3)) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})) + T((T(2) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 22274 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2 + 2)))) \\ 22275 &:= (T(5) \times T(((7 + 2) \times 2) \times T(2))) \\ 22277 &:= (((T(7) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 2) + T(2)) \\ 22278 &:= (T(T(8)) + (((7 \times T(T(T(2))))^2) + T(2))) \\ 22279 &:= (-T(9)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T((2 + 2)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22284 &:= ((T(4) \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22287 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 22288 &:= ((-T((8 \times 8))) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) / 2) \\ 22289 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((-8) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) / (-2))) \\ 22294 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((9 - 2)))) - T(2^{T(2)})) \\ 22295 &:= (-5) \times (-T((92 + 2)) + T(T(2))) \\ 22296 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(2)^{T(2)})) - T(T(2))) \\ 22299 &:= (((T(T(9)) + (9 \times T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \\ 22315 &:= (5 \times (T((T(13) + T(2)) - 2)) \\ 22323 &:= ((T(T((3^2))) + T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22324 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((2 + 3) + 2))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22325 &:= (5 \times T(((2 + T(3^2))) \times 2)) \\ 22326 &:= (6 \times ((2^{T(3)} - T(2))^2)) \\ 22327 &:= (((T(7)^{T(2)} - 3) + T((T(2)^{T(2)})) \\ 22328 &:= ((T((8 + 2)) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) - 2) \\ 22329 &:= (((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(2)^2))) \\ 22331 &:= (1 - (T(T((T(T(3)) / 3))) \times (-T(T((2 + 2)))))) \\ 22332 &:= ((T(T((-2) + T(3))) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) + 2) \\ 22333 &:= ((T(T((T(T(3)) / 3))) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + T(2)) \\ 22334 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / 3)))) + (2 + 2)) \\ 22335 &:= (5 \times ((T(3) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))))) \\ 22336 &:= ((T(T((T(6) / 3))) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 22337 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T((T(T(3)) / 3))^{T(2)} - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22338 &:= ((T((8 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) - 2)) - T(T(2))) \\ 22339 &:= (9 - (T(T((T(T(3)) / 3))) \times (-T(T((2 + 2)))))) \\ 22341 &:= ((T(T((1 + T(4)))) \times T(T((T(3) - 2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22342 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 22343 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(4) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / T(T(2)))))) + 2)) \\ 22344 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22345 &:= (T(5) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(((3 + 2) + 2)))) \\ 22347 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + (T((3 + 2) + 2)) \\ 22351 &:= ((T(T(-(1 - 5))) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22356 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(5) \times (T(T(T(3)) + 2))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 22358 &:= (T(T((-8) + T(5))) + (T(T(T(3)) / T(2)))^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22359 &:= (((T(T(9)) - 5) \times T(T(3))) + (T(2)^{T(T(2))})) \\ 22365 &:= ((5 \times T(6)) \times ((T(3)^{T(2)} - T(2))) \\ 22368 &:= ((T(86) \times T(3)) - T((2 \times T(T(2)))) \\ 22372 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22373 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(7)^3)) + T((T(T(T(2)) - 2))) \\ 22374 &:= (((T(T(4) \times 7)) \times 3) + T(2)) \times T(2) \\ 22375 &:= -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(7)) + 3) \times T(T((2 + 2)))))) \\ 22377 &:= ((T(T(7)) + ((T(7)^3 - 2)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22378 &:= ((-((T(8) - (T(7)^3)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 22379 &:= (973 \times (2 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22382 &:= ((2 + T((8 \times T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(2)) - 2)) \\ 22386 &:= (((T(6) + (8^3)) \times 2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22387 &:= (T((-7) + T(8)) + (T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))^{T(2)})) \\ 22389 &:= (((T(9) \times 83) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22392 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(2))^{T(2)})) \\ 22395 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((9 \times T(3))) \times T((2 + T(2)))) \\ 22398 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T((3 \times 2)))) + T(2)) \\ 22407 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(04))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) / (-T(2)))) \\ 22413 &:= (31 \times ((T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(2)) \\ 22417 &:= ((T(7) + 1) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) / 2)) \\ 22419 &:= (-T((T(9) - 1)) + (T((-4) + T(T(T(2))))^2)) \\ 22422 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(2)) \times T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))))) \times 2) \\ 22425 &:= ((5^2) \times (T(42) - T(T(2)))) \\ 22427 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2) \\ 22428 &:= ((T((82 + 4)) - T(2)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 22434 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((T(3) + T(4)))) - 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22435 &:= ((5 \times T(T(3))) - (-T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(2)) / T(2)))))) \\ 22438 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times 2^2)) \\ 22461 &:= (((-T(16)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-T(2)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22462 &:= ((T(26) \times (4^{T(2)})) - 2) \\ 22464 &:= (((T(T(4)) - 6) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(2))^{T(2)})) \\ 22467 &:= ((T((76 + T(4))) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22468 &:= (((T(86) + 4) \times T(T(2))) - 2) \\ 22472 &:= (2 \times ((T(7) + T((T(4) + 2)))^2)) \\ 22473 &:= (((3 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - 22) \\ 22474 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(4) + 2)^2)) \\ 22477 &:= (7 \times ((T((7 + T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 2)) \\ 22478 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4) + 2)) + 2))) \\ 22481 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(8)) + T(T((T(4) + 2)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) \\ 22482 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (T((84 + 2))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 22484 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (8 \times T((T(T(4) + 2)))))) \\ 22485 &:= (-T(5) + (((T(8) \times 4) + T(T(2)))^2)) \\ 22488 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T((8 + 4)))) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(2))) \\ 22489 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times T((4 + 2))) - 2) \\ 22491 &:= ((T((1 + T(9))) - T(4)) \times T((2 \times T(2)))) \\ 22492 &:= ((T(2)^9) + ((T(T(4)) - 2)^2)) \end{aligned}$$

- 22493** := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T(9)) + T((4 × 2)))) + 2)
22494 := (((T(4) × T(9 - 4))²) - T(T(2)))
22495 := (-5) + (((T(9) × T(4))/T(2))²)
22503 := ((30 × 5)²) + T(2)
22512 := ((T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + T(T((5 + T(2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
22515 := (T(5) × (1 + (5 × T((T(2) + T(T(T(2))))))))
22521 := (((T((1 + T(2))) × T(5))²) + T(T(T(2))))
22524 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) × T(5)) - T(T((2^{T(2)}))))
22527 := (((T(T(7))/2) × (-T(T(5)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - T(T(2)))
22533 := (((T((T(T(T(3)))/3)) × (-T(5))) - T(T(T(2))))/(-2))
22536 := (T(63) + (T(T(5)) × T((T(2) × T(T(2))))))
22539 := ((T((T(9) + T(3))) × (T(5) + 2)) - T(2))
22542 := (T((2 + T(4))) × ((T(5) + 2)²)
22544 := ((T(T(4)) × (4 + T(T((5 + 2)))) - T(T(2)))
22545 := ((T(5) + T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) × (T(2)^{T(2)})
22547 := (((T(T(7)) + 4) × T((5 × 2))) - T(2))
22548 := (((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(5)) - (2 × T(T(2)))
22554 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(5)) - (T((T(5) - 2)) × T(T(2))))
22555 := (5 × ((5⁵) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(2))))))
22556 := (T(T(6)) - (-5 × T((T((T(5) - 2)) + T(2))))
22561 := ((T(T((1 + 6))) × T((5 × 2))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
22563 := ((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) - (-T(T(5)) × T((T(T(2)) - 2)))
22564 := (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(T(6)) × T((T(5) - 2))) + T(2)))
22566 := (-6) - (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × (T(2) - T(T(T(2))))))
22568 := (T((-8) + T(6)) × (-5 + T(22))
22569 := (-T(T(T(9 - 6)))) - (-T(T(5)) × T((T(T(2)) - 2)))
22572 := (-((T(2) - T((7 × 5))) × T((2^{T(2)})))
22573 := ((T((T(3) × 7)) × (5²)) - 2)
22574 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(7))) + ((T(T(5)) + 2) × 2))
22575 := (((T(5) + T(7)) × (5²)) × T(T(T(2))))
22576 := ((6 + T(7)) × (T(T((5 + T(2)))) - 2))
22577 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) + 5) × T(T((2 + 2))))
22578 := ((T(8) × (T((7 × 5)) - T(2))) + T(T(2)))
22584 := ((T((T(T(4)) - T(8))) × T(T(5))) - ((T(T(2))^{T(2)})))
22593 := -T(T(T(3))) - T(9) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(T(2))))
22594 := (((-4) + (9 × T(T(5)))) × T(T(T(2))) - 2)
22596 := (-T(6)) × ((-9) × T(T(5))) + (2 + 2))
22598 := (((T(8) + T(T(9))) + 5) × T(T(T(2)))) + 2
22599 := ((T(9) - (9 + 5)) × (T(2)^{T(T(2))})
22617 := (((T(7) × T(16)) × T(T(2))) - T(T(T(T(2))))
22618 := (T(T(8)) + (T(-((1 - 6) - 2)))^{T(2)})
22625 := ((5²) × (T((T(6) × 2)) + 2))
22627 := ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) × T(2)))
22629 := (-9) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × ((T(T(6))/(-T(2))) - T(T(T(2))))))
22632 := (-T(T(2))) - (T(T(T(3))) × ((T(T(6))/(-T(2))) - T(T(T(2))))))
22634 := (((T(T(4)) - T(3)) × T(T(6))) - 2) × 2
22635 := (T(5) × (((T(T(3)) + T(T(6))) × T(T(2))) - T(2)))
22636 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(T(3)) - (T(T(6))/(-T(2)))) - 2)
22637 := (((T(T(7) × T(T(3))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(2)))/T(T(2)))
22638 := (T((8 + 3)) × ((T(6)/T(2))^{T(2)})
22642 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(6))) - 2) × (-2))
22644 := (T(T((4 + 4))) × ((6²) - 2))
22645 := (-T(5)) + (T(T(4)) × (T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + T(T(2))))
22646 := ((T(6) × T(46)) - T(T((2 + 2))))
22648 := (((T(T(8)) × (-4) + T(6))) + 2) × 2
22649 := (((T((9 + T(4)))) × T(T(6)))/T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))
22653 := (((T(3)⁵) - T(T(6))) + T(T(2))) × T(2)
22655 := (-5) × (5 - (T(6) × (T(T(2))^{T(2)})))
22656 := (((T(T(6)) + 5) × T((T(6) × T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))
22659 := (((9 × T(T(5))) × T(6)) - T((2 × T(2))))
22662 := -((T(T(2 + 6))) - ((6^{T(T(2))})/2))
22665 := (5 × ((T(6) × (6^{T(2)})) - T(2)))
22668 := -(((T(T(8)) - ((6⁶)/2)) - T(T(2)))
22672 := (T(T((T(T(2)) + 7))) + (T(T((6 × 2))) × T(T(2))))
22674 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(7)) × (T(6) - T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)))
22675 := (-5) - (-7 × T((T((6 × 2)) + 2)))
22677 := ((T((7 + 7)) × (6^{T(2)})) - T(2))
22678 := ((T(8) × T((-7) + (T(6) × 2))) - 2)
22691 := ((T((1 + T(9))) × T(6)) - T((2 + 2)))
22692 := ((T(2) + 9) × T((T(6) × T(2)) - 2))
22693 := ((-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(9)) × T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))))/T(2)
22694 := ((T((T(T(4)) - 9)) × T(6)) - (T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))
22695 := ((T(T(5)) × (9 × T(6))) + T((2 + T(2))))
22698 := (((8 × T(9)) × T(6)) + T(T(2))) × T(2)
22699 := (((-T(9)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(6)) - 2) + T(T(T(2)))
22701 := (T((1 + T((07 + 2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
22708 := ((T(80) × 7) + T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2))))
22714 := (((T(T(4)) + 1) × T(T(7))) - 22)
22715 := (T(T((5 - 1))) × (-T(7) + (T(T(T(2))²)))
22719 := (((T((T(9) + 1)) × (-7)) - T(T(2))) × (-T(2)))
22722 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(-((T(2) - ((7²)))))) + T(T(T(2))))
22724 := (((T((T(4) - T(2))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(2))) × 2)
22725 := (-T(5)) × (-T(2)) + (-7) × (T(T(2))^{T(2)})
22726 := (T(T(6)) - ((-T(2)) - T(T(7))) × T(T((2 + 2))))
22727 := ((T(T(7)) × (2 × T(7))) - (T(2)²))
22728 := (8 × (T((T(2) × T(7))) - (T(2)^{T(T(2))})))
22729 := (((T(T(9)) - 2) × (T(7) - T(T(2)))) + T(2))
22732 := (((T((T(T(2)))/3)) × T(T(7))) - 2) × 2
22733 := ((T((T(T(3)))/3)) × (T(T(7)) × 2) - T(2))
22734 := ((T(T((4 + 3))) × (T(7) × 2)) - 2)
22735 := (((T((T(T(5)))/3)) × T(7)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2)))

- 22736** := $((T(6)/3) \times T(T(7))) \times (2^{T(2)})$
22737 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-T(3) \times T(7))) - T(2))/(-T(2))$
22738 := $((8 \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(2))/T(2)$
22739 := $((T((T(9) + 3)) \times T(T(7)))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(2)$
22741 := $((1 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) + (2 + T(2))$
22742 := $((T((T(2) + 4))) \times T(T(7))) + T(2) \times 2$
22743 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(47) - T((T(2)^2))))$
22744 := $((T((T(4) \times 4)) \times T(7)) - (T(T(2))^{T(2)}))$
22746 := $((T(T(6) - T(4)) + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times T(T(2)))$
22747 := $((7 \times T(4)) \times T((T(7) - T(2)))) - T(2)$
22748 := $((-8) + T(T(4))) \times ((T(7) - T(T(2)))^2)$
22749 := $((-T(9) - T(47)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2))$
22752 := $((2 + T((5 \times 7))) \times T((2^{T(2)}))$
22754 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5)) - (7^{T(2)} + T(2)))$
22755 := $((-T(5)) \times (-5) + (-7 \times (T(T(2))^{T(2)})))$
22756 := $((T(T((-6) + T(5))) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})) - T(T(T(2))))$
22758 := $((T(8) \times (T(5 \times 7) + 2)) + T(T(2)))$
22759 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(5) + 7)) - (T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$
22764 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((6 + T(T(7))) + 2)) - T(T(2)))$
22765 := $((-5) \times ((T(67) \times (-2)) + T(2)))$
22767 := $((T(7) - 6) \times T(T((7 + 2)))) - T(2)$
22769 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-6) + T(7)) - (2/2))$
22771 := $((1 + T(T(7))) \times (T(7) \times 2)) - T(T(T(2)))$
22772 := $((2 \times T(7)) \times T(T(7))) + T((2^{T(2)}))$
22773 := $((-T(3) - T(7)) \times T(T((7 + 2)))) + T(2)$
22774 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(7) + 2))) - T(T(T(2)))$
22776 := $((-6) + T(7)) \times T(T((7 + 2))) + T(T(2))$
22778 := $(T(8) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(7))) - T(2) \times 2)$
22779 := $(T(9) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(7) \times (-2)) + 2))$
22782 := $((T(-T(T(2)) - T(8))) \times (7^2)) - T(2)$
22783 := $((T(-T(3) - T(8))) \times (7^2)) - 2$
22785 := $((-T(5) + T(T(8))) \times (T((7 \times 2))/T(2)))$
22788 := $(T(8) \times (8 + ((T(7) - T(2))^2)))$
22791 := $((T(T((1 \times 9))) \times (T(7) - T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))))$
22792 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) - 7) \times (-22)$
22793 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(T(9)) \times (T(7) - T(T(2)))) + 2))$
22794 := $((T((T(4) + 9)) \times T(T((7 - 2)))) - T(T(2)))$
22795 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((-9) + T(7))) - (2 + T(2)))$
22797 := $((T((T(7) - 9)) \times T(T((7 - 2)))) - T(2))$
22798 := $((8 \times T((T(9) + T(7)) + 2)) - 2)$
22801 := $((-10 \times 8) + T(T(T(T(2))))^2)$
22809 := $((T(9) \times (08^{T(2)})) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
22814 := $((T(4) + 1) \times (T((8^2)) - T(T(2))))$
22815 := $(T(5) \times ((T((1 \times 8)) + T(2))^2)$
22824 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(-T(2) - 8)) - T(2 + T(T(T(2))))$
22827 := $((T((7 + T(2)) + T(8))) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
22833 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(2)^{T(2)})))$
22834 := $((T(T(4) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(8))) + T((T(T(2)) - 2)))$
22836 := $(6 \times ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(T(2)) - 2)))$
22839 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(T(T(3))) + T(82))) \times (-T(T(2))))$
22842 := $((T(T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(8) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)))$
22843 := $((-T(3) - T(T(4))) + ((8 + T(T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))$
22844 := $((-4) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(8) \times 2))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
22845 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(8)))) + T((T(2)^2)))$
22846 := $((-T(6) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(2)))) - 2$
22847 := $((7 + 4) \times (T(8^2)) - T(2))$
22848 := $((84 \times T((8 \times 2))) \times 2)$
22849 := $((-T((T(9) + T(4)))) + ((8 + T(T(T(2))))^{T(2)}))$
22851 := $((T((1 + T(5))) \times 8) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(2)$
22852 := $((2^5) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(2 + 2)))$
22854 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5)) - (82 \times T(2)))$
22855 := $((T((5 \times T(5))) \times 8) + T(T(2 + 2)))$
22857 := $((T(T(7)) - 5) \times (T((8 + 2) + 2))$
22863 := $((T(3) - (T(6) \times ((T(8) - T(2))^2)))$
22865 := $((-T(5) - ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(8^2)))/T(T(T(2))))$
22866 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(6) + T((T(8)/T(2)))) - T(2))$
22867 := $((T((7 + 6) + 8) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 2)$
22869 := $((9 \times T(6)) \times ((8 + T(2))^2)$
22872 := $((T(2) + T(T(7))) + (T(82))) \times T(T(2))$
22873 := $((T(3) + T(7)) \times T(T(8)) - 2) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
22874 := $((4 + 7) \times T(8^2)) - T(T(2))$
22875 := $(T(5) \times (-T(7 + 8) + T(T(T(2 + 2))))$
22877 := $((7 \times ((T(T(7)) \times 8) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)))$
22878 := $((T(87) - T((8 - T(2)))) \times T(T(2)))$
22902 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(09))) \times 22)$
22905 := $(509 \times T((T(2)^2)))$
22911 := $((-1) + T((1 + T(9)))) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
22914 := $((T(4) + T((1 + T(9)))) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(2))$
22923 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times (-22)))$
22924 := $((-4) - T(2) - T(T(9))) \times (-22)$
22926 := $(T(T((6 \times 2))) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
22928 := $(8 \times (T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) + T(T(T(2 + 2))))$
22929 := $((T(9) \times ((2^9) - 2)) - T(T(T(2))))$
22932 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(((T(9) \times 2) - T(2))))$
22935 := $(5 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T((9 + 2))^2)))$
22938 := $(T(8) - ((T(3) + T(T(9))) \times (-22)))$
22944 := $((-4) + T(((T(4) \times 9) - T(2)))) \times T(T(2))$
22945 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) \times 22))$
22946 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) \times 22))$
22947 := $((-T((T(7) + T(4)))) - (-T((T(9) + 2))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
22951 := $(1 - ((T((5 + T(9))) \times (-T(2))) \times T(T(2))))$
22952 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((5 + T(9)))) \times T(2) + 2)$

- 22953** := (((-T(3)) × T((5 + T(9)))) × (-T(2))) + T(2))
22954 := (((T((T(4) × 5)) × 9) + 2) × 2)
22955 := (5 - ((T((5 + T(9))) × (-T(2))) × T(T(2))))
22956 := (((6 × T((5 + T(9)))) + 2) × T(2))
22957 := (((T(7) × T((-5) + T(9)))) + T(2)) - T(T(2))
22958 := ((T((8 × 5)) × T((9 - 2))) - 2)
22959 := (9 - ((T((5 + T(9))) × (-T(2))) × T(T(2))))
22962 := ((T(T(2)) × T((6 + (9²)))) - T(T(2)))
22964 := (-4) - (-6 × T(((T(9) × 2) - T(2))))
22965 := (5 × (-(((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) × T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
22966 := ((6 × T((6 + (9²)))) - 2)
22967 := (-T(7)) + ((-T(T(6))) + T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
22968 := ((T(8)/6) × T(((T(9) × 2) - T(2))))
22973 := (T(T(T(3))) - (T(7) - (T(T(9)) × 22)))
22974 := ((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) × T(T(2)))) × T(T(2)))
22975 := (T(5) - (-T(7) × T(((T(9) - 2) - T(2))))
22978 := (-T(T(8))) - ((-7) + T(T(9))) × (-2) - T(T(T(2))))
22983 := (T(3) + ((T(8) - T(T(9))) × (-2) - T(T(T(2))))))
22984 := ((T(4) + T(T(8))) × T((9 - 2)) + T(T(2)))
22985 := (-T(58)) + (T((T(9) + T(2))) × T(T(T(2))))
22986 := (6 × (T((89 - 2)) + T(2)))
22989 := -((T(T(9)) + ((-T(89)) × T(T(2))) + T(T(2))))
22992 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (9 - (T(T(9)) × 22)))
22993 := ((T(3) + T(T(9))) + ((T((9 - 2))^{T(2)})))
22994 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (((T((T(9) + T(9))) - T(T(2))) × T(T(2))))))
22995 := (((T(5) + T(T(9))) + T(9)) × T((2 × T(2))))
22997 := ((T(7) × T(9)) - ((-T(T(9))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 2)
22998 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(9)))/9 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))))
23045 := ((T(5) × T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((T(03) - 2)))
23047 := ((T(7) × (T(40) + 3)) + T(2))
23058 := ((T(8) × (T(50) + T(3)))/2)
23079 := ((T(T(9)) + (70 - T(3))) × T(T(T(2))))
23085 := (T(5) × (T((80 - T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
23094 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (9 + T(03))) - T(T(2)))
23115 := (-T(5)) × (-1) - T(T((1 + (3²))))
23119 := (((T(T(9)) + (T(11))) × T(T(3))) - 2)
23121 := ((T((-1) + T(T(2))) × T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + T(T(T(2))))
23124 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(T(2)) - 1))) + (T(T(3)) + T(2)))
23128 := (T((8 × T(T(2)))) + ((T((1 + T(3)))^{T(2)})))
23142 := ((2 + T(T(4))) × T(T((1 + (3 × 2))))
23143 := (((3 + T(T(T(4)))) × T((-1) + T(3))) - 2)
23145 := (T(5) × ((T(T(4)) × T((1 + T(3)))) + T(2)))
23148 := -((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(4)) - 1) × (T(T(3))²)))
23154 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(5)) - 1) + T(T((T(3) - 2))))
23155 := ((T(5) × T(T(T((5 - 1)))) + T(T((T(3) - 2))))
23157 := (((T(T(7)) + (T(5))) × T(T((1 + 3)))) + 2)
23163 := (((T(T(3)) + T(T(6))) × T(13)) + T(T(T(T(2))))
23166 := (66 × T((13 × 2)))
23175 := (T(5) × ((7 + T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - 2))
23177 := (T((7 × 7)) + (T((1 + T(3)))^{T(2)}))
23178 := (T(8) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T((1 + 3))) + 2)))
23183 := ((T(T(T(3))) + 8) × (T(13) + T(T(2))))
23184 := ((4 × T((T(8) - 13))) × T(T(T(2))))
23188 := ((8 + T(8)) × (-1) + T(32))
23194 := (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) × (1 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2)))
23197 := ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(9)) × (1 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2))))
23199 := (((9 + T(T(9))) × (1 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
23212 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (1 - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})))/(-2))
23213 := ((T(T(T(3))) + (-1) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})))/(-2))
23214 := (((T(T((T(4) + 1))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 3)/2)
23223 := (((T(T(3)) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))})) - T(T(T(3))))/2)
23226 := (((T(T(6))/T(2)) + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))))
23227 := ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + T((T((T(2) + T(T(3))))/T(T(2))))
23232 := (((T(2)^{T(3)}) - T(2)) × 32)
23233 := (((T(3)^{T(3)}) - T((-2) + T(T(3))))/2)
23235 := ((T((-5) + T(T(3))) × T((T(2) × T(3))) - T(T(T(2))))
23237 := -((T((7 + T(3))) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})/2))
23238 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(3))) × T(T(2))) + 3) × T(T(2))
23244 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) × T((2 + 3)) - T(T(2)))
23245 := ((T(5) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2)))) + T(T((T(3) - 2))))
23247 := (7 × T(((4 + 2) + 3)²))
23248 := (-8) - (-T((4²))) × T((T(3) × T(2)))
23249 := ((T((T(9) - 4)) × (T(2)³)) + 2)
23253 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))) - T(T((T(3) × 2)))
23254 := (((T(T(T(4)))/5) - T(T(2))) × T(T(T(3)))/T(2))
23255 := (-5) × (5 - T((T(2) × 32)))
23256 := (T((T(6) - 5)) × T((2 × (3²))))
23259 := ((T(T(9)))/(-T(5))) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)})/2)
23262 := (((T(T(2))⁶)/2) - T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))))))
23264 := ((T((T(4) + T(6))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × 32)
23265 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T((6 × 2))) + T(T(3)))/(-2))
23268 := ((T((T(8) - T(6))) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})))/(-2))
23269 := (((T(T(9)) × T(6)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(T((T(3) - 2))))
23272 := ((-2) × T(7)) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)})/2)
23273 := (-T((3 + 7))) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)})/2)
23275 := (((5 × 7)²) × (T(T(3)) - 2))
23276 := (T((-6) + T(7))) × (T(23)/T(2))
23277 := ((-T((7 × 7))) × (2 - T(T(3)))) + 2)
23278 := (-T(8)) - ((T(7) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)}))/2)
23283 := (((T(3) × T(T(8))) × 2) - T(T(T(3))) × T(2))
23286 := ((-6) - T(8)) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)})/2)
23288 := (-T(8)) - ((-8) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})))/(-2))

- 23289** := $((T((9+8))^2) - T(T((3+2))))$
23294 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3)) - 2))$
23295 := $(5 \times (T(((T(9) \times 2) + T(3))) + T(2)))$
23296 := $((T(6) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T((T(3) - 2))))$
23298 := $((8 \times T((9 \times T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times 2$
23299 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + 23)/2$
23313 := $-((T((T(3) - 1)) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2)))$
23316 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(13) - T(3)))) \times T(T(2)))$
23317 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(1+3))) + 3) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
23319 := $(-9) + ((T((1 \times 3))^{T(3)})/2)$
23321 := $((-1) - T(T(2))) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23322 := $((T(2) \times (-2)) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2)))$
23323 := $(-(3+2)) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23324 := $(-4) + ((T(2)^{T(3)}) \times 32)$
23325 := $((T((5-2))^{T(3)}) - T(3))/2$
23327 := $((-7) + T(T(2))) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23331 := $((T((1 \times 3))^{T(3)}) + T(3))/2$
23332 := $((-2) + T(3)) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23334 := $((-(4 \times 3)) - (T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23342 := $((T((T(2) + 4))) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/2)$
23343 := $((-(3 \times T(4)) - (T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23344 := $((4 \times 4) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23345 := $(T(5) - ((4 + (T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2)))$
23346 := $((6^4) \times T(3)) + T(3) \times T(2)$
23347 := $((T(7) + T(4)) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/2)$
23348 := $((T(8) + 4) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/2)$
23352 := $((T(T(2))^5) + (T(3))) \times 3 + T(T(2))$
23354 := $-((T(T(4)) - T(((5 + T(3)) + T(3))^2))$
23355 := $(5 \times (T(5) + T((3 \times 32))))$
23356 := $((6^5) \times 3) + T((T(T(3))/T(2)))$
23358 := $((8 \times T(53)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2$
23367 := $((T(T(7)) \times 63) - T(T((T(T(3))/T(T(T(2))))))$
23373 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((-7) + T((3^3))) \times T(2))$
23377 := $((7 \times 7) - ((T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2))$
23378 := $(T(8) - ((T(7) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/(-2)))$
23379 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(7)))/T(3)) - (T(3)^{T(T(2))})$
23382 := $((T(2) \times T(8)) + (T(3)^{T(3)})/2)$
23385 := $((T(T(5)) + ((T(8)^3) - T(3)))/2)$
23387 := $(-T(T(7))) - ((-8) \times T((T(T(3))/3))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
23388 := $((T(88) - (3 \times T(3))) \times T(T(2)))$
23389 := $((-T(9)) \times T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 2)$
23394 := $((-T(4)) \times T((T(9) - T(3))) \times (-3)) - T(T(2))$
23395 := $(-5) - (T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) \times (-T((T(3) \times 2))))$
23403 := $(-T(3)) + (T(((0 - 4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23408 := $(T((80 - 4)) \times (T(3) + 2))$
23409 := $(T((T(9) - T((04 + 3))))^2)$
23421 := $((T(12) \times T((4 \times T(3)))) + T(T(T(2))))$
23424 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times (4^3)) \times T(T(2))$
23425 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 3) + 2)$
23427 := $((-T(7)) - (-T(2)) \times T(T(4))) \times T((T(3) \times T(2)))$
23431 := $((1 + T(T(3))) + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23432 := $((T(2) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(3) + 2))$
23433 := $((T(3)^{T(3)}) - (-T(4)) \times T(T(3)))/2$
23434 := $((-4) + ((-3) + T(T(4)))^3)/T(T(2))$
23435 := $((5 + T(T(3))) + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23436 := $((6 + T(3)) \times T(((4^3) - 2))$
23437 := $((T(7)^3) - (T(T(4)) \times (-3^{T(2)})))$
23438 := $((T(8) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) + 2)$
23439 := $((T(T(9)) + ((3^4)) \times T(T(3))) + T(2))$
23443 := $(34 + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23444 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/T(4)) - T(3))^2)$
23445 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (-4) + (3^{T(2)})))$
23447 := $((7 + T(4)) \times T((T(T(4)) - 3)) + T(T(T(2))))$
23448 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((4 + 4))) - T(32))$
23452 := $((2^{T(5)}) - T(T(4)) - (T(T(3))^{T(2)}))$
23454 := $((T(45) \times 4) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(2))$
23455 := $(-5) + (T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)) + T(2))))$
23457 := $((T(T(7)) - T(5)) \times (T(4) \times T(3)) - T(2))$
23459 := $((T(9) + 5) + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23463 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T((4 \times 3)) - T(T(T(2))))$
23464 := $(T(T(4)) + (T((T(6) - 4)))^{T(3)/T(2)})$
23465 := $(56 + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23467 := $((T(T(7)) + T(6)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(3) \times T(2))$
23472 := $((T(2) + T((7 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(3) \times 2))$
23473 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(3) \times 2)$
23474 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(7)) + 4) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
23475 := $((T((T(5) + 7) \times 4) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(2))))$
23476 := $((T(6) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - (3^2)$
23478 := $((T((8 \times (7 + 4))) - 3) \times T(T(2))$
23484 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (8 - (T((4 + 3))^{T(2)})))$
23485 := $((5 + T(T(8))) \times (-T(4) - T((3^2))))$
23487 := $(78 + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23488 := $(-8) + (T((T((8 \times 4))/T(3))) \times T(T(2)))$
23492 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(9)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))))/T(2))$
23493 := $((T(3) \times T((T(9) + 43))) - T(2))$
23494 := $((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times (4 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
23495 := $(5 \times ((T(94) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(2))$
23496 := $(6 \times T((94 - (3 \times 2))))$
23497 := $((T(T(7)) - 9) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T((3 + 2))))$

- 23498** := $(89 + (T((-4) + T(T(3))))^2)$
23499 := $-((T(T(9)) - ((T(9 \times T(4)) - T(3))) \times T(T(2))))$
23523 := $(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) \times T(2))))))$
23526 := $((T(T(6)) \times (2 + T(5))) - T(3)) \times T(T(2))$
23527 := $((T(7) \times T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(5)))) - (T(T(3)))/(-T(2))$
23528 := $(T((8 \times 2)) \times (T((T(5) + 3)) + 2))$
23529 := $((T(92) \times (-5 - T(3)))/(-2))$
23531 := $(-T(T(13))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(2))$
23532 := $((T((-2) + T(3) \times T(5))) + T(3)) \times T(T(2))$
23534 := $-((T(T((T(4) + 3))) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T((3 \times 2))))))$
23535 := $((T(5) \times 3) \times (-5 + T(32)))$
23537 := $-((T(T((7 + T(3)))) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(2)))$
23538 := $((T(T(8)) \times 35) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(2)$
23541 := $((T(T(T((1 \times 4)))) \times T(5)) + (T(T(3))^2)$
23544 := $(4 \times (T(45) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
23545 := $(-T(5)) - ((-4 - T(T(5))) \times T((T(3) - 2)))$
23546 := $(-6) - (-((4^5) \times (T(T(3) + 2)))$
23547 := $((T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) + (3^{T(2)})$
23548 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(T(3))/T(2)))$
23552 := $((2^{5+5}) \times (T(T(3) + 2))$
23554 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(5)) + T(T(T(3))) - 2$
23556 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(5) + 3))) - T(T(2))$
23557 := $(7^5) + ((T(5)^3) \times 2)$
23559 := $(((-9) + T(5))^5 \times 3) + T(T(T(2)))$
23561 := $(-1) - (T(T(6)) \times ((-5) \times T(T(3))) + T(2))$
23562 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times T(((5 + T(3)) \times T(2)))$
23564 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times (T(5) + 3)) + 2$
23565 := $(5 \times ((-T(T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) - T(T(2))$
23567 := $(-T(7)) - ((-T(65) \times T(T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2))))$
23568 := $((T(8) + T((6 + 5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(2))$
23574 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (-T(3))) + 2)))$
23576 := $((T(6) \times (-7) + (T(5)^3))/T(2))$
23578 := $((8 + (T((T(7) + 5))) \times T(T(3)))) \times 2$
23583 := $((T((T(3) \times 8)) - 53) \times T(T(T(2))))$
23584 := $((-((4 \times 8)) \times T(T((5 + T(3)))))/(-T(2)))$
23585 := $(5 \times (-T(8)) + T(((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) - 2)))$
23586 := $(6 \times (T(85) + T((T(T(3)) + 2)))$
23588 := $((T(88) + T(5)) \times T(3)) + 2$
23589 := $((T(T(9)) \times (8 + T(5))) - (T(3)^{T(2)}))$
23594 := $((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times (5 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
23595 := $(-T(5)) \times (((T(9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(3))) + 2)$
23596 := $((6 + T(T(9))) \times T((-5) + T(T(3))))/T(T(2))$
23597 := $(-T(7)) - ((9 \times (5^3)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
23598 := $((T(T(8)) - T(9)) \times (T((5 + 3)) + 2)$
23624 := $-(((4^{T(T(2))}) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((3 + 2))))))$
23625 := $((T(5)^{T(2)}) \times ((6 + 3) - 2))$
23627 := $((T((7 \times 2)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(3))) + 2)$
23628 := $(T((8 \times T(2))) - ((6^{T(3)})/(-2)))$
23634 := $(T((4 \times 3)) \times (T((T(6) + 3)) + T(2)))$
23635 := $(-5) \times (((T(3) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))) - 2)$
23644 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(4) \times T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))))) - T(T(2))))$
23645 := $(5 \times (4 + ((T(T(6)) - T(3)) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
23646 := $(T(6) \times (T(46) + T((3^2))))$
23649 := $((9 \times T(((4 \times 6) \times 3))) - T(2))$
23652 := $((T(T(2))^5) + ((T(6) \times T(3))^2)$
23654 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))))))$
23655 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(6)^3) - T(T(2))$
23664 := $(T((T(4) + 6)) \times (T((6 \times 3)) + T(2)))$
23667 := $(-7) \times (-6 - ((T(6) - T(3))^{T(2)}))$
23674 := $((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-2))$
23679 := $(T(T(9)) - (-((T(7) + 6)) \times T((T(3)^2)))$
23682 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(8)) + (6^{T(3)}))/(-2)))$
23684 := $(-4) \times (8 - ((T(T(6))/3)^2))$
23685 := $((T(((5 + T(8)) + 6)) \times T(T(3))) - T(2))$
23686 := $((T((68 - T(6))) \times T(T(3))) - 2)$
23688 := $(T(8) \times (-8) + T(((6 \times 3) \times 2)))$
23692 := $((T((2 + T(9))) \times T(6)) + (T(3) - 2))$
23694 := $((T(T((4 + 9))) - T(T(6))) - (T(3)) \times T(T(2)))$
23697 := $((79 \times T((T(6) + 3))) - T(2))$
23712 := $(T((2 + T((1 + 7)))) \times 32)$
23715 := $(51 \times T(((7 + 3) \times T(2))))$
23716 := $((T(6) + 1) \times 7)^{T(3)/T(2)}$
23722 := $(T(T(2)) + (((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(3))))^2))$
23723 := $((T(T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + ((T(7)^3)) + T(T(T(2))))$
23724 := $((T(T((4 \times 2))) - 7) \times (T(3)^2)$
23725 := $(T((5^2)) \times (T(7) + T((3^2))))$
23727 := $((T((T(7) - T(2))) \times 73) + 2)$
23728 := $(((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7))) \times (-3)) - 2$
23742 := $((-2) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(7) \times T((T(T(3)) \times 2)))$
23743 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(47)) + T(T((T(3) - 2)))$
23744 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) - (T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))))))$
23745 := $(-T(5)) - (T((4 + T(7))) \times (-T((3^2))))$
23746 := $((T((T(6) + 4)) \times 73) + T(T(T(2))))$
23747 := $((-T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) - T((7 \times T(3)))) + T(2))$
23748 := $((T((T(8) - T(4))) \times T(T(7)))/T(3)) - T(2)$
23749 := $((-T(9)) + T((T(T(4)) - 7))) \times T(T(3)) - 2$
23751 := $((T(T(T(-(1 - 5)))) - ((T(T(7)) + 3))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
23752 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) + 5)) \times T(T(7))) + T(3))/T(T(2))$
23753 := $((T((T(T(3)) + 5)) \times T(T(7)))/T(3)) + 2$
23754 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((5 + T(T(7))) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
23755 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + (((T(7)^3) + T(2))))$
23757 := $((T(7) \times T(T(5))) \times 7) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))$

- 23758** := ((T(8) × (T(T((T(5) - (7)))) - T(3))) - 2)
23759 := ((T(T(9)) + ((5 - 7)) × (T(T(3)) + 2))
23765 := (5 × T((6 + T((7 + (3 × 2)))))
23766 := -(((T(T(6)) - T(T((6 + 7)))) - T(3)) × T(T(2)))
23768 := (8 × (T(67) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(2))))
23769 := (-T(9)) - (-((T(T(6)) + T((7 × T(3)))) × T(T(T(2))))
23772 := (T(T(T(2))) × (((T(7) - T(T(7))) × (-3)) - 2))
23775 := (T(5) × (T((T(T(7))/7) - ((T(T(3)) × T(T(2))))))
23777 := (((T(T(7))/7) × T(T(7))) + T(T(T(3)))) - 2)
23778 := (-T(8)) - (((T(7) - T(T(7))) × T(T(3))) × T(2))
23779 := ((T((-9) + T(7))) × T(T(7))) - (T(T(T(3)))²)
23784 := ((T((T(4) + T(8))) × (T(7) - T(3))) + 2)
23785 := (-5) × ((-8) × T((T(7) + T(3)))) + T(2))
23788 := ((T(T(8)) × T(8)) + ((T(7) - T(3))^{T(2)}))
23793 := ((T(3) + 97) × T(T(3 × 2)))
23794 := (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) × (7 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2)))
23795 := (5 × (T(97) + (3 × 2)))
23796 := ((T(T(6)) × (97 + T(3))) + T(2))
23797 := ((T((7 + 9)) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(2))
23799 := ((T(T(9)) × ((T(9) - T(7)) + T(3))) - T(T(2)))
23805 := ((T(5) + 08) × T(T(3²)))
23814 := ((T(T(4)) + (1 × 8)) × T(3^{T(2)}))
23815 := (T(T((5 - 1))) × (-8 + (T(T(3))²)))
23824 := (T(4) + ((T(T(T(2)) + T(8))) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(2))))
23826 := -((T(T(6)) + ((T(2) - T(8)) × (3^{T(T(2))})))
23828 := -((T((T(8) - T(2))) - ((8 + T(T(3)))^{T(2)}))
23829 := ((T(9) - T(T(2))) × (T(T(8)) - T(T((T(3) - 2))))
23832 := (((2 - T(3)) + T(T(8))) × (T(3)²))
23834 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) × (8 + (T(T(T(3))) × T(2))))
23835 := (-T(5)) - (((-T(3)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(3))) × T(T(2)))
23838 := (((T(T(8)) - T(3)) × T(8)) + T((T(3) × 2)))
23842 := (((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8)) - T(T(T(3)))) × 2)
23844 := (4 × ((T(T(4)) × (T(8) × 3)) + T(T(T(2))))
23848 := (8 × (T(T(4)) + T((T(T(8)/3) - 2)))
23853 := ((-3) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(8)) × (T(3)²))
23854 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(5)) + ((T(8) × T(T(3))) - 2))
23856 := ((T((T(6) + T(5))) × T(8)) - T(T(3 + 2)))
23859 := (-9) - (T((T(5) + T(8))) × (-T(3) × T(2)))
23862 := (T(T(2)) × (((6 × T(T(8))) - T(T(3))) + 2))
23864 := (-4) - (-6 × ((T(T(8)) - 3) × T(T(2))))
23865 := (T(5) - (((-6) × T(T(8))) + T(T(3))) × T(T(2)))
23866 := (((6 × 6) × (T(T(8)) - 3)) - 2)
23868 := ((T(8) × T((6 × 8) + 3))/2)
23871 := ((T((1 + 7)) × (T(T(8)) - 3)) + T(2))
23874 := ((-((T(4) + 7))) + (T(T(8)) × T(3))) × T(T(2))
23877 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(7) + 8)) + (T(T(3))^{T(2)}))
23879 := (-97) + (T(T(8)) × (T(3)²))
23883 := (((-3) + T(T(8))) × T(8)) + T((3 + 2))
23884 := (T(4) - ((-T(8)) × (T(T(8)) - 3)) - T(T(2)))
23885 := (-T((5 + 8))) + (T(T(8)) × (T(3)²))
23886 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(8))) × T(8)) + T((T(3)²))
23888 := (8 × ((T(8) × 83) - 2))
23889 := (-9) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(8))) + T((T(3) × 2)))
23892 := ((T((2 + T(9))) + (T(8)³))/2)
23894 := ((T(T(4)) × (-9)) + ((8 + T(T(3)))^{T(2)}))
23895 := (T(5) × ((T(9) × T(8)) - (3^{T(2)})))
23897 := (-79) + (T(T(8)) × (T(3)²))
23898 := (((-8) + T(T(9))) - (T(T(8))/(-T(3)))) × T(T(T(2)))
23899 := ((T((T(9) - 9)) × T(8)) + (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))))
23922 := (T(2) × ((T(2) + T((T(9) + T(3)))) × T(T(2)))
23924 := ((T(T(4)) × T(29)) - (3 - 2))
23925 := (T((5 × 2)) × T(((9 × 3) + 2)))
23928 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(2))) - 9) × T(3)) + T(T(2))
23937 := -((T((7 × T(3))) - (T(T(9)) × (T(T(3)) + T(2))))
23938 := (((-T(8)) + T((3 + T(9)))) × T(T(3))) - 2)
23952 := ((T(T(T(2))) - 5) × (T(T(9)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-2))))
23954 := (((T(4) × 5) + 9) × T(T((T(3))/T(2))))
23955 := (T(5) - (-T(5) × T(((9 × T(3)) + 2)))
23957 := ((T(T(7)) × 59) + (T(3)/2))
23958 := (((T(T(8)) × (T(5) - 9)) - 3) × T(T(2)))
23972 := (T(T(2)) - ((-7) - T(T(9))) × (T(T(3)) + 2))
23973 := ((T(3) × T(7)) + (T(T(9)) × (T(T(3)) + 2)))
23974 := ((T(T(4)) × ((T(T(7)) + 9) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(2)))
23976 := (T(((6 - 7) + 9)) × T((T(3)²))
23978 := ((T(T(8)) × T((-((7 - 9)³))) + 2)
23979 := (-T(9)) + (((7 + T(9)) × T(T(T(3)))) × 2)
23982 := (T(T(2)) + ((T(8) × T((9 - 3)²)))
23983 := (-T(3)) - ((-8) - T(T(9))) × (T(T(3)) + 2))
23984 := (((-4) × T(T(8))) × (-9)) + (T(3) + 2)
23985 := (T(5) × ((T(8) × T(9)) - T((3 × 2))))
23987 := (-7) - (-((T(89) - T(3))) × T(T(2)))
23988 := ((T(T(8)) × T(8)) + ((9 - 3) × 2))
23989 := ((T(T(9)) + 8) × (-9 - 32))
23991 := ((T((-1) + T(9))) × (T(9) - T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
23994 := ((T(-((T(4) - 99))) - T(3)) × T(T(2)))
23997 := ((T(7) - 9) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(2)))
24014 := (-T(4)) - (-104 × T(T(T(T(2))))
24015 := (T(5) × ((T(T(10)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(2))))
24017 := (7 × (T(T(10)) + T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))))))
24022 := (-T(2)) + ((T(20) - T(T(4)))²)
24024 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (04 × T(T(T(2))))
24025 := (((5 × 20) + T(T(4)))²)

- 24037** := $((-(T(7) - T(30))) \times T(T(4))) + 2$
24045 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(4) - T(T(04))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24048 := $(T(8) \times (T((40 - 4) + 2))$
24063 := $((T(T(3)) + T(60)) \times (T(4) + T(2)))$
24064 := $(4 \times (T(60) + T(T((T(4) + T(2))))))$
24126 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) + T((1 + T(T(4))))/2$
24128 := $((T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) - 1) \times (T(T(4)) - T(2)))$
24129 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + T(T((1 + 4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
24135 := $(-T(T(5)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((1 + T(4)) + T(2))))))$
24138 := $((8 \times T(31)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))$
24144 := $((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + 14))) - T(T(2)))$
24145 := $(-5) - (-T(4) \times T((T(1 + T(4)) + T(2))))$
24147 := $((T((T(7) + 41)) \times T(4)) - T(2))$
24148 := $((8 \times T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(T(4))) + T(2)$
24156 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-T(5)) + T(T((1 + T(4)))))/T(T(T(2))))$
24157 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) - 1))/(4 - 2)$
24164 := $(-T(T(T(4))) + (-T(6) \times (-1 + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))))))$
24165 := $(T(5) \times ((-6) + T((1 + T(T(4)))))) + T(T(T(2)))$
24168 := $((T(T(8)) - T((T(6) - 1))) \times (T(T(4)) - 2))$
24184 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (-T(T(8))) \times (T(T((1 \times 4))) - T(T(T(2))))))$
24185 := $(-T(5) - (-8 \times (T(T((1 \times 4)))^2)))$
24186 := $(-6) - (8 \times (1 - (T(T(4))^2)))$
24188 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
24192 := $((T(2) + 9) \times T((-1) + (4^{T(2)})))$
24194 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(9) - 1) \times T(4))) - T(T(2)))$
24195 := $(-5) - (-((9 - 1) \times (T(T(4))^2)))$
24198 := $((8 \times T((9 + 1))) \times T(T(4))) - 2$
24205 := $(-50) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24213 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(1 + 2))) \times T(T(4))) - 2)$
24214 := $(-41) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24218 := $(-((T(8) + 1)) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
24219 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(12))/(-T(4))) \times (-T(2))$
24221 := $((-1) + (T(T(T(2)))^2)) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))$
24222 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times T(T(4)))) \times 2$
24223 := $(-32) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24224 := $((T(T(4))^2 + T(2)) \times (4 \times 2))$
24225 := $(-5) \times (T(T(2)) - T((-2) + (T(4)^2)))$
24227 := $(-T(7) - (((T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)}) \times (-T(T(4))))/T(T(T(2))))))$
24228 := $(T(8) - (T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times (-4^{T(2)}))$
24232 := $((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((-T(2) + T(T(4))) \times 2))$
24234 := $((4^{T(3)} - 2) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))$
24235 := $((5 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(4) \times 2)$
24236 := $(-T(6) + (((T(T(3))^2) \times T(T(4))) + 2))$
24237 := $(-((T(73) \times T(2))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
24238 := $((T(T(8)) \times 32) + T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2))))))$
24241 := $(-14) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24242 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(4) + T(2))$
24243 := $(-3) + (((4^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)))$
24244 := $((44 \times T((2 + T(T(4)))))/T(2))$
24245 := $(5 \times (T((-T(T(4))) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 4)))) - 2)$
24246 := $((64^2 - T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)))$
24248 := $(8 \times ((T(T(4))^2) + (4 + 2)))$
24249 := $(9 \times ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))$
24261 := $((T((1 \times 6))^2) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2))$
24263 := $(T(3) - (((T(6)^2) \times T(T(4))) - 2))$
24264 := $((4^6 + T(2)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))$
24265 := $(-5) \times ((-T(6) \times T(T((2 + 4)))) - 2)$
24266 := $((T(T(6)) - ((T(6))^{T(2)})) \times T(T(4)))/T(T(T(2)))$
24267 := $((T(T(7)) - T(6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 4 \times T(2)$
24268 := $(-8) + ((T(6)^2) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))$
24272 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((7 \times 2))) + (-4) + T(T(T(2))))$
24273 := $(3 \times (((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2))))$
24274 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) - T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) - 2)$
24275 := $((T(5) \times 7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(4) \times 2))$
24276 := $((6 + T(7))^2) \times T((4 + 2))$
24278 := $(-8) + T(T(7)) \times (-T(2) - (4^{T(2)}))$
24279 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T(2)) - T(4)) \times T(2)$
24282 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) + 2))$
24283 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((8 + T(T(2)))) + T((T(4) - T(2))))$
24284 := $(-T(4) - (8 \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))))) \times 2$
24285 := $(5 \times (T(((T(8) \times T(2)) - T(4))) + T(T(2))))$
24286 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((8 + T(T(2)))) + T(4)) + T(T(T(2))))$
24288 := $(-8) \times (T(8) - ((2^{T(4)}) \times T(2)))$
24291 := $(T(-((1 - 9))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
24292 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(9)^2) - (4) \times 2)$
24294 := $((4 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(2) + T(4)))) \times T(T(2))$
24295 := $(-5) - (((T(9)^2) \times (-4)) \times T(2))$
24297 := $((T((T(7) + T(9))) \times T(2)) - (4) \times T(2))$
24298 := $((T(8) + T(9)) \times T(24)) - 2$
24304 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (0 - T(T(3)))) \times (4^2))$
24305 := $(50 - (-((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
24309 := $(9 \times T(((T(T(03)) + T(T(4))) - T(2))))$
24315 := $((T((T(5) - 1)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(T(2))))$
24316 := $(61 - (-((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24321 := $(T(T((-1) + (2 \times T(3)))) \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(2))))$
24322 := $(T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))/T(T(T(2)))$
24323 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 2$
24324 := $(-4) \times (T(2) - (T((3 \times 4))^2))$
24325 := $((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2)))$
24326 := $((T(6) + 2)^3 - (4)) \times 2$
24327 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))) - 3) \times T(4) - T(2)$

- 24328** := $(-8) + ((2 \times T(3 \times 4))^2)$
24329 := $((T((T(9) \times 2)) \times T(3)) - T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))$
24331 := $((1 + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))))$
24332 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/3) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24333 := $(-3) + ((3 \times (-3) + T(T(4)))^2)$
24334 := $-((T(T(4)) - ((33 - 4)^{T(2)}))$
24335 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) + (4^2)))$
24338 := $((T(8) \times (T((T(3) \times T(3))) + T(4))) + 2)$
24339 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times (T(3) \times 4)) + T(2)$
24342 := $(T(T(2)) - (-4 \times (T(3 \times 4))^2)$
24343 := $((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T((T(3)) - T(4)))) + 2)$
24344 := $((443 \times T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))))$
24345 := $(-T(5) - ((-T(4) \times T(T((3 + 4)))) \times T(T(2))))$
24346 := $((T(6) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) + T((T(4) + T(2)))$
24347 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(4) \times T(3))) - (T(4) + T(2)))$
24348 := $((8 \times T(T((4 \times 3))) - T((4 \times T(T(2))))$
24349 := $(T(9) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)))) \times (4^2)))$
24352 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
24354 := $((4 \times T(5)) \times T(T((3 + 4))) - T(T(2)))$
24355 := $(-5) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T((3 + 4))))/(-2))$
24356 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - ((3 + T(T(4)))^2)$
24357 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(3)))/(4 - 2)$
24358 := $((T(T((-8) + T(5))) \times (T(3) \times T(4))) - 2)$
24371 := $((-1) + (T(T(7)) \times T(3)) \times T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))$
24372 := $(2 \times ((T(T(7)) \times (3 \times T(4))) + T(T(2))))$
24373 := $-((T(T(T(3))) + (-T(7)) - (T(3) \times (4^{T(T(2))}))))$
24375 := $((T(5) \times T((T(7) - 3))) \times (T(4)/2))$
24376 := $(((-6) + T(7))^3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2$
24378 := $((-T(87)) - T(T(T(3)))) - 4 \times (-T(T(2)))$
24381 := $((1 + 8) \times 3) \times T(42)$
24382 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 8^3) - (T(4) - T(2)))$
24383 := $-((T(3) - ((T(8) - (3 + 4))^{T(2)}))$
24384 := $((T(4) \times T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times (4^{T(2)})$
24385 := $(-5) \times (T(8) - ((T(T(3)) - (4))^{T(2)}))$
24386 := $((T(6) + 8)^3) - T((4 - 2))$
24387 := $((-7) + T(8))^3 - (4 - 2)$
24388 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(8)) + T(T((3 + 4)))) + T(T(2))$
24389 := $((9 + ((8 \times 3) - 4))^{T(2)})$
24392 := $((29^3) + T((4 - 2)))$
24394 := $((T((T(4) \times 9)) \times T(3)) + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
24396 := $(-6) \times ((9 + T(T(3))) - (4^{T(T(2))}))$
24397 := $((7 + T((T(9) - T(3)))) \times (T(4) + T(T(T(2))))$
24398 := $((8 \times ((T(T(9)) \times 3) - T(T(4)))) - 2)$
24399 := $(-T(9)) + ((9 + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
24417 := $(T(7) + ((1 + (T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))))^{T(2)}))$
24422 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(2) \times T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + 2)$
24423 := $-(((T(T(3)) - T((T(2) \times T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(2))$
24424 := $((T(42) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - T(T(2))$
24425 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(4)))) - (T(T(4))^2)$
24426 := $((-T(6) + T((T(2) \times T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2))$
24427 := $((T((7 \times T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - T(2)$
24428 := $((T(T(8))/T(2)) \times T(T(4))) + (4) \times 2$
24429 := $((T(9) \times (-2) + (T(4) \times T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
24432 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times (-4)) + (4^{T(T(2))})))$
24433 := $((T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) + T(2)$
24435 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(4) \times T(2))))$
24436 := $((T((T(6) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) + T(T(2))$
24437 := $((T(7)^3) + T((T(4) \times (T(4) - T(2))))$
24438 := $((8 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T((T(4) \times 2))$
24444 := $((T((T(4) \times T(4)) - (4)))/4) \times T(T(T(2)))$
24445 := $(T(5) - (-T(4) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(42))))$
24448 := $((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) - 4 \times (4^2)$
24452 := $(2^{T(5)}) - (T((4 + 4) \times T(T(T(2)))))$
24453 := $(-((T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))) \times ((4 \times 4) + T(T(T(2)))))$
24456 := $(-6) \times ((5 \times 4) - (4^{T(T(2))}))$
24459 := $((T(9) \times 544) - T(T(T(2))))$
24462 := $((2 + T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) + (4)))) - T(2)$
24463 := $((T(T(3)) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(4))) + T(4))) - 2)$
24464 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T((4 \times 4) + T(2))))$
24465 := $((-5) \times T(T(6))) - T(4) \times (-T((4 + 2)))$
24471 := $(-1) + (T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T((4 \times 2))))$
24472 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T((4 \times 2))))$
24475 := $((-T((5 + T(7)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (4 + T(T(T(2))))$
24476 := $((6 + T(T(7))) + T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(2))$
24478 := $((T((T(8) - (7))) + T(4)) \times T(T(4))) + T(2)$
24479 := $((9 + T(T(7))) \times (4 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))$
24492 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((9 \times T(4)))) - T((T(4) + 2))$
24493 := $(-3) + ((9 - T(T(4))) \times (-4^2))$
24494 := $((T(49) \times (T(4) + T(4))) - T(T(2)))$
24495 := $(T(5) - ((T(9) \times (-4)) \times T((4^2))))$
24496 := $(T((-6) + T(9))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/T(4))^2)$
24497 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times (-4 + T((4 + 2))))$
24498 := $((-8) + T((9 \times T(4)))) - (4) \times T(T(2))$
24516 := $(-6) \times (T(-((1 - 5))) - (4^{T(T(2))}))$
24519 := $((T((T(9) - 1)) \times (T(5) + T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
24522 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(2)) - (T(5))) + (4^{T(T(2))})))$
24523 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))))$
24524 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) - (-5) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))))$
24525 := $-((T(T(5)) - (T((2 \times T(5))) \times (T(T(4)) - 2)))$
24528 := $((-8) + ((T(2) + (5))^4)) \times T(T(2))$
24531 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) \times T(5)) + T((T(T(4)) - 2)))$

- 24532** := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) + 5) × T(T(4))) + 2)
24533 := (((T(T(3)) × T(T(3))) + (5)) × T(T(4))) + T(2))
24534 := ((T(4) × T(T(3))) × T(T(5))) - T(T((4 × 2)))
24535 := ((5^{T(3)}) + (T(54) × T(T(2))))
24536 := (((T(6) × T(T(3))) + (5)) × T(T(4))) + T(T(2)))
24537 := (((T(T(7)) + 3) × (T(5) × 4)) - T(2))
24538 := (-8) + ((T((T(3) × T(5))) - (4)) × T(T(2)))
24544 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T((T(4)/5))) × (4²))
24545 := (((5 - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(5)⁴))/2)
24546 := ((T((6 × (T(4) + (5)))) - (4)) × T(T(2)))
24547 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(4))) + T(T((T(5) - (4)))) + T(T(2)))
24548 := (-8⁴) + ((T(T(5)) + (4)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
24549 := (((T(T(9)) + (4)) + T(T(5))) + T(4)) × T(T(T(2))))
24552 := (T((T(T(2)) + (5))) × ((T(T(5)) + (4)) × T(2)))
24555 := (-T(5)) - ((-T(5)) × T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × T(T(T(2))))
24557 := (-T(7)) - (T(5) × ((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2))))
24558 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) × T(5)) - (4)) × T(2))
24562 := ((T(T(2)) × T((6 × T(5)))) - (4 × 2))
24563 := ((T(3) × T((6 × T(5)))) - (T(4) - T(2)))
24564 := (((T(T(T(4))) × (T(6) - (5))) - (T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2))))
24565 := (5 × ((6 + T(5)) - (4))^{T(2)})
24566 := (((6 × T((6 × T(5)))) - T(4)) + T(T(2)))
24567 := (((7 × T((T(6) + (5)))) × T(4)) - T(2))
24568 := (-8) - ((-T(6) - T(5)) × (4^{T(T(2))}))
24569 := ((T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(5)))) - T(T((T(4) + T(2))))
24582 := (T(2) × ((8⁵)/4) + 2)
24583 := (T((T(3 + 8)) - (5))) × (T(4) + T(2))
24584 := (-T((T(4) + T(8)))) + (T(5) × T((T(T(4)) + T(2))))
24585 := ((-5) + (T((8 × 5)) × T(4))) × T(2)
24587 := (((T(T(7)) + (T(8) + (5))) × T(T(4))) + 2)
24588 := (T(8) × (T(T(8)) + (T(5) + (4 - 2))))
24591 := ((1 - (-9) × (T(T(5)) + T(4))) × T(T(T(2))))
24592 := ((-T(2)) + T(T(T(9 - 5)))) × (4²)
24594 := ((4 + T((T(9) + T(5 + 4)))) × T(T(2)))
24595 := (-5) - (T((T(9) - (5))) × (-T(4) × T(2)))
24599 := (((T(T(9)) × (9 + T(5))) - T(4)) - T(T(T(T(2))))
24609 := ((T(T(9)) × (06 × 4)) - T(T(T(T(2))))
24612 := (T(T(2)) × ((1 × 6) + (4^{T(T(2))})))
24613 := (-T(T(3))) - ((-16) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2)))
24615 := (T(5) × T((-1) + T(6))) + T((T(T(4)) - 2)))
24616 := (-T(6)) - ((-16) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(2))
24618 := -(T(T(8)) - (T((1 + 6)) × T(42)))
24619 := ((T(T((9 + 1))) × (6 + T(4))) - T(T(T(2))))
24622 := (((2 - T(T(T(2)))) × (-6⁴)) - 2)
24624 := ((T(T(4)) + 2) × ((6⁴)/T(2)))
24625 := ((T(T(5) × T(T(2)))) × 6) + T((4 + T(T(2))))
24626 := (((T(6) - 2) × (6⁴)) + 2)
24627 := ((T(T(7)) × T(2)) + (T((T(6) - (4)))²))
24628 := ((8 × T(T((2 × 6)))) - (T(4) × 2))
24631 := (T(T((1 + 3))) + (6 × (4^{T(T(2))})))
24632 := ((2 - T(T((T(3) + (6)))) × (-4 × 2))
24633 := (T(T(3)) × (-3) + T((6 + 42)))
24634 := (((4^{T(3)}) × 6) + T(T(4))) + T(2))
24635 := (5 × (((T(T(3)) × T(T(6))) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))))
24636 := ((-6) - (T(T((T(3) + (6)))) × (-4))) × 2)
24637 := ((T(T((7 + 3))) × (6 + T(4))) - T(2))
24638 := (((T((8 × T(3))) × T(6)) - T(T(4))) - T(2))
24639 := (((T((T(9) + 3)) × T(6)) - T(T(4))) - 2)
24641 := (1 - (T(T((4 + 6))) × (-4²)))
24642 := (T(T((2 × 4))) × (T(6) + ((4²)))
24643 := (((T(3) + T(4)) × T(T((6 + 4)))) + T(2))
24644 := (4 - (T(T((4 + 6))) × (-4²)))
24645 := (-T(5)) × (T(4) - T((T(6) + T((4 × 2))))))
24646 := ((T(T((6 + 4))) × (6 + T(4))) + T(T(2)))
24647 := (-7) × ((T(T(4)) - T((T(6) × 4))) - T(T(2)))
24648 := (T((84 - 6)) × (4 × 2))
24649 := (((9 × (-4) + T(6))) + (4)²)
24652 := (T(T(2)) - (((5 - T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))))
24654 := (((T(4) + T((T(5) × 6))) + (4)) × T(T(2)))
24655 := ((T(5) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (-2)))
24657 := (((T(T(7)) + (5)) × (6 × T(4))) - T(2))
24659 := ((T(T(9)) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(6)))) - (4^{T(T(2))}))
24661 := ((16 × T(T((6 + 4)))) + T(T(T(2))))
24662 := ((-2) + T(6)) × ((6⁴) + 2)
24665 := (-5) × ((-T(6)) × (T(T(6)) + (4))) + 2)
24666 := (-6) × ((6 - T(6)) - (4^{T(T(2))}))
24667 := (T(T(7)) - ((-T(6) × T(6))) × T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))
24668 := ((8 × T(T((6 + 6)))) + (T(4) × 2))
24669 := (-T(T(9))) - ((-T(6)) × T((-6) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2)))
24672 := ((T((2 × 7)) × (T(T(6)) + (4))) - T(2))
24673 := ((T((T(T(3)) - (7))) × (T(T(6)) + (4))) - 2)
24675 := (-T(5)) × ((-7) × T(T(6))) - T((T(4) - T(2)))
24676 := (((T(6) × T(7)) × T(6)) - T(4)) × 2)
24677 := (T(7) + (((7 × T(6)) + T(4))²))
24679 := (((T((T(9) + T(7))) - T(T(6))) × T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))
24682 := ((T(T(T(2))) - (-8) × T(T((6 + 4)))) × 2)
24683 := ((T(T(3)) × T((8 × 6))) - (T(4) + T(2)))
24684 := (((T(48) × T(6)) - T(4)) - 2)
24685 := ((T(5) × T((T(8) + T(6)))) + (T(T(4)) × (-2)))
24686 := (((T(6) × T((8 × 6))) - (4)) - T(T(2)))
24688 := (-8) + (T((8 × 6)) × T((4 + 2)))
24691 := ((1 - T(T(9))) + (T(6) × T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))))))

$$\begin{aligned} 24692 &:= (((T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(6)) - T(4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 24693 &:= ((T((3 + T(9))) \times T(6)) - T((4 - 2))) \\ 24694 &:= ((4 - T(T(9))) + (T(6) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))))) \\ 24695 &:= ((T((5 + T(9))) \times T(6)) - T((4^{T(2)}))) \\ 24696 &:= (T(6) \times T(((96/4) \times 2))) \\ 24697 &:= (((T((T(7) + T(9))) - T(T(6))) \times T(4)) - T(2)) \\ 24698 &:= (((T(8) - (T(T(9)) \times 6)) \times (-4)) + 2) \\ 24699 &:= (((9 \times T(9)) \times (6 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 24702 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(((0 - 7) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 24706 &:= (-60) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24715 &:= (-51) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24716 &:= ((T(6) - 1) + (T((-7) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24717 &:= (T(T((7 - 1))) \times (7 + (T(4)^2))) \\ 24732 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T(4)) + 2)) \\ 24733 &:= (-33) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24734 &:= (-T(4)) - (-T(3)) \times (T(7) + (4^{T(T(2))})) \\ 24735 &:= (T(5) - (((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(4))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 24736 &:= ((-6) - T(T((3 + 7)))) \times (-4^2) \\ 24737 &:= (-7) - (-T(3)) \times (T(7) + (4^{T(T(2))})) \\ 24738 &:= ((T(8) - T((3 \times T(7)))) \times (-4 - T(2))) \\ 24739 &:= (-((9 \times 3)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24741 &:= (T((-1) + T(4))) + (T((-7) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 24742 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - (4 \times T(T(2)))) \\ 24743 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times ((T(7) \times 4) - T(2))) \\ 24744 &:= (((-T(4)) + T((T(4) \times 7))) \times T(4)) - T(T(2)) \\ 24745 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times 7)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \\ 24746 &:= (((6 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(4) \times 2)) \\ 24748 &:= ((-8) - T(4)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24749 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-4) + T(7)) - T((T(4) + T(2)))) \\ 24751 &:= (-15) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24752 &:= ((T(T((2 \times 5))) + 7) \times (4^2)) \\ 24756 &:= ((T((6 + 5)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(4)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24757 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(4)))) / (-2)) \\ 24758 &:= ((8 \times T(T((5 + 7)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-2))) \\ 24759 &:= (9 \times (-T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 24761 &:= ((1 - 6) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24762 &:= ((2 - 6) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24763 &:= (-3) - ((-T(6)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(2)) \\ 24764 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 6) \times T(T(7))) - (4 - 2)) \\ 24765 &:= (-T(5)) \times (((6 + T(T(7))) \times (-4)) - T(2)) \\ 24766 &:= (T(T(((6 - 6) + 7))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24767 &:= ((7 - 6) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24768 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(6) \times T(7)) + (T(4)^2))) \\ 24769 &:= ((9 - 6) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24772 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(4)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 24773 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - T(7)) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24774 &:= (((T((T(4) \times 7)) - 7) \times T(4)) - T(T(2))) \\ 24775 &:= (-5) - (((T(T(7)) + 7) \times (-T(4))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24782 &:= ((2 \times 8) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24783 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times (8 + T(7))) - (T(T(4)))) \times T(2)) \\ 24784 &:= ((T(4) + 8) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24785 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(4)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 24786 &:= ((T(((T(6) - 8) \times 7)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24787 &:= (7 \times (((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24788 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(8)) + (T((7 \times 4) \times 2)) \\ 24789 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times 8) - (7 + T(4))) \times T(2)) \\ 24791 &:= (-T((1 + T(9)))) - ((T(7) \times (-4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24792 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T((T(9) + 7))) - 4) \times T(2)) \\ 24793 &:= (-T(3)) - (((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2)) \\ 24794 &:= (49 \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(4)^2))) \\ 24795 &:= (T(5) \times T(((9 \times 7) - 4) - 2)) \\ 24796 &:= (-6) - (((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(2)) \\ 24798 &:= (-T(8)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(7) - 4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 24799 &:= (-9) - (((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(2)) \\ 24804 &:= ((T(4) + 08) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(2)))) \\ 24813 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((1 + (8^4)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 24814 &:= (T(4) - (-18) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(2)))) \\ 24816 &:= ((T(6) + 1) \times T((T(T(8)/4) + 2)) \\ 24818 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (1 + T(8))) - T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24819 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(-((1 - 8))) - 4)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24822 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(2)) + (T((8 \times (4 + 2)))))) \\ 24823 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((2 \times 8) \times (T(T(T(4)) - T(2)))) \\ 24824 &:= (428 \times (T(T(4)) + T(2))) \\ 24825 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-2 - T((T(8) + T((4 + 2)))))) \\ 24827 &:= (((-T(7)) + T((T(T(T(2))) + 8))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 24828 &:= (((T(8) + T(T(2))) + (8^4)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24829 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(T(2))) - 8) \times 4) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 24832 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(3) \times 8))) + T((4^2))) \\ 24834 &:= ((43 + (8^4)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24835 &:= ((-5) - (T((T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(4)))) / (-2) \\ 24836 &:= (T((T(6)/3)) \times ((T(T(8)) - T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 24837 &:= ((-7) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(84)))) - T(T(2)) \\ 24838 &:= (((8 \times 3) \times T(T((T(8)/4)))) - 2) \\ 24839 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (3 \times 8)) - (4 - T(2))) \\ 24841 &:= (1 - ((-4) \times T((T(T(8)/4)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24842 &:= ((24 \times T(T((T(8)/4)))) + 2) \\ 24843 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(48) + 4) + T(2))) \\ 24844 &:= ((T(4) \times T(((T(4) \times 8) - T(4)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 24845 &:= (5 - ((-4) \times T(T((T(8)/4)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 24846 &:= (((6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times 8) + (T(T(4))) \times 2) \\ 24847 &:= ((T((7 \times T(4))) \times T((8 - 4))) - T(2)) \\ 24848 &:= ((T((-8) + T((4 + 8)))) \times T(4)) - 2) \\ 24849 &:= (9 - ((-4) \times T(T((T(8)/4)))) \times T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 24852** := (((T((T(2) × T(5))) × 8) + (4) × T(2))
24853 := ((T((T(-3) + T(5))) - 8) × T(4) + T(2))
24854 := (-(((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) - T(T(8)))) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))))
24855 := (5 × (T((T(5) + (84))) + T(T(T(2))))))
24856 := ((T(-((T(6) - T((5 + 8)))))) × T(4) + T(T(2)))
24857 := (((T(7) - (5)) × T((T(8) + T(4)))) - T(T(2)))
24858 := ((-T(8)) × (T((T(5) + T(8))) + T(T(4))))/(-2))
24864 := ((4 × 6) × (T(8) + (T(4)^{T(2)})))
24865 := ((5⁶) + ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4))))/(-T(T(2))))
24866 := (T((6 × 6)) - (-8) × (T(T(4))²))
24867 := ((T(7) + ((T(T(6)) × T(8)) - T(T(4)))) × T(2))
24868 := (((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) × T(8)) + (T(4²)))
24869 := (((T(T(9)) × 6) + 8) × 4) - T(2))
24871 := (T(T(-((1 - 7)))) + ((-8) × T(T(T(4)))) × (-2)))
24872 := (((T(T(2)) - (-T(7)) × T(T(8)))) × 4)/T(2))
24873 := ((37 × T(T(8))) + T(T((4 + 2))))
24874 := (T(4) - (((-T(7)) × T(T(8))) × (-4))/(-T(2)))
24875 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(7) - 8))) - T((4 + T(T(T(2))))))
24876 := ((T(T((6 + 7))) - (T(8) + (4))) × T(T(2)))
24878 := ((8 × (T(7) + T(T(8 + 4)))) + T(T(2)))
24879 := ((-T(9)) - ((-T(7)) × T(T(8))) × (-4))/(-T(2)))
24882 := (T(2) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(8))) - T(42)))
24884 := -(((T(T(T(4))) - (T(8) × (-T(8)) - T(T(T(4))))/(-2))))
24885 := (T(5) × ((T(8) × (T(8) + T(4))) + T(2)))
24886 := ((T(6) × T((8 + T(8)))) + 4^{T(T(2))})
24888 := (8 × ((T(8) + T(T(8 + 4))) - T(T(2))))
24892 := (((T(2) × T(T(9))) × 8) + T(T(4))) - T(2))
24893 := (((3 × T(T(9))) × 8) + T(T(4))) - 2
24894 := (((4 × T(T(9))) + (T(8)/4) × T(T(2)))
24895 := (((T(5) × T(9)) × T(8)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))))
24912 := (((T(2) + T(T((1 × 9)))) × 4) × T(T(2)))
24915 := (T(T((5 - 1))) × ((T(9) × T(4)) + T(2)))
24922 := (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(2)) × T(T(9)))) × 4) - 2)
24923 := (((T(T(3)) × T((T(2) + T(9)))) - (4) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
24924 := (((4 + T((2 × T(9)))) + T(T(4))) × T(T(2)))
24925 := (5 × ((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) - T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))))))
24926 := (((T(6) + (T(T(2)) × T(T(9)))) × 4) + 2)
24927 := ((T((T(7) × T(2))) - 9) × (T(4) - T(2)))
24928 := (8 × ((2 × 9) + T(T(T(4)))) × 2))
24929 := (-T((T(9) - 2))) + (T(T(9)) × (4 + T(T(T(2))))))
24931 := (T(13) + ((T(T(9)) × 4) × T(T(2))))
24932 := (23 × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) - T(T(2))))
24933 := (T(T(3)) - (((-3) - T(T(9))) × 4) × T(T(2)))
24934 := ((4 + (T(3) × T(9))) × T((T(4) + T(2))))
24935 := ((T(T(5)) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(9)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-2)))
24936 := ((6 + T(3)) × ((T(T(9)) + (4)) × 2))
24938 := (((8 × 3) × (T(T(9)) + (4))) + 2)
24939 := (-T(9)) - (((T(3) + T(T(9))) × (-4)) × T(T(2)))
24942 := (T(T(2)) - (((4 + T(T(9))) × (-4)) × T(T(2))))
24944 := (((-T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 9) × (-4²)
24945 := (-T(5)) × (-T(4)) - T(((9 + T(4)) × T(2)))
24947 := ((T(74) × 9) - T((T(4) - T(2))))
24948 := (((8 + 4) × 9) × T(T((4 + 2))))
24949 := (-T(T(9))) - (-((T(T(4)) + 9) × T(T((T(4) - T(2))))))
24954 := (((4 + T(5)) + (T(T(9)) × 4)) × T(T(2)))
24955 := (-5) - (((5 + T(T(9))) × (-4)) × T(T(2)))
24957 := (((7 + 5) × T((9 + T(T(4)))) - T(2))
24958 := (((T(T(8)) + T((T(5) + T(9)))) × T(4)) - 2)
24971 := (((1 + T(7)) × T((T(9) - (4)))) + 2)
24972 := ((-((T(2) - T(7))) × T(T(9))) - T(42))
24973 := (((3 + T(T(7))) + T(9)) × T(T(4))) + T(2))
24975 := ((T((5 × 7)) + T(T(9))) × T((T(4)/2)))
24976 := (T((T(6) + (7))) + (T((9 × T(4))) × T(T(2))))
24977 := ((T(7)^{T(-7+9)}) + (T(T(4))²))
24978 := ((T(8) × (T(7) + T((9 × 4)))) - T(T(2)))
24982 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(8))) + T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) × 2)
24983 := ((T(T(3)) × (8 + T(T(9)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-2)))
24984 := ((4 × T(8)) + ((T(T(9)) × 4) × T(T(2))))
24985 := (-T(5)) + (8 × (T(9) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-2))))
24987 := (((T(7) + T(T(8))) × (9 × 4)) + T(2))
24988 := (((-T(8)) × T((8 + T(9)))) + T(T(T(4))))/(-2))
24993 := ((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(9) × T(9)) × (-4))) × T(2))
24994 := (((T(4)^{T(9)/9})/4) - T(T(2)))
24995 := (-5) × ((-T(99)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(2)))
24996 := (-T((6 + 9))) + (T(T((9 + 4))) × T(T(2)))
24997 := (7 × (((T(9) × T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2))))
25024 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(20) × T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
25086 := ((T(T((T(6) - 8))) - 05) × T(T(2)))
25113 := ((T(3) × T(T((-((1 + 1)) + T(5)))) - T(2))
25116 := (6 × T(T(((1 × 15) - 2))))
25119 := ((T(91) × (1 + 5)) + T(2))
25121 := (-1) + (T(T(2)) × (1 + T(T((T(5) - 2))))))
25122 := (T(T(2)) + (T(T(2)) × T(T((15 - 2))))))
25124 := (-T(T(4)) - ((T((T(T(T(2))) - 1)) × (-T(T(5)))) + (T(T(T(2))))))
25125 := (T(5) + (T(T(2)) × (-1) + T(T((T(5) - 2))))))
25128 := (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(2))) - (-1) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(2))))
25137 := ((7 × T(T(3))) × T(((1 + 5) × T(2))))
25143 := ((T(3) - T((T(T(4)) - 1))) × (-T(5) + 2))
25146 := (6 × ((4 + 1) + T(T((T(5) - 2))))))
25152 := ((T(T((-2) + T(5))) + (1 + 5)) × T(T(2)))
25155 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(5)) × (1 - T(5))) + T(2))
25158 := (((-8) + T(51)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(T(2)))
25164 := (-T((T(4) + (61)))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
25168 := (8 × (((6 - 1)⁵) + T(T(T(2))))))

- 25172** := ((2 × T(T(7))) × (1 + (T(5) × 2)))
25174 := ((T(4) – T(71)) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(2))))))
25176 := ((T(T((6 + 7))) + T(-((1 – 5)))) × T(T(2)))
25179 := (((T(T(9)) + T(7)) + T((1 + T(5)))) × T(T(T(2))))
25182 := (T(T(2)) × (((T(8) – 1) × T(T(5))) – T(2)))
25185 := (–(T(5)) – ((T((T(8) – 1)) × T(T(5)))/(-T(2))))
25188 := ((T(8) × T((T(8) + 1))) – T((5 × T(2))))
25194 := ((T(4) + 9) × T(-((1 – 52))))
25195 := (–(5) – ((–(9 + 1)) × T(T(5))) × T(T(T(2))))
25197 := ((T((T(7) – (9 – 1))) × T(T(5))) – T(2))
25198 := (–(8) + ((T(91) + T(5)) × T(T(2))))
25202 := ((T(20) × T((T(2) × 5))) + 2)
25203 := (((T(T(T(3))) – T(T(T(02)))) × T(T(5))) + T(2))
25206 := ((T((60/T(2))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(2)))
25212 := (T(T(2)) – ((T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)))) – T(T(2))))
25215 := (T(5) + ((T((1 + T(2))) × T(T(5))) × T(T(T(2))))))
25218 := (((T((T(8) + 1)) × T(T(2))) – (T(5))) × T(T(2)))
25221 := ((T((-1) + T((2 × T(2)))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2))))
25223 := (T(T(3)) – (((T(T(T(T(2)))) – (T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)))) – 2))
25224 := (((T(T(4)) × T(2)) × T((2 + T(5)))) – T(T(T(2))))
25225 := ((–(T(T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) – T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (5²))
25227 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(2)))) – (–(T(2)) + T(T(5)))) × T(2))
25228 := ((T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) – 2) × T((5 + 2)))
25234 := ((T(T((T(4) + 3))) × T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) – 2))
25235 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) – T((T((-2) + T(5))) – T(T(T(2))))))
25236 := (–(6) – ((T(T(3)) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) × (-T(T(2))))
25237 := (–(T(T(7))) – ((–(T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (T(T(5)))) – 2))
25238 := (T(8) – (((T(T(T(3))) – T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)))) – 2))
25239 := ((T(9) × T((T(3) × T(2)) + T(5))) – T(T(2)))
25242 := (((T(2) × T(T(4))) × T((2 + T(5)))) – T(2))
25243 := (((3 × T(T(4))) × T((2 + T(5)))) – 2)
25245 := (T(54) × ((T(2) × 5) + 2))
25246 := ((T(T(6)) + T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) × (T(5) – 2))
25247 := (((–(T(7)) + T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) × T(5)) + 2)
25248 := (–((T(8) – (T(42) × T((5 + 2))))))
25249 := (((T(T(9)) – T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(2))) + 5)) – T(T(T(T(2))))))
25252 := (T((T(T(T(2))) – 5) – (–(T(T(2))) × T(T((T(5) – 2))))))
25254 := ((T((4 × 5)) – T(2)) × (T(T(5)) + 2))
25255 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))) + T((5 × 2)))
25256 := (((T(T(6)) × T((T(T(5))/T(2))))/T(5)) × 2)
25257 := (((T(T((T(7) – T(5)))) × T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) + T(T(T(2))))
25263 := (T(T(3)) × ((T((6 – 2)) × T(T(5))) + T(2)))
25266 := (–(6) – ((–(6^{T(2)})) × (T(T(5)) – T(2))))
25267 := ((T(7) × T((T(6) × 2))) – (T(5) + 2))
25269 := (T(T(9)) – (((–(T(T(6))) × T(T(T(2)))) × 5) + T(T(T(2))))))
25271 := (–(1) + (72 × T((5 + T(T(T(2))))))
25272 := ((2 × T((T(7) – 2))) × T((5 + T(2))))
- 25273** := (T(37) + (T(T(2)) × T((T(5) × T(T(2))))))
25274 := (–(T(4)) – (–(T(7)) × T(((T(2) × T(5)) – T(2))))))
25275 := (5 × (T((7 × 2)) + T((T(T(5)) – T(T(T(2))))))
25277 := (–(7) – (–(T(7)) × T(((T(2) × T(5)) – T(2))))
25278 := ((8 × T(((T(7) × T(2)) – (5)))) – 2)
25281 := (((T(18) + T(2)) – T(5))²)
25282 := ((T((T(T(2)) + T(8))) × T((2 + 5))) – 2)
25284 := (T(((4 + T(8)) + 2)) × T((5 + 2)))
25286 := ((T((6 + T(8))) × T((2 + 5))) + 2)
25287 := ((T(7) × T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) + (5 – 2))
25288 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(8) + 2)) – (T(T(5))/T(T(2))))
25305 := ((50 + (T(T(T(3))) × 5)) × T(T(T(2))))
25308 := (T(8) × T((035 + 2)))
25311 := (((–(1) + T((-1) + T(T(3)))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
25312 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(13))) × (–(5) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
25315 := (((T(5)¹⁺³) + (5))/2)
25322 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T((-2) + T(T(3)))) × T(T(5))) + 2)
25323 := (((T(T(3)) + T((-2) + T(T(3)))) × T(T(5))) + T(2))
25325 := ((–(T(T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) – T(T(T(3)))) + (5^{T(2)}))
25326 := ((T((6²) + (T(3)⁵)) × T(2))
25327 := ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + ((3 × 5)^{T(2)}))
25328 := (8 × (T(((2^{T(3)}) + T(5))) + T(T(2))))
25329 := (T(9) – (T((2 × T(T(3)))) × (–(5 + 2))))
25332 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(3) × T(3)) + T(T((T(5) – 2))))))
25334 := (–((T(4)³) + (T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(5)) – T(T(2))))))
25335 := (((T(5)³) + 3) × T(5))/2
25338 := ((T(T(8))/3) + (T(3) × T(T((T(5) – 2))))))
25341 := (((1 – (–(T(4)) × T(T(3)))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2))))
25342 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T((T(4) + 3)))) – 5) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
25343 := ((T(T(T(3))) – 4) + (T(3) × T(T((T(5) – 2))))))
25344 := ((4⁴) × (T(T(3)) + T((T(5) – T(2))))))
25345 := (–(5) + (T((4 × 3)) × T((5²))))
25346 := (–((T(T(6)) – ((T(T(4)) × T((T(3) × 5))) + 2)))
25347 := (((–(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) – (T(T(3)))) × (T(5) + 2))
25348 := ((–(T(8)) – ((–(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) – 5)) × 2)
25362 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(6)) + (T(T((3 + 5))) × T(T(2))))))
25364 := (–((T(T(T(4))) – (((T(T(6)) – 3) × (T(T(5)) – 2))))))
25365 := (T(5) × (T(63) – T((5²))))
25368 := ((T((T(8) + (6))) + 3) × T((5 + 2)))
25372 := (–(T(2)) – ((–(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (–(5^{T(2)}))))
25374 := (–(T((T(T(4)) + (7 + T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
25375 := (((–(T(5)) × T(T(7)))/T(3)) × (–(5²)))
25383 := ((T(T(T(3))) + T(8)) + (T(3) × T(T((T(5) – 2))))))
25386 := ((T(T((T(6) – 8))) + (3 × T(5))) × T(T(2)))
25389 := (T(T(9)) + ((–(T(8)) + T((T(3) × T(5)))) × T(T(2))))
25392 := (2 × (–(9) – (T(T(T(3))) × (–(T(5 × 2))))))

$$\begin{aligned} 25395 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 9) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25398 &:= (((T((-8) + T(9))) \times T(3)) + (T(5))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 25405 &:= (-5) + (((0 - T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25431 &:= (((1 + T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25432 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + (5 + T(T(2)))))) \\ 25433 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - (((T(T(3)) \times (-T(4))) \times T(T(5))) - 2)) \\ 25434 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(3 \times T(4))) - T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25435 &:= (T(5) - (((T(T(3)) + T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(2)))))) \\ 25436 &:= ((((-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + 5) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 25438 &:= (((T(8) \times T(3)) - 4) \times T(T(5))) - 2 \\ 25439 &:= ((T((9 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25442 &:= (((2 + T((T(4) + T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) + 2) \\ 25443 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(4) \times T(5)))) \times T(2)) \\ 25444 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25445 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + T(4)) - (T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) \times 2)))))) \\ 25446 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4)))) + T((5 + T(2)))) \\ 25448 &:= (8 \times ((T(4) \times T(4)) + T(T((T(5) - T(2)))))) \\ 25449 &:= (-T(T(9))) + (4 \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25452 &:= (((T((2 \times T(5))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(5))) - T(2)) \\ 25453 &:= (((T((T(3) \times 5)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(5))) - 2) \\ 25454 &:= ((-T(T(4)) - T(T((T(5) - 4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25455 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(5))) \times T(T(4))) - T((5 \times T(2)))) \\ 25458 &:= ((T(T(8)) - ((-5) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times T(2)) \\ 25462 &:= ((2 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + 52 \\ 25464 &:= (-4) \times (T(T(6)) - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(2))) \\ 25465 &:= ((5 + (T(T(6)) \times T(4))) \times (5 + T(T(2)))) \\ 25466 &:= (((T(6) + T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(5) + 2)) \\ 25469 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(6) + 4)) - T(T(5 + 2))) \\ 25472 &:= ((T((2 \times T(7))) - 4) \times (-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25473 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (7 - ((-T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 25475 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T((5 \times 2)))))) \\ 25476 &:= ((T(T((6 + 7))) + (4 \times T(5))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 25477 &:= (((-7) \times T(7)) \times (-T(4)) - T(T(5))) - T(2) \\ 25479 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(7))) - 4) \times T((T(5) + T(2)))) \\ 25482 &:= (2 \times (T(8) - ((-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(5 - 2)))))) \\ 25484 &:= -(((T(T(4)) + T(8)) - (T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) \times 2)))))) \\ 25485 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(8)) + ((T(45) - 2))) \\ 25487 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (8 + T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) - 2))) \\ 25488 &:= (T(8) \times (T(T(8)) + (45 - T(2)))) \\ 25494 &:= (((T(49) + 4) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25495 &:= (T(5) + (-((T(T(9)) - T(T(4)))) \times (-5) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25514 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-1) + T((T(5) + T(5)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 25515 &:= (T((T(5) - 1)) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(2))) \\ 25522 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + (T(T((5 + 2)))))) \\ 25523 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(5)))) - (T(T(5)) - 2)) \\ 25524 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (2 + T(T(5)))) \times (T(5) + T(2))) \\ 25525 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + (T((5^2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25528 &:= (((T(T(8))/T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) - 5)) - 2) \\ 25533 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(3))) - 5) \times (-T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))))) \\ 25536 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 3) \times (T(T(5)) - (5 + T(2)))) \\ 25537 &:= ((T(7) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)))) - T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) \\ 25538 &:= (((T(8) \times 3) + 5) \times (-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25539 &:= (((93 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25542 &:= ((T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) - (T(T(5)) + T(2))) \\ 25543 &:= ((T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) - (T(T(5)) + 2)) \\ 25544 &:= ((-T(4) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25545 &:= (((T(5)^4) + T((T(5) + T(5))))/2) \\ 25546 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T((T(5) - 2)))) \\ 25547 &:= (-T(7)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T((5 + (5^2)))))) \\ 25548 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (4 + T(5))) + T(T(5))) \times 2) \\ 25551 &:= (((1 + T((5 + T(5)))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25554 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - T(T((5 - 2)))) \\ 25555 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T((5 + T(5))) + T(2))) \\ 25557 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))) + 5)/(-5) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25559 &:= (9 \times T((5 \times T(5)))) - T((T(5) - 2)) \\ 25562 &:= ((((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) - T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + 2) \\ 25563 &:= ((((-3) + T(T(6))) - T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + T(2) \\ 25564 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((6 \times 5))) - 5) - T(T(2))) \\ 25569 &:= ((T((9 + T(6))) \times 55) - T(T(2))) \\ 25572 &:= ((T((T(2) + 7)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - T(2)) \\ 25573 &:= ((T((3 + 7)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25574 &:= (-4) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(5) - T((T(5) - T(2)))))) \\ 25575 &:= (T(((5 \times 7) - 5) \times T((5 \times 2))) \\ 25576 &:= ((((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (T(5)/(-5))) - 2) \\ 25577 &:= ((T(T((T(7)/7))) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) + 2) \\ 25578 &:= ((T((87 + 5)) - T(5)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 25582 &:= -((T(2) - (T(85) \times (5 + 2)))) \\ 25584 &:= (T((4 + 8)) \times (T((5 \times 5)) + T(2))) \\ 25585 &:= -((T(5) - ((8 \times (5 + T(5)))^2))) \\ 25587 &:= (((7 \times T(85)) + 5) - T(2)) \\ 25593 &:= (-3) - ((-9) \times (T((5 \times T(5))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 25594 &:= (((T(T(4)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-5))) \times (-5)) - T(T(2))) \\ 25595 &:= (-5) + (((T(9) - 5) + T(T(5)))^2) \\ 25596 &:= (T(6) - (T((T(9) - T(5))) \times (-T((5 \times 2)))))) \\ 25597 &:= ((T(T(7)) - 9) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))))) \\ 25598 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) + 2) \\ 25599 &:= (-T(9)) - ((-9) \times T((5 \times T(5)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 25613 &:= (-T((T(3) + 1))) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25615 &:= (-5) + (T((-1) + T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + 2)) \\ 25631 &:= (-T((1 + 3))) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25632 &:= (2 \times ((T((3 \times T(6))) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 25633 &:= (-T(3)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + 2) \\ 25634 &:= (-T((4^3))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2))) \\ 25635 &:= (T(5) \times (T(((3 \times T(6)) - 5)) - 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25637 &:= (-7) - ((T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(2)) \\ 25638 &:= (((T(T(8))/T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - (5 - 2)) \\ 25639 &:= ((T(T((9 - 3))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25641 &:= ((T(14) + 6) \times T(T(T(5 - 2)))) \\ 25642 &:= (-((T(2) - 4)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25643 &:= ((T(3) - 4) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25644 &:= ((T(T((-4) + T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(2)) \\ 25645 &:= (-5) - (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5))) \times (-2)) \\ 25646 &:= (-T(64) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 25647 &:= (((T(7) \times 4) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(5)^2)) \\ 25648 &:= ((-8) + (4 \times T(T(6)))) \times T((5 + 2)) \\ 25649 &:= (((T(T(9)) + 4^6) \times 5) - T(T(2))) \\ 25661 &:= ((-1) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25662 &:= ((T((2^6) - 6) \times T(5)) - T(2)) \\ 25664 &:= (-4) - (-6 \times T(((6 \times T(5)) + 2))) \\ 25665 &:= (T(5) \times T(((6 + 6) \times 5) - 2)) \\ 25667 &:= (T(7) + ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - 2)) \\ 25668 &:= (T((86 + 6) \times T((5 - 2))) \\ 25672 &:= ((T(2) + T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25673 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) - 52) \\ 25674 &:= (((-((T(4) + 7))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2))) \\ 25675 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 2)) \\ 25677 &:= ((T(7) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + 5)) \times T(2)) \\ 25678 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))/T(2))) \\ 25679 &:= ((T(9) - 7) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25682 &:= (((-2) + (T(8) \times 6)) \times T(T(5))) + 2) \\ 25683 &:= -((T(T(3)) + ((-8) \times T(6)) \times T((T(5) + 2)))) \\ 25684 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + (((8 + 6^5))) / T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25686 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(8))) / 6) + (T(5) \times T(2))) \\ 25689 &:= (((T(9) \times T(8)) \times (T(6) - 5)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25692 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (96 + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) \\ 25694 &:= (-T(4) - ((-9) \times T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25695 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T((9 + T(6))) \times (-T((5 \times 2)))) \\ 25697 &:= (-T(7) - ((T(T(9)) - 6) \times (-5^2))) \\ 25698 &:= (-T(T(8))) - (-(T(T(9)) - T(6))) \times (5 + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25704 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + (0 - T(7))) \times (T(5) + 2)) \\ 25719 &:= (T(9) - ((1 + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) \\ 25722 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T(2) + (T(7) \times T((T(5) + 2)))) \\ 25723 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(2)) + (T(7) + T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25724 &:= ((4 + T(2 \times 7)) \times (5 + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25725 &:= (T(T((5 - 2))) \times ((7 \times 5)^2)) \\ 25726 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + T(7)))) + (-5) + T(T(2))) \\ 25727 &:= (((7^{T(2)}) \times 75) + 2) \\ 25728 &:= ((8 + 2) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25732 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) + (5 + 2)) \\ 25733 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) + (5 + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25734 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(3) \times T((7 + 5)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 25736 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) + (5 + T(T(2)))) \\ 25738 &:= ((T((T(8) + 3)) \times (T(7) + 5)) - 2) \\ 25739 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-3) + T(7)) - T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25752 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(5))) + 2)) \\ 25753 &:= (((-3) - T(T(5))) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(5) - 2)) \\ 25754 &:= (-4) - ((T(5) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) \\ 25755 &:= (T(5) \times (T(((T(5) + T(7)) + T(5))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 25756 &:= ((6 \times (T(5) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25758 &:= ((T((85 + 7)) + T(5)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 25759 &:= (((T(T(9)) - 5) \times T(7)) - T(T((T(5) - T(2)))) \\ 25762 &:= (((T(2) - T(T(6))) \times (7 - T(T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25764 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) \times ((7 - T(T(5))) \times (-T(2)))) \\ 25765 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(6)) - T(7)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25767 &:= ((T((T(7) + T(6))) + (7 - 5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25772 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(7))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - 2) \\ 25773 &:= (T((T(T(3)) - 7)) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 25774 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2))) \\ 25776 &:= (((T(6) + T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)))) + 2) \\ 25777 &:= (((7 \times 7) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)))) + T(2)) \\ 25779 &:= (((9 + T((T(T(7))/7))) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25781 &:= ((T(T(-((1 - 8)))) \times (-7 - T(T(5)))) / (-2)) \\ 25782 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times T(7)) + T(T((5 + T(2)))) \\ 25784 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8) \times T((7 + T(5)))) \times (-T(2)))) \\ 25785 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-8 - T((T(7) + (T(5) \times 2)))) \\ 25788 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(8)) + T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25792 &:= (((2 \times T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times 52) \\ 25794 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T((T(9) + 7))) \times (T(5) + T(2))) \\ 25795 &:= (-5) \times (-T(97) - T(T((5 + 2)))) \\ 25797 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(97)) \times 5) + 2) \\ 25798 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(5))) - 2) \\ 25806 &:= (T(60) + (T(T(8)) \times T((5 + T(2)))) \\ 25815 &:= (-T(5)) \times (1 + (T((T(8) + 5))) \times (-2)) \\ 25816 &:= (((6 + 1) \times T(85)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 25821 &:= (((-1) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(8)))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 25823 &:= ((T(T(3)) - T(T((2 + 8)))) \times (-T(5) + 2)) \\ 25824 &:= (((T(4) \times T(2)) \times T((T(8) + 5))) - T(T(2))) \\ 25825 &:= (-5) + (T((T(T(2)) + 8)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25827 &:= (((T(7) + 2) \times T((T(8) + 5))) - T(2)) \\ 25828 &:= (((T(8) - T(T(2))) \times T((T(8) + 5))) - 2) \\ 25829 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(T(2)) + 8)) - T(T((T(5) - 2)))) \\ 25831 &:= (1 + (T((T(3) + 8)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25832 &:= (((T(T(T(2)))^3) + (T(85))) \times 2) \\ 25833 &:= ((T(3) + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((-8) + T(T(5))) - T(2)) \\ 25834 &:= (4 + (T((T(3) + 8)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25835 &:= (5 + (T((T(3) + 8)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25836 &:= ((T((T(6) - T(3))) + T(T((8 + 5)))) \times T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 25837** := $((-7) \times (-3) - T(85)) + T(T(T(2)))$
25838 := $((T(8) \times T(T(3))) \times T(8)) - (T(52))$
25839 := $((9 \times 3) \times ((8 \times T(T(5))) - T(2)))$
25851 := $((T(T(1+5))) \times (-8) + T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))$
25852 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) - (T(T(5))/T(T(2))))$
25854 := $((4 + (5 \times T((T(8) + (5)))))) \times T(T(2))$
25855 := $(-5) \times (-5) - (T((T(8) + (5))) \times T(T(2))))$
25856 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) + (5)) - T(T(T(2)))$
25862 := $(-T(-((2 - 6)))) - ((8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
25863 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(T(6)) \times (8 - T(T(5)))) + T(2))$
25864 := $(4 \times ((T(T(6)) \times T((-8) + T(5)))) - 2)$
25865 := $((T(T(5)) \times (6 \times T(8))) - T((5 \times 2)))$
25866 := $((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - (T(8) \times T(5))) \times T(T(2))$
25867 := $(-7) - ((T(T(6)) \times (8 - T(T(5)))) - 2)$
25868 := $((8 + T(6)) \times ((T(T(8)) - (5)) + T(T(T(2))))$
25869 := $((T(T(9)) \times ((-6) + T(8)) - (5))) - T(T(2))$
25871 := $(-1) - (((T(7) - T(8))) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
25872 := $((2 \times T(7)) \times T((T(8) - T(5))) \times 2)$
25873 := $(T((T(3) + T(7))) + (8 \times T(T(T(5) - T(2))))$
25874 := $((4 \times T(7)) \times T((T(8) - T(5))) + 2)$
25875 := $((-5) + T((7 + 8))) \times (T(5^2))$
25876 := $((-6) \times (7 + (-T(8)) \times T(T(5)))) - 2)$
25878 := $((T(8) \times (-7) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(5))))/T(T(2))$
25891 := $(19 - ((8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
25892 := $(-((T(-((2 - 9))) + ((-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))))$
25893 := $(-(3 \times 9)) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))$
25894 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) - T(T(8)))) \times T((5 + T(T(2))))$
25896 := $(((-6) + T(9)) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(5) - T(2)))$
25897 := $((7 \times (T(9) + T(85))) - T(2))$
25905 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-5)) - T(T(2)))$
25914 := $((4 \times T((1 + T(9)))) - (5)) \times T(T(2))$
25915 := $(-5) \times ((1 + T(T(9))) \times (-5)) - T(2))$
25917 := $((T(T(7)) - T(19)) \times T(T(5))) - T(2)$
25919 := $((T(9) - 1) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5^2)))$
25921 := $((((-1) - T(2)) + T(9)) + T(T(5)))^2$
25922 := $((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))})/(-9)) \times (-5) + 2)$
25923 := $((T(T(3)) + T(2)) \times 9) \times T(T(5)) + T(2)$
25924 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5^2)))$
25925 := $((5^2) \times (T(9 \times 5)) + 2)$
25926 := $((T(T(6)) + T(2 \times T(9))) - (5)) \times T(T(2))$
25927 := $((T(7) - T(2)) \times T(T(9))) + 52$
25928 := $(8 \times ((T(T(2)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(T(5) - 2))))$
25929 := $((9 \times T(T(2))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5^2)))$
25935 := $((T(5) + (T(3) \times T(9))) \times T(T(5) - 2))$
25938 := $((T(T(8)) \times 39) - T((5 + T(2))))$
25941 := $(T((1 + T(4))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5^2)))$
25942 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (((-4) + T(9)) + T(T(5)))^2))$
25944 := $((4 \times T(((4) + T(9)) + (5))) \times T(T(2))$
25945 := $(-5) \times (((4 + T(T(9))) \times (-5)) + T(T(2)))$
25947 := $(-T(7)) - ((4 + T(T(9))) \times (-5^2))$
25948 := $(-T(8)) + ((T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T((5 + 2))))$
25962 := $(((-2) - T(T(6))) + (T(95))) \times T(T(2))$
25964 := $(-T(4)) - ((T(T(6)) - (T(95))) \times T(T(2)))$
25965 := $((T((T(5) \times 6)) + (T(95))) \times T(2))$
25967 := $(-7) - ((T(T(6)) - (T(95))) \times T(T(2)))$
25968 := $((T(T(8)) \times (-6) + T(9)) - T((5 - 2))$
25974 := $(-T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9 - T((5 \times 2))))$
25977 := $(-7) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9 - T((5 \times 2))))$
25983 := $((3 \times T(8)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5^2)))$
25984 := $((T(T(4)) - ((T(8) - T(9))) \times T(T((5 + 2))))$
25986 := $((T(6) \times 8) + T(9)) \times (T(T(5)) + 2)$
26028 := $(T(8) \times ((T(2)^{06}) - T(T(2))))$
26047 := $(7 \times ((40 + T(6))^2)$
26055 := $(-T(5)) \times (-T(50)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-2))$
26088 := $(8 \times (T(80) + T(T((6/2))))$
26125 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times ((-1) + T(T(6))) - T(T(T(2))))$
26136 := $(6 \times ((3 \times (1 + T(6)))^2)$
26138 := $(T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))) + ((T((1 + 6))^{T(2)}))$
26139 := $(((-T(T(9))) - T((T(T(3)) - 1))) \times (-T(6))) - T(T(2))$
26145 := $((T(T((5 + 4))) + T((-1) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26163 := $(T(3 \times 6)) \times T(((1) + T(6)) - T(2))$
26166 := $(T(6) \times (T(6) + T(((1 + 6)^2)))$
26187 := $(7 \times T((8 + T((1 \times 6) \times 2))))$
26188 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(8)) + 1) + T(T((T(6))/T(T(T(2))))$
26196 := $((T(T(6)) - 9) \times (T(T(-(1 - 6)))) - 2)$
26197 := $(-((T(7) - T(9))) \times (1 + T(T(T((6 - 2))))$
26208 := $((-8) + T(T(T(02)))) \times T((T(6) \times T(2)))$
26223 := $(-((T(T(3)) - ((T(2)^{T(2)}) \times 6^2)))$
26224 := $((T((T(T(4) + T(2))) + 2)) \times 6) - 2)$
26226 := $(6 \times T((2 + T((26/2))))$
26228 := $((T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6))))/T(T(2))$
26229 := $((T((T(9) \times 2) + T(2))) \times 6) + T(2)$
26232 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times (T(2)^6)) - 2))$
26234 := $(-((T(4) - ((3^{T(2)}) \times 6^2)))$
26235 := $((T(53)/T(2)) \times T(T((6 - 2)))$
26237 := $(-7) + (((3^{T(2)}) \times 6^2)$
26238 := $((T(8) \times ((T(3)/2)^6)) - T(T(2))$
26241 := $((((-1) + T(T(4)))^{T(2)})/6) - T(2)$
26242 := $((T((2 \times 4)) \times (T(2)^6)) - 2)$
26243 := $(-((T(T(T(3) + 4))) - ((T(2) \times (T(6)^{T(2)}))))$
26245 := $((54^{T(2)}) + (6))/T(T(2))$

- 26247** := $((T((-7) + (T(4)^2)) \times 6) + T(T(T(2))))$
26262 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((6 \times (T(2)^6) + T(2)))$
26264 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(6) + (T(2) \times (T(6)^{T(2)}))))))$
26265 := $((T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(2)^6) + T(T(T(2))))$
26268 := $((-8) + T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) \times T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2))))))$
26269 := $((T(T(9)) + (6^{T(2)})) \times T(6) - 2$
26271 := $((T(T(1 \times 7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6)) \times T(2)$
26273 := $((3 \times (T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) + 2$
26274 := $((T(4) \times T(72)) - T((6/2)))$
26275 := $(-5) + (T(72) \times T((6 - 2)))$
26279 := $(-((T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(6) - T(T(2))))))$
26292 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(9)) - T(T(2))) \times T((T(6)/T(2)))$
26297 := $(-T(T(7))) + ((-T(9) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))))/(-2))$
26298 := $(T(T(8)) - ((T(92) - 6)) \times T(T(2)))$
26313 := $((-T(3) + T(T((-1) + T(3)))) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(T(2)))$
26319 := $(T(T(9)) + (T((1 + T(3))) \times T((T(6) \times 2)))$
26322 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) - 2)$
26324 := $(-T(4) + (((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)))$
26325 := $(T(5^2)) \times ((3 + 6)^2)$
26327 := $(-7) + (((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)))$
26328 := $((T(8) + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(2))$
26329 := $((92 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) + 2)$
26331 := $((T(T((-1) + T(3))) - T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)$
26332 := $((((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - 2$
26334 := $((T(4) \times 3)^3 - T(6^2))$
26335 := $((-5) + T((-T(3) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(6)) - 2)$
26336 := $((T((T(6) - T(3)) - T(3))) \times T(T(6))) + 2$
26338 := $((-8) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-3) + T(T(6))))/(-2)$
26342 := $-((T((-T(2) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(6) - T(T(2))))))$
26344 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(T(4)) - 3)) \times (-6) \times T(2)))$
26346 := $(6 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 3) - (T(T(6)) - 2)))$
26349 := $((T(94) \times T(3)) - (T(6)^2))$
26352 := $((2 + T((5 \times 3))) \times (6^{T(2)}))$
26353 := $(T(T(3)) + (((T(T(5)) - T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - 2)$
26355 := $(T(5) + (((T(T(5)) - T(3)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(2))))$
26358 := $-((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) - 3) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)))$
26375 := $(-T(5)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-3 + 62))$
26376 := $((T(T((6 + 7))) - T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))$
26382 := $(T(T(2)) \times (8 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(6) - 2)))$
26385 := $((T(T(5)) - (T(8) \times (-3^6))) + T(T(T(2))))$
26388 := $(T(8) \times (-8) + T((36 + 2)))$
26391 := $(19 \times ((T(3) \times T(T(6))) + T(2)))$
26396 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(3))) - T((T(6) - 2))$
26397 := $((T(7) + T(93)) \times 6) + T(2)$
26399 := $((9 - T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(6)) + 2$
26406 := $(T(60) + (4^6) \times T(T(2)))$
26411 := $(11 \times ((T(T(4)) - 6)^2)$
26415 := $(T(5) \times (T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + (T((T(6) + 2))))$
26418 := $((T(8) + 1) \times (T(T(4)) - T(6))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
26424 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) - (-T(T(4))) \times T((T(6) - T(T(2))))))$
26425 := $(T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(6)/T(2))))))$
26432 := $(-(2^{T(3)})) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(62))$
26433 := $((-T(33)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + T(T(2)))$
26439 := $((T(T(9)) - T(3)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) \times 2)$
26442 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((T(4) + T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(2)))$
26444 := $(44 \times (T((T(T(4)) - T(6))) + T(T(2))))$
26445 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \times 4) + T((6 + T(2)))$
26447 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + (4^6)) + T(T(T(2)))$
26448 := $((8 \times T((T((4 + 4)) + T(6)))) \times 2$
26449 := $((T(T(9)) + 4) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) \times 2)$
26454 := $(-T(45)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26455 := $(-5) + ((T(5) \times 4) \times (T(6)^2))$
26456 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(6) + 2)))$
26457 := $((T(7) \times T((5 + 4))) \times T(6)) - T(2)$
26458 := $((T(8) \times T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) - 6)) - 2$
26459 := $(-((T(T(9)) - 5)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26472 := $((2 \times 7) \times T((T(T(4)) + 6))) - 2$
26474 := $((-(4 \times 7)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 6)))/(-2)$
26475 := $(-T(5)) \times (((-T(7)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) + T(T(2)))$
26476 := $((T(6) - 7) \times T((T(T(4)) + 6))) + 2$
26477 := $((T(7) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + 6)) + T(2)$
26478 := $((-8) - T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 6) \times T(2)$
26479 := $(-9) - (-T(7)) \times T((46 - T(2)))$
26481 := $((-T((-1) + T(8))) + T((T(T(4)) + 6))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
26482 := $(-T(T(2))) + (-8) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (-T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26483 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(8))) - T((T(T(4)) - T(6)))) + 2$
26484 := $(-4) + (-8) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (-T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26488 := $((-8) + T(8)) \times T((46 - T(2)))$
26491 := $(T((1 + T(9))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) \times 2)$
26495 := $((5 + 9) \times T((T(T(4)) + 6))) + T(T(T(2)))$
26496 := $((T(T(6)) + T(9)) \times (4 \times (T(6) + T(2))))$
26498 := $((T(8) \times ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(6))) + 2$
26499 := $((T(9) - T(94)) \times (-6)) - T(T(T(2)))$
26502 := $((T(T((-2) + T(05))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)))$
26505 := $((-T(50)) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(6) - 2)$
26523 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(2) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(6) \times 2))))$
26524 := $(-4) \times ((-T(2)) \times T(T((5 + 6))) + 2)$
26526 := $((6 \times 2) \times T(T((5 + 6))) - T(T(2)))$
26529 := $((9 + T(2)) \times T(T((5 + 6))) - T(2))$
26531 := $(-1) - ((T(3) \times T(T((5 + 6)))) \times (-2))$
26532 := $(T(T((2 \times 3) + 5))) \times (6 \times 2)$
26534 := $((4 \times 3) \times T(T((5 + 6))) + 2)$
26535 := $((T(5) - 3) \times T(T((5 + 6))) + T(2))$

$$\begin{aligned} 26537 &:= (-T(7) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-5 \times (T(6) + 2)))) \\ 26538 &:= (((T(8)/3) \times T(T((5+6)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 26561 &:= (-1) - ((6 - T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) + 2)) \\ 26562 &:= (((2 + T(6)) \times 5) \times T(T(6))) - T(2) \\ 26563 &:= (((T(36) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(6)))/T(2)) \\ 26564 &:= (((T(4) - 6)) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - 2) \\ 26565 &:= ((5 \times T(6)) \times T(((5+6) \times 2))) \\ 26567 &:= ((T((T(7) - 6))) \times (5 \times T(6))) + 2 \\ 26568 &:= (T((86 - 5)) \times (6 + 2)) \\ 26569 &:= (((9 \times T(6)) - 5) - T(6))^2 \\ 26572 &:= ((T(2) + T((T(7) + T(5)))) \times T((T(6)/T(2)))) \\ 26573 &:= -(((T(3) + T(T(7))) - ((5 \times 6)^{T(2)})) \\ 26575 &:= (-5) \times ((T((7 + T(5))) \times (-T(6))) - 2) \\ 26583 &:= ((-3) + T(T(8))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-6^{T(2)})) \\ 26586 &:= (((6 \times T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6^2)) \\ 26587 &:= ((T(7) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))) - (T(T(6))^2)) \\ 26588 &:= (T(T(8)) - (((-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times 6) - 2) \\ 26589 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T((T(8) - T(5)))) \times T(6)) + T(2)) \\ 26592 &:= ((T(T((2+9))) + 5) \times (6 \times 2)) \\ 26594 &:= -(((T(T(4)) + 9 \times (T(T(5)) - T(T((6 \times 2)))))) \\ 26595 &:= ((T(59) \times T(5)) + T((6 + T(2)))) \\ 26598 &:= ((-T(8)) + T((T(9) - T(5)))) \times 62 \\ 26614 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(1 + T(6))) + T(T(6))) - T(T(2))) \\ 26624 &:= -(((T(T(4)) + ((-T(2)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))/(-2))) \\ 26625 &:= (-5^{T(2)}) \times ((T(6) - T(T(6))) - T(2)) \\ 26628 &:= ((8 - (T(T(2)) \times (T(6) - T(T(6)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 26638 &:= (((T(T(8))/3) \times T((-6 + T(6))) - 2) \\ 26642 &:= (2 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(66) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 26648 &:= (8 \times (T(4) + T(((T(6) + 6)) \times T(2)))) \\ 26649 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(6)))) - (T(6) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 26652 &:= -(((T(T(2)) + ((-T(5)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))/(-2))) \\ 26655 &:= (T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-6 - 6^{T(2)})) \\ 26656 &:= (T((T(6) - 5)) \times (6 + T((T(6) - 2))) \\ 26657 &:= (((-T(7)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6)))) - T(T((6 + T(2)))) \\ 26658 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 5) + (6^6)/2) \\ 26664 &:= ((T((T(4 + T(6))) - T(T(6))) - (T(6)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 26665 &:= (-5) - (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - (T(6)))/(-2)) \\ 26667 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (-T(6)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-6)) - T(2)) \\ 26681 &:= (((1^8) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))/(-2)) \\ 26682 &:= (T(T(2)) + (T(8) \times T(((6 \times 6) + 2))) \\ 26683 &:= (((3 - 8) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))/(-2)) \\ 26684 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - ((T(8 \times 6)) \times (T(6) + T(2)))) \\ 26685 &:= (T(5) \times (T((T(8) + T(6))) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 26689 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))/(-2)) \\ 26691 &:= ((((-1) + T(T(9))) + 6) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 26694 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T((T(9) + 6))) \times (-T(6))) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26695 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-9 + T(T(6)))) + T(T((6 - 2))) \\ 26697 &:= (((T(7) \times T(9)) \times T(6)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(2)) \\ 26712 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (((-1) + T(T(7))) + T(T(6))) \times 2) \\ 26715 &:= (-T(5) - ((1 - T(T(7))) \times T((T(6)/T(T(2)))))) \\ 26719 &:= (((T(T(9 - 1))) + T(7)) \times T(T(6)))/T(T(2)) \\ 26724 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((2 + T(7))) + T(6))) - T(T(2))) \\ 26726 &:= (((T(T(6))^2) + (T((7 + 6))))/2) \\ 26728 &:= (8 \times ((T((T(2) \times T(7))) - T(T(6))) + 2) \\ 26732 &:= (-2^{T(3)}) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 26733 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((3 \times T(T(7))) + T(T((6 - 2)))) \\ 26734 &:= (((-T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times 2) \\ 26735 &:= (5 \times (T((3 + T(7))) - (-T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 26738 &:= (((-8) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times 2) \\ 26739 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(3) + T(7)))) - 6^2) \\ 26741 &:= ((T((1 + T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T((6 - 2))) \\ 26745 &:= (-5) - (T(4) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T((6 \times 2)))) \\ 26747 &:= (-T(7) + (T(((-4) + T(7))/6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 26748 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(4) + T(7))) + 6/T(2))) \\ 26754 &:= ((T((-4) + T(5))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(6) \times 2) \\ 26755 &:= (-5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-7 - 6^{T(2)})) \\ 26763 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(6))) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-6)) + T(2)) \\ 26764 &:= (T(4) - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6) \times (-2))) \\ 26766 &:= ((6 - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) \times 2) \\ 26768 &:= ((8 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) \times (6 - 2))) \\ 26769 &:= ((T(9) \times T((6 + T(7)))) - T((6/2))) \\ 26772 &:= ((T((2 + 7)) \times T((T(7) + 6))) - T(2)) \\ 26773 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(((T(7) + T(7)) - 6))) - 2) \\ 26774 &:= ((4 + 7) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - 2) \\ 26775 &:= ((T(5) \times T(((7 + 7) \times 6)))/2) \\ 26778 &:= (((T(87) \times 7) - T(6)) + T(2)) \\ 26779 &:= (-((T(9) - T(7))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 26781 &:= ((T((1 + 8)) \times T((T(7) + 6))) + T(T(2))) \\ 26782 &:= (((-2) + T(87)) \times T(6))/T(2) \\ 26783 &:= (-((T(T(3)) - 8)) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 26784 &:= ((4 + T((8 + 7))) \times 6^{T(2)}) \\ 26787 &:= (((7 \times T(87)) - 6) - T(2)) \\ 26788 &:= (-8) + ((T(87) \times T(6))/T(2)) \\ 26814 &:= (41 \times (T(T(8)) - (6 \times 2))) \\ 26817 &:= (7 \times (T((1 + 86)) + T(2))) \\ 26824 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-28) \times T((T(6) \times 2))) \\ 26825 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-8) + T((T(6) \times 2))) \\ 26826 &:= ((6 + T((T(2) + T((-8) + T(6)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 26829 &:= -((T((9 \times 2)) - ((T(8) - 6)^{T(2)})) \\ 26838 &:= (((-8) - T(3)) \times (T(8) - T(62))) \\ 26844 &:= ((T(4) \times ((4 \times T(T(8))) + T(6))) - T(T(2))) \\ 26847 &:= ((T((T(7) + T(4))) \times T(8)) + T((T(6) - T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 26853** := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (-T(8) + T((T(6) \times 2))))$
26856 := $((6^5 + T(8 \times 6)) \times T(2))$
26857 := $((T(7) \times T(T(5))) \times 8) - (T(6) + 2)$
26859 := $((T(T(9)) + (5 + 8)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26864 := $-((T((T(4) + (6))) - ((T(8) - (6))^{T(2)})))$
26865 := $(-T(5)) \times (-T(6) - T((T(8) + T(6)) + 2))$
26872 := $(-(2^7)) + ((T(8) - (6))^{T(2)})$
26873 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(7))) + T(8)) \times T(T(6)) / (-T(2))$
26874 := $(T((T(4) \times 7)) + ((8 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26875 := $(-5) \times (7 - ((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))))$
26878 := $((8 \times T(7)) \times T((T(8) - T(6)))) - 2$
26882 := $((2^8) \times T(8 + 6)) + 2$
26883 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) + (-T(8) \times T(T(6)))) \times (-T(2))$
26884 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-8 + (6^2)))$
26887 := $((T(T(7)) \times (8 \times 8)) + T((T(6) \times 2)))$
26889 := $((T(9) \times T(T(8))) - T(T((8 + 6) - 2)))$
26891 := $-((T((1 + T(9))) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(6) \times (-2))))$
26892 := $((T(T(2)) \times (-9) + (T(8) \times T(6))) \times T(T(2)))$
26895 := $-((T((5 + 9)) - ((T(8) - (6))^{T(2)})))$
26896 := $((T((T(6) - 9)) + (86)^2)$
26898 := $((T(8) \times (-9) + (T(8) \times T(6))) + T(T(2)))$
26922 := $((T(22) + T(T(9))) - (6)) \times T(T(T(2)))$
26923 := $((T(T(T(3))) / (-T(2))) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26924 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26925 := $((5^2) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(6) \times 2)))$
26928 := $(T(8 \times 2)) \times ((T(9) + T(6)) \times T(2))$
26934 := $-((T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) - ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)})))$
26936 := $(T((T(6)/3)) \times 962)$
26937 := $(73 \times (T(T(9)) - T((6^2))))$
26942 := $((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)})$
26943 := $((T(T(3)) - (4) + T(T(9))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
26946 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(9))) - T((T(6) \times T(2))))$
26949 := $((9 + 4) \times ((9 \times T(T(6))) - T(T(2))))$
26952 := $(((-2) + T(5)) \times T(T(9))) + (T(6)) \times 2$
26955 := $(T(5) \times ((T(5) \times T(9 + 6)) - T(2)))$
26957 := $-((T(7) + T(5)) - ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26962 := $(26 \times (T(T(9)) + (6/T(2))))$
26964 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) - T(T(9))) \times (-6^2)$
26965 := $((5 + T(6)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(6 - 2))$
26967 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + T(9))) + T((T(6) - T(2))))$
26971 := $((-1) - T(7)) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)})$
26972 := $((-2) + T(7)) \times T(T(9)) + 62$
26974 := $((T(4) \times T((T(7) + T(9)))) - (6^2))$
26979 := $-((T(T(9)) + (T(T(7)) \times (9 - T(6 \times 2))))$
26982 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(9)) \times T((T(6)/T(2))))$
26985 := $-((T(5) - ((T(8) - T((9 - 6)))^{T(2)})))$
26986 := $((6 + 8) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26987 := $((78 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(6))) / T(2)$
26988 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(8) + 9) + T((T(T(6))/T(2))))$
26991 := $((1 \times 9) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26992 := $(T(T(-(2 - 9))) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26994 := $((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times (T(9) \times 6)) - T(T(2))$
26995 := $(-5) + ((T(9) - ((9 + 6))^{T(2)}))$
26997 := $-((T(-(7 - 9)) - ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
26999 := $((9/9) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
27048 := $((T(T(8)) \times 40) + T(T(7))) + 2$
27065 := $((T(5) \times T(60)) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))$
27069 := $((T(T(9)) - (60)) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
27097 := $(79 \times (07^{T(2)}))$
27125 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(21)) - T((T(7) + T(T(2))))$
27126 := $(T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-1) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2)))$
27132 := $((T(2) \times T(3)) - 1) \times T((T(7) \times 2))$
27135 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3)) - 1)) - (T((T(7) + 2))))$
27147 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((T(4) + 1))) + T((T(7) - 2)))$
27153 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(51) \times (-7))) \times (-T(2)))$
27183 := $((-3) + T(T(8))) \times (-1) + (7 \times T(T(2)))$
27188 := $((T(88) + 1) \times 7) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
27189 := $(T((T(9) + 8)) \times (17 + 2))$
27192 := $(-T((2 + 9)) \times ((-1) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2)))$
27195 := $(-T((5 + 9)) \times ((-1) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
27196 := $((T(6) + T(9) + 1) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2))$
27203 := $((30^{T(2)}) - (T(T(7)) / (-2)))$
27215 := $((-T(T(5))) \times (1 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))$
27216 := $(T(6) \times (T(((1^2) + 7)^2))$
27222 := $(T(T(2)) - (T((T(2))^{T(2)}) \times (-72)))$
27223 := $((3 + (2^{T(T(2))})) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))$
27224 := $((4 \times 2) \times T(((T(2) \times T(7)) - 2)))$
27225 := $((T((5 \times 2))^2) \times (7 + 2))$
27228 := $(T(8) + (T((T(T(T(2)))) / T(T(T(2)))))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2)))$
27231 := $(T(T(T(1 \times 3))) + ((2 + T(7))^{T(2)}))$
27234 := $((T(T(4)) \times 3)^2) + (7 + 2)$
27238 := $((T(8) - T(3))^{T(2)} + (7)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
27241 := $(1 + ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((7 - 2))))$
27242 := $((T(T(2))^4) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) - 2)$
27243 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (((4^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))))$
27244 := $((T(4) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) \times (7^2)$
27245 := $(5 + ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((7 - 2))))$
27246 := $(T(6) - ((T(T(4)))^2) \times (-7 + 2))$
27247 := $((-T(T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-2 \times 7)) + T(2)$
27248 := $(8 \times (T(T((T(4) + 2))) + (T((T(7) - T(2))))))$

- 27249** := $(9 + ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(T((7 - 2)))$
27251 := $((1 - T(T(5))) \times (2 - T((7 \times T(2))))$
27252 := $(((-2) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(2) \times 7))) - T(T(2))$
27253 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (2 + T((T(7) + 2))))$
27254 := $(-4) + ((T(T(5)) - 2) \times T((7 \times T(2))))$
27255 := $-(((T(5) - (T(5^2)) \times T(7))) \times T(2))$
27256 := $((T(T(6)) \times ((5^{T(2)}) - 7)) - 2)$
27257 := $(-7) + ((T(T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(2)))$
27258 := $((8 \times T(5) - 2) \times T((7 \times T(2))))$
27259 := $((((T(9) + T(T(5)))^2) + T(7)) + T(T(2)))$
27264 := $((T(((T(T(4)) \times 6) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(2)))$
27265 := $(-T(5) + (T(T((6 - 2))) \times T((T(7) + T(2))))$
27269 := $((-T((T(9) + T(6)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))) / (-T(T(T(2))))$
27274 := $((T(T(T(4))) / T(7)) \times T((T(2) + T(7)))) - T(T(2))$
27275 := $(-5) + (T((T(7) + T(2))) \times T((7 + T(2))))$
27277 := $((T(T((T(7)/7))) \times T((T(2) + T(7)))) - T(2))$
27278 := $-((T((T(8) + 7)) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(7))^2))$
27279 := $(9 \times (T(T(7)) - ((T(2) - T(72))))$
27293 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(9)/T(2)))) - (T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(2)))$
27294 := $((((4 \times T(T(9))) + T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2)))$
27295 := $(-5) + (T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((7 + T(T(2))))))$
27297 := $((T(7) \times T(T(9))) - (T((T(T(T(T(2))))/7)) \times T(2)))$
27301 := $((T(10) \times T((3 + T(7)))) + T(T(T(2))))$
27312 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((-1) + T(3)))) - ((T(T(7)) + 2)))$
27314 := $((T(T(4)) \times (1 + T((3 + T(7)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
27316 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T((-1) + T(3)))) - ((T(T(7)) - 2)))$
27322 := $((2^{T(T(2))}) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) - T(T(2))$
27324 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) - T(2))))))$
27325 := $((T(5) \times 2^3) + T((T(7) - T(2))))$
27328 := $((8^2) \times (T((T(T(3)) + 7))) + T(T(T(2))))$
27329 := $((9 \times T(T((2 \times T(3)))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))))$
27334 := $((4^3) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(2))$
27335 := $((5 + T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) + 7^2)))$
27336 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T((3 \times 3)))) \times (-T(7) - T(T(2))))$
27339 := $((T(9) - T(3)) \times (T(37) - 2))$
27341 := $(-1) + (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) - 7) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27342 := $((T(T(2))^4) + (T(3))) \times (7 \times T(2))$
27343 := $((3 \times T(4))^3) + (7^{T(2)})$
27345 := $((T(5) \times T((T(4) \times T(3)))) - (T((7 \times 2))))$
27346 := $(T(T(6)) - (T(T(4)) \times (3 - T((T(7) + T(2))))))$
27349 := $((9 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))$
27352 := $(((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T((T(7) - T(2))))$
27355 := $(-5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((3 \times 7)) - T(2)))$
27356 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(3))) - (7^{T(2)})$
27359 := $((T(95) \times T(3)) - 7) + T(T(2))$
27375 := $((T(5) \times 73) \times (T(7) - T(2)))$
27377 := $((T(T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(3) + T(7))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
27378 := $(T(((8 + 7) - 3)) \times T((T(7) - 2)))$
27379 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times ((3 \times 7) - 2))$
27384 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(8) \times (-3))) \times T(7)) \times T(T(2))$
27388 := $((T(88) - 3) \times 7) - T(2)$
27391 := $((1 + T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) \times T((7 + T(T(2))))$
27394 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(9)) \times (3 - T(7)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
27395 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T((9 - 3)))) - T((T(7) - T(2))))$
27396 := $(((-6) + T(9)) \times T(37)) - T(T(T(2)))$
27399 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(7) - 2)))$
27412 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times T((4 + (T(7) \times T(2))))$
27418 := $((T((8 \times (1 + T(4)))) \times 7) + T(T(2)))$
27419 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T((1 \times 4)))) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(2)))$
27423 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((-2) + T(T(4)))) - T(72))$
27425 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(4)))) - (T(7) - T(2)))$
27426 := $(T(6) \times ((T(2)^4) + T(7^2)))$
27427 := $((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) + T(2))))$
27432 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T((T(4) + T(7)))) \times T(T(2))))$
27433 := $(((-T(33)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))$
27434 := $(T(43) \times ((4 + T(7)) - T(2)))$
27435 := $(T((5 \times T(3))) \times (T(4) + (7^2)))$
27437 := $((T(73) \times T(4)) + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2))))$
27438 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(4) + T(7)))) + T(T(2)))$
27442 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((-4) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(7)) - 2)))$
27443 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((-4) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(2))))$
27445 := $(5 \times (-T(T(4)) + ((-4) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
27446 := $((T(6) \times T((-4) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))))$
27447 := $(7 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))))))$
27448 := $(8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(7) - 2))))$
27449 := $((9 \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(4)) - 7) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
27462 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T((6 + T(T(4)))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
27463 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7) - 2))$
27465 := $((T(5) \times T((6 \times T(4)))) + T((7 - 2)))$
27468 := $-((T(8) \times (T(6) - ((4 \times 7)^2)))$
27469 := $((9 \times T(6)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) + T(2))))$
27472 := $((-2) + T(T(7))) \times (-4 - 72))$
27476 := $((-67) \times (-4 - T(T(7)))) + T(T(2))$
27482 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8)) \times (T((-4) + T(7)) + 2))$
27483 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T(8) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times 2))))$
27486 := $((T(T(6)) \times ((T(8) + T(T(4))) + T(7))) - T(2))$
27488 := $((T(88) + T(4)) \times 7) + T(T(2))$
27489 := $((T(98) \times (T(4) + 7)) / T(2))$
27492 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T((9 + 4)) + T(7))) + T(2))$
27494 := $((T(T(4)) \times (94 + T(T(7)))) - T(T(2)))$
27495 := $(-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(9)) + ((T(4) \times T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27496 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T((9 - 4)))) + 7) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
27498 := $(T(T(8)) - (-((T(94) + 7))) \times T(T(2)))$

- 27506** := ((T(60) × T(5)) + (T(7) × 2))
27516 := (((T(T(6)) - 1) × T(T(5))) - ((T(7) × T(2))))
27517 := (T(7) + ((-1) + T(T(5))) × T((7 × T(2))))
27522 := (((T(T(T(2)))) - 2) × T(T(5))) + (7 × T(T(2))))
27523 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(2) + T(T(5)))) + (T((T(7) + T(2))))
27524 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((2⁵) × T(T(7))) × (-2))
27525 := ((T((T(T(5))/2)) + 5) × T((7 - 2)))
27528 := (((T(8) + 2) × T(T(5))) + T(7)) × T(T(2))
27529 := ((9 × ((T(T(T(2)))) × T(5) - (T(T(7)))) - 2)
27534 := ((4 × (T(3)⁵)) - T((T(7) × T(2))))
27544 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(-((5 - 7)))))) × T(T(T(2))))
27545 := -(((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) × T((7 × T(2))))
27546 := (((6 × (T(T(T(4))) - 5) - (T(7))) × T(2))
27552 := (((T(2) + T(5 × 5)) × T(7)) × T(2))
27553 := (-3) + (((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(7)))²)
27555 := (55 × (5 + T((T(7) + T(2))))
27556 := (((T(6) + 5) + (5 × T(7)))²)
27558 := -((T(T(8)) - ((T((T(5)/5) × T(7)))²))
27563 := (((-3) + T(T(6))) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(7)) / (-2))
27564 := (-4) × (((T(T(6)) + T(5)) × (-T(7)) - T(2))
27565 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (5 × (T(7) + T(2))))
27566 := ((T(T(6)) × (T((T(6) + 5))) + (7)) / T(2))
27567 := (-((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) × T(T(5)))) + T((T(7) - T(T(2))))
27568 := ((T(T(8)) + T((-T(6) + T(T(5)))) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))
27573 := ((T(T(3)) × (-7)) + (T(T(5)) × T((7 × T(2))))
27574 := (((-T(4)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(5))) × (-7) - T(T(2))
27576 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(7))) - T(T((T(5) - (7)))) × (-T(2))
27579 := (T(T(9)) - (-T(7)) × (T((T(5) + T(7)) + 2))
27582 := ((T(2)⁸) + (T(-((T(5) - T(7))) × T(T(T(2))))
27585 := (-T(5)) - (8 × (T(T(5)) - T((T(7) × T(2))))
27586 := (((T(T(6)) - T(8)) × T(T(5))) + T(T((7 + T(T(2))))
27587 := ((T(T(7)) × ((8 × 5) + T(7))) - T(T(T(2))))
27588 := ((8 + T(8)) × (T((5 × 7) - T(2)))
27592 := ((2 + T(9)) × T(T(5))) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))
27594 := (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) × T((-5) + T(7))) - T(T(2))
27595 := (-5) - ((T(T(9)) / (-T(5))) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(2))))
27615 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T((1 × 6)))) - (T(7 × 2)))
27616 := (T(61) + (T(6) × T((7²)))
27622 := -((T((T(T(T(2)))) / T(2)) - (((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))))²))
27625 := ((T((T(5) - 2) - 6) × T((T(7) - T(2))))
27628 := (((T(8)²) × T(6)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2))
27629 := ((T((T(9) / T(2))) × T(T(6))) - T((7 + T(T(2))))
27635 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T((6 + 7) - T(T(2))))
27636 := (((T(6)³) - T(6)) - T(7)) × T(2)
27638 := (((T(8) × T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) × T(7)) + 2
27639 := (9 × (T(T(T(3) + 6))) - (7 + T(2)))
27642 := -((T((2 + T(4))) - (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27643 := (((T(3)⁴) × T(6)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))
27644 := ((T(T(4)) × (T((T(4) + T(6))) + (7))) - T(T(T(2))))
27645 := (T(5) × ((T((T(4) × 6) + 7) + T(T(2))))
27648 := -((T(8) × ((T(4) + 6) - (T(7)²)))
27652 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(5))) - ((6 + T(7)) × 2))
27654 := (-T(4)) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (T(7) × 2))
27655 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) + T((7 + T(2))))
27656 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) - (67 - T(2)))
27657 := (-7) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (T(7) × 2))
27658 := (-T(8)) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (T(7) - 2))
27664 := ((T(T(4)) + T(6)) × (T(6) + (7^{T(2)})))
27665 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (6 + (7²)))
27669 := (-((T(9) + 6)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27672 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(7) + T(67)) × 2))
27675 := ((T(T(5 + 7)) - 6) × (7 + 2))
27677 := (((T(T(7)) + 7) × 67) + T(T(2)))
27678 := ((T(T(8)) - 7) × ((T(6) - 7) × T(2)))
27682 := ((-2) - T(8)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27683 := (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T((-8) + T(6)))) × (-7)) - 2)
27685 := (-((T(T(5 + 8)) - T(T(6))) × (-T(7) + T(T(T(2))))
27686 := (((T(T(6)) × T((T(8) - T(6)))) - T(7)) - T(T(2)))
27689 := ((T(9) × T(T(8))) - (T(67) + T(2)))
27692 := -((T(-((2 - 9)) - (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27693 := (-((3 × 9) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27694 := ((T(T(-((4 - 9))) × T(T(6))) - (T(7) - 2))
27695 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(T((9 - 6)))) - (T(7) - T(2))
27696 := ((T(6) - T(9)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((7 - 2))))
27698 := (((T(T(8)) × T(9)) - (T(67))) + T(T(2)))
27699 := ((9 × (T(T(9)) - 6)) - T(7)) × T(2)
27705 := (-T(50)) + (T(7) × T(T((7 + 2))))
27714 := ((T(T((4 + 1))) × T((-7) + T(7))) - T(T(2)))
27715 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(-((1 - 7)))) - (7 - 2))
27718 := ((T((8 + T(1 + 7))) × T(7)) - 2)
27719 := (((T((T(9) - 1)) × T(7)) - 7) + T(T(2)))
27732 := (T(T(2)) × ((3 × T(T(T((T(7) / 7)))) + 2))
27734 := (((T(T(4)) + 3) × T(T(7))) + T(T((7 + T(T(2))))
27735 := ((T(T(5)) × T((3 × 7))) + T((7 - 2)))
27741 := ((T(T((1 + 4))) × T((-7) + T(7))) + T(T(T(2))))
27744 := ((4 × (T(47) + T(7))) × T(T(2)))
27745 := (-5) - (-T(4) × T((77 - T(2))))
27746 := (((-((T(6)⁴) + T(T(7))) / (-7)) + T(T(T(2))))
27747 := ((T(74) × T((T(7) / 7))) - T(2))
27748 := -((T(T(8)) + (((-T(4)) × T(T(7))) × 7) + T(T(2))))
27752 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(5))) + ((T(7) + 7) - T(2)))
27753 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(5))) + (T(7) + (7 - 2)))
27754 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) × T((-7) + T(7)))) - T(T(T(2))))

27755 := ((-5) × (T(5) - T(7))) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2))))
27756 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) + T((-7) + T((7 - 2))))
27757 := (T(7) - (T(T(5 + 7))) × (-7 + 2))
27758 := (T(8) + ((T(T(5)) × T((-7) + T(7))) + 2))
27759 := ((9 × T(T(5 + 7))) + (T(7) + 2))
27762 := ((T(T((T(2) + (6)))) × T(7)) - (T(T(7)) × T(2)))
27764 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T((6 + 7))) × (-7) - 2))
27765 := (T(5) × (T(6) + T((T((7/7)) × T(T(2)))))
27768 := (((T(8) + T(T((6 + 7)))) + T(T(7))) × T(T(2)))
27773 := ((T((3 + T(7))) × (T(7) + T(7))) - T(2))
27774 := (-((T(4) - T(7))) × (T(T(T((7/7)))) + T(2)))
27775 := ((T(T(5)) × T((-7) + T(7))) + T((7 + T(2))))
27776 := ((T((6 × 7)) - 7) × (T(7) + T(2)))
27778 := (((T(8) + T(7)) × (T(7) + T(T(7)))) + 2)
27782 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(8))) - T(7)) × 7) + T(T(2)))
27783 := -(((T(3) - 87) × 7^{T(2)}))
27786 := (-6) + (T(8) × 772)
27788 := ((T(T(8)) + (T((T(8) + T(7))) × (-7))) × (-2))
27792 := ((T(T((T(2) + 9))) + 7) × (7 + 2))
27794 := ((T(4) × T((T(9) + T(7)))) + (T(7)²))
27795 := (T(5) × (((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2))))
27797 := ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) × (T(7) + ((7²)))
27798 := (T(T(8)) - (-((T(9) - T(7))) × T((T(7) × 2))))
27804 := (((-4) + T(T(08))) × 7) × T(T(2))
27816 := (61 × (T((T(8) - 7)) + T(T(T(2))))
27817 := -((T(T(7)) - (-1) + (T(8) × (T(7)²))))
27818 := -((T(T((8 - 1))) - (T(8) × (T(7)²))))
27822 := ((T(T(T(2))) × ((2 × T(T(8))) - 7)) - T(2))
27823 := ((T(T(3)) × ((2 × T(T(8))) - 7)) - 2)
27825 := (T(5) × (T(T(2)) + ((T(8) + 7)²)))
27828 := -((T(8) × ((T(2) + 8) - (T(7)²)))
27829 := (T(T(9)) + ((T((T(2) + 8)) × T(T(7))) - 2))
27831 := (((1 - T(T(T(3)))) × (-T((8 + 7)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
27832 := (((T(T(T(2))) × (-3) + T(T(8)))) - 7) × 2)
27834 := (((4³) × T((T(8) - 7))) - T(T(2)))
27838 := (-8) - (((-3) + T(T(8))) × (-7) × T(T(2)))
27842 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(8))) - (T(7)))/(-2))
27843 := (((T(3) × (T(T(T(4))) + 8)) - 7) × T(2))
27844 := (4 × ((T(4) × (T(T(8)) + T(7))) + T(T(T(2))))
27845 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(4)) - 8) × T((T(7) + T(T(2)))))
27846 := (T(6) × T((T(4) - 8 - 7²)))
27848 := (8 × ((T(T((4 + 8))) + T(T(7))) - T(T(2))))
27849 := ((9 × T(T((4 + 8)))) + T(T((7 - 2)))
27851 := ((-1) - T(T(5))) + ((T(T(8)) × 7) × T(T(2)))
27852 := (((-T(2)) × T((T(5) + T(8)))) × (-7)) + T(T(2))
27853 := (((T(T(3)) × T((T(5) + T(8)))) + T(7)) - T(T(T(2))))

27854 := (((T(T(4)) + (T(5))) × (-8) + T(T(7))) - T(T(2)))
27855 := (T(T(5)) + (T(5) × ((T(8) + 7)²)))
27856 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) + T(((T(8) - T(7)) × 2)))
27858 := ((T(T(8)) × (5 × 8)) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(2))))
27861 := (((-1) - T(T(6))) × (-T((8 + 7)))) + T(T(T(2)))
27862 := (2 × ((T(6) × T(T(8))) - T((7 + T(2))))
27865 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) + (T((T(8) - 7))/T(2)))
27867 := (((7 × 6) × T(T(8))) - (T(7 × 2)))
27871 := (-1) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) × (-T(7) - 2))
27872 := ((T(T(2)) + 7) × ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) × 2))
27874 := ((T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) × 8) - (7 × 2))
27876 := (((T(T(6))/7) + T(8)) × (T(T(7)) - 2))
27882 := (((T(T(2)) + T((8 + T(8)))) × T(7)) - T(T(2)))
27884 := ((-T(4) - T(T(8))) - (-8 × T((T(7) × T(2))))
27885 := (((T(T(5)) × 8) + T(8)) × T(7)) - T(2))
27886 := (((T(6) × T(T(8))) - (T(8) + 7)) × 2)
27887 := ((-7) - T(T(8))) - (-8 × T((T(7) × T(2))))
27888 := (8 × T(((88 - 7) + 2)))
27894 := (-T((4 × 9))) - (-8 × T((T(7) × T(2))))
27898 := ((T(T(8))/(-9)) + ((T(T(8)) × 7) × T(T(2))))
27915 := (-T(5)) - ((T(19) × (-7)) × T(T(T(2))))
27916 := (((T(6) × T(T(-((1 - 9)))) - (T(7)) × 2)
27917 := ((T(7) × (-1) + T(T(9))) - T(T((7 + 2))))
27919 := (T(T(9)) + ((-1) + T(T(9))) × (T(7) - 2))
27923 := (((3^{T(2)}) × T(T(9))) - T(7)) + T(T(2))
27924 := (T((T(4) + 2)) × ((-T(9)) + T(T(7))) - T(2))
27927 := (((7 × T(T(T(2)))) × T((-9) + T(7))) - T(2))
27928 := (((T(T(8)) - 2) × 9) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})))
27932 := (((T(2)³) × T(T(9))) - 7) - T(T(2))
27933 := ((T(3) × T((T(3) × (9 + 7)))) - T(2))
27935 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) - (9 + 7)) + T(T(T(T(2))))
27936 := (6 × T((3 × ((9 + 7) × 2)))
27937 := ((7 + T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) × T((7 + T(T(2))))
27938 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - (T(9) - T(7))) × 2)
27939 := ((T(T(9)) × (3^{T(9-7)})) - T(T(2)))
27942 := (((T(2) × T(T(T(4)))) + (9 + T(7))) × T(T(2)))
27944 := ((4 - (T(T(4)) × (-9))) × (T(7) × 2))
27945 := (T(T((5 + 4))) × (T((9 - 7)^{T(2)})))
27948 := -((T(T((T(8)/4))) + ((T(T(9)) × (-T(7))) - T(2)))
27949 := ((T(T(9)) + 4) + (T(T(9)) × (T(7) - 2)))
27951 := ((1 + T(T(5))) × T((-9) + T(7) + 2))
27953 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(5) - T((9 + 7)))) + 2)
27954 := (-((4⁵) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(7))) + 2))
27955 := (-5) + (-T(T(5))) × (-((9 - 7) - T(T(T(T(2)))))
27957 := -((T((T(7) + 5))) - (T(97) × T(T(2))))
27958 := (((T(T(8)) × T((T(5) - 9))) - 7) × 2)

$$\begin{aligned}
 27963 &:= (3 \times (6 - (T(T(9)) \times (-7 + 2)))) \\
 27965 &:= ((56 - 9) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) \\
 27966 &:= ((T(6) \times T((6 + T(9)))) + T(T(7 - 2))) \\
 27968 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) - (9 - 7)) \times 2) \\
 27969 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (T(6))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(7))) - T(2))) \\
 27971 &:= (((-1) + T(7)) \times T(T(9))) + (T(7) - 2) \\
 27972 &:= (((T(27) - T(9)) \times T(7)) \times T(2)) \\
 27975 &:= (((T(T(5) - 7)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(7))) + T(2) \\
 27978 &:= ((T((87 + 9)) + 7) \times T(T(2))) \\
 27979 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) - T(T(9))) + T(7)) + T(T(2))) \\
 27984 &:= (-4) \times (((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times 7) - T(2)) \\
 27985 &:= (T(5) - (((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times T(7)) + 2)) \\
 27986 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(89) - 7)) / T(2)) \\
 27987 &:= ((T(7) \times (-T(8) + T(T(9)))) + T((7 - 2))) \\
 27988 &:= -((T((8 + T(8))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(7))) + 2)) \\
 27991 &:= (T((1 + T(9))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(7) - 2))) \\
 27992 &:= (-T((-2) + T(9))) - (-T((T(9) + 7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\
 27993 &:= (T((-3) + T(9)) \times (T(9) - (7 \times 2))) \\
 27994 &:= (((-T(4) - T(9)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(2))) \\
 27996 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(9)) - T(T(9))) - T(7)) \times T(2) \\
 27999 &:= (9 \times (((-9) - T(T(9))) + 7) \times (-T(2))) \\
 28014 &:= ((T((-4) + T(10)) + 8) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28032 &:= (2 \times (30 + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28035 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(3))) + T(08)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28062 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + (T((60 + T(8)))) \times T(T(2))) \\
 28098 &:= ((T(8) + 90) \times (-8 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28119 &:= ((T(9) \times T((-1) + T((1 \times 8)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28124 &:= ((T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-1) - T(T(8)))) \times 2) \\
 28144 &:= (-4) \times (((-T(4)) \times T((1 + T(8)))) - T(T(2))) \\
 28145 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times ((1 \times 8)^{T(2)})) \\
 28146 &:= (-T(6)) - (41 \times (-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28147 &:= (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-18)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28149 &:= ((T(9) \times (-4) + T((-1) + T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28152 &:= ((T(T(T(2)) \times (T(5) + 1)) + T(8)) \times T(T(2))) \\
 28153 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) - 1)) + (T(T(8)) - 2)) \\
 28154 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5 + 1)) - T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28155 &:= (-5) - (T(T(5 - 1)) \times (-8^{T(2)})) \\
 28156 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + 1) + T((8 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28166 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-61)) + 8) \times (-2)) \\
 28167 &:= (((7 \times 6) - 1) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
 28175 &:= ((-5) + T(7)) \times ((-1) + T(8)^2) \\
 28176 &:= (((T(6) \times T(7)) - 1) \times 8) \times T(T(2)) \\
 28179 &:= -((T(9) - ((T((7 - 1)) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28182 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times ((-1) + T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) \\
 28185 &:= (T(5) \times (T((T(8) + 1)) + T((8 \times T(T(2)))))) \\
 28188 &:= ((8 \times T(T(8))) - T((-1) + T(8))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 28198 &:= ((-8) - T(T(9))) + (T(18)^2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28203 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((0 - T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(8)) \times (-2))) \\
 28212 &:= ((T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8)))) \times 2) \\
 28214 &:= (-T(4)) + ((T(T((1 + 2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28215 &:= ((T(T(5 - 1))) \times T(2)) \times T((T(8) / 2)) \\
 28217 &:= (-7) + ((T(T((1 + 2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28218 &:= (((T((8 - 1))^2) \times T(8)) - T(T(2))) \\
 28221 &:= (((T((1 + T(T(2))))^2) \times T(8)) - T(2)) \\
 28222 &:= (-2) + ((T(T(2)) \times 28)^2) \\
 28223 &:= (-((3 - 2) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28225 &:= ((-5) + T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28226 &:= (((T(T(6) / T(2)))^2) \times T(8)) + 2) \\
 28227 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T((T(2)^{T(2)}))) \times T(8)) + T(2)) \\
 28228 &:= ((8 \times T(T(T(2))))^2) + (8 / 2) \\
 28231 &:= (1 + T(3)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28232 &:= (2^3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28233 &:= (3 \times 3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) \\
 28234 &:= (T(4) + ((T(3) \times 28)^2)) \\
 28235 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(2) + (8^{T(2)}))) \\
 28236 &:= ((-6) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(8)))) \times (-2)) \\
 28237 &:= (((T(7) \times T(3))^2) - 8) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 28238 &:= (((8 \times T(T(3)))^2) + 8) + T(T(2)) \\
 28239 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T((T(T(3)) / T(2)))) - T((T(8) + 2))) \\
 28242 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(42) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)))) \\
 28243 &:= ((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times (-2) + T((T(8) - T(T(2)))))) \\
 28244 &:= ((T(4) + T(4)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28245 &:= (((5 \times T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T((8 + T(T(2)))) \\
 28248 &:= (8 \times (T(42) + T((T(8) \times 2)))) \\
 28249 &:= ((T(9) - 4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) + 2))) \\
 28251 &:= ((T((-1) + T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)))) \\
 28252 &:= (T((2 + 5)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28253 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (8^{T(2)})) \\
 28254 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(8) - 2)) \\
 28255 &:= (-5) + (T(5) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28257 &:= ((T(7) + 5) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28258 &:= ((T(8) \times (5 + T((T(2) + T(8)))) - 2) \\
 28259 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((5 + T(2)) \times T(82))) \\
 28266 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((T(6) / T(2))) - T(T(8))) \times 2) \\
 28269 &:= (T(9) + (((6 \times 28)^2)) \\
 28271 &:= (-1) + (-T((T(7) + T(2))) \times (-T(8) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28272 &:= (T((T(2) + T(7))) \times (2 + T((8 + 2)))) \\
 28273 &:= ((T(T(3)) + T(7)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2)) \\
 28274 &:= (-((T(T(4)) + (T((T(7) \times T(2))) \times (-8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 28275 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-T((7^2)) - T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) \\
 28278 &:= (((T(8) - T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times (-8)) + T(T(2))) \\
 28279 &:= ((T(T(9)) + T(7)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(8)^2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28284 &:= ((T((4 \times 8)) + T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 28287 &:= ((7 - ((T(T(8)) \times (-2)) - 8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28288 &:= ((8 - (T(8) \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T((8 \times 2))) \\ 28314 &:= ((T(41) - 3) \times (T(8) - T(2))) \\ 28315 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(1 \times 3)))) + T((T(8) - 2))) \\ 28321 &:= ((1 + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28324 &:= ((T(4)^2) + ((T(T(3)) \times 8)^2)) \\ 28325 &:= (T((5 \times 2)) \times (3 + (8^{T(2)}))) \\ 28326 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) - T((T(8) + T(2)))) \\ 28329 &:= (((T(9)^2) \times (T(3) + 8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28334 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(3) + T(T(8)))) \times 2) \\ 28335 &:= ((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) + (((T(T(3)) \times 8)^2)) \\ 28337 &:= (-T(T(7))) - (T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times (8 - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28342 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((-T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - 2) \\ 28343 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) - 3))) - T((T(8) - 2))) \\ 28344 &:= ((4 - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8))) \times 2) \\ 28345 &:= ((5^4) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((8 - T(2)))))) \\ 28346 &:= (T(6) - (T(T(4)) \times (-3) - (8^{T(2)}))) \\ 28354 &:= ((T(4) + T(T(5))) + ((T(T(3)) \times 8)^2)) \\ 28356 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + 3)) - T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28357 &:= (T(T(7)) - ((-T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((8 - 2)))) \\ 28358 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(5))) \times T(T(3))) + (8^{T(2)})) \\ 28359 &:= ((9 \times T(5)) + ((T(T(3)) \times 8)^2)) \\ 28364 &:= ((-T(4) + T(63)) \times (-8) - T(T(2))) \\ 28365 &:= (T((5 \times 6)) \times (-3 - (8^2))) \\ 28368 &:= (((T((8 \times 6)) + T(3)) \times 8) \times T(2)) \\ 28372 &:= ((T(2) + (7^3)) \times 82) \\ 28374 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(7))) + 3) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 28378 &:= ((T((T(8) + 7)) \times (-T(3) - T(8))) - 2) \\ 28379 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) - T(3)) - T((T(8) - 2))) \\ 28383 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - (-T(8) \times (T(3 + T(8)) + 2))) \\ 28386 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(-((3 - 8))))^2)) \\ 28389 &:= ((9 \times T(T(T(8)/3))) + (T(T(8)) - T(T(2)))) \\ 28392 &:= (T((T(2) + T(9))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(8)^2))) \\ 28395 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(9) \times (T(3) + T(8))) + T(2))) \\ 28397 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(3)))) + (8 - T(2))) \\ 28398 &:= ((8 + (T(9) \times T((T(3) + 8)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 28413 &:= ((3 + T(T(1 + 4))) \times T(T(8 - 2))) \\ 28419 &:= ((9 \times T((1 + T(4 + 8)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28422 &:= (T(2) \times (((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(8)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 28424 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(4) + T(T(8)/T(2)))) \\ 28425 &:= (((T(5) - 2)^4) - T((8 \times 2))) \\ 28426 &:= ((T(6) \times T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (8^{T(2)})) \\ 28427 &:= ((T(7) \times ((2^{T(4)} - 8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28428 &:= (T(8) - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(4) + T(T(8))) \times (-2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28429 &:= (((9^2) \times T(-((T(4) - T(8)))) - 2) \\ 28432 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (8 \times 2)) \\ 28435 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 28438 &:= (((T((T(8) + 3)) + T(4)) \times T(8)) - 2) \\ 28444 &:= (4 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(48) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 28446 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(4) + 8))) \times (-T(2)))) \\ 28448 &:= ((8 + T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times (8 \times 2)) \\ 28449 &:= (9 \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))) + T((8 \times 2)))) \\ 28455 &:= (T(5) \times (T(((T(5) + T(4)) + T(8))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 28458 &:= (((T(8) + 5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(8)/2)) \\ 28462 &:= ((-2) + T(6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(8) + T(T(2)))) \\ 28464 &:= ((4 \times 6) \times (T(4) + T((8 \times T(T(2)))))) \\ 28465 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + 4) + T((T(8) + 2))) \\ 28466 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(6))) \times (-4) + T(T(8)))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28473 &:= (-T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(7) + 4) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 28476 &:= (-6) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(48)) \times (-T(2))) \\ 28477 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (7 \times T(4))) + T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28479 &:= ((T(T(9)) - (7 \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(8))) \times (-T(2))) \\ 28482 &:= ((T(-((T(2) - T(8)))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 28483 &:= (((T(T(3)) - 8)^4) - T((T(8)/T(2)))) \\ 28484 &:= ((-T(T(4)) - (T(84) \times 8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28485 &:= (T(5) \times (8 + T((T(T(4)) + (8 - 2)))) \\ 28486 &:= (-6) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))/T(8)) + 2) \\ 28487 &:= (((-T(7)) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)))/(-T(8)) - T(2) \\ 28488 &:= ((8 \times T(84)) - (T(8) \times 2)) \\ 28494 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) + 8)/2) \\ 28495 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times T(4)) - (8 - T(2))) \\ 28497 &:= (7 \times (T((9 \times T(4))) - (8 \times T(2)))) \\ 28499 &:= (((-T(9) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 28512 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (1 + T(5))) \times (T(8)^2)) \\ 28514 &:= (-4) - (T((T((-1) + T(5)) - 8)) \times (-T(T(2)))) \\ 28516 &:= ((6 \times T((T((-1) + T(5)) - 8)) - 2) \\ 28518 &:= (T((-8) + T((1 + 5) + 8))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 28522 &:= (((-T(T(2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)))) + 82) \\ 28524 &:= (4 \times (((T(T(2))^5) - T(T(8))) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 28527 &:= (((7 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(8) - T(2))) \\ 28528 &:= (8 \times ((-T(T(2))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) + 2) \\ 28533 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(5)))) + T(T((8 - T(2)))) \\ 28536 &:= (((T(T(6)) - 3) + T(T(5))) \times 82) \\ 28537 &:= ((T((T(7) + 3)) \times 58) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 28538 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(3))) - 5) \times (T(8) + 2)) \\ 28539 &:= ((9 \times T(T(3))) \times (T(5) + T((8 \times 2)))) \\ 28542 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (4 + T((T(5) + (82)))) \\ 28544 &:= ((4 + 4) \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) - 2)) \\ 28545 &:= ((-T(5) - (T((4 \times 5)) \times T((8 \times 2)))) \\ 28546 &:= (((T(T(6)) - 4^5) \times (-T(8))) - 2) \\ 28548 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T((-4) + T(5))) \times (T(8) + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 28552** := $((T((2+5)) + T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) - 2))$
28553 := $-((T(T(T(3)))) + (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) - 8) \times (-2)))$
28554 := $((T((4 \times T(T((5)/5)))) \times 8) - T(T(2)))$
28555 := $(-5) - (T((5 + T(5))) \times (-T((8 \times 2))))$
28556 := $((T(T(6)) + 5) \times (-T(5) - T((8 \times 2))))$
28557 := $((T(((T(7) \times T(5))/5)) \times 8) - T(2))$
28561 := $((T((1+6)) - T(5))^{8/2})$
28562 := $((2+6) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) + 2$
28563 := $(-3) + ((T((6 \times T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)))$
28566 := $(6 \times ((T(6) \times 5) - T(8))^2)$
28567 := $(7 \times ((T((6 \times T(5))) - 8) - T(T(2))))$
28568 := $(8 \times (T(T(6)) - (-5) \times (T(T(8)) + 2)))$
28569 := $((9 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T((8 - 2)))$
28572 := $((2^{7+5}) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))$
28573 := $((-3) \times T(T(7))) + (((-5) + T(8))^{T(2)})$
28574 := $((T(4) \times (T(75) + 8)) - T(T(2)))$
28575 := $((T(T(5)) + 7) \times T(5)) \times T((8 - T(2)))$
28576 := $((T(T(6)) + 7) \times T(T(5))) + (8 \times 2)$
28581 := $((-1) + T(8)) + T((T(5) + T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
28582 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((8+5)^{8/2}))$
28583 := $(T(T(3)) - ((-8) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) - 2)$
28584 := $((T(48) + T(5)) \times 8) \times T(2)$
28586 := $((T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(5)))) - 8) \times 2$
28587 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) - (T(5))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
28589 := $(T(9) + (8 \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) - 2)))$
28594 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-5)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)))$
28599 := $((T(T(9)) - T((T(9) + T(5)))) \times (-T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))$
28615 := $((T(T(5)) + 1) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(8)) - 2$
28617 := $((T(7) + T(-((1 - 6)))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))$
28623 := $((T(T(3+2))) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(8) + T(T(2))))$
28625 := $(-5^{T(2)}) \times ((T(6) + T(T(8)))/(-T(2)))$
28626 := $(T((6 \times 2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T((8 \times 2))))$
28627 := $(T(T(7)) - (T(2) - ((T(6) \times 8)^2)))$
28629 := $(-9) - ((T((2 \times T(6))) \times T(T(8)))/T(T(T(2))))$
28632 := $((-2) + T((3+6))) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(2))$
28634 := $(-4) - ((T((T(T(3)) + T(6))) \times (-T(T(8)))/T(T(T(2))))$
28635 := $-((T(5) \times (T((3 \times 6)) - T((8^2))))$
28636 := $((T((T(6) + T(T(3)))/T(6)) \times T(T(8))) - 2)$
28638 := $(T(T(8)) \times (-3 - ((6 \times 8) - 2)))$
28642 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (4 + T(-((T(6) - T(8))))) - 2)$
28644 := $((4 \times (T(4) + T(6))) \times T(T((8 - 2)))$
28645 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T((6 - 8)))) + T(2)))$
28646 := $((T(T(6)) \times (4 + T(-((T(6) - T(8))))) + 2)$
28648 := $(8 \times (T((4 \times T(6))) + (8 + T(2))))$
28652 := $((T(T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))) + 8) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
28653 := $((T((T(3) \times T(5))) \times (-T(6))) + T(8))/(-T(2))$
28654 := $((4 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))) + (8 + 2)$
28656 := $(6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(((6 \times 8) \times 2)))$
28665 := $(T((T(5) \times 6)) \times ((6 + 8)/2))$
28667 := $(7 \times T(((T(6) \times 6) - T(8)))) + 2$
28672 := $(2 \times (7 + T(6))) \times (8^{T(2)})$
28674 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) - (T(6) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-2)$
28678 := $((T((8 + 7)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8)) - 2)$
28679 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) + (T((6 + T(8)))/(-T(2))))$
28681 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times (-T(6) - (8^2)))$
28682 := $(2 - ((-8) - T(T(6))) \times T(T((8 - T(2))))$
28683 := $((T(T(-((3 - 8)))) \times (T(T(6)) + 8)) + T(2))$
28684 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8) \times ((T(6) \times T(8)) - 2)))$
28685 := $((T(T(5)) \times (8 + T(T(6)))) + (8 - T(2)))$
28686 := $(-T(6)) \times (8 + ((T(6) + T(T(8))) \times (-2)))$
28687 := $((T(7) \times T((T(8) + 6))) + (T(82)))$
28688 := $(8 - ((-8) - T(T(6))) \times T(T((8 - T(2))))$
28689 := $(9 - ((-8) - T(T(6))) \times T(T((8 - T(2))))$
28692 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(9) + T(68)) \times 2))$
28694 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(9) \times (-6) - T(T(8)))) + T(T(2))))$
28695 := $((T(T(5)) \times (9 + T(T(6)))) - T((8 + T(T(2))))$
28696 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))/6) \times T((8 \times 2))$
28698 := $(8 \times T(T(9))) - (-6) \times T(82)$
28704 := $((4 + T(07)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))$
28722 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(2) \times T((7 \times 8)))) - T(T(2)))$
28724 := $(-4) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T((7 \times 8)) \times T(2)))$
28725 := $((T(5) + T(2)) \times T((7 \times 8))) - T(2)$
28726 := $((T(6) - T(2)) \times T((7 \times 8))) - 2$
28728 := $((8 - 2) \times T((7 \times 8))) \times T(2)$
28729 := $((T((T(9) \times 2)) \times 7) + (8^2))$
28731 := $((1 + (T(3) \times T((7 \times 8)))) \times T(2))$
28734 := $((T((T(T(4)) + (T(3) \times 7))) + T(8)) \times T(T(2)))$
28741 := $((T(T((-1) + T(4))) \times T(7)) - 8) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
28742 := $(2 \times ((T(T(4)) \times 7) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))))$
28743 := $((3 + T(4)) \times T(T((7 + (8/2))))$
28744 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7)) + 8)/(-T(2))$
28745 := $((-5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (7 \times 8)))/T(2)$
28746 := $(6 \times (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) \times 8) + T(2))))$
28749 := $((T(T(9)) \times (4 \times 7)) - T(T((8 - 2))))$
28752 := $((-2) \times T(T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8)) \times 2$
28754 := $((4^5) \times T(7)) + (82)$
28755 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-((T(5) + T(7))) \times T(T(8))) + T(2)))$
28756 := $((T((6 \times T(5))) \times 7) + T((-8) + T(T(T(2))))$
28758 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) - ((-7) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)))$
28764 := $(T((-4) + T(6))) \times (-T(7) + (T(8) \times T(T(2))))$
28765 := $(-5) + ((T(T(6)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(8))) \times (-2))$
28767 := $((T((7 \times 6))/7) \times (-8) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
28768 := $((T(T(8)) \times (-T(6))) - T(T(7))) + 8) \times (-2)$

28774 := ((T(4) × ((T(T(7)) × 7) + T(8))) - T(T(2)))
28777 := ((T(7) × (T(7) + (T(7) × T(8)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
28779 := (((T(T(9)) - 7) × T(7)) - (8 - T(2)))
28782 := (((T(2) + T(8 × 7)) × T(8))/2)
28783 := (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(8) + 7)) × (T(T(8)) - 2))
28784 := ((T(4) - 8) × (T(T(7)) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(T(2))))))
28786 := ((T(T(6)) + ((-T(8)) × T(T(7))) - 8) × (-2))
28787 := (((-T(7)) × T((T(8) + T(7)))) + T(T(8)))/(-2))
28788 := ((T((8 + 8)) + (7 × T(T(8)))) × T(T(2)))
28789 := (((T(T(9)) - 8) × T(7)) + (T(8) - T(2)))
28791 := (((1 + T((T(9) + 7)))) - 8) × T(T(T(2)))
28794 := (((T(4) + T(97)) + T(8)) × T(T(2)))
28795 := (-5) - (T(9) × ((T(7) - T(T(8))) - 2))
28796 := (((-6) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - (8 × 2)
28797 := (((-7) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - 8 + T(T(T(2)))
28798 := (((-T(89)) + T(T(7))) × (-8)) + T(T(2)))
28799 := (-T(9)) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(7))) + T(8 × 2))
28812 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((T((1 + T(8))) + T(T(8))) + T(2)))
28815 := (5 × ((1 + 8) × T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
28824 := (4 × (((T(2)⁸) + T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2))))))
28826 := (T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) × (T(T(8)) - T((T(8) - 2))))
28827 := (((T((T(7) × T(2))) + T(8)) × 8) - T(T(T(2))))
28828 := (-8) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) × (T(8) × T(2)))
28833 := (((T(T(3)) + T(3 + T(8))) × T(8)) - T(2))
28834 := (T(T((T(4) + 3))) + (8 × T(T((T(8)/T(2))))))
28836 := ((T(T(T(6 - 3)))) + T(8)) × (T(8) × T(2))
28837 := ((7 × T(T((T(3) - 8)))) - (T((T(8) - T(T(2))))))
28839 := (((T(9) × 3) + T(T(8))) × T(8)) + T(2))
28841 := (-1) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))) × (T(8) - T(2)))
28842 := ((-T(2)) + (T(T(4)) × 8)) × T(8 + T(2))
28845 := (-T(5)) × ((-4) × T(T(8))) + T((T(8) + 2))
28846 := (((T(T(6) × 4)) + T(8)) × 8) - 2
28847 := (-T(7)) - (T(T(4)) × (T(8) - T((T(8) - T(2))))))
28848 := (((T(8) × T(4 + T(8))) - T(T(8))) - T(T(2)))
28851 := (((T(1 + T(5))) + T(T(8))) × T(8)) - T(T(T(2))))
28852 := ((2^{T(5)}) - T((8 + T(8)) × 2))
28853 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (-5) + T((T(8) + T(8))))/T(T(T(2))))
28854 := ((-T(T(4)) × (T(T(5)) - T(T(8)))) - T(8 × T(T(2))))
28858 := (((8⁵) - T(88)) + T(T(2)))
28864 := (T(4) + ((T(6) + T(T(8))) × (T(8) + T(T(2))))))
28867 := ((7 × T(T((T(6) - 8)))) - T(8 + T(T(T(2))))))
28869 := (((T(T(9)) × (T(6) × 8)) - T(T(8)))/T(T(2)))
28872 := (T(T(2)) × ((T((7 × 8)) + 8) × T(2)))
28875 := ((-T(5) × (T(7) - T((8 × 8) - 2)))
28887 := (-T(78)) - ((-8) × T(T(8))) × T(T(2)))
28889 := ((T(9) × T(T(8))) - T((T(8) + (8 + 2))))
28905 := (-T(T(5))) - (T(09) × (-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(2))))

28908 := (T((8 × 09)) × (8 + T(2)))
28911 := ((11 × T((9 × 8))) + T(2))
28914 := (((T(4) + 1) × T((9 × 8))) + T(T(2)))
28916 := ((T((6 + 1)) × T(T(9))) - (8²))
28917 := ((T((T(7) - 1)) × T((9 + 8)))/2)
28923 := (((3^{T(2)}) × (T(T(9)) + T(8))) + T(T(2)))
28924 := (T((T(4) - T(2))) × ((T(T(9)) - 8) + T(T(2))))
28925 := ((T((5 + 2)) × T(T(9))) - T(8 + 2))
28926 := (-T(6)) + (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) × (-T(8))) + T(2))
28927 := (T(7) - ((T(T(2)) - T(9)) × T((T(8) + 2))))
28928 := (((-T(8)) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))) - (8 × 2))
28929 := -(((T(T(9)) + T(2)) + ((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + T(2)))
28932 := (-T(T(2))) + (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) × (-T(8))) - T(T(2)))
28933 := -((T(T(3 × 3)) + ((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + 2))
28934 := (-T(43)) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) - 2))
28935 := (T((T(5) × T(3))) + (T(T(9)) × (8 × T(2))))
28936 := (-6) + (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) × (-T(8))) - 2))
28937 := (-T(7)) - (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) × T(8)) - T(T(T(2))))
28938 := (((-8) × T(T(3))) - ((-T(98)) × T(T(2))))
28939 := -(((T(T(9)) - T(3)) + ((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + 2))
28941 := ((1 + T(4)) × (T((9 × 8)) + T(2)))
28942 := ((T((T(2) + 4)) × T(T(9))) - (T(8) + 2))
28944 := (T((4 + 4)) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(8 - 2))))
28946 := ((T(6) × T(T(T(4)))) + (9 - T(82)))
28947 := (((7 × 4) × T(T(9))) - (T(8) - T(2)))
28956 := -(((T(T((-6) + T(5))) - (T(9) × T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(2))))))
28962 := (T(T(2)) × (-((T(6) - T(98)) + T(2))))
28963 := (T(T(3)) - (((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) × T(8)) + 2))
28964 := (-((T(T(4)) + 6)) - (T(9) × (-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(2))))))
28965 := ((-T(5) - (T(69) × T(8)))/T(2))
28967 := (((7 + T(6)) × T(T(9))) + 8) - T(T(T(2)))
28968 := (((8 × T(6)) + T(9)) × T(8 × 2))
28971 := ((((-1) - T(7)) × (-9)) × T(T(8)))/T(T(2))
28972 := (2 - ((-T(7)) × T(T(9))) + (8 + 2))
28973 := (3 - ((-T(7)) × T(T(9))) + (8 + 2))
28974 := (((4 × 7) × T(T(9))) - (8 - 2))
28975 := (-T(5)) - ((-T(7)) × T(T(9))) - (8 + 2))
28976 := ((T(6) × T(7 + T(9))) + (T(8) + 2))
28977 := ((T(7) × T((T(7) + (9 + 8)))) - T(2))
28978 := (((T(T(8)) × T(7)) × T(T(9)))/T(T(8))) - 2
28979 := ((T(T(9)) × T(7)) - ((9 - 8)²)
28982 := (((28 × T(T(9))) + 8) - T(T(2)))
28983 := (((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) × (-T(9))) - T(8)) - T(T(2))
28985 := ((T((T(5) - 8)) × T(T(9))) + (8 - T(2)))
28986 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(8))) × T(9)) - (T(8) + T(2))
28987 := (7 × (T(89) + T(8 × 2)))
28989 := (9 × (8 + ((T(T(9)) + T(8)) × T(2))))

- 28992** := $((T(-((2-9))) \times T(T(9))) + (T(8)/T(2)))$
28994 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 9) - 9) \times (8 + T(T(2))))$
28995 := $(T(5) + (T(T(9)) \times T(-((9 - (8 \times 2))))))$
28997 := $((-T(7) - T(T(9))) + (T(9) \times (T(T(8)) + 2)))$
28998 := $((((T(8) \times T(9)) - 9) \times T(8))/2)$
29025 := $((5 + T(20)) \times T(9)) \times T(2)$
29028 := $((T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(09) + T(2))$
29036 := $(T((T(6)/3) \times (T(T(09)) + 2)))$
29074 := $(T(4) - (T(7) \times ((0 - T(T(9))) - T(2))))$
29084 := $((-((T(T(4)) + (T(80) \times (-9)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29115 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(11)) + (-T(9)) \times T(T(2))))$
29127 := $((T((T(7) - 2) + 1) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
29133 := $((3^3) \times (T((1 + T(9))) - 2))$
29139 := $((-9) + (T((T(3) + 1)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(2))))$
29143 := $((T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-19) - T(2))$
29145 := $(T(5) \times (-T(T(4)) - (T(T(-((1-9)))) \times (-T(2))))$
29146 := $((6 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-1 + (9 \times 2)))$
29148 := $((T((8 \times T(4)) - 1) \times 9) - T(2))$
29158 := $((T((8 \times T((5-1)))) \times 9) - 2)$
29166 := $((T(6) \times T(T(6))) + (1+9)) \times T(T(2))$
29169 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((6+1))) + (9 \times T(T(T(2))))$
29172 := $((-((T(T(2)) - T(7))) \times T((T((1 \times 9)) + T(T(2))))$
29173 := $((-3) - (T(7) \times ((-1) - T(T(9))) - T(T(2))))$
29176 := $((T(6) + 7) \times ((1 + T(T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29178 := $((T(87) + T(T((1 \times 9)))) \times T(T(2)))$
29181 := $((T(-((1-81))) \times 9) + T(T(T(2))))$
29189 := $(((-9) + T(8)) \times T((1 + T(9)))) + 2$
29193 := $((3 \times 9) \times T((1 + T(9)))) + T(T(2))$
29197 := $(7 \times (T(91) - (T(9)/T(2))))$
29205 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(02)))) + T(9 \times T(T(2))))$
29208 := $((T(80) + T(T(2))) \times 9) - T(T(2))$
29211 := $(T(T(11)) + ((T(T(T(2))) + 9)^{T(2)}))$
29213 := $((T((T(3) + 1)) - (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29214 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(9)) \times T(2)))$
29216 := $((T(6) + 1) \times (2 + T((T(9) + T(T(2))))))$
29221 := $((1 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29222 := $((2 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29223 := $((T(3) \times T(2)) - (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29224 := $((4 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29225 := $((5^{T(T(2))} \times 2) - (T(9)^2))$
29226 := $((-T(6) + T(T(2))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29227 := $((-7 \times 2) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29228 := $((8 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29229 := $((T((9 \times 2))^2 - 9) - T(2))$
29231 := $((T((1+3)) - (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29232 := $((T(2) \times (-3)) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29234 := $((-(4+3) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29235 := $((T(5) - T(T(3))) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29237 := $((-(7-3) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29238 := $((T(8) + T(T(3)))^2 \times 9) - T(2)$
29241 := $(T(((1^4) \times 2) \times 9))^2$
29242 := $((T(2) - 4) - (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29243 := $((T(3) - 4) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29244 := $((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(9) - T(T(2)))$
29245 := $((-T(5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-2) + T((9 - T(2))))))$
29247 := $(T((7-4) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29248 := $((T((8 + T(4)))^2) + (9 - 2))$
29261 := $((-1) + T(6) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29262 := $((T((T(2) \times 6))^2) + T(9 - T(2)))$
29264 := $((T(4) + T(6)) \times (-2) + T((T(9) - 2)))$
29265 := $(5 \times (T(6) + ((2 \times 9)^{T(2)}))$
29267 := $((T(7) - ((T(62) \times T(9))/T(2)))$
29268 := $(T(8) \times ((T(6) - T(2)) \times T(9) + T(2)))$
29272 := $((T(2) + T(7)) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29273 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((T(7) \times (-2) - T(T(9))) - T(T(2))))$
29274 := $((T(T(4)) + 7)^2 + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2))$
29275 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(7) \times (-2) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
29279 := $((T(9) - 7) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29283 := $((T(3) + T(8)) + (T((2 \times 9))^2))$
29284 := $((T((T(4) + 8))^2) + (T(9) - 2))$
29285 := $((-T(5) - T(T(8))) \times (2 - T(9))) + 2$
29286 := $((T(6) + ((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(9))) \times T(T(2)))$
29287 := $((7 \times T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(9)/T(2)))$
29288 := $(8 \times ((T((T(8) \times 2)) + T(T(9))) - 2))$
29289 := $((T(9 - T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) \times (-T(9)) - T(T(2)))$
29292 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(9) + (T((2 \times 9))^2)))$
29295 := $(T(5) \times T(((T(9) \times 2) - T(9 - 2))))$
29297 := $((7 \times 9) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 9))) + 2$
29298 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(9)/T(2))) \times T(9) + T(2))$
29316 := $(T((6+1) \times ((T(3) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29317 := $((7 \times T(T(13))) + (T(9)/T(2)))$
29322 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((2 \times (3 + T(9)))))) \times T(T(2)))$
29325 := $((T((T(5) - 2) - (T(3))) \times T(T(9)))/T(2))$
29326 := $((T(6) + T((-2) + T(3))) \times T((T(9) - 2)))$
29328 := $(T((T(8)/T(2))) \times (T((3 \times 9)) - 2))$
29337 := $((7 + T((-T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(9 - T(2))))$
29343 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T((T(4) + T(3)) - 9)) + T(T(2)))$
29344 := $((T(4) \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + 9)) - T(T(2)))$
29346 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(4) + T(3)))) - (T(T(9)) \times 2))$
29347 := $((T(7) \times ((T(4) + 3) + T(T(9)))) + T(2))$
29349 := $((-9) \times ((T(4) \times T(3)) - T(9^2)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 29352 &:= (((T(2)^{5+T(3)} - T(T(9)))/T(T(2))) \\ 29355 &:= (T(5) \times (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 9) - 2)) \\ 29358 &:= ((-((T(T(8)) + (T(5)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times 9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29367 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + 3)) + T(9)) \times T(2)) \\ 29368 &:= (-8) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(9)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 29373 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(7) \times (-T(3)) - T(T(9)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29375 &:= ((5^{7-3}) \times (T(9) + 2)) \\ 29376 &:= (((T(6) \times T(7 \times 3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 29378 &:= (-T(T(8))) + (-T(T(7))) \times ((T(T(T(3))) - 9)/(-T(2))) \\ 29379 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) + T(T(3))) + T((9 \times T(2)))) \\ 29382 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(8) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))))/(-2)) \\ 29385 &:= -((T(5) \times (T((8 + 3)) - (T(9)^2))) \\ 29387 &:= ((((-7) + T(T(8))) - (T(3))) \times T(9)) + 2) \\ 29388 &:= (((8 + T(T(8))) - T(T(3))) \times T(9)) + T(2) \\ 29394 &:= ((T(T((4 + 9))) \times T(3)) + T(92)) \\ 29397 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(3)))) - T((9 \times 2))) \\ 29403 &:= ((-30) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(9)))) + T(2) \\ 29414 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + (-14) \times T(T((9 + 2)))))) \\ 29415 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-1) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(9))) \times 2)) \\ 29424 &:= (-4) \times ((T(T(2)) \times (-T(49))) - T(T(2))) \\ 29425 &:= ((5 \times (-2) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29427 &:= ((-T(T(7))) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 29428 &:= (((T(T(8)) - (2 + T(4))) \times T(9)) - 2) \\ 29432 &:= (((T(2)^3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(9)))) + 2) \\ 29433 &:= (((3^3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(9)))) + T(2)) \\ 29434 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 3) \times (T(4) + 9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29435 &:= ((5 \times T(T((T(3) + 4)))) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29436 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times (9 - T(2))) \\ 29437 &:= ((7 \times T(T((3 + T(4)))) + (T(9) \times T(2))) \\ 29439 &:= (-T(9)) - (-T((3 \times 4))) \times T((9 \times T(2))) \\ 29442 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(4)) - 9) \times T(2))) \\ 29444 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times (T(4) + 9)) - T(T(2))) \\ 29445 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) \times ((T(4) \times T(9)) + T(2))) \\ 29446 &:= (((T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29448 &:= (T(8) \times (T((4 + (4 \times 9))) - 2)) \\ 29449 &:= ((9 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (9 \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29456 &:= (((6^5) - T(T(4))) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29457 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(9)) + 2)) \\ 29458 &:= ((8 + 5) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T((9 + 2)))))) \\ 29463 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(6)) - 4) + T((T(9) + T(2)))))) \\ 29465 &:= ((5 \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29466 &:= (6 \times (T((6 \times T(4))) + T(T((9 + T(2)))))) \\ 29469 &:= (T(T(9)) - (((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29472 &:= (((T(2) \times T(T(7))) + T(4)) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29474 &:= (-T(4)) + (T((-T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T((9 + T(2)))) \\ 29475 &:= (T(5) \times (T((7 + T(T(4)))) + (9 + T(2)))) \\ 29477 &:= (-7) \times ((-T(7)) - T(T((4 + 9)))) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29478 &:= (T(T(8)) - (-((7^4) \times (9 + T(2)))) \\ 29479 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((-T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 29481 &:= ((((-1) + T(T(8))) - T(4)) \times T(9)) + T(T(2)) \\ 29482 &:= (-2) - (-T((8 + 4))) \times T((9 \times T(2))) \\ 29484 &:= (((T(4) \times T(8)) + 4) \times (9^2)) \\ 29487 &:= ((T(7) \times ((8 + T(4)) + T(T(9)))) + T(2)) \\ 29491 &:= ((19 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((9 - T(2)))))) \\ 29493 &:= ((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) \times (-9))) \times T(2)) \\ 29499 &:= (((T((T(9) - 9)) - T(4)) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29511 &:= ((T(T((1 + 1)))^5) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29514 &:= -((T(41) - (T(5) \times (T(9)^2))) \\ 29517 &:= ((T((7 + 1)) \times T((-5) + T(9))) - T(2)) \\ 29518 &:= ((T(8) \times T((-1 \times 5) + T(9))) - 2) \\ 29532 &:= (T(23) \times (T(5) + (92))) \\ 29535 &:= (T(5) + ((T(3) \times T((-5) + T(9))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 29536 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T((3 + T(5))) \times T(T(9))))/T(T(2))) \\ 29537 &:= (((-T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (5 \times T(T(9))))/(-T(2)) \\ 29538 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(3))) + (-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-2)) \\ 29539 &:= (-T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) - 59)^2) \\ 29544 &:= (((4^4) \times T(T(5))) - T((T(9) + T(2)))) \\ 29545 &:= ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T((T(5) - 9)) - 2)) \\ 29547 &:= ((7 \times (T((4 \times 5)) - 9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29548 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) + T((9 - 2))) \\ 29552 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + (T((T(5) + T(9))) + 2)) \\ 29553 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + (T((T(5) + T(9))) + T(2))) \\ 29556 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(5) + T(9)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29559 &:= (((-9) + T(T((T(5))/T(5)))) \times T(9)) - T(T(2)) \\ 29562 &:= (((-2) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5) + 9)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29563 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(6)) - 59)^2)) \\ 29564 &:= ((-4) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5) + 9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29565 &:= (((T(T(5)) - (T(6))) + T(T(5))) \times (T(9) \times T(2))) \\ 29566 &:= -((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5) + 9)) - 2))) \\ 29567 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((T((T(6) + T(5))) \times T(9)) + T(2)))) \\ 29568 &:= ((8 \times T(6)) \times (5 + T((9 \times 2)))) \\ 29574 &:= (-T(4)) + (((7 + T(T(5))) + T(9))^2) \\ 29575 &:= (T(-((T(5) - T(7)))) \times T(((5 + T(9))/2))) \\ 29577 &:= (-7) + (((7 + T(T(5))) + T(9))^2) \\ 29578 &:= (((T(8) - 7) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(9)))) - 2) \\ 29582 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + 8) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(9)))) + 2) \\ 29583 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times 8) + 5) \times T((9 \times 2))) \\ 29584 &:= (4 \times (((T(8) + 5) + T(9))^2)) \\ 29586 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (8 + T(T(5)))) + (9 \times 2)) \\ 29589 &:= -((T(T(9)) + (-8) \times T(-(5 - 92)))) \\ 29592 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(5)) - (9^{T(2)}))) \\ 29597 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(T(9)) - (T(5)))) + (T(T(9)) + 2)) \\ 29598 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(9) - 5))) + T((9 + T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29617 &:= (-7) \times (-T(16) - T((T(9) \times 2))) \\ 29619 &:= (9 \times (T((-1) + T(6))) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \\ 29624 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times 92) \\ 29625 &:= ((5^{T(2)}) \times (T(T(6)) + (9 - T(2)))) \\ 29627 &:= ((T(7) \times ((2 + T(6)) + T(T(9)))) + T(2)) \\ 29628 &:= (T((T(8) \times 2)) + ((T(6) + 9)^{T(2)})) \\ 29632 &:= ((2^{T(3)}) \times (T((T(6) + 9) - 2)) \\ 29634 &:= ((T(4) \times T(T((T(3) + (6)))))) - T((T(9) + T(2)))) \\ 29635 &:= (5 \times (((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))/(-9)) - 2)) \\ 29642 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(9) \times T(2))) \\ 29643 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(6)))/9) - 2) \\ 29644 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))))) - T(T(9 + T(2)))) \\ 29646 &:= ((6 + T(T(4))) \times (6 \times (9^2))) \\ 29647 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(-((4 - 6) \times 9)))^2) \\ 29648 &:= (8 \times (T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) + T((T(9) - T(T(2)))))) \\ 29652 &:= (T(2 + 5)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(9))) + T(2)) \\ 29653 &:= ((T(3) \times T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))))) - (T(9) + 2)) \\ 29655 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(5) + T(T(6)))) + (T(9) \times T(2))) \\ 29657 &:= (((-7) + T((T(5) + T(6)))) \times T(9)) + 2) \\ 29658 &:= (((8 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(9) \times (-2))) \\ 29664 &:= (((4 + T(T(6))) \times T(6)) + 9) \times T(T(2)) \\ 29673 &:= (((-3) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) + T((T(9) \times 2)) \\ 29679 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T(7) \times ((6 - T(T(9))) + T(T(2)))))) \\ 29682 &:= ((T(-((T(2) - T(8)))) + (T(6)) \times (T(9) + T(T(2)))) \\ 29684 &:= (-T(4)) - (((T(T(8)) - (6)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29685 &:= (-5) \times (((T(T(8)) - (6)) \times (-9)) + T(2)) \\ 29687 &:= (-7) - (((T(T(8)) - (6)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29688 &:= (T(T(8)) - (((T(T(8)) - (T(6))) \times (-T(9))) + T(2))) \\ 29689 &:= (-9) - (((T(T(8)) - (6)) \times (-T(9))) + 2) \\ 29694 &:= (((T((4 \times 9)) - (6)) \times T(9)) - T(T(2))) \\ 29695 &:= (-5) - (9 \times (T(6) - T((9^2)))) \\ 29698 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) - ((6 \times T(9)) + 2)) \\ 29706 &:= ((T((60 + T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 29709 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(07)) + ((9^{T(2)})) \\ 29711 &:= (11 \times T((7 + T(9 + 2)))) \\ 29714 &:= (((T(4) + 1) \times T((T(7) + T(9)))) + T(2)) \\ 29715 &:= -((T(T(5 + 1))) + (-7) \times T(92)) \\ 29716 &:= -((T(T(6)) + (-1) - (7 \times T(92)))) \\ 29717 &:= (((T(T(7)) + 1) \times (T(7) + T(9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29722 &:= (22 \times (T(T(7)) - (-T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29728 &:= ((T(T(8)) - 2) + (T(7) \times (T(T(9)) + T(2)))) \\ 29732 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((T(7) + T(9)))))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29733 &:= -((T(33) \times (T(7) - (9^2)))) \\ 29734 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((3 + T(7))) + T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29736 &:= (6 \times (T(3) + T((7 + 92)))) \\ 29738 &:= ((T(8) \times T(T(3))) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(9))) - 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29739 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) \times T(7)) + T((9 \times 2))) \\ 29743 &:= (T(34) + (T(7) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(2)))))) \\ 29744 &:= (44 \times (T(T(7)) - (-T(9) \times T(T(2)))))) \\ 29745 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(7))) - T(9)) \times T(2)) \\ 29748 &:= ((8 + T(((4 + 7) \times 9))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 29749 &:= (T(94) + (T(7) \times T((T(9) - T(2)))))) \\ 29752 &:= (((2 \times T(57)) \times 9) - 2) \\ 29754 &:= (((-4) \times T(57)) \times (-9))/2) \\ 29755 &:= (55 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(9) \times T(2)))) \\ 29756 &:= (((6 \times T(T(5))) - T(7)) \times (T(9) - 2)) \\ 29757 &:= (7 \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) - (9 \times T(2)))) \\ 29758 &:= ((T((-8) + T(5))) \times (T(7) + T(T(9)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 29761 &:= ((T((1 + 6)) \times (T(7) + T(T(9)))) - T(2)) \\ 29762 &:= ((2 + T(6)) \times ((T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29763 &:= ((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9))) - T(2)) \\ 29764 &:= (((-4) \times T(6)) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))))/(-T(2)) \\ 29766 &:= ((T(T(6))/T(6)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(9)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 29767 &:= ((T(7) \times ((T(6) + (7)) + T(T(9)))) + T(2)) \\ 29768 &:= (8 \times ((-6) + T(T(7))) + T((9^2))) \\ 29769 &:= (((T(9) + T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9))) + T(2)) \\ 29782 &:= ((-2) - (-((T(8) - (7))) \times T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29784 &:= (((-4) + T((8 + T(7)))) \times T(9)) - T(T(2)) \\ 29785 &:= (((-5) + T(8))^{T(-7+9)}) - T(T(2)) \\ 29786 &:= -((T(T(6)) + ((-((T(8) - (7))) \times T(T(9))) - 2))) \\ 29789 &:= (((T(T(9)) - 8) \times T(7)) + T(T(9))) - 2) \\ 29791 &:= (((1 + T(T(T(9 - 7)))) + 9)^{T(2)}) \\ 29793 &:= (((-3) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(7))) + ((9^{T(2)})) \\ 29794 &:= ((T(4) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29796 &:= (((T(6) - T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times T((9 + T(2)))) \\ 29799 &:= ((99 \times 7) \times (T(9) - 2)) \\ 29808 &:= (T(80) - (-8) \times T((9^2))) \\ 29813 &:= ((T(T(T(3) + 1)) \times (T(T(8))/9)) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29814 &:= (((-((4 - 1)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29821 &:= ((1 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (-T((8 + T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29822 &:= ((2 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (-T((8 + T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29823 &:= (-T(3)) - (((-T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 29824 &:= ((T(4) - ((-T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 29825 &:= (-5) \times (((-T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times (-9)) + 2) \\ 29826 &:= ((T(6) + T(((T(2) + 8) \times 9))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 29827 &:= (T(7) - ((T(2) - T(8)) \times T((T(9) - T(2)))))) \\ 29828 &:= (-T((8 \times 2)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 29829 &:= ((((-9)/T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) - T(T(2)) \\ 29831 &:= (-1) - (((-3) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) + T(2)) \\ 29832 &:= (((T(2) - T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) - T(2) \\ 29833 &:= (((3 - T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) - 2) \\ 29834 &:= (-4) - (((-3) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) - T(2)) \\ 29835 &:= ((5 + (T(3) \times T(8))) \times (T(9) \times T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 29837** := $-((T(T(7)) + (((T(3) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) - T(2))))$
29838 := $((T(T(8) - 3) \times (T(8) + 9)) + T(2))$
29841 := $((((1 - 4) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) + T(T(2)))$
29842 := $((T((T(2) + 4)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(9) - 2))$
29843 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-T(4) + T((8 + T(9)))) + 2)$
29844 := $(-((T((T(4) + 4)) - (T(T(8)) \times T(9)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29845 := $(5 \times ((-4) - (T(T(8)) \times (-9))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29847 := $((T(7) \times T(48)) - T(T((9 + T(2))))$
29848 := $(8 \times (-T(4) + T((89 - T(2))))$
29849 := $(((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(9))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29851 := $((-1) - T(T(5))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - 2)$
29852 := $((2^{T(5)}) + (T(8) \times (-9^2)))$
29853 := $(3 \times (((T(5) \times T(T(8))) - T(9)) + T(T(2))))$
29854 := $((T(4) - T(T(5))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29856 := $(T(6) - (T(5) \times (T(8) - (T(9)^2))))$
29857 := $((T(7) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(9))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29858 := $((-T((8 + 5))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(9))) - T(T(T(2))))$
29859 := $(-T((9 + 5))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29861 := $(-1) - (-T(6) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times 2))$
29862 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(8) - (T(9) \times (-2))))$
29864 := $((T(T(4)) + (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times 9)) \times 2)$
29865 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(2))))$
29867 := $-((T((-7) + T(6))) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - 2))$
29868 := $(-T((8 + 6))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - T(2))$
29873 := $-((T((T(3) + 7))) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29874 := $((T(T(4)) + T(7)) \times (8 \times T(9))) - T(T(2))$
29875 := $-((T(5) + (-7) \times (-8) + T(92)))$
29876 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-T(7) - (-8) \times T(9)))) / (-T(2))$
29877 := $-((T(T(7)) + ((7 + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) + 2))$
29878 := $(T(8) - ((T(7) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) - 2)))$
29879 := $(-97) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(2)))$
29882 := $(((-2) + T(T(8))) \times (T(8) + 9)) + 2$
29883 := $((((T(3) + T(T(8))) - 8) \times T(9)) + T(2))$
29884 := $((T(4) \times (-8)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
29885 := $(-T((5 + 8))) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(2)))$
29886 := $((((6 + T(T(8))) - 8) \times T(9)) + T(T(2)))$
29887 := $((T(-((7 - 88))) \times 9) - 2)$
29888 := $(-88) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(2)))$
29889 := $(9 \times T(((8/8) \times 9^2)))$
29891 := $((1 \times 9) \times T((T(8) + T(9)))) + 2$
29892 := $(T(2) + ((T(9) - T(8)) \times T((9^2))))$
29893 := $(T(3) - ((-9) \times T((T(8) + T(9)))) + 2)$
29894 := $(-T(4) - ((-T(9)) \times T(T(8))) + (T((9 + 2))))$
29895 := $((T(((5 \times 9) + T(8))) \times 9) + T(T(2)))$
29897 := $(-7) - ((-T(9)) \times T(T(8))) + (T((9 + 2))))$
29898 := $(T(T(8)) - ((9 \times 8) \times T(T(9 - 2))))$
29917 := $(T(7) - ((1 \times 9) \times T((9^2))))$
29918 := $((T(T(8)) - 1) \times T(9)) - (9 - 2)$
29919 := $((T(T((9 - 1))) \times T(9)) - T(9)) - T(T(2))$
29922 := $-((T(T(2)) + (-29) \times (T(T(9)) - T(2))))$
29923 := $-((T(3) - ((2 + T((9 + 9)))^2)))$
29924 := $(-4) - (-29) \times (T(T(9)) - T(2))$
29925 := $(T((5 + T(2))) - (-9) \times T((9^2)))$
29926 := $((T((T(6)/T(2))) \times T(T(9))) + T((T(9) - 2)))$
29927 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((9 + 9))) + 2$
29928 := $((T(8) + T(2)) + (9 \times T((9^2))))$
29931 := $(T(T(T((1 \times 3)))) - (-T(99) \times T(T(2))))$
29933 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(3) \times T(99)) + 2))$
29937 := $((T(7) \times (-3) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(9)) + T(T(2))))$
29942 := $((-2) + T(T(4))) - (-9) \times T((9^2))$
29943 := $((T((3^4) \times 9)) - (-9) \times T(T(2)))$
29944 := $(T(T(4)) - ((4 - T(9)) \times (9^{T(2)})))$
29946 := $(-((6 - 4) - 9) \times T(92))$
29949 := $((T(9) \times T((4 \times 9))) - T((9 - T(2))))$
29952 := $(T(2) \times ((T(5) \times T((T(9) - 9))) - T(T(2))))$
29954 := $-(((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) + (-9) \times T((9^2))))$
29955 := $(-T(5) - ((-T(5)) \times T((T(9) - 9))) \times T(2))$
29957 := $((T(T(7)) / (5 + 9)) \times (T(T(9)) - 2))$
29958 := $((T(T(8)) \times (5 \times 9)) - (9 + T(2)))$
29963 := $((T(36) \times T(9)) - (9 - 2))$
29964 := $((T(((T(4) - 6) \times 9) \times T(9))) - T(T(2)))$
29965 := $(-5) - ((T(T(6)) - 9) \times (-T(9) \times T(2)))$
29967 := $(-7) \times ((6 - 9) - T(92))$
29968 := $((8 + T(6)) \times T(T(9))) - (T(9) + 2)$
29972 := $((T((27 + 9)) \times T(9)) + 2)$
29973 := $((3 \times T(7)) + (9 \times T((9^2))))$
29974 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(79) \times (-9)) + T(T(2))))$
29975 := $((5 \times T(T(7))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-9) \times T(2)))$
29976 := $((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - (-9) \times T(92)$
29978 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(7))) / 9) - (T((9 + 2)))$
29979 := $(9 \times (T(79) + T((9 \times 2))))$
29981 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(9)) + (9 + 2))$
29982 := $(T((2 + T(8))) + (T((9 + 9))^2))$
29983 := $(T(3) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) - (9 - 2)))$
29984 := $(-4) - ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times (-T((9 - 2))))$
29985 := $((5 \times T(T(8))) \times 9) + (T(9) / T(2))$
29987 := $(((-7) + T(8)) \times T(T(9))) - T((9 - 2))$
29988 := $(((-8) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) + T((9 \times T(2)))$
29989 := $((T(9) \times T(T(8))) + (-9) + T((9 - 2)))$
29991 := $((T(T(-(1 - 9))) \times T(9)) + T((9 - T(2))))$
29993 := $(T(T(3)) - ((-T(9)) \times T((T(9) - 9))) - 2)$
29994 := $(4999 \times T(T(2)))$
29997 := $((T(7) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(9))) - (9 \times 2)$

- 29998** := ((T(T(8)) × T(9)) + T(((T(9)/9) + 2)))
30125 := ((5^{T(2)}) × (10 + T(T(T(3)))))
30129 := -((T(T(9+2))) - (T(T(10)) × T(T(3))))
30135 := (((-5) × T(T(3))) + T(T(10))) × T(T(3)))
30189 := ((T(9) × (T(T(8)) + 10)) - T(T(T(3))))
30192 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) × T((10 + T(3))))
30244 := ((T(4) × (T(T(4))²)) - T(03))
30255 := (T(5) - (-T(5) × T((T(2) × T(T(03))))))
30285 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(8)) × (-T(2))) - T(T(03)))
30324 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(2)))) - T((3 × T(T(03))))
30384 := (4 × (T(T(8)) - (-30 × T(T(T(3)))))
30396 := (T(6) - ((T(9)³)/(0 - 3)))
30458 := ((8⁵) + (-T(4) × T(T(T(03))))
30528 := (8 × ((T(2) - T(50)) × (-3)))
30576 := (T(6) × (T(T(7)) + (50 × T(T(3)))))
30582 := (T(2) × ((8 × T(50)) - T(3)))
30585 := ((5 - (8 × T(50))) × (-3))
30597 := (7 × T(-((T(T(9)) - (T(50 - 3))))))
30618 := (81 × T((T(6) + T(03))))
30723 := (((T(T(3)) - 2) × 7) × T(T(T(03))))
30765 := ((-5) - (T(6) × (-70))) × T(T(3))
30834 := ((T(T(4)) × T((-3) + T(8))) - T(T(03)))
30849 := (((9 + T(T(T(4)))) - (80)) × T(T(3)))
30855 := (55 × T((T(8) - 03)))
30884 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) × (8 + T(03)))
30885 := (-T(5)) × (-T((8 × 8)) + T(T(03)))
30888 := (T(8) × ((T(T(8)) - (T(80)))/(-3)))
30928 := (8 × ((2 + T(90)) - T(T(T(3)))))
30996 := ((T((6 × 9)) - 9) × T(T(03)))
31122 := -((((T(2)^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(11))) × T(T(3))))
31127 := (((T(T(7)) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1)) + 1)/3)
31143 := (((-3) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))) + 1) × T(T(3))
31144 := (T((4 × 4)) × (-((1 + 1) + T(T(T(3)))))
31157 := (-T(7)) - (T((T(T(5)) - (T(11)))) × (-T(T(3))))
31164 := ((T((T((4 + 6)) - 1)) - 1) × T(T(3)))
31182 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 + 1))) - 1) × 3)
31185 := (T(((T(5) + T(8)) + T((1 + 1))) × T(T(3)))
31197 := (((T(7) × T(T(9))) + T(T(11))) + T(3))
31206 := ((T((60 - T(T(2)))) + 1) × T(T(3)))
31213 := (((T(3) + 1)^{T(2)}) × T(13))
31215 := (-T(5)) × (-1) - T((2^{T(1×3)})))
31227 := (((T((T(7) + T(2))) × T(2)) - 1) × T(T(3)))
31228 := -((T(T((8 + 2))) - (2^{T(-1+T(3))})))
31234 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(T(3)) + 2)) - T(T(13)))
31235 := (((5^{T(3)}) × 2) - T((-1) + T(3)))
31239 := (9 × ((T(T(T(3))) × T((T(T(2)) - 1))) + T(3)))
31242 := (2 × (-4) + ((T(T(2)) - 1)^{T(3)})))
31245 := (T(5) × (T((4²⁺¹)) + 3))
31248 := ((8 + T(T(4))) × T((T(2) + T((1 + T(3)))))
31249 := ((T(94) × (T(T(2)) + 1)) - T(3))
31261 := (-1) - ((T(T(6)))/(-T(2))) × T(T((1 + T(3))))
31262 := (2 × (6 + ((T(T(2)) - 1)^{T(3)})))
31263 := ((-3) + (-T(T(6))) × T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))))/(-3)
31265 := (((5⁶) × 2) + T((-1) + T(3)))
31267 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(6)))/T(2)) + (-1) + T(3))
31269 := (((T((9 × 6)) + T(2)) + 1) × T(T(3)))
31272 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7)))/T(2)) + T((1 + 3)))
31276 := (T(6) - (-7) × T((T(2) + T(13))))
31298 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(9) + 2)) - (1 + 3))
31325 := ((T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(13))
31326 := (6 × (T(T((T(2) × 3))) + T(T(13))))
31328 := (8 × T(((T(2) - T(3)) + T(13))))
31329 := ((T((9 × 2)) + T(3))⁻¹⁺³)
31331 := (T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + (31³))
31334 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((3 + (31³))))
31353 := (T(T(3)) × (5 - (T(31) × (-3))))
31361 := ((T(16) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((1 + 3))))
31365 := ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(T(6)))/T(T(3)))) × T((-1) + T(3)))
31374 := ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) × T(((3 × 1)³)))
31375 := (T(T(5)) - (-7) × T((3 + T(13))))
31383 := (3 × ((T(83) + 1) × 3))
31387 := (T((7 × 8)) + ((31³)))
31388 := ((T((8 + 8)) × T(T(T(3)))) - T((1 + T(3))))
31389 := ((9 × (T(83) + 1)) + T(3))
31392 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(9)))/(-3)) × T(13))
31394 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) × T(T(3))) - (1³))
31395 := ((T((5 × 9))/3) × T(13))
31398 := -((T(T(8)) + ((T(T(9)) × (-31)) + T(T(3))))
31413 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T((1 + T((4 + 1)))) - 3)
31416 := (T(T(6)) × T(((14 - 1) + 3)))
31422 := (T(T(2)) - (-T((2⁴))) × T(T(T((1 × 3))))
31423 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T((2⁴))) + (1 + T(3)))
31425 := ((T(T(5)) × 2) + (T((T(T(4)) - 1)) × T(T(3))))
31426 := ((T(T(6)) × T((2⁴))) + T((1 + 3)))
31428 := (T(8) × (T(T(2)) + ((T(41) + T(3))))
31429 := ((9 × T((T(2)⁴))) + T(T(T((1 + 3))))
31434 := ((T(4) + T(T(3))) × (T(T((T(4) - 1))) - T(T(3))))
31436 := (((T(T(6)) × T((T(3) + T(4)))) - 1) + T(T(3)))
31437 := ((T(T(7)) × T((3 × 4))) - T(T(T((1 × 3))))
31438 := (((T(T(8)))/(-T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (1 + T(T(3)))
31455 := (T(5) × ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(4) + 1)))) + T(3))
31458 := (((8 + 5) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))) × T(T(3)))

- 31466** := $(T((6 \times 6)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (1 - T(T(3))))$
31479 := $((-97) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) \times T(T(3))$
31482 := $(T((-2) + T(T((8 - 4)))) \times (1 + T(T(3))))$
31485 := $(-T(T(5))) - (((T(8) - T(T(T(4)))) - 1) \times T(T(3)))$
31488 := $(8 \times ((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times T((1 \times 3))))$
31489 := $((T(T(9) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((1 \times 3))))$
31524 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(5) + 1)) \times T(3)))$
31531 := $(((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T((T(5) + 1)))) - T(T(3))$
31535 := $(53 \times T((T(T((5 - 1))) - T(T(3))))$
31536 := $((6 + T(3)) \times T((51 + T(T(3))))$
31542 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-((T(T(4)) - T(51))) + T(T(T(3))))$
31548 := $(-T(T(8))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 1)) \times (-T(T(3))))$
31552 := $(T((T(T(2)) + (5 + 5))) \times (1 + T(T(T(3))))$
31575 := $((-T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(5) \times (1 - T(3)))$
31577 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((7 + 5))) - T(13))$
31582 := $(-2) - ((T(8) - T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(3)))$
31584 := $(T(((4 \times 8) + T(5))) \times T((1 + T(3))))$
31587 := $((T(7) \times T((-8) + T(T((5 - 1)))))) + 3$
31593 := $((T(T(3)) - T(9)) \times (-T(51))) - T(T(T(3)))$
31596 := $(-6) \times ((-9) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(13))$
31597 := $(T(79) \times T((5 - 1))) - 3$
31599 := $(9 \times (-((T(9) \times T(5))) + T(T(13))))$
31605 := $((T(50) + T(T(6))) - 1) \times T(T(3))$
31625 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times T((T(6) + (1^3))))$
31626 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + T(T((6 - 1)))) \times T(T(3))$
31629 := $((T(9) \times T((T(2 + 6) + 1))) - T(3))$
31635 := $((T(5) \times T((36 + 1))) \times 3)$
31646 := $((T(T(6) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - T((1 + T(T(3))))$
31647 := $((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6))) \times (1 \times 3)$
31653 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T((-5) + T(6)) + 1)) + T(3))$
31662 := $((T((2 \times 6)) \times T(T((6 + 1)))) - T(3))$
31664 := $(-4) - (-T((6 + 6)) \times T(T((1 + T(3))))$
31667 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((6 + 6))) - (1^3))$
31668 := $((8 - T(6)) \times T(T((6 + 1)))) \times (-T(3))$
31671 := $(T(17) \times (T((T(6) - 1)) - 3))$
31684 := $((T(4) + (8 \times T(6)))^{-1+3})$
31686 := $(6 \times (T(86) + T(T(T((1 + 3))))))$
31688 := $(T((8 + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) - ((1 - 3))))$
31694 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(9)) \times (T(6) - 1)) - T(3)$
31695 := $(T(5) \times ((-9) + T(61)) + T(T(T(3))))$
31723 := $((T((T(3) \times 2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((1 + 3))))$
31724 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7) \times (1 + T(T(3))))$
31725 := $((T((T(5) - T(2))) \times (T(T(7) + 1)) - T(T(3)))$
31731 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - (T(7) + 1)) \times T(T(3)))$
31735 := $((T((T(5) + 3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T((1 + 3))))$
31742 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(7)))) - T((1 + 3)))$
31743 := $((T((3 \times 4)) \times (T(T(7) + 1))) - 3)$
31746 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T((4 + 7)))) \times 13)$
31747 := $(((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7) - (-1) + T(3))$
31749 := $((9 \times T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) - 1) \times 3$
31752 := $((T(T(2 \times 5))) - T(T(7))) \times T((1 + T(3)))$
31758 := $(((-T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(7) - 1))) + T(3))$
31759 := $((T((T(T(9))/T(5))) + T(7)) \times 13)$
31764 := $(-4) \times ((-T(6)) \times T((T(7) - 1))) - 3)$
31773 := $((T(T(3 + 7))) - (T(7) - 1)) \times T(T(3))$
31774 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(7) + (1 + T(T(3))))$
31779 := $((9 + (T(7) \times T((T(7) - 1)))) \times 3)$
31782 := $(2 \times ((T(8) \times T((T(7) + 1))) + T(T(T(3))))$
31784 := $(-4) \times (-8) - (T((T(7) - 1)) \times T(T(3)))$
31788 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(8)) + (7)) + T((-1) + T(T(3))))$
31794 := $((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(9) - 71))) \times T(T(3)))$
31822 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((2 \times 8))) + T(T((1 + T(3))))$
31824 := $((4 \times T(T(2))) \times T((T(8 + 1)) + T(3)))$
31836 := $((T((T(6) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(8) - 1)) + T(T(T(3))))$
31848 := $((T(T(8)) \times 48) - T(T((-1) + T(3))))$
31857 := $(7 \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(8)) + T(T(T((1 \times 3))))$
31869 := $(9 \times ((T(6) - T(T(8))) + T(T(13))))$
31878 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T((T(8) - 1)) \times T(T(3))))$
31884 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - (8 \times (-8) + T(T(13))))$
31886 := $((T(T(6) + T(T(8))) \times T(8)) - T(T((1 + T(3))))$
31927 := $(T(7) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(9 + 1))) - T(T(3))))$
31934 := $(-((T(T(4 + 3))) - (T(T(9 + 1))) \times T(T(3))))$
31935 := $(((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-91)) - T(3)$
31937 := $(-((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9 + 1)))) + 3))$
31941 := $((T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + T((9 - 1))) \times T(T(3))$
31943 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 9) - T(T((1 + T(3))))$
31947 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times 91) + T(3)$
31948 := $((8 \times T(T((4 + 9)))) - T(T(T((1 + 3))))$
31962 := $((T(2) \times (-6)) + T(T((9 + 1)))) \times T(T(3))$
31968 := $((8 \times 6) \times T((9 \times (1 + 3))))$
31974 := $((T(T(4)) - (7)) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) + T(3)$
31979 := $((T(9) - T(T(7))) + (T(T((9 + 1))) \times T(T(3))))$
31983 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((8 + 9) - T(T(T((1 + 3))))$
31986 := $(-6) \times ((-8) \times T(T((9 - 1))) - 3)$
31989 := $(((-T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) - T((1 \times 3))$
31992 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times ((9 + 1) + T(T(3)))$
31995 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(9) + T(T(9 - 1)))) \times (-3)$
31998 := $((T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(9)) + (1 \times 3)$
32024 := $(4 \times ((20^{T(2)}) + T(3)))$
32025 := $((-T(5)) + T(T((20/2)))) \times T(T(3))$
32046 := $(-T(T(6))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(02)) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32049 := $((T(9) \times T(40)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
32064 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(023))$
32079 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(02))) - T(3))$

- 32085** := $((-5) + T(8)) \times T(T((T(02) \times 3)))$
32109 := $((T(T(9+01))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))$
32124 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T((1+2))^3)$
32131 := $(T((1+T(T(3)))) \times (1+(T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))))$
32136 := $((6+T(T((T(3)+1)))) \times T((2 \times T(3))))$
32137 := $(T(7) + ((T(T(T(3+1)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
32145 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T((1+T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32147 := $((7+T(4)) \times T((T(T(1+T(2)))) + T(3)))$
32148 := $((((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) - 1) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 3$
32154 := $((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) \times T((-1+T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3))))$
32164 := $((T(T(4)) - T(6)) \times T((1+(2 \times T(3))))$
32169 := $((9 \times (T(6) - 1))^2) - T(T(T(3)))$
32172 := $(-T(T(T(2)))) - ((7 - T(T(T(1+T(2)))) \times T(T(3)))$
32175 := $(T(5) \times T((71 - (2 \times 3))))$
32193 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(9+1))) - T(T(2))) - T(T(3)))$
32212 := $(-2) - ((T(T(T(1+T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32214 := $((T(T((4+1) \times 2)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)))$
32224 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((-2+T(3)))$
32229 := $(-T(T(9))) + (((2 \times T(T(2)))^2) \times T(T(T(3))))$
32232 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((2 \times 2^3)))$
32235 := $((-5) + T(T((3+2) \times 2))) \times T(T(3))$
32238 := $((T(T(8)) + T(32)) \times (T(2)^3)$
32241 := $(((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T((2 \times T(3))))$
32242 := $(((-T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(T(T(2))))/3))$
32243 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4)) - 2)) - T(T((-2+T(3))))$
32244 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (2 \times T(3)))$
32245 := $(((-5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((-2+T(3)))$
32248 := $(-8) - ((4^2) \times T((T(2) \times T(T(3))))$
32249 := $(-T((9+4))) - (T(T(T(2+2)))) \times (-T(T(3)))$
32253 := $((-3) - (T(T(5))^2)) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})$
32254 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 5) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (-2+T(T(3))))$
32256 := $(T(6) \times ((5+T(2))^{T(2)} \times 3))$
32259 := $(T(9) + ((T(T((5 \times 2))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))))$
32262 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T((6-2)))) - (T((2 \times T(3))))$
32263 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((6-2)))) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/3))$
32264 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) - (-2+T((2 \times T(3))))$
32265 := $((T(T(5)) \times 6) - T(2)) \times T((T(2) \times 3))$
32272 := $(-((T(T(2) + T(7))) - (2^{T(2+3)})))$
32274 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) \times (T(2) \times T(3)))$
32276 := $((T(6) \times T(T((7+T(2)))) - (2^{T(3)}))$
32277 := $((T(7) \times T((7+T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(T(3))$
32283 := $(T(3) + ((T(T((8+2))) - T(2)) \times T(T(3))))$
32284 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(8) - 2))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32286 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T((2^{T(2)})) - (T(3)))$
32288 := $((8+8) \times (2+T((T(2) \times T(T(3))))$
32289 := $(-9) + ((T(T((8+2))) - 2) \times T(T(3)))$
32292 := $((T(T(2)) - T(9)) \times (-T(2) \times T(T(23))))$
32294 := $(-((T(T(4)) - 9)) - (T(T(T(2+2)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32295 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))$
32298 := $((T((8+T(9)+2) - 2) \times T(T(3)))$
32303 := $(-((T(30) - (32^3)))$
32304 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(03))) - T((2^3)))$
32312 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(1+3)))) - T((T(T(T(2))))/3))$
32313 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(1+3)))) - (T(2)^3)$
32314 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(T(3))) - (2+3))$
32316 := $((T(6) \times T(T(T(1+3)))) - (T(2) + T(T(3))))$
32319 := $((9 \times T(T(1 \times 3))) \times T((T(2) \times T(3))))$
32321 := $((T(T(T(1+T(2)))) \times T(T(3))) - (-2+T(T(3))))$
32322 := $((T(T(T(2+2))) \times T(T(3))) - (T(2) \times T(3)))$
32324 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(3) + T((-2+T(3))))$
32325 := $((T(T(5 \times 2)) \times T(T(3))) - T(2+3))$
32327 := $(-7) - ((-T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + T(3))$
32328 := $((T(T(8+2)) \times T(T(3))) - (2 \times T(3)))$
32329 := $(-((9+2) - (-T(T(3))) \times T(T(T((-2+T(3))))))$
32331 := $((T(T(T(1+3))) \times T(T(3))) - (T(2) \times 3))$
32332 := $((T(T(T((-2+T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) - (2^3))$
32333 := $((T(T(3))/(-3)) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((-2+T(3))))))$
32334 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) - ((3^2) - 3))$
32335 := $(-5) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((3-2+3))))$
32337 := $((T(T(7+3)) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(2) - T(3)))$
32338 := $(-8) - ((-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((T(3) - 2)))) - T(3))$
32351 := $((T(T(T((-1-5)))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3))))$
32352 := $((T(T(2 \times 5)) \times T(T(3))) + (2 \times T(3)))$
32355 := $((T(55) \times T(T(3))) + T(2+3))$
32356 := $((T(6) - 5) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((-2+T(3))))))$
32357 := $(-((T(T(7)) + ((5 - (32^3))))$
32359 := $((T(T(T(9-5))) \times T(T(3))) + (-2+T(T(3))))$
32361 := $((1+T(T(T((6/3+2)))) \times T(T(3)))$
32362 := $((2^{T(6)-T(3)}) - T(T((T(T(T(2))))/3))$
32364 := $((T(T((4+6))) \times T(T(3))) + T(2) + T(T(3)))$
32367 := $((T(T(7)) + 6) \times T((T(3) \times 2))) + T(T(T(3)))$
32373 := $((T(T(T(3)))/7) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((-2+T(3))))))$
32374 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(7+T(3))) - T(T(2)))) - T(T(3)))$
32375 := $(5 \times (7 + (T(T(T(3))/T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
32376 := $(-6) \times ((T(73) \times (-2)) + T(3))$
32379 := $((T(9) \times (7-3))^2) - T(T(3))$
32382 := $((T(2) \times ((8^3) + 2)) \times T(T(3)))$
32384 := $((T(T(4)) - T((T(8) - 3))) \times (-2^{T(3)}))$
32385 := $(-T(T(5))) - ((-T(8)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times 2))) + 3$
32387 := $((T(7) - T(T(8)))/(-T(3))) \times (2+T(T(T(3))))$
32388 := $((T(8) \times T((T(8) + T(3)))) - T(T(2+3)))$
32394 := $((4 \times T(9))^{T(3)/T(2)}) - T(3)$

$$\begin{aligned} 32395 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(9) \times T(3))) - (2 + 3)) \\ 32397 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((9 + 3))) + ((T(2))^{T(3)})) \\ 32399 &:= ((T(9) \times (9^3)) - T((T(T(T(2))))/3)) \\ 32401 &:= (T(10) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(3))) \\ 32402 &:= (20 - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32403 &:= ((3 + T(T(T(04)))) \times T((2 \times 3))) \\ 32406 &:= (-60) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32407 &:= (70 + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 3)) \\ 32408 &:= ((T(80) \times T(4)) + (2^3)) \\ 32409 &:= (90 + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 32413 &:= (((T(T(3))^{1 \times 4}) - T(2))/T(3)) \\ 32414 &:= (((T(T((4 - 1)))^4) + T(2))/T(3)) \\ 32415 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-1) - (T(4) \times (T(T(2))^3)) \\ 32416 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (-1) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((-2) + T(3))) \\ 32417 &:= ((-T((7 - 1))^4) - T(T(T(2))))/(-T(3)) \\ 32418 &:= (T(8) - (((-1) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 2) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32421 &:= (((1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 3 \\ 32422 &:= (-2) - (((-T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3))) \\ 32423 &:= (T(3) - (((T(T(T(2)))^4) + T(T(T(2))))/(-T(3))) \\ 32424 &:= ((4 + T(T((2 \times 4) + 2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32425 &:= (T(5) - (((T(T(T(2)))^4) - T(T(T(2))))/(-T(3))) \\ 32426 &:= ((T(6) + 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32427 &:= (((7 - T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 3 \\ 32428 &:= (82 + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(3)) \\ 32429 &:= ((T(9) + 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32431 &:= (T((1 + T(3))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32433 &:= (-33) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32434 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(4)^2) - T(3))) \\ 32435 &:= (53 - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32437 &:= (T(7) - (((-3) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32439 &:= (T((9 + 3)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32442 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - (((-4) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 3)) \\ 32443 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(4)^2) + 3)) \\ 32444 &:= (((-T(T(4))) \times T((4 + T(T(4))))/(-T(2))) - T(3)) \\ 32445 &:= ((T(5) \times ((T(4) \times T(4)) + T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32446 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(4)^2) + T(3))) \\ 32448 &:= (((T((8 + 4)) \times 4)^2)/3) \\ 32449 &:= ((-9) + T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32451 &:= (((1 \times 5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(3) \\ 32452 &:= ((-2) - T(T(5))) \times (T(4) - T(23)) \\ 32453 &:= ((-T(T(3))) \times (-5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (2^3) \\ 32454 &:= (T((T(4) + 5))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32455 &:= ((T(T(5)) - 5) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T((2 \times 3)))) \\ 32456 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (-5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3))) \\ 32457 &:= (75 - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 32458 &:= (((8^5) - T(4)) - T((T(2) + T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32472 &:= (T(T(2)) - (((-T(7)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32473 &:= (((T(T(T(3) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32474 &:= (((-T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-4 \times 2)) - (T(3)) \\ 32475 &:= (-5) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(4) \times (-2^3))) \\ 32476 &:= (((-T(6)) \times (-7) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))) \\ 32477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (74 + T(T(2)))) - 3) \\ 32478 &:= (((8 \times T(T(7))) \times T(4)) - (T(T(2))/3)) \\ 32479 &:= (T((9 + 7)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 3)) \\ 32508 &:= (T(8) \times T((05 + 2) \times T(3))) \\ 32522 &:= (((T(T(2)) + (2^{T(5)})) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32523 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - (((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(23)))) \\ 32524 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)) + (2^{T(3)}))) \\ 32525 &:= (((-T(5) - ((2^{T(5)} + T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32526 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) - 2) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32527 &:= (((-7) + ((2^{T(5)} - T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32528 &:= (T(8) + ((2^{T(5)} - T(23))) \\ 32529 &:= ((-9) - T(T((2 \times 5))) \times (-T((2 \times 3)))) \\ 32531 &:= (((-1) - 3)^{T(5)} - T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 32534 &:= ((((-4) + T(3))^{T(5)} - T(2)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32535 &:= (-T(5)) \times (((T(3) \times T(T(5))) + T(2)) \times (-3)) \\ 32537 &:= (((-T(7) + T(3)) - ((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32538 &:= (T((T(8) - 3)) \times (52 + T(3))) \\ 32543 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((5 + 2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32544 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times T(T((5 - 2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32545 &:= (-5) - (((-T(4)) - T(T((5 \times 2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32546 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5^2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32547 &:= (((7 \times T(4)) \times T((T(5) \times 2))) - 3) \\ 32552 &:= ((2^{T(5)} - (T((5 - 2))^3)) \\ 32553 &:= ((-3) - T(5)) - (((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32556 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) + (T(T((5 \times 2))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32557 &:= (7 \times (-5) + T(((T(5) \times T(T(2))) + T(3)))) \\ 32558 &:= ((8^5) - T((5 + T((2 + 3)))) \\ 32562 &:= ((T((2 + T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - 2)) - (T(3))) \\ 32563 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))) - (2^3)) \\ 32564 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) - (5 + 2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32565 &:= (((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(T((5 - 2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32566 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))) - (2 + 3)) \\ 32567 &:= ((-7) - ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) - 3)) \\ 32568 &:= (8 \times ((T(6) - T(52)) \times (-3)) \\ 32571 &:= ((1 + (T(7) \times 5)) \times T(T((2 \times 3)))) \\ 32572 &:= (((T(2)^7) \times T(5)) - 2) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 32573 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(7) \times 5)) + 2) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32574 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) + T((T(5) - T(2)))) \times 3) \\ 32577 &:= (((-T((-7) + T(7))) \times (-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(3)) \\ 32578 &:= (((T(8) - T(7))^5) - T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32579 &:= (((T(9) - ((7^5) \times T(T(2))))/3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32582 &:= (2 \times (T(T(8)) + ((5^2)^3))) \\ 32584 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((8 \times T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 32585 &:= -(((T(T(5)) - 8^5) + (T(2) \times T(T(3)))))) \\ 32586 &:= (-((T(6) - T(8)) - ((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 32587 &:= (-(((T(T(7)) - 8^5) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32588 &:= ((T(8) + 8^5) - (T(T(2))^3)) \\ 32589 &:= (-T(9) - (T(T(8)) \times (-52 - 3))) \\ 32592 &:= (((T(2) + 9) + T(T((5 \times 2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32595 &:= (T(5) - (T(9) \times (5 - (T(2)^{T(3)})))) \\ 32597 &:= (((-((7 - 9))^{T(5)}) - T((T(2) \times T(3)))) \\ 32598 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) + T(((T(5) - T(2)) \times T(3)))) \\ 32625 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))) - T((2^3))) \\ 32627 &:= (7 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - T((-2) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 32628 &:= ((T(8) \times T((2 \times T(6)))) + T(T(2 + 3))) \\ 32634 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(3)) \times T(((6 \times 2) \times 3)) \\ 32635 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) + (2^{T(3)})) \\ 32637 &:= (((T(7) + T(T(3))) \times T((6^2))) + 3) \\ 32652 &:= (-T(2) - ((T(5) + T(T(T((6 - 2)))) \times (-T(T(3)))))) \\ 32654 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(6)) + ((2 - 3))) \\ 32655 &:= (((T(55) + T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32669 &:= (((T(96) \times T(6)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/3) \\ 32676 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(7)) \times 6) + 2) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32679 &:= (T(9) - (-((T(7) + T(6))) \times T(T(2^3)))) \\ 32684 &:= (-((T(T(4)) + (-T(8)) \times T((T(6) \times 2)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32685 &:= ((T(5) - (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})) \\ 32688 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(8)) + T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times T(3))) \\ 32697 &:= (7 \times (T(96) + T(2 + 3))) \\ 32704 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(07) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(3)))) \\ 32708 &:= (((80 \times T(T(7))) - T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32712 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(T((7 - 2))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32718 &:= ((81 \times (T(T(7)) - 2)) - T(3)) \\ 32719 &:= ((T((9 + 1)) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32722 &:= ((T(T((2 + 2))) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) - 3) \\ 32724 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) \times T(7)))) - T(T(2)))/T(3)) \\ 32725 &:= (T((5 \times 2)) \times T((T(7) + (2 \times 3)))) \\ 32726 &:= (-((T(6) - (2^{T(7-2)}))) - T(T(3))) \\ 32728 &:= ((T((T(8) - 2)) \times T(7 + T(2))) + 3) \\ 32729 &:= -((T(9) - (2^{T(7-2)}) + T(3))) \\ 32731 &:= ((T(T((1 + 3))) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) + T(3)) \\ 32733 &:= ((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times T((T(7) + T(2)))) - 3) \\ 32734 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(3) + T(7)))) + (T(2) \times 3)) \\ 32736 &:= (((T(T(6))/T(T(3))) \times T((T(7) + T(2)))) \times T(3)) \\ 32738 &:= ((T((8 \times T(3))) \times T(7)) - T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32739 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(7) + T(2))) + 3) \\ 32742 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) - (-2) + T(3))) \\ 32743 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) + ((T(2) - T(3))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32744 &:= (-4) \times (-((4^7)/2) + T(3)) \\ 32745 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) \times T(2)))))/T(3)) \\ 32746 &:= (T(6) - ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) \times T(2))))/(-T(3)))) \\ 32747 &:= (T(7) - ((-T(T(4))) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) + T(3))) \\ 32749 &:= (T((-9) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((2 \times T(3)))) \\ 32752 &:= ((2^{T(5)}) + ((7 - 23))) \\ 32755 &:= (((-((T(5) \times T(5))) + T(T(7))^2) - T(3)) \\ 32758 &:= (((8^5) - 7) + T(2)) - T(3) \\ 32759 &:= (-9) + (-((5 - 7)^{T(2+3)})) \\ 32762 &:= ((2^{6+7+2}) - T(3)) \\ 32764 &:= (-4) + (((6 + T(7)) - 2)^3) \\ 32767 &:= (T(T(7)) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7 + T(2)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 32769 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(T(6)))/7) + (-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32774 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2))))/(-3))) \\ 32775 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-T((7 + 7)) - T((2^{T(3)}))) \\ 32781 &:= (((1 - T(8)) + T((T(7) \times 2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32783 &:= (T(T(3)) - (-((8^7-2) + T(3))) \\ 32784 &:= ((T(4) + (8^{7-2})) + T(3)) \\ 32786 &:= (T(6) + (((8^7-2) - 3))) \\ 32787 &:= ((7 \times ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(3)) \\ 32793 &:= ((T(3) + T(9)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 32796 &:= (((T((-6) + T(9))) \times 7) + T(T(2))) \times T(3) \\ 32799 &:= ((T(9) \times (T((9 - 7))^{T(T(2))}) - T(3)) \\ 32802 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T((08 \times 2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32823 &:= (((T(T(3)) + 2) + T(T((8 + 2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32824 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32825 &:= (5 \times (((T(2)^8) - 2) + T(3))) \\ 32826 &:= (T(6) + ((T(2)^8) \times (2 + 3))) \\ 32832 &:= ((2^{T(3)}) + (8^{2+3})) \\ 32834 &:= (T((-T(4)) + T(T(3))) + ((8^{2+3})) \\ 32838 &:= (T(8) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T((8 \times 2)) + T(3)))) \\ 32842 &:= (-2) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (8 \times T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32844 &:= ((T(T(4)) + ((4^8)/2) + T(T(3))) \\ 32845 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T((8 + 2)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 32846 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((8^{T(2)}) - T(3))) \\ 32847 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(48) - T(2))) + 3) \\ 32848 &:= ((8 \times T(4)) + (8^{2+3})) \\ 32851 &:= (1 + (T(5) \times (T(T((8 + T(2)))) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 32852 &:= (((2^{T(5)}) - T(8)) + T(T(2 + 3))) \\ 32853 &:= ((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times ((8 - T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 32854 &:= (4 + (T(5) \times (T(T((8 + T(2)))) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 32855 &:= (5 + (T(5) \times (T(T((8 + T(2)))) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 32856 &:= (((T((6 + 5)) + 8)^2) \times T(3)) \\ 32857 &:= (((T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + T(2))/3) \\ 32858 &:= ((8^5) + (T((8 - T(2))) \times T(3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32859 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T((T(5) + T(8))) \times (-T(2)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 32865 &:= (T(5) \times (((T(6) - 8)^{T(2)}) - T(3))) \\ 32867 &:= (((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + 2) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32868 &:= (T(8) \times (T((6 + T(8))) + T((-2) + T(3)))) \\ 32873 &:= (T((T(T(3)) - (7))) + ((8^{2+3})) \\ 32878 &:= (-8) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + T((T(2) \times 3)))) \\ 32885 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((8^{8-T(2)}) - 3)) \\ 32886 &:= ((T((6 + T(8))) \times T(8)) + T((T(2)^3))) \\ 32889 &:= ((9 \times T((88 - T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32892 &:= -((T(2) - (9 \times T((82 + 3)))) \\ 32894 &:= ((4^9)/8) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32895 &:= ((T((5 \times (9 + 8))) \times T(2)) \times 3) \\ 32897 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(3))) \\ 32904 &:= (4 \times ((0 - T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2)))^3))) \\ 32907 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (09^2)) + T(T(3))) \\ 32922 &:= ((T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2))) \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32924 &:= (-4) - (-T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T((T(T(T(2)))/3))) \\ 32925 &:= (T((5 \times T(2))) + (T(9) \times (T(2)^{T(3)}))) \\ 32927 &:= ((T(7) \times T((T(2) + T(9)))) + ((2 - 3))) \\ 32928 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times ((T(9) - 2) + T(3))) \\ 32931 &:= ((T((1 + T(3))) \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) + 3) \\ 32934 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times (9 \times 2)) - T(3)) \\ 32937 &:= ((T(7) \times T((3 + T(9)))) + (T(2) \times 3)) \\ 32943 &:= ((T((T(3) \times T(4))) \times (9 \times 2)) + 3) \\ 32944 &:= (4 \times ((T(4) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2)))^3))) \\ 32946 &:= ((T((6 \times T(4))) \times (9 \times 2)) + (T(3))) \\ 32949 &:= (9 \times (T((4 + (9^2))) + T(3))) \\ 32952 &:= (((T(2) \times T((T(5) + T(9)))) + 2) \times T(3)) \\ 32955 &:= (T(5) \times (-((5 - (9 \times 2))^3)) \\ 32958 &:= ((-T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(9)))) + (T(2) \times T(3)) \\ 32964 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(6) + 9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32973 &:= ((T(3) \times T(7)) + (T(9) \times (T(2)^{T(3)}))) \\ 32975 &:= (5 \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(3)))) \\ 32977 &:= (T(7) + ((T(7) \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32978 &:= ((8 \times (T(7) + T((T(9) \times 2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32979 &:= (T(9) + ((T(7) \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) + T(3))) \\ 32982 &:= ((-T(2)) - T((8 + T(9)))) \times (-23) \\ 32985 &:= ((5 \times T(8)) + (T(9) \times (T(2)^{T(3)}))) \\ 32988 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(8)) \times (T(9) + 2)) - T(3)) \\ 32991 &:= (((-1 - 9) \times T((T(9) \times 2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 32994 &:= ((T(4) \times T((9 \times 9))) - (T(T(2))^3)) \\ 32999 &:= (((T(T(9))/T(9)) + 9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 33012 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(10)) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33015 &:= (T(5) \times (-10) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 33033 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/3))) \\ 33048 &:= ((-T(8)) \times T((-4) + T(T(03)))) \times (-T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33066 &:= ((T(6) - (T(60) \times (-3))) \times T(3)) \\ 33075 &:= (((5 + 70) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33123 &:= ((T((T(T(3)) + 2)) \times T(T((-1) + T(3)))) + 3) \\ 33124 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(2)) \times (T(T((1 + T(3)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33126 &:= ((T((T(6) + 2)) \times T(T((-1) + T(3)))) + T(3)) \\ 33129 &:= ((9^2) \times (T(T((1 + T(3)))) + 3)) \\ 33132 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(31)) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33135 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times ((1 + 3) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33137 &:= (-T(7)) + (T((T(3) - 1)) \times T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 33162 &:= (-T(2)) + (T((6 - 1)) \times T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 33165 &:= (T(5) \times T(T(((6 - 1) + 3) + 3))) \\ 33189 &:= ((T((T(9) + T(8))) \times T((1 + 3))) - T(T(3))) \\ 33214 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(3) \times T(3)))) \\ 33222 &:= ((T(T(T(2 + 2))) + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33225 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33228 &:= (-T(8)) + ((T(T(2)) \times (T(2) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33234 &:= ((-T(4)) + (T(32) \times T(T(3)))) \times 3) \\ 33237 &:= ((T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(2))) \times (3^3)) \\ 33242 &:= (((T(2) - (T(T(4))^2)) \times T(T(T(3))))/(-T(T(3)))) \\ 33243 &:= -((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T((2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(3)))))) \\ 33246 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times 4) \times T(T(2))) - 3) \times T(3) \\ 33247 &:= (-T(7)) + (((T(T(4))^2) \times T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3))) \\ 33249 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(4) + (T(2)^{T(3)}))) - T(3)) \\ 33252 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(5) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 33254 &:= (-T(4)) + (((T(T(5)) + T(2)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33255 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T((5 + (2 \times 3)))) + T(3))) \\ 33257 &:= ((T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (2^3)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33258 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2))) - (T(3)^{T(3)})) \\ 33262 &:= (-2) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times T(3))) \\ 33264 &:= ((T(4) + T((6 \times 2))) \times T((3^3))) \\ 33267 &:= (((7 \times T(6)) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 3) \\ 33274 &:= (T(4) + (((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) - 3) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33277 &:= ((7 \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) + T(3))) + T(3) \\ 33278 &:= ((8 \times T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 33279 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(7))) \times (T(T(2))^3)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33282 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(8^2)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3)) \\ 33285 &:= (T(5) \times (8 + T((2 \times 3)))) \\ 33286 &:= (-6) - (-82) \times T(T((T(T(3)))/3))) \\ 33288 &:= (8 \times (((T(8)/2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 3)) \\ 33294 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (3 \times 3)) \\ 33297 &:= (((T(7) - T(T(9))) - 2) \times (-33)) \\ 33315 &:= (T(5) \times (T((1 + 3)) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 33324 &:= ((T(4) + ((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3)) \\ 33327 &:= ((T((T(7) \times 2)) - (3 \times 3)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33336 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-T(3))) - 3) \times (-3 - T(T(3)))) \\ 33339 &:= ((T(9) \times T(((T(T(T(3)) - 3)/T(3)))) - T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

33342 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(3))) + T(33))
33344 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T((-4) + T(T(3))) × (3 - T(T(T(3))))))
33345 := ((T(5) × (T(4) + 3)) × T((3 × T(3))))
33347 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(3))) + T(T(3 × 3)))
33348 := ((-8) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) × T(T(3)))) × T(T(3))
33372 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) × ((3³) × 3))
33375 := ((5 × T(7)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(3 × 3))
33384 := (((4 × T(8)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T((-T(3) + T(T(3))))
33387 := (((T((7 × 8)) - T(3)) × T(T(3))) - 3)
33396 := ((T((T(6) + T(9))) × (-T(3) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3))))
33399 := ((T(9) + ((T(9) + 3) × T(T(T(3)))) × 3)
33411 := (((1 + T((1 + T(T(4)))) - T(3)) × T(T(3)))
33412 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 1) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)))) - T(3))
33421 := (((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)))) + 3)
33424 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(2) + T(T(4)))) - T(3)^{T(3)})
33432 := (((T(T((-2) + T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3) × T(T(3))
33435 := (((T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) × T((T(4) + T(3))) - T(T(3)))
33438 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(3)) × 4) × T(T((T(T(3))/3))))
33442 := ((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) × (-T(T(3))))
33452 := ((2^{T(5)}) + (4 × T((3 × T(3))))
33453 := ((-3) + T((5 × T(4) + T(3))) × T(T(3))
33454 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) × (-T(T(3))))
33456 := ((T(T(6)) + T(5)) × T((T(4) + (3 + 3))))
33459 := ((T(9) × ((T(T(5)) + 4) × T(3))) - T(T(3))
33462 := ((-T(26)) × (-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3))))/3)
33465 := ((T(5) × T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + T((3 + T(T(3))))
33467 := ((T(T(7)) × (6 - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))))
33468 := (T(T(8)) + (T(T(6)) × (T((T(4) + T(3))) + T(3))))
33474 := (((4 × T(T(7))) - (T(4) × 3)) × T(T(3))
33475 := (-((T(5) - T(7))) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3 × 3))))
33481 := (-1) + ((8 × T(T((T(4) + 3))) - T(3))
33482 := -((T(T(2)) - (8 × T(T((4 + (3 × 3))))))
33483 := (3 + (T(8) × ((4 × T(T(T(3))) + T(3))))
33484 := (-4) + (8 × T(T((4 + (3 × 3))))
33485 := (5 + (T(8) × ((4 × T(T(T(3))) + T(3))))
33486 := (6 + (T(8) × ((4 × T(T(T(3))) + T(3))))
33487 := (-7) - ((-8) × T(T((T(4) + 3))) - T(3))
33488 := (8 × T(T((8 - 4) + (3 × 3)))
33489 := -((T(9) - ((T(8) + T(4)) × (3^{T(3)})))
33491 := ((-((1 - 9)) × T(T((T(4) + 3))) + 3)
33492 := (((29 × T(T(4))) × T(T(3))) - 3)
33495 := -((T(5) × (T(9) - T((4³) + 3)))
33498 := (((-8) × T(T(9))) × (-4)) + (T(3³))
33516 := (T(6) × T((1 × 53) + 3))
33519 := (((9 + 1) × (T(5)³) - T(T(T(3))))
33522 := ((T((2 × T(2 + 5))) × T(T(3))) + T(3))

33525 := (T(5) × ((T(2) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) + T(T(3))))
33526 := ((T((T(6) + 2)) × T(T(5))) + T(T((T(T(3))/3)))
33528 := (8 × ((2 × T(T((5 + T(3)))) - T(T(T(3))))

33534 := ((T(4) + T((3 + 5))) × (3^{T(3)}))
33537 := ((T((7 × (3 + 5))) × T(T(3))) + T(T(3))
33552 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) + ((T(5) + 3)³))
33554 := ((T(4) × ((5⁵) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(3))
33555 := (T(5) × ((5 + T(T((5 + T(3)))) + T(T(3))))
33571 := (T(T((1 × 7))) + (T(5) × T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))))))
33572 := (2 × ((7⁵) - T((3 + 3)))
33578 := -((T(8) + ((-7⁵) × T(3))/3))
33582 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 8) × ((5 × T(T(T(3))) + 3))
33585 := (-T(5) - ((8 - T(5)) × T((3 + T(T(3))))))
33588 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(8) + T(5))) - T((3³)))
33594 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(9) + T(5))) × T(T(3))) - T(3))
33597 := ((-T(7)) × (-T(9) - (5 × T(T(T(3)))))) - 3)
33598 := ((-8) + T(T(9))) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))))
33642 := (((2 × T(T(4))) - T(6)) × T(3³))
33645 := -((T(5) - ((T(4) × 6) × T(33)))
33648 := (((-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(6)) - T(3))/T(3))
33657 := (((7 + T(56)) × T(T(3))) - T(3))
33669 := (9 × T(((T(T(6)) + (T(6) + T(3)))/3))
33675 := (T(5) × ((T(7) + T(T((T(T(6)))/T(T(3)))) + T(3))
33677 := -((T(T(7)) - ((7 × T(T(6))) + T(3))) × T(T(3)))
33684 := (-4) × ((-T(8)) × (T(T(6) + 3) + 3))
33687 := ((T((7 × 8)) × T(6)) + T((3 × T(3))))
33693 := (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(9)) - T(6)) × 33))
33696 := (-((T(6) - T(9))) × ((T(T(6)) + 3) × T(3))
33698 := ((89 - 6) × T(T((T(3))/3)))
33712 := (T((T(T(2)) + 1)) × (T((T(7) + T(T(3))) - T(T(3))))
33718 := (-8) + ((-1) + (7 × T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))))
33719 := (((9 - 1) × T(T((7 + T(3)))) + T(T(T(3))))
33722 := (2 × (-2) + (73 × T(T(T(3))))
33723 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (2 × 73)) - 3)
33726 := (T(T(6)) × (2 × (T(7) + T(3 × 3))))
33732 := (((-2) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-73) + T(3))
33733 := (((T(3) + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(7) + T(T(3))))/3)
33738 := (((8 × T(37)) × T(3)) - T(3))
33742 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(7) - T(3))) - T(3))
33744 := (-4) × (((4 - T(T(7))) × T(T(3))) + T(3))
33747 := (((T(T(7)) - 4) × (T(7) × 3)) - T(T(3))
33754 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(5) + 7)) + (-T(3)) × T(T(3)))
33759 := ((T(T(9)) - (5 + 7)) × 33)
33761 := ((1 + 6) × (-T(7)) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(3))))
33765 := (T(5) × (T(67) - (3³)))
33768 := (((-8) × T(T(6)) - T(7)) × (-3 × T(3))

- 33774** := $((T(T(4)) - T(7)) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(3) + T(3)))$
33775 := $(5 \times (-T(T(7))) + ((T(7) + 3) \times T(T(T(3))))$
33783 := $(-T(3)) + ((-8) + (7 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3)))$
33786 := $((-T(6)) \times (8 - (7 \times T(T(T(3)))) - 3)$
33789 := $((T(9) + T(8)) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3))))$
33792 := $(2^9) \times ((T(7) - T(3)) \times 3)$
33795 := $((T(5) \times T(T(9))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T((3 \times 3))))$
33798 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) + T(((T(7) \times 3) + 3))$
33814 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((1 + T(8)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))))$
33817 := $(T(T(7)) + ((1 + T(8)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))))$
33825 := $((5 + T(T(2))) \times (T(T((T(8)/3))) - T(3)))$
33848 := $(8 \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(8))) + T(3 \times 3)))$
33849 := $((T(T(9)) \times (4 \times 8)) + (3^{T(3)}))$
33852 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-5) + ((8 \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
33864 := $(T((T(4) + 6))) \times (83 \times 3)$
33873 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-7) + (T(8) \times T((3 \times 3))))$
33874 := $(-((T(T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times 83))) + T(T(T(3))))$
33879 := $(T(T(9)) + (T(7) \times (T((8 \times T(3)) - 3)))$
33888 := $(8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(((8 + T(3)) \times T(3))))$
33889 := $((T((9 + 8)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(3))))/3$
33891 := $(((-1) \times T(T(9))) + 8) \times (-33)$
33892 := $(-2) + (((T(9) \times T(8)) - T(3)) \times T(T(3)))$
33894 := $((((-T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(8)))/(-T(3))) \times T(T(3))$
33915 := $(-((T(T(5)) - 1)) \times ((-9) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(3))))$
33918 := $((T(T(8)) - 1) \times (T(9) + T(3))) + 3$
33922 := $((-2) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(9)) \times 33)$
33924 := $(((-4) - T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times 33$
33925 := $(-5) + (T(29) \times T((T(3) + T(3))))$
33926 := $(-((T(T(6)) - 2) + (T(T(9)) \times (-33))))$
33934 := $((T(4) - T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-33)))$
33936 := $(-T(6)) + ((-T(3)) + T(T(9))) \times 33$
33938 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9))) - T((T(T(3))/3)))$
33939 := $(9 \times ((3 \times T(T(9))) + T((T(3) \times T(3))))$
33942 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) - (9 - (T(3)^{T(3)})))$
33945 := $(T(T(5)) + ((-T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 33)$
33948 := $(T(8) \times (T(4) + 933))$
33957 := $((7 \times T((T(5) - 9))) \times T(T(3 + 3)))$
33963 := $((T(36) \times (T(9) + T(3))) - 3)$
33966 := $(T((6 \times 6)) \times (T(9) + (3 + 3)))$
33968 := $((T(T(8)) \times (6 + T(9))) + (T(3)/3)$
33969 := $((T(9) - T(T(6))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-33)))$
33975 := $((T(5) + T((7 + 9))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(3)))$
33978 := $((T(8) + T(T(7))) + T((T(9) + 3))) \times T(T(3))$
33984 := $((T(T(4)) + T(8)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(3) \times T(3))$
33987 := $((T((T(7) + 8)) \times (T(9) + T(3))) + T(T(3)))$
33993 := $(3 \times ((T(T(9)) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(3))^3))$
33999 := $((T(9) + T(9)) \times T((9 \times 3))) - T(T(3))$
34012 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(T(T(04))) + T(3)))$
34034 := $(-((4 - 30)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3))))$
34056 := $((T(6) + T(5)) \times T(043))$
34065 := $(T(5) \times (60 + T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))))$
34083 := $((3 + 80) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))$
34111 := $((1 + T(T(T((1 + 1)))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
34122 := $((T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))) \times (1 + T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))$
34125 := $(T(5^2)) \times T(((1 + T(4)) + 3))$
34128 := $(T(8) \times (2 + T((1 \times 43))))$
34132 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(3)) + 1) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))))$
34136 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(3))) - 1) \times T((T(4) + T(3)))$
34144 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((4 + 1)^4)) - T(T(T(3))))$
34146 := $((T((T(6) + 4)) \times T(14)) + T(T(3)))$
34155 := $((T(T(5)) + T(5)) \times T(((1^4) + T(T(3))))$
34158 := $((8 + T(5)) \times T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + 3$
34167 := $((7 \times T(T(6))) + T((1 \times 4))) \times T(T(3))$
34174 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T((7 + 1))) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(3)))))$
34176 := $((T(67) \times T((1 + 4))) + T(3))$
34179 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((7 + 1))) - T(T((4 \times 3)))$
34181 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) + (T((1 + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)))$
34182 := $(-T(T(2))) + (((T(8) + 1) \times 4) \times T(T(T(3))))$
34184 := $(-4) + (((T(8) + 1) \times 4) \times T(T(T(3))))$
34188 := $((T((-8) + T(8)) + 1) \times 4) \times T(T(3))$
34189 := $((((-T(9)) + T(T(8))) + 1) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))$
34197 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) \times (1 - T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))$
34209 := $(9 \times (T(T(T(T(02)))) + (T((4 \times T(T(3)))))$
34215 := $(T(5) \times (T((12 + T(T(4)))) + 3)$
34216 := $(T((6 + 1)) \times (-T(2)) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))))$
34218 := $(8 \times T((1 + T((T(2) + T(4))))) - T(3)$
34221 := $(T((12 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(3)))$
34224 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((2 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
34225 := $((-5) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 2)))^{-4+T(3)}$
34231 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))))$
34234 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) + T(2)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))))$
34237 := $(T(T((7 + T(3)))) - (T((-2) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
34244 := $((T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))))$
34248 := $(8 \times ((-4) + T((-2) + T(T(4)))) \times 3)$
34251 := $((T((15 - 2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)))$
34254 := $(T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3)))))$
34255 := $((T((T(5) + T(5)))/T(2)) \times (-T(4)) + T(T(T(3))))$
34263 := $(-((3^6)) \times ((2 - T(T(4))) + T(3)))$
34265 := $(((-5) - T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
34266 := $(((-T(6)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T((2^4))) - (T(3)))$
34268 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(6)/T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)$
34271 := $(-1) + (((T(T(7)) + 2) \times 4) \times T(T(3)))$
34272 := $((T(2) \times T(7)) \times T((2^4))) \times 3$

$$\begin{aligned} 34273 &:= (-T(T(3))) + ((T(7) \times T(-((T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))))) - T(3)) \\ 34275 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-7 - T((T(2) + (4^3)))) \\ 34276 &:= ((-6) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3) \\ 34278 &:= (((T(8) \times 7) \times T((2^4))) + T(3)) \\ 34279 &:= (((T(9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))))) + 3) \\ 34282 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(82) \times T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34284 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (8 \times (T(2) - (4^{T(3)})))) \\ 34287 &:= ((T((7 + T(8))) \times T((2 \times 4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34293 &:= ((-T((3 + 9))) + T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34294 &:= ((T(49) \times T((T(2) + (4)))) - (T(3))) \\ 34295 &:= (5 \times (((T(9)/T(2)) + (4)^3)) \\ 34296 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(9))^2) - T((4 \times T(3)))) \\ 34297 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((9 + 2) \times T(T((4 \times 3)))) \\ 34298 &:= ((8 \times (T(92) + T(4))) - T(3)) \\ 34299 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((9 \times (2^4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34314 &:= (((4 \times T(T((1 + T(3)))))) + T(4) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34315 &:= (T(5) + (T((1 + T(3))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))))) \\ 34334 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times T(T(3))) - (4^{T(3)})) \\ 34335 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(3 + 3))) \times (-T(4)) + T(T(3))) \\ 34338 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))) + (T((T(4) \times T(3)))) \\ 34339 &:= (((T(9) \times (3^{T(3)})) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(3)) \\ 34341 &:= ((T(T((1 + 4))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3)))) \\ 34342 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times ((T(3) + T(4)) + T(3))) \\ 34343 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((-4) + T(T(3)))) - ((T(4)^3)) \\ 34344 &:= (T((T(4) + 43)) \times (4 \times T(3))) \\ 34345 &:= ((-T(T(5))) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) + (4 + T(T(3)))) \\ 34348 &:= (-8) + ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T((3 + T(4)))) \times T(3)) \\ 34352 &:= (2 \times ((-5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 34353 &:= ((T(T((T(3) + 5))) + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 3) \\ 34354 &:= (T(4) + ((T(53) \times 4) \times T(3))) \\ 34356 &:= ((T(T((T(6) - (5 + 3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(3)) \\ 34359 &:= (T(9) + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) - T(3))) \\ 34362 &:= (T((T(2) \times T(6))) - ((-T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(3)) \\ 34368 &:= (8 \times ((T((6 + T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \\ 34374 &:= (-T(4)) + (-T(7)) \times (-3 - T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))))) \\ 34375 &:= ((5^{7-3}) \times T((4 + T(3)))) \\ 34376 &:= (((T(T(6)/7)^3) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 34377 &:= (((-T(7)) + T(T(7))) \times T((3 + T(4)))) - T(T(3)) \\ 34378 &:= (T(8) + ((T(7) - T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3))))) \\ 34383 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(3)))) \\ 34384 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((8 \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34385 &:= (((T(58) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(3)) \\ 34389 &:= (-((T(9) - T(83)) \times T(4)) - T(T(3))) \\ 34391 &:= (-T(T((1 + 9))) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3))) \\ 34392 &:= ((T((T(2) \times 9)) \times T((3 + T(4)))) - (T(3))) \\ 34394 &:= (-4) + (T((9 \times 3)) \times T((T(4) + 3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34395 &:= (5 \times ((T(9) \times T((T(T(3)) - (4)))) - T(3))) \\ 34397 &:= ((T(-((T(7) - T(9)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(43)) \\ 34398 &:= (T((T(8) - 9)) \times T((T(3) + (4 + 3)))) \\ 34412 &:= (T((T(T(2)) + 1)) \times (4 + T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))))) \\ 34418 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (-1) + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(3)) \\ 34419 &:= ((9 + (14 \times T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34435 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((4^3))) \\ 34437 &:= (((7 \times T(3)) \times T((T(4) \times 4))) - 3) \\ 34462 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(3))))) \\ 34464 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 34465 &:= (T(5) + ((T(6) + (4)) \times T((T(T(4)) - 3))) \\ 34468 &:= ((-T((8 \times 6))) - T(T(4))) \times (-T((4 + 3))) \\ 34472 &:= (((T(2)^7) - T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))) \\ 34474 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T((7 + T(4)) - (4)) \times T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34475 &:= (((T(5) + (7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))) \\ 34476 &:= (-6) \times ((-7) \times T((T(4) \times 4))) - (T(3))) \\ 34479 &:= ((T((9 + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T((T(4) + 3))) \\ 34482 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (-8) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(4) \times (-3)))) \\ 34485 &:= (T(5) \times ((T((8 \times 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34488 &:= (T(8) \times ((8 + 4) + T(43))) \\ 34489 &:= (((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(4) + 3))) \\ 34493 &:= ((T(T(3)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(4) \times T(4)))) / (-3)) \\ 34495 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(4) \times T(4))) / (-3)) \\ 34496 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(9))) - T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(3))) \\ 34498 &:= (((-8) \times T(T(9))) \times (-4)) + T((T(T(4)) - 3)) \\ 34517 &:= (-T(7)) + ((-T((-1) + T(5))) - T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 34521 &:= (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5) \times T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \\ 34524 &:= (42 \times ((T(5) \times T(T(4))) - 3)) \\ 34525 &:= (-((5^{T(2)})) + ((T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34528 &:= ((T(T(8)) + ((T(2) - 5))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)) \\ 34534 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (3 + (5^4))) - (T(3))) \\ 34536 &:= ((6^3) + (-T(T(5))) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34537 &:= (((T(7)^3) - T(T(5))) - (-T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34539 &:= (-T(T(9)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))) \\ 34551 &:= (((1 + T(5)) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34556 &:= ((T(T((6 + 5))) + 5) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))) \\ 34559 &:= (((9 + 5) \times T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34566 &:= (-T(6)) \times (65 - T((T(T(4)) + 3))) \\ 34569 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - (4))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34573 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((7 + T(5)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3))))) \\ 34574 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((7 \times 5))) - T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) \\ 34576 &:= ((T(67) \times T(5)) + T(T((4 + 3)))) \\ 34584 &:= (((48 \times T(T(5))) + (4)) \times T(3)) \\ 34585 &:= (-5) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 3) \\ 34587 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(8) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 34588 &:= (-8) + (T(8) \times (T(5) + T(43))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34589 &:= -(9 - (8^5)) + T((T(4) \times T(3))) \\ 34592 &:= (2 \times (((T(T(9)) \times T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34593 &:= ((3^9) - (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3)))) \\ 34595 &:= (5 \times (((T(9) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3))))) \\ 34596 &:= ((T(T(6)) - T(9))^{-5+4+3}) \\ 34605 &:= (-T(5) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(4))) + 3)) \\ 34614 &:= (T(T((T(4) + 1))) - (-T(6) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 3))) \\ 34626 &:= (-6) + (T(T((2 + 6))) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)) \\ 34629 &:= ((T((T(9) + (2 \times 6))) - 4) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34631 &:= (-1) + (T(36) \times (T(T(4)) - 3)) \\ 34632 &:= (T(T((2^3))) \times (T((6 + 4)) - 3)) \\ 34635 &:= (-T(5) + (((T(T(3)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) \times (-3))) \\ 34638 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (-3) + T((6 + 4))) + (T(3))) \\ 34644 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((4 + T(6)) + T(4))) - (T(3))) \\ 34645 &:= (-5) + (T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) \times T(4)) \times 3)) \\ 34647 &:= (((T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) - (T(6))) \times T(4)) - 3) \\ 34648 &:= (8 \times ((4 + T(T(6))) + (4^{T(3)})) \\ 34651 &:= (1 + ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + T(3))) \\ 34652 &:= (2 + ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + T(3))) \\ 34653 &:= ((T(35) \times T((6 + 4))) + 3) \\ 34654 &:= (((T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(4) - T(3))) \\ 34655 &:= (5 + ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + T(3))) \\ 34656 &:= ((T(65) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(3))) \\ 34657 &:= (T(7) + (((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 34658 &:= (8 + ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + T(3))) \\ 34659 &:= (9 + ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + T(3))) \\ 34662 &:= ((2 - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(6) + (4)))) \times T(3)) \\ 34665 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(6)) + T(64)) \times (-3)) \\ 34668 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(6) + T((6 \times 4))) \times 3)) \\ 34671 &:= ((T((1 + T(7)) + (6))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(3))) \\ 34672 &:= (-(((T(T(2)) + T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34674 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((-7) + T(6))) + (4)) \times T(3)) \\ 34678 &:= (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) - 6) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(3)))) \\ 34682 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(8) + T(6)))) - (T(4) + T(T(3)))) \\ 34683 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(6)))) - (T(4) \times 3)) \\ 34684 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T((T(8) + T(6))) - 4) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 34686 &:= (-6) \times ((-T((8 + 6))) \times T(T(4)) - T(3)) \\ 34688 &:= (8 \times (T(86) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))) \\ 34689 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(6)) \times (T(T(4)) - 3))) \\ 34692 &:= ((2 - ((-9) - T(6)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34695 &:= (-T(5) \times (-9) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(4)) - T(3))) \\ 34697 &:= ((T((7 + 9)) + T(6)) \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34698 &:= ((T(8) \times 964) - T(3)) \\ 34713 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(-((1 \times 7) - (4^3)))) \\ 34716 &:= ((T(T((6 - 1))) + T(T(7))) \times T((-T(4) + T(T(3))))) \\ 34725 &:= (T(5) \times (-((2 - 7) - (-T(4) \times T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34726 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34727 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(3)))) \\ 34728 &:= (T(T(8)) + ((-2) - (T(T(7)) \times (-4)) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 34731 &:= (T((T((1 + 3)) + (7))) \times (-4) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34734 &:= (((T(4) \times 3) - (T(T(7)) \times (-4))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34735 &:= -((T(T((5 + T(3)))) - (T(T(7)) \times T((T(4) + 3)))) \\ 34739 &:= (((T(T(9)) + 3) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \\ 34742 &:= (((T(T(2))^4) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(3) \\ 34748 &:= ((T(8) \times T(T(4))) + (((T(7) + 4))^3)) \\ 34749 &:= (-9) \times (T(T(4)) - T((T(7) + (T(4) \times T(3)))) \\ 34752 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T((-5) + T(7))) - 4) \times T(3)) \\ 34754 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(7)) - T(43)) \\ 34755 &:= (5 \times ((T((-5) + T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34756 &:= ((T(6) \times T(57)) + 43) \\ 34762 &:= ((-((T(2) + T(6))) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(4) + 3))) \\ 34764 &:= (-4) \times ((-T(6) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(4)) \times (-3))) \\ 34765 &:= ((T(5) \times T(67)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 34768 &:= ((-T(8)) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 34773 &:= (((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times 3 \\ 34775 &:= ((T(T((5 + 7))) - T(T(7))) \times (T(4) + 3)) \\ 34776 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (7)) \times 7) - T(4)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34782 &:= (T(T(2)) + (((8 + T(T(7))) \times 4) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 34783 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(8))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3))))) \\ 34784 &:= (T((T(T(4)) + 8)) + (((T(7) + 4))^3)) \\ 34785 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(8)) + T(-((7 - 4^3)))) \\ 34794 &:= (((4 + T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \\ 34795 &:= (5 \times (((T(T(9)) \times 7) - T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34797 &:= (-7) \times (-T((9 \times (7 + 4))) - T(T(3))) \\ 34804 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(08) \times 4) \times T(T(T(3))))) \\ 34806 &:= (-T(60)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \\ 34812 &:= (((T(2) + T((-1) + T(8))) \times T(T(4))) - 3) \\ 34822 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((2^8) \times T((T(4) + T(3)))) \\ 34823 &:= ((32 \times T((T(8) + T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34824 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 2) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4)))) - 3) \\ 34825 &:= ((T((T(5) + T((2 + 8)))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))) \\ 34834 &:= (((T(T(4)) - 3) \times (T(T(8)) + (4))) - (T(3))) \\ 34835 &:= (-5) \times (-((3^8) - T(T((4 + 3)))) \\ 34839 &:= ((T((T(9) + 38)) \times T(4)) - T(T(3))) \\ 34852 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) - 8) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))) \\ 34854 &:= ((T((-4) + T(5))) \times T((8 \times 4))) + (T(3)) \\ 34855 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(T((8 - 4)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 34857 &:= ((T((75 + 8)) \times T(4)) - 3) \\ 34859 &:= (((T(T((9 - 5))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 34872 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) - ((T(T(8)) - T(4))) \times T(3)) \\ 34874 &:= (47 \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 34875 &:= ((5 \times (7 + 8)) \times T((T(4) \times 3))) \\ 34878 &:= ((-((T(T(8)) + T(7))) - (-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 3) \\ 34881 &:= ((-((1 - 8)) + (T(8) \times 4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 34884** := $((T(4) \times T(8)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))$
34885 := $((T(T(5)) \times (8 \times T(8))) + T((4 + T(T(3))))$
34894 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(9) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(3))))$
34914 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (-1 + T(T(9)))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
34915 := $((T(T(T(5 - 1)))) + T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
34918 := $((-8) + T(T((1 \times 9))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))$
34923 := $((T(((T(3) \times 2) + T(9))) + T(4)) \times T(T(3)))$
34928 := $(8 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(9)) + (4^{T(3)})))$
34935 := $((T(T(5) \times T(39)) - T(T(4))) \times 3)$
34937 := $-((T(T(7) - T(3))) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))))$
34938 := $(T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) + ((-T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
34944 := $((T(4) + 4) \times ((T(9) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(3))))$
34945 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((-T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
34947 := $((T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) + 9) \times T(4)) - 3$
34952 := $((-(2 + 5) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))$
34956 := $((T(6) + T(5)) \times (T(T(9)) - (4^3)))$
34958 := $((8^5 + T(T(9))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3))))$
34959 := $((T(T(9)) \times ((T(5) + 9) + T(4))) - T(T(T(3))))$
34962 := $((T(2) - T(T(6))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))))$
34965 := $((T(5) \times T(6)) \times T((9 \times 4)) / T(3))$
34968 := $(8 \times T(((6 + 9) + T((4 \times 3))))$
34973 := $(T(T(3)) + ((-7) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))$
34974 := $((4 - T(T(7))) \times (-9 - T((4 \times 3)))$
34977 := $((((-7 - T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))) - 3)$
34983 := $-((((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) + 9) \times T(T(4))) - 3)$
34986 := $((T((T(6) + T(8))) + (9 + 4)) \times T(T(3)))$
34989 := $-((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-9)) - T(4)) \times (-T(3))))$
34992 := $((2 \times ((9 + 9^4)) / T(3))$
34995 := $((((5 \times T(9)) \times T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 3)$
34997 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(9) + T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 3$
35028 := $((T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) + T(05)) \times T(T(3)))$
35049 := $((9 + T(T(T(4)))) - (0 - T(T(5)))) \times T(T(3))$
35112 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (11 + T(T(5)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
35124 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times (T(5) - 3))$
35145 := $((T(T((T(5) - 4))) \times (1 + T(5))) - T(T(T(3))))$
35152 := $(2 \times ((5 + T((1 + 5)))^3))$
35154 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + (-1 + T(5)))) \times T(T(3)))$
35167 := $(T((T(7) - 6)) \times (T((1 + T(5))) + 3))$
35169 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6) + T(T(-((1 - 5)))))) - (T(T(3))))$
35211 := $((T((T(11) + 2)) \times T(5)) + T(T(3)))$
35223 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(2)) \times ((T(2) + T(5))^3)))$
35224 := $(T(4^2) \times (T((2 + 5)) + T(T(T(3))))$
35225 := $((-T(T(5) - 2) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
35226 := $((T(T(6)) + T((2 \times T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(3)))$
35227 := $((T(7) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(2)) - 5)) + 3)$
35229 := $((T(9) \times (T(2 \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) - T(3))$
35235 := $((-T(5)) \times (T((T(3) \times T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)))))$
35238 := $((T((T(8) - 3)) \times T(2)) - 5) \times T(T(3))$
35244 := $(T((44 \times 2)) \times (T(5) - T(3)))$
35247 := $(T((7 \times T(4))) + ((2^{T(5)} - T(3))))$
35248 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(2)) \times (-5 + T(T(3)))$
35249 := $((T(9) \times T(T(4))) + ((2^{T(5)} + T(3)))$
35252 := $((-T((-2) + T(5))) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
35253 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + 2))) - (T(5) \times T(3)))$
35256 := $((T(T(6)) - 5) \times 2) \times T((T(5) - 3))$
35258 := $((-85) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
35259 := $((T((9 + T(5))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))$
35262 := $((T(T(2)) + T(62)) \times (T(5) + 3))$
35265 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(2)^5)) - T(T(T(3))))$
35267 := $((-76) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
35274 := $((T((-4) + T(7))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - (T(3))$
35275 := $((-5) + ((T(7)^2) \times T(5)) \times 3)$
35276 := $((-67) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
35277 := $((T(7) \times T(7)) \times T(2)) \times T(5) - 3$
35279 := $((T(9) \times (T(7)^2)) - (-5 + T(3)))$
35292 := $((T(2) + T(T(9))) \times (-2 + T((5 + 3))))$
35294 := $((-49) + (T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
35295 := $(T(5) + (T((T(9) + T(2))) \times (5 \times T(3))))$
35298 := $(T(((8 \times 9) / 2)) \times 53)$
35301 := $((T(T(10)) + T(T(3))) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3))$
35322 := $((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(5)) / 3))))$
35325 := $((T((T(5) + 2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(5) + 3))$
35328 := $((T((T(8) - T(2))) \times T(T(3))) - 5) \times 3$
35334 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(3) \times 5)) - (T(3))$
35351 := $((-1) - T(T((5 + 3)))) \times (-53)$
35352 := $((T((2 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(5) - T(3)))$
35358 := $((T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 5) \times 3$
35364 := $((T((-4) + T(6))) \times T((T(3) + T(5)))) + T(T(3))$
35368 := $((-8) + (T(T((T(6)) / T(T(3)))) \times (-5 + T(T(3))))$
35375 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) + 3) \times (-5^3)$
35376 := $(67 \times T((35 - 3)))$
35379 := $((T((T(9) - T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((5 + 3)))$
35382 := $(T(T(2)) + (T(T(8 + 3))) \times (-5 + T(T(3))))$
35385 := $((T(T(5)) \times (8 + T(3))) + 5) \times T(T(3))$
35393 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (9^{T(3)})) / (-T(5)) - (T(T(3))))$
35394 := $((T(T(4)) + 9) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(5)) - T(3)$
35397 := $((7 + 9) \times T((T(3) + 5))) + (T(T(3)))$
35415 := $(T(5) \times ((1 + T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) / 3))))$
35421 := $((T(T(1 + 2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(5) - 3)))$
35422 := $((2 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - 3)$
35423 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((5 - 3))$
35424 := $(4^2) \times (T(T((-4) + T(5))) + 3)$

$$\begin{aligned} 35425 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4))) + (5^{T(3)})) \\ 35426 &:= (((T(6) + 2) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(5-3))) \\ 35427 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + T((T(4) \times 5))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35428 &:= (T(82) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(5)) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 35429 &:= (9 + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/T(3))) \\ 35432 &:= ((23 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - 3)) \\ 35433 &:= (((T(3) + (3^{T(4)}))/5) \times 3) \\ 35435 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/T(3))) \\ 35443 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 35445 &:= (5 \times ((4 \times T((4 \times T(5)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35448 &:= ((8 - ((-4) - T(4)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35451 &:= ((T((-1) + T(5)) - (4)) \times T((5 + T(T(3)))) \\ 35454 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(5)) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 35463 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(6) - (4)))) + T((5 \times 3))) \\ 35464 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times (4 + T((5 \times 3)))) \\ 35466 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T((T(6) - (4)))) + T(T(5))) + 3) \\ 35472 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(T((7 + 4)))) \times (-5) + T(T(3))) \\ 35475 &:= (T(5) \times ((7^4) - T((5 + 3)))) \\ 35476 &:= ((T(6) + T(7)) \times (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(3)))) \\ 35478 &:= -(((T(8) - (7^4)) \times T(5)) - 3) \\ 35483 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) - (5 + 3)) \\ 35484 &:= (((T(4) \times T(84)) + T(5)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35485 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(8)) + (4^5)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35486 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) + (5 + T(3)) \\ 35489 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) + T(3)))) \\ 35496 &:= (((6 + T(T(9))) - T(T(4))) \times T((5 + 3))) \\ 35515 &:= ((T(51) \times T(5)) + (5^{T(3)})) \\ 35532 &:= (T((T(2)^3)) \times ((T(T(5)) - (5)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 35547 &:= ((7 + T(4)) \times (-T(T(5))) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) \\ 35557 &:= ((7^5) - ((5^5) \times T(3))) \\ 35558 &:= ((8 + T(5)) \times (T(55) + T(3))) \\ 35559 &:= ((T((T(T(9))/T(5))) \times T(5)) - T(T((5 + 3)))) \\ 35563 &:= ((T(36) + (5)) \times 53) \\ 35565 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(65) - (5)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35568 &:= ((8 \times (T(6) + (5))) \times T((T(5) + 3))) \\ 35574 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(7))/5 + 5) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35586 &:= (6 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(5) \times T((5 + T(3)))))) \\ 35589 &:= ((T(9) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) + (5))) - (T(3))) \\ 35595 &:= ((T(59) + (-5) \times T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35597 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((T(9 + T(5))) \times T(T(5))) + 3)) \\ 35616 &:= ((T(61) \times T(6)) - T((T(5) \times T(3)))) \\ 35619 &:= ((T((T(9) - 1)) \times (T(6) + T(5))) - T(T(3))) \\ 35625 &:= (T(5) \times ((-2) + T(6)) \times (5^3)) \\ 35634 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times 3) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(5)))) - (T(3))) \\ 35637 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (3 \times T((6 \times T(5)))) \times (-3)) \\ 35652 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T((T(5) - 3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35655 &:= (T(5) + (((T(T(5)) - (T(6))) \times T(T(5))) \times 3)) \\ 35667 &:= ((T((T(7) - (6))) \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))) - (T(3))) \\ 35673 &:= ((-((T(3) - T(7))) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 35676 &:= ((T((-6) + T(7))) \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))) + 3) \\ 35679 &:= (((T(9) \times 7) \times (-6) + T(T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35685 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(8) \times T((6 + 5))) + 3)) \\ 35688 &:= (8 \times ((T(T(8)) \times 6) + T((5 \times T(3)))) \\ 35697 &:= ((T(7) \times T((T(9) + (6)))) - T(53)) \\ 35705 &:= ((T(50) \times T(7)) + (T(5)/3)) \\ 35706 &:= -((T(T(6)) + (0 - ((T(7) + (5))^3))) \\ 35724 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(5) - 3))) \\ 35728 &:= (((8 + T(2)) \times T(T(7))) \times (5 + 3)) \\ 35734 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(7) + T(T(5)))) + T(3))) \\ 35739 &:= (((T(9) \times T(3)) + T(7)) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) \\ 35742 &:= (((T(T(2))^4) + T(T(7))) \times (T(5) + T(3))) \\ 35743 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(7) + (T(5)^3))) \\ 35745 &:= ((T((5 \times T(4))) \times T(7)) + (T(5) \times 3)) \\ 35748 &:= (T(8) \times ((T((4 + 7)) \times T(5)) + 3)) \\ 35763 &:= ((T((T(3) + (6))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(5) \times T(3)))) \\ 35764 &:= ((4^6) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(5) - 3)))) \\ 35766 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (67)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(3))) \\ 35768 &:= (8 \times (6 + T((T(7) + T((5 + T(3)))))) \\ 35769 &:= ((T((-9) + (T(T(6))/7)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35772 &:= ((-((2^7) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(5)))) \times T(3)) \\ 35774 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (7)) \times (T(T(7)) + T((T(5) + 3)))) \\ 35775 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(7)/7))) \times T(53)) \\ 35777 &:= (-T(7) + (77 \times T((5 \times T(3)))) \\ 35778 &:= ((87 \times (T(T(7)) + (5))) + T(T(3))) \\ 35779 &:= ((9 + T(7)) \times (T((T(7) + T(5))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 35783 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times ((-8) \times T(T(7))) - (5)))/(-T(T(3))) \\ 35784 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(8)) - T((T(7) - (5)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35787 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times 87) + T((5 \times T(3)))) \\ 35793 &:= ((3 \times 97) \times (T(T(5)) + 3)) \\ 35794 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((-T(9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 35805 &:= (((-5) + T(08)) \times 5) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 35823 &:= (((3^{T(2)}) \times T((T(8) + T(5)))) + T(T(3))) \\ 35824 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T((T(2) \times 8)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35826 &:= (T(6) \times (2 \times 853)) \\ 35828 &:= ((-((8 + 2)) - T(T(8))) \times (-53)) \\ 35829 &:= (9 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - (5 \times 3))) \\ 35835 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(8) - (5))) + T(3))) \\ 35838 &:= (T((8 + 3)) \times ((T(8) \times T(5)) + 3)) \\ 35839 &:= (((9 \times T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - ((5^3))) \\ 35841 &:= (((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(5)) - 3) \\ 35842 &:= ((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((8^5) - T(3))) \\ 35843 &:= (T(T((3 \times 4))) + ((8^5) - T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35844 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-T(4)) + T(T(8)))) - (5)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35847 &:= (7 \times (T((T(4) + 8)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 35848 &:= (-8) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(8) \times (T(T(5)) + (T(3)))))) \\ 35849 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + 5))) - T(T(3)))) \\ 35852 &:= (T(T(-((T(2) - T(5)))))) + ((8^5) + 3)) \\ 35853 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - T((T(5) - 3))) \\ 35856 &:= (((T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(8)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 35865 &:= (T(5) \times (T(68) + (T(5) \times 3))) \\ 35868 &:= ((-T(8)) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(5))))/3 \\ 35874 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(8)) - T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 35883 &:= ((T((T(3) + T(8))) \times T(8)) + (T(5)^3)) \\ 35884 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) \times ((8 \times T(T(5))) - (T(3)))))) \\ 35886 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times (8 \times 5)) + (T(3))) \\ 35889 &:= (((T(T(9)) + 8) + T(T(8))) \times (T(5) + T(3))) \\ 35892 &:= (((-2) + T(T(9))) - T(8)) \times T((5 + 3)) \\ 35895 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((9 + T(T(8))) \times 53)) \\ 35898 &:= (((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8))) - T((5 + T(3)))) \\ 35916 &:= (6 \times ((1 + T(T(9))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 35917 &:= (-7) \times ((-1) - T(T(9))) - T((T(5) \times T(3))) \\ 35922 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((2 + T(T(9))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 35924 &:= (-T(T(4))) + ((T(-((T(T(2)) - T(9)))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 35925 &:= (T(5) + (T((2 \times 9)) \times T((T(T(5))/T(3)))))) \\ 35928 &:= (T(8) \times (-2) + (T((9 - 5)^3))) \\ 35931 &:= (T((13 + T(9))) \times (T(5) + T(3))) \\ 35934 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + 3)) \times T((-9) + T(5))) + 3) \\ 35937 &:= (((7 \times T(3)) - 9)^{T(5-3)}) \\ 35938 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) \times 9)) - (5)) - T(T(3))) \\ 35943 &:= (T(3) + (((T(T(4)) \times (-9))/(-T(5)))^3)) \\ 35945 &:= -((T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) - ((T((T(9) + T(5))) \times T(T(3)))))) \\ 35949 &:= ((9 \times ((4 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 35952 &:= (((2 - T(T(5))) + T((T(9) + T(5)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35955 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + 9))) - (T(5) \times 3)) \\ 35958 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (59 - 5)) - (T(3))) \\ 35962 &:= (-2) + ((6 \times 9) \times T(T((5 + 3)))) \\ 35964 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(6) - (T(9) \times T(5)))) - (T(3))) \\ 35973 &:= (3 \times (((T(T(7)) + T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 35974 &:= (((-4) - (-7) \times T(T(9))) \times 5) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 35977 &:= ((-7) \times ((-7) + T(T(9))) \times (-5)) - 3 \\ 35979 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times (-7)) + T(9)) \times (-5)) - T(T(3)) \\ 35982 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) \times 9) + (T(5) + 3)) \\ 35984 &:= (-T(4)) + (((T(T(8)) \times (-9)) - 5) \times (-T(3))) \\ 35985 &:= -((T(5) - (T(8) \times (T((9 - 5)^3)))) \\ 35987 &:= (-7) + (((T(T(8)) \times (-9)) - 5) \times (-T(3))) \\ 35989 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) - T(T(9))) - 5) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 35994 &:= (((T((4 \times 9)) \times 9) + 5) \times T(3)) \\ 35997 &:= ((((-7) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) \times (-5)) - 3 \\ 36036 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (30 + (T(6) \times T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36057 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(50) + T(6))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36124 &:= (-4) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-1 - (T(6)^3))) \\ 36144 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times 4) - T(16)) \times T(3)) \\ 36155 &:= -(((T(T(5)) - (T(5)^{-1+6}))/T(T(3)))) \\ 36162 &:= ((2 \times T(((T(6) - 1) + T(6)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 36189 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(8) - 1)) - (6 \times T(3))) \\ 36192 &:= ((T((T(T(T(2))) + 9)) - 1) \times T((6 + T(3)))) \\ 36195 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-1 + 6)) + (T(3))) \\ 36197 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-1 + (6 \times T(3)))) \\ 36198 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (9 \times (16^3)))) \\ 36219 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-1 + T((2 + 6)))) - (T(3))) \\ 36224 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((2^{T(2)}))) - T(T((T(6)/3)))) \\ 36225 &:= (T(5) \times T((2 + ((2^6) + 3)))) \\ 36226 &:= ((T((T(6) - 2)^2) + ((T(6) \times T(3)))) \\ 36231 &:= ((T(T((-1) + T(3))) \times T((T(2) + T(6)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36234 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-3) + T(T((2 + 6)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36246 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T((4^2)) + T(6))) - T(T(3))) \\ 36248 &:= ((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (26 - 3)) \\ 36249 &:= (((-T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6) + 3) \\ 36252 &:= ((T(2) + T(5)) \times (-2) + T(63)) \\ 36255 &:= (-T(5)) + (T((T(5) \times 2)) \times T((6 + T(3)))) \\ 36261 &:= (T(((1 - 1) + T(6)) - T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(3)))) \\ 36264 &:= ((T((-4) + T(6))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) + 3) \\ 36267 &:= ((T(7) \times (6^{-2+6})) - T(T(3))) \\ 36282 &:= -((T(T(2)) + ((T(8)/(-2)) \times T(63))) \\ 36284 &:= (-4) - ((T(8)/(-2)) \times T(63)) \\ 36285 &:= (T(5) + (T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) \times T((6 + T(3)))))) \\ 36287 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(8)^2)) - (6/T(3))) \\ 36288 &:= (T(8) \times ((8 \times 2) \times 63)) \\ 36294 &:= ((T(T(4)) - (-9) \times T(T((2 + 6)))) \times T(3)) \\ 36295 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(9)) + 2) \times (T(6)/(-3))) \\ 36315 &:= (T(5) \times (T((-1) + T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 36324 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \times T(6)) - T(3)) \\ 36344 &:= -((T(T(4)) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(36)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 36345 &:= (-5) \times ((T(4) \times (-3^6)) + T(T(3))) \\ 36355 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (3 + T((T(6) + 3)))) \\ 36369 &:= ((T((T(9) + 6))) + T(T(3))) \times (T(6) + T(3)) \\ 36372 &:= (T(2) \times (T(7) + (T(3) \times T(63)))) \\ 36375 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(7)) - (-3) - T(63))) \\ 36378 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T((7 + 3))) - T(T(6))) - T(T(3))) \\ 36384 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(3))) - T(T(6))) + (T(3))) \\ 36393 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(9)) + 3)/6) \times T(T(3)) \\ 36396 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T((T(9) - T(3)))) \times (6 \times T(3))) \\ 36421 &:= ((T((-12) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(6))))/(-T(3)) \\ 36423 &:= (T((T(3) \times T(2))) \times ((T(4) \times T(6)) + 3)) \\ 36424 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(T(T(2))) - 4)) \times (T(T(6)) - 3))) \end{aligned}$$

- 36425** := $((T((T(5) \times 2)) \times (4 + T(T(6))))/3)$
36427 := $((T(T(7))/(-2) + (T(T(4)) \times T((6 \times T(3))))$
36428 := $(((-8) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(6)/3)))$
36429 := $(-T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + 3))$
36432 := $(T(23) \times (T((-4) + T(6))) - T(T(3)))$
36435 := $(T((T(5) \times T(3))) + (T(T((4 + 6))) \times T(T(3))))$
36438 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times T(T(4))) - (T(6) + T(3))$
36442 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((4^6) + T(3)))$
36444 := $((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) \times (-4) + T(6))) - (T(T(3)))$
36448 := $(((((T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) - (T(3)))$
36456 := $((6 + T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6) + 3))$
36459 := $((T(9) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4))) - T((6 \times T(3)))$
36462 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(6) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6) + 3)))$
36464 := $(-T((T(4) + T(6)))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6) + 3))$
36465 := $(T(5) \times (((T(T(6)) - T(4)) \times T(T(6)))/T(T(3))))$
36468 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) - T((T(4) \times 6))) \times 3$
36474 := $(-T(4) + (T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6)) + T(3))))$
36477 := $((T(7) + T(T(7))) \times (4 \times T(6))) + T(T(3))$
36495 := $(-T(5) \times (((-T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6))) + T(T(3)))$
36498 := $((T(T(8)) - (9 - T(46))) \times T(T(3)))$
36522 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(2)) - (-T(5) \times T((T(6)/3))))$
36525 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(5)) \times T(T((T(6)/3))))$
36528 := $(8 \times (T(T(2)) + T((-T((-5) + T(6)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
36534 := $((T(T((4 + 3))) \times (T(5) \times 6)) - T(3))$
36535 := $(-5) + ((T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(T((T(6)/3))))$
36537 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(3) \times T(5))) - (6 - 3))$
36543 := $((T(T((3 + 4))) \times (T(5) \times 6)) + 3)$
36544 := $((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + (5 \times 6)))) - T(3))$
36547 := $(7 \times (T(T(4)) + ((T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))))$
36548 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) - ((-T(5) - T(T(6)))/(-3)))$
36549 := $(-9) \times ((T(T(4)) - T((T(5) \times 6))) - T(T(3)))$
36554 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5))/5)) - T(T((T(6)/3)))$
36555 := $(T(5) \times ((-5) + T(T((5 + 6)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
36561 := $((T(T((1 + 6))) \times (T(5) \times 6)) + T(T(3))$
36564 := $(-((T(4) - 6))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6)^3)$
36567 := $((T(T(7)) \times (6 \times T(5))) + (T(6) + T(3))$
36573 := $(-3) - (((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))) - (6)) \times T(3))$
36574 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(5) \times 6)) - T(T(3))))$
36576 := $((6 \times T(T(7))) \times T(5)) + (6 \times T(3))$
36579 := $(T(9) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(5) \times 6)) - (T(3))))$
36585 := $((T(T(5)) + T(8)) \times (5 + T(T(6)))) - T(T(T(3)))$
36588 := $(-T(T(8))) + ((T(8) \times T(T((T(5) - 6)))) - T(3))$
36589 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) - 5) - T((6 \times T(3)))$
36594 := $((T(T((4 + 9))) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 3))$
36615 := $(T(5) \times ((-1) + T(66)) + T(T(T(3))))$
36624 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T((2 + 6)))) - T((6 - 3))$
36625 := $(-5) + (T(T(-(2 - 6))) \times T((6 \times T(3))))$
36627 := $((T((7 + T(2))) \times T((6 \times 6))) - 3)$
36628 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(-(2 - 6)))) - (6/3))$
36642 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T((6 \times 6))) + (T(3))))$
36645 := $(T(5) + (T(T(4)) \times T(((6 + 6) \times 3)))$
36646 := $(-6) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times T((T(6)/3)))$
36648 := $(T(8) \times (T(46) - 63))$
36651 := $((T(T(-(1 - 5))) \times T((6 \times 6))) + (T(T(3))))$
36652 := $((T(T((2 \times 5))) - T(T(6))) \times T((T(6)/3))$
36654 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))) + (T(6) + 3))$
36673 := $((-3) + T(T(7))) \times T((T((6 + 6))/T(3)))$
36675 := $(-T(5) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-6)) - (6 + 3)))$
36684 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + (6 \times (6 + 3)))$
36685 := $(5 \times (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(6)))/T(T(3))))$
36693 := $(-3) \times (T(T(9)) - ((T(66) \times T(3))))$
36725 := $(-T((5^2))) \times (7 - T((T(6) - T(3))))$
36728 := $(-T((8^2))) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(3))$
36729 := $((T((T(9) + (2 \times 7))) - (T(6))) \times T(T(3))$
36735 := $(T((5 \times T(3))) \times (76 + 3))$
36744 := $((T((T(4) + T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - (T(3))$
36745 := $(-5) - ((-T(4)) \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) \times 3)$
36746 := $(-((T(T(6)) + (4^7))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
36748 := $((T((T(8) + T(4))) \times (T(7) + (6))) - (T(3))$
36764 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) - 7) \times T((6 \times 3))))$
36765 := $((T(T(5) \times 6) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(6))) - (T(3))$
36775 := $((T(-(T(5) - T(7))) \times T(T(7))) - T((6 \times 3))$
36784 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(3))))$
36789 := $((T((9 \times 8)) \times (-7) + T(6)) - 3)$
36792 := $((2 \times 9) \times (T(7) + T(63)))$
36795 := $((T(T(5)) + T(9)) \times (7 + (6^3)))$
36798 := $((T((8 \times 9)) \times (-7) + T(6)) + T(3))$
36801 := $((T(10) \times T(T(8))) + T((6 \times 3)))$
36816 := $(-(((T(T(6)) - T((1 + T(8)))) \times T((6 + T(3))))$
36819 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((1 \times 8))) - (T(6) \times T(T(3))))$
36824 := $(-4) \times (T((2 + 8)) - T(6)^3)$
36828 := $((T(T(8)) - ((T(2) \times T(8)))) \times T((T(T(6))/T(T(3))))$
36834 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(T(8)))) - ((T(6) \times T(3))))$
36852 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) + 5)) \times T((8 + 6))) - 3)$
36854 := $((T(45) \times T(8)) - T(T((T(6)/3)))$
36855 := $((T(5) \times T((5 + 8))) \times (T(6) + T(3))$
36876 := $(T(6) \times (T(7) + (8 \times (6^3))))$
36882 := $((T((2 + 8)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) + T(T(3))$
36894 := $((-T(4) + T(T(9))) \times T(8)) - T((6 - 3))$
36895 := $(-5) + (T(9) \times T((T((T(8) - T(6)))/3)))$
36897 := $((T(7) \times T(((9 + T(8)) + (6)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
36899 := $((T(9) + (T(T(9)) \times T(8))) - T(T((T(6)/3)))$
36912 := $((-2) + T(T((1 + 9))) \times (T(6) + 3))$
36918 := $((T(8) \times (1 + T(T(9)))) - T((T(6) + T(3))))$

- 36924** := (((T(T(4)) - (T(T(2)) × T(T(9)))) × (-6)) - (T(3)))
36928 := (-8) - (T((2 × 9)) × (-6³)))
36936 := ((6³) × T((9 × 6)/3))
36942 := ((2 - T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) × 6)) × T(3)
36943 := (-3) + (T((4 + 9)) × T(T((6/3))))
36944 := (-T(4)) + ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(9) - T(6))) - T(3))
36945 := (-T(5)) + (T((T(4) + T(9))) × (T(6) + 3))
36946 := (T((-6) + T(4) + 9)) × T(T((6/3)))
36947 := ((T(T(7)) × T((4 + 9))) + (6/T(3)))
36948 := ((8 + ((-T(4) + T(T(9))) × 6)) × T(3))
36951 := ((T(1 + T(5))) × (T(9) × 6)) + T(T(T(3)))
36954 := -(((T(4) - T(59)) × T(6)) + T(3))
36955 := (-5) + (T(T(T(-((5 - 9)))) × (T(6) + 3))
36957 := ((-7) - T(T(5))) × (9 - T((T(6) + 3)))
36966 := ((T(T((6 + 6))) × (-9) + T(6)) - (T(3)))
36967 := ((T(T(7)) × T((T(T(6) - 9)/6))) + (T(T(3))))
36969 := (((T(T(9)) × 6) - T(9)) × 6) - T(T(3))
36972 := ((T(T(2)) × 79) × T((6 + T(3))))
36974 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) × (-9) + T((T(6)/3)))
36975 := ((T(T((5 + 7))) × (-9) + T(6)) + 3)
36981 := (((-1) + T(8)) × (T(T(9)) + (T(6)))) + T(T(3))
36984 := ((-((T(4) + T(8))) + (T(T(9)) × 6)) × T(3))
36987 := ((T(7) × T((8 + T(9)))) - T(T((6 + T(3))))
37023 := ((T(T(3)) + 20) × T((7 × T(3))))
37029 := ((T(T(9)) × T((-20) + T(7))) - T(T(T(3))))
37044 := (4 × (T(T(-((4 - 07))))³))
37092 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) + (0 - T(7))) × T(3))
37095 := (T(5) - (-90) × (T(T(7)) + (T(3))))
37114 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((1 + T(17)) × T(T(T(3))))
37125 := ((T(5)^{T(2)}) × ((1 + 7) + 3))
37128 := ((T(T(8)) - T(2)) × (1 + T((7 + 3))))
37134 := ((T((-4) + T(T(3 + 1)))) × T(7)) + T(3)
37146 := (T(6) + (T((T(T(4)) - 1)) × (T(7) - 3)))
37149 := ((T((T(9) + T(4 - 1)))) × T(7)) + T(T(3))
37152 := ((T(2) + (T(51) × T(7))) + T(T(3)))
37158 := (T(8) + ((T(51) × T(7)) - T(3)))
37164 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(6 - 1))) - T(T(7))) × T(3))
37173 := (((3⁷) × 17) - T(3))
37177 := ((T(T(7)) × T(((7 - 1) + 7))) + T(T(T(3))))
37188 := (T(8) × (((T(8) + 1) × T(7)) - 3))
37191 := (((-1) + T(17)) × T(T(T(3))))
37212 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((1 + T(T((T(2) + 7)))) + T(T(T(3))))
37215 := (((T(51) + T(2)) × T(7)) + 3)
37218 := (((T(T(8 + 1))) × T(T(2))) - (7)) × T(3))
37219 := (-91) × ((T(2) - T(T(7))) - (T(3)))
37224 := -((T((4^{T(2)})) - ((T(T(2)) + T(7))³))
37225 := ((T(T(5) - 2)) × (T(2) + T(T(7)))) + (T(3))
37229 := ((T(T(9)) × T((2^{T(2)}))) - (T(7) + 3))
37233 := ((3 + T((3 + (2 × T(7)))) × T(T(3)))
37234 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(7)) - T(3))
37237 := (((7 × T((T(T(3)) - 2))) × T(7)) - 3)
37238 := ((T(8) × T(T((3²)))) - (T(7) - T(3)))
37239 := ((T(T(9)) × (T(3)²)) - (7 × 3))
37243 := (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7)) + 3)
37244 := (-T(T(T(4))) + ((4 + (T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7))) × (-T(3)))
37245 := (T(5) × ((T((4^{T(2)})) + T(T(7))) - 3))
37246 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T((7 + 3)))
37247 := (((7 + 4)^{T(2)}) × T(7)) - T(T(3))
37248 := (8 × T((4 × (27 - 3))))
37249 := ((9 × (4^{T(2)})) + (T(T(7)) - T(T(3))))
37254 := ((4 + T((52 + 7))) × T(T(3)))
37257 := ((T((-7) + T(5))) × T(T((2 + 7))) - 3)
37259 := ((T(T(9)) × T((5 + T(2)))) - (7 - T(3)))
37274 := (((4 + 7)^{T(2)}) × T(7)) + T(3)
37275 := (T(5) × T(((7²) + (7 × 3))))
37281 := ((T((1 × 8)) × T(T(2 + 7))) + T(T(3)))
37284 := (-4) × ((T(T(8)) × (-2 × 7)) + 3)
37285 := (-5) + ((T(T(8)) × (2 × T(7))) - (T(3)))
37287 := (((T(T(7)) × T(8)) - (T(2)⁷)) × 3)
37288 := (((-8) × T(T(8))) + 2) × (-7) + (T(3))
37289 := ((T(T(9)) × T(8)) + ((-2) + T(7)) + 3)
37293 := (((T(T(3) + T(9))) + T(T(2))) × T(7)) - 3)
37294 := -((T(T(4)) - ((92 × T(T(7))) - 3))
37296 := ((T(T(6)) - 9) × ((2 × T(7)) × 3))
37297 := (((T(7) + T(9))²) × 7) - T(3)
37298 := ((T(8) × (T(T(9)) + 2)) - (T(7) + T(3)))
37299 := ((T((T(9) - 9)) × (2 × T(7))) + 3)
37323 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3)))/7)³)
37324 := ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3)))) × (T(7) + 3))
37338 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - T(T(3 + 7))) × 3)
37349 := ((9 × T(T((T(4) + 3))) - (T((T(7) - 3))))
37352 := ((T(((2 + T(5)) + T(3))) × T(T(7)))/3)
37358 := (((T((8 + T(5)))/3) × T(T(7))) + (T(3)))
37359 := ((T((9 × 5) + T(3))) × T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))
37362 := (((T(2) × T(T((T(6)/T(3)))) - (T(T(7))) × T(3))
37365 := (T(5) × (T((63 + 7) + T(3)))
37368 := ((T(T(8)) - (6 × (3⁷))) × (-3))
37382 := (T(T(2)) + ((8³) × 73))
37387 := ((7 + (T(8) × T(T(3)))) × (T(7) + T(T(3))))
37392 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) - ((T(3) - T(7)))) × T(3))
37394 := ((T(T(4)) × (9³)) - T(73))
37395 := (-T(5) × (T(T(9)) + (T(T(3)) × (-T(7) × T(3))))
37398 := ((8 × T((T(9) - T(3)))) - (7)) × T(3))

- 37416** := $(6 \times (-1) - ((T(T(4)) - T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))))$
37419 := $(-T(T(9) + 1)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) - 3))$
37421 := $(-1) - ((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(7))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
37422 := $(2 \times ((T(2)^4) \times T((7 \times 3)))$
37425 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(7)))) + 3$
37428 := $(-T(8)) + ((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(3)))$
37429 := $((T(T(9) + T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times T(7) + (T(T(3)))$
37434 := $-(((T(4^3)) \times (T(4) - T(7))) + T(3))$
37436 := $(T((T(6)/3)) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(7))) - T(T(T(3))))$
37443 := $((T(T(3) \times T(4)) - 47) \times T(T(3)))$
37446 := $-(((T(64) \times (T(4) - T(7))) - T(3))$
37449 := $(9 \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(4) + 7))) \times 3)$
37452 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(4))) + T(7) \times (-T(3))$
37455 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-T(5)) - T((T(4) \times 7))) + 3$
37458 := $((T(T(8)) + T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))/T(7) + 3$
37464 := $((-4) + T(T(6))) - (4) \times (T(7) \times T(3))$
37465 := $-((T(T(T(5) - 6))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) - 3)))$
37479 := $((97 - 4) \times (T(T(7)) - 3)$
37482 := $(-T(2)) + ((8 + T(T(4))) \times T((T(7) + T(3))))$
37485 := $(-T(5) - T(8 + 4)) \times T((T(7) + T(3)))$
37486 := $(-6) + ((T(8) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3))))$
37488 := $(-T(8)) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(4)) - T(T(7))) \times T(3))$
37491 := $(-1) + (T(9 + 4)) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3)))$
37492 := $(T((-2) + T(9 - 4))) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3)))$
37495 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(9) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7) - 3)))$
37498 := $(-T(T(8))) - (-94) \times T((7 + T(T(3))))$
37499 := $((9 \times T(T(9 + 4))) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(3)))$
37515 := $((T(T(5) + 1)) \times T((-5) + T(7))) - T(T(3))$
37524 := $((T(T(4)) - 2) \times (T(T(5)) - (-T(7) \times T(T(3))))$
37527 := $((T(7) \times 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 7))) + T(T(T(3)))$
37528 := $(T(8) + (T((-2) + T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3))))$
37536 := $((-T(63)) \times (T(5) - T(T(7))))/T(T(3))$
37539 := $(T(T(9)) + (-T(3)) \times ((-T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3)))$
37542 := $((T(2^4) \times T((-5) + T(7))) + (T(3))$
37548 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5))) + T((7 \times T(3)))$
37555 := $((-555) \times T(T(7)))/(-T(3))$
37568 := $(8 \times (T((T(6) + 5) + T(7))) + T(T(T(3))))$
37569 := $((T(T(9) + 6)) + (T(5))) \times T(7) + T(T(3))$
37576 := $((T(6) + T(T(7))) \times (T(5) + 73))$
37577 := $((T(T(7)) + 7) \times T((-T(5) - T(7)))) - T(3)$
37582 := $(2 \times (((T(T(8)) + 5) \times T(7)) + 3)$
37583 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((T((8 + T(5))) \times T(T(7))))/(-3))$
37584 := $(-48) \times (T(T(5)) - T((7 \times T(3))))$
37593 := $(3 \times ((9 - T(T(-T(5) - T(7)))) \times (-3))$
37594 := $(T(T(4)) + (9 \times (-T(5) + T(T(7 + T(3))))))$
37596 := $((T(6) + T(T(9))) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(7))) \times T(3))$
37597 := $((T(7 \times T(9)) \times T(T(5))) + T(7) - T(T(T(3))))$
37598 := $((T(8) \times T(T(9))) - ((5 - 7^3)))$
37599 := $((9 \times (-9) + T(T(-T(5) - T(7)))) + T(3))$
37625 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times T((6 \times 7)))/3$
37626 := $((T(6) \times (2^6)) \times T(7)) - T(3)$
37629 := $(9 \times ((-2) + T(T((6 + 7)))) - 3)$
37631 := $(-1) - (((-T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)))$
37632 := $((2^{T(3)}) \times (T(6) + 7)) \times T(T(3))$
37635 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(67))) \times 3)$
37638 := $(-T(8)) + ((3 \times T(T((6 + 7)))) \times 3)$
37642 := $(T((T(2) + T((4 + 6)))) \times (T(7) - T(3)))$
37653 := $((-T(3) - T(5)) \times T(T((6 + 7))) - T(T(3)))$
37656 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-5) + (6 \times T(7))) + 3)$
37657 := $(T(7) \times (T(T(5)) + T((T(6) + T(7)))) - 3)$
37659 := $(((-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(6))) \times (-7) + (T(3))$
37669 := $((T(T(9)) \times (6 \times 6)) + T(T(7))) + 3$
37674 := $((-T(47)) + T(T(6))) \times (-7) \times T(3))$
37675 := $((T(T(5)) + T(7)) \times T((-6) + T(7))) + T(T(T(3)))$
37684 := $(T(4) \times (T(86) + T(7))) - T(3)$
37692 := $(-T(2)) + ((9 \times T(T((6 + 7)))) + T(T(3)))$
37695 := $(-5) \times (((T(9) \times (-6)) \times T(7)) + T(T(3)))$
37698 := $(T(89) + T(67)) \times T(3)$
37716 := $((T(T(6) - 1)) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(7)) \times (-T(3))$
37723 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T((7 + T(3))))$
37724 := $((T(T(T(4)))/(-2)) \times (-7 \times 7)) - T(3)$
37728 := $(8 \times ((2 + (T(7) \times T(7))) \times T(3))$
37729 := $((9 \times T(T((T(2) + 7)))) + T((7 + 3))$
37737 := $((T(T(7)) \times (3 + T(7))) - 7) \times 3$
37749 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(7) \times T(7)))) - T(3))$
37752 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) - T(3))))$
37755 := $((T(5) + T((5 + 7))) \times T(T(7))) - 3$
37758 := $((-(8 - 5)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) + 3))$
37764 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)/7) + T(7))^3))$
37765 := $((T(5) - 6) + T(T(7))) \times T((7 + T(3)))$
37769 := $(-T(9) - ((T(6) - 7) \times T(73)))$
37778 := $(-T(8) - ((7 + 7) \times T(73)))$
37779 := $((T(9) \times (7 \times 7)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(3))$
37782 := $(T(2) \times (8 + (T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + 3))))$
37784 := $((T(4) \times T(87)) - T((T(7) + 3))$
37793 := $((T(T(3)) - (T((T(9) + T(7)))) \times (-7) + T(T(3))))$
37794 := $((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times (-T(7) + T(T(7)))) - T(3))$
37797 := $((T(7) - T((T(9) + 7))) \times (-T(7))) - 3$
37799 := $((T(T(9)) \times (9 + T(7))) - T((T(7) + 3))$
37814 := $((-4 - 18) \times T(73))$
37815 := $(-T(5)) \times (-1 - (T((8 + 7)) \times T(T(3))))$
37819 := $((T(T(9)) - 1) \times T(8)) + T((T(7) + T(3)))$
37824 := $(T(4) + ((T(T(2)) + 8) \times T(73))$
37826 := $((6 \times (T(2)^8)) - T(T((7 + 3)))$

- 37828** := $((-8) + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times (T(7) + T(T(3)))$
37834 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)))) + (T(7) + T(T(3))))$
37836 := $(-6) \times (((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \times T(3))$
37839 := $((T(9) \times (T((T(T(3)) + 8)) + (T(T(7)))) - T(3))$
37841 := $(1 + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(3))))$
37842 := $((T((24 + T(8))) - T(7)) \times T(T(3)))$
37843 := $(3 + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(3))))$
37844 := $((-4) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-3))$
37845 := $(T(5) \times (((T(4) \times T(8)) \times 7) + 3))$
37846 := $(6 + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(3))))$
37847 := $(7 + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(3))))$
37848 := $((T(T((8 - 4))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-3))$
37849 := $(9 + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(3))))$
37855 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(8) + (7))))/3))$
37857 := $(((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times (8 + T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(3)))$
37859 := $((((-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) - 8) \times (-7)) + 3$
37863 := $(3 \times ((T(T(6)) - T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)))$
37869 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(6))) \times T(8)) - (7 \times T(T(3)))$
37877 := $((T(T(7)) + T((7 + T(8)))) \times T(7)) + T(T(3))$
37882 := $((T(T(2)) + 88) \times (T(T(7)) - 3))$
37884 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(8))) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(3)))$
37889 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) - 8) + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))$
37891 := $((1 + T(T(9))) \times T(8)) + T((T(7) + T(3)))$
37893 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T((T(7) \times 3))))$
37896 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T((7 + 3))))$
37897 := $((T(7 + T(T(9))) \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - T(T(3))$
37898 := $((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + (T(87)/T(3)))$
37899 := $(T(T(9)) + (9 \times (8^7 - 3)))$
37905 := $(-5) \times ((T(09) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)))$
37923 := $(-3) + (-((T(2) - T(9)) \times T((7 \times T(3))))$
37926 := $(T(6) \times (((-2) + T(9)) \times 7) \times T(3))$
37927 := $(T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) - (-9) \times T(T((7 + T(3))))$
37928 := $(-8) \times (T(T(2)) - (T(97) - T(3)))$
37929 := $((9^{T(2)}) \times (T(9) + (7))) + T(T(3))$
37932 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((-3) + T(9))) \times 7) + (T(3))$
37935 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(3) + T(T(9))) - T((T(7) \times 3)))$
37941 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T((9 + T(7))) - T(T(3))$
37944 := $((T((4 \times 4)) \times 9) \times (T(7) + 3))$
37945 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(9))))/(-7) \times T(3))$
37947 := $((T(7) - (T(49) \times (T(7) + 3)))$
37953 := $((T(T(3)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9)))) \times 7) + (T(3))$
37954 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9)))) \times 7) - T(T(T(3)))$
37961 := $((1 + T(T(6))) - T(9)) \times (-T(7) + T(T(T(3))))$
37962 := $(T(T((2 + 6))) \times ((-9) + T(7)) \times 3)$
37968 := $((T(8) \times (6 + T(9))) - T(7)) \times T(T(3))$
37974 := $(T((-4) + T(7))) - (-9) \times T(T((7 + T(3))))$
37975 := $((T(5) + ((7 + 9))) \times T((T(7) + T(T(3))))$
37978 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(3))$
37982 := $(T(T(2)) - (-8) \times (T(97) - T(3)))$
37983 := $((-3) \times T(T(8))) \times (9 - T(7)) + T(T(3))$
37985 := $((T(5) + (-8) \times (T(97) - 3))$
37988 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9)) - ((T(7)^3))$
37989 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) + (T((9 - 7)^{T(3)}))$
37994 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(3))))$
37995 := $((T(T(5)) - (99 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3))))$
37998 := $((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + T((T(9) - (7)))) - 3$
38016 := $((T(T(6)) - (T(10))) \times (T(8) \times T(3))$
38025 := $((T(5) - T(20)))^{8 - T(3)}$
38044 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(08)^3))$
38073 := $((-((T(3) - T(70)) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))$
38115 := $(T(T((5 + 1))) \times (T(18) - T(3))$
38133 := $(T((3 \times T(3))) \times (1 - (T(T(8))/(-3))))$
38136 := $((T(T(6)) - (3 + 1)) \times 8) \times T(T(3))$
38142 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) + (1 + 8)) \times 3$
38157 := $((T(7) \times (T(51) + T(8))) + T(T(3))$
38164 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((6 + 1) + T(T(8)))) - (T(3))$
38175 := $(T(5) \times (T(71) - (8 + 3)))$
38184 := $((-T(4)) \times T((T(8) + 1))) + T(T(8)) \times (-T(3))$
38193 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (9 \times T((1 + T(8)))) \times T(3))$
38223 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((2 + 2)))) + T(8)) \times 3$
38226 := $((T((T(6) - 2)) - (T(2)^8)) \times (-T(3))$
38229 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(2)^{T(2)})) \times T(8)) - 3$
38232 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(3) \times T(2)))) \times (T(8) \times T(3))$
38235 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T((2 + 8)) \times 3))$
38241 := $((T(T((1 \times 4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))$
38247 := $((T((T(7) + 4)) \times (2 \times T(8))) + T(T(T(3))))$
38248 := $(8 \times (T((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((-8) + T(T(3))))))$
38249 := $(9 \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + 8)^3)$
38255 := $(5 \times (T(5) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((-8) + T(T(3))))$
38256 := $(-6) + ((T((T(5)/2)) - 8) \times T(T(3))$
38259 := $(9 \times (((T(T(5)) - 2) \times T(8)) + 3))$
38262 := $((T(-(2 - 62))) - 8) \times T(T(3))$
38265 := $(-5) \times (T(T(6)) - (T((2 \times T(8))) \times 3))$
38268 := $(-T(8)) + (((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times 8) \times T(T(3))$
38269 := $((T(T(9)) - (((6 + 28)^3))$
38272 := $((2^7) \times ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))/3))$
38274 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(7) + 2) + T(T(8)))) - (T(3))$
38277 := $((T(T(7))/(-7)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(8)))) - 3$
38279 := $((T(97) + T(2)) \times 8) + T(T(T(3))$
38283 := $((T(T(3)) + T(8)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(3))$
38284 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(8))) \times (-2)) + (T(8)^3))$
38289 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(8))) \times 2)/T(8) - (T(3))$
38292 := $(-T(2)) + (T(T(9)) \times ((-2) + T(8) + 3))$

- 38295** := $(T((5 \times 9)) \times ((-2) + T(8)) + 3)$
38296 := $((-6) - ((T(T(9))/T(2)) \times T(T(8))))/(-T(3))$
38297 := $((T(7) - T(T(9))) + ((-2) + T(8))^3)$
38298 := $((-T(8)) - T((T(9) - 2))) \times (-T(8) + 3)$
38319 := $((9 \times T(T(13))) + T(T(8))) - T(T(3))$
38322 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3))))$
38324 := $((T(T(4)) - T(2)) \times T(T((3 + 8))))/3$
38325 := $((-5) + T((-2) \times (T(3) - T(8)))) \times T(T(3))$
38329 := $-((T(T(9)) + 2 + (-3^8) \times T(3)))$
38334 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) - ((-3) \times T(T(8))) \times 3)$
38335 := $((-5) + (T(3)^{T(3)}) - (T(8) \times T(T(T(3))))$
38338 := $(-8) + ((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) \times T(83))$
38342 := $-((2^{T(4)}) + (-3^8) \times T(3))$
38343 := $(-3) + ((-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times T(83))$
38346 := $((T(6) - 4) - T(3)) \times T(83)$
38347 := $(-((T(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-8) \times T(T(3))))$
38352 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-5) - T(3)) \times T(83))$
38357 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T((5 - 3)))) \times (8 + 3))$
38364 := $((T((T(4) \times 6)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(8 + 3)))$
38367 := $((T(T(7)) \times (6 \times T(3)))/8) \times T(T(3))$
38373 := $((T(3) \times T(T(7))) + ((-3) + T(8))^3)$
38374 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + T(3))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))))$
38376 := $(-6) \times (((T(T(7)) - T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(3)))$
38379 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(7) + 3)) \times T(8)) + 3$
38382 := $((T(T((T(2) + 8))) + T(T((T(3) - 8)))) \times T(3))$
38385 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-3)) - T((T(8) - 3)))$
38391 := $((T((1 + T(9))) - T(T(3))) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))$
38394 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times T(-((3 - 8))) - T(T(T(3))))$
38397 := $(((-T(7)) - T(T(9))) - 3) \times (-T(8)) + T(T(3))$
38401 := $((T(T(10)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
38414 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((-1) + (T(4) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-T(3))))$
38416 := $(T((6 + 1)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (8 \times T(T(3))))$
38424 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \times (8 \times 3))$
38425 := $(-5) + (T((24 + T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
38428 := $((8 + T(T(2)))^4) + (T(8)/3)$
38443 := $((T(T(3)) + 4) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(8) + T(T(3)))$
38444 := $(-T(4)) + (T((-4) + T(T(4))) \times (8 + T(T(3))))$
38445 := $(T(54) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(3))))$
38447 := $(-7) + (T((-4) + T(T(4))) \times (8 + T(T(3))))$
38448 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(4)) - 4) \times T(8) \times 3$
38451 := $((1 + T((5 \times 4))) \times T((T(8)/T(3))))$
38452 := $((25 \times T(T(4))) - (8 \times T(3)))$
38454 := $(T((4 \times T(5))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(3))))$
38455 := $(-5^5) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
38456 := $((6 + 5) \times (T(4) + T(83)))$
38463 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((6 \times T(4)))) + (T(8) - 3))$
38469 := $-((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(4) + 8))) + 3)))$
38472 := $((2 + T((T(7) + (4 \times 8)))) \times T(T(3)))$
38473 := $((T(T(3)) - 7)^4) + T(8) + T(T(3))$
38475 := $((T(5) \times T((T(7) - T(4)))) \times T((8 - 3)))$
38478 := $((T(T(8)) - T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times T((8 + 3))$
38482 := $((T(T(2)) + 8)^4) + (T((8 + 3)))$
38484 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 8) \times T(T(4))) - (T(8)^3)$
38488 := $((T(88) \times T(4)) - T(T(8))) - (T(3))$
38493 := $(3 \times ((-T(9) + T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
38497 := $((T((T(7) + 9)) \times T(T(4))) + (-8) \times T(T(3)))$
38499 := $(((-T(9)) - T(T(9))) + T(4)) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(3))$
38511 := $(11 \times (T(5) + T(83)))$
38514 := $((T((T(4) - 1)) \times T((5 + T(8)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
38524 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 25) + (8 \times 3))$
38528 := $((T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)) + 8))/(-3))$
38529 := $(9 \times (T(2) + T((T(5) + 8)/3)))$
38534 := $((T(T(4)) \times (35 + T(T(8)))) - T(T(3)))$
38535 := $(T(5) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5)))) - 8^3)$
38544 := $(44 \times (T(T(5)) + (T(8) \times T(T(3))))$
38545 := $-((T(T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times T(((5 \times 8) - 3))))$
38553 := $(-3) + (((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + T(8)) \times T(T(3)))$
38556 := $((-6) - T(T(5))) \times (-((T(5) + T(8)) \times T(3)))$
38559 := $(((-T(T(9))) - T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \times (-T(8)) + 3)$
38562 := $((T(2) \times T(65)) - 8) \times T(3)$
38565 := $(T(5) \times ((65 \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3))))$
38567 := $-((T(7) + (T((6 \times 5)) \times (-83)))$
38571 := $((T((1 \times 7)) + T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3))))$
38574 := $(-T(4)) + (T(7) \times T((58 - T(3))))$
38577 := $(-7) + (T(7) \times T((58 - T(3))))$
38586 := $(-T(6)) + ((T(T(8)) \times 58) - T(T(3)))$
38589 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) + T((T(5) + T(8)))) + 3$
38592 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((-9) \times T(T(5))) + 8) \times (-T(3)))$
38594 := $(-4) + ((T((T(9) + T(5))) + 8) \times T(T(3)))$
38595 := $(T(((T(5) - 9) \times 5)) \times 83)$
38598 := $((8 + T((T(9) + T(5)))) \times T((T(8)/T(3))))$
38619 := $((-9) - ((-1) \times T(T(6)) \times 8)) \times T(T(3))$
38622 := $((2^{T(2)}) - 6) \times T(T(8)) - (T(3))$
38625 := $((52 + 6) \times T(T(8))) - 3$
38628 := $(T(T(8)) \times ((T(2) \times T(6)) - (8 - 3)))$
38634 := $((4^3 - 6) \times T(T(8))) + (T(3))$
38638 := $-((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(3)) + (T(6) - 8)^3)))$
38643 := $((-3) \times T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) \times (-8)) \times T(T(3)))$
38644 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-8 \times 3)))$
38646 := $(T(6) \times T((T(4) \times 6))) + ((T(8) \times T(3)))$
38647 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
38649 := $((9 + T(T(4))) - 6) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(3))$

$$\begin{aligned} 38652 &:= -(T(2)) + (T(5) \times (T(68) + T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 38654 &:= -((T(T(T(4)))) - ((T((T(T(5))/6) - T(8)) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 38655 &:= -(T(5)) \times (((T(T(5)) \times (-T(6))) - T(8)) - T(T(3))) \\ 38661 &:= (((1 - T(T(6))) \times (T(6) \times (-8))) + T(T(3))) \\ 38675 &:= ((5 \times T((T(7) + (6)))) \times (-8) + T(T(3))) \\ 38681 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(8)) + T((6 \times 8))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 38682 &:= ((2 \times T((T(8) + (6)))) + T(8)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 38685 &:= (-5) \times (-T(86)) - (T(T(8)) \times T(3)) \\ 38694 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(9 + T(6)))) \times T(8)) - T(3)) \\ 38715 &:= ((-5) \times (-1 - T(7))) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 38724 &:= ((T(4) + 2) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 8) - T(T(3)))) \\ 38736 &:= (6 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(7)) - (T(8)/3))) \\ 38739 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(7) - 8)))) - T(3)) \\ 38742 &:= ((-2) + T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) \times (T(8) - 3) \\ 38745 &:= (T((5 + 4)) \times T((-7) + (8 \times T(3)))) \\ 38755 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - (83))) \\ 38779 &:= (((T((T(9) + (7))) \times T(7)) - T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 38784 &:= (48 \times (T(7) + T((T(8) + 3)))) \\ 38793 &:= (((T(T(3)) + T(T(9))) + T(7)) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 38794 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + 8)) - (T(3)))) \\ 38799 &:= ((9 \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) - T(8)) \times 3 \\ 38802 &:= ((T(20) - T(8)) \times (-8) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 38808 &:= ((80 + 88) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 38819 &:= (((T(91) + T(T(8))) \times 8) + 3) \\ 38822 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)) + (8 + T(3))) \\ 38823 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) + T((8 - 3))) \\ 38826 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(2) \times T((8 \times 8)))) \times T(3)) \\ 38829 &:= ((T(9) - 2) \times T((T(8) + (T(8)/T(3)))) \\ 38832 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 8) + (8 \times 3)) \\ 38835 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) - T(83)))) \\ 38837 &:= (((T(T((7 + T(3)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times 8) + (T(T(3)))) \\ 38841 &:= ((1 + T(48)) \times (T(8) - 3)) \\ 38848 &:= (8 \times ((4 + T(T(8))) + T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 38853 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((58 \times T(T(8))) - (T(3)))) \\ 38855 &:= (-5) \times (5 - ((T(8) \times T(8)) \times T(3))) \\ 38856 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T((T(5) - 8))) + 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38857 &:= (T((T(7) - T(5))) \times (T((-8) + T(8))) + T(T(3))) \\ 38859 &:= ((9 \times T(T(5))) \times T(8)) - T((T(8)/T(3))) \\ 38865 &:= (-5) \times (((-6) \times T(8)) \times T(8)) + 3) \\ 38866 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(6))) + 8) \times 8) - (T(3)) \\ 38874 &:= -(((T(4) \times (T(7) - T(88))) + T(3))) \\ 38875 &:= (((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T((8 + 8)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 38892 &:= (((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8))) - (-8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 38894 &:= (((T(4) + T(98)) \times 8) + T(3)) \\ 38895 &:= (T(5) - ((T(9) \times T(8)) \times (-8 \times 3))) \\ 38896 &:= ((T((6 + T(9))) \times 88)/3) \\ 38922 &:= ((T((2/2) + T(9))) \times T(8)) + (T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38924 &:= -((T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) + (-T(9)) \times T((T(8) + T(3)))))) \\ 38928 &:= (8 \times (((T(2) \times T(9)) \times T(8)) + T(3))) \\ 38934 &:= ((((-T(4)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-9)) - T(8)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 38937 &:= ((T((7 + 39)) \times T(8)) + T(T(3))) \\ 38952 &:= (-((T(2) - T(5))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T((8 + 3)))))) \\ 38955 &:= (T(5) + (59 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(3)))))) \\ 38957 &:= ((T(7) + (T(5) \times 9)) \times (8 + T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 38958 &:= (((-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-9)) + T((T(8)/3)) \\ 38964 &:= (4 \times (T(6) + ((T(9) \times T(8)) \times T(3)))) \\ 38973 &:= (-3) + (T(T(7)) \times (-9) + T((8 + T(3)))) \\ 38976 &:= ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times ((T(9) - 8) - T(T(3)))) \\ 38977 &:= (T((T(T(7))/7)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(8)) + (T(3)))) \\ 38979 &:= (-9) + ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times (T(8) \times 3)) \\ 38982 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times (-8)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8))) - (T(3)) \\ 38984 &:= (-4) + (T(8) \times (T(T(9)) + (8 \times T(3)))) \\ 38985 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(8) \times 9)) + T((8 + T(3)))) \\ 38988 &:= (((8 \times T(8)) \times T(9)) + T(8)) \times 3 \\ 38994 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) + (-9) \times T(T(8)))))) \times T(3) \\ 38995 &:= (T(T(-(5 - 9))) \times (T((T(9) - 8)) + (T(3)))) \\ 38997 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times 9) + (T((9 + 8)) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 39075 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(70))) \times (9 + T(3))) \\ 39084 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(09))) - T(T(3))) \\ 39123 &:= ((-3) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 1))) \times (9 \times T(T(3))) \\ 39132 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((-T(3)) - T((1 + T(9)))) \times (-T(3))) \\ 39135 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(31) - (T(T(9)) \times 3)) \\ 39138 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(3) + T((1 + T(9)))) + (T(3))) \\ 39186 &:= (-T(6)) \times (-T(8) - T(((1 + 9) \times T(3)))) \\ 39195 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(9) - 1))) \times (T(9) - T(3))) \\ 39222 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((2 + T(9)))) - T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 39225 &:= -(((T(T(5)) - (2 \times (T(2)⁹))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 39234 &:= (((T(4)³) + T(T(2))) \times (T(9) - T(3))) \\ 39243 &:= (-3) - ((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 39246 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) - T((9 + T(T(3)))))) \\ 39248 &:= (8 \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T((9 - 3)))))) \\ 39249 &:= (9 \times (-T(4)) + T((2 \times T(9)) + 3)) \\ 39253 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))))/(-3)) \\ 39255 &:= (-T(T(5))) + ((T((T(T(5))/2)) + T(9)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 39258 &:= (((T(8) \times T((T(5) + 2))) + T(T(9))) \times T(3)) \\ 39259 &:= -((T(9) - ((5 + 29)³))) \\ 39264 &:= ((T((4 \times T(6))) \times (2 + 9)) - (T(3))) \\ 39265 &:= ((-5) + (T(T(6)) \times T((2 \times 9)))) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 39267 &:= ((T((T(7) + (6))) \times T((2 + 9))) - 3) \\ 39268 &:= (-T(8)) + ((6 + T(-(2 - 9)))³) \\ 39279 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(9))) - (T(3))) \\ 39282 &:= (-2) \times (T(8) - ((T(2)⁹) - T(3))) \\ 39283 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((T(8) - 2)^{9/3}))) \\ 39284 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T((9 \times 3)))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 39285** := ((T(T(5)) + T((T(8)/2))) × (T(9) × 3))
39288 := (-T(8)) + (((T(8) + 2) × T(T(9))) - (T(3)))
39294 := -(T(4) - ((T(9) - (2 + 9))³))
39297 := (-7) + ((T(9) - (2 + 9))³)
39312 := ((-2) + T((-1) + T(T(3)))) × (9 × T(T(3)))
39322 := (-2) + (2 × ((3⁹) - T(T(3))))
39324 := ((4 - 2) × ((3⁹) - T(T(3))))
39325 := (-5) + (((-T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(9)))/T(3))
39327 := (((-7) + T((T(2) × 3))) × T(T(9))) - 3
39328 := (((T(8) - 2)³) + T(9)) - T(T(3))
39342 := (T(T(2)) × (-4 - ((3⁹)/3)))
39343 := (((34³) + T(9)) - T(3))
39345 := ((T((T(5) + T(4 × 3))) × 9) + (T(3)))
39346 := ((-6) × (T(4) - (3⁹)))/3
39347 := (-T(7)) + ((T((T(4) × T(3))) + T(9)) × T(T(3)))
39348 := (T(8) × ((T(4)³) + (93)))
39349 := (T(9) + ((43 - 9)³)
39354 := ((T(4)/5) × ((3⁹) - T(3)))
39355 := (-5) + (T((T(T(5))/3)) × (T(9) + 3))
39367 := (T(7) - ((6 + 3) × T(93)))
39375 := ((T(5) × (-7)) × (3 - T(9 × 3)))
39381 := ((T(18) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(9 + T(3)))
39387 := (((T(T(7)) + (T(T(8)) × T(3))) × 9) - T(T(T(3))))
39396 := (((-6) - T(93)) × (-9)) + 3
39399 := (((-9) - T(93)) × (-9)) - T(T(3))
39417 := (7 × ((T(T(1 + 4))) × T(9)) + T(T(T(3))))
39427 := ((-T(7)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) × 3))
39429 := ((T(T(9)) - 24) × (T(9) - T(3)))
39432 := (((T(T(2))³) - 4) × (-T(9) + T(T(T(3))))
39435 := (((-T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(4)) × T((T(9) - T(3))))))
39438 := (((T(T(8)) × 3) - T(T(-(4 - 9)))) × T(T(3)))
39444 := (((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) + T(4)) × (T(T(9)) + 3))
39445 := (((T(5) + T(4)) × T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(9)) × T(T(3)))
39456 := (6 × (((T(T(5)) × T(T(4))) - T(9)) + T(T(3))))
39459 := ((T((T(9) + T(5))) + 49) × T(T(3)))
39462 := (((-T(2)) - (T(T(6)) × (T(4) - T(T(9)))))/T(3))
39463 := ((3 - (T(T(6)) × (T(4) - T(T(9)))))/T(3))
39465 := (((T(T(5)) × 6) × T(T(4))) - (T(9) × 3))
39466 := ((T(6) - (T(T(6)) × (T(4) - T(T(9)))))/T(3))
39468 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) × ((-4) + T(9)) + 3))
39471 := ((T((1 + 7)) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(3))))
39472 := (((2 × 7)⁴) + T(T(9))) + T(T(3))
39474 := (((T(47) × (T(4) - T(9))) + T(3)))
39479 := (((T(9) - 7) × (4 + T(T(9)))) - 3)
39482 := ((2 + T(8)) × ((T(4) + T(T(9))) - (T(3))))
39483 := (((T(T(3)) × (T(T(8)) + T(4))) - T(T(9))) × 3)
39484 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) - (T(T(4)) × (-9³)))
39486 := ((T(T(6)) × T((8 + T(4)))) - (9 + T(3)))
39492 := (T(T(2)) × ((9⁴) + T((9 - 3))))
39494 := (-T(T((4 + 9)))) + (T((T(T(4)) + 9)) × T(T(3)))
39495 := (T(T(5)) - (9 × (-4 - T(93))))
39498 := -(((T(T(8)) - (T(94) × 9)) + T(T(3))))
39501 := (T(((10/5) × 9)) × T(T(T(3))))
39522 := (T(T(T(2))) + (T((T(2) + T(5))) × T(T((9 - 3))))
39525 := (((T(5) + 2) × 5) × T((9 + T(T(3))))
39528 := (8 × ((T(T(2)) × T((-5) + T(9))) + T(T(3)))
39534 := (((T(T(4)) × T(3)) × T(T(5))) - T(9)) - T(T(3))
39535 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3))) × (-5) + T(T(9)))/T(3))
39543 := (-3) + (((T(T(4)) × T(T(5))) - 9) × T(3))
39546 := -(((T(6) - T(45)) × (T(9) - T(3))))
39549 := (T(T(9)) + ((4 + T((T(5) + T(9)))) × T(T(3)))
39552 := ((T(2) + 5) × ((5 × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3))))
39555 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(5)) - 5) × T(T(9)))/3))
39558 := (((8 + T(5)) + T(5)) × (T(T(9)) + (T(3))))
39564 := (4 × ((6 + T(-(T(5) - T(9)))) × T(T(3)))
39576 := ((T(6) × T(T(7))) + ((5 × T(T(9))) × T(3))
39582 := (T(2) × (-T(T(8))) - (-((T(5) + T(9)) × T(T(T(3))))))
39585 := (-T(5)) + (8 × T((T(5 + 9)) - T(3)))
39588 := (T(8) + (8 × ((5 × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3))))))
39594 := ((T(T(4)) × ((T(9) × T(5)) + T(9))) - (T(3)))
39595 := (-5) + (((-T(9)) - T(T(5))) × (-9 - T(T(T(3))))))
39606 := ((T(60) × T(6)) + T((T(9) + 3)))
39624 := (((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6))) - (T(T(9)) - 3))
39627 := (((7 × T((2 + T(6)))) - T(9)) × T(T(3)))
39636 := ((T(T(6)) × T((3 × 6))) + (T(9) × 3))
39642 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(4)) - T(T(6)))) - ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))))
39644 := (((-T(T(4)) × (T(T(4)) - T((-6) + T(9)))) - T(T(T(3))))
39645 := (((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(6))) - T((T(9) - T(3))))
39648 := ((T((T(8) + 4)) + 6) × (T(9) + 3))
39654 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(5))) × 6) + (9 × T(3)))
39663 := (((T(3) × T(66)) - T(9)) × 3)
39672 := -(((T(2) + ((-7) × T(6)) × T(9)) × T(3))
39675 := -((T(5) + (((-7) × T(6)) × T(9)) × T(3)))
39684 := ((((-T(4)) + T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) × T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))
39685 := (-5) + (T((8 + 6) × T(9 × 3)))
39687 := ((T((T(7) - 8)) × (T(6) × 9)) - 3)
39711 := (T(-((1 + 1) - (7 × 9))) × T(T(3)))
39721 := (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T((7 + 9)) + T(T(3))))
39726 := ((T(6) × T((2 × T(7)))) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(3))))
39728 := (8 × (T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) + (T(93))))
39729 := ((T(9) × ((T(T(T(2))) × (-7)) + T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(3))))
39732 := ((2 × T(T(3))) × T(((T(7) + 9) + T(3))))
39735 := (T(5) × (3 + (7 × T(9 × 3))))

- 39738** := ((T(T(8))/T(3)) × (T(T(7)) - (T(9) + 3)))
39744 := (((T(4) × T(T(4))) - T(T(7))) × (T(9) + T(T(3))))
39745 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(7))) - (9 + T(3)))
39746 := ((-T(6) + T(T(4))) × (-7) + T((T(9) + 3)))
39753 := (((-3) - T(T(5))) + (T((7 × 9)))) × T(T(3))
39754 := (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)))) × T(7)) - (9 - 3))
39756 := (((-T(T(6))) - T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))))) × (-9) + 3)
39762 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) × T(7)) - 9) × T(3)
39765 := (-5) × ((T(T(6)) × (-T(7))) - T((9 × T(3))))
39767 := (-T((7 + 6))) × (T(7) - T((9 + T(T(3))))
39774 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)) - (7 + T(9)))) × T(T(3)))
39775 := (T(5) + (T(7) × ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) - T(T(3))))
39784 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(8))) + ((T(79) - T(3))))
39789 := -(T(T(9)) - ((8 × 7) × (9³)))
39792 := (2 × ((T(T(9)) × (T(7) - 9) + T(T(T(3))))
39795 := (-T(5)) × ((T(9) - T((T(7) + T(9)))) + 3)
39798 := ((T((8 + T(9))) × T(7)) - (T(9) × T(3)))
39814 := (T(T(T(4))) + (((1 + T(8)) × T(T(9))) - T(T(3))))
39816 := ((T(T(6)) + ((1 + T(8)) × T(9))) × T(T(3)))
39819 := ((T((T(9) + 1)) × T(8)) + T((T(9) - 3)))
39822 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(2))) × 8)) + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))))
39825 := ((-5) + T((T(2) × 8))) × (T(9) × 3)
39828 := ((T(8) × (2 - T((T(8) + T(9)))))/(-3))
39831 := ((1 + T((3 + T(8)))) × (T(9) + T(3)))
39834 := (((T(4) × (-3) + T(T(8)))) + 9) × T(3)
39837 := ((7 + ((T(3) + T(8)) × T(9))) × T(T(3)))
39852 := (-((T(2) - T(5))) × T(((T(8) - 9) × 3)))
39854 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((-((5 × 8)) × T(T(9))) + (T(3))))
39855 := (T(T(5)) + (-T(5)) × (-T((8 × 9))) - T(T(3))))
39858 := ((T((8 + 5)) × T((8 × 9)))/T(3))
39864 := ((T(4) × ((6 × T(T(8))) - 9)) - T(3))
39872 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) × ((-8) - T(9) + T(T(T(3))))
39873 := (((T(T(T(3))) - (7 × T(T(8)))) × (-9)) - T(3))
39876 := (((T(T(6)) - (7 × T(T(8)))) × (-9)) - 3)
39879 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) + T(8)) × (9 × 3))
39882 := (T((2 × T(8))) + ((T(8) × T(T(9))) - T(3)))
39884 := ((T(4) + T(T(8))) × ((8 + T(9)) + T(3)))
39885 := (-5) × (((T(T(8)) × (-T(8))) + T(9))/3)
39886 := ((T(T(6)) × ((8/8) + T(T(9))))/T(3))
39888 := (T(8) + ((T(8) × T((T(8) + T(9))))/3))
39907 := (T(T(7)) - ((0 - T((9 + 9))) × T(T(T(3))))
39923 := (((T(T(T(3))) × (2 + T(T(9)))) - 9)/T(3))
39924 := ((T(4) + 2) × (T((9 × 9)) + T(3)))
39926 := (((T(T(6)) × (2 + T(T(9)))) + 9)/T(3))
39927 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(2)))) + (9 × T(93)))
39928 := (-8) - (-((2⁹) × T((9 + 3)))
39933 := ((3 + T(39)) × (T(9) + T(3)))
39934 := (T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) + (9 × T(93)))
39936 := (((6/3)⁹) × T((9 + 3)))
39942 := (((T(T(2)) + T((-4) + T(9))) + T(T(9))) × T(T(3)))
39944 := (4 × (-4) + (T(9) × (-9) + T(T(T(3))))
39945 := (-T(5)) + ((T(4) × T((T(9) - 9))) × T(3))
39947 := (-T(7)) + ((-T(4) + T(T(9))) × (T(9) - T(3)))
39948 := ((T(T(8)) × T(T(4))) + ((T((9 × 9)) - 3))
39954 := (((4 × T(5)) × T((T(9) - 9))) - T(3))
39955 := (-5) + (T(T(5)) × (-T(9) - T((9 × 3))))
39963 := (T(T(T(3))) × (((6 - T(T(9))) - 9)/(-T(3))))
39969 := -((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(9) + T(3))))
39972 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7))) + (T(9) × (T(T(9)) - 3))
39974 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(9) - T(T(3))))
39976 := ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) - (-9 × T(93)))
39977 := ((-T(7)) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(9)))) + (T(T(9)) × T(T(3)))
39978 := (-T(8)) + (T((-7) + T(9)) × (9 × T(3)))
39981 := (((1 + T(8)) × (T(T(9)) + T(9))) + T(T(3)))
39983 := (((T(T(T(3))) × (8 + T(T(9)))) - T(T(9)))/T(3))
39984 := (((T(4) × T(89)) - T(9)) - T(T(3)))
39987 := (((T((7 × 8)) × 9) - T(T(9))) × 3)
39993 := ((39 × (T(T(9)) - 9)) - T(T(3)))
39997 := ((T(7) + 9) × T((T((T(9))/T(9)))/T(3)))
40326 := (T(T(6)) - (-((T(2)^{T(3)}) × T(T(04))))
40425 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(04)))
40625 := ((5^{T(2)}) × T((T(6) - (0 - 4))))
40626 := (T((6²) × (6 + T(T(04))))
40639 := ((T(9) × T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) + 04)
40646 := (((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(6))) - T(04))
40656 := (T(T(6)) × (T(T(5)) + (60 - 4)))
40662 := (T(T(2)) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(04))))
40755 := (55 × T((T(7) + T(04))))
40788 := (-T(8)) - (T(8) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(T(04))))
40796 := ((T(6) × T((9 × 7))) - T(T(T(04))))
40875 := (-5) - (-T(7) × (-80) + T(T(T(4))))
40932 := -(((T(2) × T(3)) - (T(90) × T(4)))
40934 := -(((T(4) + T(3)) - (T(90) × T(4)))
40935 := (T(5) - ((3 - T(90)) × T(4)))
40937 := ((-7) - T(3)) + (T(90) × T(4))
40938 := ((T(8)/(-3)) + (T(90) × T(4)))
40951 := ((1⁵) + (T(90) × T(4)))
40952 := -(((T(2) - 5) - (T(90) × T(4)))
40953 := (T(-((3 - 5))) + ((T(90) × T(4)))
40956 := ((T(6) - T(5)) + (T(90) × T(4)))
40959 := ((T(9)/5) + (T(90) × T(4)))
40962 := ((2 × 6) + (T(90) × T(4)))
40971 := (T(-((1 - 7))) + ((T(90) × T(4)))
40972 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T(7) + (T(90) × T(4))))

- 40974** := $((-4) + T(7)) + (T(90) \times T(4))$
40983 := $((-3) + T(8)) + (T(90) \times T(4))$
40992 := $-(((T(2) - T(9)) - (T(90) \times T(4))))$
40995 := $((5 \times 9) + (T(90) \times T(4)))$
41013 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((T(10 + 1) - (4))))$
41184 := $(T((4 \times 8)) \times T((1 + 1) + T(4)))$
41223 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) - 1)) + T(4))$
41265 := $((T(5) + T((T(6) + T(T(2)))))) \times T(14)$
41275 := $((T(T(5)) + 7) \times T((21 + 4)))$
41286 := $(-6) + (T(T(8)) \times ((T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(4))))$
41292 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-1) + T(4)))$
41295 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(9)))/T(2) - T(14))$
41322 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(2)^3) \times (-1) + T(T(T(4))))))$
41325 := $((5^2) \times T(((3 - 1) + T(T(4))))$
41328 := $((8 \times T(T(2))) \times T((31 + T(4))))$
41349 := $((T(9) \times 4) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(-(1 - 4))))$
41382 := $((T(2) - T(8)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(-(1) + T(T(4))))$
41392 := $((-2) + (T(T(9)) \times T((3 + 1)))) \times 4$
41395 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(9)))/3 - (1 + 4))$
41404 := $((40 \times T(T(T(4) - 1))) + 4)$
41424 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(4) \times T(T(-(1) + T(4))))))$
41426 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4) - 1))) - T(T(T(4))))$
41445 := $((5 - T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(T(4)) - 1))/(-T(T(4))))$
41467 := $((-T(7)) \times (6 - T(T(T(4)))) - T(-(1) + T(T(4))))$
41475 := $(T(5) \times (T(74) - T(1 \times 4)))$
41479 := $(-T(9)) + ((T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((1 + T(T(4))))$
41485 := $((-T(5)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-4) + 1)) + T(T(T(4))))$
41488 := $(-8) + ((T(8) - T(4)) \times T((1 + T(T(4))))$
41496 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(9)) - T(T((4 - 1))) \times 4)$
41498 := $((T(8) - 9) \times (T(T(T(4)) - 1)) - T(T(4)))$
41499 := $(9 \times (-T(9)) + T((41 + T(T(4))))$
41524 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((2 + 5))) - T((1 + T(T(4))))$
41525 := $((5^2) \times ((T(T(5)) + 1) + T(T(T(4))))$
41553 := $((3^5) \times T((T(5) - ((1 - 4))))$
41565 := $(-T(5)) + ((T(6) + (5 + 1)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41568 := $(8 \times (T(6) - (-5) \times T(T(-(1) + T(4))))$
41574 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) - (5 + 1) - T(T(T(4))))$
41575 := $(-5) + (T((7 \times 5)) \times T((1 + T(4))))$
41592 := $((-T(2)) - (T(9) \times T(T((5 + 1)))) \times (-4))$
41594 := $((T(T(4))^{T(9)/T(5)} + 1)/4)$
41595 := $(T(5) + ((T(9) \times T(T((5 + 1)))) \times 4))$
41596 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(9)) + (5 - 1)) \times 4$
41612 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T(61)) + T(4)$
41622 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((2 - T(T(6))) + T(T((1 + T(4))))$
41625 := $(T(5) \times T(((2^6) + T(1 \times 4))))$
41634 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(3) + T(6))) + (-1) + T(T(4)))$
41635 := $((T((5 + 3)) \times T(6)) + 1) \times T(T(4))$
41652 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 5) \times (6 + T((1 + T(T(4))))$
41656 := $((6^5) - (-((T(6) + 1) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41657 := $((7 + T(5)) \times T(61)) + T(T(4))$
41664 := $(T((T(4) + T(6))) \times (6 \times 14))$
41679 := $((T((-9) + T(7))) \times T(T(6))) - T(T((1 + T(4))))$
41685 := $((5 \times T(8)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(14))$
41689 := $(-T((T(9) + 8))) + (T((6 + 1)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41692 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) + T((6 + 1))) \times 4$
41727 := $((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) \times T((-1) + T(T(4))))$
41734 := $-((T(T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (-((T(7) + 1) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41735 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + 1 + T(T(T(4)))$
41742 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(7) - (1^4)))$
41746 := $((6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(7) - 1) + 4)$
41748 := $((T((8 + T(T(4)))) - T(7)) \times T(T(-(1 - 4))))$
41762 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) + (-T(7)) \times (-1 - T(T(T(4))))$
41768 := $(8 \times (T(T((6 + 7))) + T(T(-(1) + T(4))))$
41769 := $((9 \times T(6)) \times (T(T((7 - 1))) - T(4)))$
41773 := $(-3) + (-T(7)) \times (-7 - T(-(1) + T(T(4))))$
41775 := $((T(T(5)) - ((-7) + T(T(7))) \times T(14))$
41776 := $((T(6) + 7) \times (7 + T((-1) + T(T(4))))$
41779 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(7) + 1) - T(4))$
41785 := $(-5) + ((-8) + T(T(7))) \times T(14))$
41788 := $((8 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + T(T((1 \times 4))))$
41794 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(7)) - T((1 + T(4)))$
41823 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) - T(-(1) + T(4))))$
41832 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(38))) \times (1 + T(T(4))))$
41835 := $(-T(5)) + ((T(T((T(3) - 8))) - 1) \times T(4))$
41845 := $(-T(5)) - (-T(4)) \times T(T((8 + 1) + 4))$
41875 := $(T(5) + (-T(7)) \times (T((8 + 1)) - T(T(T(4))))$
41914 := $(T(T(4)) + (-1) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
41915 := $(T(T((5 - 1))) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
41932 := $((2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) + 1)) - T(T(T(4))))$
41935 := $(T(5) + ((T(3) + T(91)) \times T(4)))$
41937 := $((-7) \times ((-T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - 1) - T(T(T(4)))$
41938 := $(T((T(8)/3)) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
41945 := $((T(5) - ((T(4) + T(91)) \times T(4)))$
41947 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times 91) - (4)$
41948 := $((8 + T(T(4))) \times T(T((9 - 1))) - T(4))$
41952 := $(T(2) \times ((T(5) \times T(T(9))) - 1) - T(T(T(4))))$
41958 := $(T(T(8)) \times ((59 \times 1) + 4))$
41959 := $((9 \times T((5 + 91))) + T(T(4)))$
41962 := $((T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(T((9 - 1))) + (4))$
41965 := $((5 \times T(6)) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
41972 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times 7) \times (T(T(9)) + 1)) - T(T(T(4)))$
41984 := $((T(4) - T(T(8))) \times (-9) - T(T((1 \times 4))))$
41995 := $((T(5) \times 9) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
42025 := $((-5) + T(20))^{-2+4}$

- 42036 := $((6^{T(3)}) - (T(02) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 42119 := $((9 \times T(T(T(T(1+1)))) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42126 := $(T(6) \times (T(21 \times T(2))) - T(4))$
 42133 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1) \times T((T(2) + T(4)))$
 42147 := $((-T(7) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(1+2)) + T(T(T(4))))$
 42148 := $((T(8) \times T((41 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
 42149 := $((T(T(9)) \times 41) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)))$
 42168 := $((T(T(8)) \times 61) + 2) + T(T(T(4)))$
 42169 := $((-T(T(9))) + (T((6+1) \times (T(2) + T(T(T(4))))))$
 42172 := $((2 \times T(T(7))) - 1) \times (-T(2) + T(T(4)))$
 42174 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(71) \times T(2))) / T(4))$
 42175 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(7) - (1 \times 2)))) + T(T(4)))$
 42195 := $((-T(T(5)) - (91 \times T((T(2) \times T(4))))$
 42196 := $((T(6) \times ((T(9) - 1)^2)) + T(T(T(4))))$
 42222 := $((-T(T(2))) + (T((2 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 4))))$
 42224 := $(T(T((T(4) - T(2)))) \times (2 \times (-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
 42225 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(T(2) + T(T(T(2)))) / T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
 42226 := $((T((T(6) \times T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (2 \times T(T(4))))$
 42228 := $((-T(8) \times (T(2) - T(2 \times 24))))$
 42235 := $(((-5) + T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))) + 4)$
 42237 := $(T((-7) + T(3^2))) \times (2 + T(T(4)))$
 42252 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(5-2))) \times T(2))) - 4)$
 42255 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(5)) \times 2) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4))))$
 42256 := $((T(T(6)) + (T(5^2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))$
 42263 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T((T(6) \times T(2))) - T(2))) - T(4))$
 42266 := $((-T(6) \times (-6) - T(2^{T(T(2))})) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42269 := $((((-T(9)) + T(T(6))) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4)$
 42273 := $((T((3 \times 7)) \times T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
 42275 := $(5 \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(4)))$
 42276 := $(6 \times ((T(7) \times T(2))^2 - T(4))$
 42279 := $((T((9 \times 7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (2 + T(T(4))))$
 42281 := $((T(-((1 - 8^2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)))$
 42282 := $((T(2)^{8-2}) \times (T(2) + T(T(4))))$
 42283 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) \times T(2) + T((T(T(T(2))) + 4)))$
 42284 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
 42285 := $((T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - T(2))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 42287 := $((7 + T(8^2)) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42288 := $((8 \times T(T(8))) - ((-T(2)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 42292 := $((T(2)^9 \times 2) + T((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))$
 42294 := $(((-T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(2)))^4))$
 42295 := $((-T(5) - (T((9-2))^2)) \times T(T(4)))$
 42299 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(9)) - 2)) - T(T((T(2) + T(4))))$
 42312 := $((-T(2)) + (T(13) \times T((T(2) \times T(4))))$
 42315 := $(T((T(5) + (1 - 3))) \times T((T(2) \times T(4))))$
 42323 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) - (T(2) + T(4)))$
 42324 := $((T(4) \times T(T((T(2) \times 3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4)$
 42325 := $((-T(5)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) + 4)$
 42326 := $((T((T(6) \times T(2))) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(2))) - (4))$
 42328 := $((-8) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((3 \times T((2+4))))$
 42329 := $((9 + T(2^{T(3)})) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42331 := $((-1) + ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) - 4)$
 42332 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((3 \times T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(2)) - T(4))))$
 42333 := $((-3) + (T(T(3)) \times T((3 \times T((2+4))))$
 42335 := $((-T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42336 := $((6 \times T(3)) \times T((3 \times 2^4)))$
 42338 := $((-8) + ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) + T(4))$
 42345 := $((-5) + ((T(T(T(4))) / (T(3) / T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
 42346 := $((T(6) \times T((T(4) \times T(3)) + T(2))) + T(4))$
 42347 := $((T((7 \times T(4))) + T(3)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - 4)$
 42348 := $((T((8 + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) + (2 + T(4)))$
 42349 := $((T(9) \times T(43)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4))$
 42355 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 4)$
 42357 := $((7 \times T(53)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 42361 := $((1 + T(63)) \times T(T(T(2))) + 4)$
 42363 := $((T(3)^6) + (-3) \times T((-2) + T(T(4))))$
 42364 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(6) + T(3))) \times T((T(2) + 4)))$
 42365 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(T(3)) - 2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42366 := $((T(6) \times T(63)) + (T(2) \times T(4)))$
 42368 := $(T(8) + ((T(6) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) - 4)$
 42374 := $((T(4) - ((T(7)^3) \times (-2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
 42375 := $((-T(5)) \times (T((T(7) + 3)) - T((T(2)^4)))$
 42376 := $(((-6) - (T(7)^3)) \times (-2)) - T(T(T(4)))$
 42379 := $((-T((T(9) - 7))) + (T((T(T(3)) / T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 42385 := $(5 \times ((T(8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(4))))$
 42388 := $((T(8) \times T((8 \times T(3)))) - T(2) + T(T(4)))$
 42392 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3))) \times 2) - T(T(T(4)))$
 42396 := $(6 \times ((T((T(9) + 3)) \times T(T(2))) + T(4)))$
 42397 := $((T((7 \times 9)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))$
 42398 := $((T(8) \times (T((T(9) + 3)) + 2)) - T(4))$
 42399 := $((T(9) \times T(9)) - T(3)) \times T((2 + 4))$
 42415 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-1) - (T(T(T(4))) / (-2))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
 42416 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T((1 \times 4))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)))$
 42417 := $((T(7) - 1) \times ((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
 42418 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((1 + T(4)))) + 2) - T(T(T(4)))$
 42422 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)))$
 42426 := $((6^{T(2)} - T(4))^2 - T(4))$
 42427 := $((-T(T(7))) \times (-2^{T(4)}) - T(T(T(2)))) / T(4)$
 42428 := $((T(T(8)) - T(2)) \times (4^{T(2)})) - (4)$
 42432 := $(T((2 \times T(3))) \times (4 \times T(2^4)))$
 42434 := $((4 \times T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) / (-2)) \times (-T(T(4))))$
 42435 := $(T(T(5)) + (T((3 + T(4))) \times T((T(2) \times T(4))))$
 42436 := $((6^3 - T(4))^{-2+4})$

- 42438** := $((T(8) - 3) \times (-T(4)) + (T(T(2))^4))$
42439 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(4) \times 2))) + (4))$
42445 := $(T(54) - ((4^{T(T(2))}) \times (-T(4))))$
42446 := $((((T(6) \times T(4)) - (4)^2) + T(4))$
42448 := $(8 \times ((T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times T(2)) - 4))$
42449 := $((((T(9) \times 4) + (4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(4))))$
42455 := $(5 \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))))$
42456 := $((6 \times (T(T(5)) - (4))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42458 := $(-(8 + 5) \times (T(T(4)) - T((T(2))^4)))$
42462 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(64) - T(2)) - T(T(4))))$
42464 := $(4 \times (((-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) - T(4))$
42465 := $(T(5) \times (T(((T(6) + T(4)) \times T(2)) - T(T(T(4))))))$
42466 := $((6^6) - 4) - T(T((T(2) + T(4))))$
42468 := $(-T(8)) + ((-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-24))$
42475 := $((((5 \times T(T(7))) - T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
42476 := $(T(T(6)) + (T((7 \times T(4))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - 4)))$
42477 := $((-T(7)) \times ((-T(7)) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))))$
42478 := $(-T(T(8))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 24)$
42479 := $((-9) + T(T(7))) \times ((T(T(4)) - T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42483 := $(T(T(3)) \times (((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42487 := $((7 + T((8 + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 4)$
42492 := $((T((2 \times T(9))) \times T(4)) + 2) + T(T(T(4))))$
42494 := $((((4 \times T(9)) + (4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) - T(4)$
42496 := $((T(T(6)) \times (9 - T(T(4)))) + 2) \times (-4)$
42497 := $((-T(7)) - (-9) \times T(T(4))) \times T((T(2) + T(4)))$
42498 := $((T(8) - 9) \times ((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))))$
42513 := $(3 \times (((-1) + T(T(5)))^2) + T(4))$
42524 := $((T((4^{T(2)})) \times 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4)$
42525 := $(525 \times (T(2)^4))$
42526 := $(T(6^2)) + (T(T((T(5) - 2))) \times T(4))$
42528 := $((T(T(8)) + 2) + (T(T((T(5) - 2))) \times T(4)))$
42529 := $((T(9)^2) \times T(T((5 - 2))) + (4))$
42532 := $(-(23 + 5) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
42535 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((3 \times T(T(5))) - T(T(2)))) + T(T(4)))$
42538 := $(-((T(T(8)) - ((3 \times (T(T(5))^2)) + (4))))$
42542 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T((5 + 2)))) + T(4)$
42545 := $(-((T(5) - (T((4 \times 5))^2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
42546 := $(T(6) \times (T((4 \times T(5)) + T(2))) + T(4))$
42547 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) - T((T(T(T(2))) - 4)))$
42555 := $(T(5) \times (T((5 \times T(5))) - (T(2) + T(4))))$
42562 := $((-T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5))^2))) + T(T(4))$
42567 := $((7 \times T(T(6))) + (T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(4))$
42571 := $(1 + ((T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4))$
42572 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(7)) \times 5)) - (T(2) + T(T(4))))$
42573 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7))) \times 5) - 2) - T(T(4))$
42574 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T((2 \times 4))))))$
42575 := $(((-T(5)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-5 + 2)) - T(T(4))$
42576 := $(6 + ((T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4))$
42577 := $((T(T(7)) \times (7 \times T(5))) + 2) - T(T(4))$
42578 := $(8 + ((T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4))$
42579 := $(9 + ((T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4))$
42582 := $(-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times T((2 + T(4))))))$
42584 := $(-4) + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times T((2 + T(4))))$
42585 := $((T((5 \times 8)) \times 52) - T(T(4))$
42588 := $((T(8) \times T((8 + 5))) \times (T(2) + T(4))$
42592 := $(((-((2 - 9)) + T(5))^{T(2)}) \times 4)$
42597 := $(-T(7)) - ((-T(9)) + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
42613 := $(T(T(3)) + (((1 + T(6))^{T(2)}) \times 4))$
42616 := $((6 + ((1 + T(6))^{T(2)})) \times 4)$
42622 := $(-2) + (2^6) \times T(T((2 \times 4))))$
42624 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T((6 \times (2 + 4))))$
42625 := $((-5) + T((T(2) + ((6^2)))) \times T(T(4))$
42628 := $((8^2) \times T((6^2))) + (4)$
42629 := $((T(9) + 2) \times (T((T(6) \times 2)) + (4)))$
42634 := $((4^3) \times T((6^2))) + T(4)$
42636 := $((T(63) \times T(6)) + T(24))$
42644 := $(((-4) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6))) \times (-T((T(2) + (4))))$
42645 := $(((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(6)/T(2)))) - (T(T(4))))$
42648 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(4) + (6))) + T(T(2))) \times 4$
42655 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))) + 4$
42656 := $((65 + T(6)) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + T(4))))$
42659 := $((9 \times T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) - T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42669 := $((T((T(9) - (6))) \times (-T(6))) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))$
42672 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(6))) \times (2^4)$
42675 := $(T(5) \times (T(76) - (T(2)^4)))$
42676 := $((T(6) + ((T(7) - (6))^{T(2)})) \times 4)$
42678 := $((-T(8)) - T(T(7))) - (-T((T(6)/T(2)))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
42685 := $(5 \times (((T(8)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))$
42687 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((8 + 6))) + 2) + T(T(4))$
42688 := $((-8) - (-8) \times (T(T(6))^2)) / T(4)$
42693 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(9)) - (-T(6)) \times (-2 + T(T(T(4))))$
42695 := $((5 \times T(9)) \times T((T(6) - 2))) - T(T(4))$
42696 := $(6 \times (-T(9)) - (-T(T(6))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(4))))$
42699 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 4)$
42714 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((1 \times 7))) - T(T((T(2) + (4))))$
42715 := $(5 \times (((1 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4))$
42718 := $(T((T((8 + 1)) + (7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(4))$
42721 := $(-((T(T(T(1 + 2)))) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4))))))$
42722 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - 2)) + (-T(7)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
42723 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - 2) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4))))))$
42725 := $((5 \times (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(4))$
42728 := $((T((8^2)) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4))$

- 42732** := $(-T(2) + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(7))) \times (T(2) \times T(T(4))))$
42734 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(3))) - (-T(7) \times (-2) + T(T(T(4))))$
42735 := $((5 \times 37) \times T(T((2+4)))$
42736 := $(-T((T(6)+3)) + (-T(7)) \times (T(2) - T(T(T(4))))$
42739 := $-((T(9+T(T(3)))) - (-T(7) \times (-T(2) - T(T(T(4))))$
42742 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7)) + T((2 \times T(4))))$
42743 := $((-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(7))^2)/4)$
42745 := $((((5 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4)$
42746 := $((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times (-T(T(7))))/(-T((2+4)))$
42749 := $(T((T(9) + T(4))) + ((T(T(7))^2)/4)$
42762 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(6))/(-7)) \times (T(T(2))^4)))$
42763 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (-((T(6) + (7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
42764 := $(-4) - ((T(T(6))/(-7)) \times (T(T(2))^4))$
42767 := $-((T(T(7)) - ((6+7) \times T((T(2))^4)))$
42768 := $(((-T(8)) \times T(T(6)))/7) \times (-T((2 \times 4)))$
42792 := $((T(2) + 9) \times (T((T(7) \times T(2))) - 4))$
42794 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T(9) + ((T(T(7))^2)/4))$
42795 := $((T((5+9)) \times T(T(7))) - (-T(2)) \times T(T(4)))$
42796 := $(-((T(T(6)+9)) + (-T(7)) \times (T(2) - T(T(T(4))))$
42797 := $(T(T(7)) - ((-T(9 \times 7))) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(4)))$
42798 := $(-T((T(8) - 9)) + (-T(7)) \times (-2 - T(T(T(4))))$
42799 := $((9 \times (T(97) + 2)) + 4)$
42812 := $(T((T(T(2)) + 1)) \times ((-8) - T(2)) + T(T(T(4))))$
42815 := $((-5) + ((-1) + T(8))^{T(2)}) - T(T(4))$
42817 := $(-T(7)) + ((-1) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(T(4))$
42822 := $((T((2^{T(2)})) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42823 := $((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) + ((T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42824 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42825 := $(-((T(5)^{T(2)})) - ((-T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
42826 := $((T(T(T(6-2)))) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))$
42828 := $((T(8) \times (-2)) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42834 := $((4^3) \times T(T(8))) + T((2 \times T(4)))$
42839 := $(((-9) + (T(3) \times T(8)))^2) - T(4)$
42852 := $((T(2) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) + T(2)) \times 4$
42853 := $((3^5) - T(8))^2 + 4$
42855 := $(T(5) \times ((-T(5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-2))) + T(T(T(4))))$
42856 := $(T(T(6)) + ((-5) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(T(4)))$
42857 := $(-((T(7) + T(5))) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42859 := $((9 \times (T(5) + 8))^2) + T(4)$
42864 := $((-4) + (T(6) \times T(8))) \times (2 + T(T(4)))$
42865 := $((((5-6) + T(8))^{T(2)}) - T(4))$
42867 := $((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + ((-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
42871 := $((((-1) + T(7)) + 8)^{T(2)}) - 4$
42872 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (7 - (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42873 := $(3 \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) - T((T(T(T(2))) + 4)))$
42874 := $((T(47) \times (T(8) + 2)) + T(4))$
42875 := $((5 \times 7)^{T(8-2-4)})$
42877 := $(T(7) - (((T(T(7)) + 8)^2)/(-4)))$
42878 := $((T(T(8)) + (7)) \times T((8 + T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
42879 := $((T(9) \times T(7))/T(8))^{T(2)} + 4$
42882 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(8) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)))$
42883 := $(T((T(T(3)) + (8+8))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
42884 := $((4 + T(T(8))) \times (8^2)) + 4$
42885 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(8) + T(8))) + T(T((2+4))))$
42886 := $(-(6+8) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42891 := $(-(1 \times 9) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42892 := $((-T(2) + T(T(9))) + (T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4)))$
42893 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(9) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(2)))) - T(4))$
42895 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(9) \times 8) - T(2))) + T(T(4)))$
42896 := $((T((-6) + T(9))) \times T((8+2))) - 4$
42897 := $-((T(-((7-9))) - (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42899 := $(-(9/9) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42911 := $(11 + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$
42915 := $(T(5) + (T((T(-((1-9))) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42921 := $(T(T((1+2))) + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$
42922 := $(22 + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$
42923 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$
42924 := $(42 \times (T(T(9)) - (T(2) + T(4))))$
42925 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T((-2) + T(T(4))))$
42927 := $((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(92) \times T(4))))$
42942 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T((9-2)))) - T(4)$
42944 := $(44 + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$
42945 := $(T(5) + ((-((T(4) - T(9)))^{T(2)})) + T(T(4)))$
42948 := $((T(84) + 9) \times T(2)) \times 4$
42949 := $(T(9) - ((-T(T(4))) \times T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) - 4)$
42952 := $((T(T(2)) + T((-5) + T(9))) \times (-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
42955 := $(-(5^5) + (T(9) \times (2^{T(4)})))$
42956 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(5) + T((9 \times 2)))) - T(4))$
42957 := $((T(7) + T(5)) \times (T(T(9)) - T((2 \times 4))))$
42958 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(9)))) + T((-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
42961 := $(-1) + (((T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4)$
42962 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(6) + (T(9)^2))) - 4)$
42963 := $(-3) + ((T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times T(T((2+4))))$
42965 := $((T(T((T(5) - 6)))) \times (T(9) - 2) - T(T(T(4))))$
42966 := $(T(6) \times (T(6) + (T(9)^{-2+4})))$
42968 := $(-8) + (((T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4))$
42969 := $((9 \times T(6)) + (T(92) \times T(4)))$
42972 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T((-7) + T(9))) \times (T(2) + T(T(4))))$
42973 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-7)) + (T((9-2) \times T(T(T(4))))$
42974 := $(-4) + (T((-7) + T(9))) \times (T(2) + T(T(4)))$
42976 := $((T(T(T((T(6)/7)))) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4))$
42977 := $(77 + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))$

- 42978 := (T((T(8) - (7 - 9))) × (T(2) + T(T(4))))
 42979 := (T(T(9)) + (-T(7)) × ((T(9) - T(2)) - T(T(T(4))))))
 42984 := ((T(-((T(4) - T(8)))) + (T(9) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) × 4)
 42985 := (((-T(5)) × T((8 + T(9)))) × (-2)) + T(T(4))
 42988 := ((8 + T(8)) × ((T(T(9)) - T(2)) - T(T(4))))
 42995 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(9) + 2)) - T(4))
 42996 := (T(6) - (T(9) × ((-T(9)) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)))
 42997 := (((T(7) + T(T(9))) × (T(9) - T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))
 42999 := (99 + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) × T(T(4))))
 43036 := (T((T(6)/3)) × ((0 - 3) + T(T(T(4))))
 43065 := ((-T(T(5))) + T((T(6) + T(T(03)))) × T(T(4)))
 43105 := (-T(5)) + (T((01 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43113 := (-((T(3) + 1)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43114 := (-T((4 - 1)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43115 := (-5) - ((-1) × T((1 + T(3)))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43116 := ((T((6 + 1)) × T(T(T(1 + 3)))) - 4)
 43118 := ((T(81) × 13) - T(T(4)))
 43132 := ((2 × T(3)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43134 := (T(T(4 × 3))) × ((1 + 3) + T(4))
 43135 := (T(5) + (T(T(T(3 + 1)))) × T(3 + 4))
 43137 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(3 + 1)))) + (T(T(3)) - 4))
 43141 := (T(T(-((1 - 4)))) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43142 := ((T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) × (1 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
 43144 := (4 × (((T(T(T(4))) + 1) × T(3)) + T(T(T(4))))
 43145 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(4 + 1)))) × 3) - T(T(4))
 43147 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) + (-1) + T(3 + 4))
 43148 := ((T(T(T(8 - 4))) + 1) × T(3 + 4))
 43152 := ((2⁵) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43156 := ((T(6) + T(5)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43162 := ((2 × T(6)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43165 := (T((T(5) - 6)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43168 := ((8 × 6) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43172 := (-T(2)) + ((T(7) × T(T(T(1 + 3)))) + (T(T(4))))
 43173 := ((T(3) + 7) × T(((1 × 3)⁴))
 43174 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + (-1) + T((T(3) + 4)))
 43175 := ((5 + T((T(7 + 1)) + 3)) × T(T(4))
 43176 := ((T(6) + 7) × (-((1 - 3)) + T(T(T(4))))
 43183 := (T(T(T(3))) + (T((8 - 1)) × (-T(3)) + T(T(T(4))))
 43185 := (-T(5)) + ((-T(8)) × T(T((-1) + T(3)))) × (-T(4))
 43186 := ((T(6) - 8) × (1 + T((3⁴)))
 43193 := (((T(T(T(3))) - (T(9) - 1)) × T(T(T(3)))) - 4)
 43195 := ((T(T(5)) - T(9)) + (T((1 + T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))
 43204 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(02)) × T(3 + 4))
 43214 := (T(4) + (T((1 + T(T(2)))) × (3 + T(T(T(4))))))
 43225 := (((T(T(5))²) × T(2)) + T(T(3))) + (4)
 43228 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T((-2) + T(T(3)))) + 4)
 43229 := (((T(T(9)) × 2) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)
 43232 := (T((T(T(T(2)))/3)) × ((-2) + T(3)) + T(T(T(4))))
 43239 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(3))) × 2) - T(T(T(T((T(3) - 4))))))
 43243 := ((T(T(3)) × T((4^{T(2)})) - T(T(3))) + (4))
 43244 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(2)))³)) × 4)
 43245 := ((T(5) + T((T(4) + 2))) × T((3 × T(4))))
 43248 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(T(4)) + T(2))) + (3 × T(T(T(4))))
 43249 := (((T(9 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(3))) + T(4)
 43252 := (-T(2)) + (((T(T(5))²) × 3) + T(T(4)))
 43253 := ((3 × ((T(T(5))²) + T(T(3)))) - T(4))
 43255 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(5))) × T(2)) + T((T(3) + 4)))
 43256 := (T((T(6) - 5)) + (T((T(T(T(2)))/3)) × T(T(T(4))))
 43262 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(6) + 2) × T((T(3) + T(T(4))))))
 43263 := (T((3 × 6)) × T(((2 × T(3)) + T(4)))
 43264 := (((T(4) × T(6)) - 2)^{T(3-4)})
 43267 := ((T((T(7) - 6)) × T((T(2) × T(3)))) + (4))
 43268 := (((-8) × T(T(6))) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - T(T(T(4))))
 43273 := ((T(T(3)) × ((7^{T(2)}) × T(3))) + T(T(4))
 43274 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 2)) - T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
 43275 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(7) - 2))) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(4))))
 43279 := (-9) - (-T(7)) × (T(T(2)) + T(T((T(3) + 4))))
 43281 := (((-1) + T(8))^{T(2)}) + T(T((3 + 4)))
 43285 := ((58 + (T(2))^{T(3)}) × T(T(4))
 43288 := ((-8) + T(8)) × (T(T(2)) + T(T((T(3) + 4))))
 43294 := (((T((T(T(4)) + 9)) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(4))))
 43295 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(9)) × 2) × T(T(3))) - T(T(4))))
 43296 := ((T(6) + T(T(9))) × (T((T(2) × 3)) - 4))
 43298 := (((-8) + (T(T(9)) × 2)) × T(T(3))) - 4)
 43316 := (T((6 + 1)) × ((T(T(3))/3) + T(T(T(4))))
 43323 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(2^{T(3)}) - T(T(3))) + (4))
 43329 := (((9 × T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (-T(3)) × T(T(4)))
 43332 := -((T(2) - ((T(3))^{T(3)}) - T((3⁴)))
 43335 := ((T((5 + 3))³) - T((3⁴))
 43336 := ((6³) + (T((T(T(3))/3)) × T(T(T(4))))
 43338 := (((T(8)³) + 3) - T((3⁴))
 43343 := (((T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((T(T(3))/3))) + (T(T(4))))
 43344 := (T((4 + 4)) × (-T(T(3))) + T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))))
 43345 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) × T((T(3) × T(3)))) + T(T(4))
 43347 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T((3 + 3))) - 4))
 43348 := (((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3))³)) × 4)
 43351 := (T(T((1 + 5))) + (T((T(T(3))/3)) × T(T(T(4))))
 43356 := ((T(T(6)) + 5) + (T((T(T(3))/3)) × T(T(T(4))))
 43362 := ((T(T(2)) + (T(6))) × (T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
 43371 := (-1) - (-T(7)) × ((3 × 3) + T(T(T(4))))
 43372 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 7) × ((3 × 3) + T(T(T(4))))
 43373 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(7) - (T(3)³))) - T(T(4)))

- 43375** := ((T(T(5)) × (T(T(7)) - T((3 × 3))) + T(T(4)))
43378 := (-T(T(8))) + (-T(7)) × (-33 - T(T(T(4))))
43379 := ((T(T(9)) × (7 × T(3))) - T((3 + T(4))))
43385 := (-T(T(5))) + (((-T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(4))))
43389 := ((T(T(9)) × (T(8) + T(3))) - ((3⁴)))
43392 := (((2 × T(T(9))) × T(T(3))) - T((3 × 4)))
43394 := ((T((T(4) + 9)) × T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(T(3)) + T(4))))
43395 := (((T(5) + T(9)) + (3^{T(3)})) × T(T(4)))
43396 := ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) + (T((T(T(3))/3)) × T(T(T(4))))
43397 := ((((-7) × T(T(9))) + 3) × (-T(3))) - T(T(4))
43398 := ((T(8) - (T(T(9)) × T(T(3)))) × (-T(3) - (4)))
43399 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(9))) - T(3)) × T(T(3))) + T(T(4))
43405 := ((T(50) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) + T(T(4)))
43417 := ((-T(7)) × (1 - T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(3)) + (4))))
43422 := ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(3)))) / (-T(4))))
43425 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) - T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43427 := ((-T(7)) × ((-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 3) + (T(T(4)))
43428 := ((-8) + T(T((2 × 4))) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43432 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(3))) - 43)) + 4)
43435 := ((-5) + T((3 × 4))) × T(34)
43436 := (((T(63) + T(T(4))) × T(T(3))) - T(T(4)))
43438 := (((-((8^{T(3)})) + T(T(T(4)))) / (-T(3))) + 4)
43439 := (((9 × T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) × T(T(3))) - T(4)
43442 := ((2 + T((T(4) + (4)))) × T(T((3 + 4)))
43445 := (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + ((4^{T(3)}) × T(4)))
43448 := (8 × (((4⁴) × T(T(3))) + T(T(4))))
43452 := ((-T(2)) - T((5 × T(4)))) × (-34)
43456 := ((T(T(6)) + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) × (T(3) + T(4)))
43465 := (-5) + (T(6) × (T((4³)) - T(4)))
43466 := ((6⁶) - ((T(T(4)) + 3) × T(T(4))))
43467 := ((-T(7)) × (-T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(3))) + T(4))
43468 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(6))) + T(4)) × (-3)) + T(T(T(4)))
43471 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(3) + T(T(4))))
43473 := -(T(T(T(3))) - ((T(7) × T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3)))) - 4))
43474 := (-T(4)) + (-T(7)) × (-((T(4) + 3) - T(T(T(4))))
43475 := (T(T(5)) + (((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4))
43477 := (T(T(7)) - ((-T(7)) × T(T(T(4)))) + (-T(3)) + T(T(4)))
43478 := (T(8) + (T(T(7)) × ((T(T(4)) - 3) + T(T(4))))
43483 := (((T(T(T(3))) × T((-8) + T(T(4)))) / T(3)) + T(T(4)))
43484 := ((T(T(T(4))) × ((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3)))) / T(T(4)))
43485 := (T(5) × ((T((-8) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
43486 := (((T(6) × T(T(8))) - (4)) × 3) + T(T(T(4)))
43488 := (T(8) × (8 - (-4) × T((T(3) × 4))))
43489 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(T(4))) × T((3 + 4)))
43493 := (((3 × 9) - 4) × T((T(3) + T(T(4))))
43495 := (((T(5) × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) × 3) + T(T(T(4)))
43498 := ((T(T(8)) × (9 × (4 + 3))) + T(T(T(4))))
43499 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(9))) + (4)) × T(T(3))) - T(T(4))
43505 := ((T((50 + T(5))) × T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43516 := ((T((T(6) + 1)) × ((T(T(5)) - 3) + T(T(4))))
43524 := (((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) × T((5 + T(T(3)))) × 4)
43525 := (((T(T(5)) × T(2)) × T(T(5))) + T((T(T(3)) + (4))))
43526 := (((T(T(T(6)) / T(2))) × T(5)) + (T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(4)))
43533 := (T(T(3)) × ((3⁵) + T((T(3) × T(4))))
43568 := (8 × (T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(4))))
43569 := (9 × ((T(6) × T((T(5) + T(3)))) - T(4))
43575 := (-T(5)) × (-T(75) - T((T(3) + (4))))
43579 := (((9 + T(T(7))) × 5) × T(T(3))) + (4)
43582 := (((2 × T((8 + 5))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
43584 := (-4) × ((T(T(8)) + T(5)) × (-T(3) + T(4)))
43588 := ((T((T(8) + T(8))) × (-5) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))))
43589 := (((T((-9) + T(8))) × T(T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(4)))
43596 := (T(6) × (T(((9 - 5)³) - (4)))
43618 := (T(T(8)) + (T((1 + 6)) × (-T(3) + T(T(T(4))))))
43622 := (-T(2)) + ((T((2⁶)) × T(T(3))) - T(T(4)))
43623 := ((3²) × ((T(T(6)) × T(T(3))) - (4)))
43624 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(6) - T(34)))
43625 := ((T(((5 - T(2))⁶)) × T(T(3))) - T(T(4)))
43628 := (((T((8²)) × T(6)) + 3) - T(T(4)))
43629 := (((9 × T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6))) - (3 × T(4)))
43632 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T((3 × T(6)))) + ((T(3)⁴)))
43638 := ((T(8) + T(3)) × (T(T((6 + 3))) + (4)))
43646 := ((T(64) × T(6)) - 34)
43647 := ((T(7) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(6))) - (T(3) + T(T(4))))
43648 := ((8 × T((T(4) + T(6)))) × (T(T(3)) - T(4)))
43649 := ((T((9 + T(T(4)))) × T(6)) - (T(T(3)) + T(4)))
43655 := (((T((5 + T(5))) - T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) - 4)
43656 := (((T(6) × T(5)) + (6)) × T((T(3) + T(4))))
43659 := (9 × T(((5 × T(6)) - (3 + 4)))
43662 := (T(2) + (T(T(6)) × (-T(6)) - (T(T(3)) × (-T(4))))
43663 := (((3 × T(T(6))) × 63) + (4))
43665 := (T(5) × ((6 - T(6)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))))
43668 := (T(8) × (-((6 + 6)) + T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43669 := (((9 × T(T(6))) × T(6)) + (T(3) + (4)))
43673 := -((T(T(T(3))) - (-T(7)) × (-T((T(6)/3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43676 := ((T(6) × T((T(7) + (6 × T(3)))) - (4))
43678 := ((T((T(8) + T(7))) × T(6)) - (T(3) - (4)))
43683 := (3 × ((T(8) × T(T((T(6)/3)))) - T(T(4))))
43684 := ((T((4^{T(8-6)})) × T(T(3))) + (4))
43687 := ((T((T(7) + T(8))) × T(6)) + (3 + 4))
43688 := (((8 + (8⁶)) / T(3)) - (4))
43692 := (T((2 + 9)) × (T((6 × T(3))) - (4)))

- 43693** := (((T(T(3)) × 9) × T(T(6))) + 34)
43694 := -(T(T(4)) - (9 × ((T(T(6)) × T(T(3))) + T(4))))
43695 := -(T(5) - (T((96 - 3) × T(4))))
43697 := (T(7) + (((9 × T(T(6))) × T(T(3))) + T(4)))
43702 := -(T(T(2))) + ((0 - T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43704 := (-4) + ((0 - T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43708 := (T(((8 × 0) + 7)) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4))))
43711 := (T((1 + 1)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43712 := ((T(2) + 1) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43713 := ((T(3) - 1) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43714 := (T((4 - 1)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43715 := ((T(T(T(5 - 1)))) × T(7) + T(34))
43722 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(2)) × ((7³) + 4))
43723 := (((T(3)^{T(T(2))}) - 7) - T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43724 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(7)) + (T(3) + T(4)))
43725 := ((T(5) × (-2) + T((7 + 3))) × T(T(4)))
43726 := ((T(6) - T(2)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43729 := (T(9 - T(2))) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43732 := ((T(2) + T(T(3))) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43735 := ((T((T(5 + 3)) + T(7))) × T(T(3))) + T(T(4))
43736 := (((T(T(6)) / (-3)) × (-T(7))) × T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))
43738 := ((T(8) - T(3)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43742 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(7)) + 34)
43744 := (T((4 + 4)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43745 := ((5⁴) + (T(7) × T(T((T(3) + 4))))
43747 := (((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)
43748 := ((T(T(8)) × T(T(4)) + (7 + T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43749 := (9 × ((T(T(4)) × T(7)) + (T(3⁴))))
43752 := -(T(T(2)) - (T((5 + T(7))) × T((3 × 4))))
43753 := ((3 × T(5)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43754 := (-4) + (T((5 + T(7))) × T((3 × 4)))
43756 := ((6 × T(T(5))) + (-T(7)) × (3 - T(T(T(4))))
43757 := (-T(7)) + (T(5) × (-7) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43758 := (T(((8 × 5) - 7)) × T((3 × 4)))
43759 := ((T(T(9)) × 5) - (-T(7)) × T((-3) + T(T(4))))
43765 := (5 × (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(3))) - 4)))
43774 := (T((4 + 7)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43782 := (((T(2) × T(8)) × T(T(7))) - T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43783 := ((-3) + T(T(8))) + (T(7) × T(T((T(3) + 4))))
43785 := ((T(T(5)) / 8) × (-7) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43789 := ((T(9) + T(8)) + (-T(7)) × (-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43795 := ((T(5) × T(9)) + (T(7) × T(T((T(3) + 4))))
43796 := (((T(T(6)) × 9) + 7) × T(T(3))) - T(4)
43798 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(9) + 7)) × (T(3) + T(T(4))))
43813 := ((T(T(T(3))) × 183) + T(T(T(4))))
43822 := (-2) + ((-2) + T(T(8))) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))
43824 := ((-((4 - 2) + T(T(8))) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43827 := (-7) × (-((T(2)⁸)) + T((T(3) × 4)))
43828 := (((T(T(8)) - 2) × T((8 + 3))) + 4)
43834 := ((T((4³)) - T(T(8))) × (T(T(3)) + T(4)))
43835 := (((5³) + T(T(8))) + (T(3))) × T(T(4))
43836 := (-T((T(6) - T(3)))) + (T(T(8)) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43837 := (((T(T(7)) × (3 × T(8))) - T(T(3))) + T(4))
43839 := (-9) + ((3 × T(8)) × T(T((3 + 4))))
43844 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)) × T(T(3)))) × (-4))
43845 := (T(5) × (-T((T(4) - 8))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43846 := ((T(6) - T(4)) × (T(T(8)) × T(3)) - T(4))
43847 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(8)) + T(3))) + T(T(4)))
43848 := (-84) × (-((8³) - T(4)))
43849 := (((9 + T(T(4))) × T(T(8))) + T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43851 := (-T((-1) + T(5))) + (T(T(8)) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43852 := ((T(T(2 + 5))) × (T(8) × 3)) + 4)
43855 := ((T((T(5) + T(5))) × T((-8) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
43856 := ((-T(6)) × (T(T(5)) - T(T((8 + 3)))) - T(T(4)))
43858 := (((T(8) × 58) × T(T(3))) + T(4))
43862 := ((2 × T((T(6) - 8))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(4)))
43863 := ((-T(3) - T(T(6))) + (T(8) × T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43865 := ((T((5 + 6)) × T(T(8))) - T(3 + T(4)))
43868 := (((T(T(8)) × 6) - 8) × (T(T(3)) - T(4)))
43869 := -(T(T(T(9 - 6))) - (T(8) × T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))))
43872 := (((-T(2)) × T(T(7))) × (-T(8))) + (T(3) × 4)
43873 := (((-3) × T(T(7))) × (-T(8))) + T(T(3)) + 4)
43874 := (((-T(4)) - (T(T(7)) × T(8))) × (-3)) - 4)
43875 := ((T(5) × T(T(7))) + ((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) × T(T(4))))
43876 := (((6 + (T(T(7)) × T(8))) × 3) + T(4))
43877 := (((T(7) + (T(T(7)) × T(8))) × 3) - T(T(4)))
43879 := (((9 + T((T(7) + T(8)))) × T(T(3))) + T(4))
43882 := ((T(T(2)) + (T(8) × T((8 × T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))
43884 := (-T((T(4) × 8))) - (T(8) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43886 := ((T(T(6)) × T((8 + 8) + 3)) - 4)
43888 := (8 × ((8 × (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)))) - T(4)))
43893 := (3 × (-9) - (-8) × T((T(3) × T(4))))
43894 := (((T(4) + T(T(9))) × (T(8) + T(3))) + 4)
43895 := (5 × ((T(9) × (-T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4))
43896 := (((T(6) + T(9)) × T(T(8))) - (T(3) × T(4)))
43899 := ((T(T(9)) × T(9)) - ((T(T(8)) + 3) × 4))
43915 := (T(5) + ((T(19) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(4)))
43917 := (-T(7)) + ((T(19) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(4)))
43932 := ((2 × T(T(3))) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) - T(4)))
43934 := ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(4))))
43935 := (T(5) + ((T(T(3)) + T(93)) × T(4)))
43938 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(9))) - ((T(T(3))⁴)))
43941 := (T(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) + (T(93) × T(4)))
43942 := (-T(2)) - ((-T((T(4) + 9))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))

- 43945** := (((T(5) + (4)) + T((T(9) - T(3)))) × T(T(4)))
43946 := (((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) - T(9)) × T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))
43948 := (-8) + (T((4 × 9)) × T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))
43952 := ((T(T((T(2) + (5)))) × (T(9) + T(T(3)))) - 4)
43953 := ((3⁵) + (T(93) × T(4)))
43956 := (T(T(6)) + (T(5) + (T(93) × T(4))))
43962 := (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(93) × T(4))))
43965 := (T(5) × (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(3)) × T(4))))
43966 := ((T((6 × 6)) × (T(9) + T(T(3)))) + T(4))
43967 := (-7) × (((T(6) + T(T(9))) × (-T(3))) + T(T(4)))
43968 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) × ((9 × T(3)) + T(4)))
43974 := (-((T(4) - T(7))) × (T((T(9) - 3)) + T(T(T(4))))))
43975 := -((T(5) - ((T(7) + T(93)) × T(4))))
43979 := ((9 + T((T(7) - 9))) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(4)))
43983 := (3 × (T(8) - (-T(9)) × T((T(T(3)) + (4))))))
43987 := (((T(T(7)) × (-T(8))) - T(9)) × (-3)) + (4)
43988 := (T(8) + ((T(T(8)) × (T(9) + T(T(3)))) - (4)))
43989 := ((T(98) × 9) - (-T(3)) × T(T(4)))
43992 := (T((2 + T(9))) × (9 + (3 × T(4))))
43995 := (T(T(5)) + (T(9) × (T(T(9)) - (T(3) × T(4))))))
44128 := ((-T(8)) - T(T(T((T(2) + 1)))) × (T(T(T(4)))/(-T(T(4))))))
44142 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(41)) × (4 - T(T(4))))
44145 := ((T(T(5)) + (T(41))) × (-T(4)) + T(T(4)))
44165 := (((T(T(5))/6) × T(T((1 + T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
44169 := (((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) - 1) × T(T(4))) + (4))
44183 := (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) × T((1 + T(4)))) - (4)))
44215 := (5 × (-1) + (T(T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) × 4))
44216 := (((T(6) - 1) × T(T((T(T(2))) - T(4)))) - 4)
44232 := (2 × (T(3) + (T(T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) × T(4)))
44235 := (-T(5)) × (T(T(3)) - ((T(2) × T(44))))
44236 := (((T(T(6)) - T(T(3)))²) + T((4 × 4)))
44237 := -(((T(7 × T(3))) × (T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) + T(4))
44239 := (T(T(9)) + (((T(T(3)))^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4))) × 4))
44244 := ((4 + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) × T((4 + 4)))
44245 := (-5) + ((4 + T(T(T(2)))) × T((4 + T(T(4))))))
44247 := -((T(7 + T(T(4)))) + ((T(2) × T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(4))))
44248 := (T((-8) + T(T(4))) + (T((T(2) + 4)) × T(T(T(4))))
44262 := (2 × (T(6) + (T(T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) × T(4)))
44265 := ((T(5) + T((6²))) × (T(4) + T(T(4))))
44275 := ((-T(5)) + T(((7 - T(2)) × T(4))) × T(T(4)))
44283 := ((T(T(3)) + 8) × ((-T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(4)))
44286 := ((T(6) × T(T(8 + T(2)))) - T((T(4) + T(T(4))))))
44288 := ((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(8)))²) - T(4))/(-T(4)))
44289 := ((T((T(9) - 8)) × T(2)) × T((-4) + T(4)))
44292 := (((T(T(T(2))) - T(9)) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((-4) + T(T(4))))))
44295 := (T(5) + ((9 × T(T(2))) × T((T(4) × 4)))
44296 := (T(6) + (((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))))
44297 := (((T(7) × 9) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
44312 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) × (T((T(3) + T(4)) + T(T(4))))
44317 := (7 × (T(T(13)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4))))))
44324 := -((T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T((T(4) + T(4))))))
44325 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(2)³))) - T((-T(4)) + T(T(4))))
44328 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(2))) × T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) × 4)
44336 := ((6^{T(3)}) - ((T(T(T(3))) × T(4)) + T(4)))
44345 := (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T((3 + T(4))) × T(4)))
44346 := ((T(T(6)) × (-T(4))) + (T(3)^{-4+T(4)}))
44348 := (((T(8 × 4)) × T(T(3))) × 4) - (4)
44352 := ((T((2⁵) × T(3)) × (T(4) + (4)))
44355 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(5)) - T(T((3 × 4)))) + (4))
44362 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)))) + T(4))
44368 := (((8 × T(T(6))) × T(3)) + (4)) × 4)
44373 := (-T(T(3)) × (-((7³) - T((4 + T(T(4))))))
44374 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
44378 := (((-T(8)) × T(T(7))) + (3^{T(4)})) - T(T(4))
44382 := ((T(2) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(3)) × T((T(4) + T(T(4))))))
44384 := (-((4 × 8)) × (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T(T(T(4))))
44385 := (((T((5 × 8)) - 3) - T(4)) × T(T(4)))
44386 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(8) × T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))
44388 := (T(8) × ((-8) + (T(3)⁴)) - T(T(4)))
44392 := (((T(2) + T(9)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(4)) × 4)
44395 := (T(T(5)) + (((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))
44396 := (T(T(6)) + (((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
44428 := -(((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) - (T(T(4)) × T((T(4) × 4))))
44436 := (-T(6)) × (-((T(3)⁴) - T((T(4) × 4)))
44437 := ((-T(7)) × (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4))))
44455 := ((T(5) × ((-T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))
44457 := ((-T(7)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) × T((-4) + T(4)))
44465 := ((T(5))^{-6+T(4)}) - (T(T(T(4))) × 4))
44472 := ((2 + T(T(7))) × (4 + T((T(4) + (4))))
44485 := ((-5) + T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(4) + (4))))))
44486 := ((T(6) + 8) × (T(T(T(4))) - (-4) + T(4)))
44492 := (-((T(2) - (T(9) × T(44)))) - T(T(4)))
44495 := (((5 × 9) × T(44)) - T(T(4)))
44496 := ((6 × 9) × (4 + T((T(4) × 4)))
44514 := (-T(41)) + ((T(5) × T(T(4))) × T(T(4)))
44525 := ((T(5) × (T(T(-((T(2) - T(5)))) - T(4))) - T(T(T(4))))
44526 := (((6^{T(T(2))}) + (T(5))) - T((T(4) + T(T(4))))
44529 := ((9 × T(-((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))))) - T((-4) + T(4)))
44532 := -((T(2) × (T(3) - (T(5) × T(44))))
44534 := (-T(T(T(4) + 3))) - (-T(T(5)) × T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))))))
44535 := -((T(5) - (3 × T(5)) × T(44)))
44542 := (2 × (-4) - (T(5) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(T(4))))))
44544 := ((T(T(T(4))) - 4) × ((T(5) + (4)) + T(4)))

- 44545 := $(-5) - (-45) \times T(44)$
44548 := $((((-T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) / (-T(T(4)))$
44562 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - (4))))$
44565 := $(T(5) + (T((-6) + T(5))) \times T(44))$
44566 := $((6^6) - T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))$
44569 := $((9 \times (T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) - 4) + (T(T(4))))$
44574 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T((-7) + T(5)))) \times (-4) + T(T(4)))$
44575 := $(-5) \times ((-7) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) + T(4)$
44577 := $(-T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) - T(T(4)))$
44579 := $(T(T(9)) - ((-T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) - 4)$
44583 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (((8 + T(T(5))) + T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44597 := $(-7) \times (9 - ((T(T(5)) - 4) \times T(T(4))))$
44605 := $((50 - T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4)))$
44618 := $((T(T(8)) \times (1 + T((T(6) - T(4)))) - 4)$
44622 := $((T(2) + (2^6)) \times T(T((4 + 4)))$
44625 := $((-(5^{T(2)})) \times T((T(6) \times 4))) / (-T(4))$
44626 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) - T((T(6) \times 4))) + T(T(T(4)))$
44635 := $(-T(5)) + (T(-((T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(6) + 4)))))) \times T(4))$
44642 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(6)) - 4) - T(T(T(4))))$
44644 := $(((-4) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4)))) \times 4)$
44645 := $(-5) + (T(4) \times T(((T(6) \times 4) + T(4))))$
44646 := $((T((T(T(6) + 4))) - T(T(6))) \times T(4)) - 4$
44648 := $(8 \times ((4^6) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))$
44665 := $((T(5) \times T(T((6 + 6)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(4)$
44667 := $(7 \times ((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(4)) + T(T(T(4))))$
44672 := $((T(2) + ((-T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) \times 4)$
44675 := $(T(5) + (T(T(7)) \times ((T(6) - T(4)) \times T(4))))$
44679 := $(-9) + (T(7) \times T(((6 \times T(4)) - 4)))$
44682 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((8 \times T(T(6))) \times 4) + T(T(4))))$
44685 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(8) + T(6))) + T((-4) + T(T(4))))$
44687 := $(-T(7)) + (((8 + T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))$
44688 := $((-8) + T(8)) \times T(((6 \times T(4)) - 4))$
44712 := $(-T(2)) + (((1 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))$
44714 := $((T(T(4)) - 1) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44715 := $(T(T((5 - 1))) \times (-7) + T((T(4) \times 4)))$
44722 := $(2 \times (T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + T(4))))$
44723 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(2)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44724 := $((4^{T(2)}) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44725 := $(T(T(5)) + ((2 \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(4)))$
44726 := $((T(6) - T(2)) \times T((7 \times T(4)))) - 4$
44727 := $((7 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(4)))$
44734 := $(((((T(T(T(4))) + 3) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(4))$
44737 := $(7 \times (T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(4))) \times 4))$
44738 := $(T((T(8)/3)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44739 := $(9 \times (T(T(3)) + T(((T(T(7)) - T(4))/4)))$
44743 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + T((-T(4)) + T(T(4)))$
44744 := $((T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) + (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 4)$
44745 := $((T(5)^4) - (T(7) \times T((T(4) + T(4))))$
44748 := $((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(7))) \times 44$
44758 := $((8 + T(5)) \times (T((7 \times 4)) + T(T(T(4))))$
44762 := $((2 + T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4$
44765 := $((5 \times T(6)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44772 := $((T(2) + T((T(7) + T(7)))) \times T(T(T(4)))) / T(T(4))$
44775 := $(((-T(5)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-7)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4))))$
44776 := $((-(6 - 7)) + T(7)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 4)$
44778 := $(-T(T(8))) + (-T(7)) \times ((-T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))$
44782 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(8) - 7) \times (-4) - T(T(T(4))))$
44783 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(8))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(4)))$
44785 := $((-5) + T(T(8))) + T(7) \times (T(4) + T(T(4)))$
44786 := $(T(T((T(6) - 8))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(4) \times T(4))))$
44795 := $((T(5) \times 9) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
44796 := $((6 \times T(T(9))) \times 7) + T((-4) + T(T(4)))$
44814 := $(T(T(T(4 - 1)))) \times (T((-T(8)) + T(T(4))) + 4)$
44824 := $(T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(4) - T(T(4))))$
44825 := $((-5) + T(((2 + 8) \times 4))) \times T(T(4))$
44826 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) - T((T(T(8/4))) \times T(4)))$
44834 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) \times (8 + T((-4) + T(4))))$
44835 := $((5 \times 3) \times (-T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))))$
44836 := $(T(T(6)) + (((T(T(3)) \times T(8)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))))$
44844 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((4 + T(8)))) - (4^4))$
44845 := $((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(4) - T(T(4))))$
44852 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) + T((8 + T(T(4)))))) - 4)$
44856 := $((-6) - T(T(5))) \times (-((T(8) \times T(4)) - 4))$
44863 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) + (T((T(8) + 4))) \times T(T(4)))$
44869 := $((-T(T(T(9 - 6)))) - (T((T(8) + 4))) \times T(T(4)))$
44874 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((-T(7)) \times (8 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(4)))$
44876 := $((T(T(6)) - 7) - (T((T(8) + 4))) \times T(T(4)))$
44877 := $((-7) + T(7)) \times (-8) + T((T(4) + T(T(4))))$
44882 := $((2 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(4))$
44888 := $((((-8) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(8))) + 4) / (-T(4))$
44895 := $((T(5) - (T(9) \times (8 + T(4))))$
44912 := $((T(T(T(2)) + 1)) \times ((9 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))))$
44917 := $((T(7) + 1) \times (9 + T(T(T(4)))) - 4)$
44918 := $((T(T(8)) + ((1 + T(T(9))) \times (-44)))$
44924 := $((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))) \times 44))$
44925 := $(-T(5)) \times (((-T(2)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) + T(T(4)))$
44926 := $(T((T(6) + 2)) + (T(94) \times T(4)))$
44928 := $((T(8) \times T((T(2) + 9))) \times (4 \times 4))$
44929 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(T(2)))) \times T((9 + T(4)))) + 4)$
44935 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T((3 \times 9) - 4))) + T(T(4)))$
44936 := $((6^{T(3)}) - (T(9) \times 4) - T(T(T(4))))$
44945 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) - (4 \times T(T(4))))$
44955 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) - T(T(9))) \times (T(4) - T(T(4))))$
44956 := $((T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) \times 9) + T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 44965 &:= ((T(5) \times T(6)) + (T(94) \times T(4))) \\ 44968 &:= (((8 - T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times 44) \\ 44982 &:= (2 \times ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times T((-4) + T(4)))) \\ 44985 &:= (T(5) \times (T(((T(8) + T(9)) - (4)) - (4))) \\ 44995 &:= (-5) + (T(9) \times ((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 44997 &:= (((-T(7)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(4) \\ 44999 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - (9 \times 4)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45045 &:= (T(5) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(05 \times 4))) \\ 45066 &:= (T(6) + (T(6) \times T((T(T(05)) - T(T(4)))))) \\ 45085 &:= (-T(5)) - (-T((8 \times 05))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45095 &:= (-5) + (T((T(9) + (0 - 5))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45104 &:= ((T(40) \times T(T(-(1 - 5)))) + 4) \\ 45116 &:= ((6^{1 \times 1 + 5}) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45122 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + (1 + 5)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45126 &:= (((6^{T(T(2))}) + T(-(1 - 5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45132 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + (1 + T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45135 &:= (T(5) \times (T(3) + T((-1) + T((T(T(5))/T(4)))))) \\ 45144 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(41)) - T(T((T(5) - (4)))))) \\ 45155 &:= (55 \times (1 + T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))))) \\ 45165 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(6) \times T((-1) + T((T(5) - (4)))))) \\ 45175 &:= (((5 \times T(7)) - 1) \times T((T(5) + T(4)))) \\ 45225 &:= -(((T(T(5)) \times T((T(2)^2)) - ((T(5)^4))) \\ 45226 &:= ((6^{T(T(2))}) - ((T(T(T(2))) + 5) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45227 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(4))) \\ 45228 &:= ((-8) + ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 45233 &:= (((T(3)^{T(3)}) - T(2)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 45235 &:= ((T(5)^3) + (T(T((-2) + T(5))) \times T(4))) \\ 45236 &:= (((6^{T(3)}) + T((T(2) \times 5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45238 &:= (((T(8)^3) + 2) + T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 45245 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(T(4))^2)) - (T(T(5)) + T(4))) \\ 45247 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(2))) + T(T((T(5) - (4)))))) \\ 45248 &:= (8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) + T(T(5)))) \times 4) \\ 45255 &:= -((T(T(5)) - ((T(5) \times T((2 \times 5))) \times T(T(4)))))) \\ 45264 &:= (46 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times 4) \\ 45265 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(((T(6) \times 2) - (5)))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45266 &:= ((-6) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(T(2))^5))) - (4) \\ 45268 &:= (-8) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(5) + (4)))))) \\ 45272 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(7) \times (2 + 5))) - 4) \\ 45276 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (7 \times ((2^5) - 4))) \\ 45277 &:= (((T(7) \times 7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (5 - 4) \\ 45282 &:= -((T(T(2)) - (T(T(8)) \times ((2 + T(5)) \times 4))) \\ 45284 &:= (((-4) \times T(T(8))) \times (-2 - T(5))) - (4) \\ 45288 &:= (T(8) \times (8 + (2 \times (5^4)))) \\ 45295 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T((9 \times T(2)))) - T(T(5))) + T(T(4))) \\ 45297 &:= ((T(7) \times 9) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45312 &:= -(((T(T(T(2))) \times T((1 + T(T(3)))) - ((T(5)^4))) \\ 45324 &:= (((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times T(3)) - T(5)) \times 4) \\ 45325 &:= ((T((5 + 2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45326 &:= (T(6) + ((T((T(2)^3)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 45328 &:= (8 \times ((T((T(2)^3)) \times T(5)) - (4))) \\ 45332 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 45333 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + ((T(5)^4))) \\ 45335 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((3^3))) - (T(5) + T(4))) \\ 45336 &:= (-6) \times (((-3) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + (4)) \\ 45338 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(3) + (5)))) - (4)) \\ 45342 &:= ((T(T((2 \times 4))) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) - (4)))) \\ 45345 &:= (T(5) \times (-((T(T(4)) + 3)) + T(T((T(T(5))/T(4)))))) \\ 45347 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(4) + 3)) + ((T(5)^4))) \\ 45348 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T((4 \times 3))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45355 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times T((3 \times (5 + 4)))) \\ 45356 &:= (((-T(6)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-3 - T(5))) - (4) \\ 45357 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) - 3)) - T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))))) \\ 45372 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T((7 + 3)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45374 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))))) \\ 45375 &:= (((5 \times T(7)) \times T(3)) - T(5)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45377 &:= ((7 \times ((T(7) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5))) - 4) \\ 45381 &:= ((T((1 \times 8))^3) - T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45384 &:= (((T(4) \times T(8)) + T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) + (4))) \\ 45393 &:= ((-3) - T(T(9))) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T((T(5) - (4)))))) \\ 45394 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(T((9 + 3)))) \times (-T(5))) + (4)) \\ 45395 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T((9 + 3)))) - T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45396 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(9))) \times T(T(3))) - T(T((5 + 4)))) \\ 45399 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - T((3 + T((5 + 4)))))) \\ 45415 &:= (-T(5)) - ((-1) - (T(T(4)) \times T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 45419 &:= ((T(9) - 1) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45423 &:= (-T(T(3))) \times ((2 - T(T(T(4)))) - (5^4)) \\ 45424 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45425 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/T(2))) \times T(T(4))) + (T((T(5) + T(4)))))) \\ 45429 &:= ((9 \times T(T(2))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45441 &:= (T((1 + T(4))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45445 &:= (((T(5) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5))) + T(T(4))) \\ 45448 &:= ((-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T((T(4)/5)) - T(T(4))) \\ 45453 &:= (T((-3) + T(5))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45456 &:= (6 \times ((5 \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(5)) + (4)))))) \\ 45462 &:= (-T(2)) - (-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5^4)) \\ 45465 &:= ((T(5) \times 6) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45466 &:= ((6^6) + ((-T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4)) \\ 45468 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) - T(T(4))) \times 54) \\ 45471 &:= (-1) + (T(T(7)) \times ((-4) + T(T(5))) - (4)) \\ 45472 &:= ((2 \times T(T(7))) \times ((4 \times T(5)) - (4))) \\ 45474 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T((T(7) + (4)))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45476 &:= (((-6) + (7 \times T(T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) - (4)) \\ 45477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) \times 4)) + (-5) + T(4)) \\ 45483 &:= ((3 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45485 &:= (((T(5) - 8) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45486 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + (((T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(4)))) \\ 45488 &:= ((-8) + (T(T(8)) \times T((-4) + T(5)))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 45489 &:= ((-T(9)) - T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5))/(-4))) \\ 45495 &:= (T(T(5)) + (((T(9) + T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45496 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (T(9) - T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + T(4)) \\ 45497 &:= (-T((T(7) + 9))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5))/(-4))) \\ 45522 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(2)^5)) + ((T(5)^4)) \\ 45527 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) - (5))) + T(T(4)) \\ 45528 &:= ((T(8)^{T(2)}) - T(((T(T(5)))/(-T(5))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45545 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) + (T((5 \times 5)))) - T(T(4))) \\ 45549 &:= (-T((9 \times 4))) + (T(5) \times T((T(T(5))/T(4)))) \\ 47599 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + (-((5 - 7)^{T(4)})) \\ 45574 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(7) - T(T(5))))/(-5)) - T(4)) \\ 45584 &:= (-T(T(T(4)))) + (-T(8)) \times (T(T(T((T(5)/5)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45585 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) \times (T(5) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45592 &:= (2 \times ((T(95) \times 5) - (4))) \\ 45595 &:= (-5) + ((95 \times T(T(5))) \times 4) \\ 45611 &:= ((T(T(11)) \times T(6)) - T((-T(5) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45621 &:= ((T((1 + 2))^6) - T((5 + 4))) \\ 45625 &:= ((-5) + T((2 \times 6))) \times (5^4) \\ 45627 &:= (((7 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6))) + ((T(5)^4)) \\ 45628 &:= (((T(T(8)) + 2) \times T((6 + 5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45635 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) + T(6)))) - (-5 \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45639 &:= (T(T(9)) + (-T(T(3))) \times (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))))) \\ 45655 &:= ((T((5 \times T(5))) \times (T(6) - (5))) + T(T(4))) \\ 45656 &:= ((T(6) + (5)) \times ((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45661 &:= ((T(T((1 \times 6))) \times T(T(6))) - (5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45666 &:= ((6^6) - T(((6 + 5) \times 4))) \\ 45671 &:= ((T((1 + T(7))) \times (T(6) \times 5)) - (4)) \\ 45672 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(7)) + (T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) \times 4) \\ 45675 &:= (((-T(5)) \times T(T(7)))/(-6)) \times T((5 + 4)) \\ 45679 &:= ((((-T(9)) \times T(T(7)))/(-6)) \times T(5)) + (4) \\ 45682 &:= (-2) + (T(8) \times (-6) + T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45684 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times (-T(6)) - T(T(5)))/(-T(4))) \\ 45688 &:= (8 \times ((T(T((-8) + T(6))) - T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45696 &:= (-T(6)) \times ((T(9) - T(T((6 + 5)))) - T(4)) \\ 45724 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + (4)))) \\ 45729 &:= (9 \times (T(T(T(2))) + (-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45732 &:= (-T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T((7 + T(5)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 45734 &:= (-4) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T((7 + T(5)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 45735 &:= (-T(5)) + ((-3) + T(7)) \times T((T(5) \times 4)) \\ 45736 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) + ((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45738 &:= (T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) \times (T((7 + T(5))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 45742 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)) - T((7 + T(5)))) + 4) \\ 45745 &:= (-T(5)) - ((-T(4)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4)) \\ 45747 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (4 \times T(7))) - (-5 \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45753 &:= (((3 - T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(5)^4)) \\ 45755 &:= (((5^5) + T(7)) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 45762 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (T(7) + (5))) + (4))) \\ 45765 &:= (-T(5)) - (6 \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45768 &:= (8 \times ((T(T((6 + 7))) - (5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45773 &:= -(((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) - ((7 \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45774 &:= -(((T(T(4) \times 7) + T(7))) - ((T(5)^4)) \\ 45775 &:= ((-T(T(5))) - T((T(T(7))/7))) \times (-T(5) + T(4)) \\ 45783 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(7)) \times T((T(5) - (4)))) \\ 45792 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times 9) \times (T(7) + T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 45793 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (9 \times (7 + T(5)))) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 45794 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(7)))) + (-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45797 &:= ((T(7) \times T(T(9))) + ((7^5) + T(4))) \\ 45798 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) \times T(7)) - T((T(5) \times 4))) \\ 45799 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) + (4))) \\ 45808 &:= (8 \times (T(T((08 + 5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45814 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + (1 - (T((T(8) + (5))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45815 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 1) \times (-8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45822 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (-2) + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times 4)) \\ 45823 &:= (((T(3)^{T(2)}) - 8) + (-T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 45824 &:= ((4^{T(2)}) \times (T(T(8)) + (5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45825 &:= ((5 + T((2 \times 8))) \times T((T(5) + T(4)))) \\ 45826 &:= ((6^{T(2)}) - (T((8 \times 5)) + T(4))) \\ 45828 &:= (T(8) \times (-2) + T((8 \times 5) + T(4))) \\ 45829 &:= ((9^{T(2)}) + (T((8 \times 5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45832 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - (T((8 \times 5)) + (4))) \\ 45834 &:= -((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) - (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45836 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - T((8 \times (-5) + T(4)))) \\ 45837 &:= ((7 \times ((3^8) - 5)) - T(T(4))) \\ 45842 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) + (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45845 &:= (-5) \times (((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times T(5)) - (4)) \\ 45846 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-4))) \\ 45848 &:= (8 \times ((T(T(T(4)) + T(8))) + 5) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45852 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-58) + (5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45856 &:= ((T(6) - (5)) \times (T((T(8) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45857 &:= -((T(7) + T(5))) + (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45862 &:= (-2) + (-T(6)) \times ((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times (-4)) \\ 45864 &:= ((4 \times T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) - T((5 + T(4)))) \\ 45865 &:= ((56 \times T((8 \times 5))) - T(T(4))) \\ 45866 &:= (((6^6) - T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) - (4) \\ 45871 &:= ((-1) - T(7)) + (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45872 &:= (((T(2)^7) \times (T(8) - T(5))) - T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45875 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(7)) - T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + (4))) \\ 45879 &:= -((T(T(9) - (7))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(5) - T(T(4)))))) \\ 45882 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(8)) - T(T((5 + 4)))) \\ 45885 &:= (T((5 + (8 \times 8))) \times (T(5) + (4))) \\ 45886 &:= (-((6 + 8)) + (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45891 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) + (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45892 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((9 \times 8) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45893 &:= (-T(3)) + (((T(T(9)) \times T(T(8)))/T(5)) - T(T(4))) \\ 45895 &:= ((T((5 + T(9))) \times T(8)) - (-5 + T(4))) \\ 45897 &:= -((T(-((7 - 9))) - (T(8) \times T((5 \times T(4)))))) \\ 45899 &:= (-T(9)) + (((T(T(9)) \times T(T(8)))/T(5)) - T(4)) \\ 45915 &:= (T(5) + (T(-((1 - 9))) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45924 &:= (4 \times (T(T(2)) - (-9) \times T((5 \times T(4)))) \\ 45925 &:= (T(5^2)) + (T(95) \times T(4)) \\ 45926 &:= (((6^{T(T(2))}) - (T(9) \times T(5))) - T(T(4))) \\ 45927 &:= (7 \times (T(2)^{9-5+4}) \\ 45944 &:= (((T(T((4 + 4))) \times T(T(9)))/T(5)) - T(4)) \\ 45945 &:= (((-T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(9)) - (T(5)))))/(-4)) \\ 45955 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T((T(9) + (5)))) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 45958 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T((5 \times 9))/T(5))) + (4)) \\ 45963 &:= (-T(3)) + (T(T(6)) \times (9 + T((T(5) + (4)))))) \\ 45966 &:= ((6^6) - ((T(T(9)))/(-T(5))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 45969 &:= -((T(((T(9) + (6)) + T(9))) - (T(5)^4))) \\ 45972 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((7 - T(9)) + (5 \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 45973 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (79 + T(T(5)))) + 4) \\ 45974 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + T((-T(9) + T(T(5)))) + 4) \\ 45975 &:= (((5 \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times (5 + T(4))) \\ 45976 &:= (-((T(T(6)) - (7))) - (-((T(9) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 45985 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(8) - 9))) + (5^4)) \\ 45989 &:= (T(9) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/T(5)) - T(4))) \\ 45995 &:= (-5) \times (((T(T(9)) \times (-9)) + T(T(5))) - (4)) \\ 45997 &:= (-7) \times (-((9^9-5)) - T(4)) \\ 45999 &:= (9 \times (-9) + ((T(T(9)) \times 5) - T(T(4)))) \\ 46035 &:= (T(5) - (-30) \times (-6 + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 46065 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T((6 + 06))) - T(4))) \\ 46089 &:= (-T(T(9))) - (T(8) \times (T(T(06)) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 46123 &:= (T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) + (T((1 + 6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46125 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T((16 - 4)))) \\ 46128 &:= ((T(8)^{T(2)}) - T(((1 + T(6)) + T(4))) \\ 46145 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \times (1 + 6)) - T(T(4))) \\ 46155 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(((5 + 1) + 6))) - (4))) \\ 46165 &:= (5 \times (-((6 + 1)) + (6 \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 46173 &:= (3 \times ((T(71) \times 6) + T(T(4)))) \\ 46185 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(8) - (1 \times 6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46188 &:= (T(8) \times (8 + T((-((1 - 6)) \times T(4)))) \\ 46195 &:= (-5) + ((9 + T((1 \times 6))) \times T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46205 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T((02 \times 6)))) - T(4)) \\ 46215 &:= (T(5) \times T(T(((1 \times 2) + 6) + 4))) \\ 46217 &:= -((T((T(7) + 1)) - ((T(T(2))^6) - (4)))) \\ 46221 &:= -((T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((6 - T(4)))))) \\ 46222 &:= (22 \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(64))) \\ 46223 &:= -((T((3^{T(2)})) - ((T(T(2))^6) - T(T(4)))) \\ 46224 &:= (4 \times (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(T(4)))))) \\ 46225 &:= ((T(5) \times T((T(2) \times 26))) + T(4)) \\ 46228 &:= ((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T((T(2) \times T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46233 &:= (3 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T((2 + T(6))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 46235 &:= (-5) \times ((-3) \times T(T((2 \times 6))) - (4)) \\ 46236 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) + ((-2) \times T(6)) \times T(4)) \\ 46237 &:= -(((T(T(7)) + 3) - ((T(T(2))^6) - T(4))) \\ 46238 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(3))) + 2) \times (6 + T(T(4)))) \\ 46242 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T((2 + 6))) - (4)))) \\ 46245 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (-T(2) - T(T((6 + 4)))))) \\ 46248 &:= (T((-8) + T(T(4))) \times (T((T(2) + (6))) - (4))) \\ 46252 &:= (-T(2)) - ((T((T(T(5))/T(2))) + (T(6))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 46255 &:= ((T((T(5) + (5^2))) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 46263 &:= (-T(T(3))) \times ((6 + 2) - T(T((6 - T(4)))))) \\ 46265 &:= ((5 \times ((T(6)^{T(2)}) - (6))) - T(4)) \\ 46267 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((6^{T(T(2))}) + (T(6) - (4)))) \\ 46274 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(7) \times T((2 + T((6 + 4)))))) \\ 46275 &:= (T(5) \times (T((72 + 6)) + (4))) \\ 46277 &:= (-7) + (T(7) \times T((2 + T((6 + 4)))))) \\ 46284 &:= ((-T(4)) + T((T(8) - T(2)))) \times (T(6) \times 4) \\ 46287 &:= ((T(7) \times T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) + T((6 - 4))) \\ 46288 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46292 &:= ((T((T(2) + T(9))) + (T(T(2))^6) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46295 &:= (((-5) + T(T(9))) \times T((T(2) + (6)))) - T(T(4)) \\ 46298 &:= (T(T(8)) + (92 \times T((T(6) + T(4)))) \\ 46299 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - T((-2) + T(6)) + (4))) \\ 46305 &:= (5 \times (T(T(03))^{T(6-4)}) \\ 46315 &:= (((T((T(5) - 1)) \times T(T(3))) \times T(6)) + T(4)) \\ 46323 &:= (((T(3)^{T(T(2))}) - 3) + (-6) \times T(T(4))) \\ 46325 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(2)))^3) + (-6) + T(4))) \\ 46326 &:= ((6^{T(T(2))}) - (T(3) \times T((6 + 4))) \\ 46327 &:= -((T((T(7) - T(2))) - (((T(3))^6) - (4)))) \\ 46328 &:= (((T(8)^{T(2)}) - 3) - T((T(6) + (4)))) \\ 46331 &:= ((T((1 \times 3))^{T(3)}) - T((T(6) + (4)))) \\ 46332 &:= (((T(2)^3) \times T(3)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 46333 &:= (-((T((3^3)) - (T(3)^6))) + T(T(4))) \\ 46335 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(3))^3) + T(T((6 - 4)))) \\ 46343 &:= ((-T(T(3))) \times (4 - T(T((T(T(3)))/T(6)))) - 4) \\ 46344 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(43) \times (-6) + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

- 46345** := $((5 \times ((T(T(T(4))) + 3) \times 6)) + (T(T(4))))$
46346 := $-((T((6 \times 4)) - ((T(3)^6) - T(4))))$
46347 := $((T(T((7 + 4))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(6) \times (-4)))$
46353 := $(-((T((-3) + T(5)))) - (-((T(T(3))) \times T(T((T(6) - T(4))))))$
46354 := $(T(-((T(4) - (53)))) \times (-6 + T(T(4))))$
46355 := $(5 \times (-5) + (T(3) \times (6 + T(T(T(4))))))$
46356 := $((T(6) - T(5))^{T(3)} - T((6 \times 4)))$
46358 := $((8 + T(5)) \times T((3 \times T(6)))) - T(4)$
46359 := $((T((9 + T(5))) + 3) \times T((T(6) - (4))))$
46362 := $(T(T(2)) + (((6^{T(3)}) - T((6 \times 4))))$
46364 := $(-4) + (-((T(6)) \times (3 - T(T((T(6) - T(4))))))$
46365 := $((5 \times (T(6)^3)) + (6 \times T(4)))$
46366 := $((6^6) - T((3 + T(6)))) + T(4)$
46368 := $((8 \times T(6)) \times T(((T(3) + T(6)) - (4))))$
46371 := $((-1) - T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((6 \times T(4))))$
46372 := $((T(2)^7) + T(T(3))) \times T(6) + (4)$
46375 := $((-5) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(6)))) + T(T(T(4)))$
46376 := $((T((-6) + T(7)) \times 3) \times T(6)) - T(T(4))$
46379 := $(-((T(9) + (7))) - (-((T(T(3))) \times T(T((T(6) - T(4))))))$
46392 := $(-T(2)) + (T(9) \times (T(T((3 + 6))) - (4)))$
46395 := $((5 \times 9) \times (T(T((3 + 6))) - (4)))$
46396 := $((-6) \times T(9)) + ((T(3)^6) + T(4))$
46398 := $(T((-8) + T(9))) \times (T(3) \times (T(6) - T(4)))$
46399 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T((6 + 4))$
46421 := $((T(T((1^2) + T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(4))$
46423 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(2) - T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) + (T(T(4))))$
46425 := $(T(5) + ((T(2) + T(4)) \times T((T(6) \times 4))))$
46427 := $((T(((T(7) \times 2) + T(4))) \times T(6)) - (4))$
46431 := $(T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T((T(T(4)) + (T(6) - T(4))))$
46432 := $(-T(2)) - ((-T(T(3))) \times T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) - 4$
46433 := $((T(3)^{T(3)} + 4) - T(T(6))) + (4)$
46435 := $((T(T((5 \times 3) - 4))) \times T(6)) + (4)$
46436 := $((6^{T(3)}) - (4 \times T((6 + 4))))$
46438 := $((-((T(8) + T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + T(4)))$
46441 := $((T(T((1^4) + T(4))) \times T(6)) + T(4))$
46445 := $((T(5)^4) - ((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4))))$
46446 := $((6^{-4+T(4)}) - (T(6) \times T(4)))$
46448 := $((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(4) + T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))$
46452 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(5) - (4)))) + T(T(T((6 - 4))))$
46455 := $(T(5) \times (T(T((T(5)/T(4)))) - (-6 - T(4)))$
46456 := $((T(6) \times T(T((T(5) - (4)))) + (T(6) + (4)))$
46462 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + (T(6) + T(4)))$
46464 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-4)) \times T((T(6) - T(4)))$
46465 := $((T((T(T(5))/6)) \times (-T(4) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(4))))$
46466 := $((6^6) - T(((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))/4)))$
46473 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((7 + 4))) + (6 - 4)))$
46475 := $(-5) \times (((T(7) \times T(T(4))) \times (-6)) - T(T(4)))$
46478 := $(-8) + ((T(T((7 + 4))) \times T(6)) + T(T(4)))$
46486 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T((T(8) + (4))) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4))))$
46487 := $((7 + T(8)) \times T(46)) + (4)$
46488 := $((T(8) \times (8 + T(T(T(4)))) - (6 \times T(T(T(4))))$
46494 := $(T((-4) + T(9))) \times (-T(4) - 64))$
46496 := $(((-6) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6) - 4$
46499 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - T(4)) - T((T(6) - T(4)))$
46515 := $(T((5 + 1)) \times (T(T((5 + 6))) + (4)))$
46525 := $(-5) + (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4))))$
46526 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(5))) - (6 + 4)$
46528 := $(-8) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (5 + T(T((T(6) - T(4))))))$
46545 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4)))$
46546 := $((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + 5) \times T(6)) + T(4)$
46548 := $(-T(8)) \times (T((T(4)/5) - (6^4)))$
46555 := $(-5) + (T(((5 \times T(5)) + T(6))) \times T(4))$
46556 := $((6^5) - T(5)) \times 6 - T(4)$
46572 := $((T(T(2))^{T(T(7-5))}) + (T(6) \times (-4)))$
46575 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - T((5 + (6 \times T(4))))$
46579 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((T((7 - 5)) + (6)))) + (4))$
46582 := $(-2) - (T(8) \times ((T(5) + T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4))))$
46585 := $((T((-5) + T(8))) + T((5 + T(6)))) \times T(T(4))$
46592 := $((2^9) \times T((T(5) - (6 - 4))))$
46593 := $(3 \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(5)) + T(T((6 - 4))))$
46595 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(5) - (6))) - (4))$
46596 := $((6^{-9+T(5)}) - (6 \times T(4)))$
46597 := $((T(T(7)) - 9) - (-((5 \times 6)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
46599 := $((T(9) \times T((9 \times 5))) + ((6 \times 4)))$
46601 := $((1 \times 06)^6) - T(T(4))$
46606 := $((60 - (6^6))) + T(4)$
46615 := $((51 - (6^6))) + T(4)$
46616 := $((T((6 - 1)) + (6^6)) - T(T(4)))$
46617 := $(-((T(7) + ((1 - (6^6)))) + T(4)))$
46618 := $(-((T((8 - 1)) - (6^6)) + T(4)))$
46621 := $(-1) + (((T(T(2))^6) + (T(6))) - T(T(4)))$
46622 := $((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(6) - T((6 + 4))))$
46623 := $(-((T(T(3)) + ((2 - (6^6)) + T(4))))$
46624 := $((42 - (6^6))) + T(4)$
46625 := $((T((5 - 2))^6) - T(6)) - T(4)$
46626 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) - (6 + (6 \times 4)))$
46627 := $(-((T(7) - T(2)) - ((6^6) - 4)))$
46628 := $((-8) \times T(2)) + (((6^6) - 4))$
46629 := $((T((9 - 2)) + (6^6)) - T(T(4)))$
46631 := $((T((1 \times 3))^6) - T(6)) - (4)$
46634 := $(-((4 \times 3) - (6^6))) - T(4)$

- 46635** := $((-5 - T(3)) + (6^6)) - T(4)$
46636 := $-((T(6) + (3 - ((6^6) + 4)))$
46638 := $((T(8)^3) + ((6 - (6 \times 4))))$
46639 := $(-((9 \times 3) - (6^6))) + T(4)$
46652 := $((T(((2 - 5) + 6))^6) - (4))$
46653 := $(T(3) - (5 - ((6^6) - 4)))$
46654 := $((T(4)/5) + (((6^6) - 4)))$
46655 := $((T(5)/5) + (((6^6) - 4)))$
46657 := $-((T((7 - 5)) - ((6^6) + 4)))$
46658 := $(T((8 - 5)) + (((6^6) - 4)))$
46659 := $(((-9) + T(5))^6) + T((6 - 4))$
46662 := $((T(2) + (6^6)) + T((6 - 4)))$
46664 := $(T(4) + (((6^6) - 6) + 4))$
46665 := $((5 + ((6^6) - 6)) + T(4))$
46666 := $((6^6) + T(((6 - 6) + 4)))$
46667 := $((T(7) - T(6)) + ((6^6) + 4))$
46668 := $(T(8) + ((6^6) - (6 \times 4)))$
46669 := $((9 + ((6^6) - 6)) + T(4))$
46672 := $(((-2) + T(7)) + (6^6)) - T(4)$
46674 := $((4 \times 7) + (6^6)) - T(4)$
46675 := $((-5) + T(7)) + (((6^6) - 4))$
46677 := $((-7) + T(7)) + (6^{T(6-4)})$
46679 := $((-9) + T(7)) + ((6^6) + 4)$
46681 := $(((-1) + T(8)) + (6^6)) - T(4)$
46682 := $((2 \times 8) + (6^6)) + T(4)$
46683 := $((T(38) \times T(6)) \times T((6 - 4)))$
46685 := $((T(T(5)) - ((T(8) - (6^6)))) - T(T(4)))$
46686 := $((-6) + T(8)) + (6^{T(6-4)})$
46688 := $(T(8) - (8 - ((6^6) + 4)))$
46689 := $(T(9) - (8 - ((6^6) - 4)))$
46691 := $((T((1 \times 9)) + (6^6)) - T(4))$
46693 := $((3 \times 9) + (6^6)) + T(4)$
46695 := $((T(T(5)) \times 9) - T(T(6))) \times T((6 + 4))$
46696 := $((T(6) + (9 + (6^6))) + T(4))$
46697 := $(T(7) + ((9 + ((6^6) + 4))))$
46699 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + T((-6) + T(6))) + (4)$
46704 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (0 - T(T(7)))) \times (6 \times 4))$
46711 := $(((((1 \times 1) - 7))^6) + T(T(4)))$
46716 := $((6^{-1+7}) + (6 \times T(4)))$
46722 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) + (76 - T(4)))$
46723 := $((T(3)^{T(2)}) + (7 + (6 \times T(4))))$
46725 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(2 + 7))) + T(64))$
46726 := $((6^{T(2)}) + (7 \times (6 + 4)))$
46728 := $((T(8)^{T(2)}) + ((76 - 4)))$
46732 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} + T(T(7))) + (-6 \times T(T(4))))$
46733 := $((T(3)^{T(3)} - (7)) - (T(6) \times (-4)))$
46736 := $((6^{T(3)}) + ((76 + 4)))$
46738 := $((T(8) + (3^7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(4))$
46744 := $(4 \times (((T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(4))$
46745 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((-T(4) + T(T(7))) - (6))) - T(T(4)))$
46746 := $(-T(6) \times ((T(4) - T(T(7))) - T((6 \times T(4))))$
46749 := $(T(9) - ((T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (-6 \times 4))$
46752 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (T(76) - (4)))$
46753 := $((T(3)^5) + (7)) \times 6 + T(T(4))$
46755 := $(-T(T(5)) + (-((5^7) \times 6) / T(4)))$
46758 := $(-T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - (6^4)))$
46761 := $((16 \times T(76)) - T(T(4)))$
46762 := $((T(T(2))^6) + T(T(7))) - T((6 \times 4))$
46774 := $((T(T(T(4)) + T(7))) + (-T(7)) \times (-6 - T(T(T(4))))$
46784 := $(-4) \times (8 - (T(76) \times 4))$
46792 := $((T(T(2))^{T(9-7)}) + T((6 + T(4))))$
46797 := $((T((7 + T(9))) \times (T(7) + (6))) - T(T(4)))$
46799 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - (7)) + T(T(T(T(6 - 4))))$
46816 := $((T(T(6)) + (-1 + T(8))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(4))))$
46822 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) + ((T(T(8))/6) + T(T(4))))$
46824 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) - (-T(8)) \times T((6 + (4))))$
46825 := $(-5) - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((8 - T(T(6))) \times T(4)))$
46826 := $((6^{T(2)}) + T(T(8))) - T((T(6) + T(4)))$
46827 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(T(T(2) + 8))) \times T(6)) - T(4))$
46828 := $((T(8)^{T(2)}) + ((8 \times T(6)) + (4)))$
46844 := $((4 \times T((T(T(4)) + 8))) \times 6) - T(T(T(4)))$
46847 := $((7 \times T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6)) - (4)$
46852 := $(T(-((T(T(2)) - 58))) \times (-T(6) + T(T(4))))$
46855 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(8)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(4))$
46862 := $((T(T(2))^6) + ((T(8) \times 6) - T(4)))$
46865 := $((5^6) \times T((8 - 6))) - T(4)$
46866 := $(T(T(6)) - ((T(6) + (T(8) \times (-6^4))))$
46872 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(((7 \times 8) + 6) \times 4))$
46875 := $((-((5^7)) \times T(8)) / (-6)) / T(4)$
46879 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) \times T(8)) - T(6) + T(T(T(4)))$
46882 := $(2 \times ((T(88) \times 6) - T(T(4))))$
46883 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(8)^{T(8-6)}) - (4)))$
46893 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((9 + 8)) + T(64)))$
46896 := $(T(T(6)) - (-9) + (T(8) \times (-6^4)))$
46899 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(9)) + T(8))) - (6^4))$
46922 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) + ((T(9) \times 6) - (4)))$
46924 := $((T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times (T(9) - T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))$
46926 := $((T((6^2)) + T(9)) \times T((T(6) - T(4))))$

- 46928** := (((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(9)) + T(T(6))) - (4)
46929 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) × T(9)) - (T(6) × (-4)))
46932 := ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + T((T((-9) + T(6))) - T(T(4))))
46933 := (((T(3)^{T(3)}) - 9) + T(T(6))) + T(T(4))
46935 := (-T(5)) × ((-3) × T(T(9))) - (6 × 4))
46936 := ((6^{T(3)}) - ((T(9) × (-6)) - T(4)))
46939 := (((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) × T(9)) - T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4))))
46942 := ((2 × T((T(T(4)) - 9))) × T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))
46945 := (((T(T(5)) × T(4)) + T(T(9))) × T(6)) + T(4)
46949 := (((T(T(9)) + T(4)) × T(9)) - (T(6))) - T(T(4))
46956 := ((6^{T(5)-9}) + T((6 × 4)))
46957 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(T(5)) - 9)) + T((6 + T(T(4))))
46962 := ((T(T(2))⁶) + (9 × (-T(6)) + T(T(4))))
46966 := ((6⁶) + T((T(9) - T(6)))) + T(4)
46968 := ((T((T(8) + T(6))) - T(T(9))) × (T(6) + T(T(4))))
46972 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + ((T(96) × T(4))))
46975 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(7))) × T((9 + 6))) + T(T(4))
46977 := (-T(7)) + (79 × T((-T(6)) + T(T(4))))
46992 := ((T(2) + 9) × T((T((-9) + T(6))) + T(4)))
46994 := ((T(4) + T(T(9))) × T(9)) - (T(6) + T(4))
46995 := -((T(5) - ((T(9) + T(96)) × T(4))))
46997 := (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(9)) × T(9)) + (6 + T(4))))
47035 := (-5) - (-30) × (T(7) + T(T(T(4))))
47062 := ((T(T(2))⁶) + T((07 × 4)))
47066 := ((6⁶) + T(T(07))) + (4)
47095 := (-((T(T(5)) - (T(90)))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
47124 := ((4 × T(T(T(2)))) × T((1 + T(7)) + (4)))
47125 := ((5^{T(2)}) × (-1) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(4))))
47134 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) × T((1 + 7))) + T(4))
47145 := (T(5) × ((T((T(T(4)) + 1)) + 7) + T(T(T(4))))
47152 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × 51) + 7) × 4)
47165 := (((-T(5)) + (T(T((6 - 1))) × T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(4))))
47173 := -((T(T(T(3))) - (-T(7)) × (-T(17)) - T(T(T(4))))
47196 := ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) × T((1 + 7) + T(4)))
47209 := ((T(90) - T(T(2))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
47215 := (((T(5) + 1) + T(2)) × T((7 × T(4))))
47223 := ((T(3)^{T(T(2))}) + (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(7)) + T(T(4))))
47225 := ((T(T(5)) × ((T(T(2)) × (-2)) + T(T(7)))) - T(T(4))
47228 := (-((8^{T(2)})) + ((T(2) + T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
47229 := (T(9) + ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T((T(7) + (4))))
47232 := ((2^{T(3)}) × (-T(2)) + T((T(7) + T(4))))
47235 := (T((T(5) × 3)) - ((-2) - T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
47236 := (T(6) + ((T(T(3)) - 2) × T((7 × T(4))))
47238 := (((T(8)³) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))))
47245 := (((T(5) × T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) + T(7)) × T(T(4))
47264 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(6) × 2))) - ((7⁴)))
47265 := (-T(5)) × (-T((6²))) - T((7 × T(4)))
47268 := (T(8) × (((T(6)^{T(2)})/7) - T(4))
47279 := (-T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7) × 4)))
47283 := (-3) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(2) - 74))
47284 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) × (2 + T(7))) + 4)
47285 := (((-T(5)) × T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) × (-7)) - T(T(T(4))))
47286 := (((T(6) - T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) × (-74))
47288 := (T((T(8) + T(8))) - ((-2) × T(T(7))) × T(T(4)))
47289 := (((T(T(9)) + (T(8)^{T(2)})) - T(T(7))) + (4))
47295 := (-T(5)) × (((T(T(9)) × (-T(2))) + 7) - T(T(4)))
47312 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(13))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
47313 := (-T(T(3))) × ((1 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T((7 × T(4))))
47322 := ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T((T(3) × T((7 - 4))))
47324 := (((T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) - (T(T(3)))) × T(7)) + 4)
47325 := (T(5) × (T(T((2 × T(3)))) + 74))
47327 := (-7) - (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(3))) - (T((7 × T(4))))
47328 := ((T(8)^{T(2)}) - ((T(3) × T(7)) × (-4))
47332 := (-2) + (-T(T(3))) × (T(T(T(3))) - (T((7 × T(4))))
47334 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 33) - T((T(7) + T(T(4))))
47335 := ((T(T(5)) × (-((T(3) + T(3))) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(4))
47337 := ((T(7) + 3) × (-((T(3) + 7)) + T(T(T(4))))
47344 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(4) + T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(4)))
47345 := ((T(T(5)) × ((T(4) - T(T(3))) + T(T(7)))) - T(T(4))
47348 := (((-T((T(8) + 4))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7)))/(-4)
47352 := (-T(2)) - (((T(T(5)) + 3) × (-7)) × T(T(4)))
47355 := (55 × T((37 + 4)))
47362 := -((T((T(T(2)) + (T(6)))) + ((-3) - T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
47363 := (((T(3)⁶) + T(37)) + (4))
47365 := (((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) × T((-3) + T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))
47376 := ((6 × 7) × T((37 + T(4))))
47379 := ((T(9) - T(T(7))) - ((-3) - T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
47382 := (T(T(2)) + (-T(8)) × ((T(T(T(3))) - 7) - T(T(T(4))))
47383 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(T((8 + 3))) - T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))
47385 := ((T(T(5)) + T((8 - 3))) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(4))))
47388 := (T(T(8)) + (((T(8)³) + T((7 + 4))))
47397 := (T((-7) + T(9)) + ((T(3)^{T(7-4)})))
47398 := (T((89 + 3)) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
47415 := (T(5) × (1 + T((T(T(4)) + (T(7) - (4))))
47418 := (((8 + T(14)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))
47424 := ((4^{T(2)}) × T((T(4) + ((7 × 4))))
47428 := (((8²) × T((T(4) + T(7)))) + (4))
47432 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3))) × ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7))/T(4))
47434 := (((4³) × T((T(4) + T(7)))) + T(4))
47436 := ((63 + T(T(4))) × (T(T(7)) - (4)))
47445 := (T(5) × ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(7) + T(T(4))))
47446 := ((T(6) × T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) + ((7⁴)))

$$\begin{aligned} 47447 &:= (((7 + T(T(4))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) \\ 47455 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-((T(5) - (4))) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(4))) \\ 47465 &:= ((-5) + ((T(6) + T(4)) \times T(7))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 47469 &:= (T(9) + (64 \times T((T(7) + T(4)))) \\ 47475 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((-7) + T(T(4))) - (7))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47482 &:= ((T((2 + T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) + (7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47483 &:= (((T(3) \times 8) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47484 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 8) \times (4 + T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47491 &:= (T(-((1 - 94))) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47492 &:= (((-T(2)) + T(T(9 - 4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(4) \\ 47499 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - (-4 \times T(T(T(7 - 4)))) \\ 47502 &:= ((-T(2)) + T(T(05))) \times T((7 \times 4)) \\ 47505 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(T(05)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4))) \\ 47512 &:= (((T(2) - T(15))) \times T(T(7))) + T(4) \\ 47513 &:= (-((T(3) + 1)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47514 &:= (-T((4 - 1))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4))) \\ 47515 &:= (-5) + (T(15) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4))) \\ 47541 &:= (T(T(-((1 - 4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47542 &:= ((2 \times T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47543 &:= (((T(3 + T(T(4))) - T(5)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 47544 &:= ((T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) - T((-7) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47545 &:= (-T(5)) + ((-4) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) + (4))) \\ 47547 &:= (((T(T(7)) - T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(7)) + T(T(4)) \\ 47552 &:= ((2^5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47556 &:= ((T(6) + T(5)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47557 &:= (((-T((7 - 5))) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(4)) \\ 47562 &:= ((2 \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47565 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(65))) \times T(T((7 - 4)))) \\ 47566 &:= (((6^6) - T((5 \times 7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47568 &:= ((8 \times 6) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)))) \\ 47571 &:= ((T((-1) + T(7))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T((7 + 4))) \\ 47575 &:= (((-5) + ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5)))/(-7))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47578 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 47584 &:= ((T(4) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - (4)))) \\ 47585 &:= (((-5) + T(8)) \times (-5) + (T(7) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 47586 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (((-8) + T(5)) \times T(7)) + T(4)) \\ 47592 &:= (((T((2 + T(9))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T((7 \times 4)))) \\ 47595 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(5)) - (74))) \\ 47618 &:= (((81 \times T(6)) \times T(7)) - T(4)) \\ 47622 &:= (-T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(67) - T(4))) \\ 47624 &:= (-4) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(67) - T(4))) \\ 47625 &:= (-((5^{T(2)})) \times ((T(6) - T(T(7))) + (4))) \\ 47628 &:= (((T(8)^2) \times T(6)) \times 7)/4 \\ 47629 &:= (T(T(9)) + (((T(T(2))^6) - (7)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 47635 &:= ((5 \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47638 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(3 + 6))) \times T(7)) + T(4)) \\ 47642 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) \times (-T(7)) - T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47652 &:= ((2 - (T(T(5)) \times (-6))) \times T((7 + 4))) \\ 47656 &:= (((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) \times T(6)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47659 &:= ((T(95) - T(6)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47662 &:= (-((T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(6) \times T(67)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47672 &:= (((-2) + T(T(7))) \times (6 - (T(7) \times (-4)))) \\ 47673 &:= (3 \times ((7 \times T(67)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 47677 &:= (((T(7) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + ((7^4))) \\ 47682 &:= ((T((2 \times T(8))) + (T(6))) \times (T(7) - T(4))) \\ 47685 &:= ((T((5 + T(8))) + T((T(6)/7))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47689 &:= (-((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(8) - T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + (4)))) \\ 47691 &:= (T(T((1 \times 9))) + ((6^{T(7-4)})) \\ 47692 &:= (-((T(2)^9)) + (T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 47694 &:= (((T(4) \times T(96)) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47695 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-9) + T((T(6) + (7)))) + T(T(4))) \\ 47698 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(9) + (6)))) - (T(7) + T(4))) \\ 47712 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - (1 - T(T(7)))) \times (T(7) \times 4)) \\ 47715 &:= (-T(5)) \times (((-1) \times T(T(7))) - (T(74))) \\ 47725 &:= (-T(5)) + (((T(2) + T(7)) \times T(7)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47726 &:= (-T(T(6))) + ((T(2) + T(7)) \times (7 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47728 &:= ((T(8) \times (2^7)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47733 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-3) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(7))))/T(T(4)) \\ 47734 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (3 + T(7))) - T((7 - 4))) \\ 47735 &:= (-5) + (((3 + T(7)) \times T(7)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47736 &:= ((6^3) \times (T((-7) + T(7))) - T(4)) \\ 47754 &:= ((T((4 \times T(5))) \times T(7)) - T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47755 &:= (T(5) + (((T(T(5)) \times 7) + T(7)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 47759 &:= (-((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (74)))) \\ 47762 &:= (((T(T(2))^6) - T(T(7))) - T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 47769 &:= (-((T(T(9)) + (-T(6) \times T(7))) \times (T(7) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47775 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(7) \times T(7)) + (7^4))) \\ 47781 &:= (((-1) + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47794 &:= ((4 + T(T(9))) \times ((T(7) + T(7)) - T(4))) \\ 47795 &:= (-((T(5) - ((T(97) + T(7)) \times T(4)))) \\ 47815 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-((1 \times 8)) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(4))) \\ 47817 &:= (T(T((7 - 1))) \times (T(8) + T((T(7) - T(4)))) \\ 47822 &:= (-2) + ((T((T(T(T(2))) + T(8))) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47823 &:= (T(3) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(8) + T((T(7) - T(4)))) \\ 47824 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(8))) + (T(T(7)) \times 4)) \\ 47825 &:= (((T(5) \times 2) \times T((8 \times 7))) - T(T(4))) \\ 47826 &:= (((6^{T(T(2))}) + T(8)) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 47832 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + T((8 \times T((7 - 4)))) \\ 47834 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-8))) \times T(7)) + T(4)) \\ 47835 &:= ((T(5) \times 3) \times ((T(8) \times T(7)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 47838 &:= ((83 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - (4))) \\ 47842 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(8) - (7)))) - (4))) \\ 47845 &:= (-5) + (T(T(4)) \times (87 \times T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

- 47852** := $((-2) + T(58)) \times (7 \times 4)$
47853 := $((T(3) + T(T(5))) - 8) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(4))$
47854 := $((-T(4) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(8) - (7)))) + (4)$
47856 := $(-6) \times ((-5) \times T((8 \times 7))) + (4)$
47859 := $-((T(9) - ((T(58) \times T(7)) - (4))))$
47862 := $(T(2) \times (-6) + (T((8 \times 7)) \times T(4)))$
47869 := $((T(9) - (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times (-T(7)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
47872 := $((2^7) \times ((-T(8) + T(T(7))) + (4)))$
47873 := $(T((T((T(T(3)) - (7))) - 8)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4))))$
47878 := $(T(T(8)) + ((T(7) - T(T(8))) \times (-74)))$
47879 := $((T(T(9)) + (7)) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + T(T(4))$
47894 := $((49 \times T((T(8) + (7)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
47895 := $(T((5 + T(9))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-7 \times T(4))))$
47896 := $((69 \times (T(T(8)) + T(7))) + T(4))$
47897 := $((-T(7 \times 9)) \times T(T(8))) / (-T(7)) - T(T(4))$
47905 := $((T(-((T(5) - T(09)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(4))$
47912 := $((T((T(2) + T((1 + 9)))) \times T(7)) + (4))$
47922 := $((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T((7 - 4))))$
47925 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(9) - (7)) \times 4)))$
47926 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(9) \times T(7)) + T(4)))$
47929 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) \times T(9) - (T(T(7)) \times (-4)))$
47935 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-9) + T(7)) + T(T(4))$
47936 := $(T(T((T(6)/3))) + (T(97) \times T(4)))$
47938 := $((T((8 + 3)) \times T((9 + T(7)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
47942 := $((T(T(2))^4) \times (9 + T(7))) - T(4)$
47944 := $((T(T(4)) + 49) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(4))))$
47946 := $((6 + T(T(4))) \times (T(9) + T((T(7) + T(4))))$
47948 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(9) - T(7)))) - (4))$
47952 := $((T((T(2) + (5))) - T(T(9))) \times (7 - T(T(4))))$
47957 := $((7 + T(5) + 9) \times (7 + T(T(T(4))))$
47962 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - 9) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4))))$
47965 := $((5^6) + (T(T(T((9 - 7)))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
47975 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - T((T(9) - (7)))) - (4)$
47988 := $(T(8) + (T(T(8)) \times ((T(9) - T(7)) + T(T(4))))$
47992 := $((2 + T(T((T(9)/9))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4))))$
47993 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T((9 + T(9)))) \times T(7)) - (T(T(4))))$
47995 := $(T(5) + ((T(9) + T(97)) \times T(4)))$
47998 := $((T(8) \times (-T(9)) + T((T(9) + (7)))) + T(4))$
48048 := $((-T(8) - T(T(4))) \times (0 - T((8 \times 4))))$
48055 := $((T(T(5)) \times (50 \times 8)) + T(T(4)))$
48068 := $((T(8) \times T((60 - 8))) - T(T(T(4))))$
48125 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times (-1 - 8)) \times T(T(4))$
48128 := $((T(8) - T(2) - 1) \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(4))))$
48132 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (1 + T((-T(8) + T(T(4))))$
48135 := $(-T(5)) \times (31 - T((8 \times T(4))))$
48146 := $(T(6) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (-1) + T(T(8)))) \times T(T(4)))$
48156 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T((5 - 1)))) - T(T(8))) \times 4$
48165 := $(-T(5) + ((T((T(6) - 1)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))))$
48167 := $(7 \times (T(T(6)) + ((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T(4)))$
48168 := $(T(8) \times (T((T(6) - 1)) + T((-8) + T(T(4))))$
48183 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) \times (18 \times 4)))$
48196 := $((6^{T(T(9+1-8))}) + T(T(T(4))))$
48199 := $((T(9) \times (T(T(9)) + T((1 \times 8)))) + (4))$
48216 := $(-T(6) \times ((T(T((1 + 2))) \times (-T(8))) - T(T(T(4))))$
48222 := $(T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) \times (-8) + T(T(4))))$
48223 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(2)) \times T((2 + T(8)))) + T(T(T(4)))$
48224 := $(-T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-8) \times T(T(4))))$
48226 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(2))) + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))$
48231 := $((-1) + ((T(3))^{T(T(2))}) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))$
48232 := $((T((2^3))^{T(2)}) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))$
48235 := $((-5) + (T(3))^{T(2)}) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))$
48237 := $(7 \times (T(T((3 \times 2))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(4))))$
48238 := $((T(8)^3) + T(T(2))) + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))$
48244 := $((-4) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(4))))$
48245 := $(T(5)^4) - (T((-2) + T(8)) \times 4)$
48246 := $(T((T(6) - T(4))) \times (T((2 + T(8))) - T(4)))$
48255 := $(T(5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(28) - 4)))$
48257 := $((T(7) + 5)^{T(2)}) - (-8) \times T(T(T(4)))$
48262 := $((T(T(2))^6) + T((T(2) + 8))) + T(T(T(4)))$
48264 := $((4^6) + ((-2) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
48265 := $(-T((T(5) \times 6))) + ((-2) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
48268 := $(T(8) + ((6^{T(T(2))}) + T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))$
48269 := $((T(T(9)) - (6 + 2)) \times (-8) + T(T(4)))$
48273 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times 7) + ((T(T(2))^{T(8/4)})))$
48275 := $((T(5) \times T((T(7 + 2)) + T(8))) - T(T(T(4))))$
48278 := $(-T(T(8)) + ((T(7) \times 2) \times (-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4))))$
48279 := $((T(T(T(T(9 - 7)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-8) \times T(T(4))))$
48282 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(8)/T(2)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(4)))$
48285 := $(-T(5)) \times (T((8 - 2)) - T((8 \times T(4))))$
48295 := $((5 \times T(T(9))) - (-28) \times T(T(T(4))))$
48307 := $((70 - 3) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4))))$
48315 := $(-T(5)) \times (-((T(13) \times T(8))) + T(T(4)))$
48323 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) \times (T((-3) + T(8))) + T(T(T(4))))$
48324 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) \times (-4)))$
48334 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(3)) - T((-T(8) + T(T(4))))$
48336 := $((T(T(6)) - 3) \times ((T(3) \times T(8)) - 4))$
48339 := $((T((T(9) + T(3))) - (T((T(3) + T(8))) \times T(T(4))))$
48342 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) + T((8 + T(T(4))))$
48344 := $(4 \times (-T(4) + (T(3) \times T((8 + T(T(4))))$
48345 := $((T(5) + ((4 \times T(3)) \times T(8))) \times T(T(4)))$
48346 := $((-T(6)) \times ((-T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 8) + 4$
48348 := $(-T(8)) + ((4 \times T(3)) \times T((8 + T(T(4))))$
48352 := $((2^5) \times (-((T(T(3)) + 8)) + T(T(T(4))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 48355 &:= (-5) \times ((T(5) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(8)))) + (4)) \\ 48356 &:= (((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(8-4)))) \\ 48357 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - (3 + (T(8) \times T(4)))) \\ 48362 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(3) \times T(8)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48363 &:= ((T(3) - T(T(6+3))) \times (8 - T(T(4)))) \\ 48366 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(3)))) - (T(8) \times 4)) \\ 48372 &:= (T(2) \times (-T(T(7))) + (T((T(T(3)) + T(8))) \times T(4))) \\ 48374 &:= (-((T(4) + T(7))) \times ((T(T(T(3))) + T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 48375 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3))) - T((T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 48379 &:= ((T(9) \times ((T(T(7)) + 3) + T(T(8)))) + (4)) \\ 48382 &:= (-2) + ((8 \times 3) \times T((8 + T(T(4)))))) \\ 48384 &:= (-4) \times ((T(T(8)) + (T(3))) \times (-8 - T(4))) \\ 48388 &:= (((-8) \times T(8)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-8) + (4) \\ 48389 &:= ((T(9) + 8) \times (T((T(3) + T(8))) + T(4))) \\ 48394 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(3))) \times T(8)) + T(4) \\ 48395 &:= ((T((5 + T(9))) \times 38) - T(T(4))) \\ 48396 &:= (T(6) + (T(9) \times (-T(3)) + T((T(8) + T(4)))))) \\ 48398 &:= (((T(8) \times T((T(9) + T(3)))) + T(T(8))) - (4)) \\ 48424 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 8))) + T(4))) \\ 48426 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((2 \times T(4)))) - (84)) \\ 48429 &:= (T(9) + (24 \times T((8 + T(T(4)))))) \\ 48432 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T((8 + 4))) \\ 48433 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 48435 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) - T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48438 &:= ((83 + T(T(4))) \times T((T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 48439 &:= (((T(9) - T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(4)) + 8))) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 48448 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(4)) \times (8 \times 4) \\ 48463 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(4)) + 8) - T(T(4)) \\ 48465 &:= (T((T(5) - (6))) \times (-4) + T((T(8) + T(4)))) \\ 48473 &:= ((-3) + T(T(7))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 48475 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) - T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 48476 &:= (T(6) + (((7 + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 48489 &:= ((T(98) \times T(4)) - T(T(T((8/4)))))) \\ 48492 &:= (-((T(2) + 9)) \times (T(T(4)) - (8^4))) \\ 48495 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(((9 \times T(4)) + 8)) \times T(4)) \\ 48532 &:= (((T(2)^3) - 5) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 48534 &:= -((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48536 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-T(3))) - 5) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48537 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-3) + T(T(5)))) + T(T((T(8)/4))) \\ 48542 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48544 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (4 + T(5))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(4))) \\ 48545 &:= ((T(5) \times T((-4) + T(T(5)) - T(8))) - (T(T(4)))) \\ 48552 &:= (T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))/T(4))) \\ 48555 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(5)/5) - T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48556 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((5 + T(5)))) + (T(8) + T(4))) \\ 48557 &:= (-((T(7) + T(5))) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48563 &:= (((T(T(3) + 6)) - 5) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48564 &:= (T((T(T(4)) + (T(6) - 5))) \times (-T(8)) + T(T(4))) \\ 48565 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T(6))) + (T((5 \times 8)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 48571 &:= ((-1) - T(7)) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4))) \\ 48572 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (-7) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))))) \\ 48573 &:= (-3) + ((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T((8 \times 4)) \\ 48574 &:= -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - T(8)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 48576 &:= ((-((T(6) + 7))) + T(T(5))) \times T((8 \times 4)) \\ 48577 &:= (T(7) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - T((8 + T(4)))))) \\ 48578 &:= (T(T(8)) + (((T(7) \times T(58)) + 4))) \\ 48579 &:= -((T(T(T(9-7))) + (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))))) \\ 48585 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(8) + T(4)))) \\ 48586 &:= (-((6 + 8)) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48591 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48592 &:= (2 \times (((T(9) \times T(5)) \times T(8)) - (4))) \\ 48595 &:= (-5) - (((-9) \times T(5)) \times T(8)) \times T(4) \\ 48596 &:= (((6 \times T(9)) \times 5) \times T(8)) - (4) \\ 48597 &:= -((T(-((7-9))) + (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))))) \\ 48598 &:= (((-((T(8) \times T(9))) \times T(T(5))) + 8)/(-4)) \\ 48599 &:= (-((9/9)) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48615 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-((1^6) - T((8 \times T(4)))))) \\ 48618 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((1 + 68) + 4)) \\ 48624 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))) - (T(6) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-4)) \\ 48628 &:= ((-8) + (T(T(2))^6)) + (T(8) \times T(T(4))) \\ 48633 &:= ((-3) + (T(3)^6)) + (T(8) \times T(T(4))) \\ 48636 &:= ((T((6-3)^6) + (T(8) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 48642 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(46) \times T((T(8)/4))) \\ 48643 &:= (((T(T(3))^4) + T((T(6) - 8)))/4) \\ 48645 &:= ((T(5) \times T(46)) \times T((8/4))) \\ 48649 &:= ((T(9) \times T(46)) + (8 - 4)) \\ 48654 &:= ((T((4 \times 5)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(8) \times 4)) \\ 48655 &:= (((T(5) \times T(5)) \times 6) \times T(8)) + T(T(4)) \\ 48657 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(6) \times T((8/4)))) \\ 48664 &:= (((T(T((4+6))) - T(T(6))) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48665 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(((6 \times 6) - 8))) - T(T(4))) \\ 48666 &:= (((6^6) - 6) + T((8 + T(T(4)))))) \\ 48672 &:= (((T(T(2))^7)/6) + T((8 + T(T(4)))))) \\ 48673 &:= ((-((3-76)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(4))) \\ 48675 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - T((T(6) - (8+4)))) \\ 48679 &:= (-T(9)) - ((-T(T(7))) \times T(-((T(6) - T(8)))) - 4) \\ 48692 &:= (((T(2) + 9) \times T(T((T(6) - 8)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48695 &:= (-5) \times (((-T(9)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(8))) - T(4)) \\ 48696 &:= (-6) \times (((T(T(9)) - (T(6))) \times (-8)) - (4)) \\ 48705 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((0-7) - T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 48714 &:= ((T(T((4+1))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T((8/4)))) \\ 48715 &:= ((-T(5)) \times (1 - (T(T(7)) \times 8))) + T(4) \\ 48716 &:= ((T(T((6-1))) \times T(T(7))) - (8-4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48732 &:= ((T(T((2+3))) \times T(T(7))) + (8+4)) \\ 48734 &:= -((T(T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) - ((7+8)^4)) \\ 48735 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-((T(3) \times T(7)) - T(T(8+4)))) \\ 48738 &:= ((T(T((8-3))) \times T(T(7))) + (8+T(4))) \\ 48739 &:= (((T((9+T(3))) \times T(T(7))) - T(8)) + T(T(4))) \\ 48741 &:= ((T(T((1+4))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(8/4)))) \\ 48745 &:= (T(5) + (((T(T(T(4)))/(-7)) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 48751 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (8 \times 4)) \\ 48752 &:= ((T(T(2) \times 5)) \times T(T(7))) + (8 \times 4) \\ 48753 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (8+4))) \\ 48754 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(8/4)))) \\ 48755 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(8) + (4))) \\ 48757 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(7) + (T(8)/4))) \\ 48758 &:= (-8) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(8) + T(4))) \\ 48759 &:= (T(9) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(8/4)))) \\ 48762 &:= ((T(2) \times T((6 \times 7))) \times (8 + T(4))) \\ 48763 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - ((-6) + T(7)) \times (-T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 48765 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(6) + (7)))) + T((T(8)/4))) \\ 48766 &:= ((T((-6) + T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + (T(8) + T(4)) \\ 48768 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(7) \times (-8)) + T(4)))) \\ 48772 &:= (-T(2) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((7+8))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 48775 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + T((7 + T(8/4)))) \\ 48776 &:= ((67 \times T(7)) \times (T(8) - T(4))) \\ 48783 &:= ((T(T(-(3-8))) \times T(T(7))) + (8 + T(T(4)))) \\ 48785 &:= ((-T(5)) \times ((-8) \times T(T(7)) - 8)) - T(T(4)) \\ 48795 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(T(9)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times (-4))) \\ 48822 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (((T(2)^8) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48824 &:= (-T((4^2))) \times (-8 - T((T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 48825 &:= ((5^2) \times T(((T(8) + T(8)) - T(4))) \\ 48826 &:= (((T(6) \times T(2)) + 8) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 48828 &:= ((-T(82)) - T(T(8))) \times (-8 + 4)) \\ 48837 &:= (73 \times (T(T(8)) + T(8/4))) \\ 48852 &:= ((T(T(T(2)))) + 5) \times (T(8) + T((8 + T(4)))) \\ 48853 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) + (5^8))/8) - 4) \\ 48862 &:= (((T(T(2))^6) + T(T(8))) + T(T(T(8-4)))) \\ 48864 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(6) - 8)) \times (8 \times 4)) \\ 48867 &:= (-T(7) + (((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) - 8) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 48879 &:= (-((T((9-7))^8)) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48888 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) + (T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 48895 &:= ((T(T((T(5) - 9))) + (-8) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 48896 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(8) \times T(8)))) - T(T(4))) \\ 48898 &:= (((-T(8)) - T(T(9))) + 8) \times (-T(8) + T(4)) \\ 48916 &:= (T(T((6+1))) + ((T(98) \times T(4))) \\ 48917 &:= (T(T(7)) - (-1) - (T(98) \times T(4))) \\ 48925 &:= ((T(T((5 \times 2))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(4)))) \\ 48927 &:= ((-T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(9) + (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48933 &:= (T(3) + ((T(3) + T(T(9))) \times (-8) + T(T(4)))) \\ 48937 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) + ((T(98) \times T(4)))) \\ 48944 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(4) - 9)) \times (-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48945 &:= (((-5) \times T(49)) \times (-8)) - T(T(4)) \\ 48946 &:= (T(6) + ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) \\ 48956 &:= ((T((T(6) - 5)) \times (T(9) \times 8)) - 4) \\ 48964 &:= ((T((T(4) + 6)) \times (T(9) \times 8)) + 4) \\ 48966 &:= (-6) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(9) + 8) \times 4)) \\ 48969 &:= (((T(T(9)) - 6) \times T(9)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \\ 48972 &:= (T((T(2) \times 7)) \times ((T(9) + 8) \times 4)) \\ 48975 &:= (T(5) + ((T((7+9)) \times T(8)) \times T(4))) \\ 48978 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(9))) + ((T(8) \times T(4)))) \\ 48982 &:= -((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(8))/9) \times (T(T(8)) - (4)))) \\ 48984 &:= (-4) + ((T(T(8))/9) \times (T(T(8)) - (4))) \\ 48988 &:= ((T(T(8)))/(-T(8) - T(9))) \times (T(T(8)) - (4)) \\ 48989 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((T(T(8)))/(-9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(4)))) \\ 48995 &:= ((T(5) \times T((9 \times 9))) - T((T(8) + (4)))) \\ 48997 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) + T((8 + T(T(4)))) \\ 49085 &:= ((T(5))^{T(8)/09}) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 49112 &:= -((T(2) + (-11) \times T(94))) \\ 49115 &:= ((T((5-1)) + 1) \times T(94)) \\ 49126 &:= ((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (1 + T(94))) \\ 49128 &:= ((T(8)/T(2)) \times (-1) + T((9 \times T(4)))) \\ 49132 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(3)} + 1) + (T(9) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49135 &:= (((5 \times T(3)) + 1) \times (T(9) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49152 &:= -(((T(2) - T(5)) \times ((1-9)^4)) \\ 49175 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 71) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49185 &:= ((T(5) \times T(81)) - T((T(9) - T(4)))) \\ 49215 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) - (-9) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49221 &:= ((T(T(T(1+2)))^2) - (T(T(9)) \times 4)) \\ 49222 &:= (-2) + (-T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 49223 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (-2) + (T(T(9)) \times 4)) \\ 49224 &:= (42 \times (T((T(2) + T(9))) - 4)) \\ 49225 &:= ((-5) \times T(T(T(2+2)))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49228 &:= (((T(8)^{T(2)} - T(2)) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49229 &:= (((-9) + T(T(T(T(2))))^2) - (T(9) + T(4))) \\ 49231 &:= (((T((1 \times 3))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49233 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((-T(2) + T(T(9))) \times (-4))) \\ 49234 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times 32) - (-9) + T(T(4))) \\ 49235 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(94)) \\ 49238 &:= (((T(T(8))/3)^2) + 9) - T(T(4)) \\ 49244 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (4 \times 2)) - 9) \times 4) \\ 49245 &:= ((5 + (T(4)^{T(2)})) \times (T(9) + (4))) \\ 49248 &:= (T(8) \times (-T(4) + T(((T(2) + T(9)) + (4)))) \\ 49257 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (T(5))) \times (-T(2) + T(T((9-4)))) \\ 49262 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(((T(6) + 2) + T(9)))) - 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49263 &:= (-3) + ((T(T(6)))^2 - T((9 \times T(4)))) \\ 49265 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(6) + (2 + 9)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49266 &:= (T(6) \times T(((6 + 2) + 9) \times 4)) \\ 49269 &:= (((-9) + T(T(6)))^2) - T((9 - 4)) \\ 49273 &:= (((T(T(3)) + T(7)) \times (2 + T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49275 &:= (-5) - (((-7) + T(-(T(2) - T(9)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 49294 &:= (((T((4 \times 9))^2)/9) + T(4)) \\ 49295 &:= (((T(5) + T(T(9))) \times (2 + T(9))) - T(T(4))) \\ 49296 &:= (T((T(6) - 9)) \times (2 + T((T(9) - T(4)))) \\ 49328 &:= (8 \times ((2 \times T(T((3 + 9)))) + (4))) \\ 49329 &:= (-9^2) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(9) - T(4)))) \\ 49332 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (((T(T(3)))^3) - T(T(9))) - (4)) \\ 49335 &:= ((T(T(5)) - (3 - T(39))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49336 &:= (T((T(6)/3)) \times ((T(T(T(3))) - 9) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49337 &:= (((7 \times T(3)) \times T((3 + T(9)))) - T(T(4))) \\ 49339 &:= (((-9) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 9) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 49346 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times T(94))) \\ 49348 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + T(4)) \times (T(T(3)) - 94))) \\ 49351 &:= (((1 + T(5)) \times T(T((3 + 9)))) + T(T(4))) \\ 49356 &:= ((6^5) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(9) \times 4))) \\ 49357 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - T((-3) + T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49362 &:= (((T(T(2))^6) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(9) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49364 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - 6)) - (T(T(3)))) \times (T(9) - 4)) \\ 49365 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-63)) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49366 &:= (((-6) \times (-((T(6)^3)) + T(T(9)))) + T(4)) \\ 49368 &:= (8 \times (T(T(6)) - (T((T(3) \times 9)) \times (-4))) \\ 49375 &:= (((5 + T(T(7))) \times T((T(3) + 9))) + T(T(4))) \\ 49382 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times T((3 + T(9)))) - T(4)) \\ 49383 &:= (3 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(9) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49384 &:= (((-T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(9) + 4)) \\ 49386 &:= ((T(68) \times T(T(3))) + T(T((9 - 4))) \\ 49388 &:= ((8 \times (-T(8)) - (-T(3) \times T(T(9)))) - (4)) \\ 49392 &:= -(((T(2) - T(9)) \times T(((3 + 9) \times 4))) \\ 49395 &:= ((5 \times T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 49396 &:= (((-6) + T(T(9))) \times (3 + T(9))) + (4)) \\ 49422 &:= (T(2) \times ((T((T(T(2)) \times T(4))) \times 9) + 4)) \\ 49424 &:= (4 \times ((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) + 9) \times 4) \\ 49425 &:= (-5) \times (T((T(2) \times T(4))) - (T(T(9)) \times T(4))) \\ 49428 &:= ((T(8) \times T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(9) \times 4)) \\ 49434 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(4))) - 9))/T(4)) \\ 49442 &:= (-T(2)) - ((T((4 \times 4)) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49443 &:= (3 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(4)) + T((-9) + T(T(4)))) \\ 49445 &:= (((-T((5 \times 4) - 4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49446 &:= (((-T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(9)))/(-T(4))) \\ 49452 &:= (T(-((T(2) - T(5)))) \times (4 + T((T(9) - T(4)))) \\ 49456 &:= (T(T(6)) - (5 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49465 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(6))) \times T(4)) - (T(9) - T(4))) \\ 49466 &:= (T(6) - ((T((6 + T(4)) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49469 &:= (((T(T(9)) + 6) \times 49) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49472 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times ((7^4) - T(9))) - 4) \\ 49475 &:= (-T(5)) - (((-T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49476 &:= ((T(T(6)) - ((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(9))) \times (-4)) \\ 49479 &:= (-9) - ((7 - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(9)) - 4)) \\ 49484 &:= ((48 \times (-4) + T(T(9))) - 4) \\ 49485 &:= (-T(5)) - (T((8 + T((4 + 9)))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 49488 &:= ((T(8) + (8 + 4)) \times (T(T(9)) - 4)) \\ 49492 &:= (((T(2) + T(9)) \times (-4) + T(T(9))) + 4) \\ 49495 &:= (-5) - (T(((9 \times T(4)) + 9)) \times (-T(4))) \\ 49499 &:= (((T(99) \times T(4)) + 9) - T(4)) \\ 49515 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-1) + (-((T(5) + T(9))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 49524 &:= (4 \times (T(T(2)) + ((5 \times T(9)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49527 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (2 + T(T(5)))) - (9 - 4)) \\ 49528 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(2))^5) - T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49535 &:= (((T(5)^3) \times T(5)) - T(T(9))) - T(T(4)) \\ 49538 &:= (((8^3) + T(5)) \times 94) \\ 49539 &:= -(((T(T(9) + T(T(3)))) - ((5 \times T(T(9))) \times T(4))) \\ 49545 &:= (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5)) + 9))/4) \\ 49549 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T((-4) + T(5))) \times T(9)) + 4) \\ 49555 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/5)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(9))) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 49561 &:= (1 + (-T(6)) \times (-T((-5) + T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49562 &:= (2 + (-T(6)) \times (-T((-5) + T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49563 &:= (3 \times (T(6) + (T((T(5) + 9)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49564 &:= ((T(4) \times T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) - (-9 - T(T(4)))) \\ 49565 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((T((T(6) - 5)) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49566 &:= (6 + (-T(6)) \times (-T((-5) + T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49567 &:= (7 + (-T(6)) \times (-T((-5) + T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49568 &:= (8 \times (T(((T(6) \times 5) - 9)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49569 &:= ((T(9) - 6) \times (T((5 + T(9))) - 4)) \\ 49581 &:= ((T(T(-((1 - 8)))) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(9) - 4))) \\ 49585 &:= (((-5) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(9))) + T(4) \\ 49586 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(8))) \times (-T(5) - T(9))) - 4) \\ 49588 &:= (((-8) + T(8)) \times (T(T((T(5) - 9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 49599 &:= (-9) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(5) - 9^4)) \\ 49608 &:= (T(8) \times T(((06 - 9) + T(T(4)))) \\ 49618 &:= ((T(8) \times T(((1 + 6) + T(9)))) + T(4)) \\ 49623 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(2) + T(69)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 49624 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((2 \times T(6)))) - (T(9) - 4)) \\ 49625 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(2))) \times 69) - T(T(4))) \\ 49626 &:= ((6^{T(T(2))}) + ((6 \times 9) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 49627 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(9)) \times 4))) \\ 49628 &:= (((-8) \times (T(T(2)) - (6 \times T(T(9)))) - 4) \\ 49632 &:= (2 \times ((T(3) - (6 \times T(T(9)))) \times (-4)) \\ 49637 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(((3 - 6) + T(9))) \times T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

- 49638** := $(T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) - (9 + T(4))))$)
49645 := $((T(5)^{T(4)-6}) - T(T(9))) + T(T(4))$
49647 := $(T((T(7) + T(4))) \times ((T(6) - 9) + T(T(4))))$
49648 := $(8 \times ((T(T(-(4-6)))) \times T(T(9))) - 4)$
49656 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (-69)) + (4))$
49662 := $(-T(2)) - (T((T(6) + T(6))) \times (-T(9) + T(4)))$
49664 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(6) + T(6)))) - (-9) + T(4))$
49665 := $((5 \times T(T(6))) \times ((-6) + T(9)) + (4))$
49673 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 7) \times (T(T(6)) - 9) - (T(T(4))))$
49675 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(6) \times T(9)) + T(4)))$
49676 := $((((6 \times 7) + 6) \times T(T(9))) - (4))$
49678 := $(-((T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (-T((6+9)) + (4))))))$
49682 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-(8 \times 6) \times T(T(9))) + (4)))$
49683 := $(3 \times (((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4))))$
49684 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(8) + (6)))) + (9 + T(4)))$
49685 := $(-5) - ((-(8 \times 6) \times T(T(9))) - T(4))$
49686 := $(T(6) \times ((T(8) \times (T(6) + T(9))) - T(4)))$
49692 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) - (T(6))) \times (-T(9) + (4))))$
49695 := $(T(5) - (T(T(9)) \times ((T(6) - 9) \times (-4))))$
49715 := $(-5) \times ((1 + T(T(7))) - (T(T(9)) \times T(4)))$
49723 := $((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (9 + T(4)))$
49725 := $(T((T(5) + 2)) \times ((7 \times T(9)) + T(4)))$
49726 := $(T(((T(6) - T(2)) + T(7))) \times (-9) + T(T(4)))$
49728 := $((((T(T(8)) \times T(T(2))) \times (-T(7)))/(-9)) \times 4)$
49735 := $((((T(T(5))/T(3)) + T(7)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4)))$
49736 := $((6^{T(3)}) + (-((7-9) \times T(T(T(4))))$
49742 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 4) \times T(((T(7) - 9) \times 4))$
49745 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((4 \times 7))) + T(T(9))) - T(4)$
49746 := $((-(T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7) + T(9)) + 4$
49748 := $((T(8) \times (4 + T((7 + T(9)))) - (4))$
49751 := $((T(15) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) - (4)$
49752 := $(T((T(2) + (5))) \times (T((7 + T(9))) + (4)))$
49753 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) + (4))$
49755 := $(T((T(5) + T(5))) \times ((7 + T(9)) + T(T(4))))$
49759 := $(-T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) + 9)) + (4))$
49762 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(T(7)) \times 9) - T(T(4))))$
49764 := $(T((-4) + T((6 + 7))) \times (9 + 4))$
49765 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(6) + (7)))) + T(T(9))) + T(4)$
49774 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(7) + T(T(7)))) \times T(9)) + 4$
49775 := $((T((-5) + T(7)) - T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))$
49777 := $(-7) \times (((T(7) \times T(7)) \times (-9)) - T(T(4)))$
49779 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times (T(7) - 9)) - T(T(T(4))))$
49795 := $(-5) - ((-9) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(9-4))$
49796 := $((T((6+9)) \times (T(T(7)) + 9)) - (4))$
49798 := $((T(8) \times T((T(9) + (7)))) + T((9 + T(4))))$
49805 := $((T(5) \times T((T(08) + T(9)))) - T(4))$
49815 := $(T(5) \times T((T((1+8)) + (9 \times 4))))$
49824 := $(4 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)) + (T(T(9)) \times 4))$
49825 := $((T(5) \times T(((2 \times T(8)) + 9))) + T(4))$
49855 := $(-T(5)) - ((-T(5)) \times T((T(8) + T(9)))) - T(T(4))$
49857 := $(-T(7)) - (((T(T(5)) + 8) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(4)))$
49859 := $(((-T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (T((9 + 4)))$
49866 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(8))) + (9 - 4))$
49868 := $((8 \times 6) \times (T(8) + T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
49872 := $((2 \times T(7)) - 8) \times (T(T(9)) + (4))$
49875 := $(T(5) \times (T(((T(7) + 8) + T(9))) + (4)))$
49885 := $((T(T(5)) \times 8) - (8 + T(9))) \times T(T(4))$
49886 := $((T(T(6)) \times (8 \times (T(8) - 9))) - T(4))$
49892 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(8))) \times 9 - (4)$
49893 := $(3 \times (-9) + (8 \times T((9 + T(T(4))))))$
49895 := $((T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times T(T(8))) - ((T(9) + T(4)))$
49896 := $(T(T(6)) \times (T(9) + T(((8 \times 9)/4)))$
49932 := $(T(((2^3) \times 9)) \times (9 + T(4)))$
49935 := $(T(5) - (-T(39)) \times (9 + T(T(4))))$
49938 := $(((-8) + T(T(3))) + T(9)) \times T((T(9) - (4)))$
49945 := $((T((T(5) \times 4)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
49946 := $((((-T(6)) \times T(T(4))) + T(9)) \times (-T(9))) - (4)$
49962 := $((2 \times T(T(6))) + ((T(99) \times T(4))))$
49965 := $(T(5) \times ((6 + T((9 \times 9))) + (4)))$
49968 := $(8 \times ((6 \times T(T(9))) + (9 \times 4)))$
49972 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T((T(9)/9))) + 4)$
49974 := $(-((T((T(4) + T(7))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) + (4))))))$
49975 := $((T(5) \times (7 + T((9 \times 9)))) + T(T(4)))$
49987 := $((T(7) - T(T(8))) + (T((T(9)/9))^4)$
49992 := $(-T(2)) + (-99) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4))))$
49995 := $((T(5) \times T((9 \times 9))) + (T(9) \times 4))$
50176 := $((T(T(6)) - (7))^{10/5})$
50232 := $((2 \times T(3)) \times T(T((-2) + T(05))))$
50395 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-T(9) - T(30))) - (5))$
50625 := $(T(5)^{-2+6+0 \times 5})$
50637 := $((-T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) - T(60))) - (T(5))$
50667 := $(-((T(7) \times (T(6) - T(60))) - T(5)))$
50675 := $((5^7) - (T(60) \times T(5)))$
50735 := $((5^3) \times T(T(7))) - T(05)$
50736 := $(T(63) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(05))))$
50745 := $((T(5)^4) + T(T(((7 \times 0) + 5)))$
50755 := $((T(T(5)) + (5)) \times T(T(7))) + 05$
50811 := $(T(T(11)) + ((T(80) \times T(5))))$
50853 := $(T(T((T(3) + (5)))) \times (8 + T(05)))$
51045 := $(T(5) \times T((T(40)/T(-(1-5))))$
51156 := $((6 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(((1+1) + 5)))$
51162 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(11)))) - (T(T(5))))$
51225 := $((T((T(T(5))/2)) \times T((T(T(2)) + 1))) - T(5))$

- 51228** := $(T(8) \times ((T(2) + T(T(T(T(2) + 1)))) - (T(T(5))))$
51235 := $(-5) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(T(2) + 1)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
51243 := $((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T((2 + T(T(-((1 - 5))))))$
51245 := $((T(T(5) \times 4)) \times T((T(T(2) + 1))) + 5)$
51268 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(6)))/T(2) - (-1 + T(5)))$
51276 := $((T(6) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))) + (T(15))$
51281 := $(-1) - ((T(T(8)))/(-T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 5)))$
51282 := $((2 \times T(T(8)))/T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 5)))$
51283 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(8))/T(2))) + (1^5))$
51285 := $((T(5) + T(82)) + 1) \times T(5)$
51286 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(8)))/T(2) - ((1 - 5)))$
51292 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-((1 - 5)))$
51295 := $(5 \times ((T(9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T((1 + T(5))))$
51296 := $((T(T(6) - 9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-1 + T(5)))$
51336 := $((6 + T(3)) \times T(-((T(T(3) + 1)) - T(T(5))))$
51345 := $((T(5)^4) + (T(3) \times T(15)))$
51375 := $(T(5) + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) + 1) \times T(T(5))))$
51379 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-((3 + 1)) - T(T(5))))$
51384 := $((4 \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(3) + 1))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
51393 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((-9) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1) - (T(T(5))))$
51399 := $(-9) - (-T(9 \times 3)) \times T((1 + T(5)))$
51425 := $((T(5) + 2) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
51435 := $((T(5)^3) + T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(5)$
51445 := $((T(5)^4) + T((T(4) \times (-1 - 5))))$
51465 := $(T(5) \times (T((6 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(-((1 - 5))))))$
51495 := $((T(5 - T(T(9))) \times (-T(4)) - 1) \times 5)$
51525 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-2) + T(T((5 + 1)))) \times (-T(5))$
51528 := $(T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) + ((T(5)^{-1+5}))$
51558 := $((T(T(8)) - 5) \times T((T(T(5))/T(-((1 - 5))))$
51567 := $((T(T(7)) \times ((6 + T(T(5))) + 1)) + 5)$
51577 := $((T(T(7)) \times (7 + T(T(5)))) + 15)$
51585 := $((T(T(5)) \times 8) + ((T(5)^{-1+5}))$
51645 := $((T(5) + (4 \times T(T(6)))) \times T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
51646 := $(T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(6 + 1))) \times T(T(5))))$
51665 := $((T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(6) - 1))) + 5)$
51667 := $((T((7 + T(6))) + (T(6))) \times (1 + T(T(5))))$
51673 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(7)) + (T(6))) \times (1 + T(T(5))))$
51723 := $(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(15))))$
51728 := $(8 \times (-2) + (T(7) \times T(T((1 + 5))))$
51734 := $(-T(4)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (7 - T(T((1 + 5))))$
51735 := $((T(T(5)) - T((3 \times T(7)))) + 1) \times (-T(5))$
51737 := $(-7) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (7 - T(T((1 + 5))))$
51738 := $((-8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(7)) - (1 + 5)$
51744 := $((4 + 4) \times T(7)) \times T(T((1 + 5)))$
51755 := $((-5) + T((T(5) + T(7)))) \times T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
51765 := $((T((5 \times 6)) + T(7)) \times T(-1 + T(5)))$
51773 := $(-((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) - (T(T(7) + 1)) \times T(T(5))))$
51786 := $(T(6) - (T((T(8) - 7))) \times (1 - T(T(5))))$
51789 := $(T(9) - ((-8) \times T(7)) \times T(T((1 + 5))))$
51828 := $((T((T(8)/T(2))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(15)))$
51829 := $((T((9 + T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + 1) - T(T(5))$
51872 := $((T(T(2)) - (T(T(7)) \times 8)) \times (-1 - T(5)))$
51875 := $((T((5 + 7)) \times (T(T(8) - 1))) + 5)$
51893 := $((T((3 + 9)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
51897 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(8)) + T((1 + 5))$
51925 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) - T(-((1 - 5))))$
51928 := $(8 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(9) + 1))) + 5))$
51933 := $((T((T(3) + T(3))) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) - (T(5)))$
51936 := $((6^{T(3)}) - (-((T(9) - 1)) \times T(T(5))))$
51938 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((3 + 9))) - T(-((1 - 5))))$
51943 := $((T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) - 5)$
51947 := $(-T(7)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(9) \times T((1 + 5))))$
51948 := $(T(T(8)) \times ((4 + 9) \times (1 + 5)))$
51953 := $((T((-3 + T(5))) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) + 5)$
51959 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(9)) - (1 + T(5))$
51963 := $((T((T(3) + 6))) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) + (T(5))$
51965 := $((5 \times T(T(6))) \times T(9)) - T(-((1 - 5)))$
51969 := $((T(9) + 6) \times (T(T(9)) - (1 + T(5))))$
51975 := $(5 \times 7) \times T((9 \times (1 + 5)))$
51984 := $((T((T(4) \times 8)) + 9) \times (1 + T(5)))$
51996 := $(-T(6)) \times (9 - T((T(9 + 1)) + T(5)))$
52065 := $((T(5) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(02))) \times T(5)$
52068 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((6 \times 02))) + T(T(5)))$
52075 := $((-5) + T(70)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5$
52086 := $(T(6) - ((-T(80)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)))$
52095 := $((5 \times T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(02)))) + (T(T(5))))$
52122 := $(-T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(2) - T((T(T(1 + T(2)))) + T(5)))$
52125 := $((T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((1 + T(2)))) \times T(5))$
52156 := $((T(T(6)) - T((5 - 1))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5))$
52164 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - (((T(T(6)) + 1)^2) - T(T(5))))$
52173 := $(T((T(T(T(3)))/7)) \times (T(12) + T(5)))$
52175 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(7) + 1))) - 25)$
52182 := $((T(2) + T(T(8))) \times T(-((1 + 2)) + T(5)))$
52185 := $((T((-5) + T(8))) + 1) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5$
52195 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((9 - 1) + T(T(T(2)))) - 5)$
52203 := $(-3) + (T(T(T(T(02)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))$
52206 := $(T(T(6)) \times (T(T(02 \times T(2)))) - 5)$
52208 := $((T(80) \times T(T(2))) + (2^{T(5)}))$
52212 := $(T(T(2)) - (-T(T(T(1 + 2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))$
52213 := $((T(3) + 1) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))$
52215 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((1 + T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) + T(5))$
52221 := $((T(1 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5))$
52224 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 2)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (2^5))$
52227 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(T(T(T(2))))^2) - T(T((2 \times 5))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 52228 &:= (-T(T(8)) - (((2 - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5)) \\ 52233 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T((2 + (T(2) \times T(5)))))) \\ 52234 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((-2) + T(5))) \\ 52236 &:= (((T(T(6)) + 3)^2) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(5)))) \\ 52237 &:= ((T(7) + 3) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))) \\ 52238 &:= (-T(T(8)) - ((-((T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52242 &:= (T((2 \times 4) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))) \\ 52245 &:= ((5 + T((T(4) \times 2))) \times (T(2)^5)) \\ 52248 &:= ((T(8) + T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))) \times T((2 + 5))) \\ 52262 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(2))) - (T(T((2 + 5)))) \\ 52267 &:= (-T(T(7)) - ((-((T(T(6)) - T(2))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52272 &:= ((T((2 \times 7)) - T(T(2))) \times T(2^5)) \\ 52275 &:= ((T(T((5 + 7))) - T(T(2))) \times (2 + T(5))) \\ 52277 &:= (-T(7) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(5))) \\ 52279 &:= ((T(9) + T(7)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))) \\ 52283 &:= ((3 + 8) \times T((T(T(2)) + T((-2) + T(5)))) \\ 52284 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(8) + T(2))) - (T(T(2))^5)) \\ 52307 &:= (((T(70) \times T(T(3))) + 2) + T(T(5))) \\ 52321 &:= (((-((1 \times 2) + T(T(T(3))))^2) - (T(T(5)))) \\ 52323 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (-3 - T((T(2) \times T(5)))) \\ 52326 &:= ((T(T(6))^2) - T(((3^2) \times 5))) \\ 52329 &:= (-((T(T(9)) + 2)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + 5)) \\ 52332 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(2) \times T(5)))) \\ 52335 &:= (((T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(3)) + T(2))) \times T(5)) \\ 52338 &:= (T((T(8)/3) \times (T((T(3))^2)) + (5))) \\ 52339 &:= (-T(T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (-2) + T(5))) \\ 52341 &:= -((T(T((-1) + T(4))) - ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + T(5))) \\ 52342 &:= (-((2^{T(4)})) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + 5)) \\ 52344 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(2)))) + 5) \\ 52345 &:= (-T(5) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \times T(T((2 \times 5)))) \\ 52346 &:= (((T(T(6)) - 4) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((-2) + T(5))) \\ 52347 &:= ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 52353 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(5) + (T(T(3)) \times (-2) + T(T(5)))) \\ 52356 &:= (-T(6) - (T(T((T(5) - 3))) \times (-2) - T(5))) \\ 52359 &:= (((9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T((T(3)/T(2)))) - T(5)) \\ 52365 &:= ((5 + T(((T(T(6))/3) + T(T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\ 52368 &:= ((8 \times T(T((6 + T(3)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 52372 &:= (-2) - (T(T(7)) \times (-((3^2) - T(T(5)))) \\ 52374 &:= (T((4 \times 7)) \times ((3^2) + T(T(5)))) \\ 52375 &:= (T(5) - (-((T(7) + T(3))) \times T(T((2 \times 5)))) \\ 52377 &:= (T(T(((T(7)/7) \times 3))) \times (2 + T(5))) \\ 52391 &:= (-1) - ((9 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5)) \\ 52392 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - T(9 + T(T(3)))) \times (2 - T(T(5)))) \\ 52397 &:= (-T(7) - (T(9) \times ((T(T(T(3))) + 2) \times (-5))) \\ 52398 &:= (((T(T(8)) - 9) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(2) + T(T(5)))) \\ 52416 &:= ((T(T((6 + 1))) + T(4)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52421 &:= (-1) + (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) \\ 52422 &:= (((T(T((2 \times T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) \\ 52425 &:= -(((T(5)^2) \times (T(4) - (T(2)^5))) \\ 52426 &:= (((T(T(6)) - 2)^{4-2}) - (T(5))) \\ 52428 &:= (((8^{T(T(2))}) - T(4) + T(T(2)))/5) \\ 52431 &:= (-1) + (((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52432 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) - T(T(2)))) - 5) \\ 52436 &:= (((T(T(6)) - (T(3) - (4)))^2) - (5)) \\ 52437 &:= ((T((7 \times 3)) - (4)) \times T((T(T(2)) + (T(5)))) \\ 52442 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T((4 + 2)))) + 5) \\ 52443 &:= ((34 \times (T(T(T(4))) + 2) + T(5)) \\ 52445 &:= (((-5) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-2) - T(5)) \\ 52446 &:= (T(T(6)) - (((4 + T(T(4)))^2) \times (-T(5)))) \\ 52448 &:= ((8 \times 4) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 52452 &:= (-((T(2) - T(5))) \times T((T((T(4) + 2)) + (T(5)))) \\ 52458 &:= (((T(T(8)) + 5) \times T((T(4) + 2))) + T(T(5))) \\ 52462 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) - (4)) + 25) \\ 52463 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(42) - (5)))) \\ 52467 &:= (((T(7) + 6) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(2))) + 5) \\ 52468 &:= (T(8) + (((T(T(6)) - (4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52473 &:= (((3^7) \times 4) \times T(T(2)) - (T(5))) \\ 52476 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) - T(2)) \times (-T(5))) \\ 52478 &:= (-((T(T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5)))) \\ 52482 &:= (2 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((2 \times T(5)))))) \\ 52485 &:= ((T((5 \times 8)) \times (4^{T(2)})) + (5)) \\ 52486 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-25))) \\ 52488 &:= (8 \times (T((8/4))^{T(2)+5})) \\ 52495 &:= ((T((-5) + T(9))) \times (4^{T(2)})) + (T(5)) \\ 52497 &:= (((T(7) \times 9) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(2) + T(5)))) \\ 52516 &:= (T(61) + ((T(5)^{T(2)}) \times T(5)) \\ 52526 &:= (((T(T(6))^2) - T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) - T(5)) \\ 52528 &:= (8 \times ((T(2)^{5+T(2)}) + (5)) \\ 52536 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(5) \times T((2 \times 5))) \\ 52542 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) + (2 + T(5))) \\ 52545 &:= (T((T(T(5))/4) \times (T(T(5)) - (2 + 5))) \\ 52554 &:= ((4 - T((T(5) + T(5)))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(5)))) \\ 52563 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) - (2 + T(5)))) \\ 52566 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - (5))) - (-T(2) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 52575 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(7) \times (5^{T(2)})) + (5))) \\ 52578 &:= ((8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) + (2 + 5))) \\ 52584 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times 8) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \\ 52593 &:= ((T((3 \times 9)) - (5)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 52612 &:= (T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52623 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (-6 \times (-T(2) - T(T(5)))) \\ 52625 &:= ((5^{T(2)}) \times (T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + T(5)) \\ 52626 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T((-T(6)) + T((-2) + T(5)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 52628** := $((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(6/2)))) + 5)$
52629 := $((-9) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) + T(5)$
52632 := $(-(T(2)^{T(3)})) + (T(T(6))^{-T(2)+5})$
52634 := $((T(43) \times T(6)) + (2^{T(5)}))$
52636 := $((T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(T(6))) - (2^5)$
52641 := $((T(T(T(-(1-4)))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))))$
52644 := $((4 + (T(4) \times T(6))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + T(5))$
52645 := $((-5) \times T(T(4))) - ((T(6)^2) \times T(T(5)))$
52646 := $(-(T(T(-(T(6)) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(6))^2) - T(T(5))))$
52647 := $(-(T(T(T(7) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(6)) \times (T(2)^5)))$
52662 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)) - T(-((2-5)))$
52663 := $((-3) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(T(6))^2) - (5))$
52664 := $((-4) + T(T(6))) \times ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) - (5))$
52665 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(6) \times T(6) - 2)) - (T(5)))$
52667 := $(-(T(T(7) - (6))) + (-(T(6)^2) \times T(T(5))))$
52668 := $((8 \times T(T(6)))/6) \times T((T(2) + T(5)))$
52673 := $((T(3) \times T(76)) \times T(2)) + (5)$
52675 := $((T(5) + T(7)) \times T((-6) + T((2 \times 5))))$
52695 := $((-5) \times T(9)) - (-(T(6)^2) \times T(T(5)))$
52723 := $((3 \times ((-2) + T(7))^{T(2)}) - (5))$
52725 := $((-T((5 \times 2))) + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times T(5)$
52728 := $((T(T(8)) + (T(2) + (7))) \times T(-(T(2) - T(5))))$
52731 := $((T(-(1) + T(T(3)))) + 7) \times (T(2)^5)$
52732 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(7)) - T((T(2) \times T(5))))$
52734 := $(T(-(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times ((T(7)^2) + T(5))$
52735 := $((T(5) \times T(37)) + 2) \times 5$
52739 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((3+7))) - T(T(-(2) + T(5))))$
52742 := $(-T(2)) + (((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 5)$
52745 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - T((T(T(2)) + T(5))))$
52746 := $(T(6) - ((T(T(4)) - T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times T(5)))$
52749 := $((T(9) \times T((T(4) - (7)))) - T((T(2) + T(5))))$
52752 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-(T(5) - (7))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
52754 := $((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2))) - 5$
52755 := $(5 \times (-5) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 5)))$
52757 := $((-T(7)) \times (-T(57) - T(T(T(2)))) + 5)$
52765 := $((5 + T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - T(2) \times 5$
52766 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - T((7^2) - T(5)))$
52767 := $((T(7) - T((T(6)/7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5))))$
52773 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(((7 \times 2) \times 5)))$
52775 := $((-5) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) - 2) - (5)$
52779 := $(T(T(9)) - (-(T(7) \times T(7))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 5)))$
52782 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(5))))$
52785 := $((T(5) + T(8)) \times T((7+2) \times 5))$
52794 := $((4+9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(5)))$
52795 := $(-5) - ((T(T(9)) - T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
52815 := $((5 \times T((1 + T(8)))) + T(T(2))) \times T(5)$
52822 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(2))) \times (-T(T(8)))) + T(T((2 \times 5)))$
52824 := $((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (8 + T(T(T(2)))) + 5)$
52826 := $((T(6)^2) - 8) \times (2 + T(T(5)))$
52829 := $((T(9) \times T((T(2) \times 8))) - T((-2) + T(5)))$
52832 := $((2 - T((T(3) + T(8)))) \times (-2^5))$
52833 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(((8 - T(T(2)))^5))$
52834 := $((-T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (8 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)$
52836 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))$
52837 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))$
52839 := $((9 + T((3 \times 8))) \times T((T(2) + T(5))))$
52845 := $(T(5) \times ((T(48) \times T(2)) - (5)))$
52848 := $((T(T(8)) + T(4)) \times T((T(8)/T(2)))) + T(T(5))$
52857 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(2))))/5$
52858 := $((8+5) \times (T(T(-(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(5))))$
52866 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(8) - T(2)) \times T(5)))$
52874 := $(T(4) + ((T(7) \times 8) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 5))$
52875 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) - T((T(8)/2))) \times (-T(5)))$
52884 := $(T((4+8)) \times (T(T(8)) - ((T(2) - T(5))))$
52893 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(9)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(-(T(2) - T(5))))$
52895 := $(5 \times ((9 \times T((8 \times T(T(2)))) - 5))$
52896 := $(T(T(T(-(6-9)))) + T(8)) \times (2^5)$
52897 := $(-T(7)) - ((-T(9)) \times T((8 \times T(T(2)))) - 5)$
52905 := $((50 \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 5))$
52915 := $((-5) \times (-1 - T(9)))^2 + T(5)$
52932 := $((-2) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(9)) \times T((T(T(2)) + 5))$
52935 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \times T((9 - T(2)))) + (T(5))$
52938 := $((T((8 \times T(3))) \times T(9)) + (T(2) + T(5)))$
52943 := $((T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times T((9-2))) - 5)$
52947 := $((-T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)))$
52948 := $((T(T(8)) + T(49)) \times T((2+5)))$
52956 := $(-6) \times ((-T(5) - T(T(9))) - (T(T(2))^5))$
52959 := $(9^5) + (T(T((9-2))) \times (-T(5)))$
52962 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(6)) \times (-9 - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
52965 := $((T(5) \times T(T(6))) + (T((9+2)))) \times T(5)$
52983 := $(-T(T(3))) \times (-T((8 \times 9))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 5))$
52986 := $((T((6 \times 8)) \times T(9)) + T((T(T(2)) + 5)))$
52992 := $((2^9) \times T(T(9)))/2 \times 5$
52994 := $((4 + T(T(9))) \times (T(9) + T(T(2)))) + (5)$
52995 := $(-5) \times ((-9) \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) - (T(5))$
53064 := $((4 \times 6) \times T(T(T(03) + 5)))$
53115 := $((T(T((5+1))) - 1) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)$
53122 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (1 - T(T(T(3)))) + 5)$
53123 := $((T(T(T(3)))^2) - T((1 + T(T(3)))) + T(5)$
53124 := $((T((T(4) \times T(2))) + 1) \times (-T(3) + T(T(5))))$
53125 := $((T(5) + 2) \times ((-1) + T(3))^5)$
53126 := $((T(T(6))^2) + 1) - T(T(T(3))) - 5$

- 53145** := $((T(5)^4) - ((-1) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)))$
53165 := $(5 \times (((T(6) + 1)^3) - T(5)))$
53166 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - (13 \times T(5)))$
53196 := $((T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(1 + T(3)))) - (T(T(5))))$
53213 := $(- (T((T(3) + 1))) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53215 := $(5 \times (((1 + T(T(T(2))))^3) - 5))$
53231 := $(- (T((1 + 3))) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53232 := $(- (T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))))^2) - (3 + T(T(5))))$
53233 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((2^3) + T(T(5))))$
53234 := $(- (T(4)) + ((T(T(T(3))))^2) - (- (3) + T(T(5))))$
53235 := $(T((T(5) \times T(3))) \times ((2^3) + 5))$
53236 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((2 + 3) + T(T(5))))$
53237 := $(- (7) + ((T(T(T(3))))^2) - (- (3) + T(T(5))))$
53238 := $((T((T(8) - T(3))) + 2) \times (- (T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
53241 := $((T(T((1 \times 4) + 2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)))$
53242 := $(- ((T(2) - 4)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53243 := $((T(3) - 4) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53244 := $((T(T((-4) + T(4)))^2) - (- (3) + T(T(5))))$
53245 := $(T((T(5) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(3)) \times T(T(5))))$
53246 := $(- ((T(T(6)) + 4)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5))))$
53247 := $((T(T(T(7 - 4)))^2) - (- (T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
53251 := $(T(- ((1 - 5))) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53252 := $((T(T(2)) + 5) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53253 := $(- (3) + T(5) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53256 := $(T(6) - (- ((T(5) - 2)) \times T((T(3) \times T(5))))$
53261 := $(- (1) + (((T(T(6))^2) + T(T(3)) - T(T(5))))$
53262 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(T(6))^2)) + (T(T(3)) \times (-5)))$
53265 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(6)^2) + 3)) - (T(5)))$
53266 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - ((- (2) + T(T(3))) \times 5))$
53267 := $(- (T(7)) + ((T(T(6))^2) - T((T(3) + 5))))$
53268 := $(- (T(T(8))) - ((- ((T(T(6)) + T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53271 := $((T(T(- (1 - 7)))^2) - (T(3) \times T(5)))$
53272 := $((T(2) + T(7)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))))$
53275 := $(- (5) + ((T(T(7) + 2)) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)))$
53277 := $((T(T(7)) + 7) \times ((T(2) \times 3) + T(T(5))))$
53278 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3)) - 5)))$
53279 := $(- (97) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53291 := $(- (T(19)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5))))$
53292 := $(- ((T(T(2)) - (T(9 \times T(2))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
53294 := $(- (4) + (T(9 \times T(2))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
53295 := $(T(5) \times ((T(T(9)) - 2) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(5))))$
53297 := $(- (T(7)) - (T(9) \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-5)))$
53298 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) + ((T(2) \times (T(3)^5)))$
53301 := $(- (T(10)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 5))$
53306 := $(- (60) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 5))$
53315 := $(5 \times (((1 + T(T(3)))^3) + (T(5))))$
53316 := $((T(T(6))^{-1+3}) - (3 \times T(5)))$
53317 := $((T(T(7)) + 1) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(3))) + (5)))$
53318 := $(- (T((8 - 1))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53321 := $(- ((T(T(1 + T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53322 := $((- (T(2)) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53323 := $((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (3 + 35))$
53324 := $(- ((T(T(4)) - T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53325 := $(- ((T(5)^2) \times (T(3) - ((3^5))))$
53326 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2 \times 3))) - 35)$
53327 := $(- ((7^2)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53328 := $(- (8) \times T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53329 := $(- ((T(9) + 2)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53331 := $((T(T(T(1 \times 3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(3) \times 5))$
53332 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 35))$
53333 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (33 - 5))$
53334 := $(- ((4 \times 3)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53335 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(3)) + (5)))$
53337 := $((73 \times (3^{T(3)})) + T(T(5)))$
53338 := $(- (8) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T((3 + 3)))) + T(5)))$
53339 := $(- ((9 \times 3)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 5))$
53351 := $((1 \times 5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53352 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(3))) \times T((- (3) + T(5)))$
53353 := $((T(T(T(3)))^{5-3}) - (3 + 5))$
53354 := $((T(4)/(-5)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 5))$
53355 := $((T(5) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(5)))$
53356 := $((T(T(6))^{(T(5)/3)} - 3) - 5)$
53358 := $((T((T(8) - T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(- ((3 - 5)))$
53359 := $((T(T(- (9) + T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((3 - 5)))$
53361 := $(T(((1 + 6) \times 3)^{-3+5}))$
53362 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(6))^{T(3)/3}) - 5))$
53363 := $(- (3) + ((T(T(6))^{T(3)/3}) + 5))$
53364 := $(4 - ((- (T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(3) - 5)))$
53365 := $(5 - ((- (T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(3) - 5)))$
53366 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + ((3 - 3) + 5))$
53367 := $((T(7) \times T(63)) - T(T(- (3) + T(5))))$
53368 := $(- (8) + ((T(T(6))^{T(3)/3}) + T(5)))$
53369 := $((T(T(T(9 - 6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (3 + 5))$
53372 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(3) + 5))$
53373 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((7 \times 3))) + (- (3) + T(5)))$
53374 := $(- ((T(4) - T(7))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 5))$
53375 := $((T(5) - T(T((7 + 3)))) \times (-35))$
53376 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((7 \times 3))) + (3 \times 5))$
53377 := $((T((- (7) + T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(3)) - 5))$
53379 := $(T(9 - 7) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5)))$
53381 := $((- (1) + T(8)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))$
53382 := $((T(T(- (2 - 8))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(3) + T(5)))$

- 53384** := ((T(4) + 8) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + 5))
53385 := (-T(T(5)) - ((-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (3 + T(T(5))))
53386 := ((-6) + T(8)) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) - 5)
53391 := (T((1 × 9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(5))
53393 := ((3 × 9) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + 5))
53396 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(9 - 3))) + 35)
53397 := (T(T(T(-(7 - 9)))) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(5))
53398 := ((-8) + T(9)) + (T(T(T(3)))⁻³⁺⁵)
53399 := ((T(T(9))/T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(5))
53415 := (-T(T(5)) - ((1 - T((4 × T(T(3)))) × T(5))
53422 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))²) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) - T(5)))
53423 := ((T(T(T(3)))²) + (-4 + T((T(3) + 5))))
53424 := (424 × (T(3) + T(T(5))))
53425 := (-5^{T(2)}) - (T((4 × T(T(3)))) × (-T(5)))
53426 := ((T(T(6))²) + ((T(4) + 3) × 5))
53432 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) - 5))
53433 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (-4 × (-3 - T(5)))
53435 := (-T((5 × T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-35))
53436 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(4) × T(3)) + T(5))
53443 := ((3 + T(4)) × ((4^{T(3)}) + T(5))
53444 := (-4) × (4 + (T(T(4)) × (-3⁵)))
53445 := (-T(5)) - (T(T(4)) × (-4 × (3⁵)))
53448 := ((8 - (T(T(T(4)))/(-4)) × T((T(T(3)) - 5)))
53452 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5) × (-4 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(5)))
53455 := (-5) + (T(54) × T((3 + 5)))
53458 := ((T(8) × T(54)) + ((3 - 5))
53472 := (((2 × T(T(7))) × T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(5)))
53473 := (-((T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-35))
53475 := ((-5) + T(((7 × 4) × 3)) × T(5))
53481 := ((T(T(T((1 + (8/4)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(5)))
53484 := (4 × (T(T(8)) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(3) + T(5))))))
53487 := (7 × (T(T(8)) + (T((T(4) × 3)) × T(5)))
53488 := (8 × (((T(T(8)) × T(4)) + T(T(3))) + 5))
53493 := (((-T(3)) + T(T(9))) × (T(T(4)) - 3) - T(5))
53495 := -((T(T(-(5 - 9))) + (T((4 × T(T(3)))) × (-T(5))))
53496 := (((-6 × 9) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((3 + 5))
53514 := ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) + ((-T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(5)))
53515 := (T(T(T((5 - 1)))) + ((-T(5)) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(5)))
53524 := ((T((4 × T(T(T(2)))) × T(5)) - (T(T(3)) + 5))
53526 := ((T(T(6))²) + ((5 + T(3)) × T(5))
53532 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(5 - 3)) + T(5)))
53534 := ((T((4 × T(T(3)))) × T(5)) - (T(T(3)) - 5))
53535 := ((T(5) × T((T(3) × T(5)) - T(3))) - T(5))
53536 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + (5 × 35))
53542 := ((T((T(T(T(2))) × 4)) × T(5)) - (3 + 5))
53544 := (4 × ((T(T(-(4) + T(5))) × T(3)) + T(T(5))))
53545 := ((T(5) × T((4 × (T(5) + T(3)))) - 5))
53548 := ((T(84) × T(5)) + ((3 - 5))
53562 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) × (-5) + T((T(3) + T(5))))
53565 := ((T(5) × T(((6 × T(5)) - T(3)))) + T(5))
53566 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(6))) + T((T(T(5))/T(3)))) - 5)
53568 := (T(8) × (6 × (5 + (3⁵))))
53577 := ((T(T(7)) × (7 + (5³))) - T(5))
53585 := ((T(5) × T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) + 35)
53586 := (((6 + T(T(8))) + T(5)) × T((-3) + T(5)))
53592 := ((2 - 9) × (T(T(5)) - ((T(3)⁵)))
53595 := ((T((T(5) - (T(T(9)))/(-T(5)))) + 3) × T(5))
53597 := ((T(T(7)) × ((9 × T(5)) - 3)) + 5))
53613 := (T(T(3)) - ((-1) - T(T(6))) × T((T(3) + T(5))))
53622 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))²) + (T(T(6)) + (T(3) × 5))
53625 := ((5 × T((2 + 63))) × 5)
53628 := (((8 - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(5))
53632 := (T(23) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) - 5))
53634 := (T((-4) + T(T(3))) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(5))))
53635 := (-5) - (((T(T(3)) × (-T(6))) - T(3)) × T(T(5)))
53652 := (T((T(2) + T(5))) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(5))))
53654 := ((T(T(T(4)))/5) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(5))
53655 := (T(5) + (((-T(5)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(5)))
53666 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(6))) + T((T(6) + 3))) + 5))
53668 := (((-8) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(6)))) + (T(T(3)) × T(5))
53676 := (T(6) × T((-((7 - 63)) + T(5)))
53677 := ((T(7) × 7) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(5))))
53684 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (((-8) - T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(5)))
53685 := (((T(T(5)) × (T(8) - 6)) - T(T(3))) × T(5))
53694 := (((T(4) × T(9)) + T(6)) × (-T(3)) + T(T(5)))
53712 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 1) × (T(T(7)) × T(3))) + T(T(5)))
53722 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))²) + (T(T(7)) - (3 × T(5))))
53724 := ((T((T(4) + 2)) + T(T(7))) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(5))))
53725 := ((-5) + T(T((T(2) + 7)))) × 35)
53726 := ((T(T(6))²) + (73 × 5))
53732 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7)) - 35))
53736 := (T(T(6)) - ((3 - T((T(7) × 3))) × T(5))
53739 := ((9 × T(T(3))) + (T((T(7) × 3)) × T(5))
53742 := (T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) × ((T(7) + T(3)) + 5))
53743 := ((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) × ((7³) - T(T(5))))
53745 := (T(5) × (T(T(4)) - (T(7) × (-T(3)) - T(T(5))))))
53748 := (T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) - ((7 × T(3)) + 5)))
53755 := (-5) + ((T(T(5)) × T(7)) × (T(T(3)) - 5))
53774 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 7)) - (T(3) + T(T(5))))
53775 := ((T(5) + T(((7 + 7) × T(3)))) × T(5))
53794 := (((T(T(4)) × T(9)) - T(T(7))) × (T(T(3)) + 5))
53795 := (((T(T(T(-(5 - 9)))) × 7) - T(T(3))) × 5)

- 53796 := ((T((T((T(6) - 9)) - (7))) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(5))))
53798 := ((T(T(8))/(-9)) × (-7) + (-T(3)) × T(T(5)))
53799 := ((T(T(9)) × (T(9) + (7))) - (T(3) + T(5)))
53823 := (T(T(3)) × (T(2) + (((8³) × 5)))
53824 := (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) - ((T(83) × T(5))))
53825 := (((T(T(5))/2) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5)
53826 := ((T(T(6))²) + T(((8 - T(3)) × T(5)))
53829 := (((9²) × T(T(8))) + 3) - T(T(5))
53835 := (-5) × ((T(T(3)) × (-8³)) - (T(5)))
53845 := ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(83) × T(5))))
53847 := -((T((7 + T(T(4)))) - (T((T(8) - T(3))) × T(T(5))))
53849 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(4))) - T(T((T(8)/3)))) + 5)
53856 := (T((T(6) - 5)) × (T(8) × (T(3) + 5)))
53862 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6))) + (T(8) + T((T(3) × 5))))
53865 := ((5 × T(6)) + T(83)) × T(5)
53872 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))) × (8 × (T(T(3)) + 5)))
53874 := (((-4) + T(T(7))) + T(8)) × (3 + T(T(5)))
53892 := ((T(T(2)) + (-9) × T(T(8)))) × (T(3) - T(5))
53895 := (((T((T(5) + 9)) × T(8)) - T(T(3))) × 5)
53915 := (T(5) - (T(T(1 + 9))) × (-35))
53922 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))²) + T(((T(9) + 3) - T(5)))
53924 := ((T(T(4)) - T(2)) × (T(T(9)) - ((3 - 5))))
53925 := ((52 × T(T(9))) - (T(T(3)) × (-5)))
53928 := (T(8) × ((-2) + T(T(9))) + T((T(3) × 5)))
53934 := (((T(T(4)) - 3) × T(T(9))) - (T(3))) + T(T(5))
53938 := (-8) - ((T(T(T(3))) - 9) × (-3⁵))
53943 := ((((-3) + T(T(4))) × T(T(9))) + 3) + T(T(5))
53945 := (((T(T(5)) - 4) × T((9 + T(T(3)))) + 5)
53946 := ((T(T(T(T(6 - 4)))) - 9) × (3⁵))
53949 := ((T(9) + 4) × (T(T(9)) + T((T(3) + 5))))
53955 := (((T(T(5)) × (-T(5) - T(9))) - 3) × T(5))
53964 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (-6) + T(T(9))) × T(T(3))) + T(5))
53977 := (-T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) + (T(9) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-5))
53985 := (-T(5)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(9)) + T((T(3) × 5)))
53992 := ((T(T(-(2 - 9))) - 9) × T((T(T(3)) - 5)))
53995 := (-5) - ((T(T(9)) - T((9 × T(3)))) × T(T(5)))
54075 := ((5 × 7) × (T(T(T(04))) + 5))
54115 := (-5) - (-T(11)) × T((T(T(4)) - (T(5))))
54125 := ((T((T(T(5))/2)) × T((1 + T(4)))) + 5)
54135 := ((T((T(T(5))/3)) × T((1 + T(4)))) + T(5))
54156 := (6 × (T(51) + (T(T(T(4))) × 5))
54173 := -((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)) × (-14 - T(T(5))))
54187 := (7 × (T(8) - ((1 + T(T(T(4)))) × (-5)))
54189 := (-T(T(9))) + (T(8) × ((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) - 5))
54222 := (T(T(T(2))) × (2 × ((T(T(2))⁴) - 5))
54223 := (((T(T(T(3))) + 2)²) - T((-4) + T(5)))
54225 := (((-5) + T((2^{T(T(2))}))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(5)
54228 := (((T(T(8)) + 2) × (T(2)⁴)) + T(T(5)))
54234 := (-T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(3))) + 2)^{T(4/5)})
54235 := (-5) - (((T(T(T(3))) × 2) - T(4)) × (-T(T(5))))
54236 := (T(T(6)) - (((T(T(3))^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-5))
54237 := ((T(7) × T((T(T(3)) × T(2)))) - T(T((-4) + T(5))))
54238 := (((8 + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) - T(5))
54245 := ((-T(5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(2) × T(4))) × T(T(5))))
54252 := (T((T(T(2)) + 5)) × (-T(2) + (T(T(4)) × T(5))))
54255 := (((T(T(5)) × T((T(5) × 2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 5)
54264 := ((T(T(4)) - (T(6))) × T((T(T(2)) + (T(4) × 5)))
54265 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(6))²) + (4⁵)))
54268 := (((8 + T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) + T(5))
54272 := (((2 × T(7)) - T(2)) × (4⁵))
54275 := (((T(T(5)) × T((T(7) + 2))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5))
54284 := (((4 × T(T(8))) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))
54285 := ((T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) × T(5))
54288 := (T(8) × (8 - (T(24) × (-5))))
54315 := ((51 + T((T(T(3)) × 4))) × T(5))
54326 := ((6^{T(T(2))}) - ((T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) × 5))
54327 := (-7) × ((T(T(2)) × (-T(3)⁴)) + (T(5)))
54328 := ((T(82) × (T(3) + T(4))) - T(T(5)))
54336 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + (3 × T((T(4) + T(5))))
54356 := (((T(6) - T(5))^{T(3)}) + (T(T(T(4))) × 5))
54362 := (((T(2) + T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(-5))
54366 := ((6 × (T(6)³) - (T(4) × T(T(5))))
54372 := (-T(2)) - ((T((T(7) × 3)) + T(T(4))) × (-T(5)))
54375 := ((T((T((5 + 7)) + T(3))) + T(T(4))) × T(5))
54384 := (-T((4 × 8)) × ((T(T(3)) - 4) - T(T(5))))
54385 := ((T(-(T(5) - T(8))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (4⁵))
54393 := ((-3) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(3)))^{T(4/5)})
54396 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T((9 - 3)))) + (T(45)))
54425 := (((T(5) × T(T(T(2)))) - 4) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(5))))
54432 := ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + ((-4) + T(4))⁵)
54435 := ((T(((5 + T(3)) × 4) × T(T(4))) - (T(5)))
54442 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(4)) × (-T(44))) + 5))
54444 := ((T(T(4)) × T(44)) - T(T((T(4)/5))))
54445 := ((T(((T(5) - 4) × 4) × T(T(4))) - 5))
54447 := (((T(7) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T((4 + 4)))) + T(5))
54465 := ((T(((5 + 6) × 4) × T(T(4))) + (T(5)))
54468 := (T(8) × ((-T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((T(4)/5))))
54477 := ((-T(7)) × (-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (-4) + T(5))
54479 := (-((-9) + T(7))⁴) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(5))))
54488 := (8 × (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-4) + T(5)))
54494 := (((-4) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) - T(T((-4) + T(5))))
54495 := ((T(T(5)) × ((T(9) × T(4)) + 4)) + T(5))

- 54516 := (T(T(6)) × T((1 + (5 × 4))) + (5))
54522 := (T(T(2)) - (T(T(T(2)))) × (-((T(T(5)) - (4)) + T(T(5))))
54525 := (((T(5) × T(2)⁵) - T(4)) × T(5))
54527 := ((-7) - T(-(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))))) × (4 - T(5))
54528 := (8 × (T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(4))) - (T(5))))
54536 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3))) + 5) + (4 × 5))
54537 := (7 × (((T(3)⁵) + T(4)) + (5))
54538 := ((-8) - T(-(T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))) × (4 - T(5))
54566 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(6))) - ((T(T(5)) × (-T(4))) - (5))
54572 := (2 × (T(T(T(7) - T(5)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(5))))
54575 := (5 × ((-T(7)) + T(T((T(5) - (4)))) × 5))
54579 := (((-9) × T(T(7))) × (-T(5))) - T(T(T(T(4)/5))))
54585 := ((T(5) × T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) + (T(45)))
54594 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) - T(T(5))) - T(T((-4) + T(5))))
54595 := (-5) + ((T(T(9) - T(5))) - T(4)) × T(T(5))
54615 := (((T(5) + 1) × T(T(6))) - T(T(4))) × T(5))
54616 := (((T(T(6)) + 1) × T(T(6))) + (4⁵))
54623 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(2)) + T(T(6)))) + (-4 - T(T(5)))
54625 := (((T(5) × T(2)⁶) - T(4)) × 5)
54628 := (-8) - ((T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(6)))) - T((T(4) × 5)))
54633 := (-3) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6)))) - T((T(4) × 5)))
54636 := (((T(T(6)) + 3)⁶⁻⁴) - T(T(5)))
54639 := (-T(9)) - ((T(T(3)) × T(6)) × (-4 - T(T(5))))
54648 := (T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T(6) - ((4 - 5))))
54662 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(6))) + ((6⁴) + 5))
54663 := -((T(T(3)) + ((T(6) × T(6)) × (-4 - T(T(5))))
54682 := (T(2) - ((T(8) × (T(6) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5))
54683 := (-T(3)) + ((T(8) × (-T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5))
54684 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) × T(6)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(5))))
54685 := ((T(T(5)) × T((8 + T(6)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))
54694 := ((T(T(4)) - 9) × ((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))))
54699 := (((T(9) - 9) × (-T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(5))
54717 := ((-T(7)) × (-1 - T((7 + T(T(4)))) + 5))
54725 := (((5 × (T(2)⁷)) + T(4)) × 5)
54726 := ((T(6) × 2) × (T(7) + T((T(4) × 5)))
54732 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T((7 - 4)))) - T(5))
54735 := (-T(5)) × (T(3) - T((7 × T(4)) + T(5)))
54752 := ((T((2 × T(5))) + (7)) × (-4) + T(T(5)))
54756 := ((T(T(6)) + T(-(5 - 7)))^{T(4)/5})
54759 := ((9 × ((T(5) × T(T(7))) - (4))) - (T(5)))
54762 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(67) × 4) + T(5)))
54765 := (-T(5)) - ((T(T(6)) / (-7)) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5))))
54768 := ((T(8) × ((6 - T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))
54779 := (-T(9)) + (T(7) × (T((7 + T(T(4)))) + 5))
54783 := (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(8) × (T(7) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))))
54787 := (-T(T(7))) - ((T(8) × (7 - T(T(T(4)))) - 5))
54792 := -(((T(T(2)) + (-T(9)) × T(T(7))) × T((T(4)/5)))
54793 := ((3 × ((T(9) × T(T(7))) - (4))) - (5))
54795 := (((T(5) × 9) × T((7 × 4))) - T(5))
54822 := -((T((2 × T(T(2)))) + (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))))
54823 := ((T(T(T(3))) / (-T(2))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54824 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(2)) + T((8 × 4)))) / (-T(5))
54825 := (T(5) × T((2 + T((8 + 4))) + (5)))
54828 := (T(8) × (T(2) + (8 × T((4 + T(5))))
54834 := (T((4 × 3)) × T(((8 × 4) + 5)))
54837 := ((-T(7)) × (T(T(3)) - (T(8) × T(T(4)))) - (T(5)))
54842 := ((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54846 := ((6⁴) + (T(84) × T(5)))
54849 := (((-T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(8))) - T(T((-4) + T(5)))
54855 := (-((5 - 58) × T(45))
54857 := (-((T(7) + T(5))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54867 := ((T(7) × (-T(6)) + (T(8) × T(T(4)))) + (T(5)))
54868 := ((8 + T((-6) + T(8))) × (-4) + T(T(5)))
54871 := ((-1 - T(7)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54872 := (((2 + T(7)) + 8)^{T(4)/5})
54878 := ((-T(8)) - T(T(7))) - ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)))
54879 := (-T((T(9) - (7)))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) + 5))
54882 := ((2 × T(T(8))) + (T(84) × T(5)))
54884 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(8)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(4)) - T(T(5))))
54885 := (-((T(5) × T(8))) - ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(5))
54886 := (-((6 + 8)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54887 := ((-7) - T(T(8))) - ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))
54891 := (-((1 × 9)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54894 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) - T((8 + T(T(4)))) - T(5))
54897 := (-T(-(7 - 9))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54899 := (-((9/9)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54915 := (T(5) - (-T(-(1 - 9))) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))
54924 := (4 × (T(T(2)) - (-9) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))))
54925 := (-T((5²))) × (-((T(9) + (4))) - T(T(5)))
54936 := ((T(T(6)) + T(T(3))) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) / 5))
54942 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(9))) / (-T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))))
54944 := (4 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 9) + (-4) - T(T(5))))
54945 := ((T(5)⁴) - (-((9 × 4)) × T(T(5)))
54959 := (((9⁵) - T((9 × T(4)))) + (5))
54974 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(9)) × T(T(4))) - (5))))
54975 := ((T((-5) × (T(7) - T(9)))) + T(4)) × T(5))
54983 := ((T(T(3)) × (T((8 × 9)) - T(4))) + (5))
54988 := (-8) - ((T(8) × (9 - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))
54996 := (((6 + T(9)) × T(T(9))) + T(T((-4) + T(5))))
55056 := (T(T(6)) - T((T(50) / T(5))) × (-T(5)))
55125 := ((5 × T(T(T(2)))) × (T((-1) + T(5))) × 5))
55132 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 1)) + T(55))
55162 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(6))) - (-1) - (T(T(5)) × T(5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 55176 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T(T(7)) + 1) \times (-T(5) - T(T(5)))))) \\ 55184 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) - (T((1 + T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55188 &:= (T(8) \times (-((8 - 1) + T(55))) \\ 55215 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 1) \times T(2 \times T(5))) - T(T(5))) \\ 55216 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 1) \times ((T(2)^5) - (5))) \\ 55221 &:= ((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 5))) + 5) \\ 55224 &:= (-T((4 \times 2))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(55)) \\ 55225 &:= ((T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) - 2) \times (5 \times 5) \\ 55231 &:= ((T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 5))) + T(5)) \\ 55233 &:= (T(3 \times T(3))) \times (-2 + T((5 \times 5))) \\ 55236 &:= (6 \times ((T(T(3)))^{T(2)} - 55)) \\ 55237 &:= ((T(7) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55245 &:= ((T(5)^4) + (T(2) \times T(55))) \\ 55246 &:= (((T(T(6)) + 4)^2) + T(T((5)/5))) \\ 55247 &:= (-T(7)) - (T(T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-5 \times 5))) \\ 55248 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5))/5)) \\ 55257 &:= ((7 \times (T(T(5)) + (T(T(2))^5))) - (T(5))) \\ 55264 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55266 &:= ((6 \times (T(6)^{T(2)}) - T((T(T(5))/5))) \\ 55269 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(6)) + T((T(2) + 5))))/5) \\ 55271 &:= (-1) - (-7 \times ((T(T(2))^5) + T(T(5)))) \\ 55272 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-T(7) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(55)))))) \\ 55275 &:= (T(((T(5) + 7) \times T(2))) \times (5 \times 5)) \\ 55278 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((T(7) \times T(2)) - (5/5))) \\ 55284 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) - (T((T(2) + 5))) + T(T(5))) \\ 55293 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T((9 \times (T(2) + 5)))) + (5)) \\ 55332 &:= (T(2^3)) \times (-3 + T(55)) \\ 55335 &:= (((5^3) - T(3)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) \\ 55336 &:= ((T(T((T(6)/3))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 5))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 55338 &:= ((T(T((T(8)/3))) \times (3 + T(5))) - (T(T(5)))) \\ 55344 &:= ((-4) - (-T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(5))/5)) \\ 55345 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(5)) - 5) \\ 55346 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T((5 \times 5)))) \\ 55349 &:= (-T((9 + 4))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 55362 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((5 \times T(5)))) \\ 55364 &:= (-((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55365 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(3)) - 5)) - (5))) \\ 55368 &:= (T(8) \times (-((6/3) + T(55))) \\ 55373 &:= -(((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) - (T((T(3) \times 5)) \times T(T(5)))))) \\ 55374 &:= (-T((4 + 7))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 55383 &:= (-((T(T(3)) + T(8))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55389 &:= (((9 \times T(8)) \times T((3 + T(5)))) - (T(5))) \\ 55392 &:= (-((T(2)^9)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((5 \times 5)))))) \\ 55394 &:= (-((T(T(4)) - 9)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55395 &:= (((5 \times T((T(9) + T(T(3)))))) \times 5) + (T(T(5))) \\ 55398 &:= ((T((8 \times 9)) \times T(T(3))) + T((5 + T(5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55412 &:= -((T((T(T(2)) + 1)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55414 &:= (T(4) - ((1 - T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55419 &:= ((T((9 - 1)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((T(5)/5))) \\ 55422 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5)/5)) \\ 55424 &:= (-((4^2)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55425 &:= -((T(5) - (T((2 \times 4)) \times T(55))) \\ 55427 &:= ((-7) - T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \\ 55428 &:= (-((T(8)/T(2))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55429 &:= (-((9 + 2)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55432 &:= ((T((2^3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/T(5))) \\ 55433 &:= ((T(T(3))/(-3)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55434 &:= -((T(T((-4) + T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55435 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4)/5)) - 5) \\ 55438 &:= ((-8) + T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \\ 55452 &:= (-((T(2) - T(5))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55455 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(4)/5)))) + T(5)) \\ 55456 &:= ((T(6) - 5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55461 &:= (T((1 \times 6)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55464 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-6)) - 4) \times (-T((T(5)/5))) \\ 55465 &:= (((T(5) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 \times 5)) \\ 55473 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/7) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55475 &:= ((5 \times 7) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55476 &:= (-((6 - 7)) + T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \\ 55482 &:= (T(T(2)) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \\ 55485 &:= (T(5) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + T(5))) \\ 55486 &:= (T(6) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times 5)) \\ 55487 &:= (-T(7)) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (-5 \times T(5)) \\ 55488 &:= ((T(8) \times (8 + T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))))) \\ 55495 &:= (T(T(-(5 - 9))) \times (4^5 - T(5))) \\ 55512 &:= ((-2) - T(T(T(-(1 - 5)))) \times (-T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55524 &:= ((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5) + T(T((T(T(5))/T(5)))))) \\ 55533 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (3^5)) + (T(T(5)) \times (-5))) \\ 55536 &:= (((T(6)^3) - 5) \times T((T(5)/5))) \\ 55543 &:= (((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) - 5) \\ 55544 &:= (-((4^4)) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))))) \\ 55545 &:= (-T(5) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) + (T(T(5)))))) \\ 55548 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(4)/5)) + T(55))) \\ 55575 &:= (T((T(5) + T((7 - 5))) \times T((5 \times 5))) \\ 55576 &:= -(((T(T(6)) - 7) - (T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))))) \\ 55584 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) + ((T(T(5))/5) + T(T(5)))) \\ 55617 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (1 + T((T(6) - 5)))) - 5) \\ 55623 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (2 + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(5))) \\ 55624 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((6 \times 5)) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 55626 &:= (((T(T(6))^2) + (T(65))) + T(T(5))) \\ 55629 &:= (-T((9 \times 2))) + (T((6 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) \\ 55646 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(T(6))) - (5 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

- 55647 := $-(T((7 + T(4))) - (T((6 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))))$
55648 := $(-8) + ((T(T(4))) + 6) \times T((T(T(5))/T(5)))$
55656 := $((T(6) + T(5)) \times (6 + T(55)))$
55659 := $((9^5) + ((T(T(6)) - 5) \times (-T(5))))$
55662 := $(2 \times (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(5))))$
55664 := $-(T((T(4) + 6))) - (T((6 \times 5)) \times T(T(5)))$
55665 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(6))) + (T(5)) \times T(5)$
55666 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - 5)$
55671 := $(T(T(-((1 - 7)))) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 5)))$
55672 := $(-(2^7) + (T((6 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))))$
55692 := $(-(T(2) - T(9))) \times T(((T(6) + T(5)) + T(5)))$
55695 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((9 + T(6)))) - T(T(5))) + T(5)$
55725 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((2 + T(7)))) + (-5) \times T(5))$
55727 := $(-T(T(7))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((7 - 5)^5)))$
55728 := $((T(8)/2) \times (T(T((7 + 5))) + T(5)))$
55734 := $((4 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(5) - T(T(5))))$
55743 := $((T(3)^4) \times (T(7) + T(5))) + T(5)$
55749 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) - T(-((7 - 55)))$
55755 := $((T(T(5)) - T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) + 5))$
55776 := $((6 \times T(7)) \times (7 + T((5 \times 5))))$
55785 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((8 + 7) + T(5))) - T(5))$
55795 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + (T(7) \times T(5)))) - 5)$
55815 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((-1) + T(8) - 5)) + T(5))$
55824 := $((T(T((4 \times 2))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(5))$
55825 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(-(T(T(2)) - T(8)))) + (5 \times 5))$
55826 := $(T(6) + ((T(-((T(T(2)) - T(8)))) \times T(T(5))) + 5)$
55836 := $(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) \times (T((T(8) + 5)) - T(5)))$
55839 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) + (T(85) \times T(5)))$
55842 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times (T(8) + T((5 + T(5))))$
55845 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) \times T((T(8) + 5))) - T(T(5))$
55847 := $(T(T(7)) - ((T(T(4))) \times (-T(8)) - 5/5))$
55864 := $(-4) \times ((-T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + (5 + T(5))$
55867 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(6) + (T(8) \times T(55))))$
55872 := $(T(2) \times ((T(7) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(5))/5)))$
55875 := $((5 + T(T(7))) + T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 5)$
55884 := $(-4) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(8) - T(5))) + T(5))$
55914 := $((T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(5))/5)$
55915 := $(-5) + ((1 + T((T(9) - T(5)))) \times T(T(5)))$
55932 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T((-9) + T(5)))) + 5)$
55935 := $((-((T(5) + 3)) + T(T(9))) \times 55)$
55936 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(9)) + T(55)))$
55939 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-3)) + (9^5 - 5))$
55944 := $(T(T((4 + 4))) \times (9 - (-5) \times T(5)))$
55945 := $((54 \times T(T(9))) + 55)$
55953 := $-(T(T((-3) + T(5))) + (-((9^5) + T(5))))$
55963 := $-(T(T((T(3) + 6))) - ((9^5) - 5))$
55968 := $((8 \times T(6)) + (T((T(9) - T(5))) \times T(T(5))))$
55995 := $((T(5) \times T(((9 \times 9) + 5))) - T(T(5)))$
55997 := $(-T(7)) - (-T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) + T((5 + T(5))))$
55998 := $((-T((8 + 9))) \times T((T(9) + T(5))))/(-5)$
56087 := $(-T(7) - (T((80 + 6)) \times T(5)))$
56115 := $(T(5) \times T((T(T(T((1 + 1)))) + (65))))$
56133 := $((3^{T(3)-1}) \times T((6 + T(5))))$
56168 := $((T(T(8)) - T((T(6) + 1))) \times T((T(6) - 5)))$
56196 := $((-T(6) - T(T((9 + 1)))) \times (-T(6) + T(5)))$
56214 := $((T(T(4)) - 1) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T((-6) + T(5))))$
56217 := $(7 \times (T(T(12)) + T((-T(6)) + T(T(5))))$
56232 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(3))^{T(2)} + T(T(6))) - T(T(5))))$
56238 := $(T(T(8)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + T(T((6 + 5))))$
56244 := $((4 \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)))) - T(T(5))$
56252 := $(2 \times (T(T((5 + 2))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))))$
56253 := $((3^{T(5)/T(2)}) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5))$
56255 := $((5^5) \times T(2)) \times 6 + 5$
56259 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((5 \times 2))) - T((T(6) + T(5))))$
56265 := $((5 + 6)^2) \times T((6 \times 5))$
56268 := $(T(8) \times (T(T(6)) - (-2) \times T((T(6) + T(5))))$
56272 := $((-2) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(2)) \times T(T(6))))/(-5)$
56274 := $((T(T(4)) + T(7)) \times ((T(2) \times T(T(6))) - T(5)))$
56275 := $(-5) + ((T(T(7)) + ((T(2) \times T(6))) \times T(T(5)))$
56287 := $((T((7 + T((T(8)/T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6))))/(-T(5))$
56295 := $((T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) + (T((2 \times T(6)))) \times T(5))$
56322 := $((T(T(T(2)))^2) + T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(5)))$
56324 := $(-T(4) - ((-2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(5)))$
56327 := $(-7) - ((-2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(5))$
56334 := $((4 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(3)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5))$
56337 := $((T(7) \times T((3 \times T(3)))) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))))$
56343 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T((T(3) + T((6 + 5))))$
56344 := $(4 \times ((T(T(4)) + T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - 5)$
56346 := $(T((6 \times T(4))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)) + 5)))$
56348 := $((T(8) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) + 5)$
56349 := $((9 + 4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(5)$
56364 := $((4 \times T(6)) \times (T(36) + 5))$
56379 := $((-9) + T((T(7) - T(3)))) \times T(T(6)) + T(5)$
56383 := $(-T(T(3)) - ((8 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(6)) + 5)))$
56385 := $((T(5) \times T(8) - 3) \times T(6)) \times 5$
56424 := $(-4) \times ((T(T((2 \times 4))) \times (-T(6))) - T(T(5)))$
56425 := $((T((T(5) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times 6) - 5)$
56432 := $(2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))))$
56435 := $((T((T(5) + 3)) \times T(T(4))) \times 6) + 5)$
56439 := $(-T(T((9 + 3))) - (T((T(4) + T(6))) \times T(T(5))))$
56442 := $((T((T(2)^4)) \times (-4) + T(6)) - T(5))$
56445 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(6))) + 5)$

- 56448 := (T((8 + T(T(4)))) × T(-((4 - 6) - 5)))
56463 := -(((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) + (-T(T(4))) × T(T((-6) + T(5))))))
56469 := (((T(T(9)) - 6) × T(T(4))) - 6) - T(T(5)))
56475 := ((T(T(5)) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(6)) × 5))
56478 := ((T(8) × (T(7) + T(T(T(4)))))) + (6 × 5))
56484 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(8)) - ((-4) × T(T(6))) - T(T(5)))
56485 := (((-5) - T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 65
56496 := ((((-6) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) + (T(6))) - T(T(5)))
56498 := ((8 + T(9)) × (T(46) - T(5)))
56535 := ((T(T(5)) × (T(3) + T((5 × 6)))) + (T(5)))
56544 := (T(((4 × 4) + T(5))) × (-6) + T(T(5)))
56565 := (((5 + T(T(6))) × (-T(5))) - T(T(6))) × (-T(5))
56589 := (T(9) - (T(T(8) - 5))) × (6 - T(T(5)))
56616 := -((T(T(6) - 1)) - (T(T(6)) × (T(T(6)) + (T(5))))))
56625 := ((T(T(5)) + T((2⁶) + T(6))) × T(5))
56628 := (T((T(8)/T(2))) × (6 - (-6) × T(T(5))))
56638 := ((8 + T(T(T(3)))) × (6 + T(T(6)))) - 5
56672 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) × T((T(6) + (6 - 5))))
56679 := (((T(T(9)) × T(7)) - (T(6))) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(5))))
56684 := ((T(T(T(4))) - 8) × ((T(6) + T(6)) - 5))
56694 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) - (T(6) × (6 + 5)))
56695 := (((-5) × T(9)) × (-T(6) - T(T(6))) - 5)
56721 := (T(T((1 + 2))) × T((7 + T((6 + 5))))
56726 := ((T(6) × T(-((T(2) - 76)))) + 5)
56734 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 37) - ((T(T(6)) + (T(5))))
56736 := ((T(6) × T(-((3 - 76)))) + (T(5)))
56742 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(4))) - (-7) - (T(T(6)) × 5)))
56748 := ((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(7)) × T((T(6) - 5))))
56755 := ((T((5 × 5)) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - T(T(5)))
56763 := ((T((3 × T(6))) × T(7)) + (T(6) × T(5)))
56775 := (((-5) × T(T(7))) × (-T(7))) - (65))
56784 := ((T((4 + 8)) × T(7)) × (T(6) + 5))
56796 := (-6) × (((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × T(6)) + 5))
56799 := (((T(9) × T(9)) × T(7)) - T(6)) + T(T(5)))
56814 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T((1 + 8)))) - T(T(6))) + T(T(5)))
56818 := (T((T(8) + 1)) + (T(86) × T(5)))
56821 := (((T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) × T(T(6))) - 5)
56823 := ((-3) + T(28)) × (T(6) + T(T(5)))
56826 := (T(T(6)) × ((T(2) + 8) × T(6)) + T(5))
56829 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + (T((T(8) - 6))) × T(T(5)))
56831 := (((T((-1) + T(T(3)))) + T(8)) × T(T(6))) + 5)
56832 := ((2^{T(3)}) × (T((T(8) + 6))) - (T(5)))
56835 := ((T(T(5)) × T(3)) + (T(86) × T(5)))
56844 := (-4) × (((T(4) + T(T(8))) × (-T(6))) - (T(5)))
56847 := (((7 + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) + (T(T(6)) × 5))
56848 := (8 × ((-4) - T(T(8))) + ((6⁵)))
56849 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(4))) - T((-8) + T(6))) + (T(5)))
56856 := (-6) × (((-5) - T(8)) × T(T(6))) - 5))
56862 := ((-T(2)) - T(T(6))) × (-T((8 - 6)⁵))
56867 := (((7 + T(T(6))) × (8 + T(T(6)))) - (T(5)))
56894 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) - (T((T(8) - 6))/T(5)))
56895 := (T(5) - ((-9) - T((T(8) - 6))) × T(T(5)))
56897 := (-T(7)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T((8 - 6) × 5)))
56904 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(09))) - (6 + T(5)))
56914 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T((1 × 9)))) - (6 + 5))
56919 := ((T(T(9)) × T((1 + 9))) - (T(6) - T(5)))
56922 := (-T(2)) - (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(9))))/T(6)) × 5))
56924 := ((T(T(4)) × (2 + T(T(9)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5))))
56925 := (T((T(5) × T(2))) × T((9 + 6) - 5))
56926 := ((T(T((6 - 2))) × T(T(9))) + (6 - 5))
56931 := ((T(T((1 + 3))) × T(T(9))) + (T(6) - T(5)))
56934 := ((T((4 + T(3))) × T(T(9))) + (-6) + T(5))
56937 := (((7 + T(T(T(3)))) + 9) × T(T(6))) - (T(T(5)))
56941 := ((T(T((1 × 4))) × T(T(9))) + (T(6) - 5))
56942 := (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + (6 + 5)))
56943 := (-3) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + (6 + T(5)))
56944 := (T(4) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + (-6) + T(5)))
56945 := (-5) × (-4) + (T(T(9)) × (-6 + 5))
56946 := ((T((6 + 4)) × T(T(9))) + (6 + T(5)))
56947 := (T(7) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) - (T(6) - T(5))))
56949 := ((T(T(9)) × T(T(4))) + ((T(9) - 6) - T(5)))
56951 := ((T(T(-((1 - 5)))) × T(T(9))) + (T(6) + 5))
56952 := ((T((2 + 5)) × 9) × (T(T(6)) - 5))
56954 := ((T(T(4)) × (5 + T(T(9)))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(5))))
56955 := ((55 × T(T(9))) + (6 × 5))
56965 := (-5) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T((-6) + T(5)))
56969 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) × T(9)) - (6 - 5))
56973 := (T(T(3)) - ((T(7) × (-9)) × (T(T(6)) - 5)))
56974 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 9)) - (T(6) - T(5)))
56991 := ((T((1 + 9)) × T(T(9))) + (T((6 + 5))))
56994 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + ((9 × 6) + T(5)))
56995 := (-5) × ((-9) × (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)))) - 5))
56996 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(9)) + (T(6) + 5))
57126 := (((T(6) + T((T(T(2)) - 1))) × T(T(7))) - (T(T(5))))
57132 := ((-T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) - 1))) × T((T(7) - 5))
57134 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-1) - T((7 + T(5))))))
57155 := (T((5 × (T(5) - 1))) × (T(7) - 5))
57159 := (9⁵) + (T((-1) + T(7))) × (-5))
57162 := (T(T(T(2))) × (((6 + 1) × T(T(7))) - T(T(5))))
57168 := (T(8) × ((61 × T(7)) - T(T(5))))
57222 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)}) + (T((T(7) - 5))))
57224 := (((4^{T(T(2))}) × (2 × 7)) - T(T(5)))
57227 := ((T(7) + T((T(2) × T(T(T(2)))))) × T(7)) - 5)
57228 := ((T(8) × (-T(2)) + T((2 × T(7)))) - T(T(5)))

- 57231** := (((T(T((-1) + T(3)))) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) - T(5))
57233 := (((T(T(T(3)))/T(3)))^{T(2)}) × (T(7) + T(5))
57234 := (((-T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))) - 5)
57237 := (((T(7) + T((T(T(3)) × T(2)))) × T(7)) + 5)
57239 := ((T(T(9)) - T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) × T((T(7) - T(5))))
57241 := (((T(T((1 + 4))) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) - 5)
57246 := (((T(T(6) + 4) × (-T(2))) × T(T(7)))/(-5))
57248 := (-8) + (T((4²) × (T(T(7)) + (T(5))))
57249 := (9 × (((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(7)) + 5))
57251 := (((T(15) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) + 5)
57252 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 5) × ((T(2)⁷) + T(5)))
57253 := (-3) + (T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(7)) + (T(5))))
57256 := (T((6 + (5 × 2))) × (T(T(7)) + (T(5))))
57261 := (((T(T(-(1 - 6)))) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) + T(5))
57266 := ((T(T(6) × (T(T(6) + T(T(T(2)))))) - T((T(7) + T(5))))
57267 := (((T(T(7) × T(6)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7) × T(T(5))))
57275 := (T(5) - ((T(T(7) + T(2)) × (T(7) × (-5))))
57276 := (((-T(6) + T(T(7))) + 2) × (T(7) + T(T(5))))
57277 := ((T(T(7) + T((7 + 2))) × (7 + T(T(5))))
57282 := (T(T(2) - (T(T(8) × (-2) × (T(7) + T(5))))
57283 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (8 × (T(2) + T(7)))) - 5)
57284 := (4 × (((8^{T(2)}) × T(7)) - T(5))
57288 := ((T(8) × (-8) + T((2 × T(7)))) + T(T(5)))
57293 := (((T(T(3) + ((T(9)²))) × T(7)) + (5))
57315 := -((T(5) - (T(13) × T((7 × 5))))
57316 := (((T(T(6) - 1) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(7) - T(5))))
57325 := ((T((T(5) × T(T(2)))) × (T(T(3) - (7))) - 5)
57328 := (8 × ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (3 + T(7))) + 5))
57343 := (((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) × (T(T(T(3)) + 7)) - T(5))
57344 := ((T(4) × ((4^{T(3)}) × 7))/5)
57345 := (-T(5) × ((T((T(4) + T(3))) × (-T(7))) - (T(5))))
57349 := (((T(T(9) × T(T(4))) + 3) + T(T(7))) + (T(5)))
57352 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7) + T(T(5))))
57357 := (((T(T(7) - (T(5))) × T(T(3))) × 7) - T(T(5)))
57358 := (-8) + (((T(T(5) + T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(5))))
57366 := ((T(T(6) × T(T(6))) + T(((3 × T(7)) + (5))))
57372 := (((T(T(2) + T(T(7))) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(7) × T(T(5))))
57375 := (-5) × (((-T(73) + T(T(7))) × 5))
57378 := (T(87) + (T((3 × T(7))) × T(5)))
57396 := (T(6) + (T(9) × T(((3 + 7) × 5)))
57399 := (((-9) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T((7 + T(5))))
57431 := ((T(T(T((1 × 3)))) - 4) × T((7 + T(5))))
57432 := (-T(2) - ((T(T(T(3))) + (-T(4) × T(T(7)))) × T(5))
57434 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((3^{T(4)}) - 75)))
57435 := ((T((T(5) + T(3))) + (-T(4) × T(T(7)))) × (-T(5))
57436 := ((T(T(6) × T(T(T(3)))) - ((-T(4) × T(T(7))) - (T(5))))
57438 := ((T(T(8) × 3) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T((-7) + T(5))))
57456 := ((T(6) + T(5)) × T(((T(4) × T(7))/5))
57462 := (2 × (T(T(6)) + ((T(4) × T(75))))
57463 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(4)))) + ((7⁵)))
57464 := -((T(T(4) + (T(T(6) × (4 - T((7 + T(5)))))))
57475 := (-5) × (((T(T(7) + 4) × (-T(7))) - (T(5))))
57477 := ((7 × T(T((7 - 4))) × (T(T(7) - (T(5))))
57484 := (T(T(T(4))) + (84 × T(T((-7) + T(5))))
57485 := (T(5) - ((-T(8) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7) × (-5))))
57488 := (8 × (((T(T(8) × T(4)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(5))))
57492 := (T(T(2) + ((T(T(9) × T(T(4))) + T((T(7) + (5))))
57494 := (-((T(4) + 9) × (T(T(4)) - T(T((7 + 5))))
57495 := ((5 + T((94 - 7))) × T(5))
57525 := (-T((5²))) × (-57 - T(T(5)))
57528 := (T(8) × (2 + T(((T(T(5)) × (-7))/(-T(5))))
57532 := (((T(T(2) + T((T(T(3) - 5)))) × T(T(7))) - (T(T(5))))
57562 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6))) + (T(5) + T(T((T(7) - T(5))))
57564 := ((4 × T(T((6 + 5))) + (T(T(7) × T(T(5))))
57572 := (((-2) + T(T(7))) - (T(5))) × (T(7) + T(T(5)))
57624 := ((T(T(4) - T(T(2))) × T((-6) × (7 - T(5))))
57629 := ((T((T(9) + T(2))) × (T(6) + T(7))) + (5))
57633 := (((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))) - 6) + T((-T(7) + T(T(5))))
57639 := ((T((T(9) + 3)) × (T(6) + T(7))) + (T(5)))
57645 := ((T(5) + T((-4) + T((6 + 7)))) × T(5))
57652 := (T(T((2 + 5))) × ((T(6) × 7) - (5)))
57657 := ((T(T(7) × (-5) + (T(6) × 7)) + (5))
57667 := ((T(7) + (T(T(6) × T(T(6)))) + T((-T(7) + T(T(5))))
57672 := ((T((2 × T(7))) + (6)) × T((-7) + T(5)))
57673 := (T(T(3) - (T(T(7) × ((T(6) × (-7) + (5))))
57675 := (-5) - ((T(T(7) + (6)) × (T(7) × (-5)))
57679 := (T(T(9) + ((7 + T(T(6)))⁷⁻⁵))
57684 := (((T(T(4) × 8) - T(T(6))) × T((T(7) - (5))))
57687 := (-7) × (((-T(8) × T(T(6))) + (75)))
57722 := ((T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T(7)) - T(T((T(7) - T(5))))
57729 := ((T(T(9) × (2 × T(7))) - T(T(T(T((7 - 5))))
57736 := (-T(T(6)) - ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)))) × (-T((T(7) - T(5))))
57743 := ((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(4) × T(7))) × (-7) + T(T(5)))
57744 := (((T(4) × T(T(4))) - T(T(7))) × (T(T(7) - (5)))
57764 := ((4 × T(T(6))) - (T(T(7) × (T(7) × (-5))))
57765 := (T(5) × ((-T(6) - T(T(7))) + T((-T(7) + T(T(5))))
57772 := ((T(T(2) - (-7) × T(7)) × (T(T(7) - T(T(5))))
57783 := (T((-3) + T(8)) × (T(7) + 75))
57785 := (T((5 + 8) × (T((T(7) + (7))) + (5)))
57792 := (((T(2) + T(9)) × T(7)) × (T(7) + T(5)))
57794 := (-4) - (T((T(9) - (7))) × (-T((7 + 5))))
57798 := (T((T(8) + (9 - 7))) × T((7 + 5)))
57816 := ((T(6) + 1) × T((T(8) × (7 - 5))))

- 57822 := (T(T(2)) - T((2 × T(8))) × (-7) - T(5)))
57825 := ((T(5)²) × ((T(8) × 7) + (5)))
57826 := (T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + (T(87) × T(5)))
57827 := (-T(7)) - T((T(T(T(2))) + T(8))) × (-7 × 5)))
57834 := (T((-4) + T(T(3))) × T(-((8 - (7 × 5))))
57844 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((-4) × T(8)) × (T(T(7)) - T(5)))
57855 := (((5 - T(T(5))) + T(T(8))) × (7 × T(5)))
57876 := ((6 × 7) × T(((T(T(8)) - T(T(7)))/5)))
57877 := (((T((T(7) + T(7))) × T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(5)))
57878 := ((T(T(8)) + (7)) × (8 + T((7 + 5))))
57882 := ((T(2) + T((T(8) + T(8)))) × (7 + T(5)))
57885 := (((-5) + T(8)) + T(87)) × T(5))
57888 := (T(8) × ((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) + T((T(7) - (5))))
57889 := (((T(T(9)) × 8) - 8) × 7) - (T(5)))
57893 := (((T(3) × 9) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (5))
57897 := ((7 × 9) × (T(T(8)) + T((7 + T(5))))
57925 := (-5) - (2 × ((T(T(9)) × (-T(7))) + (T(5))))
57927 := (((T(7) × 2) × T(T(9))) - (T(7) + (5)))
57936 := (((T(6)³) - T(9)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(5))))
57937 := (((7 + T(T(T(3)))) - 9) × T((7 + T(5))))
57938 := (((8 + (3 × T(9))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(5)))
57942 := (T(T((2 × 4))) × (9 + T((7 + 5))))
57945 := (((T(T(5 + 4))) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - (T(5)))
57947 := ((T(7) × ((T(T(4)) × T(9)) - T(T(7)))) + (T(5)))
57948 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) × (T(7) + (5)))
57955 := (((T(T(5)/T(5)) × T(T(9))) × 7) - (5))
57972 := ((2 × T(7)) × T(T(9))) + ((7 + 5))
57974 := ((T(4) × ((-T(7)) × T(T(9))) - (7)))/(-5))
57975 := (((-((5 - 7)) × T(T(9))) × T(7)) + (T(5)))
57985 := (-T(5)) - (8 × ((T(T(9)) × (-7)) - (5)))
57986 := (T(6) - (((-8) × T(T(9))) × 7) - (5))
57996 := (T(6) - (((T(T(9)) + T(T(9))) × (-T(7))) - (T(5))))
58095 := ((T(5) × T(90)) - (T(T(8)) × 5))
58125 := ((5^{T(2)}) × T(((1) + T(8)) - (5)))
58164 := (((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) - 1)) × (-T(T(8))))/(-T(5)))
58173 := (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(7) + 1)) × T(T(8))))/(-5))
58177 := (-7) × ((T(T((7 - 1))) × (-T(8))) + (5))
58179 := ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × (-((1 + 8)) - T(T(5)))
58207 := (((-7) × T(T(T(T(02)))) × (-T(8))) - 5)
58212 := ((T(21) × T(2)) × (-T(8) + T(T(5))))
58217 := (((-7) × T(T(T((1 + 2)))) × (-T(8))) + 5)
58225 := (-T(5)) - (T((2^{T(T(2))}) × (-T((-8) + T(5))))
58227 := ((T(7) × T((2^{T(T(2))}))) - (8 + 5))
58229 := ((9^{2+T(2)}) - T((8 × 5)))
58233 := (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (T(2) × (T(8) - T(T(5))))))
58236 := ((T(6) + T((T(T(3)) - 2))) × T((8 + T(5))))
58239 := (9 × (3 - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T((-8) + T(5))))))
58263 := (((3^{T(6-2)}) - T(T(8))) - T(T(5)))
58275 := (T(((T(T(5)) + T(7))/2)) × (T(8) - T(5)))
58279 := ((9 × ((T(7) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8)) - 5)
58289 := ((T(9) × (T(8)²)) - (T(8) - (5)))
58296 := (((-6) - T(T(9))) × (-2)) × T((-8) + T(5)))
58297 := (((T(7) × 9) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (85))
58298 := ((T((T(T(8))/9)) × T(T(T(2)))) + (8 + T(5)))
58317 := (7 × (((-1) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(8))) + T(5))
58331 := ((T((1 + T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (8 - T(T(5))))
58332 := (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(3)))) - (-8) × T(5))
58335 := (T(5) × (T(T(T(3))) - (-3) - T(85)))
58344 := (44 × T((T((3 + 8)) - T(5))))
58345 := (((5 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-38)) + T(5))
58364 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (-6) × (-T(3)) - (T(T(8)) × (-T(5))))))
58365 := (((-5) × T(6)) + (T(3) × T(T(8)))) × T(5))
58368 := ((T((8 + T(6))) + T(T(3))) × (8 + T(T(5))))
58373 := -((T(T(T(3))) + ((7 - T(T(3))) × T(T((8 + 5))))))
58374 := (((T(T(T(4))) - 7) × 38) + (T(T(5))))
58395 := ((T(59) × (-3) + T(8)) - T(5))
58398 := -((T(T(8)) - ((9 × 3⁸)) + T(5)))
58422 := ((-T(2)) - (-2) × T(T(4))) × (T(T(8)) - T(T(5)))
58424 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) × (-4) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(5))))))
58425 := (-T(5)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(((T(T(4)) × 8)/5)))
58428 := (T(8) × ((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) + (85))
58443 := (-((3 - (4⁴))) × T((T(8) - T(5))))
58444 := (4 × ((T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - 5))
58457 := (7 × ((5 × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)) - (T(5))))
58462 := (-2) - (-T(6)) × ((4 × T(T(8))) + T(T(5)))
58464 := (T(T(T(-((4 - 6)))) × ((4 × T(T(8))) + T(T(5))))
58465 := -((T(5) - ((6 + T(4)) × T(85)))
58472 := (T(2) - ((T(T(7)) × (-4) × T(8)) - (5)))
58473 := (-T(3)) - ((T(T(7)) × (-4) × T(8)) - (T(5)))
58476 := (((T(T(6)) × (-7)) - (4)) × (-T(8))) + T(T(5))
58477 := (T(7) - ((T(T(7)) × (-4) × T(8)) + (T(5))))
58478 := ((T(T(8)) × (-7)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(8) + (5))))
58479 := (((T(9) - 7) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(8) + (5)))
58485 := (-T(5)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) + (85))
58487 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(8) × 4)) + (8 + T(5)))
58488 := ((T(T(8)) × ((8 × T(4)) + 8)) - T(T(5)))
58492 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × 9) + T(4)) × T((-8) + T(5)))
58493 := ((T(T(3)) × T((T(9) + (4)))) + (8⁵))
58497 := ((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) × (-T((4 + 8)) + T(5)))
58509 := ((9⁰⁵) - (T(8) × T(5)))
58522 := -((T(T(2)) + ((2 - T(T(5))) × T((T(8) - (5))))))
58524 := (-4) - ((2 - T(T(5))) × T((T(8) - (5))))
58525 := (5 × ((T(25) × T(8)) + (5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 58528 &:= (((-8) + T(T(2))) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(8) - (5))) \\ 58536 &:= -(6^3) \times (5 - T((8 + T(5)))) \\ 58545 &:= (((-T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-T(5))) - T(T(8)) \times 5 \\ 58547 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5)) + (-8) + T(5))) \\ 58548 &:= ((8 + (4 \times T(5))) \times T((T(8) + (5)))) \\ 58553 &:= (3^{5+5}) - T((T(8) - (5))) \\ 58563 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(((6 \times 5) - 8))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 58566 &:= ((T(6) + 65) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(5)))) \\ 58568 &:= (8 \times (((6 + 5) \times T(T(8))) - (5))) \\ 58584 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(5))) \times (-8)) / (-5) \\ 58594 &:= (-T(4)) - (-((9 + 5) \times T(T(8 + 5)))) \\ 58597 &:= (-7) - (-((9 + 5) \times T(T(8 + 5)))) \\ 58619 &:= ((T(91) \times (6 + 8)) + T(5)) \\ 58621 &:= (T((T(T(1 + T(2)))) + 6)) \times (T(8) - (5)) \\ 58623 &:= (((T(32)/6) \times T(T(8))) + (T(5))) \\ 58624 &:= ((-4) - (-2) \times T(T(6))) \times (8 + T(T(5))) \\ 58629 &:= (-T(9)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)) + (8 + T(5)))) \\ 58635 &:= (-5) \times (3 - (T(68) \times 5)) \\ 58638 &:= (-T(8)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)) + (8 + T(5)))) \\ 58642 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(T(4)) + (6))) \times (-T(8) - (5)))) \\ 58643 &:= (3^{T(4)}) - T(((T(6) - 8) + T(5))) \\ 58645 &:= (((T(5) + T(4)) \times T(68)) - (5)) \\ 58648 &:= (8 \times ((-T(4) - T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + (5)) \\ 58664 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + (8 + T(5)))) \\ 58665 &:= ((-5) + T(((T(T(6))/T(6)) \times 8)) \times T(5)) \\ 58667 &:= (-7) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + (8 + T(5)))) \\ 58674 &:= (T(T(T(-(4 - 7)))) \times (T(T(6)) + (8 + T(5)))) \\ 58688 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(8) + T(6)))) - T((8 \times 5))) \\ 58692 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \times (-68 + 5)) \\ 58695 &:= (-5) \times (-9) - (T(68) \times 5) \\ 58697 &:= (-T(7)) - ((9 \times T((T(6) + 8))) \times (-T(5))) \\ 58717 &:= (71 \times (7 + T((8 \times 5)))) \\ 58722 &:= (-T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(7)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(5)))) \\ 58725 &:= (((T(5) - T(T(2))) \times T((-7) + T(8))) \times T(5)) \\ 58752 &:= (((T(T(2))^5) \times 7) - (-T(8) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 58765 &:= (((5 - T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(8)))) + (5)) \\ 58773 &:= (3^{T(T(7)/7)}) - T((8 + T(5))) \\ 58785 &:= (T(5) \times (T(87) + T((8 + 5)))) \\ 58788 &:= (T(((8 \times 8) + 7)) \times (8 + T(5))) \\ 58795 &:= (((T(5) + T(T(9))) \times (7 \times 8)) - (5)) \\ 58815 &:= ((5 + T((1 \times 88))) \times T(5)) \\ 58824 &:= ((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(88) \times T(5)))) \\ 58825 &:= (-5) - ((T(T(2)) + T(88)) \times (-T(5))) \\ 58829 &:= ((9^2) + 8) \times (T(T(8)) - (5)) \\ 58842 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((4 \times 8))) + (T(T(8)) \times 5)) \\ 58848 &:= ((-84) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(5)) \\ 58855 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((T(5) \times T(88)) - (5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58866 &:= ((T(6) \times 6) + (T(88) \times T(5))) \\ 58872 &:= (((T(T(2 \times T(7))) + T(8)) \times T(8)) + T(T(5))) \\ 58873 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (7 \times T(8))) + ((T(T(8)) - (5)))) \\ 58878 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((-7) \times T(8)) \times T((T(8) - T(5)))) \\ 58884 &:= ((4 \times T(8)) + (T(88) \times T(5))) \\ 58896 &:= (T(6) + ((9 + T(88)) \times T(5))) \\ 58905 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(09))) \times (T(8) + T(5))) \\ 58923 &:= -(((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) - (((T(9) - T(8))^5))) \\ 58926 &:= (T(6) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-((9 + 8) \times T(5)))) \\ 58929 &:= (((9^{T(T(2))})/9) + (-8) \times T(5)) \\ 58935 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(3) + ((T(9) - T(8))^5))) \\ 58938 &:= ((T(T(8))/(-T(3))) + (((T(9) - T(8))^5)) \\ 58944 &:= -((T((T(4) + (4))) - (((T(9) - T(8))^5))) \\ 58946 &:= (((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) + (T(8) + (5)) \\ 58949 &:= ((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (((T(9) - T(8))^5)) \\ 58963 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T((T(6) - 9))) \times T(8)) - (5)) \\ 58965 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) + T(85)))) \\ 58968 &:= ((T(8) \times T(6)) \times T(((9 + 8) - 5))) \\ 58982 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times T(T(9))) - (8 + 5)) \\ 58983 &:= -((T((3 + 8)) - ((T(9) - T(8))^5)) \\ 58992 &:= (-T(2)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-((9 \times 8) + T(5)))) \\ 58994 &:= -(((T(4) + T(9)) - ((T(9) - T(8))^5)) \\ 58995 &:= (T((5 \times 9)) \times ((9 \times 8) - T(5))) \\ 58997 &:= ((-7) - T(9)) + ((T(9) - T(8))^5) \\ 59021 &:= -((T((1 + T(T(2)))) - (09^5)) \\ 59022 &:= -(((T(2)^{T(2)}) - (09^5)) \\ 59023 &:= -((T(3) + ((20 - (9^5)))) \\ 59024 &:= ((-4) - T(T(T(2)))) + (09^5) \\ 59026 &:= -((T(6) + ((2 - (09^5)))) \\ 59027 &:= ((-T(7)) + T(T(2))) + (09^5) \\ 59028 &:= -((T((8 - 2)) - (09^5)) \\ 59042 &:= ((T(2) - T(4)) + (09^5)) \\ 59043 &:= (((3^{T(4)}) + 09) - T(5)) \\ 59046 &:= -((T((6 - 4)) - (09^5)) \\ 59054 &:= (T(4) - ((5 - (09^5)))) \\ 59055 &:= (T((T(5)/5)) + (09^5)) \\ 59057 &:= ((-7) + T(5)) + (09^5) \\ 59059 &:= (T((9 - 5)) + (09^5)) \\ 59064 &:= (T(-((T(T(4)) - (60)))) + (9^5)) \\ 59065 &:= ((-5) + T(6)) + (09^5) \\ 59077 &:= (T(7) + (((7 \times 0) + 9)^5)) \\ 59078 &:= (T(8) - ((7 - (09^5)))) \\ 59082 &:= -(((T(2) - T(8)) - (09^5)) \\ 59092 &:= ((-2) + T(9)) + (09^5) \end{aligned}$$

- 59104** := $(T(T(4)) + (((0 \times 1) + 9)^5))$
59112 := $-(((T(2) - T(11)) - (9^5)))$
59114 := $(T((T(4) + 1)) - ((1 - (9^5))))$
59115 := $(T((T((5 - 1)) + 1)) + (9^5))$
59124 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) - (1 - (9^5)))$
59126 := $(T((6 \times 2)) - (1 - (9^5)))$
59127 := $(T(((7 + T(T(2))) - 1)) + (9^5))$
59128 := $(T((T(8)/T(2))) + (1 + (9^5)))$
59133 := $((3 \times T((T(3) + 1))) + (9^5))$
59134 := $((4 \times T(T(3))) + (1 + (9^5)))$
59136 := $(T(T(6)) \times ((3 + 1)^{9-5}))$
59139 := $((9 \times T((3 + 1))) + (9^5))$
59143 := $((3^{T(4)}) - (1 - 95))$
59149 := $((T(9) + T(T(4))) + ((1 \times 9)^5))$
59152 := $((-2) + T((T(5) - 1))) + (9^5))$
59153 := $((T(T(3)) \times 5) - ((1 - (9^5))))$
59154 := $(T((T(4) + (5 - 1))) + (9^5))$
59155 := $(T(T(5)) - (T(5) - (1 + (9^5))))$
59157 := $((-T(7)) + T((T(5) + 1))) + (9^5))$
59159 := $((-9) + T(T(5))) - ((1 - (9^5)))$
59163 := $((-T(3)) + T(T((6 - 1)))) + (9^5))$
59168 := $(T((T(8) - T(6))) - ((1 - (9^5))))$
59169 := $(T((9 + 6)) + ((1 \times 9)^5))$
59175 := $(T(T(5)) + ((7 - 1) + (9^5)))$
59185 := $(T(((T(T(5))/8) + 1)) + (9^5))$
59202 := $(T((20 - T(2))) + (9^5))$
59214 := $((T(T(4)) \times (1 + 2)) + (9^5))$
59217 := $((T(7) \times T((1 + 2))) + (9^5))$
59231 := $((T(13) \times 2) + (9^5))$
59232 := $((T(2) \times (T(T(3)) + ((T(2)^9)))) + T(T(5)))$
59233 := $((-T(3)) + T((T(T(3)) - 2))) + (9^5))$
59235 := $((T(5) + T((T(3) \times T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59237 := $-((T(7) - ((T(3)^{T(2)}) + (9^5))))$
59238 := $((-T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) - (9^5))$
59239 := $(T((T((9 - 3)) - 2)) + (9^5))$
59243 := $((3^{T(4)}) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times 9) + 5))$
59244 := $(((-T(4)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(2))) + (9^5))$
59245 := $((T((T(5) + 4)) + T(T(2))) + (9^5))$
59246 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59247 := $((T((7 + 4)) \times T(2)) + (9^5))$
59248 := $((-(8 \times 4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59249 := $(((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times (-2)) + (9^5))$
59252 := $((T(T((2 + 5)))/2) + (9^5))$
59253 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((T(5)^2) + (9^5))))$
59255 := $((-(5 \times 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59257 := $((-(T(7) - 5)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59259 := $((T((9 + 5)) \times 2) + (9^5))$
59261 := $(T((-1) + T(6)) + ((2 + (9^5))))$
59262 := $-((T(2) - ((6^{T(2)}) + (9^5))))$
59264 := $(((-T(4)) + T(T(6))) - T(T(2))) + (9^5))$
59265 := $((-T(5)) + T(T(6))) + ((T(2)^{9-5}))$
59267 := $((T(7) + T((T(6) - 2))) + (9^5))$
59268 := $((T(8) \times 6) + T(2)) + (9^5))$
59269 := $((T(9) - 6)^{T(2)} - T(9) - 5)$
59271 := $((T(T((1 + 7)))/T(2)) + (9^5))$
59273 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(7)))/(-2)) - (9^5))$
59274 := $((T((4 + T(7))) + T(T(2))) \times (-9) + T(T(5)))$
59275 := $((-5) + T((7 \times T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59276 := $(T(T(6)) + ((-7) + T(2)) + (9^5))$
59277 := $(T((-7) + T(7)) - (T(2) - (9^5)))$
59292 := $((T(2) \times (9^2)) + (9^5))$
59294 := $((-T(T(4))) + T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) + (9^5))$
59295 := $((T(5) + T(T((9 - T(2)))))) + (9^5))$
59297 := $((-(T(7) - T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (9^5))$
59314 := $((T(T(4)) + T((-1) + T(T(3)))) + (9^5))$
59319 := $((T(9) \times T((1 \times 3))) + (9^5))$
59322 := $-(((T(2) - T(23)) - (9^5)))$
59324 := $((T(T(4)) \times (2 + 3)) + (9^5))$
59325 := $(T((T(5) + (2^3))) + (9^5))$
59328 := $((T(8) + T(2))^3 + (T(9)/5))$
59329 := $((T(9) - T(T(2)))^3 + T((9 - 5)))$
59334 := $((T(T(4)) + 3) \times (T((-3) + T(9))) + T(T(5)))$
59335 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(3))/3))) + (9^5))$
59338 := $((8^3) + (T(T(3)) \times T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))))$
59342 := $((2 + T(T(4))) \times (T(3) + T(T(9)))) + 5)$
59343 := $(T((T(3) \times 4)) - (T(3) - (9^5)))$
59344 := $((T((4 + T(T(4))))/T(3)) + (9^5))$
59345 := $((5 \times T(T(4))) + T(T(3))) + (9^5))$
59346 := $(T((6 \times 4)) - (3 - (9^5)))$
59349 := $(((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times (-3)) + (9^5))$
59354 := $((T((4 \times T(5)))/T(3)) + (9^5))$
59355 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) - 9) \times 5)$
59357 := $((T(7) \times (5 + T(3))) + (9^5))$
59358 := $((8 + 5) \times (T(3) + T(95)))$
59364 := $((4 \times T(6)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (9^5))$
59367 := $(7 \times (T(T((6 + T(3)))) - (-T(9)) \times T(T(5))))$
59369 := $((T(9) - 6)^3 + T(9) + 5)$

- 59372** := $((-2) + T((T(7) - 3))) + (9^5)$
59374 := $(T(((4 \times 7) - 3)) + (9^5))$
59382 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(8)))/(-T(3)) + (9^5)$
59384 := $(-(4^8) - ((-T(3)) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(5)))$
59385 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(8) \times T(3)) + (9^5))$
59388 := $((T(8) \times T((T(8)/3) + T(9))) - T(T(5)))$
59393 := $((-3) + T(T(9)))/3 + (9^5)$
59395 := $((-5) + T(9)) \times T((T(3) \times 9)) - (5)$
59396 := $((-6) - T(T(9)))/(-3) + (9^5)$
59411 := $(11 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59415 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((1 + T(4)) \times T(9))) + (T(5)))$
59417 := $(T((T(7) - 1)) - (T(4) - (9^5)))$
59418 := $((-T(T(8))) + T(T((-1) + T(4)))) + (9^5)$
59421 := $(T(T((1 + 2))) + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59422 := $(22 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59423 := $(T(3^{T(2)})) - (4 - (9^5))$
59424 := $((4 \times T(T(2))) + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59425 := $((5^2) + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59427 := $(T(((T(7) + T(2)) - 4))) + (9^5)$
59433 := $(33 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59434 := $((T(T(4)) \times (3 + 4)) + (9^5))$
59436 := $((6 \times T(3)) + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59439 := $((T(9) - T(3)) \times T(4)) + (9^5)$
59455 := $(55 \times T((-4) + T(9)) + (5))$
59457 := $((-7) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \times 9 + T(T(5))$
59459 := $(T(T(9)) - ((5^4) - (9^5)))$
59463 := $((3 \times T(6)) + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59464 := $((T(46) \times T(T(4))) + (T(9)/5))$
59465 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(6) + T(4)))) - T(T(9 - 5)))$
59466 := $(66 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59469 := $((T((9 + T(6))) - 4) \times (9 + T(T(5))))$
59472 := $(T(2) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (-9 - T(T(5))))$
59475 := $(((-5) + T(T(7))) \times T(4)) - T(9) \times T(5)$
59476 := $((T(6) + T((7 \times 4))) + (9^5))$
59477 := $(77 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59479 := $(T(9) - ((-7) \times T(T(4))) - (9^5))$
59483 := $(-T(3)) - ((-8) \times T(T(4))) - (9^5)$
59484 := $(T((T(T(4)) - (T(8) - T(4)))) + (9^5))$
59485 := $((5 - T(T(8))) \times (T(4) \times (-9))) - (5)$
59487 := $(T(T(7)) + ((8 \times 4) + (9^5)))$
59488 := $(88 + ((T(T(4)) \times 9) \times T(T(5))))$
59493 := $((T(3) - ((T(9) \times T(4)) + (9^5)))$
59495 := $((T(T(5)) \times 9) \times T(T(4))) + (95)$
59496 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) \times ((T(T(4)) - 9) - T(T(5))))$
59497 := $((-7) \times (-9 - T(T(4)))) + (9^5)$
59499 := $(9 \times (((9^4) + T(9)) + (5)))$
59514 := $((T(4) - 1)^5 + T((T(9) - T(5))))$
59515 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(((1 - T(5)) + T(9)))) - (5)$
59532 := $(-T(2)) - (-T(T(3))) \times (-T(5) + T((-T(9) + T(T(5))))$
59534 := $((T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(5))) + (9 + 5))$
59535 := $((-T(53)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9)))) \times T(5)$
59538 := $(-T(T(8))) - ((T(T(3))) \times (-5)) - (9^5)$
59544 := $((T(T(4)) \times (4 + 5)) + (9^5))$
59545 := $(T((T((T(T(5))/4)/T(5))) + (9^5))$
59547 := $(T((-T(7)) + T(T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) + (9^5))))$
59549 := $(9 \times T(T(4))) + (5 + (9^5))$
59553 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)))/5) + (9^5)$
59556 := $(T(6) \times (T(5 \times T(5))) - (9 + 5))$
59557 := $(7^5 - (-T(5)) \times T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))))$
59559 := $(T(9) + T((T(5) + T(5)))) + (9^5)$
59565 := $((5 + 6) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (T(5))))$
59572 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(5)) + (9^5)$
59577 := $((T(T(7)) \times 7) - 5) \times T((-9) + T(5))$
59582 := $(2 \times ((T(8) - 5)^{T(9)/T(5)}))$
59583 := $(-T(3) - ((T(8) \times T(5)) + (9^5)))$
59598 := $((T((T(8) - 9)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T((-9) + T(5))))$
59622 := $((T(2) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(6) \times T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))))$
59625 := $((T(5)^2) \times ((6 \times T(9)) - 5))$
59628 := $((T(8) \times T((T(2) + ((6 \times 9)))) + T(T(5)))$
59637 := $((7 + T(T(3))) \times T(6)) + (9^5)$
59642 := $((-2) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) + (9^5))$
59644 := $(T((T(4) + ((4 \times 6)))) + (9^5))$
59645 := $((T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6) - T(9))) + 5)$
59646 := $(T(T(6)) - ((T(T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(5)))$
59647 := $(-T(7)) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(9))) \times (-5))$
59649 := $((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times (-6) + (9^5)$
59652 := $(T(2) \times ((T(T(5 + 6))) \times 9) - (T(5)))$
59654 := $((T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + (9^5))$
59655 := $((T(T(5)) \times 5) + ((6 + (9^5))))$
59665 := $((T((T(5) - 6)) \times T((6 + T(9)))) - (5)$
59675 := $((T((57 - 6)) \times T(9)) + (5))$
59677 := $((T(T(7))/7) \times (-6 + T(T(9)))) - (5)$
59678 := $((-8) + T(T(7))) + T(T(6)) + (9^5)$
59679 := $((T(9) \times (-7) + T(6))) + (9^5)$
59682 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-8 + T(((6 + 9) \times 5))))$
59684 := $((-T(4)) + T(T(8))) - (T(6) - (9^5))$
59685 := $((-T(5)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-6)) + 9) - T(T(5)))$
59687 := $((-7) + T(T(8))) - (T(6) - (9^5))$
59688 := $(T(8) \times (T((8 \times 6) + 9)) + (5))$
59692 := $((T(2) \times 9) \times T((T(6) + T(9)))) - (5)$

- 59694** := $((T((4 \times 9)) - T(6)) + (9^5))$
59695 := $((-5) \times ((-9) \times T((6 + T(9)))) - (5))$
59696 := $(T(6) - ((-T(9)) \times T((6 + T(9)))) - (5))$
59697 := $((-T((-T(7) - T(9)))) - (T(6) \times T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))))))$
59703 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (07 - T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))))$
59708 := $(T(T(8)) - (07 - (9^5)))$
59712 := $((-T(2)) + T(T((1 + 7)))) + (9^5)$
59715 := $(T(T((T(5) - (1 \times 7)))) + (9^5))$
59722 := $(T(T((2^{T(2)}))) + ((7 + (9^5))))$
59727 := $((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7))) + (9 \times 5)$
59728 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) + ((7 + (9^5))))$
59737 := $((7 \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((9 - 5)))$
59742 := $(T(2) \times ((T(T((4 + 7))) \times 9) + T(5)))$
59745 := $((T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))$
59748 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 7)) + T(95))$
59749 := $((-T(9) - T(T(4))) \times (-7)) + (9^5)$
59752 := $(T(2 + (5 \times 7))) + (9^5)$
59755 := $(T((T(T(5))/5)) + ((T(T(7)) + (9^5))))$
59758 := $(T(T(8)) + ((T(5) + T(7)) + (9^5)))$
59763 := $((T(T(3)) \times (6 + T(7))) + (9^5))$
59764 := $((T(T(4)) \times (6 + 7)) + (9^5))$
59766 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + (7 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))))$
59768 := $(8 \times (T(T(6)) - ((-7) \times T(T(9))) + (5)))$
59775 := $((-T(5) + T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5)))$
59783 := $(T(38) - ((7 - (9^5))))$
59784 := $(T((T(T(4)) - 8)) \times ((-7) + T(9)) + T(5))$
59785 := $((T(5) + T(T(8))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T((9 - 5)))$
59832 := $((T(2) + T((3 + T(8)))) + (9^5))$
59834 := $((-T(4) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(89) \times T(5)))$
59835 := $((T((5 \times 3)) + T(T(8))) + (9^5))$
59837 := $((-7) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(89) \times T(5))$
59838 := $((83 \times T(T(8))) + T(95))$
59862 := $(2 \times ((T(6) \times T((8 + T(9)))) - T(T(5))))$
59865 := $((T(5) \times (-6) + T(89)) - T(T(5)))$
59868 := $(T(8) \times (T((T(6) + T(8))) + T(9 - 5)))$
59872 := $((T(T(T(2))) - ((T(7) + (T(89) \times T(5))))))$
59874 := $((T(T(4)) \times (7 + 8)) + (9^5))$
59875 := $((T(T(5)) - T((7 + T(8)))) - (9^5))$
59883 := $((T(T(3)) \times 8) + T(T(8))) + (9^5)$
59886 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) + (T(8) \times T((T(9) + (5)))))$
59892 := $(2 \times ((T(9) \times T(T(8))) - (9 + T(5))))$
59895 := $((T(T(5)) + T(9)) \times (T((T(8) - 9)) - T(5)))$
59922 := $((-T(2)) - ((-2) - T(9)) \times T((T(9) + (5))))$
59925 := $((5 - T(2)) + T(9)) \times T((T(9) + (5)))$
59935 := $((T(T((5 + 3))) \times (T(9) + T(9))) - (5))$
59937 := $((-7) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(9)) + (9^5)$
59943 := $((-3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times ((9 + T(9)) - T(5))$
59944 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(9)))) - (-9 + T(5)))$
59945 := $((-5) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T((9 - 5)))))$
59946 := $(T(T(6)) + (T((4 \times 9)) + (9^5)))$
59949 := $((-T(9) - T(T(4))) \times (-9)) + (9^5)$
59952 := $(T((T(2) \times (5 + 9))) + (9^5))$
59954 := $((-T(4) - T(T(5))) + T(T(9))) + (9^5)$
59955 := $((5 + T((T(T(5)) - T(9)))) \times T((-9) + T(5)))$
59957 := $((-7) - T(T(5))) + T(T(9)) + (9^5)$
59964 := $((4 \times T(T(6))) - ((9 - (9^5))))$
59976 := $((T(6) \times T((7 + 9))) \times T((-9) + T(5)))$
59982 := $(2 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) + T((-9) + T(5))))$
59983 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T((-8) + T(9))) + (9^5)))$
59984 := $((T(T(4)) \times (8 + 9)) + (9^5))$
59985 := $(T(5) \times ((T(89) + 9) - T(5)))$
59994 := $((T(4) \times (-9)) + T(T(9))) + (9^5)$
60228 := $((8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(06))))$
60474 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(7)) \times 40) - 6$
60594 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(5))) - 06$
60645 := $((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (60 - T(6)))$
60837 := $((-7^3) + T(80)) \times T(6)$
61095 := $(T(5) \times ((T(90) - 1) - T(6)))$
61215 := $((T(T((5 - 1))) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 1))) \times T(T(6)))$
61226 := $((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((1 + T(6))))$
61236 := $(T((T(6)/3)) \times (T(2)^{1+6}))$
61248 := $(T((84 + T(2))) \times 16)$
61278 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T((7 + T(T(2)))) + 1)) + 6)$
61335 := $((T((T(5) \times T(3))) - T(3)) \times T(-((1 - 6))))$
61359 := $((9^5) + (T((3 + 1)) \times T(T(6))))$
61376 := $((T(T(6)) - 7) \times (T(T(3)) + T((1 + T(6))))$
61422 := $((-T(2)) - ((T((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) - 1) \times (-T(6))))$
61425 := $(T(5) \times T(((2^4) - 1) \times 6))$
61426 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) - (-1) + T(6)))$
61434 := $((4^{T(3)}) \times T((4 + 1))) - (6)$
61438 := $((-8) - (-T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + T((1 \times 6))))))$
61443 := $((-3) + (T((T(4) + T((T(4) + 1)))) \times T(6)))$
61446 := $(T(6) \times T((T(4) + T(((4 + 1) + 6))))$
61455 := $(T(5) - (T(5) \times (-((4 \times 1)^6))))$
61462 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + 16)$
61466 := $((T(6) \times T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (-1) + T(6))$
61467 := $((T(76) \times T((4 - 1))) + T(6))$
61479 := $(9 \times ((-T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T((1 + T(6))))$
61488 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) \times T(6)$
61494 := $((-T(4) + T(T(9))) \times T(4) - 1) \times 6$
61534 := $(T(T(4)) - (-((3^5)) \times T((1 + T(6))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 61572 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (T((75 + 1)))) \times T(6)) \\ 61584 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (8 \times 5)) - 16) \\ 61594 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - (5))) - (1 \times 6)) \\ 61635 &:= (T(5) + (T(T((T(3) + (6)))) \times (-1) + T(6))) \\ 61642 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) - 1)) + (T(6)))) \\ 61648 &:= (8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times (6 - 1)) + 6)) \\ 61655 &:= (((T(5) \times T((T(5) \times 6))) - 1) + T(6)) \\ 61656 &:= ((T((6 \times T(5))) \times T((6 - 1))) + T(6)) \\ 61676 &:= (((T(6) \times T(76)) - 1) + T(6)) \\ 61677 &:= (((7 + 7) + T((T(6) + 1))) \times T(6)) \\ 61682 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(8) + T(T(6)))) - ((1 - 6))) \\ 61683 &:= (T(3) - (((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) \times T((1 \times 6)))) \\ 61694 &:= (((-T(4) \times T(T(9))) \times (-6)) - T(T((1 + 6)))) \\ 61698 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) - 1) \times (-6))) \\ 61732 &:= (((T(T(2))³) + T(7)) \times T((1 + T(6)))) \\ 61734 &:= ((T((-4) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(7)) - 1) - T(T(6))) \\ 61747 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T((7 + 1)))) - (T(6))) \\ 61748 &:= (((-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))) - (-1 + T(6)) \\ 61784 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) \times T(7)) + 16) \\ 61824 &:= (((T(T(4))²) - (81)) \times T(6)) \\ 61839 &:= ((93 \times (T(T(8)) - 1)) - (6)) \\ 61869 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6) - (81))) - T(T(6))) \\ 61887 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((8 + 8) + 1)) - T(T(6))) \\ 61938 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (3 \times ((9 + 1) + T(6)))) \\ 61964 &:= (((T(4) \times 6) \times T(T(9))) - T(16)) \\ 61989 &:= ((T(9) \times T((8 + T(9)) - 1)) - (T(6))) \\ 61995 &:= (-T(5) - (-T(9)) \times T((T(9) + (1 + 6)))) \\ 62094 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(9))) \times T(T(02))) - (6)) \\ 62118 &:= (T(T((8 - 1))) \times T(((1 - T(2)) + T(6)))) \\ 62124 &:= ((T((-4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) + 6) \\ 62139 &:= (((T(9) \times T(3)) - (1²)) \times T(T(6))) \\ 62208 &:= (((T(8) \times 02)^{T(2)}) / 6) \\ 62229 &:= ((T(9) \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(2))) - 6) \\ 62232 &:= ((((-T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2))))²) + T(T(6))) \\ 62235 &:= ((T(5) \times 3) \times (-T(2)) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 62244 &:= (((T(44) - 2) \times T(2)) \times T(6)) \\ 62253 &:= (3 \times ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 62256 &:= (((6⁵) + T(T(2))) \times (2 + 6)) \\ 62259 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(52) + T(T(2)))) - (T(6))) \\ 62271 &:= ((1 + T(T(7))) \times T(((2 + 2) + T(6)))) \\ 62272 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times (2 + T((2 + T(6)))) \\ 62283 &:= (-T((3 + T(8))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) / T(2))) \times (-T(6)) \\ 62286 &:= (-T(6) + ((-T(8) + T((T(T(T(2)))) / T(2)))) \times T(6)) \\ 62288 &:= ((T((8 + 8)) \times 2) \times (-2) + T(T(6))) \\ 62289 &:= (T(T(9)) - ((T(82) \times T(2)) \times (-6))) \\ 62292 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(9) \times T(T(2)))) - T((2 \times 6))) \\ 62294 &:= (-T(T(4)) + (((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(2))) - (T(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62295 &:= (T(5) - (T(9) \times (2 - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)))))) \\ 62298 &:= (-T(8) - (((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times (-6))) \\ 62319 &:= ((T(9) \times (-1) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(2)))))) - 6) \\ 62325 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 2) \times T(32)) + T(6)) \\ 62328 &:= ((T((8 \times T(T(2)))) \times (32 + T(6))) \\ 62346 &:= (-6) \times (4 - (T((3²)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 62347 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((-4) + T(T(3)))) + (-2) + T(T(6))) \\ 62349 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(4)) + 3) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \\ 62352 &:= (((-T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(2)) \times (-6) \\ 62355 &:= (-T(5) - (-((T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(2))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 62364 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times (3^{T(2)})) - (6)) \\ 62365 &:= (-5) - (T(T(6)) \times (T((3²)) \times (-6))) \\ 62369 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) \times T(3)) - (T(T(2)) / 6)) \\ 62385 &:= -((T(5) - ((T(8) - T(3)) \times T((2⁶)))) \\ 62391 &:= (((T((-1) + T(9))) \times T(T(3))) \times T(2)) + (T(6)) \\ 62393 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(9) \times T(3))) + (2 + T(6))) \\ 62394 &:= ((4 + (T(9) \times T(T((3 \times 2)))) \times 6) \\ 62395 &:= (-5) - ((9 + T(T(3))) \times (-T((2⁶)))) \\ 62396 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(9) \times T(3))) + 26) \\ 62398 &:= (-8) - (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(2))) \times (-6)) \\ 62412 &:= (((2 \times T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + 2) \times T(6)) \\ 62418 &:= ((8 + (T((-1) + T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 6) \\ 62424 &:= (T((4²)) \times (T((T(4) \times T(2))) - (6))) \\ 62425 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(-(2 - 6)))) \\ 62426 &:= (((T(6) / T(2))⁴) \times 26) \\ 62433 &:= (((T(3) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) - T(2)) \times T(6)) \\ 62436 &:= (T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3)))) \times T((T(42) / T(6)))) \\ 62439 &:= (((9 + 3)⁴) \times T(2)) + T(T(6)) \\ 62444 &:= (4 \times ((T(4) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 2)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 62454 &:= ((4 - (T(54) \times (-2))) \times T(6)) \\ 62457 &:= ((T((T(7) + T(5))) \times T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(6))) \\ 62463 &:= (3 \times (T(6) + (T(4) \times T((2⁶)))) \\ 62468 &:= ((T((8 \times 6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (2 + T(6))) \\ 62469 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(6)) \\ 62472 &:= (274 \times (-T(2)) + T(T(6))) \\ 62474 &:= ((-T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 2)) - 6) \\ 62475 &:= ((T(5) \times 7) \times T(((T(4) + T(2)) + T(6)))) \\ 62478 &:= ((T(8) + T(T(T((7 - 4)))) \times (T(2) + T(T(6)))) \\ 62479 &:= (-T(9) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) / T(-(2 - 6)))) \\ 62481 &:= (T(T((1 + 8))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6))) \\ 62488 &:= (-8) + ((T(T(8)) - (-T(4) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6)) \\ 62489 &:= ((T(T(9)) + 8) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6))) \\ 62521 &:= (((1 + T(2)) \times (5^{T(T(2))})) + (T(6))) \\ 62524 &:= (4 \times ((25^{T(2)}) + (6))) \\ 62526 &:= (6 \times (T(T(T(2))) + (5 \times T((2⁶)))) \\ 62538 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) - 2))) + (T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

- 62542** := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((-4) \times (5^{T(T(2))})) - (T(6)))$
62543 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(4)) \times (52 + T(T(6))))$
62544 := $(-4) \times (T(4) - ((5^{T(T(2))})) + (T(6)))$
62548 := $(-T(8)) + (4 \times ((5^{T(T(2))})) + (T(6)))$
62553 := $(-T(3)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + T(T(6)))$
62554 := $((-4) \times (-T(5)) - (5^{T(T(2))})) - (6)$
62556 := $(-T(65)) - (T(T((T(5) - T(2)))) \times (-T(6)))$
62557 := $((T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times T(5)) - (2 + T(T(6))))$
62559 := $(9 \times ((-T((5 \times 5)) - T(T(2))) \times (-T(6))))$
62565 := $(T(5) \times ((-T(6) + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + 6))$
62568 := $(8 \times ((6^5) + T((T(2) + (6))))$
62574 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - T((5 + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 6$
62583 := $(-((T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) \times (-T((5^2))) + T(T(6))))$
62584 := $(-(4 - 8) \times ((5^{T(T(2))})) + (T(6)))$
62586 := $(-6) \times (-T(8)) - ((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(T(6)))$
62592 := $(-T(2)) - (T(9) \times (-5 - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)))))$
62595 := $((5 \times 9) \times (5 + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))))$
62601 := $((T(10) + (6^{T(2)})) \times T(T(6)))$
62619 := $((T(9) \times ((1 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)))) - (T(6)))$
62621 := $((T(T(12)) \times T(6)) - T(2^6))$
62622 := $((-T((2 \times T(2)))) + T((T(T(6))/T(2)))) \times T(6)$
62628 := $(-((T(T(8)) + ((2 - T((T(6) + 2))) \times T(T(6))))$
62634 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times ((6 \times 2) - T(T(6))))$
62637 := $((T(7) \times T(T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) + (T(2)^6))$
62646 := $((T(T(6)) - 4) \times T((T(6) + 2))) - (6)$
62647 := $(-((T(T(7)) + T(4)) - (T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times (-T(6))))$
62648 := $(8 \times (T(T(4)) - ((6^{T(T(2))})/(-6)))$
62657 := $(-((T(T(7)) + T((T(5) + (62))) \times (-T(6))))$
62658 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times T(T(6))))$
62664 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(6))) - (T((T(2) \times T(6))))$
62679 := $((T(9) \times (7 + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(2)))) - (6))$
62684 := $(-((T(4) + (-86) \times (T(2)^6)))$
62685 := $(-T(5)) \times (((-T(8)) \times T(T(6)))/2) - (T(6))$
62687 := $(-7) - (-86) \times (T(2)^6)$
62694 := $(-((T(4) - 96) \times (T(2)^6)))$
62713 := $(31 \times (7 + T((T(2) \times T(6))))$
62715 := $(T(5) \times ((1 + T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) - 6))$
62727 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7 - 2) \times T(6)$
62735 := $((T(5) \times T(T((T(3) + 7)))) - T(T(-(2 - 6))))$
62742 := $((T(2) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) \times T(T(2))) - 6$
62744 := $(-4) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) \times (T(2) \times (-6)))$
62746 := $((-6) + (T(4) \times T(7))) \times (-2 + T(T(6)))$
62748 := $((T(8) \times T(4)) + T(72)) \times T(6)$
62766 := $((T(T((6 + 6))) + T(T(7))) \times (T(2) \times 6))$
62769 := $((T(9) \times T(T(6))) + T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6))$
62772 := $(T(2) - 7 \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6))))$
62775 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) + 7) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(6)))$
62784 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(8))) \times T((7 - 2))) - 6)$
62793 := $(3 \times ((T(9) \times T((T(7) + 2))) + (6)))$
62796 := $((T(69) \times (T(7) - 2)) + (6))$
62811 := $((T(T(11)) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(6))$
62826 := $((T(T(6)) \times (2 \times T((8 \times 2)))) - (6))$
62829 := $((T((9 \times 2)) + 8) \times T(26))$
62832 := $((T(23) - (8/2)) \times T(T(6)))$
62835 := $(T(5) \times (3 + T(T(((T(8) - 2) - T(6)))))$
62838 := $(((-8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(8) - 2)) + 6$
62845 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) + T(T(-(2 - 6))))$
62853 := $(-(((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + T(T((2 \times 6))))$
62859 := $((T(T(9)) / (-T(5))) \times (-8 - T(2 \times T(6))))$
62865 := $(-T(5)) \times (((6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))$
62874 := $(-((T(4) - (T(7) \times T(8))) \times (T(2) \times T(6))))$
62894 := $((-4) + T(9)) \times (T(T((8 + 2))) - (6))$
62895 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) - T(8^2)) \times (-T(6))$
62916 := $(-6) \times (-1 - (T(9) \times (2 + T(T(6)))))$
62922 := $(T(T(2)) \times (2 + (T(9) \times (2 + T(T(6)))))$
62924 := $(-4) - ((T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) \times (T(2) - T(T(6))))$
62925 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(9)) \times (-2 - T(T(6))))$
62928 := $(8 \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T((2 + T(6))))$
62937 := $((T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((9 + T(2)) + T(T(6))))$
62943 := $((T((3 \times 4)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(6))$
62944 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) + ((-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(6)))$
62946 := $((6 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(2))) - (6)$
62958 := $(T(8) \times (T(59) - T(T(T(2)))) - 6)$
62959 := $(-((T(T(9)) - (((-5) + T(9))^{T(2)} - (6))))$
62964 := $((T(T(4)) + 6) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(2) \times 6))$
62988 := $(T(T(8)) + ((-8) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times 6$
63063 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(03))) \times T(T(6))$
63072 := $(T((2 + 70)) \times (3 + T(6)))$
63105 := $(-T(5)) \times ((0 - T(T(13))) - (T(6)))$
63126 := $((T((T((6 \times 2) - 1)) + 3) \times T(6))$
63129 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T((1 + 3)))) - (6))$
63134 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(3)) - 1) + T(T(3)))) - 6)$
63135 := $(T((T(5) \times 3)) \times (T(T((1 + 3)))) + (6))$
63189 := $((T(((T(9) + T(8)) - 1)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(6))$
63195 := $(T(5) \times ((T(91) + T(3)) + T(6)))$
63217 := $(7 \times (1 + ((T(T(T(2)))^3) - T(T(6))))$
63224 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(2)) - T(T((2 \times T(3)))))) \times T(6)))$
63225 := $((5 + T((2 + T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(3)) + T(T(6)))$
63231 := $((T((-1) + T(T(3)))) \times T((T(2) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(6))$
63249 := $(-T(9)) + (((T(T(4))^2) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(6)))$
63252 := $(2 \times ((T(T(5)) - (-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(6))$
63273 := $((T(3) \times T(7)) \times T((T(2)^3)) - T(T(6))$
63279 := $((9 \times T(7))^2 + T(3)) - T(T(6))$

- 63282 := (T(2) + ((-T(8) - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(3) - T(T(6))))
63286 := ((T(T(6)) - 8) - (T((T(T(T(2))))/3)) × (-T(6)))
63287 := ((T(7) × 8) - (T((T(T(T(2))))/3)) × (-T(6)))
63288 := (T(8) × (((T(T(8)) - T(2)) × 3) - T(T(6))))
63292 := (-2) - (((T(9) - 2) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(6))))
63294 := (((T(4) × T(9 - 2)) - T(3)) × T(T(6)))
63316 := (T((T(6) + 1)) - (T((T(T(3)))/3)) × (-T(6)))
63339 := (T(9) - ((-T(T(3))) × T((T(T(3)))/3))) - T(T(6)))
63342 := (((T(T(2))⁴) + (T(T(3))³)) × 6)
63345 := (5 × ((T(T(4)) × T(T(T(3)))) - 36))
63348 := (((T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(3)))))/(-3)) × 6)
63354 := (((T(T(4)) × 5) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(3 × 6))
63355 := (-5) - (-T(T(5))) × T(((T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) + (T(6))))
63357 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(3) × T(3)))) + (T(6)))
63363 := ((T(T(3)) × T((T(T(6)))/3)) + T(3 + T(6)))
63378 := (((T(8) × T(7)) × 3) - T(3)) × T(6)
63384 := (((T(T(4)) - 8) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-3 + T(T(6))))
63396 := (((T(T(6)) × T(9)) + T(3 × T(3))) × 6)
63399 := (T(T(9)) - ((T(9) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(3))) + 6)
63405 := (-T(50)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(3)) + T(6)))
63415 := (5 × (-1) - ((-T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(6)))
63423 := ((T(3) + (T(2)⁴)) × (3⁶))
63424 := (4 × (((T(T(T(2))) + 4)³) + T(T(6))))
63427 := (T((7 + T(T(2)))) × (4 + (3 × T(T(6))))
63429 := ((T(9) × (T((-2) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3)))) - (T(6)))
63435 := (5 × ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(4))) - (3 × 6))
63441 := ((-1) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - 3)) × T(6)
63445 := (5 × (-T(4)) - ((-T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) + 6))
63448 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) × (T(4) + T((T(3) + (6))))
63459 := ((9⁵) - ((-T(4)) × T(T(3))) × T(6))
63462 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(3 × T(6))))
63465 := (5 × ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) - (T(3) + (6))))
63468 := (((-8) + T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 36)
63476 := -((T((T(6) + T(7))) + (T(T((4 × 3))) × (-T(6))))
63483 := (((T(T(3)) × (T(8) × 4)) × T(T(3))) - (T(6)))
63485 := (-5) × (8 - (T((4 + T(3))) × T(T(6))))
63492 := (T(T(2)) + (((T(T(9)) × T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) × 6))
63494 := (((-4) + T(9)) × (T(T(T(4))) + 3)) + T(T(6))
63495 := (((T(T(5)) + 9) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(3 + 6)))
63498 := (T(T(8)) - (((T(9) - 4) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(6))))
63504 := (((T(T(4)) × 05) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6)))
63516 := ((T((T(6) + 1)) + (T(5))) × (T(3) + T(T(6))))
63519 := ((T(91) × T(5)) + (3⁶))
63524 := (((-T(T(4))) × T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-5)) - (T(3)/6))
63525 := ((T((5 × 2))⁵⁻³) × T(6))
63528 := (8 × (T(T(T(2))) - (-T(T(5))) × T((T(T(3)))/T(6))))
63531 := (((T(T((1 + 3))) × 5) × T(T(T(3)))) + 6)
63534 := (((-T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-5)) + (3 + 6))
63543 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(4)) × 5)) + (3 × 6))
63546 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) × (T(5)/3)) + (T(6)))
63547 := (T(7) + (((T(T(4)) × 5) × T(T(T(3)))) - 6))
63549 := (T(9) + (((T(T(4)) × 5) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6))))
63555 := (5 × ((55 × T(T(T(3)))) + 6))
63567 := ((T(T(7)) × ((T(6) + 5) × T(3))) + T(T(6)))
63582 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(5))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))
63597 := (((T(T(7)) + T(9)) × (T(T(5)) + T(T(3)))) + (6))
63645 := (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(4))^{6/3}) × (-T(6))))
63648 := ((8 × T((-4) + T(6) × 3)) × 6)
63666 := ((T(6) × T(T((6 + 6)))) - T(T(3 + 6)))
63672 := (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) - T(T((6 + T(3)))) × (-T(6)))
63693 := (((-3) + T(T(9))) - (T(6))) × (3 × T(6))
63714 := (41 × ((T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) × 6))
63735 := ((T((5 × T(3)) - 7)) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6))
63742 := ((T(2) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(7)) + (3 × T(T(6))))
63748 := (-8) + (T(((T(4) + 7) + T(3))) × T(T(6)))
63762 := (T(T(2)) × (((-6) + T(7))³) - T(6))
63769 := ((((-9) + T(6)) + T(7))³) - T(T(6))
63774 := -((T(4) - (T(7) × T((73 - 6))))
63777 := (((T(7) + T(77)) + T(3)) × T(6))
63783 := (((3 - T(8)) + T(T(7))) × T(3 × 6))
63784 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) × T(7)) + (T(3 × T(6))))
63792 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) × (7³) - 6)
63825 := (-T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(2))) × (T(8) - T(T((T(3) + (6))))))
63828 := (T(8) × ((2 + T(T(8))) × 3) - T(T(6)))
63834 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(8)) + (T((T(3) + (6))))
63837 := (((T(7)³) - T(T(8))) × 3) - (T(6))
63847 := ((T(7) × T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))
63855 := (-T(5)) × ((T(T(5)) × (-T(8))) + (3 × T(6)))
63864 := ((T((T(4) × 6)) × T(8)) - T(3 × T(6)))
63882 := (((T(2) + T(8)) × T((T(8)/3))) × T(6))
63887 := ((-7) + T(8)) × (-8) + T(T((T(T(3)))/T(6)))
63888 := (8 × ((T(T(8)) × (T(8)/3)) - (6)))
63924 := ((T(T(4)) - ((T(2) × T(T(9))) - (T(3)))) × (-T(6)))
63936 := ((T(T(6)) - (3 × T(9))) × T(36))
63939 := -((T(T(9)) + (((-3) × T(T(9))) × T(T(3))) + T(T(6))))
63942 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(4)) × T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))
63945 := (((-5 × 4) + T(T(9))) × (3 × T(6)))
63954 := ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) × T((9 + 3))) - 6)
63955 := (-5) + (T((-5) + T(9))) × T((T(3) + (6)))
63958 := -((T(8) - (((-5) + T(9))³) - (6)))
63966 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(T(6)) + T(9))) - (T(T(3)) - T(T(6))))
63973 := (T(37) × T((T(9 + 3))/6))
63987 := ((7 + ((T(8) + 9) × T(3))) × T(T(6)))
63993 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T((T(T(9))/T(9)))) - (-T(3) - T(T(6))))

63996 := ((T(T(6)) + 9) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(6)))
63998 := -((T((-8) + T(9))) + (T(T(9+3))) × (-T(6)))
64125 := -((T(5)²) × ((1 - T(T(4))) - T(T(6))))
64149 := ((T(T(9)) × (-4) + T((1 + T(4)))) - (T(6)))
64152 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) × (T((1 + T(4))) + T(T(6))))
64155 := (-5) × ((T(T(5)) × (-T(14))) - T(T(6)))
64174 := (T(T(4)) - ((-T(7) + 1) × T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))))
64218 := (((T(T(8))/(1 × 2)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(6)))
64222 := (2 × (2 + ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6))))
64233 := (-T(3)) - ((-T(T(3))) × ((2 × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(6))))
64234 := (((-4) + T(T(T(3))))²) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(6))))
64235 := (((T(T(5))/3)^{T(2)}) + (4)) + T(T(6))
64239 := (((T(T(9)) + 3) × T(2)) - T(T(4))) × T(6)
64242 := (T(2) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64249 := (-T(9)) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(4)) - (T(6))))
64251 := ((-1) - T(T(5))) × (-T(24) - T(T(6)))
64252 := (-2^{T(5)}) - ((T(2) × T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64255 := (-5) - ((-T(5) + T(2)) × T((4 × T(6))))
64272 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) × (T(2) + T((-4) + T(6))))
64273 := (((T(3) + T(7)) × T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(6)))
64274 := (-T((4 × 7))) - ((2 × T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64275 := (T(5) × (7 + T(2 × 46)))
64281 := (((-1) + T(8)) × T((T(T(2)) × T(4)))) + T(T(6))
64284 := (((T(48) - T(2)) × T(T(4))) - T(T(6)))
64287 := (-7) - ((-T(8) - 2) × T((T(T(4)) + (6))))
64294 := ((4 + (T(T(9)) × 2)) × (T(4) + T(6)))
64323 := ((-T(3) × T(2)) + T(T((3 × 4))) × T(6))
64325 := ((-5) + T(2^{T(3)})) × (T(4) + T(6))
64329 := (((T(T(9) + T(2))) - (T(3))) × T(T(4))) - (T(6))
64335 := (-T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(3)) × (-T(T(4)) + T(T(6))))
64337 := (((T(7)³) × 3) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6))
64344 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(3) + T(4))) × T(6))
64349 := ((T(T(9)) × (4³)) - T((T(T(4)) + (6))))
64354 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(3)))) × 46)
64356 := (((T(65) × 3) × T(4)) + (6))
64365 := (((5 - T(6)) + T(T((3 × 4)))) × T(6))
64368 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(63))) × (4 × 6))
64371 := (-1) - ((-T(7) - T(3)) × T((T(T(4)) + (T(6))))
64372 := (-T(T(2)) - T(7)) × T((T(T(3)) + T((4 + 6))))
64384 := ((4⁸) + 3) - (T(T(4)) × T(6))
64386 := (((T(6) - T(8)) + T(T((3 × 4)))) × T(6))
64387 := ((T(T(7) + T(8))) - 3) × (T(4) + T(6))
64389 := ((T(9) × T((T(8) + T(T(3))) - (4)))) - 6
64394 := (((T(T(4)) × T((T(9) + 3))) - T(T(4))) - T(T(6)))
64395 := (-T(T(5))) + ((-T(T(9))) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))/T(6))
64416 := ((-T(6)) - T(T((-1) + T(4)))) × (-T(T(4)) + (6))

64425 := (T(5) × ((T(2) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T((4 + T(6))))))
64427 := -((T(T(T(7) - T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(6)))
64428 := (T((T(8)/T(2))) × (T((T(4) × 4)) + (6)))
64429 := ((T(9) × T((-2) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(6))))
64439 := (((T(T(9) + 3)) - (4)) × T(T(4))) - (T(6))
64449 := (((9 - 4) × T(T(4))) + (4)) × T(T(6))
64452 := (T(2) - (((-5) × T(T(4))) - (4)) × T(T(6)))
64454 := (((T(4) × T(T(5))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 6
64455 := (-T(T(5))) - (((-5) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6))
64465 := (-T(5) - (T(64) × (T(4) + T(6))))
64469 := (((T(T(9)) × 64) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6)))
64473 := ((T(3) × ((7 × T(T(T(4)))) + 4)) - T(T(6))
64476 := (6 × ((7 × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(6))))
64477 := (T(7) - ((T((-7) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(4))) + T(T(6))))
64482 := (T(T(2)) + (T(8) × (T((4 + T(T(4))) + (T(6))))))
64484 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (T(8) × (4 + T((T(4) × 6))))))
64485 := (T(5) × (T((-8) + (T(4) × T(4)))) + (T(6)))
64491 := (((1 + T(9)) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(4)))) × T(6))
64492 := (2 × (-94) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(6))))
64495 := (T(5) + (T(9 + T(T(4)))) × (T(4) + T(6)))
64512 := (2 × ((-1 - 5) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64521 := (T(T(12)) - (T(5) × (-4⁶)))
64526 := ((-T(T(6))) × (T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) + T(T(T(4))))/(-6))
64533 := ((T(T(T(T(3)))/3) + (T(5) + T(T(4)))) × T(6))
64539 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) + ((5 × T(T(4))) × T(T(6))))
64547 := (-T(7)) - (((T(T(T(4))) - 5) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64548 := (T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(((5 - 4) + T(6))))
64554 := (((4 + (5⁵) - T(T(4))) × T(6))
64565 := (-T((-5) + T(6))) - (T(T((T(T(5))/T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
64569 := (((9 × 6) × T(T(5))) × T(4)) - T(T(6))
64572 := (-T(2)) - (7 × (T(5) - (T(T(T(4))) × 6)))
64575 := ((5 × 7) × (T(5) + T((T(4) × 6))))
64584 := (T(-((T(4) - T(8)))) × (T((T(5) + (4)) - (6)))
64588 := ((-8) + T((8 + T(5)))) × (T(4) + T(T(6)))
64596 := (-T(6)) × (T(T(9)) - (T(5) + (4⁶)))
64599 := ((T(T(9)) + (9 + T(5))) × (T(T(4)) + (6)))
64612 := (2¹⁶) - (4 × T(T(6)))
64617 := ((T(T((7 - 1) + 6))) - (4)) × T(6)
64623 := (T(3) - ((T(T(2 × 6))) - (4)) × (-T(6)))
64625 := (-((5^{T(2)}) × (-T(6)) - T((T(4) + T(6))))
64629 := (-T(9)) - (((-2) × T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) + 6
64632 := (2 × (-3) - ((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))
64634 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) - 46
64635 := (-T(53)) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(6)))
64638 := ((T(8) + T(T(3))) × ((T(6) × T(T(4))) - (T(6))))
64652 := ((T(T(-((T(2) - T(5)))) × T(6)) - (T(T(4)) - (6)))
64655 := (-5) × (5 - ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) + T(T(6))))

$$\begin{aligned} 64659 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(6))) \\ 64662 &:= (T(2) - (((T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6))) \\ 64664 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(6))) - (T(4) + (6))) \\ 64665 &:= (-T(5) - (((T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T((4 + 6)))))) \\ 64667 &:= (-7) - (((T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 6) \\ 64668 &:= ((8 - 6) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 6)) \\ 64672 &:= (-2) - (((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(4)) + (6)) \\ 64674 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((-7) + T((6 + 4)))) - (6)) \\ 64675 &:= (-5) - (((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 + 6)) \\ 64678 &:= (-8) - (((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(4) - (6)) \\ 64679 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(7)) \times 64) + T(T(6))) \\ 64692 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(9 - 6))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 6) \\ 64694 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) \times 64) - (6))) \\ 64695 &:= (T(5) - (((T(9) \times (-6)) - T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64701 &:= ((T((T(10) - 7)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6))) \\ 64704 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (0 - 7)) - 4) \times (-6)) \\ 64714 &:= ((-T(T(4))) \times (-1) - T((-7) + T(T(4)))) - (T(6)) \\ 64716 &:= (6 \times ((1 \times 7) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 6) \\ 64719 &:= ((T(9) + T((-1) + T(7))) \times T((-4) + T(6))) \\ 64722 &:= (2 \times ((T((2 \times T(7))) - T(T(4))) \times T(6))) \\ 64725 &:= ((T(5) \times T(2)) + ((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64728 &:= ((8 \times T(T(2))) + ((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64729 &:= ((9 - 2) \times (7 + (T(T(T(4))) \times 6))) \\ 64736 &:= ((6/3) \times (T(7) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6)))))) \\ 64752 &:= (((-T(2) - T(5)) + (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 6) \\ 64755 &:= ((5 \times T(5)) + ((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64756 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((5 + 7)))) + T((4 + 6))) \\ 64757 &:= (-T(7) - ((T(T((5 + 7))) + 4) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 64758 &:= (((-((8 + 5)) - (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6)) \\ 64764 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(7)) - (-4) \times T(6)) \\ 64778 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times T(T(7)))/4) + (T(6)) \\ 64782 &:= (((-T(2)) - (-T(8)) \times T((T(7) - 4)))) \times 6) \\ 64785 &:= (-T(5) - (((-T(8)) \times T((T(7) - 4)))) \times 6) \\ 64794 &:= (((-T(4) + 9) - (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6)) \\ 64799 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) - 46) \\ 64821 &:= (((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) + (T(6)) \\ 64824 &:= (((T((4 \times T(T(2)))) \times T(8)) + 4) \times 6) \\ 64827 &:= (((7^{T(2)}) \times T(8))/4) \times T(6) \\ 64833 &:= (T(3) - ((T(3) + T(T((8 + 4)))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 64836 &:= (6 \times (T(3) + (T(8) \times T((4 \times 6)))) \\ 64839 &:= -(((T(T(9)) + T(3)) - (T(8) \times T((T(4) \times 6)))) \\ 64842 &:= (2 \times ((T(4) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) + (T(6))) \\ 64843 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((4^8) - (4 \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64844 &:= (-4) - (((T(T(T(4))) + 8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 64845 &:= (-T(5) - (T((T(4) + T(8))) \times (T(4) \times (-6)))) \\ 64848 &:= (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T((8 - 4)))) \times T(6) \\ 64849 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - 4) - (T(8) \times T((T(4) \times 6))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64853 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + T(46)) \\ 64854 &:= ((4 \times T(5)) \times T((T(8) + T(4)))) - (6) \\ 64855 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(5) \times T(8))) + T((4 + 6))) \\ 64862 &:= (2 \times (T((T(6) - 8)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 64869 &:= ((-9) - (((6 - 8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 64876 &:= (((T(6) \times T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - 4))/6) \\ 64884 &:= (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) - (-T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 64911 &:= ((T((T((1 + 1)) + T(9))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \\ 64922 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(2) + 9)))) + (-T(4) + T(T(6)))) \\ 64925 &:= (((5 + T(2)) + T(9)) \times T((T(T(4)) - 6))) \\ 64926 &:= (-6) + (-T(2) - T(9)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \\ 64929 &:= (-T(9) - (T(T(T(2)) + T(9))) \times (-T(T(4)) - 6)) \\ 64931 &:= (-1) - ((3 - T(9)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6)) \\ 64932 &:= (2 \times ((-T(3)) - T((T(9) + T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 64934 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(9)) - 4^6) \\ 64935 &:= (-T(5) \times ((-3) - T((9 \times T(4)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 64936 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T((3 + 9)))) + 4) + T(T(6))) \\ 64938 &:= (-T(8) + (T((T(3) + T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - 6))) \\ 64944 &:= ((T(T((4 + 4))) - T(T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 64945 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(T(4)) + 9))) \times (T(4) + T(6))) \\ 64953 &:= (3 \times ((T((5 \times 9)) - 4) \times T(6))) \\ 64962 &:= ((T(2) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(9))) - 4)) - T(T(6))) \\ 64964 &:= (-T(4) + (T((6 + T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - 6))) \\ 64965 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(6) \times T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) + 6)) \\ 64967 &:= (-7) + (T((6 + T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) - 6)) \\ 64974 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(7))) - T(T(9))) \times (T(4) - T(T(6)))) \\ 64983 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times 8) + ((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(4)) + 6)))) \\ 64984 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 8) \times T(T(9))) + T(4) - T(T(6))) \\ 64985 &:= ((5 + T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(T((4 + 6)))) \\ 64989 &:= (9 \times (T(T(8)) + ((9^4) - 6)) \\ 64992 &:= ((T(2) + T(9)) \times ((T(9) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6)))) \\ 64995 &:= ((T(5) \times T((T(9) + T(9)))) + T((4 \times T(6)))) \\ 64998 &:= ((T((T(8) - 9)) + T(T(9))) \times 46) \\ 65088 &:= ((-8) \times T(8)) \times (05 - T(T(6))) \\ 65136 &:= (T((T(6) + (3 - 1))) \times (5 + T(T(6)))) \\ 65142 &:= (2 \times ((T(T((4 - 1))) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 65184 &:= (((4^8) - 1) - T((5 + T(6)))) \\ 65223 &:= (3 \times (T(T(2)) - (T((T(2) \times T(5))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 65226 &:= ((T(T((6 \times 2))) + 25) \times T(6)) \\ 65232 &:= ((2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(2))) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(6))) \\ 65236 &:= -(((T((T(6) + 3)) - 2^{-5+T(6)})) \\ 65247 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(2) + T(5)))) \times T(6) \\ 65259 &:= ((9^5) + (T((T(2) \times T(5))) \times 6) \\ 65268 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((T(6) \times 2) + (56))) \\ 65274 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)))) \times 6) \\ 65283 &:= ((T(-T(3) - T(8))) - 2) \times (T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \\ 65284 &:= ((4^8) + ((T(2) - T(5)) \times T(6)))$$

- 65289** := ((98 × T(T(T(2) + (5)))) + (T(6)))
65292 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) × T((T(T(T(2))) + 5))) + 6)
65295 := -(T(5) - (((T(T(9)) × (-T(2))) - 5) × T(6)))
65296 := -((T(T(6)) + (9 - (2^{-5+T(6)}))))
65319 := ((T((T(9) - 1)) × T((T(3) + (5)))) - (T(6)))
65325 := (T(T(5)) - ((-T(2)) × T((3 × T(5)))) × T(6)))
65326 := (T(6) + ((2^{T(T(3))-5}) - T(T(6))))
65334 := ((T((T(4) × 3)) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(6)))
65346 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) × (-6)))
65373 := (((-3) + T(T(7))) - (T((3 × 5)))) × T(T(6)))
65379 := (T((9 + T(7))) × (3 - (T(5) × (-6))))
65394 := -((((T(4) - T(93)) × T(5)) + T(6)))
65416 := (T(61) + ((T(T(4)) × 5) × T(T(6))))
65422 := (((2²⁴) - T(T(5))) + (6))
65425 := (((-5) + T(T(T(2))))⁴) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(6))))
65436 := ((T((6 + 3)) - 4) × T(56))
65444 := ((-T(4)) × (T(T(4)) - (T(T(4)) × T(T(5)))) - 6))
65446 := (((6 + T(4))⁴) + (T(5) × (-6)))
65456 := ((T((6 × T(5))) - 4) × (-5 + T(6)))
65472 := (T((T(2) + T(7))) × (-4 + T((-5) + T(6))))
65475 := (T(5) × (T(((T(7) - T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) - 6))
65478 := (((8 × T(T(7))) - T(4)) - T(T(5))) × T(6))
65493 := (3 × (((T(9) × 4) × T(T(5))) + T(T(6))))
65505 := -((T(T(5)) - ((05⁵) × T(6)))
65515 := (-5) - ((-1) - T(5)) × T((T(5) × 6)))
65533 := (-3) + (((3 - 5))^{-5+T(6)})
65534 := -((T((T(4) + 3)) - ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65535 := -(((T(5) × T(3)) - ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65537 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) × T((5 × 6)))
65539 := (((T(93) × T(5)) - 5) - T(6))
65541 := (-(((1 × 4) - (5⁵))) × T(6))
65542 := ((2^{-4+5+T(5)}) + (6))
65545 := (T(5) + ((4^{T(T(5))/T(5)}) - 6))
65556 := ((T(6) + T(5)) × ((T(T(5)) × T(5)) + T(6)))
65559 := ((T((T(T(9) - T(5)))/5)) × T(5)) - 6)
65562 := ((T(2) - ((6 - (5⁵)))) × T(6))
65564 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(6) × (5⁵)) - 6)))
65565 := ((T(T(5)) + T(6)) × T((-5) × (T(5) - T(6))))
65568 := -((T(8) - ((T(6) × (5⁵)) - T(6)))
65571 := ((T(((1 - T(7)) + T(T(5)))) × T(5)) + 6)
65576 := -(((T(6) + T(7)) - ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65583 := ((T(3) - (8 - (5⁵))) × T(6))
65584 := ((4⁸) + ((T(T(5))/T(5)) × 6))
65585 := -((5 × 8) + ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65586 := ((T((T(-6) + T(8)))/5) × T(5)) + (T(6)))
65595 := ((T(5) - T(9)) + ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65597 := (((-T(T(7))) × T((T(T(9))/T(5))))/(-T(5))) + T(T(6)))
65598 := -(((T(8) - 9) - ((5⁵) × T(6)))
65622 := ((2 + ((T(2)⁶) × T(5))) × 6)
65625 := (((T(5) × 2)/6)⁵) × T(6))
65634 := ((4 + ((3⁶) × T(5))) × 6)
65649 := ((9 × ((T(T(4)) + 6) × T(T(5)))) - T(T(6)))
65655 := (((5⁵) × T(6)) + ((5 × 6)))
65664 := ((T((T(4) × 6)) - 6) × (T(5) + T(6)))
65667 := (-7) × ((-T((6 + 6)) × T(T(5))) - (T(6)))
65681 := (-1) + ((-T(8) - T(T(6))) × (-T(5) - T(T(6))))
65682 := -((T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(6))))
65685 := (T(T(5)) + (T((T(8) - 6)) × (T(T(5)) + T(6))))
65688 := (8 × ((T(8) × T(6)) + (-5) × T(6)))
65706 := ((60 + T(T(7))) × (T(T(5)) + T(6)))
65715 := -((T(T(5)) - (((-1) + T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) × T(T(6))))
65723 := ((T(T(T(3))) - 2) × (-T(7) - (T(5) × T(6))))
65736 := ((T(6) + ((3⁷) × 5)) × 6)
65737 := (T(7) + (T(T(3)) × ((T(7) × T(T(5))) - T(T(6))))
65739 := ((T(T(9)) + 3) - (T(T((7 + 5))) × (-T(6))))
65746 := (T(T(6)) + (((4^{-7+T(5)}) - T(6)))
65758 := ((T(T(8)) + 5) × (-7 - (-5) × T(6)))
65764 := (T(T(4)) + (-T(6)) × ((-T(7)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(6))))
65769 := (((-T(9)) + T((6 + T(7)))) × T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))
65772 := ((-T(2)) × T(T(7))) × (-75 + T(6))
65778 := -((T(T(8)) - (T(7) × ((7 - T(T(5))) × (-T(6))))
65793 := (((-3) × T(T(9))) - T(7)) × (-T(5) + 6))
65796 := ((-6) × T(9)) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(6)))
65799 := (9 × ((T(T(9)) × 7) + (T((5 + 6))))
65814 := -((T(T((4 + 1))) - (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) - T(6))))
65815 := -(((T(T(5)) - 1) - (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) - T(6))))
65824 := ((T(T(4)) × (-2)) + (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) - T(6))))
65826 := (6 × ((T(2) × T(85)) + 6))
65832 := (-T(2)) + ((T((3 × 8)) - T(5)) × T(T(6)))
65834 := (-((4^{T(3)})) + (T(T(8)) × (5 × T(6))))
65835 := -((T(5) - T((3 × 8))) × T((T(5) + 6)))
65838 := ((8 + (3 × T(85))) × 6)
65843 := -((T((3 + T(4))) - (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) - T(6))))
65848 := (-8) + (T(48) × 56))
65851 := (((1 - 5)⁸) + (T(5) × T(6)))
65853 := -((3⁵) × (-((8 × 5) - T(T(6))))
65854 := ((T((4 × T(5))) × T(8)) - (5 + T(6)))
65856 := (T(((T(6) - T(5)) × 8)) × 56)
65859 := ((T((T(9) + T(5))) × T(8)) - (T(5) + 6))
65862 := (T(T(2)) + (T((6 × 8)) × 56))
65864 := ((T((T(4) × 6)) × T(8)) - (-5 + T(6)))

$$\begin{aligned} 65877 &:= (((T(7) \times T(7)) \times (-T(8) + T(T(5)))) + (T(6))) \\ 65878 &:= (-((8 \times 7)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 65886 &:= (-((6 \times 8)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 65889 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (8 \times 8)) - T((5 + T(6)))) \\ 65892 &:= ((T(2) - T(9)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 65897 &:= (-((T(7) + 9)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 65898 &:= (-T(8) + ((-9) \times T(T(8))) \times (-5 + 6)) \\ 65913 &:= (-T(T(3))) + (T(T(-((1 - 9)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 65916 &:= (-6) \times ((-1) - T((T(9) + T(5)))) \times 6 \\ 65925 &:= (-((T(5)^{T(2)})) + (T((9 + T(5))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 65928 &:= (82 \times (T(T(9)) - T((T(5) + (6)))) \\ 65934 &:= (((-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times 9) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))) \\ 65944 &:= (4 \times (T((-4) + T(9))) + (5^6)) \\ 65952 &:= ((-2) - T((T(5) + T(9)))) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\ 65955 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((-T(5) + T(9 + T(5)))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 65988 &:= (-T(8)) \times (T((T(8) - 9)) - T((5 + 6))) \\ 65994 &:= (((T(T(4) + 9) \times T(T(9))) - (T(5))) - T(T(6))) \\ 66066 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T((60/6)))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 66129 &:= ((T((T(9) + T(2))) + 1) \times T(6)) - T(T(6)) \\ 66189 &:= ((T((T(9) + T(8))) \times (-1) + T(6)) - T(T(6))) \\ 66214 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (1 + (2 \times T(6)))) - 6) \\ 66219 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times ((1 \times 2)^6)) - (T(6))) \\ 66225 &:= (-5) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(2)) \times T(66))) \\ 66229 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (2^{T(T(2))}) - (T(T(6))/T(6))) \\ 66234 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (-T(2) + T(T(6)))) \times T(6)) \\ 66241 &:= (T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - (T(T(2 \times 6))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 66246 &:= ((64 \times T(T((T(2) + (6)))) + 6) \\ 66249 &:= (-9) \times (T(4) - (T(26) \times T(6))) \\ 66252 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(5)) \times T((2 + T(6)))) + (6))) \\ 66255 &:= (T(5) \times (-5) - (-2) \times T(66)) \\ 66258 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(T(5))/2))) + (T((T(6) + (6)))) \\ 66276 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (T(7) \times 2)) \times T(T(6))) - (T(6))) \\ 66288 &:= (8 \times ((8 \times T(T((T(2) + (6)))) + 6) \\ 66294 &:= (((T(4) \times T((T(9) + 2))) - T(T(6))) \times 6) \\ 66297 &:= (((T(79) - 2) \times T(6)) - T(6)) \\ 66324 &:= (((T(4) \times T(2)) \times T(T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) - 6) \\ 66345 &:= (T(5) + ((T(4) \times 3) \times T(66))) \\ 66348 &:= (T(8) \times ((T((4^3)) - (6)) - T(T(6))) \\ 66354 &:= ((-4) - (5 \times T(T((T(T(3))/T(6)))))) \times (-6) \\ 66355 &:= (-5) \times (-5) - (T(3) \times T(66)) \\ 66366 &:= ((T((-6) - T(T(6)))/(-3)) \times T(6)) + 6) \\ 66369 &:= (((-9) + T(T(6))) \times T((3 + T(6)))) - T(T(6)) \\ 66374 &:= (-((T(T(T(4))) - (((-7) + T(T(3))) \times T(6)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66375 &:= (T(5) + (T((73 + 6)) \times T(6))) \\ 66378 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T((7 + T(3))))/(T(6) + T(6))) \\ 66381 &:= ((T((1 + T((T(8)/3))) \times T(6)) + (T(6))) \\ 66384 &:= (48 \times (-3) - (-6) \times T(T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66399 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(6)))) - (T(6))) \\ 66423 &:= ((-3) - T(((T(2) + T(T(4)) + (T(6)))))) \times (-T(6)) \\ 66424 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T((6 \times 6))) \\ 66435 &:= (5 \times ((T(3) \times T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) + (T(6))) \\ 66444 &:= ((4 + T(((T(4) \times T(4)) - T(6)))) \times T(6)) \\ 66456 &:= ((T((-T(6) + T(T(5)))) \times 4) + (6^6)) \\ 66457 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (T(5))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66465 &:= (T(5) \times (((T(6) \times T(4)) \times T(6)) + T(6))) \\ 66471 &:= ((-1) + T(T(7))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 66472 &:= (T((T(T(T(2))) + 7) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66474 &:= (((4 \times T(74)) - T(6)) \times 6) \\ 66478 &:= ((T(8) + (7)) \times (T(T((4 + 6))) + (6))) \\ 66484 &:= ((4^8) + (-4) \times (-6 - T(T(6)))) \\ 66522 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times (T((2^5)) \times T(6))) - (6)) \\ 66524 &:= (-4) + ((T((2^5)) \times 6) \times T(6)) \\ 66528 &:= ((T(8) \times T((2 + 5))) \times 66) \\ 66544 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(T(6)))) - (6)) \\ 66549 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((4^5) \times 66))) \\ 66594 &:= (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))) - (6)) \\ 66647 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(6) \times T(T((6 + 6)))) \\ 66675 &:= (-T(5)) \times (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))/(-T(6))) + (T(6))) \\ 66693 &:= (((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) \times (-66)) - T(T(6))) \\ 66699 &:= ((T(9) \times T((9 \times 6))) + (-6) \times T(6)) \\ 66717 &:= ((T(71) \times T(7)) + (-T(6) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66735 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(37) \times (-6)) - T(T(6))) \\ 66738 &:= (((-T(8) + T((-3) + T(7))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(6))) \\ 66753 &:= (((3 - T(T(5))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))) - (6)) \\ 66759 &:= (((T(9) + T(T(5))) \times T((7 + T(6)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 66765 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-6) + T(T(7))) + (-T(6) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66787 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((T(8) \times T(7)) - T(6)))/6) \\ 66789 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) + (6))) \\ 66795 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) \times (-7 + 66)) \\ 66816 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 1) \times ((8 \times 6) \times 6)) \\ 66819 &:= ((T(9) \times T(((1 + 8) \times 6))) - (6)) \\ 66822 &:= ((2 - (-2) \times T(8)) \times T((T(6) + T(6)))) \\ 66825 &:= ((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T((8 \times 6) + 6)) \\ 66879 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((7 \times (T(8) + (6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 66885 &:= (T(5) \times (T((8 + 86)) - (6))) \\ 66922 &:= (-2) + ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \times (-66)) \\ 66924 &:= ((T(42) - T(9)) \times T((6 + 6))) \\ 66934 &:= (T(4) + ((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) \times (-66))) \\ 66939 &:= ((T(9) \times (3 + T((9 \times 6)))) - T(6)) \\ 66945 &:= ((T(54) \times T(9)) + T((-6) + T(6))) \\ 66969 &:= (T(9) + ((T(6) - T(T(9))) \times (-66))) \\ 66975 &:= (T(5) \times T(((7 + 9) + T((6 + 6)))) \\ 66976 &:= (T(T((6 + 7))) \times (96/6)) \\ 66984 &:= (-4) \times ((-T(8)) \times T((9 + T(6))) - (6)) \end{aligned}$$

- 66999 := ((T(9) × (9 + T(9 × 6))) - T(T(6)))
67134 := (((T(T(4)) × (-3)) × (-1 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6)))
67144 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(4)) + ((1 - 7)))) - T(T(6)))
67158 := (T((T(8) + (5))) × T(-((1 - 7) - 6)))
67193 := (((3 + T((T(9) - 1))) × T(T(7)))/6)
67221 := ((T(T((1 + T(2)))) × (T(2) × T(T(7)))) + T(T(6)))
67225 := ((T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(2) + T(7)))) - T(T(6)))
67234 := (((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))²) × T(7)) + (6))
67235 := (5 × ((T(T(3)))^{T(2)}) + T(T((7 + 6))))
67242 := (T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(4)) × T(2)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(6))))
67248 := -((T(T(8)) - ((42 × 7) × T(T(6))))
67249 := (((T(9) + (4))²) × T(7)) + T(6))
67254 := -((((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) × T(T((2 + 7)))) + (T(6))))
67255 := -((T(T(5)) - (T((5 × 2)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))))
67263 := (((T(T(3)) + (T(6))) × T((2 × T(7)))) + T(T(6)))
67275 := ((-5) × T(T((7 + 2))) × (-7 + 6))
67284 := (-4) × (((-T(8)) - T(T(2))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(6)))
67298 := ((8 + (T(9)/T(2))) × T(76))
67299 := ((T(T((T(9)/9))) × T((T(T(T(T(2))))/7))) - (T(6)))
67314 := ((-T(T(4)) × (1 - T((T(3) + T(7)))) - 6)
67326 := ((T(T(6)) - 2) × (T(3) × (T(7) + T(6))))
67338 := (((T(83) - 3) × T(T(7)))/T(6))
67341 := ((T(T((1 + 4))) × T((T(T(T(3)))/7))) + (T(6)))
67344 := (-T(4) + ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) - (T(6))))
67347 := (-T(7) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(3 + 7) - 6))))
67353 := ((T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) × (7 + 6))
67354 := ((T(T(4)) × T(((T(5) + T(3)) + T(7)))) - (T(6)))
67359 := ((T(9) × (-T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(3)) × 7))) - 6)
67368 := (8 × ((T((T(6) + 3)) × T(7)) + (T(6))))
67372 := (-T(2) + (T((7 + 3)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67374 := ((T(T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) - 3) × (-T(7))) × (-6))
67375 := (T(T(((5 + 7)/3))) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67384 := (((4⁸) + T(T(T(3)))) - (-7 × T(T(6))))
67388 := (-8) + ((T(83) × T(T(7)))/T(6))
67389 := ((T(((9 × 8) - 3)) × T(7)) - T(T(6)))
67419 := ((T(9) - 1) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67424 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67425 := ((T((T(5) - 2)) × T((T(4) + T(7)))) - (6))
67428 := (T(8) × (T(2) + (T(T(4)) × (T(7) + (6))))
67429 := ((9 × T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67431 := (T(13) × T(-((4 - (7 × 6))))
67437 := ((T((7 + T(3))) × T((T(4) + T(7)))) + (6))
67441 := (T((1 + T(4))) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67445 := ((T(5) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67452 := (((2⁵) × T(4)) - T(7)) × T(T(6))
67453 := (T((-3) + T(5)) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67465 := ((T(5) × 6) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67473 := ((3 × T((7 + T(4)))) × (7 × T(6)))
67483 := ((3 × T(8)) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67487 := -((T(T(7)) - ((T((8 × T(4)) - 7)) × T(6)))
67488 := (T(8) + ((-8) + T((-4) + T(7))) × T(T(6)))
67494 := ((T(T(4)) - (9 × (T(T(4)) - T(T(7)))) × T(6))
67495 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(9) + T(4)) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
67499 := ((T(9) × (-T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (7 - T(T(6))))
67522 := (T(-((T(2) - T(2 × 5)))) × (T(7) + T(6)))
67536 := ((T(T(6)) + T((3 + T(5)))) × (T(7) × 6))
67551 := ((T(15) × T((5 + T(7)))) + T(T(6)))
67573 := ((T((T(T(T(3)))/7)) × T(T(5))) + (T((T(7) - 6))))
67578 := (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) × 5) + T(7)) × T(6))
67579 := -((T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(7) + T(6))))))
67593 := (-T(T(3)) + ((T((T(T(9)))/T(5))) × T(7)) - 6)
67596 := ((T(6) + (9⁵)) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(6))))
67599 := ((T((9 + T(9)) + T(5))) × T(7)) - (T(6))
67626 := ((T(((T(6) × T(2)) + 6)) × T(7)) + (6))
67627 := ((T(T(7)) × (-2) + (6 × T(7))) + T(T(6)))
67635 := (T(5) × (T((T(-T(3) - T(6))) - (T(7)))) + T(T(6)))
67646 := ((T(T(6)) - 4) × (67 + T(T(6))))
67662 := ((2 × T(6)) × ((T(T(6)) × 7) - 6))
67683 := (((T(3 × 8)) + T(6)) - T(7)) × T(T(6))
67694 := ((-4) + T(T((-9) + T(6)))) × (T(7) - 6))
67722 := ((T(2) - ((-T(2) + T(T(7))) × (-T(7)))) × 6)
67725 := ((T(5) × (-2 - 7)) × T((7 × 6)))
67729 := (-T((9²)) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(6))))
67743 := -((T((3 × T(4)) - (T(T(7)) × (T(7) × 6))))
67745 := (-T(5) + (T(T(4)) × (7 + T((T(7) + T(6))))))
67746 := (-T(6) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) × (7 × T(6))))
67747 := -(((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)) × (T(7) × 6))))
67754 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (-5 - (7 × 7))) - 6)
67767 := (((-7) + T(T(6))) + T(7)) × T(6))
67782 := (T(T((-2 × 8) + T(7))) × (T(7) - 6))
67788 := ((8 - ((-8) × T(T(7)) + T(7))) × T(6))
67815 := (T(T((5 - 1))) × (8 + T((T(7) + T(6))))
67837 := (T(T(7)) + (T(38) × T((7 + 6))))
67839 := ((T((T(9) - T(3)) × 87) - (T(6)))
67848 := -((T(8) × T(4)) - ((8 × T(T(7))) × (-T(6))))
67851 := ((T((T((-1) + T(5))) - T(8)) × T(7)) + T(T(6)))
67869 := (-T(9) + (((-6) - T(8)) × (-7)) × T(T(6)))
67872 := ((-2) + T(T(7))) × ((T(8) - T(7)) × T(6))
67893 := ((T(3) + T((9 + 8))) × (T(T(7)) + (T(6))))
67896 := ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) × ((T(8) × 7) - 6))
67914 := (((-4 - 1) + T(9)) × 7) × T(T(6))
67924 := (T(4) + (((T(2) - T(9)) × (-7)) × T(T(6))))
67925 := ((T((5 + T(T(2)))) × T(T(9))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6))))
67932 := (T(T((2³))) × ((T(9) - T(7)) × 6))

$$\begin{aligned} 67938 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) \times (T(9) - T(7)))) + (6)) \\ 67943 &:= (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(T(7)) + (6))) \\ 67956 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times T((7 \times 6)))) \\ 67958 &:= ((8^5) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + (6)))) \\ 67968 &:= (8 \times (-((T(6) + 9)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 67972 &:= ((2^{7+9}) + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) \\ 67977 &:= (((T(7) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(9 - 7))) - T(T(6))) \\ 68082 &:= ((2 + T(80)) \times T((T(8)/6))) \\ 68124 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((1 + 8))) - T(T(6))) \\ 68145 &:= ((-5) + T(((4 - 1) \times 8))) \times T(T(6)) \\ 68148 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(4) - 1)) + (8 \times T(T(6)))) \\ 68163 &:= (((3 + T(61)) \times T(8)) - T(6)) \\ 68166 &:= ((T(66) + T(T((1 + 8)))) \times T(6)) \\ 68169 &:= (((9 + T(61)) \times T(8)) - T(T(6))) \\ 68172 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(-((1 - 8)))) - (6))) \\ 68187 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times 8) - 1) \times T((T(8)/6))) \\ 68208 &:= ((8 \times T(028)) \times T(6)) \\ 68219 &:= -((T((T(9) + 1)) - (T((T(2) \times 8)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 68229 &:= ((T((9^2)) + (-2) \times T(8)) \times T(6)) \\ 68235 &:= (((-T(T(5))) + T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \times T(8)) - (T(6)) \\ 68238 &:= ((T(T(8)) + 3) \times ((T(2) \times T(8)) - (6))) \\ 68249 &:= (((T(9) - 4)^{T(2)}) - T(T(8))) - (6)) \\ 68265 &:= (T(5) \times ((T((T(6) - T(T(2)))) \times T(8)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68271 &:= ((((-1) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) + T(T(6)) \\ 68278 &:= ((8 \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 8)) + 6) \\ 68284 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) \times (T(T(2)) + (8 \times T(T(6))))) \\ 68287 &:= (((T(T(7)) - T(T(8))))^2) + (T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \\ 68289 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T((8 + T(2)))) - T((T(8)/6))) \\ 68292 &:= (T(2) + ((T(T(9)) \times T((T(2) + 8))) - (T(6)))) \\ 68294 &:= (-T(4) + ((T(T(9)) \times T((T(2) + 8))) - (6))) \\ 68295 &:= (-T(5) + (T(T(9)) \times ((T(2) + 8) \times 6))) \\ 68297 &:= (-7) + ((T(T(9)) \times T((T(2) + 8))) - (6)) \\ 68328 &:= (T((T(8) \times 2)) \times (-((3 - 8)) + T(6))) \\ 68339 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) + (8 + T(6))) \\ 68344 &:= (-T(4) + ((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8 - T(T(6)))) \\ 68347 &:= (-7) + ((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8 - T(T(6))) \\ 68349 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)))) - (T(8)/6)) \\ 68352 &:= ((2^{5+3}) \times (T(8) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68354 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T((T(5) + T(3)))) \times (8 + T(T(6)))) \\ 68355 &:= ((T(5) + ((T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(8))) \times T(6)) \\ 68373 &:= (-3) + (T(7) \times (T(T((3 + 8))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68375 &:= (((-T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3)) + 8)) + (T(6))) \\ 68376 &:= (((6 + T(7)) + 3) \times 8) \times T(T(6)) \\ 68382 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T(T((T(8)/3))) - (-T(8) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 68384 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(8)) \times T((T(3) + 8))) - (6))) \\ 68394 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - (3 + T((T(8) + (6))))) \\ 68397 &:= (((T(7) + 9) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 8) + (T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68415 &:= (T(5) \times (1 + T(-((T(4) - T((8 + 6)))))) \\ 68418 &:= (((T(81) - T(T(4))) - 8) \times T(6)) \\ 68434 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + 3)) \times (4 + T(8))) - 6) \\ 68439 &:= ((T(9) \times ((-T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 8) - T(T(6))) \\ 68442 &:= (((T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + T(4)) \times T(8)) + 6) \\ 68445 &:= (T((5 + T((-4) + T(4)))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68448 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(4) \times T(4))) + (8 \times T(T(6)))) \\ 68467 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(6) \times T((T(4) \times 8))) + (T(6)))) \\ 68499 &:= (9 \times ((9 \times T((4 + T(8)))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68535 &:= ((T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times (-5 + T(8))) - 6) \\ 68541 &:= (T(T((1 + T(4)))) \times ((-T(5)) + T(T(8)))/T(6)) \\ 68544 &:= (-4) \times ((4 - T((5 \times 8))) \times T(6)) \\ 68547 &:= ((T(T((7 + 4))) \times (-5 + T(8))) + (6)) \\ 68549 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T((-4) + T(5))) + 8) + T(T(6))) \\ 68562 &:= ((T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))) \times (-5 + T(8))) + (T(6))) \\ 68565 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((T(6) + (5))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68577 &:= (((T(7) + 75) \times T(T(8))) - (T(6))) \\ 68586 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(8)) - T(5)) \times T((8 + 6)))) \\ 68589 &:= (-9) - (T(T(8)) \times ((T(T(5)) + 8) - T(T(6)))) \\ 68592 &:= (((-2) + T((9 + 5))) \times T(T(8))) - (6) \\ 68595 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(95) - 8) + T(6))) \\ 68598 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (T((9 + 5)) - (8 - 6))) \\ 68628 &:= (((T(8) + 2) \times T(6)) \times 86) \\ 68634 &:= (((T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times T((6 + T(8)))) + (6)) \\ 68649 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((-T(6)) + T(T(8))) + (6)) \\ 68655 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (-5) \times ((-T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 68684 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (8 \times T(T(6)))) \times (8 - T(T(6)))) \\ 68694 &:= (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times (T(6) + T(T(8)))) - (6)) \\ 68712 &:= (((-T(2)) - T(T((1 \times 7)))) \times (-8) \times T(6)) \\ 68733 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((3 + T(T(7))) \times (8 \times T(6)))) \\ 68739 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((-3) + T(T(7))) \times (8 \times T(6))) \\ 68742 &:= (T(2) \times ((4 - T(T(7))) \times (-T(8) + T(6)))) \\ 68769 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) \times 7) - (T(T(8)) \times 6)) \\ 68775 &:= (-5) \times (((7 - T(7)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) \\ 68781 &:= (((T(18) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(8))) + (T(6))) \\ 68796 &:= ((T(69) \times T(7)) + T((8 \times 6))) \\ 68829 &:= ((9 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(8)) - (T(T(8)))) - (T(6))) \\ 68832 &:= (((2^3) \times T(8)) \times (8 + T(T(6)))) \\ 68838 &:= ((T(8) - 3) \times (T((8 \times 8)) + (6))) \\ 68848 &:= ((T(T(8)) - 4) \times (8 \times (-8) + T(6))) \\ 68849 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8) - (T((-8) + T(6)))) \\ 68859 &:= (((-T((9 + 5))) \times (8 - T(T(8)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 68892 &:= (((-T(2)) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(8)) \times T((8 + 6)))) \\ 68894 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - (T(T((8/8) + 6)))) \\ 68895 &:= (-T((5 \times 9))) + (T(T(8)) \times T((8 + 6))) \\ 68919 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T((1 + 9))) - 8) - (T(6))) \\ 68921 &:= (((-1) - T(2)) + T(9))^{T(8-6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68922 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (2 \times ((T(9) \times T(8)) + T(6)))) \\ 68925 &:= (((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(8)))) - 6 \\ 68928 &:= ((8^2) \times (T(T(9)) + ((T(8) + (6)))) \\ 68934 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(3) + T(9)))) - (T(T(8)) \times 6)) \\ 68942 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + ((-4) + T(9))^{T(8-6)}) \\ 68943 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(T((4+9))) - T((T(8) + (6)))) \\ 68949 &:= -(((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) - ((-9) \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 68952 &:= (((T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(8)))) + (T(6))) \\ 68957 &:= (-T(7)) + (-5) \times ((9 - T(T(8))) \times T(6))) \\ 68982 &:= (((T((T(2) + 8)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(8))) + (6)) \\ 68985 &:= (((5 \times T(T(8))) - T(9)) \times T((T(8)/6))) \\ 68997 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(9)) \times T((9+8))) - (6)) \\ 69014 &:= -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(10)) \times T(9)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 69015 &:= -((T(5) \times (T(10) - T(96)))) \\ 69024 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(09)) - 6) \\ 69054 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 5) \times T(09)) - (T(6))) \\ 69114 &:= (((T((T(4) + 1)) + 1) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(6))) \\ 69124 &:= (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1) + T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69132 &:= ((T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(3)))) + T((1 + T(9)))) \times T(6) \\ 69144 &:= (((4 - T(T(T(4)))) - 1) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6)) \\ 69168 &:= (8 \times ((T(T((6+1))) + T(T(9))) \times 6)) \\ 69174 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times (T((1+9)) + (6))) \\ 69178 &:= (((T(8) + T(7)) \times T((1 + T(9)))) - (6)) \\ 69195 &:= (-5) \times ((-9) \times T(T((1+9)))) + (T(6)) \\ 69204 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 02) \times T(9)) - 6) \\ 69222 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(2) + T(T(2)))) - (T((-9) + T(6)))) \\ 69223 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69224 &:= (-T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(2+2)))) \times T(9)) - (T(6)) \\ 69225 &:= (-T((5^2))) \times ((2 \times 9) - T(T(6))) \\ 69228 &:= (T(8) \times (((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times 9) - (T(6)))) \\ 69231 &:= (((T(T(T(1+3)))) - 2) \times T(9)) + (T(6)) \\ 69234 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(3^2)) - ((T(9) + T(6)))) \\ 69237 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(3) \times T(2)))) - (9 \times T(6))) \\ 69242 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69244 &:= (T(T(4)) - (((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times (-T(9))) + (T(6)))) \\ 69246 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((4 \times T(T(2)))) - (9 \times 6)) \\ 69249 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(2) - ((9 \times 6)))) \\ 69257 &:= -((T(7) + T(5))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69258 &:= (-T(8)) - ((T(T((5 \times 2))) \times (-T(9))) + (6)) \\ 69261 &:= (((1 - T(T(T(6-2)))) \times (-T(9))) + 6) \\ 69264 &:= ((4 \times T((6 \times 2))) \times (-9) + T(T(6))) \\ 69271 &:= ((-1) - T(7)) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69272 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + 7) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69273 &:= (-T(T(3))) + ((T(T((7 + T(2)))) \times T(9)) - 6) \\ 69276 &:= ((T((-6) + T(7))) - 2) \times (T(9) + T(T(6))) \\ 69279 &:= ((T(9) \times T((7 + T(2)) + T(9))) - (T(6))) \\ 69282 &:= (T(2) + ((T(T((8 + 2))) \times T(9)) - (T(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69284 &:= (-T(4)) + ((T(T((8+2))) \times T(9)) - (6)) \\ 69285 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(T((8-2))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69286 &:= (-((6+8)) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69287 &:= (-7) + ((T(T((8+2))) \times T(9)) - (6)) \\ 69288 &:= (8 \times ((T(8) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 9) + (T(6))) \\ 69291 &:= -((1 \times 9)) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69294 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((9-2)) \times T(9))) - (6)) \\ 69295 &:= (-5) - (((T(T(9)))/(-T(2))) + T(9)) \times T(T(6)) \\ 69297 &:= (-T(-((7-9))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69299 &:= -((9/9)) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6))) \\ 69311 &:= (11 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69312 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(1+3)))) \times T(9)) + 6) \\ 69315 &:= (T(5) + ((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69321 &:= ((T(T(T((1^2) + 3))) \times T(9)) + (T(6))) \\ 69322 &:= (22 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69323 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 2) + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69324 &:= (((4^{T(2)}) + 3) \times T(T(9))) - (T(6)) \\ 69325 &:= ((5^2) + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69333 &:= (33 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69334 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69336 &:= ((6^3) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69339 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(9) - (6))) \\ 69342 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((-T(4)) + T(T((3+9)))) + T(T(6))) \\ 69344 &:= (44 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69345 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times ((-3) + T(T(9))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69348 &:= (-T(T(8))) + (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) - T(T(6))) \\ 69349 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((-T(3)) + T(T(9)))/T(6)) \\ 69351 &:= (((1 + T((5 + T(3)))) \times T(T(9))) + (6)) \\ 69354 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(5) \times 3)) + (9 \times 6)) \\ 69355 &:= (55 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69357 &:= ((T(T((7+5))) \times T(T(3))) + T(96)) \\ 69363 &:= (((T(3) \times T((T(6) + T(3)))) + T(T(9))) \times T(6)) \\ 69366 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(6) + 3))) + ((T(9) + T(6)))) \\ 69375 &:= -((T(5) \times ((T(7) + 3) - T(96)))) \\ 69377 &:= (77 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69378 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(7))) + 3) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(6)) \\ 69384 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (8 - T(3))) \times T(9)) - 6) \\ 69388 &:= (88 + (T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69405 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(04))) \times 9) + (T(6)))) \\ 69411 &:= (((1 + 1) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) + (T(6)) \\ 69414 &:= (((-((4-1)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6))) \\ 69415 &:= (T((T(5) + 1)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(6)))) \\ 69423 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - (T(2)^{T(4)}) - (T(9) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 69424 &:= (T(4) + (((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - (T(6)))) \\ 69426 &:= ((T(6) \times 2) \times T(((4 \times 9) + T(6)))) \\ 69427 &:= ((T(T(7)))/(-2)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69429 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(2) + T((T(4) + T(9)))) - (6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69432 &:= (T(2) + ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - 6)) \\ 69434 &:= (-((T(4) - (3^{T(4)}))) + (T(9) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 69435 &:= (-((T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times T((9 + T(6)))))) \\ 69437 &:= ((-7) + (3^{T(4)})) + (T(9) \times T(T(6))) \\ 69441 &:= (((1 - T(T(T(4)))) - 4) \times (-T(9)) + 6) \\ 69442 &:= (T(2^4)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + 6)) \\ 69445 &:= ((T(5) + 4) \times T((T(4 + 9)) - 6)) \\ 69447 &:= (-7) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (-4 \times T(9))) - (T(6))) \\ 69453 &:= (3 \times ((T(5) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(9) + 6)))) \\ 69454 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(5) - 4)) \times (T(T(9)) - 6))) \\ 69459 &:= ((9^5) + (T(4) \times (T(T(9)) + 6))) \\ 69462 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) - 4) \times (T(9) + 6))) \\ 69465 &:= -((T(5) \times ((T(6) + 4) - T(96))) \\ 69472 &:= ((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - T(T(6))) \\ 69474 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-T(7))) - 4) \times (-T(9))) - 6) \\ 69477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(7) - T(4)))) + ((T(9) + 6))) \\ 69478 &:= (((8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))))/9) + 6) \\ 69479 &:= (-((T(9) + 7))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + T(T(6))) \\ 69483 &:= ((T(T(3)) + T(8)) \times (T(49) - 6)) \\ 69484 &:= (T(T(4)) - (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69489 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(T(8 - 4)))) + (9 \times T(6))) \\ 69492 &:= (T(2) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (9 \times T(6)))) \\ 69495 &:= ((T(5) \times (-9)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69498 &:= (((8 + T(T(9))) + T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(6))) \\ 69504 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + 05) \times T(9)) - (T(6))) \\ 69519 &:= (((T(T(9 + 1))) + 5) \times T(9)) - 6) \\ 69522 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((T(T(2))^5) \times 9) - T(T(6)))) \\ 69525 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + ((T(5) - T(96)))) \\ 69531 &:= ((1 + T(((3 \times 5) + 9))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 69534 &:= -(((T(T(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(9)))) + 6)) \\ 69543 &:= (-3) - (((T(T(T(4))) + 5) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6))) \\ 69546 &:= (((T(T(6 + 4))) + 5) \times T(9)) + (T(6)) \\ 69547 &:= (T(7) + (((T(T(T(4))) + 5) \times T(9)) - 6)) \\ 69549 &:= (((9 - T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6)) \\ 69552 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(55) \times T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69564 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-6) + T((5 + T(9)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 69573 &:= (3 \times ((T(7) \times T((-5) + T(9))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69575 &:= (T((T(5) + 7))) \times (5 + (T(9) \times 6)) \\ 69576 &:= ((67 \times T(5 \times 9)) + T(T(6))) \\ 69588 &:= ((8 \times T(8)) + (T((T(5) + 9)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 69594 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + ((5 + 9) \times T(6))) \\ 69597 &:= (T((T(7) + 9)) \times (T((5 + 9)) - 6)) \\ 69615 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T((1 + 6))) - T(9)) \times T(6)) \\ 69621 &:= (((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(-((T(6) - T(9)))))) + (T(6))) \\ 69624 &:= ((T(T(4 + T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) - 6) \\ 69625 &:= (T((5^2)) + (T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69629 &:= ((T(T(9 - 2))) \times (6 - T(T(9))))/(-6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69642 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) + 6)) \\ 69645 &:= (T(5) + (T((4 + 6)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69651 &:= ((T(T(-((1 - 5)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) + (T(6))) \\ 69654 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (-T(5) - T(T(6)))) \times (T(9) - 6)) \\ 69657 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(5) - ((6 - 9)))) + T(T(6))) \\ 69678 &:= ((T(T(8)) - ((-7) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(9))) \times T(6)) \\ 69693 &:= (-3) + ((T(T(9)) + (T(6))) \times (T(9) + T(6))) \\ 69696 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times T(((T(6) + T(9))/6)) \\ 69697 &:= ((T(T(7)) - 9) + (T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69726 &:= ((T((T(6) - T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(9) - T(6)))) \\ 69727 &:= (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(T(2) + 7))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6))) \\ 69732 &:= ((T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(7) + (T(9) \times 6)) \\ 69734 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + (9 \times T(T(6)))) \\ 69735 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times (-7) + T(96)) \\ 69741 &:= (T(((1 - T(4))^{-7+9}) \times T(6)) \\ 69744 &:= (((-T(4)) - (T(T(4)) \times T(7))) \times (-T(9))) - 6) \\ 69747 &:= ((74 - 7) \times (T(T(9)) + 6)) \\ 69753 &:= (((T(3)^5) - T(7)) \times 9) + T(6) \\ 69756 &:= (T(6) - (T(5) \times (7 - T(96)))) \\ 69762 &:= ((T((T(2) + T(6))) - ((7 - 9))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 69765 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T((6 + 7))) + T((9 + T(6)))) \\ 69768 &:= ((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(9)))/6) \\ 69776 &:= -(((T(T(6)) + T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(9)))/6)) \\ 69783 &:= ((3 - (-8) \times (T(T(7)) + 9)) \times T(6)) \\ 69789 &:= ((T(9) \times (T((8 \times 7)) - T(9))) - 6) \\ 69795 &:= (((-5) + T(9)) + 7) \times T((9 \times 6)) \\ 69825 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(9 - 6)))) \\ 69828 &:= (T(((8 + T(T(2))) + 8) \times (T(9) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69835 &:= (-5) + (T(-((3 - 8))) \times T(96)) \\ 69846 &:= (T(6) + ((-4) - T((T(8) + T(9)))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 69849 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 8)) + (9 \times T(6))) \\ 69852 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((-5) - T((T(8) + T(9)))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 69855 &:= (T(5) + (T(5) \times T((8 \times (-9) + T(6)))) \\ 69858 &:= (((8 \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) + T(T(9))) \times 6) \\ 69861 &:= (T(T(-((1 - 6)))) + (T((T(8) + T(9))) \times T(6))) \\ 69864 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(6) - 8)) \times T(9)) - (T(6))) \\ 69876 &:= ((T((T(6) - 7))) \times T(T(8))) - (9 \times 6) \\ 69879 &:= (-9) + ((-7) - T((T(8) + T(9)))) \times (-T(6)) \\ 69888 &:= ((8 \times 8) \times ((T(8) + T(T(9))) + (T(6)))) \\ 69891 &:= (((T(T((1 + 9))) + 8) \times T(9)) + T(T(6))) \\ 69927 &:= ((7 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(9) + T(6)))) \\ 69942 &:= (T(T(2)) + (((T(T(T(4))) + 9) \times T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 69945 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((-4) - T((9 \times 9))) \times T(6)) \\ 69948 &:= ((T((8 + 4)) + 9) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 69951 &:= ((T(-((1 - 5))) + (T((9 \times 9)))) \times T(6)) \\ 69954 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(9)) - T(T(9 - 6))) \\ 69955 &:= (-5) \times (-5) + (T((T(9) - 9)) \times (-T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

- 69963** := $(-3) + (69 \times (T(T(9)) - (T(6))))$
69966 := $(T(T(6)) - (6 - (T((9 \times 9)) \times T(6))))$
69969 := $((T((T(9) - (6))) \times (T(9) + T(9))) - T(T(6)))$
69972 := $(T((T(2) \times 7)) + (T((9 \times 9)) \times T(6)))$
69978 := $-((T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times ((9 + T(9))/6)))$
69984 := $((4 \times T(8)) \times ((9 \times 9) \times 6))$
69993 := $((3 + 9) + T((9 \times 9)) \times T(6))$
70128 := $(T(8) \times ((2 + T(T(10))) + T(T(7))))$
70288 := $(8 \times (T(T(8)) - (-20) \times T(T(7))))$
70434 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(3) + 40)) - (T(T(7))))$
70488 := $-((T(88) \times (T(4) - T(07))))$
70531 := $((T(T((1 + 3))) \times T(50)) + T(T(7)))$
70735 := $((5 \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(70) \times T(7))))$
70756 := $((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + (7)) \times T(07)$
70848 := $((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times (80 + T(7)))$
70896 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times (8 \times 07))$
70948 := $((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - (0 - T(7))$
71139 := $(-9) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-11) \times T(7))$
71145 := $(T(5 \times T((4 - 1))) \times T(17))$
71148 := $(T(T(T(T(8/4)))) \times (11 \times T(7)))$
71162 := $(T(T((2 \times 6) + 1)) \times 17)$
71176 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(7) \times 11)) + T(7))$
71198 := $(T(8) + (T(91) \times 17))$
71225 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T((2 + 2)))) \times (1 + T(T(7))))$
71253 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(5)^{T(2)})) + T((-1) + T(7)))$
71268 := $((T(8) + T(T(6)))^2 - T(-(1 - 7)))$
71282 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8))^2 - (1 \times 7))$
71283 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(8))^2 + ((1 - 7)))$
71295 := $(T(5) \times T((T(9) \times 2) + (1 \times 7)))$
71308 := $((T(80) \times (T(T(3)) + 1)) + T(7))$
71325 := $((T(5)^2) \times 317)$
71372 := $((T((T(2) \times T(7))) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)) - T(7))$
71379 := $(9 \times (-7) + (T(T(3)) \times T((-1) + T(7))))$
71414 := $((T((T(4) - 1)) \times T((T(4) + 1))) - (T(T(7))))$
71424 := $(T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (4 \times T((1 + 7))))$
71427 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))) - (1 + T(7)))$
71428 := $((T((T(8) - 2)) \times T(T((4 + 1)))) + T(7))$
71442 := $((T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-1) + T(7))$
71448 := $(-8) + ((-T(T(4)) + T(T(T((4 - 1)))) \times T(T(7))))$
71453 := $(-3) + (((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) + 1) \times T(T(7)))$
71456 := $((T((6 + T(5))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((1 \times 7))))$
71457 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + (1 + T(T(7))))$
71462 := $(T(T(2)) - (((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times (-1)) \times T(T(7))))$
71463 := $(T(T(3)) \times T(((T(6 + 4)) - 1) + T(7)))$
71469 := $(-9^6) + (T((T(T(4)) - 1)) \times T(T(7)))$
71554 := $((T(T(T(4)))/(-5) \times (-T(T((5 + 1)))) + (T(T(7))))$
71568 := $(T(((8 + 6) \times 5) + 1)) \times T(7)$
71595 := $((T(T(5)) + 9) \times (T(T(5)) + T((1 + T(7))))$
71596 := $((T(((T(6) + T(9)) + (5))) + 1) \times T(7))$
71632 := $((T(T((-2) + T(3))) - T(T(6))) \times (-1) - T(T(7)))$
71644 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) - 1)))) - (T(T(7)))$
71655 := $((T(T(5)) + T((T(5) \times 6))) \times 17)$
71679 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-6) \times (1 + T(7))))$
71685 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(8) + T(6))) \times (-1) + T(T(7)))$
71694 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times T((6 + 1))) - (T(T(7)))$
71728 := $(-8) - ((T(T(2)) + (T(71))) \times (-T(7)))$
71733 := $(-3) + ((T(3) + T(71)) \times T(7))$
71736 := $((T((6 - 3)) + T(71)) \times T(7))$
71774 := $(T(4) + ((7 + T(71)) \times T(7)))$
71778 := $(T((-8) + T(7))) + ((T(71) \times T(7)))$
71786 := $(-6) - ((-8) - T(71)) \times T(7))$
71827 := $((T((T(7) \times 2)) \times T((8 + 1))) + (7))$
71828 := $(T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(T(2))) - 8))) \times 17)$
71862 := $((2 - T(T(6))) + T(T((8 - 1))) \times T(T(7)))$
71865 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(((T(T(8)) - 1)/7))))$
71925 := $(-5) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T((9 - 1))) \times T(T(7))))$
71927 := $((T(T((7 + T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times 17)$
71928 := $(T(T(8)) \times (-2 \times 9) \times (1 - 7))$
71947 := $((T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9)))) - T(17))$
71955 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-5) \times T(T(9)) + T((-1) + T(7)))$
71974 := $((47 \times T(T(9 + 1))) - T(T(7)))$
72138 := $((T(8) - 3) \times (-1) + (T(2)^7))$
72156 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5) + 1)/2))) \times T(7))$
72178 := $(T(T(8)) + ((T(71) - 2) \times T(7)))$
72184 := $((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(8 + 1))) + T(2))) \times T(7))$
72194 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(9) - 1)))/T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)))$
72198 := $((-T(8)) + (T(T(9)) \times T((1 + T(2)))) \times 7)$
72226 := $((T((T(6) - 2)) \times T((T(2)^{T(2)}))) + T(T(7)))$
72268 := $((8 \times T(6)) + T((2 + 2))) \times T(T(7))$
72275 := $((57 + 2) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))))$
72282 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(8)))) - (T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7))))$
72288 := $(T(8) \times (-8) + T(((T(2)^2) \times 7)))$
72289 := $(-T(98)) + (T((T(T(T(2))) - 2)) \times T(T(7)))$
72324 := $(T((-4) + T((T(2) \times 3))) \times (T(2) \times T(7)))$
72338 := $((T(8) \times T((3 \times T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7)$
72345 := $((T(5) - (T(4) \times T(T((3^2)))) \times (-7))$
72348 := $((T(8) \times T((T(4) \times T(3)))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7))))$
72349 := $(-9) - ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7))))$
72352 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))$
72353 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(5) \times T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))))$
72354 := $((T(T(4)) \times 5) - (T(3))^2) - (7)$
72356 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(3)) - T(2) - T(T(7)))$
72359 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3)) \times T(2) - T(T(7)))$
72365 := $((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(2))) - T(T(7))$

$$\begin{aligned}72369 &:= ((9 + T((T(6) - T(3)))) \times T((T(T(T(T(2))))/7))) \\72393 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - (9 \times T(3))) \times (T(2) + T(T(7)))) \\72394 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(9))) - (T(3) + 2)) \times 7) \\72401 &:= ((-T(10)) \times (-T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\72424 &:= (4 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(-(T(2) - T(7))))) \\72429 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(2)) + (4))) - T(2)) \times 7) \\72432 &:= ((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(4))^2) - (7))) \\72435 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(34)) + T(T(2 + 7))) \\72436 &:= (((T(T((6 + 3))) \times (-T(4))) + 2) \times (-7)) \\72448 &:= ((T(T(8)) - ((T(4) \times T(4)))) \times (2^7)) \\72464 &:= (-((4 - (6^4) \times 2)) \times T(7)) \\72468 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(6))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))))/7) \\72478 &:= (((-T(8)) + T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))) \\72482 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \times T((4 + T(T(T(2)))))) + 7) \\72488 &:= (T((8 + 8)) \times (-T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(7))) \\72491 &:= (-1) + (((T(T(9)) \times T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 7) \\72492 &:= ((2 + T((T(9) - (4)))) \times (T(2) \times T(7))) \\72499 &:= ((9 + (T(T(9)) \times T(4)) - 2) \times 7) \\72512 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(-(1 - 5)))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(7)))) \\72524 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(((2 + T(5)) \times T(2)))) - T(T(7))) \\72527 &:= (T((7 + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5)) + (2 \times T(T(7)))) \\72528 &:= (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(2)) + T((T(5) + T(2)))) \times T(T(7)))) \\72532 &:= (-2) + (T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(7)))) \\72534 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) \\72548 &:= ((T(8) \times T((4 \times T(5)) + T(2))) - T(7)) \\72549 &:= -(T(T(9)) - (T((4 \times (T(5) + T(2)))) \times T(7))) \\72555 &:= (T(5) \times ((-T(T(5))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))))) + 7) \\72557 &:= (((T(7) + (5)) \times T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(7)))) \\72562 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) \times T(5))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))) \\72568 &:= (-8) + ((6^5)/T(2)) \times T(7) \\72569 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(6))) - T((5 + 2))) \times 7) \\72576 &:= (-6) \times ((7 + 5)^{T(2)}) \times (-7) \\72577 &:= (T(T(7)) + (((T(7) + (5)) \times (T(2)^7))) \\72582 &:= (T(T(2)) + (T(8) \times T((T(T(5) - 2)) - T(7)))) \\72585 &:= (T(5) \times (-T(8)) - (-T(5)) \times T(-(T(2) - T(7)))) \\72618 &:= (((T((8 + 1)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 7) \\72624 &:= (((T(T(4)) - 2) - T(T(6))) \times (-2) - T(T(7))) \\72625 &:= (-((5^{T(2)})) \times (T(T(6)) - (2 \times T(T(7)))) \\72639 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6) - T(2))) \times 7) \\72644 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times (-2) + T(7)) \\72645 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(4)) + (T((T(6) - T(2))) \times T(7))) \\72655 &:= (-5) + (T(5) \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 7)) \\72674 &:= ((T(4) + ((7 + 6)^2)) \times T(T(7))) \\72675 &:= (57 \times T((T((6 \times 2)) - T(7))) \\72684 &:= (T(4) + ((8 + T((T(6) - T(2)))) \times T(T(7))) \\72688 &:= (-88) \times (-T(T(6))) - T((T(T(2)) + T(7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72695 &:= (-5) \times (((9 \times T(T(6))) - 2) \times (-7)) \\72699 &:= (-T(9)) + (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)) \times 7) \\72723 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T((2 + 7))) - T(T(2))) \times 7) \\72729 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (T(72) \times 7)) \\72732 &:= ((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(((T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)))/T(7))) \\72737 &:= (((7 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T((7 + 2))) - (T(7))) \\72739 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 7) - (-2) + T(7)) \\72744 &:= ((T((-4) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7))) \times (T(T(2)) \times 7)) \\72758 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(5)) + T(T(7))) - 2) \times 7) \\72762 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(T(6)) \times (7 \times T((2 + 7)))) \\72764 &:= (((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\72765 &:= ((T(5) \times T(6)) \times T(((7 \times 2) + 7))) \\72769 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) \times 7) - ((T(2) - (7)))) \\72772 &:= ((-2) \times T(T(7))) + (T(72) \times T(7)) \\72779 &:= (((T(9) \times T((-7) + T(7))) + 2) \times 7) \\72785 &:= (-T(5)) + ((8 \times T((T(7) - T(2)))) \times T(7)) \\72786 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) \times 7)) \\72792 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(9) \times 7)) + 27) \\72793 &:= ((T((T(3) \times 9)) \times (7^2)) + T(7)) \\72796 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(9) \times 7)) + (T(2) + T(7))) \\72825 &:= (5 \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(8) \times (2 - T(T(7))))) \\72828 &:= (((T((8 - T(2))) + T(8))^2) \times T(7)) \\72835 &:= (5 \times (T(T(T(3))) + ((8^{T(2)}) \times T(7)))) \\72842 &:= ((2 \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2)))) - T(T(7))) \\72844 &:= (-T(4)) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) \times 2) - T(T(7))) \\72847 &:= (-7) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) \times 2) - T(T(7))) \\72848 &:= (-T(T(8))) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-8) \times T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) \\72849 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7) \\72854 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(5) + T(8))) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(7))) \\72855 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(5) - ((T(8)/T(2)) \times T(T(7)))) \\72856 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + (82)) \times T(7)) \\72857 &:= (((-7) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7))) \\72864 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(8) + T(27))) \\72881 &:= -(T((1 + T(8))) + (T((T(8) \times 2)) \times (-T(7)))) \\72884 &:= (((-4) + T((T(8) + T(8)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7) \\72885 &:= (T(5) \times (8 + T((8 + T(T(2))) \times 7))) \\72893 &:= (((T(3) \times (9 + T(8)))^2) - (7)) \\72895 &:= (-5) + ((T(9) \times T(8)) \times T((2 + 7))) \\72899 &:= (((T(9) \times T(9)) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))) - (7) \\72912 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((1 + T(T(9))) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)))) \\72918 &:= (-T(T(8))) + (T((T(-(1 - 9)) \times 2)) \times T(7)) \\72922 &:= -(T(T(2)) - (((T(T(2)) \times T(9))^2) + T(7))) \\72923 &:= ((T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 7) \\72924 &:= (-4) + (((T(T(2)) \times T(9))^2) + T(7)) \\72925 &:= (-5) + (T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) \times T((T(2) + (7)))) \\72926 &:= ((T(6) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9)) - 2)) \times 7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72927 &:= (T((7 + T((2 + 9)))) \times 27) \\72928 &:= (((8 - 2) \times T(9))^2) + T(7) \\72943 &:= ((T((T(3) + T(4))) + T(9)) \times (-T(2)) + T(T(7))) \\72945 &:= ((T(5)^4) - (-T(9)) \times T((T(2) + T(7)))) \\72948 &:= (T((-8) + T(T(4)))) - (-T(9)) \times T((2 \times T(7))) \\72949 &:= (-9) - ((-T(T(4))) \times T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - (T(7))) \\72955 &:= (-5) + (-T(T(5))) \times ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7))) \\72961 &:= ((1 + 6) \times ((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))) \\72963 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((6 \times (9 + 2)))))/(-7)) \\72964 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T((6 + T(9)))) + T(T(2))) + T(7)) \\72966 &:= ((-T(6)) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((9 + 2)))))/(-7)) \\72967 &:= ((-T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((9 + 2)))))/(-7)) \\72968 &:= (((-8) - (T(T(6)) \times T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-7) \\72975 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-9) - T(2)) + (7)) \\72988 &:= (-8) + ((T((8 \times 9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) \\72996 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (-9) + T(((9 \times 2) + 7))) \\73017 &:= (T((T(7) - 10)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) \\73062 &:= (T((T(T(T(2))) + (60))) \times (-T(3) - T(7))) \\73065 &:= (-T(5)) - (-((60 \times 3)) \times T(T(7))) \\73125 &:= ((T(5)^2) \times T((-((1 \times 3)) + T(7))) \\73143 &:= ((3^4) \times T((T((1 \times 3)) \times 7))) \\73154 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(51)) + T(T(T(3)))) - 7) \\73185 &:= (T((5 + T(8))) \times (1 - (-3) \times T(7))) \\73192 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(13))) + (T(7))) \\73206 &:= (T(6) \times T((T(T((0 - 2) + T(3)))) + (T(7)))) \\73227 &:= ((7 \times T(2)) \times (T(T((2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\73233 &:= (T(3) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T((2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\73234 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(7))) \\73245 &:= (T(5) \times (4 + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7)))) \\73248 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2))) - 3) \times T(7))) \\73255 &:= ((T(T(5)) - 5) \times (T(T((2 \times 3))) + T(T(7)))) \\73264 &:= ((-T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(23) + T(7)) \\73269 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))) - ((T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) \\73273 &:= (-3) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(T(3)))))) \times T(7)) \\73276 &:= ((T((T(6) + 7))) + T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(T(3)))))) \times T(7) \\73278 &:= ((8 + T(T(7))) \times ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\73286 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(8)) \times T(23)) - T(T(7))) \\73288 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times ((T(T(8)) - T(T(2)))/T(3))) + T(7)) \\73293 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(9^2) \times (T(3) - T(7)))) \\73297 &:= (((7 + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(7)))) \\73332 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(3) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(7)))) \\73346 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \times (-3) + T(T(7))) \\73348 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times T((-T(3) + T(T(3)))) + (T(7))) \\73353 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(5) \times T(T((3 + 3)))) + T(7)) \\73359 &:= (T(T(9)) + (((T(T(5)) + 3) \times T(T(3))) \times T(7)) \\73368 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(63) - T(3)) + T(7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73369 &:= ((T((T(9) + T(6))) \times 33) + T(T(7))) \\73374 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(3) \times T(7))) \\73388 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(8))) - (T(T(3))/3)) \times T(7)) \\73392 &:= (((T(2) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(3) - T(7))) \\73416 &:= ((-6) + T((T((1 + T(4))) + (T(3)))) \times T(7)) \\73428 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times 2) \times T(T(4))) + (T(3) \times T(7))) \\73458 &:= (T((T(8) - T(5))) \times (T((4 + T(T(3)))) - 7)) \\73472 &:= ((T((T(2) \times T(7))) - T(43)) \times T(7)) \\73478 &:= (-8) + ((T(7) + T((-4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(7))) \\73482 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(T(8)) - 4) \times 37)) \\73486 &:= (((T(6) \times 8) + T(4) + 3) \times T(T(7))) \\73492 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(9) + T((T(4) + T(3)))) \times T(T(7)))) \\73493 &:= (((3 + T(9)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)))) \\73514 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times ((1 + T(5)) \times 3)) - (T(T(7)))) \\73524 &:= (4 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(5) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))))) \\73528 &:= ((T((T(8) \times 2)) - (5 - 3)) \times T(7)) \\73536 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 7))) \\73538 &:= (((8 \times 3) \times T(T((T(5) - 3)))) - (T(T(7)))) \\73539 &:= (-T(9)) + (T((-3) + T(5)) \times T(3)) \times T(7)) \\73545 &:= (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) + T(7)))))) \\73548 &:= (-T(8)) + (T((4 \times (T(5) + 3))) \times T(7)) \\73549 &:= (9 + T(4)) \times ((T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\73563 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T(T((6 + 5)) + T(3))) \times T(7))) \\73569 &:= (T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(3)) - T(T(7)))) \\73574 &:= -((T(4) - (T((75 - 3)) \times T(7))) \\73577 &:= ((T(7) \times T((75 - 3))) - 7) \\73582 &:= (-2) + (T((T(8) \times (5 - 3))) \times T(7)) \\73584 &:= (T(((T(4) - 8) \times T((5 + 3))) \times T(7)) \\73594 &:= (T(4) + (T((9 \times (5 + 3))) \times T(7)) \\73625 &:= (-((5^{T(2)}) \times (6 - T((T(3) + T(7)))) \\73626 &:= (-T(6)) \times ((2^6) - T((3 \times T(7)))) \\73629 &:= (T(9) + (T(((2 \times 6) \times T(3))) \times T(7)) \\73634 &:= (-T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-6) + T((-3) + T(7)))) \\73644 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) + (T(6))) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\73647 &:= ((T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) + (T(6))) \times (3 \times 7)) \\73648 &:= (-8) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(6)^{T(T(3)/7)})) \\73655 &:= ((T(5) \times T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) - T((T(3) + T(7)))) \\73656 &:= ((-T(65)) - T(T(6))) \times (-3) - T(7)) \\73668 &:= (((T((8 + T(6))) \times 6) + T(T(3))) \times T(7)) \\73675 &:= (-5) \times (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(37))) \\73676 &:= (-((6 - ((7 \times 6)^3)) - T(T(7))) \\73681 &:= ((-1) + ((T(8) + (6)^3)) - T(T(7))) \\73682 &:= (((T(2) \times (8 + 6))^3) - T(T(7))) \\73688 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(8)))/6) - T(T(T(3)))) - 7) \\73689 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) - 6) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(7)))) \\73695 &:= (-T(5)) + (T(9) \times ((T(T(6)) + 3) \times 7))\end{aligned}$$

73697 := $-(T((7 + T(9))) - (T(T(6)) \times T((-3) + T(7))))$
73724 := $((T(T(4)) + (-2^7)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(7))$
73725 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + (-7) \times T(37))$
73728 := $(T(8) \times (2^{7-3+7}))$
73748 := $((8 + T(-(T(4) - T(7)))) \times (T(3) + T(T(7))))$
73749 := $((T((9 + T(4))) - 7) \times (-3) + T(T(7)))$
73752 := $((T(T(2)) + T((5 + 7) \times T(3))) \times T(7))$
73773 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(73)) + T(T(7))))$
73794 := $((T(T(4)) \times 9) + 7) \times T(T(3)) \times 7$
73812 := $(-T(2)) + (T((1 + T(8))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 7)))$
73815 := $(T((5 + 1) + 8)) \times T(37)$
73824 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times (-T(8) + (-3) \times T(7)))$
73828 := $-(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(2)) + T(8))^3 + T(T(7))))$
73835 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(8)) - T((T(3) + 7))$
73836 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(3))) \times (T((8 \times 3) - 7))$
73839 := $(T(9) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(83) + T(7))))$
73842 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - (T(3) + 7)))$
73843 := $((3 + T(T(T(4)))) - T(8)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(7))$
73844 := $((-T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times 8)) \times (-T(3)) - (T(T(7)))$
73853 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(5))) \times (T(T(8)) + 3) - (T(T(7))))$
73857 := $(7 \times ((T(5) \times T(T(8))) + T((T(T(T(3)))/7)))$
73863 := $(3 \times (-T(6)) + (T(T(8)) \times 37))$
73864 := $((T(4) + T((6 + T(8 + 3)))) \times T(7))$
73885 := $(5 \times ((8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 7)$
73889 := $(-9) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(8)))/T(3)) - T(7))$
73892 := $((T((2 \times 9)) + (8 + 3)) \times T(T(7)))$
73894 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 9) \times (8 \times T(3)) + (T(T(7))))$
73895 := $((T(T(5)) - 9) \times T(T(8))) - (3 + T(7))$
73898 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(8 + 3))) - T(7))$
73913 := $((T(T(T(3 + 1)))) \times (T(9) + 3) - 7)$
73934 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (3 + T(9))) + (T(T(3)) - 7))$
73935 := $((-53) \times T(9)) \times (-3) - T(7))$
73942 := $(-T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) + 3)) + (T(7)))$
73944 := $(-4) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) + 3)) + (T(7)))$
73948 := $((-8) \times T(T(4))) + T(T((9 + 3))) \times T(7)$
73962 := $((T((T(2) \times 6)) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 7)$
73975 := $((T(T(5)) - T(7)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) + 7)$
73979 := $((T(9) \times T((T(7) - 9) \times 3)) - T(T(7)))$
73982 := $((T(T(T(T(2))) + T(8))) \times T(9)) + (3 - T(T(7)))$
73983 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(8) + T(T(9 + 3)))) + T(T(7)))$
73984 := $-(T(T(T(4))) - 8) - ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(7))$
73986 := $((T(6) + T(8)) \times (T((9) + T(3))) - T(7))$
73987 := $((T(7) \times T(8 \times 9)) - 3) + T(T(7))$
73995 := $(-5) \times (T(T(9)) + (-T(9) - T(3)) \times T(T(7)))$
74046 := $(-T(6)) \times (-40 - T((T(4)) + T(7)))$
74088 := $((T(T(8)) - (-T(8) \times T(T(04)))) \times T(7))$
74137 := $((T(7) + T(T(3))) \times ((1 + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7))))$

74145 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((-1) + T(T(4)) + T(7))))$
74182 := $(2 \times (((T(T(8)) + 1) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(7))))$
74214 := $((41 - T(2)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 7)))$
74222 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(2)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(7)))$
74223 := $((T((T(T(3)) + 2))^2 - T((T(T(4)) + 7)))$
74228 := $((8 + T(2)) \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times T(7)))$
74229 := $(-T(T(9))) - ((2^{T(T(2))}) \times T((T(T(4)) - 7)))$
74235 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) - (2 \times T((T(4) \times 7))))$
74241 := $(T(T((-1) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(7))))$
74245 := $(-5) - (-T(T(4))) \times (T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) - (T(7)))$
74253 := $(3 \times (-T(5)) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))))$
74256 := $((T((T(6) + T(5))) - T(2)) \times (4 \times T(7)))$
74257 := $((-T(7) - T(52)) \times T(T(4))) + 7)$
74268 := $(T(8) \times (T((T(6) \times T(2))) + 47))$
74277 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) - 2)) + T(T(4))) \times 7$
74278 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(7))))$
74284 := $((4 \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) \times T(7)$
74289 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(8) \times 2)) - T(T(-((4 - 7))))$
74298 := $((8 + T(9 \times 2)) + 4) \times T(T(7))$
74318 := $(8 \times (-1) + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7))))$
74326 := $((T(6) \times (2^{T(3)})) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(7))$
74328 := $((T(T(8))^2)/T(3) - 4) + T(T(7))$
74333 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times 4))) - (T(T(7))))$
74334 := $((T((4 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(4) + T(7))))$
74349 := $(-9) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(T(7))))$
74352 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-5 - (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7))$
74355 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(T(4)) - 7)$
74358 := $((T(8) + T((T(5) \times T(3)))) \times (-T(4) - T(7)))$
74368 := $((T(8) + 6)^3 + (T(4) \times T(7)))$
74379 := $((T(T(9)) \times 73) - T((T(T(4)) - 7)))$
74382 := $(T((T(2) + 8)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - T(7)))$
74384 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)) \times (3 \times (T(4) + T(7))))$
74385 := $((T(5) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) \times (-4 - 7))$
74394 := $((-T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(9))) - T((T(T(3)) + 4))) - (T(T(7)))$
74398 := $(8 \times (9 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7))))$
74424 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-4) + T(7))$
74428 := $((8 \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) + (T(7)))$
74429 := $((T(9) \times (T((2 + T(T(4)))) + T(4)) - (T(T(7))))$
74439 := $(-9) + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) \times T(47))$
74442 := $((T(2)^{T(4)}) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(4)) - 7))$
74448 := $(T(8) \times (44 \times 47))$
74452 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) + 4)) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(7)$
74466 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(6) \times 4)) - (-4) + T(7)))$
74473 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(47))))$
74492 := $((2 \times T(T(9))) \times T((4 + 4)) - T(7))$
74495 := $((-5 \times 9) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-47)$
74496 := $((T(6) - 9) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(4)) - 7))$

$$\begin{aligned} 74514 &:= (-T((T(4)+1)) \times ((5-T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))))) \\ 74518 &:= (T((T(8)+1)) \times (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) + (T(7)))) \\ 74527 &:= ((72 \times T(T((5+4)))) + (7)) \\ 74528 &:= (8 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(54)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 74532 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-3) + (5 \times T((T(4) \times 7)))) \\ 74535 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(3) \times 5) \times T((T(4) \times 7))) \\ 74536 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(T(3)) - (5)))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T(7))) \\ 74542 &:= (2 \times (-4) + (T(5) \times T((T(4) \times 7)))) \\ 74543 &:= (((3 \times T(4)) \times T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) - 7) \\ 74562 &:= (2 \times (6 + (T(5) \times T((T(4) \times 7)))) \\ 74565 &:= (T(5) + ((6 \times 5) \times T((T(4) \times 7))) \\ 74592 &:= ((T(T((2+9))) + T(T(5))) \times (4 + T(7))) \\ 74594 &:= ((T(T(-(4-9)))) \times (5^4)) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 74613 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times (T((1 + T(6))) - (T(4) \times (-7)))) \\ 74628 &:= (T(8) + (T(T((2+6))) \times (4 \times T(7)))) \\ 74642 &:= (((T(-(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + 7) \\ 74648 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times 4) + (6-4)) \times T(7)) \\ 74655 &:= (T(5) \times (T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) + (T(T(4)) - T(7)))) \\ 74659 &:= (-T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) + 64) \times T(T(7))) \\ 74663 &:= (-T(3)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) - T(T(7))) \\ 74664 &:= (T((T(4) + (6))) \times (T(6) + T((4 + T(7)))) \\ 74669 &:= ((T(T(T(9-6)))) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) - (T(T(7))) \\ 74673 &:= (((T(-(3) + T(7))) \times T(T(6))) + (4)) - T(T(7))) \\ 74676 &:= (((-6) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) \times (-4 \times 7)) \\ 74682 &:= -(((T(T(2)) - (8 \times T(6))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 74683 &:= -(((T(T(3)) + (((-8) - T(T(6))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 74704 &:= ((T((40+7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) \\ 74725 &:= (5 \times ((T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7) \\ 74727 &:= ((-T(7) + T((2 + T(7)))) \times T(-(T(4) - T(7)))) \\ 74732 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T((3 \times T(7))) - T(4))) - (T(7))) \\ 74736 &:= ((T(6) + T(3)) \times (T(74) - 7)) \\ 74746 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (T(4) + T(7))) \\ 74749 &:= (T(9) + ((T(47) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7))) \\ 74784 &:= (-4) \times (((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(4))) + (7)) \\ 74787 &:= ((-7) - T(T(8))) - ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7)) \\ 74788 &:= ((-T(8)) + ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(4))) \times 7 \\ 74794 &:= (-T((4 \times 9))) - ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7)) \\ 74802 &:= (T(20) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4) \times T(7))) \\ 74822 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((2 + T(T(8))) \times (4 \times T(7)))) \\ 74823 &:= (T((3 \times 2)) \times (T(84) - 7)) \\ 74826 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(2)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4) \times T(7))) \\ 74832 &:= (((T((2^{T(3)})) \times T(8)) - T(T(4))) + (7)) \\ 74834 &:= (-T(4)) - (-T((3+8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))))) \\ 74837 &:= (-7) - (-T((3+8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))))) \\ 74844 &:= ((T(T(T(4)))/(-T(4))) \times ((-8) \times T(4) - T(T(7)))) \\ 74851 &:= ((-1) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(T(8)/4)) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 74854 &:= ((T((-4) + T(5))) \times T((-8) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74855 &:= (-5) \times (5 - (T(8) \times (T(4) + T(T(7)))))) \\ 74862 &:= (((T((2^6)) \times T(8)) + T(4)) - T(7)) \\ 74865 &:= (-T((5 \times 6))) \times (-8 - T((T(4) + (7)))) \\ 74872 &:= (((-((T(2) - 7)) \times T(T(8))) + T(4)) \times T(7)) \\ 74892 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (9 \times T(8))) + (T(T(4)) - (7))) \\ 74893 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + ((T((9 \times 8)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 74899 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((T((9 \times 8)) + T(4)) \times T(7))) \\ 74908 &:= ((T(8) \times T((09 + T(T(4)))) + (T(7))) \\ 74922 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((9 + T(T(4)))) + 7)) \\ 74925 &:= ((T(5)^2) \times (-T(9)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(7)))) \\ 74926 &:= (((T(6) - T(2)) \times T(T(9))) \times 4) + T(T(7))) \\ 74928 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 9) \times (4 \times T(7))) \\ 74929 &:= -((T(T((9+2))) - (T((9+T(4))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 74938 &:= (((T(8) + T((T(3) + T(9)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(7)) \\ 74942 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(-(T(4) - 94)))) - (T(7)) \\ 74963 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((-6) - (-9) \times T(4))) - (7)) \\ 74964 &:= (-4) \times (-T(6) + (T(9) \times (-T(4) - T(T(7)))))) \\ 74965 &:= (-5) + (T(6) \times T((T(9+4)) - (7)))) \\ 74975 &:= (5^7) + ((T(9) \times T(4)) \times (-7)) \\ 74976 &:= ((6 + T((7+9))) \times T((4 + T(7)))) \\ 74982 &:= (2 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(-(4-7)))))) \\ 74985 &:= (T(5) + ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times (T(4) \times 7))) \\ 74987 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (T(89))) \times (T(4) + 7)) \\ 74998 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 7) \\ 75075 &:= ((5 \times T((70-5))) \times 7) \\ 75122 &:= -((T((T(2 \times T(T(2)))) - 1)) - ((5^7))) \\ 75123 &:= -((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) - (1 + (5^7))) \\ 75174 &:= (T(T((4+7))) \times (-1 - (5 \times 7))) \\ 75184 &:= (-T(4)) + ((T((T(8) - 1)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) \\ 75187 &:= (-7) + ((T((T(8) - 1)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) \\ 75194 &:= ((T(((4 \times 9) - 1)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) \\ 75222 &:= (T((T(2)^{T(2)})) \times (T((T(2) + T(5))) + T(7))) \\ 75229 &:= (((T(9) - 2)^{T(2)}) - T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))) \\ 75243 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 75245 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times (-4)) \times T(T(2))) + (5^7)) \\ 75246 &:= ((T((T(6) \times 4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((-5) + T(7))) \\ 75247 &:= (((T(T(7)) - T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + 7) \\ 75248 &:= ((-T(T(8))) - T(T(-(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) + ((5^7))) \\ 75249 &:= (-9) + (T(T((4 \times 2))) \times (T(T(5)) - (7))) \\ 75252 &:= (-T(T(2))) + (T(T((5 + T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (7))) \\ 75254 &:= (-4) + (T(T((5 + T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (7))) \\ 75255 &:= (T(5) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T(2) - T((5 \times 7)))) \\ 75257 &:= ((7 + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) \times T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) \\ 75258 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((5^{T(2)}) - (5 + 7))) \\ 75264 &:= (((-4) \times T(6)) \times (-2^5)) \times T(7) \\ 75268 &:= -(((T(T(8)) - 6) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(5)))) - T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

- 75275** := $-((T((5 \times T((7 - 2)))) - (5^7)))$
75277 := $(((-7) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2))) + (5^7)$
75285 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(8) + 2)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(7))))))$
75286 := $((((-T(6)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(T(7))))$
75287 := $((T((7 + T(8))) \times (-T(2))) + (5^7))$
75288 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(8) \times T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(7)))$
75292 := $(2 \times ((9 \times T(T((-2) + T(5)))) - (T(7))))$
75328 := $((T(82) + T(T(3))) \times (T(5) + (7)))$
75335 := $((T((5 \times T(3))) \times (-T(3))) + (5^7))$
75339 := $(-9) + ((3 \times T(3)) \times T(T(-((T(5) - T(7))))))$
75342 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(5)) + T(7))))))$
75347 := $-((T(74) + ((3 - (5^7)))))$
75348 := $(T(8) \times ((T((4^3)) - T(5)) + T(7)))$
75353 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(5) - 3)) + (5^7))$
75364 := $((4 - T(T(6))) \times ((-3) \times T(T(5))) + T(7))$
75376 := $((6 + T(73)) - T(5)) \times T(7)$
75379 := $-((T(9) + T(73)) - (5^7))$
75384 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(((T(8) + T(T(3))) - (5)))) - (T(T(7))))$
75424 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) - (T((T(5) - (7))))))$
75425 := $((((5 + 2) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 5) \times 7)$
75427 := $((7^2) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + T(7))$
75432 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(5) - (7))))))$
75435 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(7))))))$
75437 := $((T(7) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (-5 + T(7))$
75453 := $(T(T(3)) \times (((T(T(5))/4) \times T(T(5))) - (7)))$
75455 := $(T(5) + (T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7)))$
75466 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) - (T(5))) + T(T(7))$
75468 := $((T(8) \times (-6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 57$
75472 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + 7)$
75473 := $((T(T(3)) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(5) - T(7)))$
75474 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) + (T(4)/5) \times 7)$
75475 := $(T(T(5)) - ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) \times (-7))$
75479 := $-(((T((T(9) + T(7))) - T(T(4))) - (5^7)))$
75481 := $(((-1) + T(8)) \times T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) + (T(T(7)))$
75482 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-4)) + (5^7)))$
75485 := $((-5) \times T((8 \times 4))) + (5^7)$
75487 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(57)))$
75488 := $((8 + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) + (57)))$
75494 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))))$
75495 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(9) - T(4)))) + (T(5) \times (-7)))$
75497 := $-((T((-((T(7) - T(9))) + T(T(4)))) - (5^7)))$
75516 := $((-6) \times ((-1) - T(5)) - T(5)) \times T(T(7))$
75518 := $((T(T(8)) \times ((-1) + T(T(5))) - (5))) - T(T(7))$
75522 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T((T(2) + T(5))) + (T(5))) \times T(T(7))))$
75523 := $((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))$
75524 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))$
75528 := $(T(8) \times (-2) + ((5 \times T(5)) \times T(7)))$
75534 := $-((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))))$
75542 := $((-T(2) - T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))))$
75557 := $((T((7 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(5) + T(7)))$
75565 := $((T(T(5)) \times (6 \times T(5))) - (5)) \times 7$
75569 := $-((T(((T(9) + T(6)) + (5))) - (5^7)))$
75571 := $(-1) + ((T((7 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) - T(7))$
75572 := $((-2) + T((T(7 + 5)) - (5))) \times T(7)$
75576 := $(67 \times T(((5 \times T(5)) - T(7))))$
75577 := $((T((T(7) + (7))) \times T(T(5))) - (-5 + T(7)))$
75579 := $-((T(T(T(9 - 7)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))))$
75581 := $(-1) + (T((T(8) + T(5))) \times 57)$
75582 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times T((T(5) + T((T(5) - (7))))))$
75585 := $-((T(5) - (8 \times T(5)) \times T((5 \times 7))))$
75586 := $((-6 + 8) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))))$
75588 := $((T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (5 + 7)$
75591 := $((1 \times 9) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))$
75593 := $((T(3) \times T((9 + 5))) \times T(T(5))) - (7)$
75594 := $((T(-((T(4) - T(9)))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(-((5 - 7))))))$
75595 := $(-5) \times (-((T(9 \times 5)) \times T(5))) + T(T(7))$
75597 := $-((T(-((7 - 9))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))))$
75599 := $((9/9) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7))))$
75605 := $((T(T(5)) \times (0 - T(6))) + (5^7))$
75615 := $(-T(5)) \times (-1 - ((-6) \times T(T(5))) \times (-7))$
75622 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T((T(2 \times 6)) - (5))) \times T(7)))$
75624 := $(-4) + (T((T(2 \times 6)) - (5))) \times T(7)$
75625 := $((5 \times T(T(-(2 - 6))))^{-5+7})$
75628 := $(T(((T(8) \times 2) + (6 - 5))) \times T(7))$
75635 := $(-5) \times ((-((T(3) \times T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - (7))$
75636 := $((6^{T(3)}) - (T(T((-6) + T(5)))) \times (-T(7)))$
75642 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T((6 + 5))) - T(7)))$
75645 := $((-5) \times T((T(4) + T(6)))) + (5^7)$
75648 := $((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (6 \times (T(5) - (7))))$
75683 := $-(((T(T(3 + 8))) + T(T(6))) - (5^7))$
75684 := $((4 \times (T(T(8)) + (6))) + (T(5))) \times T(7)$
75686 := $-((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-6) + T(T(5)))) - (7)))$
75699 := $-((T(T(9)) - ((T(9) \times T(6))/5) \times T(T(7))))$
75708 := $((80 \times T((T(7) + T(5)))) + T(7))$
75726 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(2) \times T(7))) + T((T(5) - (7))))$
75728 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + ((7 - (5^7))))$
75734 := $((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(7)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))$
75744 := $((T(4) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(7)))$
75752 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(5)) - (7))) + (5^7))$
75762 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - T((5 + 7))))))$
75764 := $((T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(75) - T(T(7))))$
75768 := $((8 \times T(T(6))) \times ((T(7) - T(5)) + T(7)))$

$$\begin{aligned}75769 &:= (((-T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(5) + (7)))) \\75773 &:= (((-3) \times T(7)) \times T(7)) + (5^7) \\75779 &:= -((T(-(9 - 77))) - (5^7)) \\75784 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - T(8))) \times (T(T(7)) - (5))) - (T(T(7)))) \\75785 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(8)) - (7)) \times (5 - T(7))) \\75786 &:= -((T(68) - (7 + (5^7)))) \\75789 &:= ((-9) + T(8)) \times ((T(T(7)) - (5)) \times 7) \\75792 &:= (((T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) \times T(T(7))) + (T((-5) + T(7)))) \\75796 &:= (((T(6) + T((T(9) + T(7)))) - (T(5))) \times T(7)) \\75812 &:= ((2 + T((-1) + T(8))) \times T(T(5))) - T(7) \\75823 &:= (((3 + 2) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(5)) - (7))) \\75824 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2))) \times T((T(8) - T(5)))) - T(T(7))) \\75828 &:= ((-T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-8 - T((-5) + T(7))) \\75845 &:= -(((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(8))) - (5^7))) \\75846 &:= (6 \times (T(T(4)) - ((T(8) - (5)) \times T(T(7)))) \\75852 &:= ((T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(T((8 + 5))) + T(7))) \\75853 &:= -((T((T(3) \times T(5))) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(7))) \\75855 &:= (-5) \times (-T(5) - (T(8) \times (T(5) + T(T(7)))) \\75888 &:= (-T(8)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(8) + T((5 + 7)))) \\75914 &:= -((T(T((T(4) + (1^9)))) - (5^7))) \\75922 &:= -((T(2) - (2 \times 95))) \times T(T(7)) \\75923 &:= -((T(T((T(T(3))/T(T(T(2)))))) - ((9 + (5^7)))) \\75924 &:= (T(T((4 \times 2))) \times (9 - (T(5) \times (-7)))) \\75925 &:= (T(T((5 \times 2))) + (T(9) \times T(57))) \\75927 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) - (-5 - T(T(7)))) \\75935 &:= ((-5) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(9)) - (5^7)) \\75936 &:= -(((T(T(6)) - T((-3) + T(9))) \times (T(T(5)) - (7))) \\75937 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(9)) - (-T(5) - T(T(7)))) \\75938 &:= ((83 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))) - (7)) \\75943 &:= (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9) + (5))) - 7) \\75946 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(9) \times T(57))) \\75964 &:= ((4 + (-T(6)) \times (-9 - T(T(5)))) \times T(7)) \\75967 &:= (((T(7) \times T(6)) + T(9)) \times T(T(5))) + (7) \\75978 &:= ((-T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9))) \times T(T(T(-(5 - 7)))) \\75993 &:= ((T(3) + T(T(9))) \times ((9 \times 5) + T(7))) \\75998 &:= ((T(T(8))/9) \times (T(T(9)) - (T(5) - (7)))) \\76125 &:= -((T((T((5 + 2)) + 1)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(7)))) \\76195 &:= ((-T(5)) - T(T((9 + 1)))) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\76215 &:= (T(5) \times (-1 - (T(T(T(2))) \times (6 - T(7)))) \\76222 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times T(26)) + T(T(7))) \\76223 &:= (((T(3) \times T(T((2 + 2)))) \times T(T(6))) - (7)) \\76224 &:= (((-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) - T((T(6)/7))) \\76225 &:= (-5) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T((T(6)/7)))) \\76242 &:= (((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))) - 2) \times (-T((T(6)/7))) \\76243 &:= (T(3) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) + (7))) \\76244 &:= (((T(4) + (4))^{T(2)}) - T(6)) \times T(7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76245 &:= (T(5) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)))))/T(7)) \\76246 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) - 2) \times 6) + T(7) \\76248 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(4) + T((2^6))) + T(7))) \\76249 &:= (-9) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) + T(7)) \\76258 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times T((2 \times T(6)))) + T(T(7)) \\76263 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) + T((2^6))))/7) \\76264 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))) + (6 + T(7))) \\76265 &:= (5 \times ((T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) + 7)) \\76272 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T((7 + T(2))) \times T(T(6))) + (7))) \\76286 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (T(82))) \times T(6)) - T(7)) \\76288 &:= (-8) - (-T((8 \times 2))) \times T((T(T(6))/7)) \\76293 &:= (((-3) - T(T(9)))/(-2)) \times (T(6) \times 7) \\76325 &:= (5^2) \times (T(T((T(3) + (6)))) - (T(7))) \\76328 &:= (((-(8^2)) + T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(7)) \\76329 &:= (-9) \times (T((T(2) \times 3)) + (-T(6) \times T(T(7)))) \\76335 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) + (7)))) \\76342 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\76349 &:= ((T((T(9 + 4)) - T(3))) \times T(6)) - T(T(7)) \\76351 &:= ((-1) - T(T(5))) \times ((T(3) - T(T(6))) - T(T(7))) \\76366 &:= (((T(6) + T(6))^3) + T(67)) \\76398 &:= (((T(8) \times 9) - 3) \times (T(T(6)) + (7))) \\76405 &:= ((50 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T((6 + T(7)))) \\76428 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + (6 + T(T(7)))) \\76433 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (((T(3) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))) - T(7))) \\76434 &:= (-T(T(4))) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\76455 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(5)) + T(4)) \times (T(6) \times T(7)))) \\76461 &:= ((1 - (-6) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T((T(6)/7)))) \\76468 &:= (((T(8) - T(T(6))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) \times T(7)) \\76482 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(6))) \times 7)) \\76488 &:= (8 \times (T(T((T(8)/4))) - (-T(6) \times T(T(7)))) \\76492 &:= ((-T(2)) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\76493 &:= ((-T(3)) \times (-T(9) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) - (7)) \\76495 &:= (T((5 \times 9)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(7)))) \\76524 &:= ((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)))) \\76531 &:= (T(13) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)))) \\76545 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T((T(4)/5))^6) \times (-7)) \\76546 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5))) \times 6) + T(T(7)) \\76552 &:= (((T(2)^5) \times T(5)) \times T(6)) + (7) \\76555 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T((T(5) + T(6))) - T(7))) \\76564 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (-T(6)) + (5^{-T(6)+T(7)}))) \\76566 &:= ((T(6) \times 6) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)))) \\76584 &:= ((4 \times T(8)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)))) \\76589 &:= ((T(9) \times T((-8) + T((5 + 6)))) - T(T(7)) \\76593 &:= (-T(3)) + (9 \times (-T(5)) - (-T(6) \times T(T(7)))) \\76594 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) + (5))) - T((T(6) + (7)))) \\76615 &:= (T(T((5 - 1))) \times ((6 \times T(T(6))) + (7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76618 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(16) - T(6))) + T(7)) \\ 76632 &:= ((T((T(2) \times 3) - T(T(6))) \times (-6 - T(T(7)))) \\ 76635 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(T(3)) \times T((-6) + T((6 + 7)))))) \\ 76642 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))) + (6) + T(T(7))) \\ 76678 &:= ((-8) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + (6)))) \times 7 \\ 76689 &:= (-T(9)) + (((8 \times T(6)) + T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 76692 &:= ((2 \times T((9 \times 6))) - T(T(6))) \times T(7) \\ 76695 &:= (T(5) + (9 \times (-6) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 76698 &:= (-T(8)) + ((9 \times T(6)) \times T((T(6) + (7)))) \\ 76713 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T((-1) + T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(7)))) \\ 76724 &:= (-T(4)) + (((2 + 7) \times T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 76725 &:= ((5 \times T((2 + T(7)))) \times T(T(6)))/7 \\ 76727 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((2 + 7) \times T(6))) - (7)) \\ 76732 &:= (-2) + (((T(3) \times T(7)) + T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 76734 &:= (((-4) + T(3)) + (7)) \times T(6) \times T(T(7)) \\ 76741 &:= (((1 - T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) + (7) \\ 76744 &:= (T(4) + (T((T(T(4)) - T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(7)))) \\ 76748 &:= ((T((T(8 + 4)) + (7))) \times T(6)) - (7) \\ 76755 &:= ((T(T(5)) - (5 \times 7)) \times T((6 \times 7))) \\ 76762 &:= (((-((T(2) + (6))) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) + T(7)) \\ 76779 &:= (T(9) - ((T(T(7)) - T((T(7) + (6)))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 76783 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(((T(8) + T(7)) + T(6)))) + T(7) \\ 76798 &:= (T(8) + (((-9) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) + T(7)) \\ 76855 &:= (-5) + ((5 \times T(8)) \times (T(6) + T(T(7)))) \\ 76859 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(58) + (6))) - T(T(7))) \\ 76869 &:= (9 \times (-((T(6) - T(8))) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 76875 &:= (((T(T(5)) - (7)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-7))) \\ 76888 &:= ((-T((8 \times 8))) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(6) + (7)) \\ 76893 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (9 \times (-8) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 76912 &:= (T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) \times ((T(9) + T(T(6))) + T(7))) \\ 76923 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(2) - ((-9) + T(6)) \times T(7))) \\ 76934 &:= ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times ((-T(9)) - T(T(6)) + (7))) \\ 76937 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(3))) \times 9) + T(T(6))) - T(7) \\ 76942 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(9)))/T(6)) + 7 \\ 76944 &:= (4 \times ((T((4 \times 9)) + T(6)) \times T(7))) \\ 76959 &:= ((T(9) \times 5) - ((-9) \times T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 76962 &:= ((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) - ((-9) \times T(6)) \times T(T(7)) \\ 76965 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-((T(6) \times T(9)) - T(T((6 + 7)))) \\ 76972 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(7)) \times 9)) + ((T(T(6)) + (7)))) \\ 76992 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(9) \times T(-(9 - 67))) \\ 76995 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times T(-(9 - 67))) \\ 77112 &:= ((T((T(T(T(2))) - (1 + 1))) \times T(T(7))) - T(7)) \\ 77125 &:= (-T(5)) + (T((2 + 17)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 77133 &:= ((T(((3 \times T(3)) + 1)) \times T(T(7))) - (7)) \\ 77222 &:= -((T((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) - (-((2 - 7)⁷))) \\ 77224 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + T((2^{T(2)}))) \times (7 \times 7)) \\ 77226 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(2)²)) \times T((T(T(7))/7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 77228 &:= ((-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-((2 - 7)⁷)) \\ 77229 &:= (9 \times (T(T(2)) + (T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7)))) \times 7)) \\ 77238 &:= (((8 + T(3))^{T(2)}) \times T(7)) + T(T(7)) \\ 77245 &:= (5 \times ((T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7) - (T(7)))) \\ 77248 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 77256 &:= (((T((T(6) + T(5))) \times (-2)) \times T(T(7)))/(-7)) \\ 77264 &:= (-((T(T(4)) - T(T(6)))) \times ((T(T(T(T(2))))/7) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 77265 &:= (T((T(5) - (6))) \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(T(7))/7)))) \\ 77283 &:= (3 \times (T(8) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((7 \times 7)))) \\ 77294 &:= ((T((-4) + T((9 + T(2)))) \times T(7)) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 77295 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((9 \times T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7)))) \times 7)) \\ 77322 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T((2 + 3))) + T(T(7))) \times 7)) \\ 77328 &:= (T(8) \times (T(2) + T((37 + T(7)))) \\ 77329 &:= (((9 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (3 + T(T(7))) + (T(7))) \\ 77343 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T((T((4 \times 3)) + (7))) + T(7)) \\ 77357 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times (T(7) + (7))) \\ 77364 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(3)) + T(7)) - T(T(7))) \\ 77374 &:= (-((4⁷) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + (T(7)))) \\ 77378 &:= (((-T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(7)))) + (T(7))) \\ 77382 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(T((8 + 3))) \times (T(7) + (7))) \\ 77385 &:= (T(T((5 + (T(8)/T(3)))) \times (T(7) + (7))) \\ 77427 &:= (((T((7²)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + 7) \\ 77429 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + (T(7) + T(T(7)))) \\ 77439 &:= (-9) + (-T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(7))) \\ 77445 &:= (T((5 + 4)) \times (T(4) + T((T(T(7))/7)))) \\ 77448 &:= (T(T((8/4))) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times T(7))) \\ 77463 &:= (T((3 \times 6)) \times (47 + T(T(7)))) \\ 77469 &:= ((T(9) + (6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (-7) + T(7))) \\ 77476 &:= ((-6) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(7))) + T(7)) \\ 77483 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times ((8⁴) - T(T(7)))) - (7)) \\ 77488 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) + (4)) \times T(T(7)))/7 \\ 77494 &:= ((T((T(4) + 9)) \times (4 + T(T(7)))) - T(T(7))) \\ 77525 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)) + (5))) \times 7) + (T(7)))) \\ 77532 &:= ((-T(2)) + ((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(7))) \times T(7)) \\ 77537 &:= -((T((T(7) + T(3))) - (((5⁷) + 7))) \\ 77539 &:= (((T(9) - T(T(T(3)))) - 5) \times (-T(T(7))) - 7) \\ 77543 &:= (-3) + ((T((4 + T(5))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) \\ 77546 &:= (((T(T(6)) - (4)) - T((T(5) - (7)))) \times T(T(7))) \\ 77548 &:= -(((T((8 + T(4))) - (5⁷)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 77557 &:= -((T((T(7) + (5))) - (((5⁷) - 7))) \\ 77564 &:= ((T(4) \times (6⁵)) + (-7) \times T(7)) \\ 77572 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-7)) - (-((5⁷)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 77589 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((T(8) \times T((5 + 7))) \times T(7)))) \\ 77599 &:= -((T(T(T(9)/9)) + (-((5⁷)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 77616 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (-((1 - 6) - 7)) \times T(7)) \\ 77622 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 77623** := (((T(32) × T(6)) × 7) + (7))
77637 := (((7³) × T(T(6))) - T((T(7) + T(7))))
77672 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) + (T(67))) × T(7))
77679 := (9 × ((T(T(7)) × T(6)) + (T((7 + 7))))
77685 := -((T(T(5)) - ((-T(8)) + T(T(6))) × (-7) + T(T(7))))
77693 := ((T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) × (T(T(6)) + T(7))) - 7)
77694 := ((T(T(4)) × ((T(T(9)) - (T(6))) + T(T(7)))) - T(T(7)))
77712 := (((T(T(2)) - 1)⁷) - T(T(7))) - (7))
77722 := ((T(2) + (-((2 - 7)⁷)) - T(T(7)))
77728 := ((T((8 + T(2))) - (T(T(7)) × 7)) × (-T(7)))
77729 := -((T(T(9)) - ((-2) - (-7) × T(7))) × T(T(7)))
77746 := -((T((6 × T(4))) + (T(T(7)) × (-7) × T(7))))
77753 := (((T(3) + (5⁷)) - T(T(7))) + T(7))
77756 := ((T(T(6)) + (-5) - T(77)) × (-T(7)))
77769 := (T(T(9)) + ((T((6 + T(7))) - T(T(7))) × T(T(7))))
77775 := (((5⁷) - T(T(7))) + (T(7) + T(7)))
77779 := ((T(9) × T((T(T(7))/7))) + (T(7) × T(7)))
77784 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(8)) - (-T(7)) × T(T(7)))) × (-7)))
77785 := ((T(T(5)) × (T(T(8)) - T(7))) + (T((7 × 7))))
77824 := ((4^{T(T(2))}) × (-T(8)) + T(T((T(7)/7))))
77826 := (T(6) + (T((2 + T(8))) × T((7 + 7)))
77845 := (-5) × (T(T(4)) + (T(8) × (-T(7) - T(T(7))))
77888 := -((8 × 8) × (8 - T((7 × 7)))
77894 := (((4 × T(9)) × T((T(8) - 7))) - T(T(7)))
77895 := (-5) × (T(9) + (T(8) × (-T(7) - T(T(7))))
77896 := (((T(6) + T(9)) × T(8)) + T(T(7))) × T(7))
77922 := ((T(2) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-((T(9) + T(7))) + T(T(7))))
77924 := ((T((4^{T(2)})) + T((9 + T(7)))) × T(7))
77946 := (T(T(6)) + (T(T(4)) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) - T(7)))
77952 := (((T(2) - T(5)) × (-9 + 7)) × T(T(7)))
77973 := (T(T(3)) × (T((79 + 7)) - T(7)))
77975 := (((5⁷) - T(9)) - T((7 + 7)))
77983 := (-((T(3) × T(8))) × (T(9) - T(T(7)))) + (7))
78122 := -((T(2) - (-((2 + 1) - 8)⁷))
78127 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(T(2) + 1))))/8) - (T(7)))
78134 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(3) + T((1 + 8)))) - (T(T(7))))
78142 := (2 × ((T(T(4)) × T((1 + T(8)))) + T(T(7)))
78146 := (T(6) + (((4 + (1⁸))⁷))
78148 := ((T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T((-1) + T(8)))))) + (T(7))
78153 := (T(T(3)) + ((5⁻¹⁺⁸) + (7)))
78204 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(02))) × T((8 × 7)))
78225 := (-5) × (T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2))) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(7))))
78228 := (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(2) × T(T(8))) + T(T(7))))
78245 := ((5^{T(4)-T(2)}) + T((8 + 7)))
78246 := (T(6) × ((4^{T(T(2))}) + T(8)) - T(T(7)))
78249 := (T(9) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) × T((8 × 7)))
78252 := (T(T(2)) × (((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(8))) + (T(T(7))))
78255 := (5 × (T((T(5) × T(2))) + (T(8) × T(T(7))))
78256 := ((T(6) + (52)) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))))
78261 := (T(16) + (-((T(2) - 8)⁷))
78267 := (-T((7 × 6))) - ((T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)) × (-T(T(7)))
78272 := ((-2) + T((7²))) × (T(8) + T(7))
78274 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(7))) + ((-T(2)) × T(T(8))) × (-T(7)))
78275 := (((5⁷) - (2⁸)) + T(T(7)))
78288 := ((-T((T(8) + T(8))) - (T(T(T(2))) × 8)) × (-T(7)))
78325 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)))) + (7))
78326 := (((6 × 2) × (3⁸)) - T(T(7)))
78328 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(2) × (3 + T(8)))) + T(T(7)))
78329 := (T((9 + (2^{T(3)}))) × (T(8) - (7)))
78335 := ((5^{T(T(3))/3}) + T((-8) + T(7)))
78344 := -(((T(4) - (T((4 × 3)) × T(8))) × T(7)))
78345 := (-T(5)) × (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(3)) - 8) × T(T(7))))
78346 := (T(T(6)) - ((T(4) - (-((3 - 8)⁷)))
78355 := (-5) + (T(T(5)) × ((-T(3)) + T(T(8))) - (7)))
78356 := (T(T(6)) + ((5^{T(3)+8-7}))
78358 := ((85 - (-3) × T(8)) × T(T(7)))
78362 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) + (-((3 - 8)⁷))
78364 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(3))) + (T(8) + (7))))
78372 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(7)) + T(T((3 + 8))) × T(7))
78393 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(93) - T(T(8))) + T(7)))
78396 := ((T(6) - 9) × ((3⁸) - T(7)))
78408 := (T(8) × (T(T(T(04))) + ((T(T(8)) - T(7))))
78422 := ((T(2) - (-2) × T(T(4))) × (T(T(8)) + T(7)))
78428 := (((T((8²)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) × T(7))
78429 := (-T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2))) × (4 × T((T(8) + (7))))
78432 := ((T(T(2)) - T((T(3) × T(4)))) × (-T(8) + (7)))
78435 := (-T(5)) × (((3⁴) + T(T(8))) × (-7))
78454 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(5)) × (4 + T(T(8)))) - T(T(7))))
78456 := (-T(6)) × (((5 - T(4)) × T(T(8))) - T(T(7)))
78462 := (T(T(2)) + (-6) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T(8) × T(T(7))))
78477 := (((T(T(7)) + 7) × T((T(T(4)) - T(8)))) + 7)
78485 := (5 × (T((T(8) + T(4))) + (T(8) × T(T(7))))
78492 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))) × (T(T(-((4 - 8)))) + 7))
78512 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 1) × T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) - (T(7)))
78518 := ((-((T(8) + 1)) + T(T(5))) × T((T(8) + (7))))
78526 := ((T(62) × (5 × 8)) + T(T(7)))
78531 := (((-1) + T(3))^{T(5)-8}) + T(T(7))
78533 := ((T(T(3)) × T((T((-3) + T(5)) + 8))) - (T(7)))
78535 := (((T(T(5)) - 3) × (5 + T(T(8)))) + T(7))
78539 := ((T(9)³) + ((5 - T(8)) × T(T(7)))
78552 := (-T((2⁵))) + (T(T(5)) × (T(T(8)) - (7)))
78561 := (T((1 × 6)) × T((58 + T(7))))

$$\begin{aligned} 78562 &:= -(((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + T(7)))) \\ 78568 &:= -(((T(86) \times (T(5) - T(8))) - (7))) \\ 78569 &:= -((T(9) \times T(6))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \\ 78573 &:= -(3^7) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) + (7))) \\ 78575 &:= ((5^7) + T(5)) + T((T(8) - (7))) \\ 78579 &:= -((T(9) - ((T((7 + 5)) \times T(8)) \times T(7))) \\ 78582 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(85) + (87))) \\ 78588 &:= (T(8) \times (T((8 + 58)) - T(7))) \\ 78595 &:= (((T(59)/T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + (7)) \\ 78596 &:= (((-T(T(6))) + T((T(T(9))/T(5)))) \times T(8)) - (T(7)) \\ 78622 &:= (-2) - ((T(26) \times (-8)) \times T(7)) \\ 78624 &:= ((-4) \times T(26)) \times (-8 \times 7)) \\ 78625 &:= ((5^{T(2)}) \times ((T(T(6)) - 8) + T(T(7)))) \\ 78634 &:= (T(4) + (T((T(3) + (6))) \times (T(8) \times T(7)))) \\ 78645 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) + T(8) \times 7)) \\ 78652 &:= (((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (6 + T(T(8)))) + T(7) \\ 78669 &:= (T(9) + ((T((6 + 6)) \times T(8)) \times T(7))) \\ 78677 &:= -((T((T(T(7))/7)) - (T(6) \times T(87)))) \\ 78722 &:= -((T(2) - ((T(2)^7) \times T(8)) - (7))) \\ 78725 &:= (((5 - 2)^7) \times T(8)) - (7) \\ 78726 &:= (-6) - ((T(2)^7) \times (-8 - T(7))) \\ 78728 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(8) + T(T(7))) \\ 78731 &:= (-1) - ((3^7) \times (-8 - T(7))) \\ 78732 &:= (((-T(2) - T(3))^7) \times (8 + T(7))) \\ 78733 &:= -((T(3) + ((-3^7) \times T(8)) - (7))) \\ 78739 &:= (((9/3)^7) \times T(8)) + (7) \\ 78748 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times T((7 + 8))) + T(7)) \\ 78764 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(7))) \times (T(8) - (7))) \\ 78774 &:= ((T(4) + T(7)) \times (-7) + T((T(8) + T(7)))) \\ 78792 &:= ((T((2 + T(9)) + T(7))) - T(8)) \times T(7) \\ 78794 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(9)))/(-7)) \times 8) - (T(T(7))) \\ 78822 &:= ((T(2) + T((T(T(2)) + T(8)))) \times 87) \\ 78833 &:= (((T(T(3)) - T(T(3 + 8))) \times (-T(8))) - (7)) \\ 78842 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times 8) - (T(T(7))) \\ 78844 &:= (4 \times (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(8)) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 78846 &:= ((6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(8) + ((8 + 7))) \\ 78848 &:= (((8 \times 4) \times 88) \times T(7)) \\ 78855 &:= (-T(5)) \times (T(5) + (-8) \times (T(T(8)) - (7))) \\ 78868 &:= (((T(8) - (6)) \times T((T(8) + T(8)))) + T(7)) \\ 78884 &:= -((T(4) - T(8)) \times (T((T(8) + T(8))) + T(T(7)))) \\ 78885 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T((8 + 8) - 7))) \\ 78928 &:= (((T(T(8))/T(T(2))) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)))) + (7)) \\ 78939 &:= (((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) - (T(8) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 78943 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(9) + 8))) + (7))) \\ 78967 &:= ((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times ((9 + 8) - T(T(7)))) \\ 78976 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7)) + 9) \times (T(8) + T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79128 &:= ((T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 19) - (T(T(7))) \\ 79135 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(T((3 + 1)))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79138 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 3) - (-T(19)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 79142 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) \times (1 + T(T(9)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 79152 &:= ((2 + T(5)) \times T(-((1 - 97))) \\ 79155 &:= (-T(5)) - ((-5) - T(19)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 79165 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(6)) - T(-((1 - 9)))) \times T(T(7))) \\ 79169 &:= ((T(96) + 1) \times (T(9) - T(7))) \\ 79192 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + T((9 + 1))) \times (T(T(9)) + (7))) \\ 79212 &:= (((-T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) - T(9)))) \times T(7)) \\ 79226 &:= (((T(T(6)))/(-T(2))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(9)))) - (7) \\ 79227 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T((2 + 2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79228 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 9))) + (T(7))) \\ 79232 &:= ((2^{T(3)}) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(9)) - T(7))) \\ 79233 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))))) \\ 79234 &:= (-T(T(4)) + (((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) \times (-T(T(9)))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 79236 &:= (6 \times (-3) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))))) \\ 79242 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9)) + 7) \\ 79244 &:= ((T(((T(4) + T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 79245 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times ((2 + T(T(9))) + T(T(7)))))) \\ 79252 &:= (-2) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 79254 &:= ((T((T(4) + (5))) + T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 79255 &:= (T(((5 + T(5))/2)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79264 &:= (T(4) + ((T(6) \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 79275 &:= (T(5) \times (((T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 9) - 7)) \\ 79276 &:= (T(6) + (T((7 + T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79283 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(8)) \times T((T(T(2)) + 9))) - (T(T(7)))))) \\ 79285 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2))) - T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) \\ 79289 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T((T(8)/T(2)))) - T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \\ 79298 &:= (((-T((T(8) + T(9)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(9))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 79335 &:= (-T(5)) \times (3 + (T(T(3)) \times (-9) \times T(7))) \\ 79342 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(9))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 79344 &:= ((T(4) - T(T((T(4) + 3)))) \times (9 - T(7))) \\ 79362 &:= (T(2) \times (-6) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(9) \times T(7)))) \\ 79365 &:= -((T(5) + ((-63) \times T(9)) \times T(7))) \\ 79373 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times ((T(7) \times 3) \times T(9))) - (7)) \\ 79375 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((7 + 3)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79376 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T((7 + 3)))) \times (T(9) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79387 &:= ((T((T(7) - 8)) \times T((3 \times 9))) + (7)) \\ 79389 &:= (T(9) + (T(8) \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(9))) - 7)) \\ 79392 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79395 &:= (-5) \times (-T(9)) + (-39) \times T(T(7))) \\ 79422 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(((2^4) + T(9)))) \times 7) \\ 79423 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(9)) + (7)))) \\ 79426 &:= (T((T(6) - T(2))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79432 &:= (((-T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9) + 7) \\ 79434 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (-((4 - 9)^7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79436 &:= (-T(T(6))) - (((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(7))) \\ 79442 &:= (((T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - (T(7))) \\ 79443 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T((9 + T(7))))) \\ 79445 &:= (T((T(5) + (4))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79447 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(4)) \times ((4 + T(T(9))) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79458 &:= ((T(T((8 + 5))) - (4)) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79464 &:= ((4 \times T(6)) \times T(((4 \times 9) + 7))) \\ 79465 &:= (T((T(T(5)/6)) + ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7))))) \\ 79472 &:= (2 \times ((T(7) + T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7))) \\ 79475 &:= (((5^7) + T(T(T(4)))) - T((-9) + T(7))) \\ 79477 &:= (((T((T(T(7)/7)) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) + 7) \\ 79485 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T(((4 \times 9) - 7))) \\ 79486 &:= (T(68) + (T((T(4) + 9)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 79488 &:= ((8 \times T(8)) \times T(((4 - 9) + T(7)))) \\ 79489 &:= (-T(9)) + (T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79497 &:= ((-((T(T(7)) + T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(9) + T(7))) \\ 79498 &:= (-T(8)) + (T(T((9 + 4))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79507 &:= ((T(7) + T(05))^{T(9-7)}) \\ 79522 &:= ((T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)))) + 7) \\ 79523 &:= (((T((T(3)^2)) \times T(T(5))) + 9) - T(T(7))) \\ 79524 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(T((-2) + T(5))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79527 &:= ((7 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times ((T(5) \times 9) + T(T(7)))) \\ 79532 &:= ((T((2 \times T(3))) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(9))) - T(7)) \\ 79534 &:= (T(T((T((4 + 3)) - T(5)))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79536 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(5))) \times (9 + 7)) \\ 79553 &:= ((T((-3) + T(5))) \times (-T(5) + T(T(9)))) - (7) \\ 79559 &:= (((-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-T(5)) - T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \\ 79563 &:= ((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) - (T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (-T(7))) \\ 79568 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(6) + (5 \times 9)))) - T(7)) \\ 79569 &:= (-((T(T(T(9 - 6)))) + (T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 79572 &:= ((2 + T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79575 &:= (-((T(T(5)) - (T((7 + T(5))) \times (T(9) \times 7))) \\ 79576 &:= ((T(T(6)) - T(7)) \times ((5 + 9) \times T(7))) \\ 79579 &:= (T(9) + (T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79582 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((-8) + T((T(T(5)) - T(9)))) \times T(7)) \\ 79587 &:= (T(7) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(9)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 79588 &:= (-8) + (T(8) \times T((59 + 7))) \\ 79596 &:= (T((T(6) + T(9))) \times T((5 + T((9 - 7)))) \\ 79624 &:= ((T((4 \times 2)) \times T((T(6) + T(9)))) + T(7)) \\ 79625 &:= ((5^{T(2)}) \times (T(T(T(-((6 - 9)))) + (T(T(7))))) \\ 79629 &:= ((9 + 2) \times (-6) - (T(T(9)) \times (-7))) \\ 79632 &:= (T(2) \times ((3 + (T(6) \times T(9))) \times T(7))) \\ 79637 &:= ((-T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(69)))/7) \\ 79638 &:= (T((T(8)/3)) \times ((-T(6)) + T(T(9))) + (7)) \\ 79646 &:= (-T(6)) + (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times T(9)) - (T(7))) \\ 79648 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) + 6) \times (-9 + T(7))) \\ 79649 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(4) \times 6))) - T((T(9) + T(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79653 &:= ((-T(3)) - (-((5 + 6) \times T(T(9)))) \times 7) \\ 79657 &:= ((T((-7) + T((5 + 6)))) \times T(9)) + (7) \\ 79662 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(69)))/(-7)) \\ 79667 &:= ((((-7) \times T(T(6)))/(-T(6))) \times T(T(9))) - T(7) \\ 79668 &:= (T(8) \times (T(66) + (9 - 7))) \\ 79674 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times ((T(7) - T(6)) + T(9))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 79678 &:= (((T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times 6)) \times (-T(9))) + T(7)) \\ 79682 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(8)) \times T((6 + 9))) - (7))) \\ 79689 &:= (-((T(T(9)) - (((8 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(9))) \times T(7))) \\ 79692 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(6)))/T((9 - 7))) \\ 79693 &:= ((T(3) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(6))))/(-T((9 - 7))) \\ 79694 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (-9 - T(T(6)))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 79695 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times (6 + (9 \times 7))) \\ 79723 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(2) \times T(7)))) + (T(97))) \\ 79724 &:= ((4^{T(T(2))}) - (-T(7)) \times T((T(9) + T(7)))) \\ 79725 &:= ((T(5) \times (-2 - 7)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(7))) \\ 79744 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) + (T((T(7) + 9)))) \times T(7)) \\ 79749 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (T((4 + T(7))) \times T((T(9) - T(7))))) \\ 79758 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(7)) - T((-9 + T(7)))) \\ 79759 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((T(T(5)) + (79)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 79772 &:= ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-9)) + T(7))) \\ 79785 &:= (-T(5)) + (T((T((8 + 7)) - T(9))) \times T(7)) \\ 79815 &:= (T(5) - (T((1 - (T(T(8)))/(-9)))) \times (-T(7))) \\ 79823 &:= ((T(T(3 + 2))) \times T(T(8))) - (97) \\ 79828 &:= (((-8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((8 \times 9))) \times T(7)) \\ 79845 &:= (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - (T((T(T(8))/9)) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 79848 &:= (T(8) \times ((-4) + T((8 \times 9))) - T(T(7))) \\ 79853 &:= (T(3) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - ((T(9) + T(7)))) \\ 79858 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T((T(8)/9)))) - 7) \\ 79859 &:= (-T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - (9 + 7)) \\ 79868 &:= ((T((T(8) - T(6))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(9) + (7))) \\ 79882 &:= ((T(T(-((T(2) - 8)))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(9) - (7))) \\ 79883 &:= ((T(T(-((3 - 8)))) \times T(T(8))) - (9 + T(7))) \\ 79884 &:= (((T((4 + 8)) \times T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(7)) \\ 79892 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) \times (8 \times T(9))) - (T(7))) \\ 79893 &:= (3 \times (-T(9)) + (T(8) \times T((T(9) - (7))))) \\ 79899 &:= ((T(T((T(9)/9))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(9 - 7)))) \\ 79913 &:= ((T(T((T(3) - 1))) \times T(T(9 - 9))) - 7) \\ 79924 &:= (((T(4) + T(2)) + T(9)) \times T((T(9) + (7)))) \\ 79926 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((T(2) + T(T(9)))/T((9 - 7)))) \\ 79927 &:= ((T(T((7 - 2))) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + (7)) \\ 79928 &:= (8 \times ((T(2) \times T((9 \times 9))) + T(7))) \\ 79933 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(9)))/(-9))) + 7) \\ 79948 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T((4 + (9/9)))) + T(7)) \\ 79956 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(7)))) \\ 79968 &:= ((T(T(8)) - T((T(6) - 9))) \times T((9 + 7))) \\ 79982 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(8))/9)) + T(T(9)))) - (T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

- 79994** := $(T((T(T(4)) - 9) \times ((9 \times 9) - 7)))$
80352 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times T(08))$
80385 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + T(-((T(3) - T(08))))$
80545 := $((5^4) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(08))))$
80583 := $(-3) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(08)))$
80595 := $((T(5) \times T(9)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(08))))$
80625 := $(-(5^{T(2)})) \times (T(6) - T(T(08)))$
80655 := $(T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-6) - T(T(08))))$
80755 := $(-5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-7) - T(T(08)))$
80892 := $((T(T((2 + 9))) + T(8)) \times T(08))$
80955 := $(-5) \times ((-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(08))$
81142 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(11)) \times T(8)))$
81144 := $((T(T(4)) \times 41) - 1) \times T(8)$
81251 := $(-1) - (((T(T(5)) + 2) \times (-1)) \times T(T(8)))$
81252 := $((-2) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(2 \times 18))$
81276 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T((T(7) - 2)) + 1)) - T(8))$
81312 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (1 + T(-((T(3 + 1)) - T(8))))$
81396 := $((6 + T(9)) \times T(((T(3) + 1) \times 8)))$
81432 := $((T(T(2^3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) \times T(8)$
81445 := $((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T((4 + 1))) \times T(T(8)))$
81455 := $(-5) \times (-((5^{T(4-1)})) - T(T(8)))$
81528 := $(T(82) + 5^{-1+8})$
81537 := $((7 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T((1 \times 8))))$
81542 := $(-((T(T(2)) + ((4 - T(T(5))) \times T((1 + T(8))))$
81543 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T((51 + T(8))))$
81544 := $(-4) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times T((1 + T(8))))$
81548 := $((-((8 - 4)) + T(T(5))) \times T((1 + T(8))))$
81549 := $(-((T(T(9)) - ((4 + T(T(5))) \times T(T((1 \times 8))))$
81564 := $((T(4) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(T(5)) - 1) \times T(T(8))))$
81627 := $(T((7 + T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T((1 \times 8))))$
81647 := $(-T(7)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T((6 \times (1 + 8))))$
81657 := $((T(7) + T(5)) \times (T(61) + 8))$
81684 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 8)) + (T((T(6) + 1)))) \times T(8))$
81694 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((9 \times 6)) + 1)) - T(8))$
81738 := $((8 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T((T(7) - 1)) - T(8))$
81745 := $(-5) \times (-(((4^7) + 1)) + T(8))$
81746 := $(-((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(7)))) - (-1) + T(T(8))))$
81747 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((7 - 1)))) + T(T(8))$
81765 := $(T(T((T(5) - 6))) \times (71 + 8))$
81774 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(77)) \times 18)$
81784 := $((4 \times 8) \times T(71)) - 8$
81795 := $((T(T(5)) + T((9 - 7))) \times (-1) + T(T(8)))$
81843 := $((T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) \times (T(8) + 1)) + T(8))$
81864 := $((-4) + T((68 - 1))) \times T(8)$
81945 := $((T((T(5) \times 4)) - 9) \times T((1 + 8)))$
81972 := $(T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7)))) \times (9 \times T((1 \times 8)))$
82026 := $(T(62) \times (T(T(02)) + T(8)))$
82128 := $((8 \times T(T(2))) \times T(((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(8))))$
82144 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - T((-1) - (-2) \times T(8))))$
82173 := $(T((T(3) + (7))) \times T((T((1 + 2)) + T(8))))$
82179 := $((9 \times T((T(7) + 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)$
82188 := $(T(8) \times (T((T(8) - 1)) + T((T(T(T(2))) + T(8))))$
82215 := $(T((T(5) - 1)) \times (T(2) + T((T(2) + T(8))))$
82224 := $((T(((4^{T(2)})) + T(2))) + T(T(2))) \times T(8)$
82225 := $(-((T((5^2)) \times (T(2) - (2^8))))$
82228 := $((T((82 + T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 8)$
82233 := $(-3) - (-T(T(3))) \times T((-T(2)) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))))$
82236 := $(T(6) \times T(((3^2) + 2) \times 8))$
82244 := $((T((44 \times 2)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 8)$
82251 := $((T((-1) + T(5))) + T(T(2))) \times T((2 + T(8)))$
82259 := $((T(9) \times T((T(T(5))/2))) - T((T(T(T(2))) - 8)))$
82269 := $(9 \times ((T(6)^{T(2)} - T(T(-(T(2) - 8))))$
82272 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T((7 + T(T(2)))) - T(2)))) + T(8)$
82284 := $((T(4) \times ((T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(8))))$
82287 := $((T((7 + 8)) + T(2)) \times (T(2) + T(T(8))))$
82293 := $(-T(T(T(3)))) - (-92) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))$
82296 := $(-6) \times ((T((9 \times T(2))) + T(2)) \times (-T(8)))$
82297 := $(T((T(7) + T(9))) - (T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(8)))$
82341 := $((T((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) + (T(T(8))))$
82342 := $((T((T(T(2)) \times T(4))) \times T((3^2))) - 8)$
82344 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(3)))) \times (T(2) \times 8)$
82353 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(5)) + (T(3) - 2)) \times T(T(8))))$
82359 := $((-T(9)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(2)) - (T(T(8)))$
82362 := $(-T(T(T(2)))) \times (-6) - T(((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times 8))$
82368 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(6))/3) + T(T((T(2) + 8))))$
82374 := $((T(T(4)) \times 7) \times T(T(T(3))) - ((T(2)^8))$
82377 := $((T(7) + T(7)) + T(T(T(3))))^2 + 8$
82384 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) + (-8) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))))$
82385 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)))) - T((2 + 8)))$
82392 := $((T(2) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(3))^{T(2)})) \times 8$
82397 := $(79 \times (T(T((3^2))) + 8)$
82412 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 2) + (T(T(8))))$
82422 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8))))$
82425 := $(T(5) \times (-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))))$
82432 := $((-T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) + (4)))) \times (2^8)$
82446 := $(-T(6)) \times (-T(4)) - T((T(T(4)) - ((T(2) - T(8))))$
82448 := $(8 \times (T(4) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8))))$
82455 := $(T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((4 + 2))) - T(T(8))))$
82461 := $(-1) + (((T(T(6)) + T(T(4)))^2) + T(T(8)))$
82462 := $((T((2 + T(6))) + T(4))^2) + T(T(8))$
82467 := $((-7) \times T(T(6))) \times (4 - T((2 + 8)))$
82473 := $(37 \times T(T(-(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8)))$
82475 := $((5^7) - (-T(4)) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 8)))$

- 82476** := $((T(67) + T(4)) + T(2)) \times T(8)$
82484 := $(-T(4) - ((-T(8) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8))))$
82487 := $(-7) - ((-T(8) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))$
82492 := $((T(T(2)) \times 9) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (2 + T(T(8)))$
82494 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (9 \times (4 + 2))) - (T(T(8))))$
82496 := $((6 \times 9) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (-2 + T(T(8)))$
82524 := $((T(T(4))^{T(2)} + (5))/2) - T(T(8))$
82531 := $(T(13) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))))$
82534 := $((-T(4^3)) \times T(T(5)))/(-T(2)) - T(T(8))$
82539 := $(-T(9) - (((-T(3)) - T(T(5))) + 2) \times T(T(8))))$
82542 := $((T(2) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(5)) - T(2)) \times T(T(8))))$
82548 := $((T(T(8)) \times T((T(4) + (5)))) + T(2 \times T(8)))$
82555 := $((T(T(5)) - 5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))))$
82563 := $(-T(T(3)) + (((-6) - T(T(5))) + 2) \times T(T(8))))$
82566 := $((-T(6) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(5^2))) + T(T(8))$
82572 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(7) + ((T(T(5))^2) - T(T(8))))$
82574 := $(-T(4) + ((7 + T(T(5))) - T(2)) \times T(T(8)))$
82577 := $(-7) + ((7 + T(T(5))) - T(2)) \times T(T(8))$
82582 := $(-2) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-5^{T(2)})) + T(T(8)))$
82584 := $((-4) \times T(T(8))) \times ((T(5)/T(2)) - T(8))$
82592 := $((-2) + T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 8)$
82593 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9)))/T(5)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8))$
82629 := $(T(9) - (-((2 \times 62)) \times T(T(8))))$
82648 := $((T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times T(6)) \times T(T(2)) - 8$
82656 := $((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) \times (T(6) \times (2 \times 8)))$
82657 := $(T(T(7)) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) \times T((2 + T(8))))$
82665 := $(-T(5)) \times (((-T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(2))) - T(T(8)))$
82678 := $(T(T(8)) - (-T(T(7))) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) - 8))$
82684 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times T(T((6 - 2)))) - T(8)$
82686 := $((T((T(6) + 8)) \times T((T(6) - 2))) + T(8))$
82692 := $(-((T(2) - T(9)) \times T(62))) + T(T(8))$
82719 := $(9 \times (-1) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))$
82722 := $((-T(2)) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-2 + T(8))$
82725 := $((-T(5) \times T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(8)))$
82728 := $((82 \times T(7)) + 2) \times T(8)$
82733 := $((T(3^3) - 7) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - 8)$
82734 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(3)) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)$
82744 := $((T(4)^4 + (7^{T(2)})) \times 8)$
82755 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(7)) + T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))$
82762 := $(-2) + ((T(67) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8))$
82764 := $((T(46) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(2)))) \times T(8))$
82776 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(7)) - T(T(2)))) + 8)$
82779 := $(-T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times ((-T(7)) \times T(T(2))) - T(8))$
82782 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(8) \times T((7 + T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8))))$
82788 := $((T(88) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)$
82795 := $(-5) - (T(T(9)) \times (-72 + 8))$
82796 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(7)))) - T((-2) + T(8))$
82824 := $((T(T(4)) + 2) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(2 \times 8))$
82836 := $((T(T(6 + T(3)))) - (T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(8))$
82839 := $((T((T(9) - 3)) \times T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8)))$
82842 := $(2 \times (T(T(4)) \times T((T(8) + 2))) + T(T(8)))$
82844 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - ((8 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8))$
82845 := $((T(5) \times T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times T((T(T(2)) + 8))$
82846 := $((T(T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8 - T(2)))) \times T(T(8)))$
82855 := $((T((5 \times 5)) - T(8))^2) - T(T(8))$
82872 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(7) \times 82)) \times T(8))$
82875 := $((5 + T((7 + 8))) \times (-T(2) + T(T(8))))$
82881 := $((-1) + T(88)) \times T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))$
82908 := $((80 \times T(T(9))) + ((T(2) \times T(8))))$
82923 := $(-T(T(3)) - (((T(2) + T(9))^2) \times T(8)))$
82926 := $((-T(T(6)) + T(2)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 8))$
82928 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(2))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(T(2))) + 8))$
82929 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(8))$
82932 := $((T(2) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8))$
82934 := $(-T(4) - ((3 + T(9))^2) \times T(8))$
82935 := $(-T(5)) \times ((-3) + T(T(9))) - (T(2)^8)$
82936 := $((-6) \times (-3 - T(9))^2) - 8$
82937 := $(-7) + (((3 + T(9))^2) \times T(8))$
82938 := $((T(T(8)))/(-3)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 8)$
82944 := $(T((4 + 4)) \times (9 \times (2^8)))$
82945 := $((T((T(5) \times 4)) \times T(9)) + T((-2) + T(8)))$
82953 := $((-3) + T(T(5))) \times ((T(9) - 2) + T(T(8)))$
82956 := $((-65) \times (-T(T(9)) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8)))$
82968 := $(8 \times (T(T(6)) \times T(9)) - (T(2) \times 8))$
82971 := $(T(-((1 - 7))) \times (-T(9)) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))))$
82977 := $(-T(T(7))) - ((-T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8)$
82989 := $(T(9) + (T(8) \times (9 \times (2^8))))$
82992 := $((-T(2)) - (T(T(9)))/(-9)) \times T((2 + T(8)))$
82995 := $((T((T(5) + T(9))) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))$
82998 := $(T((8 + T(9))) \times (T((9 + 2)) - 8))$
83052 := $(T(2) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(03)))) - T(8))$
83088 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(80) \times (-3))) \times 8)$
83124 := $((T(4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1^3)) \times T(8))$
83125 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times ((1^3) - T(T(8))))$
83127 := $((T(T(7 - 2))) + 1) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)))$
83145 := $(-T(5)) - ((T(4) \times T(T(T(1 \times 3)))) \times (-T(8)))$
83152 := $((T(2) \times T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(1 \times 3)))) - 8$
83155 := $(-5) - ((T((5 - 1)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(8)))$
83192 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) + (1 + 3)) \times 8$
83196 := $((T(T(6)) + T((9 + T((1 + 3)))) \times T(8))$
83214 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 1) \times ((T(2) \times T(3)) + T(8))$
83223 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(2) - (T(T(2)) \times (T(3) - T(T(8))))))$

- 83229** := $((9 \times (T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)})) - T(T(-(3-8))))$
83232 := $((2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((-2) + T(3)))) \times T(8))$
83235 := $(-T(5) + (((3+2)^3) \times T(T(8))))$
83238 := $(((((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(3)) - T(T(8))))$
83245 := $(-5) - (-(((T(4)/2)^3) \times T(T(8))))$
83265 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(2) + T(T(3) + 8))$
83268 := $(((((T(T(8)) \times (-T(6))) - T(2)) \times (-T(3))) - T(T(8))))$
83278 := $(-(((T(T(8)) - T(7)) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(8))))))$
83286 := $((((-T(6)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2))) \times (-T(3)) - T(T(8)))$
83292 := $(-T(2) - (T(9) \times (-T(2) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-8))))$
83294 := $(((((T(T(T(4))) \times (-9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(3))) + 8)$
83295 := $(T(5) \times (9 + ((T(2) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 8)))$
83322 := $((T((T(2)^{T(2)})) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(3) \times T(T(8))))$
83328 := $((T((8+23)) \times T(T(3))) \times 8)$
83334 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(3) + T(3)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(8)))$
83341 := $(((-1) + T(4)) \times (T(T(3))^3) - 8)$
83344 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (3 + T(T(3)))) - T(8))$
83349 := $((T(9) + 4) \times (T(T(3 \times 3))) + T(T(8)))$
83358 := $((T(T(8)) \times (5^3)) - (-3 \times T(8)))$
83376 := $((T(T(6)) \times (7+3)) + (T(3))) \times T(8)$
83385 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(8))))$
83397 := $((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(-(T(3) - 8)))$
83412 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) - (-T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8))$
83413 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 1)) - ((-T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8)))$
83427 := $((T((T(7) - 2)) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(8)$
83432 := $((T((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(3))) \times 8)$
83439 := $((T((93-4)) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(8)))$
83445 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(4)) - (T((-4) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(8))))$
83446 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) - ((-T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8)))$
83448 := $(T(8) \times (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) + 8))$
83449 := $((9 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3)) \times (-T(8)))$
83458 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-3 \times T(T(8)))$
83464 := $((((-4) + T(6))^4) - T(T(3))) - T(8)$
83472 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-74) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
83479 := $(((((T(9) - T(7))^4) - T(3)) - T(8)))$
83488 := $(8 \times (-T(8)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times 8))$
83492 := $((T(T(2)) \times 9) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(3))) + 8)$
83494 := $(T(4) - (9 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(3))) - T(8))))$
83495 := $(5 \times (-T(9)) + (4 \times T(T((T(3)) - 8))))$
83496 := $(T(6) - (-T(9)) \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(3)))) - T(8)))$
83497 := $(((((T(7) - T(9))^4) - (3 \times 8)))$
83512 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times (T(T(5)) \times 3)) - 8)$
83514 := $(T((T(T(4)) + 1)) + ((T(T(5)) + 3) \times T(T(8))))$
83524 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2 \times 5))) - T((T(3) \times 8)))$
83526 := $(T((T(6) + 2)) - (-((5^3) \times T(T(8))))$
83529 := $(-9) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (3 - T(T(8))))$
83532 := $(-((T(T(2)) + ((-T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times (-3) + T(T(8))))$
83534 := $(-4) - ((-T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times (-3) + T(T(8)))$
83538 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times ((T(5) \times T(3)) + T(8)))$
83556 := $(((((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(5))) \times 3) + T(8)))$
83565 := $((T(5) \times T(6)) - (-((5^3) \times T(T(8))))$
83574 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8))))))$
83578 := $((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + (3 + 8)))$
83584 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)) \times (T(5) + 3))) \times (-8))$
83592 := $((-T(2) + T(T(9))) \times (T(5) + T((3+8))))$
83595 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8))))$
83622 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T((-2) + T(6))) \times T(T(3))) - 8)$
83624 := $((T(T(T(4)) \times T((-2) + T(6)))) + 3) \times 8)$
83625 := $(-((5^{T(2)}) \times (-((6-3)) - T(T(8))))$
83628 := $((T(T(8)) - 2) \times (T(6) \times T(3))) - T(8)$
83644 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(6))) - T(T((3+8))))$
83655 := $((T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(6)))) \times (-3) + T(8))$
83682 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) - (3 + T(8))))$
83685 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(6))) + (T(3) \times T(T(8)))$
83712 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 1) \times T(T((7+T(3)))) - 8)$
83733 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(3)))) - 7) \times T(38)$
83739 := $(-9) - (-T(3) \times (-T(7)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
83744 := $((T(4) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) \times 3)) \times 8)$
83747 := $((-T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times (-((7^3) - T(T(8))))$
83748 := $(T(T((8/4))) \times (-T(7)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
83752 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) + 5))) - 7) \times 38)$
83763 := $(-T(3) + (-T(6)) \times (7 - (T(3) \times T(T(8))))$
83764 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (((T(67) + T(3)) \times T(8))))$
83769 := $(T(T((9-6))) \times (-7) + (T(3) \times T(T(8))))$
83776 := $(-(((T(T(6)) - 7) \times (T(T(7)) - T((3+T(8))))$
83784 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((8 \times 7))) - (T(3) \times T(T(8))))$
83797 := $(T(T(7)) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(T(-(T(3) - 8))))))$
83799 := $((T(T(9)) - (T(T(9)) \times T(7))) \times (-3)) - T(8)$
83824 := $(((-4) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)))) \times T(T(3))) - 8)$
83825 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(T(3)) - 8))$
83826 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(2)) \times T(T((8-3))) + T(T(8)))$
83828 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T((2+8)))) \times 38)$
83829 := $((T(9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) + (3 + T(T(8))))$
83832 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(3) + 8)))$
83835 := $((T(T(5)) + 3) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(8))$
83848 := $((-8) + T(T(4))) \times ((-8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 8)$
83853 := $(T(T(3)) \times (((5 \times T(T(8))) - 3) + T(T(8))))$
83862 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - 3)) - T(8))$
83864 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(6) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-T(3))) + 8)$
83865 := $(-T(5) + (((6 \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) - T(8)))$
83868 := $((T(8)/6) \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - 8))$
83895 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(9) - 8))) - T(-(T(3) - T(8))))$
83913 := $(3 \times (-1) - (-((T(9) - 3)) \times T(T(8))))$

- 83916** := ((T(6) × ((1 × 9) - 3)) × T(T(8)))
83922 := (T(T(2)) - (((T(2) - T(9)) × 3) × T(T(8))))
83935 := ((5^{T(3)}) + (T(T(9)) × T((3 + 8))))
83943 := (((3⁴) × T(T(9))) - (-3) × T(8))
83944 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(4) + T(9)))) + (T(T(3)) × (-T(8))))
83946 := (-6) × ((4 - 9) - (T(T(3)) × T(T(8))))
83952 := ((T(2) - T((5 + T(9)))) × (-T((3 + 8))))
83955 := ((T((5 × T(5))) + T(9)) × (T(T(3)) + 8))
83965 := (-5) - (-6) × (9 + (T(T(3)) × T(T(8))))
83967 := (((T(7) × T(T(6))) - 9) × (T(T(3)) - 8))
83972 := ((2 × T(T(7))) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(3)))) × 8))
83982 := (((2 + T(8)) × T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) - T(8))
83985 := (-T(T(5))) - (-T(89)) × T(T(T(-((T(3) - 8))))))
84013 := -((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(10)) × T(T(4))) - T(T(8))))
84034 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T((3 × 0) + 4))) - (T(T(8))))
84044 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) + (T(04) - T(T(8))))
84124 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T((T(2) - 1))) + 4) × (-T(T(8))))
84128 := ((T((T(8) × 2) + 1) × (4 × 8))
84132 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(3))) + T(T((1 + T(4)))) × T(8))
84134 := ((T((T(4) × T(3))) - 1) × (T(4) + T(8)))
84144 := (T(T(4)) + (((T(T(T(4))) + 1) × T(T(4))) - (T(T(8))))
84187 := (((T(7) - T((8 + 1)))⁴) + T(T(8)))
84204 := (((T(40) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8))
84216 := ((T(T(6)) + 1) × (T(2) + (T(4) × T(8))))
84224 := (((T(T(T(4))) - (2^{T(2)})) × T(T(4))) - T(8))
84225 := (T(T(5)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T((T(2)⁴) + 8))))
84227 := (-((T(T(7)) - T(2))) × (T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) × (-8)))
84235 := (-5) - ((T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) × (-T(4) × T(8)))
84244 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - ((2 + T(T(4))) × 8))
84245 := (((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T((T(2) + (4)))))/8)
84246 := (6 × (T(T(4)) - (-T((2 + 4))) × T(T(8))))
84249 := ((T(9) × (-4) + T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))
84252 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5) × (-T(2) - (T(4) × T(8))))
84254 := (((4 + T(T((5 × 2)))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))
84255 := (T(5) + (T(T(5)) × (T(T((2 × 4))) + T(8))))
84273 := (T(T(3)) × (-7) - (T(T(2)) × (-4) - T(T(8))))
84275 := (T(5) - (-T((7 + T(2)))) × (T(T(T(4))) - 8))
84279 := (((T(9) + T(7)) × T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(4))) - T(8))
84282 := ((T(T(2)) × ((T(T(8)) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) + T(8))
84288 := ((T((T(8) + T(8))) + T(T(2))) × (4 × 8))
84318 := ((81 - 3) × T((T(4) + T(8))))
84328 := ((T(T(8)) - 2) × (T((3 + T(4))) + T(8)))
84329 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) × (3⁴) + 8)
84334 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) × T((T(3) + (4)))) - T(8))
84336 := (T(T(6)) - (T(T(3)) × (-T((3⁴) + 8))))
84343 := (-T(T(3))) - (((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) × (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8))))
84344 := (T(4) - (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) × (-T(T(4)))) + T(8)))
84348 := (((8 × (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)))) × T(8))
84355 := (-5) + (T(T(5)) × T((-((3 - 4) + T(8))))
84362 := ((T(T(-((2 - 6)))) × (-T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 8)
84364 := (((T(T((4 + 6))) + (T(3))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))
84374 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((7 - T((T(3) + T(4)))) × T(T(8))))
84385 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(8))) + T((3 + T(T(4))) + T(8)))
84392 := (((-((T(T(2)) - T(9))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 8)
84394 := (T(4) - (((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(8)))
84397 := ((T((T(7) + T(9))) × (T(T(3)) + T(4))) + T(T(8)))
84406 := (((6 - T(T(T(04)))) × (-T(T(4)))) + T(8))
84414 := (((T(T(T(4))) - 1) × T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T((T(4) - 8))))))
84425 := (((-((T(5)/T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(-((4 - 8))))
84428 := ((8 × T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(4)) × (T(T(T(4))) - 8))
84429 := ((T(9) × T((2 + 4) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))
84432 := (-T(23)) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) + 8)
84433 := (-T(T((3 + 3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - T(8)))
84436 := (-T((T(6) + 3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) + T(8))
84437 := ((T(T(7)) - 3) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - (T(T(8))))
84439 := ((T(9) × T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(4) - T(T(8))))
84442 := (-2) + (((T(T(T(4))) - 4) × T(T(4))) - T(8))
84443 := -((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(4))) - ((T(4) - T(8))))))
84444 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - (4⁻⁴⁺⁸))
84446 := ((T((6 + T(T(4)))) × T(4)) + (4⁸))
84448 := ((8 × T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) × (-T(4) - T(8)))
84452 := ((-2) × T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - 8)
84453 := (-3) + (T((T((T(5)/T(4))) - T(4))) × T(8))
84454 := (-T((4 × 5))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) - T(8))
84456 := ((-6) - T((T(5) × 4))) × (-T(4) + T(8))
84461 := (((-((1 - 6)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(4)))) + T(8))
84462 := (T(T(2)) + (T((64 + 4)) × T(8)))
84463 := (((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(4))) × T(T(-((4 - 8))))))
84468 := (-((T(T(8)) + (6))) + (T(T(4)) × (T(T(T(4))) + 8))
84469 := (-T((T(9) + T(6)))) - (-T(T(4)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(8)))
84472 := (((T(T((T(2) + (7)))) - 4) × T(T(4))) - 8)
84473 := (-3) - (-T(7) × ((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - 8))
84474 := (((T(T(T(4))) + 7) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(4)) - T(T(8))))
84476 := ((T(6) + (7)) × ((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - 8))
84477 := (-T((-7) + T(7))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) + 8))
84483 := (T(T(T(3))) - (((8 - T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(4))) + 8))
84484 := (((T(T(T(4))) + 8) × T(T(4))) + (T(4) - T(T(8))))
84492 := ((T(T((2 + 9))) + T((4 × 4))) × T(8))
84496 := (((-T(T(6)) + 9)) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(4))) + T(8)))
84525 := ((5 × T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(5) + T((4 + T(8))))
84528 := (T(8) × (2 + T((T(5) × 4) + 8)))
84529 := (((9 + T(T((2 × 5))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))
84534 := (((T(4) × T(3)) × (-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))

- 84538** := $(-8) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(5) - T(-((T(4) - T(8))))))$
84541 := $((((-1) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5)) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)))$
84544 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - (-T(5) + T((T(4) + 8))))$
84545 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - 5) \times T(T(-((4 - 8))))))$
84546 := $(T(T(6)) \times (((T(T(4)) \times 5) + T(T(4))) + T(8)))$
84548 := $((8 + T((4 \times T(5)))) \times (T(4) + T(8)))$
84564 := $((-T((T(4) + (6)))) + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times T(8))$
84573 := $((-T(T(3)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (-T((5 \times 4)))) + T(T(8))))$
84574 := $((-T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(8))))))$
84576 := $(-6) - ((-7) - T((5 + T(4)))) \times T(T(8)))$
84578 := $(((-8) \times T(T(7))) - (5)) \times (T(4) - T(8))$
84582 := $((T((2 \times 8)) - (5 + 4)) \times T(T(8)))$
84586 := $(T(T((T(6) - 8))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-4 - T(T(8))))$
84595 := $(-5) - ((T(9) - T(T(5))) \times T((T(T(4)) - 8)))$
84614 := $((41 \times T(64)) - T(T(8)))$
84623 := $((T(T(3))/T(2)) \times (-T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(4)) \times 8)))$
84625 := $((-5^{T(2)}) \times (-((T(6) - T(4)) - T(T(8))))$
84627 := $((T((T(7) - 2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(4))) + T(8))$
84628 := $(-T(8)) + ((T(T(-((2 - 6)))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(8))$
84639 := $((T(9)^3) - (6 \times T((T(4) + T(8))))$
84643 := $((-T(T(3)) - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((6 + 4)))) - T(8)))$
84644 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - (64 - 8))$
84645 := $((-T(54) \times (T(6) - T((4 + 8))))$
84664 := $((T(T((4 + 6))) \times T((6 + 4))) - T(8))$
84666 := $(-6) - (-((T(6) + T(6))) \times T((T(T(4)) + 8)))$
84671 := $(-1) + (((T(7) \times T(6)) \times 4) \times T(8))$
84672 := $((T(2) \times T(7)) \times T(6)) \times 48$
84674 := $((T(4) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(T(4)))) - T(8))$
84678 := $((-T(T(8)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))$
84692 := $((T(-((2 + 9)) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 8$
84694 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (-9) + T(6)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))$
84697 := $((-T(T(7))) - ((-T(9)) \times T((6 + T(T(4)))) - 8))$
84699 := $(9 \times (-T(9)) + (6 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8))))$
84724 := $((-T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(2)) - (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 8))$
84728 := $(-8) - ((2^7) \times (4 - T(T(8))))$
84732 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) - T((4 \times 8))$
84733 := $(-3) + ((T(T(3 + 7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(8))$
84734 := $((-T(T(T(4))) + (-T(3)) + (-T(7)) \times T(T((4 + 8))))$
84735 := $((T(T(5)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) \times (T(T(4)) + 8))$
84736 := $((T(T((6 - 3) + 7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(8))$
84742 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(8))$
84755 := $(55 \times ((-7) + T(T(T(4)))) + 8)$
84756 := $((-T(6)) \times (((T(T(5)) \times (-T(7))) - T(4)) - T(T(8))))$
84757 := $((-T(7) - (5^7)) + (T(4) \times T(T(8))))$
84777 := $(T((-7) + T(7)) \times (7 + (T(4) \times T(8))))$
84778 := $((-8) + T((7 + 7)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8))))$
84783 := $((-T(T(T(3)) + T(8))) - ((7^4) \times T(8)))$
84792 := $((T(2) + 9) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(4) \times T(T(8))))$
84795 := $((-T(5)) \times ((T(T(9)) - T(7)) - (T(4) \times T(T(8))))$
84816 := $(T((-((6 - 1)) + T(8))) \times T((T(4) + 8)))$
84824 := $((T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((8 + T(4)))) + 8)$
84844 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(8) \times (-4 - 8)))$
84846 := $((T((6 \times T(4))) \times (T(8) + T(4))) + T(T(8)))$
84852 := $((-T(T(2) - T((5 \times 8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8))$
84864 := $(T((T(4) + (6))) \times (8 \times T((4 + 8))))$
84888 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(8) \times 84)) \times (-T(8)))$
84896 := $((T((6 + T(9))) \times 8) + (4) \times 8)$
84916 := $((T(61) - T(9)) \times (T(4) + T(8)))$
84924 := $((T(T(4))^2 - T((9 \times 4))) \times T(8))$
84925 := $((5^{T(T(2))}) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(-((4 - 8))))))$
84942 := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(9)))) / (-T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))$
84945 := $((T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(4) \times 8)))$
84955 := $(-5) + (T(59) \times 48)$
84972 := $(T(2) \times (((T(7) \times T(T(9))) + T(4)) - T(T(8))))$
84973 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times (9 + T((T(T(4)) - T(8))))$
84975 := $((5 + T(7)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(-((4 - 8))))))$
84983 := $(((-3) + T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + 8)$
84984 := $((T((4 + 8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(4)))) - T(8))$
84992 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((9 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8))$
85095 := $((5 \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(05)) \times T(T(8))))$
85125 := $((-5^{T(2)}) \times (-15 - T(T(8))))$
85184 := $((T(T(T(4))) / (T(8) - 1))^{-5+8})$
85194 := $(T(4) + ((T(9) - 1)^{-5+8}))$
85209 := $((T(90) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))))$
85217 := $((7 + T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \times (5 + T(T(8))))$
85224 := $((T((T(4) \times 2)) \times T(T((2 + 5)))) - T(8))$
85233 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + 2)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))))$
85237 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(5) + 8))$
85239 := $((93 + T(T(2))) \times T((5 + T(8))))$
85242 := $((-T(T(2)) + (-((4 \times (2^5)))) \times T(T(8))))$
85244 := $(-4) - (-((4 \times (2^5))) \times T(T(8)))$
85245 := $((-T(5)) - (-T((T(4) \times 2))) \times T(T((T(5) - 8))))$
85247 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((T(4) \times 2))) - (5 + 8))$
85248 := $(T(T(8)) \times (((4 - T(2)) + T(5)) \times 8))$
85254 := $(((-4) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(8))$
85255 := $(-5) + (T((T(T(5)) / T(T(2)))) \times T(T((T(5) - 8))))$
85257 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(5)) / T(T(2)))) + ((5 - 8))$
85274 := $((T(4) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 5)) - T(8))$
85275 := $(T(5) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(2 + 5)) - 8)))$
85293 := $((-((3^9) / T(2)) \times (-5 + 8))$
85294 := $(T(T(4)) + ((9 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (5 + T(8))))$
85321 := $((1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) \times (5 + T(8)))$
85323 := $((-T(3)) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(3) \times T(5)))) + (T(T(8))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 85328 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T((T(2) \times 3))) \times T(T(5))) + 8) \\ 85329 &:= ((T(T(9 - T(2))) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)))) - T(T(8))) \\ 85332 &:= (T(2) + ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)))) - T(T(8)))) \\ 85338 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(3))) \times T(3)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85344 &:= (4 \times ((T((T(T(4)) - 3)) \times T(5)) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 85356 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((5^3) \times (T(5) + T(T(8)))) \\ 85365 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(6)^3) - T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) \\ 85374 &:= ((T(4) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(5)))) - T(8)) \\ 85378 &:= (-T(T(8)) - (-T(7) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5)))) - 8)) \\ 85386 &:= (-T(6) \times (T(T((8 - 3))) - T(T((5 + 8)))) \\ 85392 &:= ((T((T(2) \times 9)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 5)) - T(8)) \\ 85415 &:= (T(T((5 - 1))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + 8))) \\ 85422 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))) + T(8)) \\ 85425 &:= ((-5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(4) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85428 &:= (T(8) \times (-T(2)) + (T((-4) + T(5)) \times T(8))) \\ 85448 &:= ((T(T(8)) + ((T(4)^4) + T(5))) \times 8) \\ 85464 &:= ((-T(T(4))) \times ((-T(6) - T(T(T(4)))) - 5) - (T(T(8)))) \\ 85472 &:= (2 \times ((T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) + T(8))) \\ 85478 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(T((4)/5)))) + 8) \\ 85492 &:= ((-T((2 + 9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 58) \\ 85536 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(3)^5)) / (-T(5) - T(8))) \\ 85539 &:= (-T(93) - ((-T(5) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85545 &:= (-5) + ((T(4) \times 5) \times T(58)) \\ 85572 &:= (2 \times ((T(75) \times T(5)) + T(8))) \\ 85574 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(7) + T(55))) - T(T(8))) \\ 85575 &:= ((T(5) \times (-7)) \times (5 - T((5 \times 8)))) \\ 85596 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(9))) + 5) \times (T(T(5)) - T(8)) \\ 85624 &:= ((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times ((6^5) + 8)) \\ 85626 &:= ((-((T(6) - (T(2)^6))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(8))) \\ 85632 &:= ((T(2) + T(36)) \times (T(T(5)) + 8)) \\ 85672 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - 8) \\ 85674 &:= ((4 + T((-7) + T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)))) \\ 85683 &:= (-((T(T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(6))) / (-5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85688 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times T((T(6) - (5)))) + 8) \\ 85695 &:= (T(5) - (-((T(9) - T(6)) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) \\ 85698 &:= ((T(T(8)) - T(9)) \times (6 \times (T(5) + 8))) \\ 85722 &:= ((T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(8)))) \\ 85728 &:= ((T(T((T(8)/T(2)))) \times T(7)) - (T(5) \times T(8))) \\ 85743 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(7))) + (T(5) + 8))) \\ 85744 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) - (T((-5) + T(8)))) \\ 85746 &:= (-6) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times (5 - T(8))) \\ 85749 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(7))) - (T(T(5)) + T(8))) \\ 85764 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (6 + 7)) \times T(T(5))) - T(8)) \\ 85792 &:= ((T(-((T(T(T(2)) - T(9)))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(5)))) - 8) \\ 85794 &:= ((-4) \times ((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(5)))) - T(T(8)) \\ 85797 &:= ((T(-((T(7) - T(9)))) \times T((T(7) + (5)))) - T(8)) \\ 85824 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) + T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 85833 &:= ((-3) \times T((-3) + T(8))) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\ 85843 &:= (T(34) - ((-8) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85844 &:= (-T(4) + (((T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(8)))) \\ 85847 &:= (-7) + (((T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(8))) \\ 85848 &:= (-((8^4) - 8)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\ 85854 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(8)))) \\ 85869 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (68 + T(5))) - T(8)) \\ 85876 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(8))) + T(T((T(5) - 8)))) \\ 85888 &:= ((8 + 8) \times ((T(T(8)) + (5)) \times 8)) \\ 85893 &:= -((T(T(3)) + ((-9) + (-8) \times T(5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85904 &:= (-T(4) - ((0 - 9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85907 &:= (-7) - (((0 - 9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85911 &:= (-T((1 + 1)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85912 &:= (-2) + (((1 \times 9) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85914 &:= (-((T((4 - 1)) - (9 \times T(5)))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85932 &:= ((T(2) \times T(3)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85935 &:= ((T(5) + T(3)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85938 &:= ((8 \times 3) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85942 &:= (T((T(2) + (4))) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85947 &:= ((7 \times T((-4) + T(9))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85949 &:= ((T(9) - T(4)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85954 &:= ((T(T(4)) - (T(5))) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85957 &:= ((T(7) + T(5)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85959 &:= (T(9) + ((T(T(5)) + (T(9)/5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 85967 &:= -((T(7) - ((T(6) \times T(9)) \times T((5 + 8)))) \\ 85968 &:= (((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) \times (-9) - (T(5)) \times T(8)) \\ 85974 &:= ((47 \times T((T(9) + T(5)))) - T(8)) \\ 85978 &:= ((T(8) + T(7)) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 85983 &:= (-3) + (((T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(8))) \\ 85986 &:= (((T(6) \times T(8)) - T(9)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(8)) \\ 85992 &:= (-T(2) - (T((T(9) + T(9))) \times (T(5) - T(8)))) \\ 85995 &:= ((T((5 + 9)) \times 9) \times T((5 + 8))) \\ 86024 &:= (((4^{T(T(2))}) \times T(06)) + 8) \\ 86163 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T((T((6 - 1)) \times 6)) + 8)) \\ 86184 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T((8 - 1))) \times (T(6) + T(8))) \\ 86188 &:= ((T(88) \times (1 + T(6))) + T(8)) \\ 86226 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(2) \times (-6) + T(8)))))) \\ 86229 &:= ((T(9) - T(T(2))) \times T(-(2 - 68))) \\ 86232 &:= ((T((T(T(T(2)))/3)) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) - T(8)) \\ 86253 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T((T(5) - 2)))) - (T((T(6) + T(8)))) \\ 86272 &:= ((2^7) \times ((2 + 6) + T(T(8)))) \\ 86273 &:= (-3) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T((2 \times 6))) - 8) \\ 86274 &:= (((4 \times T(T((7 + 2)))) \times T(6)) - T(T(8))) \\ 86275 &:= (T(5) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) + 8) \\ 86276 &:= (((T(6) + (7)) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) + 8) \\ 86279 &:= (((-9) + T(7))^2) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) \\ 86286 &:= (-6) - ((T((T(8) \times 2)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

- 86292** := ((T(T(T(2)) × (9 + T(2)))) - T(T(6))) × T(8))
86295 := (T(T(-(5 - 9))) × (T(2 × T(6))) + T(T(8)))
86297 := ((T(7) × T(T(9 + T(2)))) + (T(6) + 8))
86328 := (T(8) × (-2) + (T(3 + T(6)) × 8))
86344 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)) + T(6)))) - (T(T(8))))
86346 := ((T((T(6) × 4)) × (3 + T(6))) + T(T(8)))
86352 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(5)) × T(-(T(3) - T(6)))) - 8))
86367 := (((-7) + T((T(6) + T(3)))) × T(T(6))) + T(T(8)))
86373 := (-T(T(3)) × (73 - T(T((T(6) - 8))))
86374 := -(T(T(T(4))) - (T(T((7 + T(3)))) × T(6) + 8))
86385 := (-T(5) - (8 × T(3 + T(6))) × (-T(8)))
86394 := ((-4) + T(9 × 3)) × T(T(T(T(-(6 - 8))))))
86436 := (((T(6)/3)^{T(4)-6}) × T(8))
86472 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) + (T(6)) × T(8))
86474 := (-4) - (T(T(7)) × (T(4) - T(T(6)) + 8))
86478 := ((T(8) × 7⁴) + 6) + T(8))
86493 := ((T(T(3)) × (-9 - 4⁶)) + T(T(8)))
86496 := ((T(T(6)) + (T(T(9)) × T(4)) + T(T(6)))) × 8)
86526 := (6 × (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5))⁻⁶⁺⁸)))
86534 := -(T(T(T(4) + 3)) - (T(T(5)) × (T(6) × T(8))))
86535 := (-T(5) × ((-3⁵) × T(6)) - T(T(8)))
86544 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (-4) × (T(5) - T(T(6)))) × T(8))
86555 := (-5) × (5 - ((5 + T(6)) × T(T(8))))
86556 := (((T((6 × T(5))) - 5) × T(6)) + T(T(8)))
86561 := (-1) - ((-6) - T(T(5))) × (T(6) + T(T(8)))
86562 := ((T(T(2)) × (-T(6))) × -(T(5) + 6)) - T(T(8)))
86565 := (-T(5) - (6 - T((-5) + T(6))) × T(T(8)))
86574 := ((T((T(4) + T(7))) × T(T(5))) - (T(68)))
86583 := (T(T(3)) × (T(8) + T(T(5) × 6)) - 8))
86589 := (((T(9) × 8) + T(5)) × T(T(6))) - T(8))
86592 := (((T(T(2 + 9))) × 5) - T(T(6))) × 8)
86625 := (((5²) × T(T(6))) × (T(6) - T(8)))
86633 := (((-3) + T((T(3) + T(6)))) × T(T(6))) + 8)
86644 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(T(4))) + (6 × 6))) - T(8))
86646 := (T(6) × ((4⁶) - 6) + T(8))
86652 := (((T(2) + T(5)) × T(T(6))) × T(6)) - T(T(8)))
86661 := ((T(T(-(1 - 6))) × 6) × T(6)) + (T(T(8)))
86664 := (46 × (T(T(6)) + T((T(6) + T(8))))
86688 := (((8 + 8) × 6) × T((6 + T(8))))
86694 := ((T((T(T(4)) + 9)) × (T(6) + T(6))) - (T(T(8))))
86724 := ((T((T(T(4)) + (2 × 7))) - 6) × T(8))
86733 := ((T(T(T(3) + T(3))) × T(7)) + (T((-6) + T(8))))
86743 := -(T(T(3)) × (T(T(4)) - T(T((7 + 6)))) + 8))
86745 := (T(5) × (T(T(4)) × T((-7) + T(6))) + 8))
86747 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(4) + 7)) × (T(T(6)) - 8))
86757 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(5) + T(7))) × (T(T(6)) + 8))
86764 := ((T((T(4) + T(6))) × (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - T(8))
86772 := (T(T(T(2))) × (((T(7)/7)⁶) + T(8)))
86775 := (T((T(5) + T((T(7)/7)))) × (T(T(6)) + T(8)))
86778 := ((T(8) × (-7) + (T(T(7)) × 6)) - T(T(8)))
86784 := ((T(T(4)) × (T((8 × 7) - 6))) - T(T(8)))
86793 := (T(T(3)) × ((-T(9)) + T(T((7 + 6)))) - 8))
86796 := (-6) - ((-9) - T(7)) × T(68))
86797 := ((T(7) + T(9)) × (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(8)))
86829 := (((T((T(9) × 2)) + 8) × T(6)) + T(T(8)))
86832 := ((-T(2)) + T(((T(3) × 8) + T(6))) × T(8))
86848 := (((-8) + T(T(4))) × 8) × T(T(6)) - 8)
86856 := (T(T(6)) × ((5 + T(8)) + 6) × 8)
86892 := (((2 + T(9)) × 8) × T(T(6))) + T(8))
86904 := ((4 × T(T(9))) × T(6)) - T(8))
86922 := (T(T(2)) × (-T(2)) + (T(T(9)) × (6 + 8)))
86924 := ((-4) × (T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) × (-T(6)))) + 8)
86925 := (-T(5) - (T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) × (-6 + 8))
86927 := (((T(7) × T(2)) × T(T(9))) - (T(6) - 8))
86932 := (((-2) + T(3)) × T(T(9))) × T(6) - 8)
86934 := (((4 × T(T(3))) × T(T(9))) - T(T(-(6 - 8))))
86935 := (-5) - ((-T(3)) × T(T(9))) × (6 + 8))
86937 := (((T(7) × 3) × T(T(9))) - T(-(6 - 8)))
86939 := ((T(9)^{-T(3)+9}) - T(T((T(6) - 8))))
86941 := (1 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86942 := (2 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86943 := (((T(T(3)) × 4) × T(T(9))) + T(-(6 - 8)))
86944 := (-4) - ((4 × T(T(9))) × (-T(6)) - 8))
86945 := (5 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86946 := (6 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86947 := (7 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86948 := ((T(8) × T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6)))) + 8)
86949 := (9 - (T(((T(4) × 9) - T(6))) × (-T(8))))
86955 := (T(5) - (T((T(5) + (9 × 6))) × (-T(8))))
86961 := (T((1 × 6)) × (-T(9)) + T(T((T(6) - 8))))
86964 := (4 × ((T(6) × T(T(9))) + T(T(-(6 - 8))))
86972 := ((-T(2) - 7)) × (T(T(9)) × T(6)) + 8))
86975 := ((5 × 7) × T(T((-9) + T(6))) - 8))
86976 := (((T(6) - 7) × T(T(9))) × 6) + T(8))
86979 := (T(9) - ((-T(7)) × T(T((-9) + T(6)))) - (T(T(8))))
86982 := ((T(T(2)) + T(8)) × (9 × T(T(6))) - 8))
86985 := (-T(5) × (((T(T(8)) × (-9)) + T(T(6))) - T(8)))
86988 := (-T(8) - (T(T(8))/(-9) × T(6 × 8)))
87114 := ((T(T(4)) × T((1 + 1) × T(7))) - T(T(8)))
87123 := ((T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) × (1 + T(7))) + T(8))
87129 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + ((1 - 7) × T(T(8))))
87186 := (((T(T(6)) - T(81)) × (-T(7))) + T(T(8)))
87192 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T((T(9) + 1) + T(7))) + T(T(8)))

- 87213** := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(12)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(8))))$
87214 := $((T(4) + T(T(12))) \times T(7) + T(T(8)))$
87219 := $((T(9) \times T((T(T(1 + T(2)))) + 7)) - (T(T(8))))$
87224 := $((T(T(4)) \times (2 + T((2 \times T(7)))) - T(T(8)))$
87225 := $(-T(5) - ((-T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(2) + (7)))) + (T(T(8))))$
87228 := $((T(8) \times T(T(2))) \times (-2) + T(T(7))) - T(8)$
87235 := $(-5) - ((-T(T(3))) \times T(T((T(2) + (7)))) + (T(T(8))))$
87238 := $((T(T(8)) \times (3 + (2^7))) - 8)$
87242 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (2 \times T(7))) + (T(T(8)))$
87246 := $((T(T(6)) - ((T(4)^2)) \times T((T(7) + 8)))$
87254 := $((-((T(4) - (T(5)^2))) \times T(T(7))) - T(8))$
87255 := $(T(5) \times ((5 \times T(T(T(2)))) + (7 \times T(T(8))))$
87256 := $((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) \times (-2) + T(T(7))) - 8$
87262 := $(-2) - (-6) \times ((-2) + T(T(7))) \times T(8))$
87264 := $(T(T(-((4 - 6)))) \times ((-2) + T(T(7))) \times T(8))$
87268 := $((T(8) + T(T((6 \times 2)))) \times T(7)) - 8$
87275 := $((-T(5) - T(T(7))) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8))))$
87276 := $((6 \times 7) \times (-2) + T((T(7) + T(8))))$
87282 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8)))) / (-T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - 8$
87289 := $((T((-9) + T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (-7 + T(8))$
87297 := $(-7) \times (9 - (T(T(2)) \times T((T(7) + T(8))))$
87298 := $((T((T(8) - 9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7) - 8))$
87317 := $((T((T(7) - 1)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((7 - 8)))$
87318 := $(-81) \times ((-T(3)) - T(T(7))) - T(T(8))$
87324 := $((T((4^{T(2)})) \times (T(3) \times 7)) - T(8))$
87326 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(2)^3))) - ((T(7) - T(8))))$
87333 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(3^3)) + (7 + 8))$
87336 := $((6 \times 3) \times (T(T((T(3) + 7))) + (T(T(8))))$
87339 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T(8)))$
87342 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-T(4)) + (T(3) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-T(8)))$
87347 := $((T((-T(7)) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (-7 + T(8))$
87354 := $((T((4 + T(5))) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) + 8))$
87355 := $(-5) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) + 7))) \times 8)$
87372 := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(7)) - 3) + T(T(7))) \times T(8)))$
87374 := $((T((T(T(4)) - T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (7 \times 8))$
87375 := $(T(5) - ((-7) \times T(3)) \times T((T(7) + T(8))))$
87384 := $((-4) + T(T(8))) \times ((T(3) \times T(7)) - T(8))$
87393 := $(T(T(3)) - ((9 - (T(3) \times T(T(7)))) \times T(8)))$
87396 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((9 \times 3))) + (78))$
87416 := $((-T(6)) - T(T(T(1 \times 4)))) \times (-7 \times 8))$
87422 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7 \times 8)))$
87423 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) + (T(T(8))))$
87426 := $((T(6) + T(T(2))) \times (-T(4)) + (T(T(7)) \times 8))$
87429 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-4) - T(T(7))) + T(8))$
87432 := $(2 \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + 8)$
87435 := $((T(T(5)) + (3^4)) \times T((-7) + T(8)))$
87437 := $(-((7^3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T((7 \times 8))))$
87438 := $((T((8 \times T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times 78)$
87444 := $((T((4 \times 4)) - T(4)) \times (T(7) + T(T(8))))$
87455 := $(-T((5 \times 5)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T((7 \times 8))))$
87456 := $(-6) \times ((-T(5)) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)) \times T(8))$
87464 := $((T((-4) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7)) \times 8$
87465 := $(-((T(5) \times T(6))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T((7 \times 8))))$
87472 := $((-((T(T(2)) - T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (7 \times 8))$
87486 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) - (T(7) - 8)))$
87489 := $((T(9) \times (-8) + T((T(T(4)) + 7))) - T(8))$
87492 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((9 + 4)))) - (T(T(7)) + 8))$
87497 := $(-T(7)) + (T(9) \times (T((T(T(4)) + 7)) - 8))$
87498 := $(-T(8)) + ((T(9) \times (T(T(T(4)) + (T(T(7)))))) - T(8))$
87522 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-2) \times T(5)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(8))))$
87523 := $((3^{T(2)}) \times T(T(5))) + (7 + T(8))$
87534 := $((-T(4) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(5) \times T(7))) - T(T(8))$
87544 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times 57) - 8$
87546 := $(-6) \times ((T(4) + T(5)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$
87552 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) / (-5)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8))))$
87574 := $(-T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) - T(5)) \times (T(7) \times 8))$
87576 := $((T(T(6)) - 7) \times (-T(5) + T(T(7)))) - 8$
87577 := $(-7) + ((T(T(7)) - T(5)) \times (T(7) \times 8))$
87584 := $((T(T(4)) + T(8)) \times T(T(5))) + T(7) \times 8$
87622 := $(-2) - ((-2) + (6 \times T(T(7)))) \times (-T(8))$
87624 := $((-((4 - 2)) + (6 \times T(T(7)))) \times T(8))$
87632 := $(-((2^{T(3)})) - ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8))))$
87633 := $((-3) \times T(T(3))) - ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8)))$
87639 := $((T(9)^3) - T((T((6 + 7)) - 8)))$
87641 := $((-1) \times T(T(4))) - ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8)))$
87644 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) - (-T(67)) - T(T(8))))$
87647 := $((T(T(7) \times 4) + T(6)) \times (-7) + T(T(8)))$
87655 := $(-5) - (((T(5) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + T(8))$
87659 := $(-T(9)) - (((T(5) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) - 8)$
87675 := $(-((T(T(T(-((5 - 7)))))) + ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8))))$
87679 := $((-((T(9) - T(7))) - ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8))))$
87682 := $(-((T(T(2)) + (((T(8) \times (-6)) \times T(T(7))) + 8)))$
87683 := $(-((T(T(3)) + (((T(8) \times (-6)) \times T(T(7))) - 8)))$
87684 := $(-4) - (((T(8) \times (-6)) \times T(T(7))) + 8)$
87688 := $((T(T(8) \times T(8)) / 6) \times T(T(7))) - 8$
87693 := $(-3) + ((T((9 - 6)) \times T(T(7))) \times T(8))$
87696 := $((T(T(6) + T(9)) + T(6)) \times T(7)) \times T(8)$
87712 := $((2 + ((-1) + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) \times 8)$
87716 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((-1) + T(7))) + T(T(7))) - 8$
87723 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T((T(2) + 7)))) - 7) - T(8))$
87724 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((2 \times T(7)))) - (7 \times 8))$
87725 := $((-T(5)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7)) + (-7) + T(8))$
87726 := $(-6) \times ((2 - 7) - (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$

- 87729** := $(-9) - (T(T(2)) \times (-7) - (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$
87732 := $((T(T(2))^3) \times T(T(7))) + (T(7) + 8)$
87734 := $(-4) - (-T(3)) \times (7 + (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$
87738 := $((T(8)/T(3)) \times (7 + (T(T(7)) \times T(8))))$
87742 := $(-2) + ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) + T(7)))) - T(8))$
87744 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((4 \times (7 + 7)))) - T(8))$
87745 := $(T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(7) - 8))))$
87752 := $((T(T(T(2)))) + ((-T(5) + T(T(7))) \times T(7)) \times 8)$
87754 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T((5 + 7)))) \times (7 - T(8)))$
87772 := $((T((T(2) + 7))) \times T((T(7) + T(7)))) - 8)$
87775 := $(-5) - (T(T((T(7)/7))) \times (-T((7 \times 8))))$
87786 := $(-6) \times ((-T(8)) \times T(T(7))) - (7 + 8))$
87792 := $(T(T(2)) \times (9 + 7) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$
87795 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T((T(9) - 7))) \times (-7) - T(T(8)))$
87822 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(-((2 - 8))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8))))$
87834 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(8)))) - T(78))$
87842 := $((T((2 \times T(4)) + 8) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(8)))$
87844 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T((4 + 8)))) \times T(7) + T(8))$
87849 := $((T(9) \times T((T(T(-((4 - 8)))) + 7))) - T(8))$
87856 := $(T((T(6) - 5)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) - 8)))$
87863 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T((T(6) - 8)))) - (7 + T(8)))$
87864 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(6) + 8)) \times (7 \times 8))$
87872 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + T(7))) + 8)$
87892 := $((-2) + T(9)) \times (-T(8) + T((T(7) + T(8))))$
87894 := $((T(4) + 9) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 7) - T(8)))$
87906 := $(T(6) \times T(T((T(T(T((09 - 7)))) - 8)))$
87912 := $((T(2) \times (-1) + T(9)) \times T((T(7) + 8)))$
87933 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(3)) - T((T(9) - T(7)))) \times T(T(8))))$
87939 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T((3 + 9)) + 7)) - T(8))$
87942 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T((4 + 9))) \times (-7) + T(8))$
87944 := $(-4) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(9))) + (-T(7)) \times T(T(8))))$
87948 := $((84 \times T(T(9))) + ((T(7) \times T(8))))$
87955 := $(-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T((T(9) - 7))) - 8))$
87963 := $(-3) - (-6) \times (T(9) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8)))$
87967 := $((T((T(7) + 6))) \times T(T(9)))/7 - 8)$
87969 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(T((T(6) - 9))) \times (-T(7))) - (T(T(8))))$
87976 := $((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times 9) - T(7)) \times 8)$
87978 := $(-((T(8) + 7))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(78))$
87984 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-T((9 + 7)) + 8))$
87993 := $(3 \times ((T((T(9) + T(9))) \times 7) + T(T(8))))$
88128 := $((T((8 \times 2)) \times 18) \times T(8))$
88143 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T((T(4) + 1)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8))))$
88164 := $((T((T(4) \times (6 + 1))) - T(8)) \times T(8))$
88192 := $(T(-((T(2) - T(9 + 1)))) \times (8 \times 8))$
88215 := $((T(T(5)) - 1) \times T((2 + T(8)))) + T(8))$
88227 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-8) \times T(T(8)))$
88236 := $((T((63 + T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times T(8))$
88242 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(4)) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(8))))$
88252 := $(-2) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((2 + T(8)))) - T(T(8)))$
88254 := $((T((T(4) + 5))) \times T((2 + T(8)))) - T(T(8))$
88264 := $((T(4) - T((T(6) \times T(2)))) \times (-8) - T(8))$
88272 := $(2 \times ((T((7^2)) \times T(8)) + T(8))$
88312 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(13))) + T((-8) + T(8)))$
88326 := $(-T(6)) \times (T(T(2)) + (-T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(8)))$
88335 := $(-T(5)) \times ((T(3) - (3^8)) + T(T(8)))$
88344 := $(4 \times ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \times T(8)) + (T(T(8))))$
88362 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T((T(6)/3))) \times T(8)) + (T(T(8))))$
88395 := $(-5) \times (9 + (T(T((3 + 8))) \times (-8)))$
88423 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \times (-8 \times 8))$
88425 := $(T(5) \times ((T(-((2 - 4)))^8) - T(T(8))))$
88429 := $((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (-4) \times (8 + T(T(8))))$
88432 := $((T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(8))) - 8)$
88438 := $((T(8) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (-8) + T(T(8)))$
88444 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-T(8)))$
88446 := $((T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) + (T(T(8))))$
88452 := $(T(2) \times ((T(54) - T(T(8))) \times T(8))$
88464 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) \times (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) + T(8)))$
88473 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (7 + ((T(T(4)) - 8) \times 8))$
88474 := $((4 \times (T(7)^{T(4)-8})) + T(T(8)))$
88482 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)) + T(8))$
88524 := $((T(4)/2)^5 - T(T(8)) \times T(8))$
88528 := $((T((8^2)) \times 5) + T(T(8))) \times 8)$
88536 := $((T(6) + T(35)) \times T((8 + 8)))$
88542 := $((T(2) + T(4) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - T(8)$
88544 := $((T((4 \times 4)) \times (-T(5) + T(T(8)))) + 8)$
88566 := $(-6) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T((5 + 8)))) - T(T(8))$
88569 := $(-9) + (((T(6) + T(T(5))) - 8) \times T(T(8)))$
88572 := $((T(2) \times 7) \times T(T((5 + 8))) + T(T(8)))$
88578 := $(T(T(8)) \times (((7 \times T(5)) + T(8)) - 8))$
88586 := $((T(T(6) - 8) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + 8)$
88624 := $((-T(4)) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) \times 8)) \times 8)$
88642 := $(T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) + (T(68) \times T(8)))$
88647 := $((7 \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))) + (-8) \times T(8))$
88654 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T((5 + 6)) - 8)) - (T(T(8))))$
88659 := $((9 + T(T(5))) \times (T(6) + T(T(8)))) + T(8)$
88661 := $(-1) - (-T(6)) \times (T(T((T(6) - 8))) + T(8))$
88662 := $(T(T(-((T(2) - 6)))) \times (T(T((T(6) - 8))) + T(8)))$
88668 := $((8 \times T(T(6))) \times (6 \times 8)) - T(8)$
88689 := $(-((T(9) - 8)) \times (T(T(6)) - T((T(8) + T(8))))$
88722 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) - (T((T(8) + T(8))))$
88739 := $(T(T(9)) - ((T(3) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(8))) - 8)$
88749 := $(-T(9)) - ((T((T(4) \times 7)) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(8)))$
88792 := $((-2) - T((9 \times 7))) \times (-8) - T(8))$

- 88794** := $((T(((T(T(4)) - T(9)) \times 7) \times T(8)) - (T(T(8))))$
88836 := $((-T(6) + (-3) \times T(T(8))) \times (-8 - T(8)))$
88872 := $(T(T(2)) \times 7 \times (T(8) + T((8 \times 8))))$
88896 := $((T(T(6)) - ((T(9) \times T(8)))) \times (-8 \times 8))$
88927 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(98) + 8))$
88934 := $(((((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-9) + T(8)) / (-T(8)))$
88943 := $(((((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-9) / (-T(8))) + 8)$
88956 := $(-6) \times ((T(59) \times (-8)) - T(T(8)))$
88968 := $((T((T(8) + 6)) - T(T(9))) \times (-8 - T(T(8))))$
88992 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + T((T(9) + 8))) \times T(8)$
89133 := $(33 \times T((1 + (9 \times 8))))$
89155 := $(55 \times (1 + (T(9) \times T(8))))$
89223 := $(3 \times ((2 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(9) \times T(T(8))))$
89232 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) / T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \times (-8)))$
89235 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(3^2) + (-9) \times T(T(8)))$
89238 := $(-((T(T(8)) + T(3)) + (-((T(2) \times T(9))) \times T(T(8))))$
89242 := $(-2) - ((-T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 9)) \times (-T(T(8))))$
89244 := $((44 - (-2) \times T(9)) \times T(T(8)))$
89248 := $(-((T(T(8)) - 4) + (-((T(2) \times T(9))) \times T(T(8))))$
89252 := $(-(((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) - 8)$
89254 := $(T(4) - (-((5^{T(2)}) + 9)) \times T(T(8)))$
89262 := $(T(2) \times (-((6^{T(2)}) + (T(9) \times T(T(8))))$
89268 := $(-86) \times (-T(2) - T(9 + T(8)))$
89273 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(7)) + (-((T(2) \times T(9))) \times T(T(8))))))$
89278 := $((8 + T(7 \times T(T(2)))) \times 98)$
89281 := $(T((1 + T(8))) \times ((T(2) \times T(9)) - 8))$
89284 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-8) + T(2 + 9)) - T(8))$
89289 := $(((((T(9) \times T(T(8))) \times T(2)) + T(9)) - T(T(8)))$
89316 := $((T(T((6 + 1))) \times (-T(3)) - T(9)) \times (-T(8)))$
89334 := $((T((4 \times T(3))) \times T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) - (T(T(8))))$
89337 := $((T(T((7 + T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(9) + 8))))$
89346 := $(-6) - ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(9 \times 8)))$
89349 := $((9 + T(4 \times 3)) \times (T(T(9)) - 8))$
89351 := $(-1) + (T((-5) + T(T(3))) \times (-9) + T(T(8))))$
89352 := $((-2) + T((5 + 3)) \times T(9 \times 8))$
89355 := $(T(((5 \times T(5)) - T(3))) \times (T(9) - 8))$
89373 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(7) + T(3)) \times T(9 \times 8)))$
89376 := $(-T(6)) \times (T((T(7) + T(3))) - (T(98)))$
89379 := $((T(T(9)) \times ((7 \times T(3)) + T(9))) - T(T(8)))$
89385 := $(-T(5)) \times (((T(T(8)) - 3) \times (-9)) + 8)$
89424 := $(T(((T(4) + T(2)) + T(4))) \times (9 \times T(8)))$
89425 := $(T(5^2) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(9) \times T(8))))$
89436 := $(-((T(T(6)) + (T(3^4)) \times (9 - T(8))))$
89445 := $(-T(5)) - ((T(4) + (T(T(4)) \times T(9))) \times (-T(8)))$
89452 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) + (4 \times T(T(9)))) - 8)$
89455 := $(-5) - (T(((T(5) + T(4)) + T(9))) \times (-T(8)))$
89472 := $((2^7) \times (-4) + T((T(9) - 8)))$
89475 := $(T(5) - (T((7 \times (T(T(4)) - T(9)))) \times (-T(8))))$
89488 := $(T((8 + 8)) \times (T((4 \times 9)) - 8))$
89496 := $((T(6) \times 94 \times T(9)) + T(T(8)))$
89497 := $((T(T(7)) - 9) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(9) \times T(8))))$
89526 := $((T(6) \times T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + ((T(9) \times T(8))))$
89532 := $((2 + T((T(35)/9))) \times T(8))$
89535 := $(-T(5)) - (3 \times (T(T(5)) - (T(9) \times T(T(8))))$
89568 := $((8 \times 6) \times (T((T(5) + T(9))) + T(8)))$
89586 := $((6 + T((T(8) - T(5)))) \times T((-9) + T(8)))$
89595 := $(-T(5)) \times (T((-9) + T(5)) + (-9) \times T(T(8)))$
89604 := $(-4) \times (((0 - T(6)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(8)))$
89622 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) + (-T(6)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(8))))$
89625 := $(-((5^{T(2)})) \times ((-6) - T(9) - T(T(8))))$
89644 := $(-4) \times (-T(4) + ((-T(6)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(8)))$
89646 := $(-6) \times (-T(4) - (-T(6)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(8))))$
89648 := $(8 \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(6))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-8)))$
89649 := $(T(9) - (-4) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(8))))$
89655 := $(T(5) \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(6))) + (T(T(9)) - 8))$
89664 := $((T((4 + T(6))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(9))) - T(8))$
89667 := $((T(7) - (6/6)) \times T((T(9) + T(8))))$
89676 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(9))) \times T(8)$
89682 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-86) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(8)))$
89685 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(8) \times T(6))) - T(9 + T(8)))$
89689 := $(-9) - ((-86) \times (T(T(9)) + 8))$
89698 := $((8 + T(T(9))) \times (T((T(6) - 9)) + 8))$
89733 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((3 \times T(7))) + T((T(9) - 8))))$
89739 := $((T(9)^3 - T((7 + T(9)))) - 8)$
89743 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(4)) \times T(T(7)) + (9 + 8))$
89745 := $(-T(5)) \times ((4 + 7) + (-9) \times T(T(8)))$
89748 := $(T(8) \times (((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) \times (-9)) - T(T(8))))$
89754 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(57) - 9)) - T(T(8)))$
89763 := $(3 \times (-((T(6) + T(7))) + (T(9) \times T(T(8))))$
89766 := $(-6) \times (-T(6) - ((T(T(7)) + 9) \times T(8)))$
89768 := $((T(T(8)) - 6) \times T((7 + 9)) + 8)$
89775 := $(-5) \times ((-7) + T(T(7))) \times (-9) - T(8))$
89782 := $(-2) - ((T(T(8)) - (T(79))) \times T(8))$
89784 := $((T((T(T(4)) + (8 + 7))) + 9) \times T(8))$
89796 := $(-((T((-6) + T(9))) - (T((7 + 9)) \times T(T(8))))$
89802 := $(T(2) \times (((0 - T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))) - T(8)))$
89823 := $(T(T(3)) - (T(2) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) + T(8)))$
89827 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - 8) + (-T(9) - T(T(8))))$
89829 := $((T(9) \times T(2)) \times T(T(8)) - ((T(9) + T(8))))$
89835 := $(-T(5)) \times (-3) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-9) + 8))$
89838 := $(-T(8)) - (((-3) \times T(T(8))) \times T(9)) + T(8))$
89846 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(4)) - (8 - T(9)))) + 8)$
89853 := $(-((T(T(3)) + (((T(5) \times T(T(8))) \times (-9)) + T(8))))$
89856 := $((6 - (T(5) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-T(9) - T(8)))$

- 89865** := (((T((-5) + T(6))) × T(T(8))) - T(9)) - T(T(8)))
89874 := (((4 - 7) × T(T(8))) × (-T(9))) - T(8))
89875 := (-5) × (7 + (T(T(8)) × (9 - T(8))))
89886 := (T(-(6 - 8))) × ((T(T(8)) × T(9)) - 8))
89893 := ((3 × T(9)) × T(T(8))) - (9 + 8))
89895 := (-T(5)) × ((-9) × T(T(8))) + (9 - 8))
89912 := (2 × (1 - (-T(9)) × (T(T(9)) - T(8))))
89913 := (3 × ((1⁹) + (T(9) × T(T(8))))
89919 := (9 × (1 + (T((T(9)/9)) × T(T(8))))
89922 := (2 × (T(T(2)) - (-T(9)) × (T(T(9)) - T(8))))
89925 := (T(5) - (((-2) × T(9)) - T(9)) × T(T(8)))
89928 := (-T(8)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(99) + T(T(8))))
89937 := (((-T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(9))) × 9) + T(8))
89946 := ((T((6 + T(T(4)))) × T(9)) + (T(98)))
89952 := (T(2) × ((5 + 9) + (T(9) × T(T(8))))
89962 := (-2) - (-T(6)) × (T(99) - T(T(8)))
89964 := ((-4) × T(6)) × ((T(9) × (-9)) - T(T(8)))
89973 := (3 × (T(T(T(-(7 - 9)))) + (T(9) × T(T(8))))
89982 := (((-T(2)) × T(T(8))) × (-T(9))) + ((9 × 8))
90345 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(30))) × T(9)))
90585 := ((5 + T(T(8))) × (T(5) × 09))
90768 := ((8 × 6) × T(70 - 9))
90939 := -(T(T(9) + T(T(3)))) + (-90 × T(T(9)))
91125 := (T(5) × T(2))^{T(11-9)}
91128 := (8 × (T(T(2)) + (11 × T(T(9))))
91146 := (T(T(6)) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(11) - 9)))
91239 := ((T(9)³) + (T(T(2)) × 19))
91245 := ((-T(T(5))) × ((T(T(T(4)))/(-2)) + 1)) - T(T(9))
91264 := -(T(T(T(4) + T(6))) × (T(T(2)) - T(19)))
91332 := (2 × ((T(3)^{T(3)}) - T((-1) + T(9)))
91335 := (5 × (-3) - (T(T(T(3) + 1))) × (-T(9)))
91344 := ((-4) + T((4³))) × (-1) + T(9))
91345 := (((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T((3 + 1)))) + T(9))
91388 := ((T((8 × 8)) - 3) × (-1) + T(9))
91392 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(93) - (19)))
91395 := ((T(5) + T(9 × (T(3) + 1))) × T(9))
91422 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(4) + 1))) - 9))
91425 := (((T(T(5))/2) × (T(T(T(4)) + 1)) - T(T(9)))
91476 := (T(T(6)) × (T((7 × 4)) - (1 + 9)))
91539 := (((T(9) × (T(T(T(3))) - 5)) + 1) × 9)
91552 := (-2^{T(5)}) - (T(T(5)) × (-1) - T(T(9)))
91575 := (((-5) × T(T(7))) - (5)) × (-1) × T(9))
91584 := (((4 × T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) × T(-(1 - 9)))
91624 := (((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) × T(61)) - T(T(9)))
91637 := (T((7 + T(3))) × (-T((6 + 1))) + T(T(9)))
91656 := ((6 - T(T(5))) × (T(T(6)) - T(T((1 × 9))))
91697 := (((T(T(7)) - 9) × T(T(6))) - (1 + 9))
91728 := (T((T(8)/T(2))) × T((-7) + T((1 + 9))))
91755 := (((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) × T((T(7) - 1))) + T(T(9)))
91756 := ((T(T(6)) - 5) × T(T((7 × (1⁹))))
91765 := (((-5) + T(T(6))) × T(T(7))) + (1 × 9))
91834 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) × T((T(8 - 1)) + T(9)))
91945 := (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) × (T(9) + ((1 - 9)))
91974 := -(T(T((4 + 7))) - (91 × T(T(9))))
91995 := -(T(T(5)) - (T(T(9)) × ((T(9) - 1) + T(9))))
92115 := ((T((T(5) - (1 + 1))) - 2) × T(T(9)))
92137 := ((T(T(7 + T(3)))) × (1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))
92139 := (((T(9)³) - T(T((1 + 2)))) + T(T(9)))
92145 := (-T(5)) + ((T((T(4) - 1))^{T(2)}) + T(T(9)))
92162 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) - 1) × T(T(-(2 - 9)))
92178 := (((-T(8)) + T((T(7) + 1))) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9)
92183 := (T(T(T(3) - 8)) × ((-1) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)))
92224 := (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(T(2))) + (T((T(2) × 9))))))
92232 := (T((T(2)³) × (T(22) - 9))
92235 := (T((T(T(5)) - T(T((T(3) - 2)))) × (-2) + T(9))
92237 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - 9)
92239 := (((T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 2)²) + T(T(9)))
92243 := ((-3) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(-(2 - 9))))
92245 := ((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(2) × T(T(T(2)))) × T(9))
92246 := (-T(T((6 + 4)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(-(2 - 9))))
92248 := (-8) + (T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)))
92253 := (((3 × T(5))^{T(2)}) + T((2 + T(9))))
92255 := (5 × ((T((-5) + T(T(T(2))))²) - T(9))
92256 := (T((6 + (5²))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9))
92259 := ((T((T(9) + T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(2)) + T(9))
92265 := (((5⁶) × T(T(2))) - T((T(T(2)) × 9)))
92268 := (T(8) × ((T(T(6)) + 2) × (2 + 9))
92272 := (-2) - (T((7 + T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))
92274 := (-T(((4 + 7) + 2)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))
92276 := (((6⁷) - T(2))/T(2)) - T(T(9))
92283 := (T(3) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) × 2) - T(T(9))
92284 := (T(4) - (T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))
92287 := (T(T(7)) + ((T(82) × T(2)) × 9))
92293 := (-((3 - 92) × (2 + T(T(9))))
92295 := (T(5) × (((T(T(9)) - 2) × T(T(2))) - T(9))
92319 := (T(9) - (T(13) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))
92325 := (-T(5)) × (T(T((-2) + T(3))) - (T(T(2)) × T(T(9))))
92334 := ((T((T(T(4)) - 3)) + (T(T(3)))) × T((2 + 9))
92337 := ((7 × T(T(T(3)))) - (T((T(T(3)) × T(2))) × (-T(9))))
92346 := (T(T(6)) + ((T((T(4) + 3)) - 2) × T(T(9)))
92349 := (((-9) × T((T(T(4)) + 3))) × (-T(T(2))) - T(9))
92355 := (-T(5)) × (53 - (T(T(2)) × T(T(9))))
92372 := ((-T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(-(2 - 9))

- 92373** := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(3^{T(2)})) + T(T(9))))$
92376 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(3)))) + T(T(T(2))) - T(9))$
92382 := $((T(T(2)) + (83)) \times (T(2) + T(T(9))))$
92385 := $((T(5) \times T(8)) \times T((T(3) \times T(2)))) + T(9)$
92391 := $((T((1 \times 9)^3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)))$
92393 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-(T(9^3) + 2)) - T(T(9)))$
92394 := $((T(((T(4) + T(9)) + 3)) \times T(T(2))) \times 9)$
92406 := $((60 \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(2) - 9)))$
92415 := $((-(T(T(5))) \times (1 + T(T(T(4)))) / (-2)) - T(9))$
92421 := $((T(T(12)) \times (T(4) \times T(2))) - 9)$
92424 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(2)) \times T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(9)$
92425 := $(-5) - ((T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(2) + 9)))$
92442 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(2) - T(9)))$
92443 := $((T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (-2 + T(9))$
92445 := $((5 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(4) + 2) + T(9))$
92448 := $(T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) + ((-4) - T(2)) + T(T(9))))$
92454 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(5) \times 4)) + (T(T(2)) \times 9))$
92466 := $(6 \times (T(T(6)) - (-(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))))$
92475 := $((5 + T(T(7))) \times ((T(4)/2) \times T(9)))$
92482 := $(-2) - (-(T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))))))$
92484 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) - (4))) \times (-(T(2) - T(9))))$
92488 := $(-88) \times (-(4^2) - T(T(9)))$
92496 := $((T((T(6) - 9)) + (4)) \times T((2 + T(9))))$
92519 := $(-T((T(9) + 1))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(-(T(T(2)) - T(9))))$
92523 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(2)) \times T(T((5 + 2))) - T(9))$
92525 := $((T(T(5))^2) + (5^{-2+9}))$
92529 := $((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))) \times 9$
92547 := $(7 \times ((T(T(-4) + T(5))) \times T(T(2)) - T(9)))$
92565 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(6) + T(5)) + T(2))) - T(T(9)))$
92568 := $(T((T(8) + T(6))) \times ((5 + T(T(2))) + T(9)))$
92574 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) + (5)))) \times T(2) + 9)$
92577 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))) + 9$
92578 := $(-8) - (-(T(T(7)) - (5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))$
92583 := $(3 \times ((-T(T(8))) + T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times 9))$
92584 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 9)))$
92595 := $(T(T(5)) - (T(9) \times (T(5) - (2 \times T(T(9))))))$
92601 := $((10 \times (T(6)^{T(2)})) - 9)$
92613 := $((T(T((T(3) + 1))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(2))) + T(9))$
92619 := $((9 + 1) \times (T(6)^{T(2)}) + 9)$
92625 := $(-T(5)) \times (-(T(2^6)) - T((2 \times T(9))))$
92627 := $(-T(7)) - (-(T(2^6)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9))$
92628 := $(-(T(T(8)) + (-2) \times ((6^{T(T(2))}) - 9)))$
92637 := $(73 \times ((T(T(6)) + T(2)) + T(T(9))))$
92647 := $(T(7) + ((T(4) \times (T(6)^{T(2)})) + 9))$
92655 := $((5 + 5) \times (T(6)^{T(2)}) + T(9))$
92658 := $((T(T(-8) + T(5))) \times T(T(6))) - T((2 + T(9)))$
92664 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times ((6^2) \times 9))$
92672 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (2^9))$
92673 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + (-(T((6 \times 2))) - T(T(9))))$
92676 := $((((-6) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))$
92685 := $(-T(5)) - (-(T(8)) \times (T(T(T(6 - 2)))) + T(T(9))))$
92691 := $((1 + T(9)) \times T((T(6) \times T(2))) - T(9))$
92694 := $((-4) + T((T(9) + T(6))) \times (-(T(2) - T(9))))$
92715 := $((5^{-1+7}) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(9)))$
92718 := $((T(81) \times T(7)) - (T(T(2)) \times T(9)))$
92723 := $(-T((T(T(3))/T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92725 := $(-5) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))))$
92741 := $((-1) \times T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92742 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(7))) - T((T(T(2)) + 9)))$
92743 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times (T(T(7)) - 2) + T(T(9)))$
92745 := $((T((T(5) \times 4)) + T((7 \times T(2)))) \times T(9))$
92748 := $((T(T(T(T(8/4)))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(2) + T(T(9))))$
92751 := $((T(T(1 + 5))) \times T((7 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))$
92752 := $(T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9)))$
92753 := $((T((T(3) + T(5))) \times T(T(7))) + 2) - T(T(9))$
92754 := $(T((T(4)/5)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92755 := $(-5) - (-(T(T(5))) \times (-7) + T(-(T(T(2)) - T(9))))$
92757 := $((T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))))$
92758 := $((-8) + T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))$
92762 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) / T(6)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92763 := $(T(3) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))$
92764 := $(T(4) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(2)) - T(T(9))))$
92766 := $(T(6) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))$
92769 := $(-(T(9) + (6))) \times (-(T(7^2)) - T(T(9)))$
92772 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(7)) \times T((7 \times T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92773 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(7) - T(T(2))) - T(T(9))))$
92776 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(7) - T(2))) - T(T(9))$
92778 := $(-(T(8) \times T(7))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(-(T(2) - 9))))$
92779 := $(-(T(T(9)) - T(7))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(-(T(2) - 9))))$
92787 := $(-(T(7) \times T(8))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9))$
92793 := $(-3) + T(9) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
92796 := $((T(T(6)) - 9) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(2) + 9)))$
92799 := $((T((9 \times 9)) \times T(7)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times 9))$
92826 := $((T((T(6) - (-2) \times T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)))$
92829 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(8))) + T(2) + T(T(9)))$
92832 := $(-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(8)^{T(2)} - 9)))$
92835 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-T(3)) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) - T(9))$
92853 := $((3 + (T(5) \times T(8))) \times T((2 \times 9)))$
92859 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((5 + 8))) - T((T(T(2)) + T(9))))$
92861 := $(-1) - ((-6) - T(8)) \times T(T((2 + 9)))$
92862 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times T((T(8 - 2)) + T(9)))$
92865 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2)) - T(T(9))$
92876 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(8)) - T((-2) + T(9))$

$$\begin{aligned} 92883 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((-8) + T(8))) - T(-((T(2) - T(9)))) \\ 92884 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-88) \times (T(2) + T(T(9)))) \\ 92886 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T((8 \times 8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9))) \\ 92889 &:= ((-T(9)) - T(T(8))) + ((T(8^2)) \times T(9))) \\ 92895 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((9 + 8) - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 92897 &:= -((T((T(7) + 9)) - ((T(8^2)) \times T(9)))) \\ 92919 &:= (((91 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \\ 92922 &:= (2 \times (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(9)) - T(2)) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 92925 &:= ((-T(5)) + T((-2) + T((9 + 2)))) \times T(9) \\ 92928 &:= ((T(T(8))/(-T(2))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-2) \times T(9))) \\ 92934 &:= (((T(4) \times (-3) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(2))) \times 9 \\ 92937 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) \\ 92943 &:= ((T((3 + 4)) \times T(9^2)) - T(9)) \\ 92946 &:= (T((6 \times T(4))) + (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - 9)) \\ 92955 &:= ((-T(T(5))) \times (5 - T((T(9) - T(T(2)))))) - T(9) \\ 92961 &:= (((1 - T(T(6))) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 9 \\ 92964 &:= (T((T(4) \times 6)) + ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + 9)) \\ 92967 &:= (-((T(7) \times T(6))) + ((9 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9))) \\ 92968 &:= ((T((-8) + T(6))) \times (T(T(9)) - 2) - T(T(9))) \\ 92972 &:= ((2 \times T(T(7))) + (T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(9))) \\ 92973 &:= -((T(3) - ((T(7) \times T(9^2)) - 9)) \\ 92974 &:= (((T(T(T(4)))/7) + 9) \times T(T(-((2 - 9)))) \\ 92976 &:= -((T(6) - ((T(7) \times T(9^2)) + 9)) \\ 92979 &:= (-9) - (-T(7)) \times T(((9^{T(2)})/9)) \\ 92982 &:= -((T(T(2)) - (T((T(8) + T(9))) \times T(-((2 - 9)))) \\ 92984 &:= (-4) + (T((T(8) + T(9))) \times T(-((2 - 9)))) \\ 92985 &:= ((-T(5)) \times (8 - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)))) - T(9) \\ 92988 &:= ((-8) + T(8)) \times T(((9^{T(2)})/9)) \\ 92996 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(2))))/(-9)) \\ 92997 &:= ((T(7) \times T((-9) - (T(9) \times (-2)))) + 9) \\ 93099 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times 90) - (T(3) + T(9))) \\ 93127 &:= (((T(7) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(13))) + T(T(9))) \\ 93129 &:= ((-T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(13)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93132 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-3) + (T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93135 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(3) \times T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93145 &:= (-5) + ((T((4 + 1)) \times T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93165 &:= (T(5) + ((T((6 - 1)) \times T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93177 &:= (((T(7) \times T((T(7) - 1))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times 9) \\ 93195 &:= (((-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-1) \times T(3)) + T(9) \\ 93213 &:= (((T(T((T(3) + 1))) + 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))) \\ 93221 &:= (-1) - (-2) \times ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - T(9)) \\ 93222 &:= (2 \times (((2 \times T(2))^{T(3)}) - T(9))) \\ 93225 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-2) - T(2)) + (-T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93237 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(39)) \\ 93242 &:= (2 \times (T(4) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - T(9))) \\ 93247 &:= (7 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T(2)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93249 &:= (9 \times ((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(9))) \\ 93252 &:= (2 \times (T(5) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - T(9))) \\ 93255 &:= (T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(2) - T(39)))) \\ 93264 &:= ((T(4) - T(62)) \times (-3) - T(9)) \\ 93267 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (T(6))) \times (T(T(2))^{3})) + T(T(9))) \\ 93273 &:= (((T(3)^7)/T(2)) - 39) \\ 93275 &:= (T(-((T(5) - T(7)))) \times (-T((-2) + T(3))) - T(T(9))) \\ 93276 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - 2) - (3 + T(9))) \\ 93279 &:= (-T(9)) - (-((T(T(7)) - 2) \times T(T(-((3 - 9)))))) \\ 93282 &:= (2 \times (((T(8)^{T(2)}) - T(3)) - 9)) \\ 93285 &:= ((-((T(5) - 8)) + T((2^{T(3)}))) \times T(9)) \\ 93312 &:= (2 \times (T((1 \times 3))^{-3+9})) \\ 93321 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (T(3)^{T(3)})) + 9) \\ 93324 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(9))) \\ 93325 &:= (-5) + (2 \times ((T(3)^{T(3)}) + 9)) \\ 93327 &:= (((T(T(7)) - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((T(3) - 9)) \\ 93336 &:= ((T((6 + 3))^3) + T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) \\ 93339 &:= (((T(9)^3) + 3) + T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) \\ 93345 &:= (T(5) + ((T((4^3)) - T(3)) \times T(9))) \\ 93348 &:= (T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) - ((-3) \times T(3)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93357 &:= (((7 - 5) \times (T(3)^{T(3)})) + T(9)) \\ 93366 &:= (-6) \times (((6^{T(3)})/(-3)) - 9) \\ 93372 &:= (((-2) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (3 + T(9)) \\ 93375 &:= ((-5) + T(((7 - 3)^3)) \times T(9)) \\ 93377 &:= (-T(T(7))) - ((-T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((T(3) - 9)) \\ 93384 &:= ((4 \times T(T(8))) + (T((3 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) \\ 93393 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(9)) - (3 \times T(3))) \times 9) \\ 93424 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((4^3)) \times T(9))) \\ 93429 &:= -((T((9 \times 2)) - (T((4^3)) \times T(9))) \\ 93432 &:= ((-2) - T((T(3) \times T(4)))) \times (-T(3) + T(9)) \\ 93435 &:= (((T(T(5))/3) \times T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(9)) \\ 93437 &:= -((T(7) - ((-3) + T((4^3))) \times T(9)) \\ 93441 &:= (((-1) - (T(T(T(4))) \times T(4))) \times (-T(3))) + T(T(9)) \\ 93447 &:= -((T((7 + T(4))) - ((T((4^3)) \times T(9)))) \\ 93448 &:= (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3))) + 9) \\ 93456 &:= ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times (T((T(4) + 3)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93462 &:= -((T(2) - ((T(64) - 3) \times T(9))) \\ 93464 &:= -((T((T(4) + 6)) - ((T((4^3)) \times T(9)))) \\ 93465 &:= (-5) \times ((T(64) - 3) \times (-9)) \\ 93472 &:= -((2^7)) + (T((4^3)) \times T(9)) \\ 93476 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - T(4)) - T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) \\ 93483 &:= (3 \times ((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times (T(3) + T(9))) \\ 93484 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93489 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) - T(9) \\ 93492 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) - (4 + 3)) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93495 &:= -((T((5+9)) - (T(4^3)) \times T(9))) \\ 93519 &:= (9 \times ((1-5) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(9))) \\ 93522 &:= -((T(2 \times T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93523 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93524 &:= ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93525 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-25) + (-T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 93527 &:= (-T(7) - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 93528 &:= ((T(8) \times (-2)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93534 &:= -((T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93542 &:= ((-T(2) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93543 &:= (3 \times (-4) + ((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-9))) \\ 93546 &:= (((T(64) \times 5) - T(3)) \times 9) \\ 93555 &:= ((T(5) - T(T(5))) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) \times (-9))) \\ 93557 &:= (-((T(7) + T(5))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93564 &:= (46 \times ((-5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9) \\ 93567 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))) - T((T(T(5))/T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93568 &:= (-86) \times (-53) - T(T(9))) \\ 93571 &:= ((-1) - T(7)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39)) \\ 93572 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + (7 - (T(T(5)) \times T(39)))) \\ 93573 &:= -(((T(3) \times (T(7) - (5^{T(3)}))) + 9)) \\ 93576 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - (-5) \times (3 - T(9))) \\ 93579 &:= -((T(T(T(9-7))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93584 &:= (-((4^8)) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(3) + T(9)))) \\ 93585 &:= -((T(5) - ((8 \times T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93586 &:= (-((6+8)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93591 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93595 &:= (-5) + (T(((9-5)^3)) \times T(9)) \\ 93597 &:= -((T(-((7-9))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93599 &:= (-((9/9)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(39))) \\ 93609 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(06))) + (T(3))) \times 9) \\ 93615 &:= (T(5) + (T((1+63)) \times T(9))) \\ 93639 &:= (T((T((9+3))/6)) \times (-T(3)) + T(T(9))) \\ 93642 &:= (-((T(2) - (T(4) \times (T(6)^3)))) + T(T(9))) \\ 93645 &:= (((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + (T(63))) \times T(9)) \\ 93646 &:= (T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(63) \times T(9))) \\ 93647 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-4) + T(T(6))) + T((T(3) \times 9))) \\ 93672 &:= (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))) - T((T(3) + 9)))) \\ 93675 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) - T(T(-(3-9)))) \\ 93684 &:= (((T(4) \times 8) - (6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))) \\ 93707 &:= (-70) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93711 &:= (-T(11)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93713 &:= (-T((T(3) + 1))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93716 &:= (-61) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93717 &:= ((T(7) - 1) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 93721 &:= ((1 - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9))) \\ 93722 &:= (-((2^{T(T(2))})) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(-(3-9)))) \\ 93723 &:= -((T(T(3)) + ((T(T(2) + T(7))) \times T(T(3))) \times (-9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93724 &:= ((4 - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93725 &:= (-52) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93726 &:= -(((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(7)))) - T((T(3) + T(9)))) \\ 93727 &:= (T(T(7)) - (((T(T(2))^7)/(-3)) - 9)) \\ 93728 &:= ((8 - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93729 &:= (-T((9+2))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93731 &:= (-1) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + (T(3) \times 9)) \\ 93732 &:= ((T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(3) \times 9) \\ 93734 &:= (-T(4)) - ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + 3))) \times (-9)) \\ 93735 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(3) + T(9))) \\ 93737 &:= (-7) - ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + 3))) \times (-9)) \\ 93738 &:= ((T(T((8)/T(3)))) \times T(T(7))) - (3 + T(9)) \\ 93741 &:= (((1 + T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(3))) - T(9) \\ 93742 &:= (-2) - (T((T(T(4)) + 7))) \times (-3 - T(9)) \\ 93743 &:= ((T(3) - 4) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9))) \\ 93744 &:= (((4 \times T(T(4))) + T(7)) \times T((3 \times 9))) \\ 93745 &:= ((-5) \times T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93746 &:= ((6 - T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93747 &:= ((T(T(T(7-4))) \times T(T(7))) - 39) \\ 93748 &:= ((8 - T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93749 &:= ((9 - T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93751 &:= (T(-((1-5))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93752 &:= ((T(T(2)) + 5) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93753 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(5) + 7)^3)) \times (-9)) \\ 93756 &:= ((T((T((6+5)) + T(7))) \times T(T(3))) - 9) \\ 93758 &:= (-T((-8) + T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(-(3-9)))) \\ 93759 &:= ((T(T(-9) + T(5))) \times T(T(7))) - (3 \times 9) \\ 93761 &:= (-1) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3))) - T(9)) \\ 93762 &:= (T(2) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - (3 \times 9))) \\ 93764 &:= (-T(4)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - (3 + 9)) \\ 93765 &:= (T((T(5+6)) + T(7))) \times T(-(3-9)) \\ 93766 &:= ((T(T(6))/(-T(6))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 93767 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))) - ((7+3) + 9)) \\ 93768 &:= (T(8) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - (T(3) \times 9))) \\ 93771 &:= ((T(T(-(1-7))) \times T(T(7))) - (T(3) + 9)) \\ 93772 &:= ((T(2) + T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93773 &:= ((-T(3) - T(T(7))) + (T((7+T(3))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 93774 &:= ((T((T((4+7)) + T(7))) \times T(T(3))) + 9) \\ 93775 &:= ((5-7) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9)) \\ 93776 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - ((7 - T(3)) + 9)) \\ 93777 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (77 \times 3)) - 9) \\ 93778 &:= (-8) + (T(T(7)) \times T((-7) \times (T(3) - 9))) \\ 93779 &:= ((9-7) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9)) \\ 93782 &:= (-((T(2) - 8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9)) \\ 93783 &:= ((T(3) + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \\ 93784 &:= (-((T(T(4)) - 8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(9)) \\ 93786 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(((8-7) + (3 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93787 &:= -(((T(T(7)) - 8) - (T((7 + T(3))) \times T(T(9)))))) \\ 93789 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(T(3)) \times 9)) \\ 93792 &:= (T(T(2)) - (((T(9) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) / (-T(9)))) \\ 93794 &:= (-((T(4) - 9)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9)) \\ 93795 &:= (((5^{T(9-7)}) \times T(3)) + T(9)) \\ 93797 &:= (-((7 - 9)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 9)) \\ 93813 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(-(1 - 8)))) + (3 \times 9)) \\ 93816 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(-(1 - 8)))) + (T(T(3)) + 9)) \\ 93825 &:= (T(5) \times ((T((2 \times 8)) + 3) \times T(9))) \\ 93828 &:= ((T(8) \times T((2 \times T(8)))) - (T(39))) \\ 93831 &:= ((T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) + T(9)) \\ 93834 &:= (-((T((4 \times 3))) \times ((-8) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93837 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(8)/T(3)) + T(9))) \\ 93852 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (-T((T(8) + T(3))) + T(9))) \\ 93855 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)))) - (T(T(T(3)) + 9))) \\ 93885 &:= (T(5) + ((T((8 \times 8)) + T(3)) \times T(9))) \\ 93894 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(9)) + T(T(8))) + (T(3)))) + 9) \\ 93912 &:= (T((T(2) + (1 + 9))) \times (-3) + T(T(9))) \\ 93915 &:= (-T(5) \times (((1 + T(T(9))) \times (-T(3))) - T(9))) \\ 93924 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \times 3) + 9) \\ 93927 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(9) + 3)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93933 &:= (((T(T(3))^3) + T((T(9) + 3))) \times 9) \\ 93945 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(9)))) \\ 93948 &:= (T(8) - (-T((4 + 9))) \times (-3) + T(T(9))) \\ 93957 &:= ((T((T(7) - T(5))) \times (T(T(9)) - 3)) + T(9)) \\ 93961 &:= (T(T((1 + 6))) - ((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 93967 &:= ((T(T(7)) + 6) - ((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 93972 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(9 - 3)))) - T(9))) \\ 93975 &:= (-T(5) \times (-T(79)) - (3 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 93978 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(7))) \times T(9)) + (T((3 \times 9)))) \\ 93982 &:= (-2) + (89 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 93984 &:= (((T(4) \times 8) + 9) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 94114 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T((1 + 1)) + T(T(4)))) + 9) \\ 94116 &:= ((T(6) + 1) \times T((1 + T((4 + 9)))) \\ 94122 &:= ((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(9)) \\ 94137 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 1)) - (T(4) + T(9))) \\ 94162 &:= ((2 + T(6)) \times (-1) + T((T(4) \times 9))) \\ 94176 &:= ((T((6 + 7)) \times T(T(-(1) + T(4)))) - 9) \\ 94182 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(T((8 + 1))) \times T((4 + 9))) \\ 94185 &:= (T((5 + 8)) \times T(((1 + 4) \times 9))) \\ 94194 &:= ((T((4 + 9)) \times T(T(-(1) + T(4)))) + 9) \\ 94206 &:= (T(6) - ((0 - T((T(2) + T(4)))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94213 &:= (T((T(3) + 1)) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94219 &:= ((91 \times 2^{T(4)}) + T(T(9))) \\ 94224 &:= (((T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) + 2) \times T(T(4))) + 9) \\ 94225 &:= ((T(T(5))/T(2)) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94227 &:= ((7 \times T(T(2))) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94234 &:= ((T(T(4)) - (T(3))) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94236 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) + ((T(4) \times T(9)))) \\ 94237 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(2) + (4)))) + T(9)) \\ 94239 &:= ((9 \times T(3)) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94254 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + 5) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + 9) \\ 94263 &:= (T((T(3) + (6))) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94273 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(T(T(2))) + T(4)))) - 9) \\ 94275 &:= ((-5) + (7 \times T(24))) \times T(9) \\ 94276 &:= (-T((6 + 7))) \times ((T(2) - 4) - T(T(9))) \\ 94281 &:= ((T(T(-(1 - 8))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-9))) \\ 94284 &:= ((4 + (-8) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 9) \\ 94295 &:= (-5) - ((-92) \times (-T(4) + T(T(9)))) \\ 94305 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((0 - T((3 + T(4)))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94322 &:= (2 \times (((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9)))) \\ 94323 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 2) \times (T(3) + T((T(4) \times 9)))) \\ 94325 &:= ((T(T(T(5 - 2)))) / 3) \times T(49) \\ 94327 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + T(9))) \\ 94329 &:= (((T(9) \times (2 + T(T(T(3)))) - 4) \times 9) \\ 94365 &:= (-T(5) \times ((-T(6)) \times T((T(3) \times 4))) + 9) \\ 94367 &:= (-T((7 + 6))) \times ((-T(3) - 4) - T(T(9))) \\ 94372 &:= (-T(2)) - (((-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 4)) + T(T(9))) \\ 94376 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + 9) \\ 94395 &:= (-T((5 + 9))) \times (T((T(3) + T(4))) - T(T(9))) \\ 94416 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(-(1 - 4) + T(4))) \times T(T(9))) \\ 94425 &:= (((5 + T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(9)) \\ 94426 &:= (((6 + T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - 9) \\ 94428 &:= (T(8) \times ((2 + T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(4)) - 9))) \\ 94434 &:= (-T(T(4)) - ((-T(3) - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(4)) + 9))) \\ 94438 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times 3) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) - 9)) \\ 94445 &:= (((T(T(5) - 4)) - 4) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \\ 94446 &:= (T((T(6) - T(4))) \times T((4 + 49))) \\ 94458 &:= ((T(T(8)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \times (4 + 9)) \\ 94464 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(6))) + ((T(4)^4)) \times 9) \\ 94465 &:= (-T((T(5) \times 6))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) + 9)) \\ 94482 &:= (2 \times (T(T(8)) - ((T(4) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94494 &:= (-T(T(4)) + ((T(T(9)) + 4) \times (-T((4 + 9)))) \\ 94495 &:= (-5) - ((-T(9)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 94527 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) - T((-4) + T(9)))) \\ 94535 &:= (T((-5) + T((-3) + T(5))) \times (-T(4) - T(9))) \\ 94536 &:= (6 \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((-5) - T(4)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 94545 &:= ((T(T((T(5) - 4))) - ((T(T(5)) - T(4))) \times T(9)) \\ 94572 &:= ((2 + (T(7) \times 5)) \times T((4 \times 9))) \\ 94575 &:= ((-57) \times (-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(9) \\ 94577 &:= (T(7) - (T((T(7) - T(5))) \times (-4) - T(T(9)))) \\ 94596 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (-T(95)) + T(T(4))) - 9) \\ 94629 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + ((T(64) \times T(9)))) \\ 94635 &:= (T((T(5) \times 3)) + (T(64) \times T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

- 94637 := (((T(T(7)) × (T(3) + T(T(6)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(9))
94647 := ((T((7 × 4)) × T(T(6))) + T((-4) + T(9)))
94662 := (((T(2) × T(6)) × (-T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9)))
94665 := (T(T(5)) + (((T(6) + T(64)) × T(9))))
94667 := (((T(T(7)) + (6)) × T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(9)))
94674 := (((4 + T(T(7))) × T(T(6))) - (4 × 9))
94695 := (((T(5) + T(9)) × (T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(9)))
94722 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(2)) + T(T(7)))) - ((T(4) × T(9))))
94725 := (((-T(5)) × T((2 × T(7)))) × (-4)) - T(T(9)))
94727 := (-T(7) - ((T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)) + (4)))) - T(9))
94731 := (-T(13)) × (-T((7 - 4))) - T(T(9)))
94735 := (((5 + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(7))) - T((T(T(4)) - 9)))
94743 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(47) × 4)) - 9)
94746 := ((T(T(6)) × (4 + T(T(7)))) + (4 × 9))
94755 := ((T(T(T((T(5)/5)))) × (T(T(7)) + (4))) + T(9))
94763 := (-3) + (((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) + T(T(9)))
94765 := (-5) - (-6) × ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) × T(9)))
94766 := (((T(T(6)) × T((T(6) + (7)))) - T(T(4))) + T(T(9)))
94773 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) + ((7 - T(T(4))) + T(T(9))))
94776 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T(((T(T(7)) - T(4))/9)))
94785 := -((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(8)) - T(74)) × T(9)))
94815 := (((T(5) × T((1 + T(8)))) - T(4)) × 9)
94821 := ((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(T((8/4)))))) + T(T(9)))
94825 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(2) + T(8)))) + T(49))
94827 := ((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T((8/4))) + T(T(9))))
94845 := (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))))
94857 := (7 × (T(5) - ((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-9)))
94864 := (((4 × T(T(6)))^{8/4})/9)
94867 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) + (T(8) + T(4))) + T(T(9)))
94876 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T(T((8 - 4)))) + T(T(9)))
94887 := (((-7) + T(T(8))) × (T(8) × 4)) - 9)
94892 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(9)) + 8) × (-T((4 + 9))))))
94926 := ((T(6) × (T(T(2)) + (T(94)))) + T(T(9)))
94932 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(3))) + (T(9) × 4))) - 9)
94962 := ((T((2 × T(6))) + T(T(9))) × 49)
94965 := (-T(5)) × (-6) + ((T(T(9)) × T(T(4)))/(-9))
94968 := ((-8) + ((T(6) + T(T(9))) × T(4))) × 9)
94994 := (-T(4) - ((9 + T(T(9))) × (-T((4 + 9))))
94995 := (((T(T(5)) × 9) + T(T(9))) - (4)) × T(9))
94997 := (-7) - ((9 + T(T(9))) × (-T((4 + 9))))
95127 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) × T(T((1 + 5)))) - T(9))
95172 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) × T(T((15 - 9))))
95175 := (((5 × T(7)) + 1) × T(5)) × T(9))
95215 := (-5) - ((-1) - T((-2) + T(5))) × T(T(9)))
95219 := ((T(T(9)) - 1) + (T((-2) + T(5))) × T(T(9)))
95235 := (T(5) + (((T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) + T(5)) × T(T(9))))
95238 := (T(T(8)) × ((T(3) + 2) + (T(5) × 9)))
95256 := (((6 + T(T(5)))²) × (T(5) - 9))
95262 := (T(2) × ((T(6) + (2^{T(5)})) - T(T(9))))
95265 := (T(5) × (T(T(6)) - (T(T(2)) × (T(5) - T(T(9))))))
95274 := (-T(4) - (-T(7)) × T((T((-2) + T(5)) - 9)))
95277 := (-7) - (-T(7)) × T((T((-2) + T(5)) - 9))
95284 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(82))/T(T(-(5 - 9))))
95325 := ((T(5) + T((-2) + T(T(3)))) × T(-(T(5) - T(9))))
95326 := ((T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(-(5 - 9))))
95337 := (((T(T(7)) + (T(3))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(9)))
95344 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) × 59)
95349 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(5)) - 9))
95355 := ((T(T(5)) × (53 × T(5))) - T(9))
95382 := (2 × ((T(8)³) + T((5 × 9))))
95425 := ((T(52) × (T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) - T(T(9)))
95437 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(5)) - 9)))
95445 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T((4 + 4)))) - (-T(5)) × T(T(9)))
95462 := ((T((2 × 6)) + T(T(T(4)))) × 59)
95469 := (-((T(T(9)) + (T(6)))) - (T(-(T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) × (-T(9))))
95474 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (7 + T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - 9))
95475 := (57 × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) × 9)))
95524 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T((5 × 5)) + 9))
95535 := (-T(5)) × (T(3) - (5 × T((5 + T(9))))))
95571 := (T((T((1 + 7)) + (5))) × (T(T(5)) - 9))
95585 := (-5) × (8 - (T(5) × T((5 + T(9))))))
95586 := (T(T(6)) + (((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(9))))
95589 := (T(((T(9) + 8) - T(5)) × (T(T(5)) + 9))
95597 := (-T(7)) - ((T(9) - T(T(5))) × T((5 + T(9))))
95616 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T((1 + 6)))) + T((T(5) + T(9))))
95622 := (2 × (((T(T(2))⁶) + T(T(5))) + T(T(9))))
95625 := ((T(T(5)) - T((T(2) + (6)))) × T((5 + T(9))))
95628 := ((-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(65) × T(9)))
95634 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) × ((T(6) - T(5)) × 9))
95637 := ((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(6) - T((T(5) + T(9))))
95676 := (-T(67)) × (-T(6) - T((T(5) - 9)))
95679 := (((T(T(9)) + T(7)) × (6 × T(5))) + 9)
95697 := ((7 × 9) × (-T(6) + T(T(T(-(5 - 9))))))
95724 := (-4) × ((T((2 × T(7))) × (-T(5)) + 9))
95725 := (T(T((5 × 2))) + (T((T(7) - T(5))) × T(T(9))))
95742 := (((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-7)) + 5) × 9)
95744 := (44 × (T(T(7)) + (T(59))))
95745 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) × (T(T(5)) + T(T(9))))))
95746 := ((T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(7) - T(5))) × T(T(9))))
95748 := (T((8 × 4)) + ((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) × T(T(9)))
95756 := (((T(T(6)) + (5)) × T(T(7))) - (T(5) + T(9)))
95775 := (T(5) - (T((T(7) + T(7))) × (-T(5) + T(9))))
95784 := (-4) × (8 + (T(T(7)) × (-59)))
95795 := (((5 - T(T(9))) × (T(7) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(9)))

$$\begin{aligned} 95823 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(2) + T((T(8) + (59)))))) \\ 95825 &:= (((5 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((-8) + T(5)))) + 9) \\ 95827 &:= ((-T(7)) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - (T(85))) - T(9)) \\ 95832 &:= ((T(2) - (T(3) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-T(5) + 9)) \\ 95835 &:= -(((T(5)) \times (T(T(3)) - T((8 \times 5)))) + T(9)) \\ 95837 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T((-8) + T(5)))) + 9)) \\ 95838 &:= (T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) - (-T((8 + 5)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 95845 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-T((8 + 5)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 95862 &:= (-T(2)) - (-T(T(6)) \times (T(T((-8) + T(5)))) + 9)) \\ 95865 &:= ((5 \times T(T(6))) \times ((8 + T(T(5))) - T(9)) \\ 95868 &:= (-T(8)) - ((6 \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(5) + 9)) \\ 95883 &:= ((-T(38)) \times (-8) - T(T(5))) + T(T(9)) \\ 95925 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(95))) - T(9)) \\ 95955 &:= -((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) \times T((5 + 9)))) \\ 95976 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) + T(T(5))) + T(T(9))) \\ 95982 &:= (-T(2)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times (T(5) \times (-9))) \\ 95985 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(8) + (T(9) \times T(5))) \times 9)) \\ 96075 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(7)) - (0 - T(6))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 96165 &:= (((T(5) + T(61)) + T(T(6))) \times T(9)) \\ 96177 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((7 - 1) + T(T(6)))) - T(9)) \\ 96207 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(02))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(9))) \\ 96213 &:= ((T(T((T(3) + 1))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6)))) - 9) \\ 96216 &:= ((T(6) + T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 96222 &:= ((-T(T(2)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((-2) + T(6)) + 9)) \\ 96228 &:= (T((T(8) \times 2)) + ((T(6^6)) \times T(9))) \\ 96231 &:= ((T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6)))) + 9) \\ 96237 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)))) + (6 + 9)) \\ 96252 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T(5) + T((2 \times 6))) \times T(T(9))) \\ 96255 &:= (T((T(5) + T(5))) \times (T(2) \times 69)) \\ 96267 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((6^{T(2)}) + T(6))) + T(9)) \\ 96273 &:= (T(3) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6)))) + T(9)) \\ 96276 &:= (T(6) - ((-72) - T(6)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 96282 &:= (2 \times ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T((6 \times 9))) \\ 96294 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (9^2)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\ 96324 &:= ((T(4) - (-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 69) \\ 96327 &:= (((T(T(7)) + 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(6)) \times 9)) \\ 96333 &:= (T(3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(6)) - T(9)))) \\ 96345 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-T((4 + 3))) \times T(T(6)) + T(9)) \\ 96348 &:= (((8 \times T(T(4))) - (T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) - 9)) \\ 96372 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(6)))) + T(9)) \\ 96387 &:= (((-T(T(7))) - T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(6)) - T(9)) \\ 96391 &:= (((1 + T(9))^3) - (T(6) \times T(9))) \\ 96426 &:= (((T(6)^2) \times (-T(4)) + T(T(6)))) - T(T(9)) \\ 96429 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (-4) \times T((6 + T(9)))) \\ 96435 &:= ((5 + (3 \times T((4 \times T(6)))) \times 9) \\ 96441 &:= (T(T(-((1 - 4))) + T(T(4))) \times (6 + T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96447 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (4 \times 4)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(9))) \\ 96459 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) - ((T(6) + T(9)))) \\ 96462 &:= ((-2) - T(T(6))) \times (-46 \times 9)) \\ 96465 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(4)) + (6 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 96475 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(7)) - (4)) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)) \\ 96492 &:= ((-T((T(2) + 9))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\ 96495 &:= (T(5) - (T(T((9 - 4))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96497 &:= (-T(7)) - (-T(9)) \times T(-((4 - 69)))) \\ 96522 &:= ((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96525 &:= ((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T((56 + 9))) \\ 96528 &:= ((8 \times T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96545 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96546 &:= (T(6) - ((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) \times T((6 \times 9))) \\ 96549 &:= ((T(9) \times T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) - ((T(6) - T(9)))) \\ 96555 &:= ((5 \times T(5)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96564 &:= ((4 \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 96576 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(5) \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)))) \\ 96585 &:= -((T(5) + (-((8 \times 5)) \times T(69))) \\ 96595 &:= (-5) + ((T(9) - (5)) \times T(69)) \\ 96615 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-1) \times T(T(6))) - (6 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 96624 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2))) + (T(6))) \times (-T(6)) + T(9)) \\ 96642 &:= (T((T(2) + T(4))) \times ((T(6) + (6)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 96645 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T(-((T(T(4)) - T((-6) + T(6)))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 96669 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-6 \times 69))) \\ 96735 &:= (T(5) - ((3 - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)) \\ 96756 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T((5 \times (7 + 6))) \times T(9))) \\ 96768 &:= ((8^{T(6)/7}) \times (T(6) \times 9)) \\ 96774 &:= (T((T(T(4)) + (7))) + (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(9)))) \\ 96784 &:= ((T(4) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)) \\ 96792 &:= -((T(T(2)) + (-((T(9) + T(7))) \times T((6 + T(9)))) \\ 96794 &:= (-4) - (-((T(9) + T(7))) \times T((6 + T(9)))) \\ 96795 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times (9 + 7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(9)) \\ 96798 &:= (((T(8) + 9) + T(7)) \times T((6 + T(9)))) \\ 96824 &:= (T((T(4) + T(2))) \times ((8 + T(6)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 96843 &:= ((((-3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 8) \times (-T(6)) - 9) \\ 96867 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(8))) + (T(69))) \\ 96873 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times 7) \times T(T(8))) + (6)) - T(T(9)) \\ 96876 &:= (-6) \times ((T(T(7)) + 8) \times (6 - T(9))) \\ 96885 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (T((8 + 8)) \times 6)) - T(T(9)) \\ 96915 &:= (T((T(5) + T((1 + 9)))) \times (-6) + T(9)) \\ 96957 &:= (-7) \times ((-((T(5) + T(9))) \times T(T(6))) + 9) \\ 96975 &:= (((5 + T(T(7))) + 9) \times T(T(6))) - T(9) \\ 97011 &:= ((-1) + (T(T(10)) \times 7)) \times 9) \\ 97015 &:= (-5) + (T(T(10)) \times (7 \times 9)) \\ 97065 &:= (((T(5) \times T(T(6))) \times T(07)) + T(9)) \\ 97128 &:= (T(((T(8) \times 2) - 1)) \times (-7) + T(9)) \\ 97146 &:= ((-T(6)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times 7)) \times (-9) \end{aligned}$$

- 97155 := $(-T(5) \times ((T(T((5+1))) \times (-T(7))) - 9))$
97185 := $(-T(5) - (T(8) \times (1 - T((T(7) + T(9))))))$
97209 := $((T(9) \times T(T(T(T(02)))))) + (T(T(7))) \times 9$
97228 := $(-8) + (T((2^{T(2)})) \times T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97233 := $(-3) - (-(T(3)^2) \times T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97236 := $(T((6 \times T(3))) \times (2 \times (T(7) + T(9))))$
97239 := $-((T((T(9) + 3)) - (T(2)^7) \times T(9)))$
97242 := $(T(T(2)) - (-(T((4 \times 2))) \times T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97243 := $(T((-3) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7) + 9)))$
97244 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times T((7 \times 9))))$
97245 := $((-5) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) \times T(9)$
97249 := $((T((T(9) + 4))) + T(T(2))) \times 79$
97251 := $(T(T((1+5))) \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + 9))$
97257 := $((T(T(7)) + T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(-(7-9))))$
97263 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9)))$
97266 := $(T(T((6+6))) + (T((T(T(2)) + 7))) \times T(T(9)))$
97272 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(7)) \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(7)) - 9))$
97275 := $(T(T(5)) - (T(7) - (T(2)^7) \times T(9)))$
97319 := $((T(9) + 1)^3 + T(7)) - T(9)$
97335 := $((T(5) \times T(T(3))) \times (-(T(3) - (7 \times T(9))))$
97344 := $((4 \times T((4 \times 3)))^{-7+9})$
97345 := $(-5) - (-(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3)) + (-7) + T(9))))$
97362 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(6) - (-(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + T(9))))))$
97365 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(((6+T(3)) + T(7)))) - T(T(9)))$
97383 := $((T(T(3)) - 8) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(9)))$
97386 := $-((T(T(6)) - ((T(83) \times T(7)) + 9)))$
97389 := $(T(9) - (T(8) \times (-3) - T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97392 := $(-T(2) - ((9 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + T(9))$
97394 := $(-T(T(4))) - ((9 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) - 9$
97395 := $((T(59) \times T((3+7))) + T(9))$
97398 := $((T(T(T(T(8)/9))) + T(3)) \times (7 \times 9))$
97416 := $((6^{-1+4}) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9)))$
97417 := $(T(T(7)) - ((-1) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 7)) \times (-9))$
97424 := $((-(T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(7) - 9))$
97425 := $-(((T(T(5))^2) + (T((T(4) \times 7)) \times (-T(9))))$
97426 := $(T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-7 \times 9)))$
97431 := $((1 - T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (-T(T(7))) - 9$
97434 := $((4 + ((T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7)) \times 9)$
97442 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(7) + 9))$
97443 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) + (-7) + T(9))$
97445 := $((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(4)) + 7)) + T(T(9))$
97449 := $((9 + T(T((-4) + T(4)))) \times T(T(7))) + 9$
97455 := $((T((5 \times 5)) \times T((-4) + T(7))) - T(9))$
97461 := $((-(1+6) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7 \times 9))$
97476 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) - ((4 + T(T(7))) \times (-9))$
97479 := $((T(9) \times T(T((7+4)))) - (T((7 \times 9)))$
97482 := $(T((T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (7 \times 9)))$
97485 := $((T(T(5)) \times (8/4)) \times T(T(7))) + T(9)$
97488 := $(T(8) \times (8 + (T((-4) + T(7))) \times 9))$
97489 := $((T(T(9)) + (8^4)) \times (T(7) - 9))$
97495 := $-(((T(T(5)) + (T(9) - T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(9))))$
97524 := $(T(42) \times ((5+7) \times 9))$
97525 := $((T(T(5)) \times 2) - 5) \times (T(T(7)) + 9)$
97533 := $((T((T(3) \times T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(7))) - T(T(9)))$
97545 := $((T(5) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(7))) - T(T(9)))$
97563 := $((T(T(3)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(5))) \times T(7)) - T(9)$
97575 := $(-T(5) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))) - T(T(7))) - 9)$
97578 := $((T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) + 5) \times (-T(7)))) \times (-9))$
97587 := $((7 \times T(T(8))) - (T(5))) \times T(T(T(-(7-9))))$
97596 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))) - T((-7) + T(9)))$
97602 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(06) + T(T(7)))) - T(T(9)))$
97623 := $((T(T(3) \times 2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(9))$
97627 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T((2 \times 6)))) \times T(7)) - 9$
97638 := $(T(8) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(6) - T(T(7)))) + T(T(9))))$
97645 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-4) - T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) + 9))$
97653 := $((T(T(3)) + (T(5) \times T(T(6)))) \times T(7)) + T(9)$
97656 := $(-6) - ((-T(5) - T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - 9))$
97662 := $-(((T(T(2)) - T(T(6))) - (T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - 9))$
97668 := $(T(8) \times ((6+6) + T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97671 := $((1 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9))$
97679 := $(-97) \times ((T(6) + 7) - T(T(9)))$
97683 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T(8) \times (-6) - T((T(7) + T(9))))$
97695 := $((T(T(5)) + (9 \times T(T(6))) - T(7)) \times T(9))$
97713 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T((1+7))) \times 7) - 9))$
97725 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((2 + T(T(7))) + T(T(7)))) + T(9))$
97734 := $(T((4 \times 3)) \times (-7) + (T(7) \times T(9)))$
97743 := $((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times (-7) + T(79))$
97749 := $(-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(7))) \times (-7 \times 9))$
97755 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(7))) + (7 \times T(9))$
97768 := $(-8) - (-(T(6)) \times T((T((7+7)) - 9)))$
97776 := $(T(6) \times T((T(7) + ((77-9))))$
97782 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - (-(T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(T(-(7-9))))))$
97783 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 8) \times T(T(7))) - (-7) \times T(T(9))$
97785 := $((T((58+7)) + T(7)) \times T(9))$
97796 := $((T((6+9)) - T(7)) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))))$
97833 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T((T(T(3)) + 8) - 7)) - T(T(9)))$
97836 := $(-T(6) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-7) + T(9)))$
97839 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((T(T(3)) - 8))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9))$
97845 := $((5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(8) + T(7))) - T(T(9))$
97846 := $((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(((T(8) \times (-7))/(-9))))$
97848 := $((T(8) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 8) \times 7)) \times 9$
97857 := $((T(T(T((7-5)))) \times (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - T(9))$
97863 := $(T(3) - ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) \times (-7)) + T(9))$

$$\begin{aligned} 97866 &:= (((-6) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(8) - (7)))) - 9) \\ 97867 &:= ((T((T(7) - (6))) - T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9))) \\ 97873 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)) + (T(8) \times T((T(7) + T(9)))))) \\ 97875 &:= -(((T(57) - T(87)) \times T(9))) \\ 97893 &:= (((T(-(3 - 9))) \times T(T(8))) \times 7) - 9) \\ 97923 &:= (-T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-9) - T(T(7)) - 9)) \\ 97934 &:= (-T(4) - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((-9) - T(T(7)) - 9))) \\ 97937 &:= (-7) - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((-9) - T(T(7)) - 9)) \\ 97944 &:= (T(T((-4) + T(4))) \times ((9 + T(T(7)) + 9)) \\ 97945 &:= (-5) \times ((-4) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(7) - 9)) \\ 97956 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(5) \times T((T(9) - (7)))))) \times (-9) \\ 97965 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (6 \times T((9 + 7)))) + T(9)) \\ 97972 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(9 + 7) - T(9)))) \\ 97983 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) \times (9 + 7))) \times 9) \\ 98124 &:= (T((T(T(4)) - (T(2) + 1))) \times (T(T(8)/9)) \\ 98145 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + T((1 \times 8))) \times T(9)) \\ 98217 &:= (7 \times ((T(T(1 + 2))) \times T(T(8))) + T(9)) \\ 98226 &:= (6 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - 9)) \\ 98229 &:= ((-T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T((T(2) + 8))) \times T(9))) \\ 98235 &:= (T(5) \times (-3) + ((T(2)^8) - 9)) \\ 98248 &:= (8 \times (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 98252 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((T(5) - (-2) \times T(8)))))/(-9)) \\ 98253 &:= (3 \times ((T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 98265 &:= (((-5) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 8))) - T(9) \\ 98271 &:= ((T((1 + 72)) \times T(8)) + T(T(9))) \\ 98275 &:= (-5) \times (T(7) - (T(2)^{-T(8)+T(9)})) \\ 98287 &:= (7 \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((T(8)/9)))) \\ 98297 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(2)) + (89))) \\ 98319 &:= (((T(9) - 1) \times T(T((3 + 8)))) + T(T(9))) \\ 98325 &:= (T(5) \times (T(2) + ((3^8) - 9)) \\ 98343 &:= ((-T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times ((3 \times T(T(8)) + 9)) \\ 98345 &:= ((-T(T(5))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) \times 89) \\ 98346 &:= (T(6) + ((-T(4)) + T((T(3) + 8))) \times T(T(9))) \\ 98347 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8)) - T(9)) \\ 98355 &:= (T(5) \times (5 + ((3^8) - 9)) \\ 98379 &:= (((T((T(9) + T(7))) + 3) \times T(8)) + T(T(9))) \\ 98388 &:= (T(8) \times (T((8 + T(3))) + T((8 \times 9))) \\ 98425 &:= ((5^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(4) \times 8) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 98427 &:= (7 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times (4 + T(T(8)))) - 9)) \\ 98437 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) + T(9)) \\ 98445 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(4) \times 4))) + (T(8) + 9)) \\ 98455 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((-T(5) + T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(8)/9)))) \\ 98467 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(4))) + (T(T(8)) - T(9))) \\ 98469 &:= (9 \times (T(T(6)) + (T(4) \times (T(8) + T(T(9)))))) \\ 98475 &:= (((-5) \times T(T(7))) \times (-48)) + T(T(9)) \\ 98482 &:= (-T(T(2))) + (8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 98484 &:= (-4) + (8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98485 &:= (-T(T(5))) + (((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) + T(9)) \\ 98487 &:= (-T(7)) + (((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) - T(9)) \\ 98488 &:= (((8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((8 \times 9)) \\ 98496 &:= ((T(-(T(6) - T(9)))) + 4) \times (T(8) \times 9) \\ 98523 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) + T((T(2) + (5)))) \times (-T(T(8)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 98532 &:= ((2 \times T(T(3))) \times T(((T(5) + 8) + T(9)))) \\ 98535 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((3^{T(5)-8}) \times T(9))) \\ 98545 &:= (-5) + ((T(4) \times T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) - 9)) \\ 98554 &:= (((T(4)^5) - T(5)) - T((8 + T(9)))) \\ 98568 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T((T(6) + T(5)))) \times T(T(8)))/9) \\ 98577 &:= ((-7) \times ((T(T(7)) - (T(5))) \times (-T(8)))) + T(9) \\ 98578 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(T(5)))) + T((T(8)/9))) \\ 98587 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times T((5 + 8))) + T(T(9))) \\ 98592 &:= (T(T((T(2) + 9))) \times (T(5) + ((8 + 9)))) \\ 98595 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(9 - 5)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times T(9) \\ 98622 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(68)) + T(9))) \\ 98627 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - T((T(8)/9))) \\ 98637 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(6) \times (-8 - 9)))) \\ 98658 &:= ((-8) + T((5 + 6))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) \\ 98682 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(6))) \times T((8 + 9))) \\ 98685 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(8))) - (6)) \times T((8 + 9)) \\ 98687 &:= ((-7) + T(8)) \times T((T((T(6) - 8)) - 9)) \\ 98713 &:= ((T((T(T(3)) + 1)) \times T(T(7))) - (T(89))) \\ 98726 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) + (89)) \\ 98739 &:= ((T(9) \times (3^7)) + (T(8) \times 9)) \\ 98743 &:= (((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(7) + T(8))) - 9) \\ 98746 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + T(8))) - T(9))) \\ 98748 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((8 + 9)))) \\ 98775 &:= (((T(-(5 - 7)))^7) + 8) \times T(9) \\ 98784 &:= ((T(T(4)) + 8) \times (T(7) + T(T(T(8)/9)))) \\ 98793 &:= (3 \times (T(9) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(8) + T(9)))) \\ 98819 &:= (-T((T(9) + 1))) - (-T(8)) \times T((T(T(8)/9))) \\ 98829 &:= (-T(T(9)) - ((2 + T(8)) \times T((8 \times 9)))) \\ 98856 &:= ((6^5) + (88 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 98865 &:= (((-5) \times (6 - T(8))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(9)) \\ 98884 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (8 \times 8)) + (T(8) \times 9)) \\ 98892 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(9) - 8)) \times (-T(T(8)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 98928 &:= (T(8) \times (T((2 + T(9))) + ((T(8) \times T(9)))) \\ 98937 &:= (((7 \times T(-(3 - 9))) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(9))) \\ 98945 &:= (-T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + (-98) \times T(T(9))) \\ 98946 &:= ((T(6) \times (T((T(4) \times 9)) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(9))) \\ 98955 &:= (((T(5) + T((T(T(5)) - T(9)))) - (T(T(8)))) \times T(9) \\ 98985 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((T((T(T(8)/9)) \times T(8)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 99135 &:= ((T(T((5 + T(3)))) + ((1 - 9))) \times T(9) \\ 99176 &:= ((T(6) + T(7)) \times (-1) + (T(9) \times T(9))) \\ 99222 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T(T(2)) - T(T((2 + 9)))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 99225 &:= (T(((5 + 2)^2)) \times (9 \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99228 &:= ((-T(8)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T((2+9))) \times (-T(9)))) \\
 99234 &:= (((T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(9)) + 9) \\
 99246 &:= (T(6) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times (T(9) \times T(9)))) \\
 99252 &:= (-((T(2)^5)) - (T(T((2+9))) \times (-T(9)))) \\
 99255 &:= (-T(5) + ((-5) + T(T((2+9)))) \times T(9)) \\
 99262 &:= ((-2) - T(T(6))) - (T(T((2+9))) \times (-T(9))) \\
 99264 &:= -((T(T(T(T(-((4-6)))))) - (T(T((2+9))) \times T(9))) \\
 99267 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (6)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(9) + T(9)))) \\
 99279 &:= (((T(9) \times 7)^2) + 9) + T(9)) \\
 99288 &:= (8 \times ((T(8)/T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - 9) \\
 99315 &:= (((5 + T(13)) \times T(T(9))) - T(9)) \\
 99324 &:= (-4) \times (((-T(2)) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))) + 9) \\
 99327 &:= ((-T(7)) \times T(T(2))) + (T((T(T(3)) + T(9))) \times T(9)) \\
 99342 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2))) - 4) - (T((T(T(3)) + T(9))) \times T(9))) \\
 99344 &:= (-4) \times (4 + ((T(T(3)) - T(9)) \times T(T(9)))) \\
 99345 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((T(T(4)) - T(3)) \times (T(9) \times T(9)))) \\
 99351 &:= (((1 + T(5)) \times T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - 9) \\
 99355 &:= (-5) + (((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) - T(9)) \times T(T(9))) \\
 99357 &:= (((7^5) \times T(3)) - T((9 + T(9)))) \\
 99369 &:= (((T(T(9) + T(6))) - 3) \times T(9)) + 9) \\
 99372 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times (3 + (T(9) \times T(9)))) \\
 99375 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3) \times T(T(9))) + 9)) \\
 99378 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T((3+9)) \times T(T(9)))) \\
 99387 &:= (((7 \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) + T((9 + T(9)))) \\
 99396 &:= ((T(6) + T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(9 + T(9)))) \\
 99429 &:= (((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((4+9)))) - T(T(9))) \\
 99435 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(4) + 9)))) + T(T(9))) \\
 99462 &:= (2 \times (T(T(6)) + ((T(4) \times T(99)))) \\
 99465 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times T(9)) - T(9))) \\
 99467 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(((6-4) + 9))) \times T(9)) \\
 99468 &:= (-T(8)) + ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times T(9)) + 9) \\
 99477 &:= (-7) \times (((T(T(7)) \times (-4)) + T(9)) \times 9) \\
 99478 &:= (-8) + ((T(T((7+4))) \times T(9)) - 9) \\
 99486 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (T(8) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - 9) \\
 99492 &:= (-T(2)) + (T(9) \times T(T((T(4) + (9/9)))) \\
 99495 &:= (T((594/9)) \times T(9)) \\
 99504 &:= ((T(T((-4) + T(05)))) \times T(9)) + 9) \\
 99516 &:= (T(6) + (T(T((1+5)) + T(9))) \times T(9)) \\
 99522 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T((-2) + T(5))) \times (T(T(9)) - 9)) \\
 99525 &:= (-T(5)) + ((T(T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) \times T(9)) + T(9)) \\
 99531 &:= (((1 + T(T((T(3) + (5)))) \times T(9)) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99535 &:= (-5) + ((T(T((T(3) + (5)))) \times T(9)) + T(9)) \\
 99555 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((-5) + T(9))) + T(T(9)))) \\
 99567 &:= ((-7) + ((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) \times T(9))) \times 9) \\
 99582 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-8) + (5 \times T((9 \times 9)))) \\
 99595 &:= ((T(-((5-9)))^5) - (9 \times T(9))) \\
 99615 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((T((1 \times 6)) + T(9))) \times T(9))) \\
 99625 &:= (-5) + ((T(2) + T((T(6) + T(9)))) \times T(9)) \\
 99627 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(9) - T(T(9)))) \\
 99645 &:= ((T(5) \times T(4)) - (T((T(6) + T(9))) \times (-T(9)))) \\
 99647 &:= (-T(7)) + ((4 + T((T(6) + T(9)))) \times T(9)) \\
 99648 &:= ((8 \times 4) \times ((T(T(6)) \times 9) + T(T(9)))) \\
 99654 &:= (((T(4)^5) - T(T(6))) + (T(T(9))/(-9))) \\
 99655 &:= (-5) \times (-5) + (-6) \times T((9 \times 9)) \\
 99666 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - ((-6) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(9))) \\
 99672 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(-((6-9)))))) + T(T(9))) \\
 99675 &:= (((5 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 9)) + T(T(9))) \\
 99724 &:= ((T(4)^{-2+7}) - T((T(T(9))/T(9)))) \\
 99726 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(2) + (7 \times 9))) \times T(9))) \\
 99747 &:= (((T(T(7)) - T(4)) \times (T(7) \times 9)) - T(9)) \\
 99753 &:= ((3 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) + (9 \times T(9)))) \\
 99756 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T((T(9)/9)))) \\
 99765 &:= (((T(T((5+6))) + (7)) \times T(9)) - T(9)) \\
 99786 &:= (-6) + ((T(8) \times T(7)) \times 99) \\
 99792 &:= ((T((2+9)) \times T(7)) \times (9 + T(9))) \\
 99813 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(-((1-89) - 9))) \\
 99828 &:= (T(8) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (8 \times (9 + T(9)))) \\
 99834 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((3 + T(8))) + T(T(9)))) + 9) \\
 99846 &:= (((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + 8) \times T(9)) - 9) \\
 99855 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T((T(T(8))/9))) - T(9)) \\
 99864 &:= (((T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))) + 8) \times T(9)) + 9) \\
 99873 &:= ((T((T(T(3)) + T(7))) + 8) \times (9 \times 9)) \\
 99876 &:= ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times ((T(8)/(-9)) + T(9))) \\
 99885 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((-8) \times T((-8) + T(9))) - T(T(9)) \\
 99891 &:= ((T(-((1-9))) \times T((T(T(8))/9))) - 9) \\
 99936 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(-((3-9)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) \\
 99945 &:= (((T(5) \times T(4)) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + T(9)) \\
 99954 &:= (((T(4)^5) - T(9)) - (9/9)) \\
 99955 &:= (((5+5)^{T(9)/9}) - T(9)) \\
 99985 &:= (-T(5)) + (T((T(8)/9))^{T(9)/9}) \\
 99991 &:= (((1+9)^{T(9)/9}) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of num-

bers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, Quadratic numbers, Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients, S-gonal numbers, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

3.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$1 := 1^1$	$3529 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2$
$23 := -2^2 + 3^3$	$4316 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3$
$1239 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$4355 := 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5$
$1364 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3$	$39339 := -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$1654 := -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5$	$46350 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4$
$1837 := 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3$	$46360 := 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6$
$2137 := -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2$	$397612 := 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3$
$2173 := -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7$	$423858 := 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5$
$2537 := 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$637395 := 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7$
$3125 := -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5$	$758014 := 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8$
$3275 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5$	$778530 := 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8$
$3435 := 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5$	$804637 := 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7$

$15647982 := 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6$
$17946238 := 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7$
$57396108 := -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8$
$134287690 := 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1$
$387945261 := 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5$
$392876054 := 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6$
$392876540 := -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

3.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$13825 := 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5}$	$= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1$
$14641 := (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$	$= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$
$15552 := (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2$	$= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16377} &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 \mathbf{23328} &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 \mathbf{116565} &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 \mathbf{131072} &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 \mathbf{147419} &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{147429} &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{147491} &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{156252} &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{656250} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656251} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656252} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656253} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656254} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656255} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656256} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656257} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656258} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 \mathbf{656259} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

3.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{145} &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & \mathbf{361469} &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{733} &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & \mathbf{363239} &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 \mathbf{1463} &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & \mathbf{363269} &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 \mathbf{5177} &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & \mathbf{364292} &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 \mathbf{10077} &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & \mathbf{397584} &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 \mathbf{40585} &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & \mathbf{398173} &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 \mathbf{80518} &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & \mathbf{403199} &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 \mathbf{317489} &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & \mathbf{408937} &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 \mathbf{352797} &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & \mathbf{715799} &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357592} &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & \mathbf{720599} &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 \mathbf{357941} &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}
 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

3.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3+9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839795 := -8 + (-3+9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3-9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3-9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1+5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9+1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

3.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9} / 6 &= 6^{(\sqrt{9+2-1})}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2896} &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{331779} &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{342995} &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 \mathbf{759375} &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}}. \\
 \mathbf{759381} &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5040} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5041} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5042} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5043} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5044} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5045} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5046} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5047} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5048} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 \mathbf{5049} &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$\mathbf{120} := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!$	$\mathbf{25} := 5^2$
$\mathbf{127} := -1 + 2^7$	$\mathbf{64} := \sqrt{4^6}$
$\mathbf{1673} := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$\mathbf{289} := (9 + 8)^2$
$\mathbf{1679} := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$\mathbf{3894} := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$\mathbf{1680} := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$\mathbf{4957} := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$\mathbf{38970} := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$\mathbf{6992} := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$\mathbf{38986} := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$\mathbf{26493} := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$\mathbf{40310} := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$\mathbf{30792} := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$\mathbf{90894} := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$\mathbf{54476} := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$\mathbf{91560} := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$\mathbf{75989} := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

3.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{143} &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{986} &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{1178} &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\
 \mathbf{2585} &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 \mathbf{12819} &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{24297} &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 \mathbf{39394} &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74997} &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{87937} &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 \mathbf{98703} &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{34} &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & \mathbf{36} &:= 6^{F(3)} \\
 \mathbf{233} &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & \mathbf{143} &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{630} &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & \mathbf{231} &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 \mathbf{1178} &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & \mathbf{377} &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{2079} &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & \mathbf{986} &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{4864} &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & \mathbf{1165} &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{8759} &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & \mathbf{1596} &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{8849} &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) & \mathbf{2592} &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\
 \mathbf{9349} &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & \mathbf{9756} &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{834660} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834661} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834662} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834663} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834664} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834665} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834666} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834667} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834668} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834669} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{21960} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21961} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21962} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21963} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{21964} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21965} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21966} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21967} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21968} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21969} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

3.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$\mathbf{1069} := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	$\mathbf{874} := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
$\mathbf{1081} := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	$\mathbf{0105} := 50 + T(10)$
$\mathbf{2887} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	$\mathbf{1155} := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
$\mathbf{4965} := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	$\mathbf{1224} := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
$\mathbf{4999} := 49 + T(99)$	$\mathbf{2418} := T(81) - T(42)$
$\mathbf{99545} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	$\mathbf{99632} := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
$\mathbf{99546} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$	$\mathbf{99633} := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2210} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2211} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2212} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2213} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2214} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2215} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2216} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2217} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2218} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2219} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [21, 31].

3.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, m \geq r \geq 0, m, r \in N.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6435} &:= C(C(6, 4), 3+5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4}+6) \\ \mathbf{15504} &:= C(15+5, 0!+4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ \mathbf{42504} &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05+24) \\ \mathbf{54264} &:= C(5+4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4!-6/2, (\sqrt{4}+5)!) \\ \mathbf{74613} &:= C(7 \times 4-6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3!+16, (-4+7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$\mathbf{12650} := C(-1+26, 5-0!)$	$\mathbf{28} := C(8, 2)$
$\mathbf{12870} := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7+0!)$	$\mathbf{792} := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$
$\mathbf{14950} := C(-1+4!+\sqrt{9}, 5-0!)$	$\mathbf{924} := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$
$\mathbf{18564} := C(18, (5-6+4)!)$	$\mathbf{2024} := C(4!, 2+(0 \times 2)!)$
$\mathbf{19448} := C(19-\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4}+8)$	$\mathbf{4845} := C(5 \times 4, 8-4)$
$\mathbf{26334} := C(2+C(6, 3), 3+\sqrt{4})$	$\mathbf{00378} := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0!+0!)$
$\mathbf{43758} := C(4!-3!, 7-5+8)$	$\mathbf{00792} := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7-0!-0!)$
$\mathbf{53130} := C(5^{3-1}, 3!-0!).$	$\mathbf{00924} := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0!+0!)).$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$\mathbf{25920} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0$	$\mathbf{98280} := 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25921} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1$	$\mathbf{98281} := 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25922} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2$	$\mathbf{98282} := 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25923} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3$	$\mathbf{98283} := 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25924} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4$	$\mathbf{98284} := 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25925} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5$	$\mathbf{98285} := 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25926} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6$	$\mathbf{98286} := 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25927} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7$	$\mathbf{98287} := 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25928} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8$	$\mathbf{98288} := 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9})$
$\mathbf{25929} := (-2+5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9.$	$\mathbf{98289} := 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8-\sqrt{9}).$

For more details refer author's work [22].

3.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$4992 := P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2)$	$8967 := 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8)$
$7744 := (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$9504 := 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9)$
$7896 := 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6)$	$9744 := 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9})$
$65485 := -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5$	$49281 := 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!)$
$65943 := P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3)$	$49548 := -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4$
$67977 := (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!)$	$50424 := 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!})$
$72495 := -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5$	$52895 := (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5$
$83544 := \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}$	$53995 := (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$86640 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0$	$5640 := 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86641 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1$	$5641 := 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86642 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2$	$5642 := 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86643 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3$	$5643 := 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86644 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4$	$5644 := 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86645 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5$	$5645 := 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86646 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6$	$5646 := 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86647 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7$	$5647 := 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86648 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8$	$5648 := 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$
$86649 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9.$	$5649 := 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{2883} := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & \mathbf{00938} := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{2888} := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & \mathbf{01051} := K(15, 010) \\
 \mathbf{3640} := K(3!, 6) \times 40 & \mathbf{01199} := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 \mathbf{14939} := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & \mathbf{59938} := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 \mathbf{14959} := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & \mathbf{62424} := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 \mathbf{15144} := K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & \mathbf{63384} := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 \mathbf{15347} := (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & \mathbf{63744} := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 \mathbf{15399} := K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9 & \mathbf{63973} := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).
 \end{array}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{99360} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99361} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99362} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99363} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99364} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99365} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99366} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99367} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99368} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{99369} := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{array}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

48 := $-Q(4) + Q(8)$	49 := $Q(-9 + Q(4))$
81 := $Q(8 + 1)$	89 := $Q(9) + 8$
128 := $1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	224 := $(Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$
292 := $Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	275 := $Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
322 := $Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	736 := $Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$
1036 := $10^3 + Q(6)$	0107 := $7 + Q(010)$
1125 := $Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	0231 := $-Q(13) + Q(20)$
1729 := $1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	1257 := $7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
9843 := $(Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	2239 := $-Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$
10025 := $100^2 + Q(5)$	08136 := $Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$
10384 := $(-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$	99712 := $Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$
99378 := $9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	37293 := $-3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3)$.

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12680} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12681} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12682} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12683} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12684} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12685} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12686} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12687} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12688} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{12689} &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

3.12 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times C(5)$	$512 := C(2 + 1 + 5)$
$522 := 5 \times 2 + C(C(2))$	$991 := (C(1 + 9) - 9)$
$991 := -9 + C(9 + 1)$	$0235 := 5 \times (C(3) + 20)$
$1371 := (1 + 3) \times C(7) - 1$	$0263 := C(3) + C(6) + 20$
$1715 := 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5$	$1735 := 5 \times (3 + C(7) + 1)$
$2587 := -C(2) + 5 \times (C(8) + 7)$	$5974 := -4 + 7 \times (C(9) + C(5))$
$9945 := C(9) + 9 \times 4^5$	$00157 := -C(7) + 5 \times 100$
$10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times C(5)$	$01928 := 8 \times (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(10))$
$16444 := C(16) \times 4 + C(4) - 4$	$45194 := -4 + C(9) \times (1 + C(5) - C(4))$
$30375 := C(30) + C(3 + 7 + 5)$	$99535 := 5 \times (C(C(3)) + C(5) + 99)$
$99873 := C(9) \times (9 + C(8)/(7 - 3))$	

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 22950 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22951 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22952 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22953 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22954 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22955 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22956 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22957 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22958 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22959 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

For more details refer author's work [25].

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